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Authors: Anna Matamala (UAB)

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Abstract:

This document presents and analyses the results of pilot actions in the ImAc project. It considers both pilot actions with professional users, who have assessed the tools, and with home users, who have assessed the interface and different presentation modes.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document provides an evaluation of the results of pilot and pre-pilot actions, differentiating between the actions in which the tools have been tested with professionals and the actions in which the presentation modes and the player have been tested with end users. For all actions, five central elements are presented: measures, participants, materials, experimental protocol, and results. A final discussion is included on the main results, which have an impact on user requirements and technical development in WP2, WP3 and WP4.

Pilot actions have been developed following D5.1. Pilot operation plan and D5.2 Pilot evaluation methodology, under T5.1. Execution and evaluation plan. The evaluation results are related to the actions developed as part of the German pilot (T5.3), the Spanish pilot (T5.4), and the cross-national pilot (T5.5), on content generated under Content Production (T5.2).

The full methodology for each pilot action and the report provided by the partner responsible for the analysis are included as annexes.

CONTRIBUTORS

First Name	Last Name	Company	e-Mail
Anna	Matamala	UAB	Anna.matamala@uab.cat
Àngel	Quero	CCMA	Aquero.f@ccma.cat
Anita	Fidyka	UAB	Anita.Fidyka@uab.cat
Belén	Agulló	UAB	Belen.Agullo@uab.cat
Doreen	Ritter	RBB	Doreen.Ritter@rbb-online.de
Francesc	Mas Peinado	CCMA	Fmas.z@ccma.cat
Kimia	Mirehbar	ANGLA	Kimia@anglatecnic.com
Mario	Montagud	i2Cat	Mario.montagud@i2cat.net
Olga	Soler Vilageliu	UAB	Olga.Soler@uab.cat
Pilar	Orero	UAB	Pilar.orero@uab.cat
Sonali	Rai	RNIB	Sonali.raai@rnib.org.uk

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

Acronym	Description
2D	Two-dimensional
3D	Three-dimensional
ACM	Accessibility Content Manager
AD	Audio description
AD-C	Audio description presentation mode (Classic)
AD-E	Audio description presentation mode (Extended)
AD-R	Audio description presentation mode (Radio)
AST	Audio subtitles, audio subtitling
AST-AD	Audio subtitling with audio description
AVT	Audiovisual Translation
CCMA	Corporació Catalana de Mitjans Audiovisuals
cps	Characters per second
D	Deliverable
E2R	Easy-to-Read
HMD	Head-mounted display
ImAc	Immersive Accessibility
IPQ	Igroup Presence Questionnaire
M	Month
MA	Master of Arts
PhD	Doctor in Philosophy
QoE	Quality of Experience
QoS	Quality of Service
RBB	Rundfunk Berlin-Brandenburg
RNIB	Royal National Institute of Blind People
SDH	Subtitling for the Deaf and hard-of-hearing
SL	Sign Language
ST	Subtitling
SUS	System Usability Scale
T	Task
TC	Time code
UAB	Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona
UI	User interaction
US	United States

USAL	University of Salford
VR	Virtual Reality
wpm	Words per minute
WP	Work Package
P1-P31 AD	Participants in audio description web editor test (UAB)
P1 2019 – P24 2019	Participants in AD editor test in September 2019
US1-US3 AD	Participants in audio description web editor test – US round
wps	Words per second

1. INTRODUCTION

This introduction describes the purpose of this deliverable, its scope, status and relationship with other ImAc activities.

1.1. Purpose of this document

This document presents the evaluation of the pilot and pre-pilot actions developed under WP5. Pilot actions are understood as any tests in which ImAc services and products are demonstrated and feedback from users is gathered.

ImAc is a user-centric project (D2.1) in which input from users (D2.2) is gathered in different iterations and forms. Under WP5, demonstration pilots take place. The results of such pilots have an impact on user requirements, which have an impact on T2.2 and T2.3, and also on the development of the immersive platform under WP4 and on the development of Accessibility Service Tools in WP3, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Diagram of relation between work packages, and its cycles (iterations)

1.2. Scope of this document

This document summarises the development and results of pilot actions under WP5 with two different profiles: on the one hand, professional users creating accessible content with the tools and, on the other hand, end users consuming accessible content on the ImAc player interface.

Chapter 2 presents an overview of the pilot actions (which follows D5.1 Pilot operation plan) and the methodology used, which follows D5.2 (Pilot evaluation methodology and plan). Chapter 3 presents the results of the evaluation performed by professional users on the tools, namely the accessibility content manager (ACM), the subtitling (ST) editing tool, the Sign Language (SL) and the audio description (AD) editing tool. Chapter 4 presents the results of testing the player interface, through actions with home users with hearing loss at CCMA and RBB, and actions with home users with sight loss at RNIB and UAB. Chapter 5 presents the results of testing different subtitling presentation modes, Chapter 6 focuses on the results of the tests on SL presentation modes, Chapter 7 deals with AD modes, and Chapter 8 summarises audio subtitling (AST) tests. For each pilot action, five central elements are presented: measures, participants, materials, experimental protocol, and results. In Chapter 9, the open Spanish and German pilots are reported, and in Chapter 10 final conclusions are included.

1.3. Status of this document

This is the third iteration of D5.4, delivered in Month 30.

The first iteration of the deliverable presented results linked to pilot phase 1 of the German (T5.3.) and the Spanish pilots (T5.4.) as well as results of the first round of professional tests on the Accessibility Content Manager, the subtitling editing tool, and the audio description editing tool. The second version included the evaluations performed with the tools in its second iteration, and added the results of pre-pilot 2 actions for both the German and Spanish pilots as well as pre-pilot actions for the cross-national pilot (T5.5). The current final version reports on all project pilot actions, including results from the cross-national pilot, the SL editor test, easy-to-read subtitle tests, and pilot phase 2 results for German and Spanish pilots.

1.4. Relation with other ImAc activities

D5.4 presents the results of the pilot actions carried out according to the plan developed in D5.1 and the methodology designed in D5.2, using content created under D5.3. This document reports on the evaluation performed under T5.6. Evaluation.

All WP5 tasks and deliverables are tightly linked and were initially designed based on WP2 input. The results of the evaluation feed on T2.2 User requirements, which have also an impact on WP3 and WP4. Similarly, results are disseminated under WP6. Figure 2 provides an overview of the relationship between the different tasks and deliverables.

Figure 2: Diagram of tasks and its outcomes (deliverables). In this case, there are also 2 iterations

2. PILOT OVERVIEW: PILOT ACTIONS AND METHODOLOGY

Pilot actions in WP5 have its origin in WP2. In WP2, multiple possibilities or requirements by users were suggested through focus groups, interviews and pre-pilot 1 actions (D2.2). Users were classified into two main groups: on the one hand, home users, i.e. end users who will be consuming the services; on the other hand, professional users, i.e. users who will be creating the services.

Home users put forward needs and requirements in relation to the services, focusing mainly on two broad categories identified during the analysis: presentation modes and player interface (personalisation and interaction). Professional users also contributed to the previous requirements but focused mainly on the features the access services editing tools should have. Figure 3 summarises the relationship between WP2 and WP5.

Figure 3: WP2-WP5 relationship

Based on WP2 user input, requirements for implementation of user suggestions and criteria for user testing were defined in D5.2. They could be summarised as follows:

- Requirements from users referring to the editing tools should be implemented, if technically feasible, and should be tested.
- Requirements from users referring to the services, both concerning the player interface and the presentation modes, should be implemented if technically and methodologically feasible. When more than one implementation options are suggested by users, testing may be considered.
- Requirements already tested in previous projects should not be tested.

Pilot actions have been organised in different phases, depending on the pilot: Figures 4, 5 and 6 summarise the phases for the Spanish and German pilots, the cross-national pilot, and the professional tools pilot actions, respectively, and indicate in what deliverable the results are discussed. The output of each round of pilot actions has allowed to fine-tune the requirements, improve the services and tools, and provide suggestions for further testing.

Figure 4: Spanish and German pilots: home users

Figure 5: Cross-national pilot: home users

Figure 6: Professional tools

This deliverable reports results under three main categories:

- a) the tools,
- b) the player interface and
- c) the presentation modes for each service.

Results from pilot phase 2 in Spanish and German pilots are reported in an independent section.

2.1. The tools

Concerning professional user and professional tools, pilot actions were planned in two stages: during the tool development (first iteration) and once user requirements were implemented (second iteration) (Figure 6). An additional action to test innovative systems for subtitle angle positioning, not initially planned, was added at the end of the project in the form of two focus groups. Table 1 summarises all the actions that have been performed with professional tools. It also includes information on when these actions took place, who was responsible for the pilot action, and refers to the annexes where the methodology and the partner reports are available. It also indicates the section where the summary of the results is discussed.

What?	Who?	Phase	When?	Resp.	Method	Report	Section
ACM	Professionals	Development (1 st iteration)	July 2018	UAB	Annex 1	Annex 3	D5.4, 3.1
	Professionals	Implementation (2 nd iteration)	July-October 19	CCMA	Annex 2	Annex 4	
	Professionals	Implementation (2 nd iteration)	July- Sept. 19	RBB	Annex 2	Annex 5	
ST editor	Professionals	Development (1 st iteration)	July 2018	UAB	Annex 6	Annex 8	D5.4, 3.2
	Professionals	Implementation (2 nd iteration)	July- Sept. 19	CCMA	Annex 7	Annex 9	
	Professionals	Implementation (2 nd iteration)	July- Sept. 19	RBB	Annex 7	Annex 10	
AD editor	Professionals	Development (1 st iteration)	Sep-Oct 18	UAB	Annex 11	Annex 13	D5.4, 3.3
	Professionals	Implementation (2 nd iteration)	July-Sept 19	UAB	Annex 12	Annex 14	
SL editor	Professionals	Implementation (one iteration)	October 20	RBB	Annex 15	Annex 16	D5.4., 3.4
ST angle setting	Professionals	One iteration	February 20	IRT	Annex 17	Annex 18	D5.4., 3.5
	Professionals	One iteration	February 20	UAB	Annex 17	Annex 19	

Table 1: Summary of pilot actions: professional tools

2.2. The player interface

The player interface was tested at different stages in the project and by different user profiles, as shown in Table 2. Results from pilot phase 2 (German/Spanish pilot) are included in section 2.4.

Who?	Phase	When?	Respons.	Methodology	Report	Section
Home users: persons with hearing loss	Development: pilot phase 1 action	October 2018	CCMA	Annex 20	Annex 21	D5.4, 4.1
Home users: persons with hearing loss	Development: pilot phase 1 action	September-October 2018	RBB	Annex 20	Annex 22	D5.4, 4.2
Home users: persons with hearing loss	Development: pre-pilot 2 action	May-June 2019	CCMA	Annex 23	Annex 24	D5.4, 4.3
Home users: persons with hearing loss	Development: pre-pilot 2 action	May-June 2019	RBB	Annex 23	Annex 25	D5.4, 4.4
Home users: persons with sight loss	Development: pre-pilot action 2	May 2019	RNIB	Annex 26	Annex 27	D5.4, 4.5
Home users: persons with sight loss	Development: pre-pilot action 2	May-June 2019	UAB	Annex 26	Annex 28	D5.4, 4.6
Home users: persons with sight loss	Implementation: cross-national	November 2019-January 2020	RNIB	Annex 29	Annex 30	D5.4, 4.7
Home users: persons with sight loss	Implementation: cross-national	January-February 2020	UAB	Annex 29	Annex 31	D5.4, 4.8

Table 2: Player interface pilot actions

Home users with hearing loss focused on the traditional menu in a Head-Mounted Display and on the traditional menu on a tablet, in different versions. Home users with sight loss focused on the voice interaction menu and on the enhanced accessibility menu (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Player interface features tested in pre-pilot actions

2.3. Presentation modes

As far as presentation modes are concerned, pilot actions were planned for ST presentation modes (Table 3), SL presentation modes (Table 4), and AD and AST presentation modes (Table 5), in different stages and by different partners. Pilot phase 2 actions are reported separately (see 2.4.).

a) ST presentation modes

Who?	Phase	When?	Respons.	Methodology	Report	Section
Home users: persons with hearing loss	Development: pre-pilot 1 action	April 2018	CCMA	Reported in D2.1	D2.1	D2.1, 3.2.4
Home users: persons with hearing loss	Development: pre-pilot 1 action	April 2018	RBB	Reported in D2.1	D2.1	D2.1, 3.2.5
Home users: persons with hearing loss	Development: pilot phase 1	July-Sept. 2018	CCMA	Annex 20	Annex 21	D5.4, 5.1
Home users: persons with hearing loss	Development: pilot phase 1	July-October 2018	RBB	Annex 20	Annex 22	D5.4, 5.2
Home users: persons with hearing loss	Development: pre-pilot 2 action	May-June 2019	CCMA	Annex 23	Annex 24	D5.4, 5.3
Home users: persons with hearing loss	Development: pre-pilot 2 action	May-June 2019	RBB	Annex 23	Annex 25	D5.4, 5.4
Home users: persons with and without hearing loss	Development: intermediate/ pre-pilot 2 actions	November 2018	UAB	Annex 32	Annex 33	D5.4, 5.5
Home users: persons with and without hearing loss	Development: intermediate/ pre-pilot 2 action (E2R)	May-June 2019	UAB	Annex 34	Annex 35	D5.4, 5.6
Home users: persons with and without hearing loss	Development: intermediate/ pre-pilot 2 action (E2R)	October 2019	UAB	Annex 36	Annex 37	D5.4, 5.7

Table 3: ST presentation modes pilot actions

The features considered for each pilot action are summarised in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Subtitling: testing conditions

b) SL presentation modes

Who?	Phase	When?	Responsible	Methodology	Report	Section
Home users: persons with hearing loss	Development: pre-pilot actions 1	April 2018	RBB	Reported in D2.1	D2.1.	D2.1., 3.2.6
Home users: persons with hearing loss	Development: pre-pilot actions 2	May-June 2019	RBB	Annex 38	Annex 39	D5.4, 6.1

Table 4: SL presentation modes pilot actions

The features considered for the SL presentation modes actions are summarized in Figure 9.

Figure 9: SL: testing conditions

c) AD/AST presentation modes

What?	Who?	Phase	When?	Respons	Methodology	Report	Section
AD	Home users: persons with sight loss	Development: pre-pilot actions 1	April 2018	RNIB	Reported in D2.1.	Reported in D2.1.	D2.1, 3.1.5
	Home users: persons with sight loss	Development: pre-pilot actions 1	April 2018	UAB	Reported in D2.1.	Reported in D2.1.	D2.1, 3.12
	Home users: persons with sight loss	Development: pre-pilot actions 2	May 2019	RNIB	Annex 26	Annex 27	D5.4, 7.1
	Home users: persons with sight loss	Development: pre-pilot actions 2	June 2019	UAB	Annex 26	Annex 28	D5.4, 7.2
	Home users: persons with sight loss	Cross-national pilot	Nov 19-Jan 20	RNIB	Annex 29	Annex 30	D5.4., 7.3
	Home users: persons with sight loss	Cross-national pilot	Jan-Feb 20	UAB	Annex 29	Annex 31	D5.4., 7.4
AST	Home users: persons with sight loss	Development: pre-pilot actions 2	May 2019	RNIB	Annex 26	Annex 27	D5.4, 8.1
	Home users: persons with sight loss	Development: pre-pilot actions 2	June 2019	UAB	Annex 26	Annex 28	D5.4, 8.2
	Home users: persons with sight loss	Cross-national pilot	Nov 19-Jan 20	RNIB	Annex 29	Annex 30	D5.4., 8.3
	Home users: persons with sight loss	Cross-national pilot	Jan-Feb 20	UAB	Annex 29	Annex 31	D5.4., 8.4

Table 5: AD/AST presentation modes pilot actions

The features considered for the AD/AST presentation modes actions are summarised in Figure 10.

Figure 10: AD/AST testing conditions

2.4. Pilot phase 2

Pilot phase 2 includes the German pilot and the Spanish pilot. The results of the previous pilot phases and pre-pilots for subtitles and Sign Language are implemented.

a) German pilot

The aim of this open pilot is to test immersive content with subtitles and Sign Language on RBB's website:

- German: <https://rbb-online.de/imac-nutzertest> and <https://rbb-online.de/imac-user-test>
- English <https://rbb-online.de/imac-user-test> and <https://rbb-online.de/imac.user-tests>

Through a website available both in German and English, users are given information about ImAc and about the specific features of the player, and are invited to watch different videos: *360° Abendschau* (subtitles in German and German Sign Language), *I, Philip* (subtitles in German and other languages, German Sign Language), *Täter | Opfer | Polizei* (subtitles in German and English and German Sign Language) and then provide their input through a questionnaire. While navigating, objective data are tracked: information about user profile, about the options and settings used, about the videos played, and quality of service and quality of experience metrics.

b) Spanish pilot

The aim of this open pilot is to test immersive content with subtitles on CCMA's website: <https://www.ccma.cat/experiencia-immersiva-accessible/> Users are given the possibility to watch different video content in three different scenarios: (a) on a companion screen synchronously with a web browser on a PC (Web-based 360° Companion Screen); (b) on a

companion screen synchronously with standard HbbTV content (HbbTV 360° Companion Screen), and (c) with virtual reality glasses or other devices (360° Video Portal).

The videos include the “making of” of the evening news programme (*El Telenotícies per dins*), *Making of FAQs*, *Cuinant en 360°*, *Diada de Sant Jordi*, *Òpera Romeo i Juliette al Liceu*, *Desconcert “Leyre”* and *Desconcert “Havanna”*.

Who?	Phase	When?	Respons.	Methodology	Report	Section
Home users	Implementation: pilot phase 2	February-March 2020	RBB	Annex 40	Annex 41	D5.4, 9.1
Home users	Implementation: pilot phase 2	February -March 2020	CCMA	Annex 40	Annex 42	D5.4, 9.2

Table 6: Spanish and German pilot phase 2

Figure 11: Spanish and German pilots: pilot phase 2

2.5. Methodological overview

As thoroughly explained in D5.2, three key concepts framed the methodological design (Figure 12): usability, preferences, and presence. In pilot phase 2 a new concept has been added: user behaviour metrics related to quality of experience (QoE) and quality of service (QoS).

Figure 12: Key methodological concepts

- **Usability** is understood as the ability of the user to use a thing or carry out a task successfully.
- **Presence**, sometimes also referred to as immersion, refers to the sense of “being there” [1].
- **Preferences** and opinions include general feedback gathered from users.
- **User behaviour metrics** allow to understand how users interact with the ImAc player features.

Depending on the type of test or action, one or more of the previous measures were chosen. For each of these measures, a specific methodological tool was also selected, as shown in Figure 13 [2] [3]. The reasons for selecting these questionnaires are explained in D5.2.

Figure 13: Methodological tools

SUS [4] (Annex 43) includes 10 items, is easy to administer and provides reliable results with small sample sizes. It can be accessed here: <https://www.usability.gov/how-to-and-tools/methods/system-usability-scale.html>. SUS is available in English and also has a validated version in German (<https://experience.sap.com/skillup/system-usability-scale-jetzt-auch-auf-deutsch/>). Catalan and Spanish versions were produced by CCMA and UAB.

IPQ [5] (Annex 44) combines previous questionnaires and it was the first presence questionnaire to specifically differentiate between spatial presence, involvement, and experienced realism. In this questionnaire, spatial presence refers to the sense of being there in the virtual environment. Involvement refers to the attention to the real and the virtual environment, and experienced realism refers to the reality judgment of the virtual environment. The questionnaire has been validated in different virtual environments, including HMD in a laboratory. It can be accessed here: <http://www.igroup.org/pq/ipq/download.php>. IPQ is available in English and German, as well as Dutch and French. Catalan and Spanish versions were produced by CCMA and UAB.

Regarding the post-questionnaire, it was created *ad hoc* for each pilot action, aiming to gather additional user input, especially concerning preferences but also opening the questions to more general feedback.

User tracking metrics were introduced in pilot phase 2 for the Spanish and German pilot, to gather information on user behaviour while interacting with the ImAc player and content. They include various types of Quality of Service and Quality of Experience metrics.

The methodological procedure followed in the actions shared some features (Figure 13), with adaptations when needed depending on the test:

1. The first step was to welcome participants, inform about the project and carry out ethical protocols as approved by UAB's ethical committee. In this regard, all participants gave their informed consent to take part in the action and they were informed their data would be kept confidential.
2. The second step was to gather information from the users through a questionnaire. To this end, three versions of demographic questionnaires were developed:
 - a. Demographic questionnaire for professionals using the editors (Annex 45),
 - b. Shorter demographic questionnaire for ACM users (Annex 1), and
 - c. Demographic questionnaire for home users (Annex 46).

When necessary for a pilot action, the demographic questionnaire was moved later in the process. In open pilot actions, demographic data were kept to a minimum.

3. The third step was to perform one or multiple tasks, followed by the corresponding questionnaires. This central step obviously changed in each pilot action, and will be thoroughly explained in the sections below.
4. The final step in all pilot actions was to thank the participants and offer them the possibility to get more information about the project.

Figure 14 summarises the key steps in pilot actions.

Figure 14: Shared protocol for pilot actions

3. TESTING THE TOOLS

Three tools were tested: the Accessibility Content Manager (section 3.1), the subtitling editing tool (section 3.2), the audio description editing tool (section 3.3), and the Sign Language editor (section 3.4). The subtitling editor procedure to set the angle was also compared on a focus group to an innovative approach with virtual reality glasses (section 3.5). Procedures and results are discussed in this chapter.

For each pilot action, a general description of the pilot action is given, followed by information on measures, participants, materials, experimental protocol, and results.

- The general description reports on the tool used, the general category of users, the partner responsible for the tests, the dates, and format of the pilot actions in which the tool was tested.
- “Measures” are based on the framework described before. If an *ad-hoc* preference questionnaire is used, it is reproduced in this section.
- “Participants” provide a thorough description of the participant profile, summarising the data obtained through the demographic questionnaires in both iterations.
- “Materials” describe the different content and questionnaires used for the tests. It must be stressed out that testing with 360° content is challenging, due to the fact that it is an emergent technology and contents are not widely available. More information on the content developed as part of ImAc is available in D5.3 Pilot Content.
- “Experimental protocol” specifies how the general framework was implemented in each pilot action.
- “Results” provide an evaluation of the pilot actions, with their main outcomes. More specific details, with a thorough reproduction of all replies, are included in the full reports in the annexes.

3.1. Accessibility Content Manager

The main features of the accessibility content manager pilot actions are summarised next:

- **ACM tested:** version 24 in first iteration (development), version 46 in second iteration (implementation). <https://imac.gpac-licensing.com/acm/>
- **Users:** 7 professional users (first iteration) + 27 professional users (second iteration).
- **Partner responsible for tests:** UAB (first iteration, with tests performed by RBB and CCMA). CCMA and RBB (second iteration).
- **Dates:** July 2018 (first iteration: development) and July-October 2019 (second iteration: implementation).
- **Format:** face-to-face (first iteration: development) and online (second iteration: implementation).

The full version of methodology for the ACM pilot action during the first iteration is included in Annex 1. The full version of the methodology for the second iteration of pilot actions is included in Annex 2. Before launching the final professional tests, CCMA and RBB performed an internal test and USAL performed a technical functional test. Only when these tests were successful were the final pilot actions launched.

The full reports with all the results are included in Annex 3 (first iteration, development) and Annex 4 (second iteration, implementation CCMA) and 5 (second iteration, implementation RBB). What follows is a summary of the main elements, reproducing when appropriate excerpts of the full reports.

3.1.1. Measures

The Accessibility Content Manager pilot actions measured usability and preferences. It was decided that immersion was not a relevant measure for this test.

For usability, SUS was used.

For preferences, a specific questionnaire with the following questions was developed:

- What did you like most about the accessibility content manager?
- What did you like less about the accessibility content manager?
- What do you think could be improved, and how?
- What missing functionalities did you find?
- Was it intuitive? If not, please write why.
- Other comments: (open field)

3.1.2. Participants

First iteration

Seven participants took part. There were 2 females (28.5%) and 5 males (71.5%). Three participants were recruited at RBB and 4 participants were recruited at CCMA. Ages ranged 31 to 60, mean age being 40.5. The participants had technological expertise and experience in the field of access services, varying from 3 to 28 years. Their current jobs were defined by themselves in the following terms: 'Project engineer', 'Innovation', 'Engineer', 'TV station', 'Broadcast manager', 'Research manager', 'Accessibility manager'. Participants declared using different content management software in their daily work (Confluence, WordPress, Adobe AEM, WP, WPMS, Fingertext and others).

Second iteration

27 participants took part. Three of them had taken part in the first iteration. There were 11 females (40.74%), 15 males (55.56%) and one person preferred not to reply (3.70%). Fourteen participants were recruited at RBB and thirteen participants were recruited at CCMA. Ages ranged 28 to 58, mean age being 37.6. 24 (88.89%) participants used content management softwares in their work. All participants had experience in the field of access services, varying from 2 to 21 years. Their current jobs were defined by themselves in the following terms: 'Editor', 'Engineer', 'Project Manager', 'System Administrator', 'News director's assistant', 'Documentarist', 'Scrum Master', 'Software Engineer/Developer', 'Head of Software Department', 'Head of Content Management', 'Information Manager', 'Audiovisual Researcher', 'Analyst-Programmer'. Participants declared using different content management software in their daily work (Adobe AEM, WordPress, Blue Orange, tailor made systems, subtitle editor, Delivery, SharePoint, Mam, Drupal, Digition, Jira, Confluence, Agile).

3.1.3. Materials

Participants were given access to the accessibility content manager online, which contained a clip from the CCMA humour programme *Polònia* and a subtitle file. See D5.3 Pilot Contents for further details on the ImAc contents.

Figure 15: ACM (first iteration)

Figure 16: ACM (second iteration)

Participants were also given a document with instructions and a user guide.

Three online questionnaires were prepared for this test: demographic, SUS, and preference. The only difference was that the second iteration asked if they had taken part in the first test.

3.1.4. Experimental protocol

The experimental protocol followed the framework summarised in Figure 14. It was specifically implemented in these pilot actions as follows:

- Participants are welcomed and ImAc project and the specific test is presented (face-to-face in first iteration, online in second iteration).
- Ethical clearance: participants sign informed consent forms.

- Participants are given instructions on how to access and use the accessibility content. In the first iteration, a short presentation plus a short user guide was given to the participants, who performed the test online. In the second iteration, the aim was to involve more users, so an online test was prioritised. An updated user guide was used in this case.
- The tasks to be performed are indicated, as follows.
 - In the first iteration:
 - Create a new asset
 - Upload a video
 - Create a subtitling task
 - Duplicate an asset
 - Create a subtitling task in more than one language
 - Assign the subtitling task to a user
 - Upload an existing subtitle file to the asset
 - Delete an asset
 - Recover an asset from the bin
 - In the second iteration, the tasks were slightly changed to adapt to the new terminology and functionalities used in the enhanced version of the ACM:
 - Access ACM
 - Create a new asset
 - Upload a low-quality video
 - Create a subtitle instance
 - Duplicate an asset
 - Create subtitle instances in more languages
 - Assign the subtitling instance to a subtitler
 - Upload an existing subtitle file to the asset
 - Delete an asset
 - Restor an asset from the bin
 - View reports
- Participants fill in a demographic questionnaire (online form)
- Participants fill in SUS questionnaire (online form)
- Participants fill in preference questionnaire (online form)
- Participants are thanked

3.1.5. Results

Results are reported for the two measures selected for this pilot: usability and preferences, and for the two iterations (development/implementation).

Regarding **usability in the first iteration** version under development, the SUS results are shown in Figure 17. The average score is 54.6 (below average, as the average is 68). The letter grade is D, and the obtained score corresponds to the percentile rank: 17-19%. The red line indicates where the ACM is at the moment the test was performed.

Figure 17: SUS score for Accessibility Content Manager pilot action (first iteration)

Regarding **usability in the second iteration**, the SUS average score is 72.31 (above average, as the average is 68) (Figure 18). The letter grade is C+, and the obtained score corresponds to the percentile range: 60-64 %.

Figure 18: SUS score for Accessibility Content Manager pilot action (second iteration)

Concerning **preferences in the first iteration**, participants positively assessed the look (icons, arrangement, style, not too much unnecessary text, responsiveness) and the possibility to manage all videos from one screen in the ACM. In the **second iteration**, once user requirements were implemented, they valued the clean look and structure of the interface with simple actions and easy upload. The icons were also assessed positively, together with the mouse-over-tooltips, as well as the drag-and-drop approach and the asset list. Participants also commented positively on the fact that a user can quickly see all parts of the asset (video, Sign Language, audio description, subtitles) on asset information.

The **aspects assessed less positively in the first iteration** were: virtual folder structure (paths for assets), the functionality of adding videos, user interface interaction, bugs in certain icons, video treatment (which was deemed too slow), managing actions with mouse, and other inconsistencies and functionalities that needed to be completed. Among the items participants liked less were some aspects to be improved such as:

- subtitling handling, as it is not clear how many subtitles are pre-defined in the asset;
- video upload: two progress bars show the same state and multiple upload of videos in assets; tooltips, which would benefit from a cleaner integration;
- assets webpage, which allows for different presentations (as box or as lines) but only returns to the “box” presentation after each action;
- html screen refresh code, and visibility of the icons (which could be increased) and use of colours (which could be improved to distinguish different matters).

In the **second iteration**, when previous user requirements had been implemented, participants put forward further improvements related to the use of colours, file browser, the navigation in the 360° player, as well as the screen layout and the distribution of icons and work areas. Minor problems can be linked to functional failures of the system.

When asked about **missing functionalities in the first iteration**, two participants replied that there were none and one considered that it was still a “very first version”. The other four participants provided some suggestions, such as: edit the subtitles in a WYSIWYG editor, provide an indicator for open tasks, give the possibility to add more than one subtitler at the same time for a subtitling job, set thumbnail for the video, and improve the seek video timeline. In the **second iteration**, two users suggested an undo-button, and two participants suggested search filters.

Most participants deemed the Accessibility Content Manager **intuitive in both iterations**: 71.43% in the first one and 74.1% in the second one. Those who replied negatively to the previous question explained it in the following terms: “too many options to do the same work”, “could be improved”. In the second iteration, they mainly point out that it was necessary for them to check the manual to proceed with the tasks, meaning there is a learning period, and one participant would prefer a different placement of buttons for the tool to be even more intuitive.

In the **open comments** field, in the **first iteration**, three participants provided general remarks indicating that the software was still under development and had to be improved, but one felt confident that “the usability could be fine once these improvements are resolved”. Specific additional suggestions were made, namely:

- there were issues showing the password when clicking on the eye icon during login;
- the upload time of the video was not considered right;
- the icon for assigning the subtitlers was not clear or in the wrong position;
- the download icon while uploading a file was considered confusing, and some additional comments related to features such as preview or “Programme ID” were also made.

In the **second iteration**, participants provided some additional specific feedback, but overall the most praised aspect in the test was that the editor was “easy to understand” and “easy to use”.

3.2. Subtitling editing tool

The subtitling editing tool was tested in two iterations. The main features of the actions are summarised next:

- **Subtitling editing tool tested:** version 23 in first iteration (development) and version 46 (implementation)
- **Users:** 27 professional users + 16 professional users
- **Partner responsible for tests:** UAB (development, first iteration), RBB/CCMA (implementation, second iteration)
- **Dates:** from 17/07/2018 to 31/07/2018 (development), July-August 2019 (implementation)
- **Format:** online

The full methodology for the subtitling tool pilot actions is included in Annex 6 (first iteration: development) and Annex 7 (second iteration: implementation). Before launching the final professional tests, CCMA and RBB performed an internal test and USAL performed a technical functional test. Full reports with all the results for the subtitling editing tool pilot actions are included in Annex 8 (development UAB) and Annex 9 (implementation CCMA) and Annex 10 (implementation RBB). What follows is a summary of the main elements, reproducing when appropriate excerpts of the reports in the annexes.

3.2.1. Measures

The ST editing tool test focused on two measures: usability and preferences. For usability, SUS was used. For preferences, a specific questionnaire with the following questions was developed:

- What did you like most about the subtitle editor?
- What did you like less about the subtitle editor?
- What do you think could be improved, and how?
- Did you miss any functionality? If yes, can you tell us which?
- Do you find the feature for setting the angle for the subtitle easy to use? Explain why.
- Were the preview modes useful for you? Explain why.
- Do you think it will take you longer to subtitle videos in 360°? Why?
- Do you think 360° videos will impact your work as a subtitler?
- Other comments:

3.2.2. Participants

First iteration

Twenty-seven participants took part in the test (20 females=74%, and 7 males=26%), ages ranging 24 to 48. Their main languages were Catalan, Spanish, Croatian, English, Basque, Polish and Romanian, and they usually subtitled in these languages. Their jobs were mainly AVT translators, subtitlers for different kind of products, university lecturers and researchers. Only one participant (3.7%) had subtitled a 360° video before. They presented a varying experience

in the field of subtitling (varying from 1 month to 20 years). 16 participants (59.3%) had produced more than 300 hours of subtitled content, 3 (11.1%) between 151 and 300 hours, 4 (14.8%) between 51 and 150 hours, and 4 (14.8%) less than 50 hours. Participants declared using different subtitling software (FAB, WinCAPS, Aegisub, VisualSubSync, Subtitle Workshop, EZTitles, Swift, Subtitle Edit, TED, Amara, YouTube, Spot, VICOM, Jayex, proprietary software from clients, among others).

Most participants (26= 96.3%) had university studies: some participants had a degree or MA degree on translation and interpreting studies (or languages degrees), some of them specialising in Audiovisual Translation and some of them had PhD studies. Only 1 participant reported further education training. 24 participants (88.9%) received specialized training on subtitling in MAs, specialized courses or training.

When asked about which devices they used on a daily basis, all participants agreed on using mobile phones; 23 participants (85.2%) used laptops; 21 (77.7%) used TV, 17 (62.9%) used PCs, and 9 (33.3%) used tablets.

When asked about how often they watch virtual reality content, none of the participants had watched virtual reality content on a tablet, 23 participants (85.2%) had never watched virtual reality content in a smartphone plugged to HMD or in HMD; some (14, 5.8%) occasionally watched virtual reality content in a smartphone, 12 (44.4%) on a PC, 4 (44.4%) on a smartphone plugged to HMD and 3 (11.1%) in HMD; 1 participant (3.7%) watched virtual reality content on a PC at least once a month, and 1 participant (3.7%) in an HMD; finally, 1 participant (3.7%) watched VR content in smartphone at least once a week.

When asked to explain why they had never used virtual reality content such as 360° videos or only occasionally, 3 participants (11.1%) replied that they were not interested, 4 participants (14.8%) replied that it was not accessible, 16 participants (59.3%) replied that they had not had the chance to use it, and others (18.5%) gave other reasons such as: expensive price, difficulties to use the technology or lack of appealing contents.

When asked to state their level of agreement with the statement “I am interested in virtual reality content (such as 360° videos)”, 3 participants (11.1%) replied that they strongly agreed, 13 (48.2%) replied that they agreed, 7 (25.9%) that they neither agreed nor disagreed and 4 (14.8%) disagreed.

Finally, when asked if they owned any device to access virtual reality content, 15 participants (55.6%) replied that they didn't, 5 replied (18.5%) that they didn't know or prefer not to reply and 7 (25.9%) replied that they did, and later specified the following devices: BOBVR Z4, HTC Vive, PC, laptop, smartphone and PlayStation VR.

Second iteration

Sixteen participants (CCMA and RBB) took part in the test (10 females=62.5%, and 6 males= 37.5%), ages ranging 23 to 51 (mean=37.87). Their main languages were German, Russian, Slovak, Spanish, Catalan, and Basque. Their current jobs, described with their own words, were: 'Subtitling for the hard of hearing', 'Subtitling editor-in-chief', 'audiovisual translator', 'university lecturer', 'subtitler'. Only one participant (6.25%) had subtitled a 360° video before. They presented a varying experience in the field of subtitling (varying from 1 year to 29 years). 8 (50%) had produced more than 300 hours of subtitled content, 6 (37.5%) between 51 and 150 hours, and 2 (12.5%) less than 50 hours. Participants declared using different subtitling software (Aegishub, Bellenuit, FAB, EZTitles, Subtitle Edit, Sublime, Wincaps/Screen, Swift, Spot, various Freeware, Diferits, Multisub, Subtitle Workshop, Amara, the one of my company). Participants usually subtitled content into the following languages: English, Russian, German, Slovak, Spanish, Catalan, French, Basque, and Latin American Spanish.

All participants had university studies: some participants had a BA or MA degree on translation and interpreting studies (or languages degrees), some of them specializing in Audiovisual Translation and some of them have PhD studies, one participant had a degree on Economics and one had one BS and one MS. Twelve participants (75%) had received specialised training on subtitling in MAs, specialised courses or training.

When asked about which devices they used on a daily basis, 9 participants (56.25%) used TV, 11 participants (68.75%) used PC; 12 participants (75%) used laptop, 14 participants (87.5%) used mobile phone, 5 participants (31.25%) used tablets, and 4 participants (25%) used HMD.

When asked about how often they watched virtual reality content, most participants had never watched virtual reality content in any device. 6 participants (37.5%) watched it occasionally in a smartphone; 4 participants (25%) watched it occasionally on a tablet; 9 participants (56.25%) watched it occasionally on a PC; two participants (12.5%) watched it occasionally in a smartphone plugged to the HMD; and two participants (12.5%) watched it occasionally in an HMD. One participant (6.25%) watched VR content at least once a month in a smartphone; one participant (6.25%) at least once a week in an HMD; one participant (6.25%) watched VR content every day in a smartphone; and one participant (6.25%) watched VR content every day on a PC.

When asked to explain why they had never used virtual reality content such as 360° videos or only occasionally, 5 participants (31.25%) replied that they were not interested, 1 participant (6.25%) replied that it was not accessible, and 8 participants (50%) replied that they had not had the chance to use it.

When asked to state their level of agreement with the statement “I am interested in virtual reality content (such as 360° videos)”, 7 participants (43.75%) replied that they strongly agreed, 6 (37.5%) replied that they agreed, 3 (18.75%) that they neither agreed nor disagreed and 4 (25%) disagreed.

Finally, when asked if they own any device to access virtual reality content, 9 participants (56.25%) replied that they didn't, 4 replied (35%) that they didn't know or prefer not to reply and 3 (18.75%) replied that they did, and later specified the following devices: Samsung Gear VR, Lenovo Explorer Mixed Reality Headset, VR-Brille von Renkforce, We have a HMD to watch with a smartphone, but I haven't used it yet.

3.2.1. Materials

Participants were given access to the ST editing tool, which contained one clip to be audio described. In the first iteration, the clip chosen was *Life on Mars: At Home in The Habitat* (minutes 00:00 to 01:11). This video is part of The New York Times series *The Daily 360*. The full video is available here: <https://www.nytimes.com/video/science/100000005108770/life-on-mars-at-home-in-the-habitat.html>. In the second iteration, the clip was changed to avoid a learning effect in case some participants took part in the test again. In this case, the clip chosen was an excerpt from *I, Philip* (minutes 02:05 to 02:38). A short clip was prioritised to make sure the test would last less than 30 minutes.

Participants were also given a document with instructions and a user guide on how to use the editor. In the second iteration, the user guide was improved with all the new functionalities.

Figure 19: ST Editor (first iteration)

Figure 20: ST Editor (second iteration)

Three online questionnaires were prepared for this test: demographic, SUS, and preference.

3.2.2. Experimental protocol

The experimental protocol followed the framework established for all pilot actions and it was previously tested before using it for the tests.

- Participants are welcomed and ImAc project and test is presented (by email)
- Ethical clearance: participants sign informed consent forms (online form)
- Participants fill in a demographic questionnaire (online form). The only difference in the second iteration is that they are asked if they took part in the first one
- Participants are given instructions on how to access and use the subtitling web editor (instructions online)
- Participants are instructed about the tasks to be performed

- In the first iteration the tasks were the following:
 - Open the video that has been assigned to the user
 - Subtitle the video excerpt into your native language:
 - Add subtitles with the correct timecodes
 - Assign different colours to different characters in the video
 - Set angle for each subtitle
 - Set a second region for the subtitles and apply it to one subtitle
 - Change the alignment to the left for one subtitle
 - Insert a subtitle between two existing subtitles
 - Delete two subtitles
 - Look for a subtitle by content
 - Preview the video with forced mode
 - Save the subtitles and go back to the main window
 - Open the video again
 - Preview the video with free mode
 - Save the subtitles and go back to the main video
- In the second iteration, the tasks' terminology was adapted to the new functionalities, as follows:
 - Go to the ACM editor interface
 - Click the edit button on the subtitle task that has been assigned to you to open the web subtitle editor with the video
 - Subtitle the video into your native language:
 - Add subtitles with the correct timecodes
 - Set the character (colours) for the speaker in each subtitle
 - Set the speaker's location angle in each subtitle. If the speaker does not appear on the scene, select the "voice over" option
 - Save the speaker's location angle and set it in another subtitle
 - Change the settings of a second region and set this region to one subtitle
 - Set the alignment of the subtitle to the left for one subtitle
 - Insert a subtitle between two existing subtitles
 - Delete two subtitles
 - Find a subtitle by text
 - Preview the video with the "forced preview" mode. In case of showing errors, correct them
 - Save the subtitles and close the web subtitle editor window
 - Click the edit button on the subtitle task to open the web subtitle editor again
 - Preview the video with "free preview" mode
 - Save the subtitles and close the web subtitle editor window
- Participants fill in SUS questionnaire (online form)
- Participants fill in preference questionnaire (online form)
- Participants are thanked (face-to-face)

3.2.3. Results

Results were obtained for usability and preferences, for both iterations.

Regarding **usability during the first iteration**, the SUS average score is 59.5 (below average, 68 or more is considered above average). Figure 21 provides a graphical representation and the red line specifies where the ImAc subtitle editor is when tested. The letter grade is D+, and the score corresponds to the percentile rank 29-30%.

Figure 21: SUS score for subtitling editor (first iteration)

Regarding **usability during the second iteration**, the SUS score is 65, with letter grade C, and percentile rank 41-59%.

Figure 22: SUS score for subtitling editor (second iteration)

As far as **preferences** are concerned, the replies for this questionnaire were very different and specific among participants, so it is recommended to carefully look at them one by one on the annexes. However, for the sake of clarity, the most relevant ideas are summarised next.

What participants liked most in the first iteration was that the tool was cloud based/online (2 replies), and it was easy (9 replies) and intuitive (2 replies). They also highlighted as preferred elements the “set the angle” option (4 replies), the interface (4 replies), the reading speed thermometer (2 replies), and the navigation and subtitling of 360° videos (5 replies).

In the **second iteration**, participants highlighted again the “set the angle” option and the user interface: the fact that it is a 360 editor that allows placing subtitles in certain angles according to the speaker’s location was very welcome. Overall, it was considered “easy to use” (4

replies), with a good overview of all features and a clear interface (6 replies). Some subtitlers especially valued the customisation options, such as the shortcuts (1 reply) – a requirement from the first iteration – and the easy access to time codes (1 reply). The fact that all buttons had a text indicating their function was also mentioned as a positive aspect of the editor (2 replies).

What participants liked least during the first iteration was the configuration for the default shortcuts (3 replies): although participants were aware that shortcuts are customisable, they considered them uncomfortable and requested a more comfortable default setting. One participant did not like the buttons “fast backward” and “step backward” since they did not work properly. A functional frame-by-frame button to navigate the video was considered needed. One participant did not like the speed thermometer. They thought that it is important to get the characters per line limit and also that the thermometer should work with the parameter of characters per second (cps) rather than (or apart from) words per second (wps). Two participants did not like they had to change modes in order to edit the subtitles, they would rather prefer to have the editing and preview modes integrated. Two users reported that the video went black several times and that they needed to load the video again to fix this issue. Two participants remarked that they don’t like to have not enough freedom to break subtitle lines as they wish. Also, they reported that going to the next subtitle should be an automatic action.

In the second iteration, problems were fewer and mainly concerned with time code (TC) synchronisation issues, audio monitoring, UI design, error indications, and some missing functionalities. Two users were also concerned about the size of the screen and icons, and another reported that integrating the dialogues of two characters in one subtitle was not possible. Other comments were related to the fact that professional subtitlers have different expectations depending on the editing tool they usually work with, and this has an impact on their analysis. They would need to “get used to it”, as one participant indicates.

When asked about what could be improved and about missing functionalities (first iteration), three participants referred to the shortcuts, as explained above. Also, one participant would like to listen to the audio when moving frames forward or backward. As explained before, subtitlers would like to be able to preview the video in the edit mode or edit the video in the preview mode, either way, but both functionalities should be integrated to facilitate spotting. Two participants discussed the possibility of improving the arrow in the preview/edit mode, as they considered it should be more visible. Also, one user complained about the fact that the auto-save option was deactivated each time they pressed F5 to load the video or went back to the main menu. They considered the software should remember this setting. Also, participants complained that subtitles in the subtitle list were not shown with the actual segmentation. Four participants would like to have the subtitles in the subtitle list properly segmented. Two participants replied that the pop-up information from the control buttons covered the time codes and that was distracting. One participant suggested including general actions (and its corresponding shortcuts) such as copy, paste, cut, etc. Seven participants requested to have a sound wave to improve accuracy when spotting. Also, a participant requested an automatic separation by 3-4 frames between subtitles. Two participants asked about the possibility to include a spell-checker or quality assessment functionalities. Also, three participants thought that segmentation should be customisable and more flexible (not automatically done by the editor based on the thermometer parameters).

In the **second iteration**, most of the previous aspects did not come up as they had been implemented, but some improvements and missing functionalities were still suggested: the possibility to scroll subtitles using the mouse’s wheel, a maximum/minimum duration function, better timecode relevant interconnectivity, bigger waveform, missing hotkeys, jump to a

subtitle shortcut, line length indication, back arrow, “ignore the problem” option, and a timeline view. How to include the dialogue of two speakers in the same subtitle, both in terms of colours and angle setting, was an aspect put forward that merits further discussion. One user also considered that the interface is quite complex for someone not familiar with it, probably due to the many functions available.

Regarding the “set the angle” option, in the first iteration, most users (23) thought it was easy to use (also sometimes it did not work properly), and some users found it difficult. Two participants highlighted that the arrow could be improved and be more visible. One participant also raised their concerns regarding the level of precision and accuracy of this functionality. A participant suggested that it would be good to have an option to apply the same angle to consecutive subtitles. Also, one participant wondered what to do when the speaker is off-screen. An angle option for off-screen voices needs to be implemented. Finally, a participant suggested that she/he would prefer to move in 5-10° increments rather than in just 1°. One participant found the arrow a bit confusing around the 180° (135-225) and the 360° (315-45). **In the second iteration**, setting the angle was also an unknown and innovative task, but navigating in the sphere and setting the actual angle was considered by ten users easy, although a few participants felt they would need more knowledge about immersive content in 360 and had minor doubts as to where to position the marker.

As far as the **preview modes** are concerned, as explained before, four participants in the **first iteration** thought these modes were useful, but they would like to be able to edit subtitles in the preview mode or be able to preview subtitles in the edit mode. These functions should be integrated for an optimal spotting process. In the **second iteration**, preview was considered “definitely useful” although some users struggled to see the difference between both modes. The preview possibility also got generally positive feedback, despite a few users’ difficulties. It was mostly seen as being useful and helping to check subtitle placement in time and sphere. The forced preview was considered a good tool to check the angle positioning.

When participants were asked about the impact of subtitling 360° videos on the job of a subtitler, different opinions were presented. In the **first iteration**, some (7) were not sure about it, others (16) thought subtitling will take longer since they have to set the angle for the subtitle, and others (4) thought that it should not take longer or have any impact if you have the right tools and software to edit. In general, subtitlers are a bit worried about the time-consuming tasks that this type of subtitling can bring. Also, one participant thought that subtitling is not the right way to localise 360° videos, although they probably were thinking about interlingual subtitling. Subtitling for the deaf and hard of hearing will always be necessary to access audiovisual content. **In the second iteration**, users also pointed out that subtitling 360 content will take a bit longer than 2D video, especially navigation in the sphere and setting the angles. However, as one user indicated, “it is a question of practice”. One user indicated that she/he is already starting to get such projects, others were a bit more sceptical about the technology, and one stated that “it’s an exciting and interesting option for the future”, a view supported by another user who found it “interesting and fun”. Generally speaking, there was a feeling that “this type of material will present great opportunities in the industry”.

In the final **open section (first iteration)** of the questionnaire, an issue was raised by one participant, who spotted that certain shortcuts correspond to characters in other alphabets (for instance, the Polish letter *ą*). In the **second iteration**, apart from minor issues, some users expressed an interest in knowing more about the editor and the technology: “I would be happy to receive any updates about this new editor”, “I would like to find out more about the use of this method and its application” and “I would love to continue helping improve the software” were some of the comments made. One of the remarks also put forward a methodological set

back ImAc is well aware of: the length of the test does not allow users to get used to the tool, hence it is difficult to do a thorough evaluation. However, as shown in the previous paragraphs, the wealth of information provided by participants is an excellent feedback that can have a positive impact not only in future developments of the tool but also on future projects in which 360 subtitling editors are designed.

3.3. Audio description editing tool

This section reports on measures, participant profile, materials, experimental protocol of the AD editing tool pilot actions, and discusses its results.

- **AD editing tool tested:** version 26 in first iteration (first iteration: development) and version 46 (second iteration: implementation)
- **Users:** 24 professional users (first iteration: development) + 24 professional users (second iteration: implementation)
- **Partner responsible for tests:** UAB
- **Dates:** from 22/09/2018 to 14/10/2018 (1st iteration: development), 22/07-08/09/2019 (2nd iteration: implementation). During development, two rounds of testing were performed, the first between 24.09-12.10.2018, aiming at different countries, and the second between 3.10-19.10, aiming at US respondents thanks to a cooperation with US company RYOT. RYOT, part of the Oath brand, is a global creative studio specialising in immersive content with presence in fourteen countries across five continents. Taking into account the number of completed tests in the second set, results of both rounds are presented together, using the code US for the second set.
- **Format:** online

The full methodology for the AD editor pilot action is included in Annex 11 (first iteration) and Annex 12 (second iteration). Before launching the final professional tests, CCMA performed an internal test and USAL performed a technical functional test. The full report with all the results for the AD editor pilot action is included in Annex 13 (first iteration) and Annex 14 (second iteration). What follows is a summary of the main elements, reproducing when appropriate excerpts of the full reports in the annex.

3.3.1. Measures

The audio description editing tool report focused on two measures: usability and preferences. For usability, SUS was used. For preferences, a specific questionnaire with the following questions was developed:

- What did you like most about the AD editor?
- What did you like less about the AD editor?
- What do you think could be improved, and how?
- Did you miss any functionality? If yes, can you tell us which?
- Do you find the feature for setting the angle for the AD easy to use? Explain why.
- Were the preview modes useful for you? Explain why.
- Do you think it will take you longer to audio describe videos in 360°? Why?
- Do you think 360° videos will impact your work as an audio describer?
- Other comments:

3.3.2. Participants

First iteration

31 participants initially took part in the first round of tests and responded to the pre-questionnaire with demographic information. 21 out of 31 completed the whole test, which means that 10 participants dropped the test. The reasons expressed were technological (9.67%), personal (9.67%) and unknown (12.9%). The profile of the 21 participants who completed the test is described next. In the US round, 3 participants completed the test. This makes a total of 24 completed tests for this tool.

There were 15 females (62.5%) and 8 males (33.3%), and one user who preferred not to reply to this question (4.17%), with ages ranging 25-64. Their main languages were Catalan, Spanish, Bosnian, English, Dutch, Polish, German and Swedish, and they usually audio described in the same languages plus Croatian. Their jobs were mainly AVT translators, freelance audio describers, PhD researchers, academic lecturers, media accessibility/audio description supervisors, and project managers. Only four participants (16.67%) had audio described a 360° video before. They presented a varying experience in the field of AD (from less than 1 year to around 30 years). 9 participants (37.5%) had produced more than 300 hours of AD content, 4 (16.67%) had produced between 151 and 300 hours, 4 participants (16.67%) had produced between 51 and 150 hours and 7 participants (29.17%) had produced less than 50 hours. Participants declared using different AD and subtitling software as well as video players for producing AD (Fingertext, Aegisub, FAB, Best player, Subtitle Workshop, Audition, WinCaps, Annotation Edit, ProTools, Earcatch, Google docs, F4, Swift ADePT, Starfish, Pro Tools, 3Play Media, CADET, QuickTime), but some of them used word processing tools for writing the script. Most participants (21= 87.5%) had studies at university level, often specialising in translation or languages, but also with other specialisations in journalism or audiovisual communication. Most participants had received specific training on AD: in workshops, through company or association training, with specific courses on AD, modules in university courses, MA studies, seminars and conferences. Participants used many devices on a daily basis (95.83% (23) mobile phone, 58.33% (14) PC, 87.5% (21) laptop, 62.5% (15) TV, 33.33% (8) tablet, 4.17% (1) other, but only one 4.17% reported using an HMD.

When asked about how often they watch virtual reality content, 21 (87.5%) had never watched virtual reality content in a smartphone plugged to an HMD; 2 (8.33%) occasionally watched virtual reality content in a smartphone plugged to HMD, and 1 (4.17%) watched virtual reality content in such a way at least once a month. 21 (87.5%) participants had never watched virtual reality content in HMD, 3 (12.5%) used HMD occasionally and 1 (4.17%) used HMD at least once a week. 11 participants consumed VR content in smartphone occasionally (11= 45.83%) or at least once a month (1= 4.17%). 7 (29.17%) used occasionally tablets to consume VR content and, regarding PC, 13 (54.17%) used this device occasionally and 1 (4.17%) at least once a month to access such content.

When asked to explain why they have never (or only occasionally) used virtual reality content such as 360° videos, 6 participants (25%) replied that they were not interested, 3 replied (12.5%) that they were not accessible, 12 (50%) replied that they had not had the change to use it, and 3 (12.5%) chose the option “other reasons”. One of them explained in an additional comment that s/he didn’t normally access these contents because she/he thought they were just a few, but reported being surprised when accessing the project.

When asked to state their level of agreement with the statement “I am interested in virtual reality content (such as 360° videos)”, 4 participants (16.67%) strongly agreed, 8 (33.33%) agreed, 9 (37.5%) neither agreed nor disagreed, 1 (4.17%) disagreed and 2 (8.33%) strongly disagreed. Finally, when asked if they own any device to access virtual reality content, 11

(45.83%) replied that they didn't, 5 replied (20.83%) that they didn't know or prefer not to reply, and 8 (33.33%) replied that they did (including smartphone, Google cardboard, Laptop, Tablet, Virtual reality glasses and virtual reality headset, PC, Oculus Go, VR SHINECON Virtual Reality Glasses and TV).

Second iteration

The same number of completed tests were gathered, that is, 24 participants completed the test (18 female – 75%, 5 male – 20.83%, 1 participant preferred not to reply to this question – 4.17%), with ages ranging 24 to 61. 7 participants (29.2%) had already taken part in the first iteration.

The main languages of the participants were Spanish (8), English (3), German (3) and Catalan (3). Their professions were mostly: researcher/professor, audio describer, PhD candidate, translator, project manager and accessibility consultant. Only 2 participants (8.33%) taking part in the study had audio described a 360° video before. When asked how long they had worked in the field of AD, participants provided varying replies: from 1 year to 19 years. More than half of participants had produced less than 50 hours of AD in their professional life (13=54.17%) and 5 participants (20.83%), more than 300 hours. Participants provided AD in the following languages: Catalan and Spanish (6), English (4), Spanish (4), German (3), Russian (2), Slovak (2), Dutch (2) and Cantonese (1). 14 participants (58.33%) reported using software when producing AD, whereas 10 participants used text editors when producing AD (41.67%). 7 participants (29.17%) recorded their ADs and 13 participants (54.17%) did not record the AD themselves (4 participants – 16.67% asked other professionals to record their ADs). 22 participants (91.67%) had university level education (mostly in Translation Studies) and 2 participants (8.33%) reported having further education. 22 participants (91.67%) received a specific training on AD.

The responses of participants confirmed their technological potential: 13 participants (54.17%) used TV, 17 participants (70.83%) PC, 21 participants (87.5%) laptop, 22 participants (91.67%) mobile phone, 10 participants (41.67%) tablet. None of participants used a head-mounted display on a daily basis. When asked about how often they watched virtual reality content, most of participants (22=91.67%) reported never watching VR content in a smartphone plugged to HMD or in HMD. 9 participants (37.5%) consumed VR content in smartphone at least once a month or occasionally. 4 participants (16.67%) consumed VR content occasionally on a tablet and 7 on PC (29.17%). When asked for reasons behind not using VR content or using it only occasionally, most of the participants (18=75%) replied that they had not had the chance to use it, 5 participants (20.83%) pointed to the lack of interest in such content and 1 participant (4.17%) pointed to lack of accessibility of such content. When asked to state their level of agreement with the statement “I am interested in virtual reality content (such as 360° videos)”, 2 participants (8.33%) strongly agreed, 10 participants agreed (41.67%), 9 participants neither agreed or disagreed (37.5%) and 3 participants disagreed (12.5%). Finally, when asked if they own any device to access VR content, only 2 participants (8.33%) provided an affirmative answer to this question, further specifying that they used Buro VR glasses and mobile phones/iPads.

3.3.3. Materials

Participants were given access to the corresponding version editor, which contained one clip to be audio described. The clip chosen was an excerpt of [private_content]¹. Different excerpts were chosen during the two iterations to avoid a learning effect. During the first iteration, the participants worked on the initial clip of [private_content] (00:00-01:10). In the second

¹ The name of the video used has been substituted in all public documents delivered by ImAc due to copyright issues.

iteration, participants were requested to produce AD to a 50-second excerpt (3:30-4:20) of the same video.

To select the clip, two main features were considered: the length was adequate for the test, and it included actions in different angles, posing a challenge to the audio describer.

Participants were also given a document with instructions and a user guide on how to use the editor. The user guide was improved with the new functionalities in the second iteration.

Three online questionnaires were prepared for this test: demographic, SUS and preference.

Figures 23 and 24 show the AD editor in both iterations. The window for content is black as we used private content.

Figure 23: AD editor (first iteration)

Figure 24: AD editor (second iteration)

3.3.4. Experimental protocol

The experimental protocol followed the general framework established for all pilot actions. It was first tested and then applied as follows:

- Participants are welcomed and ImAc project and test is presented (by email).
- Ethical clearance: participants sign informed consent forms (online form).
- Participants fill in a demographic questionnaire (online form).
- Participants are given instructions on how to access and use the web editor (instructions online).
- Participants are instructed about the tasks to be performed. They are requested to record the ADs.
 - In the first iteration, the tasks were the following:
 - Open the video that has been assigned to the user.
 - Audio describe video excerpt in native language, namely:
 - Add AD instances with the correct timecodes.
 - Set the angle for each AD instance.
 - Record the AD segments produced.
 - Insert one AD segment between two existing ones.
 - Delete two AD segments.
 - Preview the video with “forced preview” mode.
 - Preview the video with “free preview” mode.
 - Save the AD and go back to the main window.
 - In the second iteration, the tasks were replicated except for when a task was considered redundant or new functionalities were present. The terminology was also adapted:
 - Go to the ACM editor interface.
 - Click the edit button on the AD task that has been assigned to you to open the web AD editor with the video.
 - Audio describe video excerpt in native language, namely:
 - Add AD segments with the script and correct time codes.
 - Set the location angle for each AD segment.
 - Record the AD segments.
 - Preview the video with “forced preview” mode.
 - Preview the video with “free preview mode”
 - Save the AD and close the editor.
- Participants fill in SUS questionnaire (online form).
- Participants fill in preference questionnaire (online form).
- Participants are thanked.

3.3.5. Results

Results are presented for the two measures under analysis: usability and preferences, differentiating between the two iterations (development and implementation).

Regarding **usability during the first iteration**, the SUS average score is **55.9** (below average, 68 or more is considered above average). The letter grade is D, and the obtained score corresponds to the percentile rank: 15-34% (see Figure 25).

Figure 25: SUS score for AD editor (first iteration)

Regarding **usability in the second iteration**, the SUS score is **60.52**, corresponding to a letter grade D and the percentile rank 15-34% (Figure 26).

Figure 26: SUS score for AD editor (second iteration)

Regarding preferences in the first iteration, the whole list of replies is included in the full report in Annex 13, but results are summarised next. Annex 13 also includes an additional report one respondent provided after the usability test. Regarding preferences in the second iteration, the full report is found in Annex 14.

What participants appreciated the most in the first iteration was that the whole process of producing AD, including recording, takes place in a single piece of software. Many comments referred to interface, which was described by participants as “very clear”, “simple”, “easy to use” and “easy to understand”. One of the comments pointed to the fact that all the most important functions are displayed on one page, which facilitates the production of AD: “It is

quite easy, it has shortcuts and everything is visible and easily accessible on one page (segments, controls)". It was also appreciated that the software is available online. Also setting of the angle was assessed positively.

In the second iteration, participants appreciated the following features of the editor: visual design and the layout of the user interface, the fact that the buttons for each function are well-placed and easy to identify, being able to complete the whole process of producing AD in one single piece of software, being able to customise the shortcuts, the 'setting angle' option, sound wave, speed thermometer, the blue/yellow colours which help to see how the recorded AD fit in the video. Some participants accessed the usability of the editor positively in their comments: "The program was really easy to use", "It's complete and accurate, and it allows writing and voice recording in an efficient way", "It is easy to use and very practical if you want to complete the whole process of writing the script and recording it", "It is easy to use", and "I think it's quite intuitive to use which I liked very much".

Many of the responses in the second question asking participants about the **elements they liked the least, in the first iteration**, pointed to the problems in the recording and preview modules: they were not working properly in the first action. Also, some participants reported that the video froze. Some of the improvements suggested in the first action related to recording controls, preview function, and shortcuts: most participants would prefer a different, more intuitive configuration, or they would like to customise the shortcuts themselves. Regarding the recording, one response suggested that a line changing the colour would be helpful to know when to start recording. One comment also suggested that it would be helpful to preview the produced AD in HMD. One response suggested that better playback features would be needed. Some participants also reported that some buttons were frozen or they would be replying with delay. Additionally, some of the responses suggested that better video quality to see all the details would be needed. **In the second iteration**, many of the previous improvements were already solved, but some additional suggestions were made by the participants: the need to have the text of the AD segment fully displayed when recording; adjustable text and window sizes; automatic jumping to a specific time when clicking on a timed segment; the possibility to visualise the video full screen; improving the functions forward and backwards, and an option to print the script.

Regarding **missing functionalities in the first iteration**, the responses suggested that the following features could be implemented: a waveform to indicate when a character starts or finishes speaking, jumping back to 5-10 frames at a time, synchrony between AD segments and video, an option to export the script to a text file for professional recording, being able to join or separate descriptions, and at the same time add or subtract timecodes. One participant suggested also that more options for the fading of program audio could be added. **In the second iteration**, users suggested further functionalities: they would like to navigate using the segment list, and the possibility to choose the narration speed in characters per second, not words per minute.

Regarding the **"set the angle" option, in the first iteration**, most participants (75%) found it easy to use. However, one participant reported that the screen on her or his laptop would regularly turn black after trying to set the angle: the sound would remain, but the image disappeared. One response suggests that a participant would prefer to set the angle only for very important situations, and not for all AD segments: "Yes, just 1 key command. But I would like to have more freedom. The tutorial tells me we need an angle for each segment. I would like to have an angle only for very important situations." **In the second iteration**, a similar percentage (70.83%) found the "set the angle" option easy to use, a positive percentage since this is a totally new concept for audio description.

As far as the **preview modes in the first iteration** are concerned, some of the participants did not encounter any problems while using them (e.g. “Yes, one allows you to move, the other one makes you see your fixed angles”), but for 50% participants one or both preview modes were not working properly (e.g. “I think they are useful, but my video screen went black when trying them”) or they could not see the difference between free and forced mode (e.g. “No. I could not hear myself and I did not see any difference between them”). Two participants reported that not all of the recorded segments played in the preview mode. In **the second iteration**, 11 participants (45.83%) assessed the preview modes positively in their comments. Some participants did not use the preview options due to unordered TC values or problems during the recording. The problems related to recording functions or displaying the video may be due to the PCs used by participants taking part in the test, or to the lack of experience in recording AD (only 13 participants, i.e 54.17%, reported recording AD in their practice). For some participants several buttons (such as long test or short test) were not displayed correctly which may be due to performing the test with lower screen resolution than necessary, despite test instructions advised on this. Although one participant deemed the editor “too complex”, this response may be related to the profile of this audio describer, who is 61 years old, does not use any software for producing AD and never audio described a 360° video before.

When asked about whether it takes longer to audio describe videos in 360°, in the first iteration, most participants (79.2%) replied positively, as there are more visual details to describe, 360° content require more thorough content selection and the angles need to be set for every AD segment. **In the second iteration**, the percentage of those thinking that audio describing 360° videos will take longer was 70%, with some participants indicating that it is all a matter of practice.

Regarding the impact of audio describing 360° videos on their AD practice, participants presented varying opinions. **In the first iteration**, 58.3% of the participants considered, however, that it will impact on their work in the coming years. Participants who replied positively to this question mentioned the following reasons: (1) the application for this medium is fast, (2) it is a whole new approach for the production of AD. **In the second iteration**, the percentage was 75%. Some participants admitted not having thought about the impact of virtual reality on their future work, and some were uncertain about the future of this new technology.

Finally, in the final open field of the questionnaire, **additional comments** were made during the **first iteration** regarding the shortcuts, which in opinion of the participants should be customisable, as it would be easier to manage faster the AD 360° editor. Also, some participants reported some technological issues: problems with the recording and problems playing the video: “stepping back and forwards in the video didn't work so well”. One participant added a comment about the edit mode: “I sometimes forgot to put it back in “Edit mode” in order to make changes. If you could make the change between modes more distinctive somehow that would be helpful.” Another participant commented: “I would like to understand better how to output and review completed work.” **In the second iteration**, these previous problems were not reported and, on the contrary, some users expressed very positive remarks: “Fascinating exercise and project”, “I really like the editor”, “Thank you for this software. I am looking forward to using it in my work”, “I think it’s a very exciting area and having a tool that addresses 360° videos – which are here to stay- is very cool. I look forward to hearing more about how the tool progresses”, among others. One user indicated that the tool could also be used for traditional videos, not only for 360° videos.

It is worth highlighting that one participant who had taken part in the first test expressed: “I participated in the last test, and I found this version much easier to use. I was able to master most of the functions without going back and forth to the manual, whereas last time I was a bit

confused. Very well marked and placement of most used buttons is excellent". The improvements in the shortcuts and the inclusion of a soundwave were also valued by participants taking both takes, as they realised their suggestions had been taken into account.

4 participants reported that it took them a while to get used to the program as they had no previous experience of using it. Such factors as lack of familiarity with the new format of 360° videos and the new software, age, usage of AD editors, not being accustomed to record AD, and the fact that most participants described the 360° video for the first time may explain the score in SUS questionnaire. This was expressed by several participants in the following comments: "I would definitely need some technical training and previous practice in order to be able to use this editor for my work", "I really like the editor. I wasn't comfortable recording the AD myself. I usually write the script and professional voice actors record it", "As any new software you don't feel confident until you've used it a lot. I'd try to use it to be more familiar with it", or "A tutorial video would be great or a presential class".

3.4. Sign Language editing tool

This section reports on measures, participant profile, materials, experimental protocol of the Sign Language editing tool action, and discusses its results.

- **SL editing tool tested:** version 54
- **Users:** 6 participants
- **Partner responsible for tests:** RBB
- **Dates:** 25th October 2019
- **Format:** all materials were online but to facilitate participation the test was performed in a lab

The full methodology for the SL editor action is included in Annex 15 and the full report with the results is included in Annex 16. What follows is a summary of the main elements, reproducing when appropriate excerpts of the full reports in the annex.

3.4.1. Measures

The SL editing tool report focused on two measures: usability and preferences. For usability, SUS was used. For preferences, a specific questionnaire with the following questions was developed:

- What did you like most about the SL editor?
- What did you like less about the SL editor?
- What do you think could be improved, and how?
- Did you miss any functionality? If yes, can you tell us which?
- Do you find the feature for setting the angle for the SL instances easy to use? Explain why.
- Were the preview modes useful for you? Explain why.
- Do you think it will take you longer to interpret videos in 360°? Why?
- Do you think 360° videos will impact your work as a SL interpreter?
- Other comments:

3.4.2. Participants

Six participants (3 male, 3 female), with ages ranging 31 to 61 and university studies took part in the test. 2 reported having German as their main language, 2 report having German Sign Language as their main language, and 2 report having both as their main languages. Their job profiles are: management assistant/editor (1), SL interpreter (4), and research assistant (1). Their working experience in the field of SL varies from 9 years (3) to 4 (1), 2 (1) and 6 months (1). Three participants report having produced less than 50 hours of SL interpreting, whilst 1 reports between 151 and 300 and another one, more than 300. When asked about the software they normally use when interpreting, 2 do not give a reply and 1 indicates that “other persons are setting everything up”. Only Adobe, Finalcut, iMovie and Linon Media are mentioned by the other participants. Most of them have received specific training on SL interpreting, although one does not reply to this question. All of them use a laptop on a daily basis, but none of them report using an HMD. None of them have watched virtual reality content on an HMD, on a tablet or on a smartphone, and only one reports having watched occasionally this type of content on a tablet. The reasons for not having watched it are lack of accessibility (2 replies) and lack of chance to use it (5 replies). When asked if they agree with the statement “I am interested in virtual reality content”, 2 strongly agree, 2 agree and 2 neither agree nor disagree.

3.4.3. Materials

Participants were given access to the SL editor, which contained one clip to be interpreted. The chosen clip was an excerpt of *Täter | Opfer | Polizei* crime scene investigation, with a length of one minute and 33 seconds, but participants were asked to interpret from timecode 00:00:04:01 to 00:01:27:24. Subtitle files were available in English and German so that interpreters could work from these files in case they could not hear or understand the original audio.

Participants were also given a video tutorial before performing the test. It was available both in English and in German. They were also given access to a quick user guide and an instructions sheet with the tasks to be performed.

Three online questionnaires were prepared for this test: demographic, SUS, and preference.

Figure 27 shows the SL editor tested.

Figure 27: SL editor

3.4.4. Experimental protocol

The experimental protocol followed the general framework established for all pilot actions:

- Participants are welcomed and ImAc project and test is presented (by email).
- Ethical clearance: participants sign informed consent forms (online form).
- Participants fill in a demographic questionnaire (online form).
- Participants are asked to watch a video tutorial and read a quick user guide (online).
- Participants are instructed about the tasks to be performed (online):
 - Go to the ACM editor interface.
 - Click the edit button on the SL task that has been assigned to you to open the web SL editor with the video.
 - Sign interpret the video:
 - Define segments for each speaker by playing the main video, pausing and setting the resulting time code as TCin and Tcout.
 - Set the character for the speaker's name on each segment and, if necessary, a different angle. If a speaker moves to a different location, create a new segment and set the new angle.
 - Activate the camera and adjust your position if necessary.
 - Record the SL video(s). Either you record one video for the full length of the content, or you record shorter videos. Subtitles over the main video will be displayed during the recording. If necessary, you can delete unwanted recordings.
 - Preview the video with "forced preview" mode. In case of timing errors, move the SL segments, if necessary.
 - Save the SL file and close the SL editor window.
- Participants fill in SUS questionnaire (online form).
- Participants fill in preference questionnaire (online form).
- Participants are thanked.

3.4.5. Results

Results are presented for the two measures under analysis: usability and preferences.

Regarding **usability**, the SUS average score is **39.17** (below average, 68 or more is considered above average). The letter grade is F, and the obtained score corresponds to the percentile rank: 0-14% (see Figure 28).

Figure 28: SUS score for SL editor

Regarding preferences, the whole list of replies is included in the full report in Annex 16, but results are summarised next.

What participants liked most about the SL editor was that it gives the possibility to interpret immersive videos, setting the angle and showing the position of the speaker. The clear structure of the control was also highlighted.

What participants liked less about the SL editor was the complexity and the number of elements on the user interface. One participant did not like having the subtitle, and another one reported that it was not possible to shorten the SL interpreter video segment. Another participant was confused by some function elements that partly overlap.

Regarding **what could be improved, and how**, the following suggestions were made:

- first of all, it would be better to open and close different user interface sections;
- secondly, it would be positive to cut video segments in which the SL interpreter does not interpret, and
- finally, it was suggested to mark the time-code in in green and the time-code out in red and to allow the timeline of the video to be edited.

As for **missing functionalities**, participants referred to the replies in the previous question and highlighted the need to cut specific segments. For instance, if the interpreting is longer than the segment, one participant explains that the interpreting window is black and the interpreter cannot see how far she/he has to extend the segment.

Regarding the **“set the angle” option**, two participants thought it difficult to understand at the beginning, but then found it simple. Another participant stated that it is sufficient, as it is offered. One participant did not provide feedback on this, and another one encountered some problems.

As far as the **preview modes**, two participants found it useful, one did not use it and one did not provide an answer. One highlighted that a good PC is needed to watch videos in real time.

When asked about whether it takes longer to interpret videos in 360°, three participants replied positively, the reason being the need to set the angle of the speaker and the orientation. Another one considered it would not take longer and it would highly depend on the difficulty of understanding the subtitles. One participant stated that “once you understand the editor, it’s a very good tool for translating SL well and quickly”.

Regarding the impact of audio describing 360° videos on their practice, two replied “no”, one stated that she/he did not know, another one considered that “not yet”, and two replied “yes”. It is important to highlight that one participant said “for the deaf, interpreting 360° videos are a further step towards participation”. In the final open field of the questionnaire, **additional comments** were made indicating that the tool is “easy to learn” but it takes some time. This is reflected in the various comments received: one participant considered she/he was not able to successfully use the tool, whereas another one was happy to “learn new things”. Some suggestions were made to make the quick guide easier to understand.

Overall, participants have a positive attitude towards this new technological development and provide interesting feedback on possible improvements. They find the workflow to produce SL video segments for 360° videos with the ImAc tool different from the standard productions they are used to, and this has a direct implication on the results of the objective usability data.

3.5. Setting the angle focus groups

Setting the angle has been an innovative feature of 360° videos and has been included in the different editors. ImAc wanted to take a step further and, in its final stages, a new method for setting the angle in subtitling was tested through qualitative methods. Participants were asked to test the ImAc method (editor) and the new approach developed by IRT in which the professional sets the angle with a controller pad while wearing virtual reality glasses. Since this approach is in an early development stage, it was considered that a focus group was the best methodological approach, as it would trigger a lively discussion. Two focus groups were developed, at IRT and UAB. Results are presented below for both focus groups. Methodology and reports are found in the Annexes.

Figure 29: Setting the angle feature in the editor

Figure 30: Setting the angle with Oculus Quest app

3.5.1. Measures

Preferences were gathered through two focus groups. A list of questions was prepared in advance to lead the discussion:

- What do you like best about the two solutions?
- What do you like less about the two solutions?
- How do you think they could be improved?
- Which one would you prefer to use in your professional life, and why?
- Apart from setting the speaker position, are there other subtitle parameters you could imagine to perform in the HMD app?
- Do you have any suggestions?

3.5.2. Participants

In the Barcelona focus group six participants were recruited, but only four could finally participate. In the German focus group, six participants took part. They were all professional subtitlers. All participants in Barcelona were in their late 20s and were Catalan/Spanish speakers, whereas the Munich participants' age range was between 25 and 43 and they were German speakers. None of the participants had ever subtitled a 360° video. Participants in Germany were more experienced (5 out of 6 had subtitled more than 300 hours) than in Barcelona, where only 2 reported having subtitled this number of hours. All participants reported using subtitling software and having university studies, as well as using various devices on a daily basis. They generally do not watch VR content (only a few of them do occasionally), the reasons being varied (because they are not interested, because it is not

accessible, because they have not had the chance to use it). When asked if they agree with the statement “I am interested in VR content”, three strongly agree in Barcelona and one neither agrees nor disagrees. In Germany, two agree, three neither agree nor disagree, and one disagrees. Only one participant, in Germany, has VR glasses.

3.5.3. Materials

The test was developed in a lab environment. Each participant had one computer with access to the subtitling editor, where one short video excerpt was ready. Consent forms and the ImAc demographic questionnaire were prepared. VR Glasses “Oculus Quest” including right hand controller and positioning app installed were available, and a two-page visual guide for VR positioning tool was created. Additionally, a page containing the most basic keyboard shortcuts (like play, pause, jump to position) was provided to the participants.

3.5.4. Experimental protocol

The following steps were taken during the focus group:

- Opening: welcome and brief presentation of the ImAc project, the aim of the focus group and its development. Participants read and sign consent form and fill in demographic questionnaire.
- Subtitling editing tool presentation, focusing on setting the angle only.
- Presentation of alternative method for setting the angle on VR.
- Participants are allowed to freely set the angle with the subtitling editing tool on a computer, and at the same time they are shown on a one-to-one basis the alternative method and are allowed to test it for approximately 2 minutes each.
- Focus group discussion about the two methods, following the suggested list of questions.
- Wrap up: summary of focus group conclusions, which are approved by all participants.

3.5.5. Results

The **approved conclusions for the UAB focus group** are the following: participants are very satisfied with the tools. The editor is intuitive, and the VR glasses open many possibilities. Even though none of the participants had used the editor or had ever used VR glasses, in general they did not have any problems.

They believe that it is ideal to be able to choose which option (editor/VR glasses) the subtitler prefers. The group believes that, currently, a good solution would be to create the subtitles in the traditional editor and set the angle on the VR glasses.

It is suggested that there could even be two different professional profiles (subtitler and simulator), and that they could work simultaneously: if the simulator detects an error in a subtitle with the VR glasses, the subtitler corrects it in real time in the editor. They also express that ideally in the future the subtitler could focus on linguistic and creative issues.

They propose some suggestions for improving the VR glasses app, such as:

- One controller could be used to set the angle and the other controller could be used to undo the previous action or include shortcuts;
- In static fragments, certain scenes could be filtered, and the same angle could always be set for certain characters, so that these fragments could be directly reviewed;

- The subtitles could be marked with the VR controller and this mark could go to the subtitle list (to know what to check, etc.). Subtitlers could go directly to the marked subtitles on the editor and review them;
- To include an "auto-safe mode".

They propose some improvements for the editor:

- Reverse navigation (reverse mouse) led to some problems, but they admit it is a matter of practice;
- The editor should work properly with Mac and should not get bumpy (in one case it did, maybe because of the connection);
- Possibility of reviewing subtitle by subtitle and possibility of reviewing everything;
- When you click on a subtitle, it should take you to the specific character and angle;
- In static fragments, certain scenes could be filtered out and the same angle could always be established for certain characters, so that these fragments can be reviewed directly;
- Subtitles where the angle is not marked could be automatically identified.

Participants make suggestions based on the VR glasses:

- Inclusion of speech recognition so that they can subtitle with the VR glasses and then post-edit with the editor. This opens up many possibilities in SDH, where one could automate the inclusion of non-speech information, the inclusion of colours (perhaps with a different number of clicks), or the automatic coding of the source of the sound (for example, a telephone).
- Possibility that the pointer automatically resets the music in creative karaoke-type subtitles (possibility to fill in the subtitle for karaoke).
- Ability to apply Instagram technology that allows you to select a person and make the text follow them. The program could recognize the characters and automatically assign the angle, with the option to uncheck it when desired.

The participants note that it is necessary to assess how the technology of virtual reality will evolve and to evaluate the viability of doing a whole working day with VR glasses. In any case, it is a question of habit and of seeing the evolution of the technology.

Overall, participants consider that the collaboration between developers and professional subtitlers is necessary, so that the tools respond to the subtitlers' needs.

The **approved conclusions for the IRT focus group** were the following. The participants found that the two authoring methods cannot be compared directly and additionally neither of them compare to the applications that they use. Thus, the question "which one would you prefer" cannot be answered directly.

Both methods have their advantages:

- The VR glasses are easy to use and pointing at a speaker is very intuitive.
- In the tested web editor implementation, the positioning requires three steps: 1. Mark subtitle as a 'positioned subtitle'; 2. Drag & drop video such that speaker is positioned in the center; 3. Click button to set the angle. That is a very time-consuming process and a lot slower than the solution with VR glasses.
- Potential advantage: The web editor as well as other classic environments have the advantage that setting the speaker's position might be 'just another mouse click'

during the authoring process (setting speaker location should be easier to integrate in authoring process).

- The orientation within the 360° scene is better in the VR glasses application.
- The VR controller is more comfortable to use than the mouse.
- The participants would prefer VR glasses for a quality check process (i.e. when only minor corrections need to be done).
- At the current stage, participants could only use the web editor in their professional live, because the VR glasses application lacks relevant features for subtitle authoring.

The participants liked a lot the idea to use VR glasses for editing 360° content. The participants discussed about possibilities to combine a classic subtitle editor with VR glasses when it comes to 360° content and suggested various approaches:

- One idea would be to project assistive items like a keyboard or even the entire desktop environment into the VR glasses. This could be temporary (e.g. desktop environment for a specific authoring step) or permanent (e.g. a virtual keyboard for a visual feedback of a real keyboard that is attached as input device to the VR glasses application).
- The participants could imagine that a non-premium production or a production where most of the text is already available (e.g. via speech to text algorithms) could be realised using VR glasses only (assuming that additional features are available in the VR application). In that case, a virtual object showing the audio envelope curve would be very helpful to set timing for subtitles.
- Another idea is to add a marker functionality in the VR app that allows to mark subtitles with issues that cannot be fixed directly in the app. The issue could be handled afterwards on a PC.

The participants made concrete suggestions for improvements:

- One of the main missing features in both applications is the possibility to play the video with higher speed (e.g. 2x real time).
- In the web editor, the speaker position should be set via a simple mouse click, maybe pressing a keyboard button simultaneously (e.g. ctrl+click: set position; click: grab&drag video for rotation).
- In the VR app, the user should be able to position the subtitle while the video is running (in order to avoid auto-pause and accelerate the process).

The participants assume that it would be more difficult to establish the exact timing of subtitles within VR glasses application. Accurate timing is important for them in higher quality productions.

The participants assume that one would get used to using VR glasses for a limited amount of time (e.g. time for authoring a 360° video of about 10 minutes length), but more “recovering time” is needed than for a PC screen. One participant could imagine that one would get used to even longer usage times with VR glasses.

3.6. Conclusions

Regarding the tools that were tested in two iterations, SUS scores were generally below average (68 or more is considered above average) and on the D range for the three tools (Figure 31) during the first iteration. This did not come as a surprise as the tools were under development and the ultimate aim was to get user feedback from a very early stage. Indeed, the fact that tools were at an early stage but had lot of potential was a comment made in the first action by some participants. The invaluable output provided by the participants, especially through qualitative feedback included in the post-questionnaires, allowed to improve the tools in the second round, and get higher marks, as shown in Figure 31.

Figure 31: SUS scores for editors

Although the recruitment criteria were the same in both user testing, the sample was not homogeneous in both iterations. Regarding the experimental procedure, it was kept as similar as possible, but some changes had to be made to the instructions due to improvements in the tools and previous experience. Therefore, a comparison between results should be taken with caution.

It should also be stressed that, although all participants fulfilled the requirements, their level of technological expertise and software usage differed, therefore impacting the results. For instance, in the AD editor test, many professionals indicated that they do not currently use specific software and a considerable number expressed that they are only in charge of writing the audio descriptions, not actually recording them. Facing an integrated tool that allows both for script writing and recording in a short test may have proven challenging for many of them.

As one of the test participants put it, “as any new software you don’t feel confident until you’ve used it a lot”. However, the ImAc approach was to address all those professionals who actually perform this job, so as to get their first impressions on a new tool, fully aware that a learning period would be needed to actually grasp the full potential of the tool.

As for the SL editor, it was only tested in one iteration and objective SUS results scored lower than the other tools. A possible explanation for this is that the number of participants was six and most of them –as it is normally the case in this work environment– do not use specific software for SL interpreting in their professional life. As one participant expressed it, “other persons are setting everything up”. This shows that, in order for the tool to be successfully adopted, participants will need a longer training than the short explanation provided during the test. However, as another user put it, “once you understand the editor, it’s a very good tool for translating SL well and quickly”.

Beyond numerical data, tests have provided invaluable qualitative feedback. The tools have been mainly praised for being easy to use and easy to understand, and mostly intuitive. The novelty of the “setting the angle” function has been valued positively by users, who see future possibilities in the virtual reality industry. Focusing specifically on this feature, two focus groups have been performed in the last stages of the project to test an innovative approach to setting the angle in subtitling by means of virtual reality glasses and a controller. This approach has been welcomed by subtitlers, who have made multiple suggestions on how this could be taken a step further including new technologies and expanding this approach to other subtitling functions.

The feedback received from the various tests have allowed to improve the ImAc tools taking into account user needs and requirements, but not only: the list of requirements, user needs, suggested improvements and user views on the future of 360° provide interesting food for thought beyond the realm of ImAc regarding the role of accessibility service professionals in relation to new types of media.

4. TESTING THE PLAYER INTERFACE

The player interface is tested in ImAc at different moments:

- During development:
 - Pilot phase 1, both at CCMA and RBB, with persons with hearing loss.
 - Pre-pilot phase 2 actions, both at CCMA and RBB, with persons with hearing loss.
 - Pre-pilot 2 action, both at RNIB and UAB, with persons with sight loss.
- Once user requirements have been implemented:
 - Pilot phase 2 at RBB and CCMA.
 - Cross-national pilot at RNIB and UAB.

In the same session as the player interface was tested, additional tests on presentation modes were performed. The same users were targeted as it was considered this would facilitate their participation. However, for the sake of clarity, results are presented separately: Chapter 4 reports on the results of the tests on the player interface and Chapters 5 to 8 report on the tests on service presentation modes. Chapter 9 focuses on pilot phase 2 actions.

During development, the interface testing focused on two aspects:

- a) traditional menu in both tablet and head-mounted display, tested by persons with hearing loss, and
- b) voice interaction and enhanced accessibility menu tested by persons with sight loss.

Results are presented separately per stage and keeping always the following structure:

- General description of the pilot action: users, version, dates and format.
- Measures used, based on framework presented in Figures 12 and 13. If an ad-hoc preference questionnaire is used, it is reproduced in this section.
- Participants' description, summarising the data obtained through the demographic questionnaires. Given that we are within the realm of media accessibility, it was decided to take a wider approach to testing and use different user profiles who claim using subtitles.
- Materials, presenting the different materials and content used for the tests.
- The experimental protocol, which follows the general framework in Figure 14.
- Results, with a discussion of the main results of the pilot action. More specific details, with a thorough reproduction of all replies, are included in the full reports included as annexes.

Full methodology and reports are presented as annexes. These full reports include data both for subtitling presentation modes and player interface, which are presented separately here and in a summarised version for easier understanding.

4.1. CCMA pilot phase 1

The main features of the subtitling pilot action at CCMA in which the player interface was tested are summarised next:

- **Users:** 13 home users

- **Version:** 3.2, http://84.88.32.46/imacpilot1_part2/
- **Dates:** 1/10/2018, 16-19/10/2018
- **Format:** face-to-face

4.1.1. Measures

The same measures were used for both RBB and CCMA player interface test, namely usability and preferences. Usability was measured by means of SUS, translated into Catalan by CCMA and validated by UAB. Some usability questions were also included in the preference questionnaire.

- Did you use the setting "Indicator"? Yes/No
- What was the function of "Indicator"?
- Did you use the setting "Area"? Yes/No
- What was the function of "Area"?
- Which other subtitle personalisation options did you use?
- What did you like most about the ImAc player?
- What did you like less about the ImAc player?
- What do you think could be improved, and how?
- Did you miss any options? If yes, can you tell us which?
- Other comments:

4.1.2. Participants

13 participants took part in the test (7 male= 53.8% and 6 female= 46.2%) users, age ranging between 19 and 66. 6 users (46.2%) indicated Catalan as their main language, 3 indicated Spanish (23%), 3 indicated Catalan Sign Language (23%) and 1 indicated both Catalan and Catalan Sign Language (7.7%). Most of the users had at least secondary education studies, 46.13% with university degrees. 8 testers (61.5%) defined themselves as deaf and 5 as hearing impaired (38.5%). For the majority of users (69%), the impairment began at birth or below the age of 4, while for only 1 user the impairment started over 60 years.

The technical device used most often on a daily basis by participants was a smartphone (100%), followed by TV (12= 92%) and laptop (10=83.3%), while tablet had less use (6=46.15%) and PC was the less used device (5 users=38.5%). HMDs were used by only one user, while another user indicated the use of a Sennheiser magnetic induction loop & a video game console. Nine of the users (69.23%) had never watched virtual reality content before, mostly because they were not interested or had not had the chance to. When directly asked if they were interested in virtual reality content, all testers replied positively. Most of the users (8=61.5%) did not own a device to access virtual reality content, while 4 users (30.76%) owned some kind of device (cardboard, HMD, tablet, smartphone, Oculus Rift or Play Station game console).

In terms of content preferences, most of the testers liked news, fiction, talk-shows and documentaries, while some also liked sports, and cartoons. Almost all of them used subtitles for all types of content. There was an even distribution between 0 and more than 4 hours among the testers in terms of how many hours a day they consume subtitled content and most of the testers used subtitling because it was their only way of accessing the dialogues. Those

who did not activate it reported that the interface was not accessible or that they did not want subtitling in all content (for instance, sports), only in certain types.

4.1.3. Materials

For the user interface test, the traditional menu of the player was ready in Catalan and content was uploaded. The content was a musical concert, *Desconcert 1*, in Catalan, with all modes and services tested (in this case subtitles) implemented in Catalan.

Figure 32: Player User Interface, traditional menu (in Catalan)

Two devices were tested: HMD and tablet.

Three types of questionnaires were ready: the demographic questionnaire, the SUS questionnaire, and the preference questionnaire. It has been shown that SUS provides reliable results with a sample of 8-12 participants [6].

4.1.4. Experimental protocol

The same experimental protocol was followed at CCMA and RBB:

- Participants are welcomed and ImAc project and test is presented (face-to-face)
- Ethical clearance: participants sign informed consent forms (paper copies)
- The facilitator explains how the ImAc player/menu works
- Users are requested to perform two tasks. Order of the tasks is randomised across participant.
 - Task HMD. Instructions given on paper:
 - After some seconds, pause the video.
 - Please play the video again.
 - Please change the volume.
 - Please open the menu and activate subtitles in your language.
 - Please randomly personalise subtitles, using all available options.
 - Task Tablet. Instructions given on paper:
 - After some seconds, pause the video.

- Please play the video again.
 - Please change the volume.
 - Please open the menu and activate subtitles in your language.
 - Please randomly personalise subtitles, using all available options.
- After each task, SUS questionnaire is administered
 - After both tasks, preference questionnaire is administered
 - Participants are thanked

4.1.5. Results

SUS scores were obtained for the traditional menu in the player interface, both when an HMD and a tablet were used. When using an HMD (Figure 33), the average score is 68.8 (above average, 68 or more is considered above average). The letter grade is C and the score corresponds to the percentile rank: 46-50%.

Figure 33: SUS score for HMD (CCMA pilot phase 1)

When using a tablet (Figure 34), the average score is 82.9 (above average, 68 or more is considered above average). The letter grade is A and the score corresponds to the percentile rank: 90-95%.

Figure 34: SUS score for tablet (CCMA pilot phase 1)

A Wilcoxon signed rank test shows that the observed differences between HMD and tablet ratings are significant ($Z=-2.160$, $p=.031$, ties=1). The user interface presented on a tablet is rated significantly higher than the HMD interface in terms of usability.

The user interface is well-received by all of users, because it offers the possibility to access to immersive 360° videos adding the accessibility services adapted to this new environment.

Regarding the setting “indicator”, 100% of the users reported using it and was well understood by most users. Regarding the setting “area”, 75% of the users reported using it but understanding its real function proved challenging.

Participants also reported using most functions, such as change language, size, and position on screen, indicators or background.

Concerning positive feedback, they highlighted the extensive personalisation, and they also referred to the indicator, the font selection, the simplicity of the options. They also stressed some aspects more related to the actual experience, such as the immersion and the possibility to access 360° images.

Concerning negative feedback, most users expressed their disagreement with the solution developed with the yellow pointer that is used to access the interface menus when using the HMD device. The main reason is the difficulty that it represents using it because it disappears constantly, which leads to the absolute disorientation of the user.

When asked for improvements, one of the users even made a graphical proposal (Figure 35) on how to implement the solution, recommending that the pointer is always active at a comfortable distance from the menu. Some users recommended that the pointer could be always active while the menu is ON and disappear when the menu is OFF.

Figure 35: Suggestion by CCMA user

Some users had difficulty finding the switch to activate / deactivate the subtitles, although they had previously been explained in detail how the interface works. Some users disagreed with the different colour of the arrow and recommended to use the same colour as the subtitle. In general terms, users were happy with the results and would like to repeat in new tests.

4.2. RBB pilot phase 1

The main features of the subtitling pilot action are summarised next:

- **Users:** 12 home users
- **Version:** 3.2

- **Dates:** 27-28/09/2018, 15-19/10/2018
- **Format:** face-to-face

4.2.1. Measures

The user interface test focused on two measures: usability and preferences.

For usability, SUS was used. Some usability questions were also included in the preference questionnaire, after discussion among partners. The questions were the following:

- Did you use the setting "Indicator"? Yes/No
- What was the function of "Indicator"?
- Did you use the setting "Area"? Yes/No
- What was the function of "Area"?
- Which other subtitle personalisation options did you use?
- What did you like most about the ImAc player?
- What did you like less about the ImAc player?
- What do you think could be improved, and how?
- Did you miss any options? If yes, can you tell us which?
- Other comments:

4.2.2. Participants

12 users took part in the tests: 7 female (58.3%) and 5 male (41.7%) users, aged between 36 and 63. 5 users (41.7%) indicated German as their mother tongue, 5 (41.7%) indicated German Sign Language, 1 user indicated both German and German Sign Language (8.3%) and 2 (16.7%) indicated Serbian. Most of the users had at least secondary education studies or higher. 7 participants (58.3%) defined themselves as deaf, 4 (33.3%) as hearing impaired, and one user reported having a cochlear implant. For almost all users, the impairment began at birth or below the age of 4, while for 2 users (16.7%) the impairment started between 41 and 60 years.

The technical device used most often on a daily basis was smartphone (11 users= 91.7%), followed by TV and laptop (both 9 users=75%), while tablet and PC were used less often (both 6 users= 50%). HMDs were not used by any of the participants. Almost all users (83.3%) had never watched virtual reality content before: only two reported watching it occasionally (1 user) or daily (1 user) on a smartphone, one reports using it occasionally on a smartphone plugged to an HMD or in an HMD. The main reasons for not using virtual reality content were that they were not interested (33.3%) or had not had the chance to (58.3%). When directly asked if they were interested in virtual reality content, most of the testers replied positively (58.3%) while some were not sure (5=41.7%). Most of the users (66.7%) did not own a device to access VR content or did not know or did not want to reply (25%).

In terms of content preferences, most of the testers liked news, fiction and documentaries, while some also liked sports, talk shows and cartoons. Almost all of them used subtitles for all types of content. The smaller group of testers that did not always use subtitles explain that they only used subtitles for certain types of content or that they sometimes understood well enough without subtitles. There was an even distribution between 0 and more than 4 hours among the participants in terms of how many hours a day they consumed subtitled content, and the majority of the testers used subtitles because it was their only way of accessing the dialogues.

4.2.3. Materials

For the user interface test, the traditional menu of the player was ready, and content was uploaded. The content was a musical concert, *Desconcert 1*, in Catalan, with all modes and services tested (in this case subtitles) implemented in German.

Figure 36: Player User Interface, traditional menu (in German)

Two devices were tested: HMD and tablet. Three types of questionnaires were ready: the demographic questionnaire, the SUS questionnaire and the preference questionnaire, all in German versions.

4.2.4. Experimental protocol

The experimental protocol followed the general framework established for all pilot actions. It was first tested in a pilot test, improved, and then implemented as follows:

- Participants are welcomed and ImAc project and test is presented (face-to-face)
- Ethical clearance: participants sign informed consent forms (paper copies)
- Participants fill in a demographic questionnaire (online)
- The facilitator explains how the ImAc player/menu works
- Users are requested to perform two tasks. Order of the tasks is randomized across participants
 - Task HMD. Instructions given on paper:
 - After some seconds, pause the video.
 - Please play the video again.
 - Please change the volume.
 - Please open the menu and activate subtitles in your language.
 - Please randomly personalize subtitles, using all available options.
 - Task Tablet. Instructions given on paper:
 - After some seconds, pause the video.
 - Please play the video again.

- Please change the volume.
- Please open the menu and activate subtitles in your language.
- Please randomly personalize subtitles, using all available options.
- After each task, SUS questionnaire is administered
- After both tasks, preference questionnaire is administered
- Participants are thanked

4.2.5. Results

Concerning SUS, results for the tablet and HMD are presented in Figure 37 and Figure 38.

Figure 37: SUS score for HMD (RBB pilot phase 1)

The SUS average score for the HMD is 77.3 (above average, 68 or more is considered above average). The letter grade is B+, and our score corresponds to the percentile rank: 80-84%.

Figure 38: SUS score for tablet (RBB pilot phase 1)

The SUS average score for the tablet is 75.4 (above average, 68 or more is considered above average). The letter grade is B, and our score corresponds to the percentile rank: 70-79%.

A Wilcoxon signed ranks test shows no significant differences between the ratings of Tablet and HMD interfaces ($Z=-.059$, $p=.953$, $\text{ties}=3$).

Almost all testers completed the tasks of the user interface test without problems. However, 8 users (66.67%) had great difficulties in finding the on/off button for the subtitles and needed

help with this task. It thus seems to be necessary to change the position of the on/off button in the accessibility interface.

Regarding the settings “indicator” and “area”, 10 participants (83.3%) used the first one and 11 (91.66%) used the second one as well. None of these terms were clear for the users, but at least the indicator was understood by most of them after trying. The area setting was not understood by any of the users because most of them only recognised the change in font size. We therefore conclude that the wording for these functions should be revised and we doubt the benefit of the area function.

Concerning positive feedback, what the testers like most about the player was the amount of personalisation settings and the clear design of the menu.

Concerning negative feedback, two users (16.6%) did not like the subtitles following their head movements (especially when tilting the head but also when turning the head) and two users (16.6%) found it difficult to find the menu in the HMD after opening it. Furthermore, it bothered many users that they did not find the on/off button and that the menu was very small on the tablet, which made it very difficult to select the options. Instead of adding a zooming function (as suggested by one user), we conclude that it might be necessary to show the enhanced accessibility interface in tablets by default.

Some improvements suggested by participants were: one user suggested that the subtitling submenu could be closed by clicking somewhere outside the menu in the HMD, which is already the case in the tablet mode. Another user asked for a better (or adjustable) contrast in the menu (not white/grey).

When asked about missing functionalities, two users would like to be able to customise the subtitle colour (e.g. for visual impairments regarding certain colours). Two users wanted to display subtitles and signer at the same time. One user had the idea to drag/drop the radar to a different position if it obscured an important area of the video. One user asked for a better “translation” of sound and music, e.g. with vibrations or visualizations such as spectra.

Beyond questionnaires, user observation by the facilitators allowed to identify some further interesting issues worth considering. For instance, usage of the HMD was uncomfortable for users wearing glasses, cochlear implants or hearing aids. The users wearing the last two devices asked explicitly whether it was possible to stream the audio directly to their device. The consequence was that the users either tried to use the headphones and their hearing aids together or just took off the hearing aids. The same applied for the glasses. Additionally, some users mentioned that the HMD was too heavy, and it was not comfortable to wear it for longer periods of time. The low video quality in comparison to standard resolution of TV content together with the weight and fit of the device were other reasons why users seemed not willing to wear an HMD on a regular basis.

Although users had not used 360° content in an HMD before the test, they were mainly amazed by the experience. They mentioned that they would like to see documentaries or concerts. Facilitators could see that users were partially part of the story and reacted with body movement if something came nearer. In conversation with *I, Philip*, a tester shook his head for no.

Facilitators also observed that it was easy for them to learn the usage of the controller to select an option in the menu and the large number of personalisation options was positively evaluated. The specific options like indicator and area for the usage in an HMD were not clear immediately. The testers got an idea about the functionalities once they tried them. We assume that this is part of a learning procedure and we should maybe revise the current wording. The main problem for all users was to locate the on/off button and to find the menu

once it was opened as it was not in all cases in the field of view or the contrast was not high enough.

The usage on the tablet was mainly difficult because the size of the menu was too small, and we propose to use the enhanced accessibility menu for tablets and smartphones to avoid this problem. Please find all details below.

4.3. CCMA pre-pilot 2 action

The main features of the subtitling pre-pilot 2 action are summarised next:

- **Users:** 12 home users
- **Version:** 7.1 <https://imac.gpac-licensing.com/test-ui-cat/>
- **Dates:** 13.05.2019-06.06.2019
- **Format:** face-to-face

4.3.1. Measures

The user interface test focused on two measures: usability and preferences.

For usability, SUS was used. Some usability questions were also included in the preference questionnaire, after discussion among partners. The questions were based on the previous pilot action but included the initial questions on usability were changed to adapt to the new developments in the tool:

- Were you able to activate the subtitles without any help? Yes/No
- Were you able to select the language of the subtitles without any help? Yes/No.
- Which other personalisation options did you use?
- Were you able to activate/deactivate the preview for the personalisation settings without any help? Yes/NO.
- Was the previous of the personalisation settings helpful to you? Yes/No?
- What did you like most about the ImAc player?
- What did you like less about the ImAc player?
- What do you think could be improved, and how?
- Did you miss any options? If yes, can you tell us which?
- Other comments:

4.3.2. Participants

12 users took part in the tests: 5 female (41.7%) and 7 male (58.3%) users, aged between 26 and 72 (mean age= 63). 10 users (83.3%) indicated Catalan was their mother tongue, whereas 1 user selected Spanish and one user chose Catalan and Spanish. Most of the users had at least secondary education studies or higher. 7 participants (58.3%) defined themselves as deaf, and 5 (41.7%) as hearing impaired. The hearing impairment began at different moments in their life: from birth (4=33.3%), before the age of 4 (1=8.3%), between 5 and 12 (2=16.7%), between 13 and 20 (2=16.7%), between 21 and 40 (1= 8.3%) and between 41 and 60 (2= 16.7%).

The technical devices used most often on a daily basis were smartphones and TVs (11 users= 91.7%), followed by PC (8=66.7%) and tablet (7=58.3%) and laptop (4=33.3%). Most users had never watched virtual reality content before: only 1 (8.3%) reported watching it at least once a

month on a tablet and 2 (16.7%) reported watching it at least once a month on a PC. The other usages were occasional. The main reasons for not using virtual reality content were that they did not have the chance to use it. Most showed interest or a strong interest in virtual reality content, whereas one did not agree nor disagree with the statement “I am interested in virtual reality content such as 360° videos). 5 users (41.7%) reported using a device to access virtual reality content, whereas 7 (58.3%) did not. The devices they owned were smartphones, tablets, PC, but in one case an HMD Samsung Gear/Play Station VR and in another case an HMD.

In terms of content preferences, most of the testers liked news, fiction, documentaries and sports. They showed less interest in talk shows and cartoons. They reported activating subtitles always when available for news and fiction (11=91.7%), talk shows, sports and cartoons (8=66.7%). When they did not activate it, it was because the interface was not accessible and because the subtitles in sports hid the results. They reported watching a considerable number of hours of subtitled content every day: 7 (58.3%) reported more than 2 hours, and only one (8.3%) reported not using subtitles although he defined himself as a person with hearing loss. They reported using subtitles because they helped them understand (3=25%) and because they were the only way to have access to the dialogue (8=66.7%), whilst 1 (8.3%) also acknowledged using them for language learning.

4.3.3. Materials

For the user interface test, the traditional menu of the player was ready, and content was uploaded. The content was a musical concert in Catalan, *Desconcert 1* (Leyre), with all modes and services tested (in this case subtitles) implemented in Catalan.

Figure 39: Player Interface in Catalan

Two devices were tested: HMD and tablet. Three types of questionnaires were ready: the demographic questionnaire, the SUS questionnaire and the preference questionnaire, all in the local language versions.

4.3.4. Experimental protocol

The experimental protocol followed the general framework established for all pilot actions and the specific methodology developed for all user interface tests, with updates where new functionalities were available.

- Participants are welcomed and ImAc project and test is presented (face-to-face)

- Ethical clearance: participants sign informed consent forms (paper copies).
- Participants fill in a demographic questionnaire (online)
- The facilitator explains how the ImAc player/menu works
- Users are requested to perform two tasks. Order of the tasks is randomised across participants.
 - Task HMD. Instructions given on paper:
 - Select the video from the initial webpage and press “Play”
 - After some seconds, pause the video.
 - Please play the video again.
 - Please change the volume.
 - Please open the menu and activate subtitles in your language.
 - Please randomly personalise subtitles, using all available options.
 - Task Tablet. Instructions given on paper:
 - After some seconds, pause the video.
 - Please play the video again.
 - Please change the volume.
 - Please open the menu and activate subtitles in your language.
 - Please randomly personalise subtitles, using all available options.
- After each task, SUS questionnaire is administered
- After both tasks, preference questionnaire is administered
- Participants are thanked

4.3.5. Results

SUS scores were obtained for the traditional menu in the player interface, both when an HMD and a tablet were used. When using an HMD (Figure 40), the average score is 70.62 (above average, 68 or more is considered above average). The letter grade is C and the score corresponds to the percentile rank 41-59%.

Figure 40: SUS score for HMD (CCMA pre-pilot action 2)

When using a tablet (Figure 41), the average score is 86.2 (above average, 68 or more is considered above average). The letter grade is A+ and the score corresponds to the percentile rank 96-100%.

Figure 41: SUS score for tablet (CCMA pre-pilot action 2)

A Wilcoxon signed ranks test comparing SUS ratings for HMD and tablet shows statistical differences between them. The SUS scores obtained are significantly higher for tablet (86.25) than for HMD (70.62). $Z = -2.364$, $P = .018$, ties=1.

Most users (11= 91.7%) were able to activate the subtitles without any help and most users (10=83.3%) were able to select the language without any help. Regarding the personalization options used, they indicated: font size, position, subtitle on/off, background, indicator: arrow/radar, menu, language, with diverging uses among them. Most of them (11=91.7%) were able to activate/deactivate the preview for the personalisation settings without any help, and 9 (75%) found it helpful. One user (8.3%) did not like it this way and another user (8.3%) found it difficult. When asked what they liked best, they liked the 360° experience (“the feeling of being inside and understanding the subtitles”, one user said), the personalisation, the sharpness, the radar indicator, and the simple and minimalist interface with a quick response. What some users did not like was moving the head around in the HMD: three of them reported feeling uncomfortable with HMD, which probably had an impact on the scores. Some individual participants reported as the things they liked less the movements to select the option, the radar option (which was selected by another one as the thing she/he liked best), the button sensitivity, and the wide range of options, which demand a lot of time. It is worth noting that although the question addressed the ImAc player, some users were commenting on the HMD experience. This is why, two referred to the HMD weight and fasten system, when they were asked about improvements. Concerning specifically the player, some suggestions were made by individual participants regarding the radar indicator, the head movement to activate the menu, the information provided/icons, and the menu bar. Four users did not have any suggestions and one even said, “it is perfect”. Most users did not miss any options (7=58.3%). One (8.3%) suggested an option to describe additional sounds or voices, and one (8.3%) suggested a help button. Another one (8.3%) suggested using the arrow to move up/down. In the final comments, only three (25%) participants provided further feedback, which referred to the opening menu (she/he found it annoying to wait for it to start), the language identification, and the radar indicator. One user (8.3%) stated that she/he liked the player.

Regarding the three users that had taken part in the previous test, they gave very positive comments: they liked the improved version of the radar, the freedom of movements, and

found “everything ok”, and only reported problems concerning the button sensitivity and the uncomfortability of the HMD. They also provided some further suggestions for improvement.

To sum it up, the main improvements that were suggested are:

- It is difficult to enter the menu when using an HMD. It would be better only to use one click.
- When the menu is displayed, the subtitles are behind, and it is difficult to verify if you have the correct settings.

4.4. RBB pre-pilot 2 action

The main features of the subtitling pre-pilot 2 action are summarized next:

- **Users:** 12 home users
- **Version** 7.1 <https://imac.gpac-licensing.com/test-ui-ger/>
- **Dates:** 06.05.2019-24.05.2019
- **Format:** face-to-face

4.4.1. Measures

The same measures as for the CCMA test were used: usability (SUS) and preferences, with the following questions:

- Were you able to activate the subtitles without any help? Yes/No
- Were you able to select the language of the subtitles without any help? Yes/No
- Which other personalisation options did you use?
- Were you able to activate/deactivate the preview for the personalisation settings without any help? Yes/No
- Was the previous of the personalisation settings helpful to you? Yes/No?
- What did you like most about the ImAc player?
- What did you like less about the ImAc player?
- What do you think could be improved, and how?
- Did you miss any options? If yes, can you tell us which?
- Other comments:

4.4.2. Participants

12 users took part in the tests: 4 female (33.3%) and 8 male (66.7%) users, aged between 21 and 47 (mean age= 39.1). 8 users (66.7%) indicated German was their mother tongue. 4 users (33.3%) indicated German Sign Language was their mother tongue and 1 (8.3%) user chose Swiss Sign Language. It must be stressed out that participants were assigned to the subtitling or the Sign Language test according to their preferences, which they expressed by replying to the question: “You are watching a film for which subtitles and sign languages are available. Which service do you prefer?”

Most of the users had at least further education studies or higher (10=83.3%). 5 participants (41.7%) defined themselves as deaf, and 6 (50%) as hearing impaired, whereas one (8.3%) preferred to define him/herself as a person with a “minor hearing loss”. The hearing impairment began at different moments in their life: from birth (6=50%), before the age of 4 (4=33.3%), or after 21 (2=16.7%).

The technical device they all used on a daily basis was a mobile phone. Half of them also used a tablet, and 5 (41.7%) used a TV and 4 (33.3%), a PC. None of them report using an HMD on a daily basis, and 1 user reported using an ebook reader.

None of the participants had taken part in previous ImAc tests. Most of them had never watched VR content such as 360° videos (9=75%) on a smartphone or an HMD, even less on a PC. Only 1 (8.3%) reported watching it at least once a week on a smartphone. The reasons for not having watched it at all or only occasionally were related to the inaccessibility of 360° videos (3=25%) or because they had not had the chance to use it (6=50%). Other reasons were that there was not much content, that it was expensive or that the content was not interesting. In fact, when faced with the statement “I am interested in virtual reality content (such as 360° videos), 2 (16.7%) strongly agreed, 6 (50%) agreed, and 4 (33.3%) neither agreed nor disagreed. No users reported owning an HMD, although some of them acknowledged having an iPad or smartphone that allowed them to access VR content.

In terms of content preferences, the majority of the testers liked news, fiction, documentaries and, to a lesser extent, sports. They showed less interest in talk shows and cartoons. They reported activating subtitles always when available for news and fiction (11= 91.7%), documentaries and cartoons (10=83.3%), sports (9=75%) and talk shows (8=66.7%). When they didn't activate it, it was because the interface was not accessible or because they just wanted subtitling in certain content. They reported watching a considerable number of hours of subtitled content every day: 6 (50%) reported more than 2 hours, and only one (8.3%) reported not using subtitles, probably because his/her hearing loss was not severe. They reported using subtitles because they helped them understand (8=66.7%) and because they were the only way to have access to the dialogue (1=8.3%), whilst 1 (8.3%) also acknowledged using them for language learning. One (8.3%) user indicated that all reasons apply to him, and another one (8.3%) stressed out that only with subtitle s/he could follow the content.

4.4.3. Materials

For the user interface test, the traditional menu of the player was ready and content was uploaded. The content was a musical concert in Catalan, *Desconcert 1* (Leyre), with all modes and services tested (in this case subtitles) implemented in German. Two devices were tested: HMD and tablet. Three types of questionnaires were ready: the demographic questionnaire, the SUS questionnaire and the preference questionnaire, all in German versions.

Figure 42: Player Interface in German

4.4.4. Experimental protocol

The same experimental protocol used at CCMA was used at RBB (see section 4.3.4).

4.4.5. Results

SUS scores were obtained for the traditional menu in the player interface, both when an HMD and a tablet were used. When using an HMD (Figure 43), the average score is 74.79 (above average, 68 or more is considered above average). The letter grade is B and the score corresponds to the percentile rank 70-79%.

Figure 43: SUS score for HMD (RBB pre-pilot action 2)

When using a tablet (Figure 44), the average score is 63.9 (below average, 68 or more is considered above average). The letter grade is C- and the score corresponds to the percentile rank 35-40%.

Figure 44: SUS score for tablet (RBB pre-pilot action 2)

A Wilcoxon signed ranks test comparing SUS ratings for HMD and Tablet shows statistical differences between them ($Z=-2.091$, $p = .036$, ties=1).

Most users (7= 58.3%) were able to activate the subtitles without any help but activating the language of the subtitles proved difficult to most of them (10=83.3%). Some user did not identify the icons in the settings menu but were afterwards able to select the right ones for subtitles. This is why it was suggested to add abbreviations to the icons for the services.

Regarding the personalisation options used, they indicated: font size, position, background, size, language, indicator, sound on/off, area, with diverging uses among them. Font size was the one selected by all of them. Many of them (7=58.3%) report having problems activating/deactivating the personalisation settings. Some of them did not find the preview of

personalisation settings useful; either because they did not recognize it, did not need it and did not use it.

Concerning what they liked most about the ImAc player, the answers vary from specific presentation modes to general comments on the 360° experience. Regarding the player interface features, they refer to the possibility to change the position of the subtitles and in many cases the menu. The things they liked less refer to the opening of the menu by looking down – so it as suggested to open it by one click or tapping on the touch screen –, the changing of the volume, the language settings, and the button to activate/deactivate subtitles. Three users did not refer to anything they did not like. Users made some suggestions concerning how to improve the player, mainly related to the settings and the menu. One user (8.3%) missed the option of changing the colour for the subtitle, and another one (8.3%) asked for a short explanation of each menu. Three (25%) users did not report any additional requirements. At the end of the test, some minor comments were made regarding the immersive experience, the position of the subtitles behind the menu, and contrast. The icons were difficult to identify by some users.

To sum it up, all users liked the variety of personalisation settings, and suggested some improvements. Based on their input, RBB suggested some improvements:

- Adding an abbreviation next to the icons for the services to help users identify them.
- Revise the language and accessibility settings, as some users were confused with these menus.
- The preview functionality was mainly important for the usage on the tablet as the activated subtitles are behind the menu. Most of the users found this feature just by trying available functionalities. This preview is not necessary for most of the users and one user explicitly said that all changes should be visible immediately.

4.5. RNIB pre-pilot action 2

This pre-pilot action had a different aim: testing the methodology previous to the cross-national pilot. Therefore, a lower number of users was aimed at: 5 per partner.

- **Users:** 5 home users
- **Version:** 7.2., <http://84.88.32.46/test-ad-1-eng/>
- **Dates:** 7/05/2019-27/05/2019
- **Format:** face-to-face

4.5.1. Measures

The same measures as for all user interface tests were used: usability (SUS) and preferences, with the following questions in this case:

- What do you like the most about the menu interaction?
- What do you like less?
- What do you think could be improved and how?
- Other comments.

4.5.2. Participants

5 users took part in the tests: 3 female and 2 males. Their ages were 22, 33, 35, 43, and 69, being English their main language. 4 had university studies and 1, further education. Three of

them defined themselves as blind and 2, as partially sighted. 4 were visually impaired from birth, and one between 13 and 20 years old. All of them reported using TV, a laptop and a mobile phone on a daily basis, and one reported using a PC on a daily basis. None of them selected HMD.

When asked how often they watch virtual reality content (for instance, 360° videos) on different devices, none of them reported using it. Only one reported having used it occasionally on a smartphone. The reason was that this type of content was not accessible (although they were strongly interested or interested) and, in one case, the user was not interested. Two participants reported having a device to access the Virtual Reality content and 1 participant chose the option 'I don't know or I don't want to reply.' In terms of the content they liked watching the most, 1 participant chose the option 'news', 2 participants chose the option 'fiction' and two participants chose the option 'sports'. Despite one user reported not watching audio described content regularly, all the rest watched at least 1 hour a day. To access online content, one user used a magnifier, another one a screen reader, two users used both assistive technologies, and one used none.

4.5.3. Materials

For the user interface test, two menus were ready: the voice interaction menu and the enhanced accessibility menu. Users were expected just to test one of the menus. The content that was available was episode 4 of *Holy Land* with Classic AD. One device was tested: HMD. Three types of questionnaires were ready: the demographic questionnaire, the SUS questionnaire and the preference questionnaire.

Figure 45: Activation of voice-interaction menu

Figure 46: Activation of enhanced accessibility menu

4.5.4. Experimental protocol

The experimental protocol followed the general framework established for all pilot actions and the specific methodology developed for all user interface tests, with updates where new functionalities were available.

- Participants are welcomed and ImAc project and test is presented (face-to-face)
- Ethical clearance: participants sign informed consent forms (paper copies)
- Participants fill in a demographic questionnaire (online)
- Blind users are assigned to the voice control test, and partially sighted users are assigned to the enhanced accessibility menu (high-contrast accessible user interface)
- The facilitator explains how the ImAc player/menu works
- Users are requested to perform the following actions:
 - Open the player
 - Find content
 - Play content
 - Turn AD on/off
 - Volume up/down
 - Pause content
 - Move backward and forward
 - Stop content
 - Close the player
- After the task, SUS and preference questionnaire is administered
- Participants are thanked

4.5.5. Results

Five users tested voice interaction, and only one tested the enhanced accessibility menu. The other user with sight loss preferred to use the voice interaction.

SUS scores for the voice interaction were positive, with a score of 78.13 and a letter grade of B+ (percentile rank: 80-84%). However, it should be considered that only 5 users took part in the test, which aimed at testing the methodology. In this regard, the methodology proved useful, although some users showed a preference to test the menu that was not initially assigned to them.

Figure 47: SUS scores for voice interaction (pre-pilot action 2, RNIB)

Only one user tested the enhanced accessibility menu, therefore results are not relevant and purely anecdotal. However, the values were very high, with a score of 84.37, which equals a letter grade of A+ and corresponds to the percentile rank 96-100%.

Figure 48: SUS score for enhanced accessibility menu interaction (pre-pilot action 2, RNIB)

Regarding the open questions, participants provided some food for thought. They liked the player because it was simple to use and straight forward (voice interaction) and because of the colour contrast and different sizes (enhanced accessibility menu). On the contrary, what they liked less in voice interaction was that the phrasing was not natural – an aspect that was later proposed as an improvement – and they could not turn the AD off when the video was paused. One user asked how the list of videos would be shown and also suggested to include information about the length of the videos. Another suggestion concerned the inclusion of

audible beeps to tell you whether it was on or off. Regarding the enhanced accessibility menu, the user made some suggestions regarding the icons.

It is important to highlight that one user who was defined as partially sighted and regular user of magnification and audio description was assigned to the enhanced accessibility menu, but she/he was unable to use it independently and then moved to the voice interaction menu, which provide very useful.

Another aspect observed during the pilot action is that three testers with severe sight loss (blind) did not feel comfortable wearing the HMD. They could not see the point as they were not engaging with the content visually and, on being explained that the HMD was required to track their head movements, they requested for equipment that was lighter and did not pinch or applied less pressures on the area surrounding their eyes.

Overall, the main aim was not to get results on a small sample but rather to test the methodology. In this regard, it is important in the cross-national pilots to find a way that the sample between those testing the voice interaction and the enhanced accessibility menu is balanced.

4.6. UAB pre-pilot action 2

This pre-pilot action had the aim of testing the methodology previous to the cross-national pilot. Therefore, a lower number of users was aimed at: 5 per partner.

- **Users:** 6 home users
- **Version:** 7.2., <http://84.88.32.46/test-ad-1-cat>
- **Dates:** 11/06/2019-13/06/2019
- **Format:** face-to-face

4.6.1. Measures

The same measures as for the RNIB user interface test were used (see 4.5.1).

4.6.2. Participants

6 users took part in the test (1 female and 5 male). Participants were aged between 23-31 years (23, 26, 27, 28, 31, 34). The main languages of participants were: Spanish (4), Catalan (1) and both (1). 3 participants had university studies and 3 participants had further education. When asked about their degree of sight loss, 3 participants declared themselves as partially-sighted, 2 participants declared themselves as blind and one participant chose the option 'other'. 1 participant was visually impaired from birth, 1 participant became visually-impaired between 0-4 years, one participant between 5-12 years and 3 participants between 13-20 years. When asked about what technology they use on a daily basis, 4 participants reported using TV, 1 – PC, 4 – Laptop, 6 – mobile phone, and none of participants uses HMD on a daily basis. When asked how often they watch Virtual Reality content (for instance, 360° videos) on different devices, only 1 participant declared watching such content occasionally in HMD and 2 participants declared watching such content occasionally in smartphone.

When asked why they never used VR content or used it only occasionally, 2 participants chose the option: 'Because it's not accessible', 2 participants chose the option 'Because I am not interested' and 2 participants chose the option 'Because I have not had the chance to use it'.

When asked to state their level of agreement with the statement: "I am interested in Virtual Reality content (such as 360° videos)", 1 participant strongly agreed, 2 participants agreed, 3 participants neither agreed nor disagreed and 3 participants disagreed. None of participants

reported having a device to access VR. In terms of the content they liked watching the most, 3 participants chose the option 'news', 2 participants 'fiction', 1 participant 'documentaries' and 3 participants 'sports'. When asked about how many hours a day they watched audio described content, 3 participants replied 'none', 1 participant replied 'less than 1 hour', and 2 participants replied 2-3 hours. To access online content, 1 participant used magnifier, 4 participants used screen reader, 2 users used both assistive technologies and 1 used none.

4.6.3. Materials

For the user interface test, the same menus and content as in the previous test were ready (see 4.5.3), in this case translated into Catalan and Spanish.

Figure 49: Enhanced accessibility menu (left) and traditional menu (right)

Figure 50: Enhanced accessibility menu settings

4.6.4. Experimental protocol

The same experimental protocol as in 4.5.4. was followed.

4.6.5. Results

6 participants took part in the test, but only results from 5 could be recorded due to technical problems: data from 4 users testing voice interaction, and 1 user testing the enhanced accessibility menu could be gathered.

SUS scores for the voice interaction were positive, with a score of 71.88 and a letter grade of C+ (percentile rank: 60-64%). However, it should be considered that only 4 users took part in

the test, which aimed at testing the methodology. In this regard, the methodology proved useful.

Figure 51: SUS score for voice interaction (pre-pilot action 2, UAB)

Only one user tested the enhanced accessibility menu, therefore results are not relevant. The value was 52.5, letter grade D, percentile rank: 15-34%.

Figure 52: SUS score for enhanced accessibility menu interaction (pre-pilot action 2, UAB)

Regarding open questions for participants who tested the voice interaction, they liked the fact that different voice navigations options were available and commands can be given in an agile and smooth way without the need to interact manually. They also highlighted that users can forward the video and go backward, stop and open the menu, etc., whenever they want. What they liked less, though, was the syntax to be used in the voice interaction. They also pointed out the fact that the menu is not entirely accurate in terms of forwarding/moving back at this stage, and that the changes in volumes are really subtle, so that some users may not notice them. In terms of improvement, the syntax for the voice interaction was mentioned again. They made also some suggestions on the use of the controller and on how to access the content.

Regarding open questions on the enhanced accessibility menu, the user considers that the button used to enlarge the menu (located in top left corner of the menu) should be larger, as it is difficult to direct the pointer at it. Also, this user considers that looking down to open the menu is not convenient (this person would prefer to look up to open it). Regarding the options in the menu that should be improved on, this participant pointed to inconsistencies in the option 'Volume up/Volume down' (the volume would change directly from 0% to 100%) and in forwarding the video or moving it backward by means of video bar.

Overall, as in the RNIB test, the main aim was not to get results on a small sample but rather to test the methodology. In this regard, it is important in the cross-national pilots to find a way that the sample between those testing the voice interaction and the enhanced accessibility menu is balanced.

4.7. Cross-national pilot: player interface (RNIB)

The aim of this test was to test the voice control menu with blind users and the enhanced menu with partially sighted users. The full methodology is described in Annex 29 and the full report is found in Annex 30.

- **Users:** 31
- **Version:** 0.8, <http://imac.i2cat.net/voicetest>
- **Dates:** 05.11.2019-30.01.2020
- **Format:** face-to-face

4.7.1. Measures

The same measures as for the previous tests were used, namely usability (SUS) and preferences, with the following questions:

- What do you like most about the menu interaction?
- What do you like less?
- What do you think could be improved, and how?
- Other comments:

4.7.2. Participants

31 users from across the UK participated in the cross-national pilot. 9 of these 31 were partially sighted and 22 identified as blind. 14 were female and 17 males with ages ranging between 19 -73 years (mean age=42). 20 participants attended university and 11 had undertaken further education. With the exception of 3, all selected English as their native or main language. Other languages outlined were Punjabi, South Korean and German and English. TV, laptops, mobile phones, and tablets were the most frequently used devices with a few participants also identifying the following devices that they used frequently: ORCAM, Apple Watch, Braille reader, Braille note - Humanware, Bluetooth keyboard, Braille Display. In response to how often do they watch virtual reality content, most participants answered never with the exception of 9 who responded occasionally - 3 on a smartphone and 2 each on PC, smartphone plugged to an HMD and dedicated HMD. 11 participants reported sight loss from birth. On access technology, 7 participants reported using magnification to access content, 19 used screen readers, four used a combination of both for navigation and one who preferred not to answer or none.

4.7.3. Materials

The same materials as in the pre-pilot action 2 were used (see 4.5.3). Special care was taken to use the same type of quality headphones at UAB and RNIB.

4.7.4. Experimental protocol

The same experimental protocol as in the pre-pilot action 2 was followed. The only exception is that some commands were included: resume video, activate extended AD, switch-off extended AD, zoom features.

4.7.5. Results

31 participants took part in the test, but for technical reasons data from 7 participants could not be used. 15 participants tested the voice interaction. SUS scores were very positive, with a score of 82.67 and a letter grade A (percentile rank: 90-95%).

Figure 53: SUS score for voice interaction (cross-national, RNIB)

9 participants tested the enhanced menu. The SUS score was 93.33, which corresponds to A+ (percentile rank: 96-100%).

Figure 54: SUS score for enhanced menu (cross-national, RNIB)

As for the preference questions, they allowed to draw some conclusions on both systems. Whilst participants found the experience of using the ImAc player through voice interaction and enhance interface satisfactory and overall accessible, specific recommendations were put forth to improve the user experience.

Regarding voice interaction, most participants commented that the interaction with the ImAc player through Amazon Echo was accessible and easy to use. It is worth noting that most participants also admitted to either having tested an Echo previously or using Echo or another voice assistant like Google Home on a regular basis.

Anecdotal evidence also suggests that with both iOS and Android now supporting voice interaction through their native voice assistants (Siri and Google Home) and screen readers, growing number of blind and partially users are now accustomed to navigating connected services through voice. However, during the tests, most of the participants also expressed a strong interest in using other navigational mechanisms such as gestures/ swipes and tactile buttons for this experience.

Participants also expressed frustration with the need to use specific commands to trigger specific actions. It was widely acknowledged that this was characteristic of the way Echo or voice assistants in general were designed but participants felt that using conversational language instead of the suggested commands would vastly improve the experience.

Some participants also asked if using the same device could be used for consuming content and voice interaction. Example: using Siri to open and navigate BBC iPlayer in combination with VoiceOver.

However, it must be noted that even in view of the recommendations, using and navigating the ImAc player using Echo was popular among most participants who offered to test the player again if the changes they had suggested, particularly on the ability to use conversational language, were to be implemented.

Concerning the enhanced interface, generally, the experience was reported as accessible and easy to use. Even though recommendations were put forth by most testers, it would be useful to confirm these with a wider sample of users with low vision as these might closely relate to personal preferences and requirements for their level of sight. These recommendations included, for example, changing colour when you point towards the buttons, bigger sliding bar and bigger box of controls, using border around controls, etc. (see Annex for further details).

In addition, as expressed during the previous pilot actions, participants with severe sight loss expressed frustration with the need to wear VR headset which was considered unnecessary and cumbersome.

4.8. Cross-national pilot: player interface (UAB)

The aim of this test was to test the voice control menu with blind users and the enhanced menu with partially sighted users. The same methodology as in the UK pilot was followed (see Annex 29). The full report of results is found in Annex 31.

- **Users:** 30
Version: 0.8, http://imac.i2cat.net/voicetest_cat/
- **Dates:** January-February 2020
- **Format:** face-to-face

4.8.1. Measures

The same measures as for the UK test were used, namely usability (SUS) and preferences (see 4.7.1).

4.8.2. Participants

31 participants took part in the test, with ages ranging between 22-78 years (mean age=48.7). Their main languages were Catalan (7), Catalan/Spanish (7), Spanish (15), and Bulgarian/Spanish/Russian, English and Catalan (1). Most participants had university (20) or further education (7). 18 participants defined themselves as partially-sighted persons and 13 participants as blind persons. Participants taking part in the study reported starting losing sight from birth (10), between 0-4 years old (2), between 5-12 years old (5), between 13-20 years old (4), between 21-40 years old (2), 41-60 years old (5), more than 60 years old (3). When asked which technologies participants use on a daily basis, all participants reported using mobile phones (31), followed by television (21), laptop (14), PC (12) and tablet (9), which suggests that users are frequent users of technological devices. As far as immersive technologies are concerned, only one participant reported using head-mounted display on a daily basis, and most of the participants never watch VR reality content on smartphones (28), on a tablet (30), on a PC (30), in a smartphone plugged to HMD (29) or in HMD (28). Similarly, only 2 participants reported having a device to access VR content (PS4 and Play Station VR). As few as 3 participants reported watching immersive content occasionally (1) or every day (1) in a smartphone, on a tablet (every day – 1), on a PC (every day – 1), in a smartphone plugged to HMD (every day – 2) or in HMD (every day – 3). The most frequent reason behind not watching such content was not having had the chance to use it (21), followed by lack of accessibility (5) or interest (3). Regarding the level of interest in immersive content, most of participants were strongly interested (12) or interested (11), followed by a neutral attitude (“neither agree nor disagree” – 7), and only one participant chose option “strongly disagree”. The following question asked participants about their preferred type of content on television or online. Participants were also asked about how many hours a day they watch audio described content. In this question, 14 participants chose the option “none”, 10 participants “less than one hour”, 2 “1-2 hours”, 1 “2-3 hours”, 3 “3-4 hours” and 1 “4 hours or more”. In the last question, which asked about the devices that participants use to access online content, most of participants reported using screen readers (14), two participants reported using magnifiers, 8 participants chose option “both” and 8 “none”.

4.8.3. Materials

The same materials as in the UK test (see 4.7.3), adapted to Spanish in the voice interaction.

4.8.4. Experimental protocol

The same protocol as in the UK test was followed (see 4.7.4).

4.8.5. Results

31 participants took part in the test, but for technical reasons data from 3 participants could not be used. 19 participants tested the voice interaction. SUS scores were positive, with a score of 77.37, and a letter grade B+ (percentile rank: 80-84 %).

Figure 55: SUS score for voice interaction (cross-national, UAB)

9 participants tested the enhanced menu. The SUS score was 86.39, which corresponds to A+ (percentile rank: 96-100 %).

Figure 56: SUS score for enhanced menu (cross-national, UAB)

As for the preference questions, participants' responses show that the interaction was deemed: "practical", "easy", "comfortable", "useful" and "functional". Participants appreciated that they can interact by voice with the menu, without the need to use sight, and responsiveness of the device). One participant commented positively on the voice of Alexa, which sounds natural and not robot-like.

The second and third questions asked about what participants liked less and how the interaction with the menu can be improved. In these two questions, the comments indicate that many participants would prefer shorter commands, ideally without verb and with a wider variety of structures.

Regarding the participants who tested the enhanced accessibility menu, they deemed the interaction in their comments "practical", "intuitive", and "easy to use". Participants especially appreciated the possibility to adjust the menu to their needs, contrast and the fact that the menu can move according to user's head position. One partially-sighted participant did not finish the test with accessible menu because of weak contrast between the pointer (yellow) and the video (*Holy Land 4* takes place during daytime at the desert and seaside which are in light colours). In fact, one participant expressed their willingness to choose the colour and size of the pointer, and another one suggested that more separation between the buttons would be useful.

4.9. Conclusions

Regarding the user interface testing with persons with hearing loss, SUS scores differ for HMD and tablet, especially at CCMA. Figure 57 summarises the results for pilot phase 1 and Figure 58 summarises the results for pre-pilot 2 actions.

Figure 57: SUS scores: pilot phase 1

Figure 58: SUS scores: pre-pilot 2

The player interface has evolved along the project development to include new features and functionalities. All tests performed on an HMD show that all versions of the player are assessed by users both in Germany and Spain with a value above average in the SUS score, ranging from 68.8 (CCMA, first iteration) to 77.3 (RBB, first iteration). Concerning the same user interface on a tablet, results range from 63.96 (RBB, second iteration), to 86.25 (CCMA, second iteration). In any case, the values obtained are one A+, one A, one B+, two B, two C and 1 C-, most of them above average.

Comparing the SUS results of the different iterations and locations is not feasible for different reasons. Demographics vary across pilot actions: for instance, RBB users from pre-pilot 1 were older (M=47) than participants from pre-pilot 2 (M=39). Additionally, qualitative questions were not the same in one pilot and the other and some features may have had a big impact on the results, such as the feature to activate/deactivate subtitles or setting the language. It has also been observed that some users felt uncomfortable with the HMD and suggested improvements related to HMD, rather than the player interface. Therefore, even if it was stressed that the usability testing referred to the player, it may well be that they also considered the HMD experience.

The drop in tablet assessment at RBB (from B to C), and also the fact that the tablet was not preferred by RBB's user group, may be explained by the fact that the users did not see the changes immediately and reacted negatively to it. In other words, when users enabled the subtitles, they were confused because subtitles did not appear immediately, and closing the menu to see the settings' changes was considered cumbersome. Additionally, the fact that users were not familiar with the icons selected and abbreviations were not included had probably an impact in the results. In any case, these aspects have been further discussed within the consortium after the tests to provide a more suitable player interface in the final open pilot.

Beyond quantitative usability data, the aim of such pilot actions was to gather valuable qualitative input on the functionalities that had been developed such as the indicator, the setting "area", personalisation options, pointer features, activation/deactivation options, language settings, menu opening option, subtitle obstruction in the preview function, and icon identification.

Overall, users with hearing loss are attracted by the technology and show interest, providing valuable feedback that can help improve ImAc player. The player was generally praised for its simplicity.

Regarding the user interface testing with persons with sight loss, it should be stressed that in the first action the aim was to test the methodology and checked it was fit for the cross-national pilots. It was observed that care should be taken to balance participants across conditions, as in the pre-pilot actions 2 this proved challenging and most participants preferred to test the voice interaction menu. Despite the reduced sample due to the nature of the aim of this action, the results on the voice interaction showed promising results, with scores above average: 78.13 (B+) in English in the UK and 71.88 in Spanish in Spain.

In the cross-national pilot both at UAB and RNIB the results were extremely positive, with high values in both voice interaction and enhanced accessibility menu, as shown in Figure 59.

Figure 59: SUS scores: cross-national (RNIB & UAB)

5. TESTING THE SUBTITLING PRESENTATION MODES

Presentation modes for subtitling have been tested in ImAc at different moments (see Table 3 for a whole list and Figure 8 for testing conditions):

- During development:
 - Pre-pilot 1 actions, both at CCMA and RBB (see D2.1), with persons with hearing loss 8.
 - Pilot phase 1, both at CCMA and RBB, with persons with hearing loss.
 - Pre-pilot 2 actions, both at CCMA and RBB, with persons with hearing loss.
 - Intermediate / pre-pilot 2 actions at UAB, with persons with and without hearing loss.
 - Pre-pilot 2 action at UAB on easy-to-read subtitling.
- Once user requirements have been implemented, in the final implementation phase:
 - Pilot phase 2 at RBB and CCMA.

The presentation modes tests were performed with the same users that tested the player interface, during the same testing session. Results are presented separately per stage and keeping always the following structure:

- General description of the pilot action: users, version, dates and format.
- Measures used, based on framework presented in Figures 12 and 13. If an *ad-hoc* preference questionnaire is used, it is reproduced in this section.
- Participants' description, summarising the data obtained through the demographic questionnaires. Given that we are within the realm of media accessibility, it was decided to take a wider approach to testing and use different user profiles who claim using subtitles.
- Materials, presenting the different materials and content used for the tests.
- The experimental protocol, which follows the general framework in Figure 14.
- Results, with a discussion of the main results of the pilot action. More specific details, with a thorough reproduction of all replies, are included in the full reports in the annexes.

The full methodology and reports are available as Annexes. These full reports include data both for subtitling presentation modes and interface, which are here presented separately here and in a summarised version for easier understanding.

5.1. CCMA pilot phase 1

The main features of the subtitling pilot action at CCMA are summarized next:

- **Users:** home users
- **Dates:** 1/10/2018, 16-19/10/2018
- **Format:** face-to-face

The test aimed to compare two guiding mechanisms, namely arrow (Figure 60) and radar (Figure 61).

Figure 60: Subtitle with arrows

Figure 61: Subtitle with radar

5.1.1. Measures

The subtitling presentation mode test focused on two measures: presence and preferences. For presence, IPQ was used, in its translated version into Catalan. For preferences, the same questionnaire as for RBB was used, translated into Catalan. It is reproduced in its English version again for easier access:

- When directions need to be indicated, what system do you prefer? Arrow/Radar.
- Please explain why you prefer the above-indicated option.
- Please explain why you did not choose the other option in question 1.
- What do you think could be improved, and how?
- Would you implement another system to guide you to the user?
- How easy was to identify who was speaking on the clip with the arrow system? (1-5 Likert scale, 1= very difficult, 5= very easy)

- How easy was to identify who was speaking on the clip with the radar system? (1-5 Likert scale, 1= very difficult, 5= very easy)
- Do you think you will be able to enjoy 360° videos with this type of subtitles? Explain your answer.

5.1.2. Participants

13 users, the same participants as for the user interface test, took part in this test. See section 4.1.2. for further details on the characteristics of the participants.

5.1.3. Materials

Since the pilot actions at RBB and CCMA followed the same methodological approach, the same film was used, in this case the short science fiction film *I, Philip*, cut in two excerpts (first clip from 00:30 to 06:29 [5:59 minutes] and second clip from 06:29 to 12:26 [5:57 minutes]). For the Catalan pilot, the English short film was subtitled into Catalan, and two versions were created: Catalan subtitles with arrow, and Catalan subtitles with radar. Therefore, the stimuli for the tests were:

I, Philip, part 1, subtitled in Catalan, with arrow = Clip A1-CA.

I, Philip, part 1, subtitled in Catalan, with radar= Clip A2- CA.

I, Philip, part 2, subtitled in Catalan, with arrow= Clip B1- CA.

I, Philip, part 2, subtitled in Catalan, with radar= Clip B2- CA.

The test was performed on an HMD and the clips were available on the ImAc player.

Regarding the length of the clips, as with any other test in the ImAc project, various factors were considered: first of all, very long clips would produce a tiresome effect on the users, who could react negatively to a long experimental procedure. Secondly, previous tests in which presence in virtual reality has been tested usually use clips which are 1-2 minutes long [7] [8]. Finally, typical 360° clips tend to be short compared to traditional cinematic narrative content such as films or series. The average duration is from five to ten minutes [9] [10] [11]. According to a corpus study performed within the ImAc project on virtual reality content from *The New York Times* and BBC the typical duration varies from two to four minutes [12].

Demographic questionnaire, IPQ questionnaire and preference questionnaire in Catalan were also prepared in online forms.

5.1.4. Experimental protocol

The experimental protocol is exactly the same as for the German pilot. It is reproduced next for easier access:

- Participants are welcomed and ImAc project and test is presented (face-to-face).
- Ethical clearance: participants sign informed consent forms (paper copies).
- Participants fill in a demographic questionnaire (online).
- Pilot action part 1: user interface. See 4.1.4 for details.
- Pilot action part 2: presentation modes. Participants are requested to watch two clips, one in which the arrow is implemented and one in which the radar is implemented. Order of presentation of arrow/radar is randomised across participants, but the clip always follows a chronological order because otherwise the action could not be understood.

- Participants watch clip 1.
- Participants watch clip 2.
- After watching each clip, participants are administered the IPQ questionnaire.
- After watching both clips, participants are asked a preference and general feedback questionnaire.
- Participants are thanked.

5.1.5. Results

Results are presented for the presence questionnaire and for the preference open questions posed at the end.

Table 7 presents median values for the comparison of arrow versus radar per each scale through the IPQ questionnaire, which measures spatial presence, involvement and experienced realism.

Presentation mode	General presence	Spatial presence	Involvement	Experienced realism
Arrow	6	5.60	4.00	3.50
Radar	6	5.80	4.75	3.50

Table 7: Comparison of arrow versus radar (CCMA)

Statistical analysis shows the following results:

- A Wilcoxon Signed-Ranks test indicated that the ranks of Arrow and Radar for Spatial Presence scale are not statistically different ($Z=36.5, p=.094$)
- A Wilcoxon Signed-Ranks test indicated that the ranks of Arrow and Radar for Involvement scale are not statistically different ($Z=22, p=.952$)
- A Wilcoxon Signed-Ranks test indicated that the ranks of Arrow and Radar for Experienced Realism scale are not statistically different ($Z=28.5, p=.918$)

Therefore, no significant differences between the arrow and the radar were found, meaning that none of these presentation modes has a negative impact on presence.

Concerning preferences, most users (9=69.23%) preferred the arrow indicator, as it is simple and easy to understand. However, some users (4=30.76%) showed more interest in the radar, as this allows them to have much more accurate information about the position of the speakers.

Users felt that the radar was too big and interfered when trying to enjoy the video, but they agreed it is quite interesting to use this indicator, and some improvements in the design would definitely help. Some users proposed improvements which were contrasted with the interviewers through the help of hand-painted graphs on a blackboard.

When asked on a 5-point Likert scale (1= very difficult, 5= very easy) how easy it was to identify the speaker with the arrow or the radar system, results are the following: the arrow (M=4) is considered easier than the radar (M=3.69). For the arrow, 6 participants (46.15%) gave a score of 5, 3 participants (23.09%) gave a score of 4, 2 participants (15.38%) gave a score of 3, and 2 participants (15.38%) gave a score of 2. For the radar, 5 participants (38.46%) gave a score of 5, 2 participants (15.38%) gave a score of 4, 3 participants (23.08%) gave a score of 3, and 3 participants (23.08%) gave a score of 2.

When asked if they would implement another system to guide them to the speaker, most participants did not make any suggestions as they were happy with either the arrow or the radar.

All in all, all users were really interested in ImAc subtitles implementation for immersive 360° contents; they felt very satisfied with the first results and expressed a great desire to collaborate in the future developments through the contribution of ideas.

5.2. RBB pilot phase 1

The main features of the subtitling pilot action are summarised next:

- **Users:** home users
- **Dates:** 27-28/09/2018, 15-19/10/2018
- **Format:** face-to-face

The same conditions as in the Catalan pilot were tested: arrow versus radar as guiding mechanisms.

Figure 62: Subtitle with arrows

Figure 63: Subtitle with radar

5.2.1. Measures

The subtitling presentation mode test focused on two measures: presence and preferences, as in the CCMA action. Presence was prioritised as the aim was to elicit if any of the two presentations modes guaranteed a higher immersion, which is one of the goals a 360° video aims to achieve.

For presence, IPQ was used. For preferences, a specific questionnaire with the following questions was developed:

- When directions need to be indicated, what system do you prefer? Arrow/Radar.
- Please explain why you prefer the above-indicated option.
- Please explain why you did not choose the other option in question 1.
- What do you think could be improved, and how?
- Would you implement another system to guide you to the user?
- How easy was to identify who was speaking on the clip with the arrow system? (1-5 Likert scale, 1= very difficult, 5= very easy) [13]
- How easy was to identify who was speaking on the clip with the radar system? (1-5 Likert scale, 1= very difficult, 5= very easy)
- Do you think you will be able to enjoy 360° videos with this type of subtitles? Explain your answer.

5.2.2. Participants

12 users, the same as in the user interface action, started the test. See section 4.2.2 for a thorough description of the users. However, data from all users could not be gathered for all questionnaires.

Regarding the presence IPQ questionnaire, data from only 10 participants were gathered because there were technical problems with the data from one user (RBB10) and another user felt uncomfortable and did not watch the videos on the HMD (RBB11). Concerning the preference questionnaire, data from participant RBB10 was also lost due to technical problems and data from participant RBB11 was based on the videos watched in the usability test. Although she/he did not undergo the same experimental conditions, data are included as they are mainly report on preferences and future suggestions.

5.2.3. Materials

For the presentation mode test, the short film *I, Philip*, cut in two excerpts, was used, as in the CCMA pilot. The plot of the short film is as follows: 23 years after Philip K. Dick's death, in 2005, David Hanson, a young engineer in robotics, revealed his first android with human form, "Phil". *I, Philip* immerses the audience in the memories of what could be the last love affair of the writer. It may well be, though, that these memories are the fruit of the imagination of an android which has learned, little by little, how to become a human.

This sci-fi drama whose original language is English was subtitled into German, and two versions were created: German subtitles with arrow, and German subtitles with radar. Therefore, the stimuli for the tests were:

I, Philip, part 1, subtitled in German, with arrow = Clip A1-GER.

I, Philip, part 1, subtitled in German, with radar= Clip A2-GER.

I, Philip, part 2, subtitled in German, with arrow= Clip B1-GER.

I, Philip, part 2, subtitled in German, with radar= Clip B2-GER.

The test was performed on an HMD and the clips were available on the ImAc player.

Demographic questionnaire, IPQ questionnaire and preference questionnaire in German were also prepared in online forms.

5.2.4. Experimental protocol

The experimental protocol followed the general framework established for all pilot actions. It was identical for both CCMA and RBB test. It was first tested in a pilot test, improved, and then implemented as follows:

- Participants are welcomed and ImAc project and test is presented (face-to-face)
- Ethical clearance: participants sign informed consent forms (paper copies)
- Participants fill in a demographic questionnaire (online).
- Pilot action part 1: user interface. See 4.2.4 for details.
- Pilot action part 2: presentation modes. Participants are requested to watch two clips, one in which the arrow is implemented and one in which the radar is implemented. Order of presentation of arrow/radar is randomised across participants, but the clip always follows a chronological order because otherwise the action could not be understood.
 - Participants watch clip 1
 - Participants watch clip 2
- After watching each clip, participants are administered the IPQ questionnaire
- After watching both clips, participants are administered a preference questionnaire.
- Participants are thanked

5.2.5. Results

Results are presented for the presence questionnaire and for the preference open questions posed at the end. Regarding presence, it was measured through the IPQ questionnaire, which provides results concerning spatial presence, involvement and experienced realism. Spatial presence refers to the sense of being physically present in the virtual environment. Involvement measures the attention devoted to the virtual environment. Experience realism measures the subjective experience of realism in the virtual environment. The IPQ questionnaire features a 1 to 7 scale. Table 8 presents median values for the comparison of arrow versus radar per each scale.

Presentation mode	General presence	Spatial presence	Involvement	Experienced realism
Arrow	7	4.70	3.37	3.62
Radar	7	5.30	2.62	3.87

Table 8: Comparison of arrow versus radar (RBB)

Statistical analysis shows the following results:

- A Wilcoxon Signed-Ranks test [14] indicated that the ranks of Arrow and Radar for Spatial Presence scale are not statistically different ($Z=21, p=.858$)
- A Wilcoxon Signed-Ranks test indicated that the ranks of Arrow and Radar for Involvement scale are not statistically different ($Z=3.5, p=.276$)
- A Wilcoxon Signed-Ranks test indicated that the ranks of Arrow and Radar for Experienced Realism scale are not statistically different ($Z=12.5, p=.799$)

The p value shows the significance level of the test. It should be smaller than 0.05 for the differences to reach significance. Z is the statistics used in the Related-Samples Wilcoxon Signed-Ranks Test. This test assessed whether the distribution of two paired variables in two related samples is the same.

No significant difference in terms of presence between the arrow and the radar were found.

Concerning preferences, most of the users (8=72.73%) preferred the arrow because it was immediately clear and easy to understand. Those few users who preferred the radar (3=27.27%) liked it because it gave them a good overview and found it especially suitable for many speakers at the same time.

Most of the testers did not like the radar because it was not intuitive, and it was visually disturbing. Those who did not like the arrow argued that it was not precise enough when more than two speakers were present.

Regarding suggested improvements, two users (18.18%) asked for a better way to understand that an off-voice is speaking. A few testers found it difficult to follow fast conversations and suggested that either the arrow is displayed before a person starts speaking or that the field of view can be enlarged in order to have a better overview. One user (9.9%) asked for a drag/drop function for the radar to move it away in case it obscures the video. One user had the idea to also display the depth of speakers in the radar (at least relative to each other).

There were two ideas for other guiding mechanisms: indicating the speaker position via audio (3D audio) and showing an arrow above the speakers (similar to football analysis videos). The rest of the participants (8= 72.73%) did not have any suggestions, in one case because s/he found the arrow ideal and, in another case, because this environment was considered very new.

When asked on a 5-point Likert scale (1= very difficult, 5= very easy) how easy it was to identify the speaker with the arrow or the radar system, results are the following: the arrow ($M=3.64$) is considered easier than the radar ($M=3.1$). 6 participants (54.4%) select 4 or 5 for the arrow, whilst for the radar only 4 (36.37%) select these values.

Regarding enjoyment, most users (7= 63.63%) thought they could enjoy 360° videos with subtitles but not too often and depending on the content. A few users found the HMD uncomfortable or not technically satisfying.

5.3. CCMA pre-pilot 2 action

The main features of the subtitling pre-pilot 2 action are summarized next:

- **Users:** 12 home users
- **Dates:** 13.05.2019-06.06.2019
- **Format:** face-to-face

The aim of the action was to gather user feed-back on:

- subtitle positioning: always visible with arrow (Figure 64) versus fixed positioned with arrow (Figure 65), and

Figure 64: Always visible with arrow (Catalan)

Figure 65: Fixed positioned with arrow (Catalan)

- non-speech sound representation: emojis (Figure 66) versus text (Figure 67).

Figure 66: Non-speech information - emoji (Catalan)

Figure 67: Non-speech information - text (Catalan)

5.3.1. Measures

The measures chosen were presence and preferences for the positioning test. For the sound representation test through text or emojis preferences were chosen as a measure. For presence, IPQ was used. For preferences, a specific questionnaire was developed for each task.

Task on positioning:

- What system do you prefer for subtitles? Always visible with arrow. Fixed positioned with arrow.
- Please explain why you prefer the above indicated option.
- Please explain why you did not choose the other option in question (1)
- What do you think could be improved, and how?
- How easy was it to read the subtitles in option a/option b? 1-7 Likert scale (Very difficult-Very easy).
- How easy was to find the subtitles in option a/option b? 1-7 Likert scale (Very difficult-Very easy).
- How easy was to find the speaker in option a/option b? 1-7 Likert scale (Very difficult-Very easy).

- Did you like the blinking effect in the arrows? Yes/No.
- Other comments.

Task on sound representation:

- What system do you prefer for sound representation? Emoji/Text
- Please explain why you prefer the above indicated option.
- Please explain why you did not choose the other option in question (1).
- What do you think could be improved, and how?
- How easy was it to understand the representations of sound with emojis/text? 1-7 Likert scale (Very difficult-Very easy)
- How easy was it to imagine the the sound represented by emojis/text? 1-7 Likert scale (Very difficult-Very easy)
- Did the text representation/emojis representation for sound break your immersion in the story? Yes/No

5.3.2. Participants

The same users that took the user interface test participated in the presentation modes test. Their profile is described under 4.3.2

5.3.3. Materials

I, Philip, a science fiction short clip in English subtitled by CCMA in Catalan, was used for the tests on presentation modes. Different clips were chosen depending on the task. For the subtitling positioning task, it was split in two parts (Part 1 and Part 2). For the task on sound representation, selected snippets where sound was relevant and could be represented with emojis were chosen: Clip 1 and Clip 2, as indicated next.

Clip 1 (Total timecode: 00:01:50.02 - 00:06:30.11)

Scene Name	Timecode of scene	Emoji (C1)	Text (C2)	TC In	TC out
Introduction	00:01:50.02 - 00:02:56.17	😄	U+1F603 *Laughs*	00:02:36.12	00:02:38.12
Auditorium	00:02:56.18 - 00:05:21.15	👏	U+1F44F, U+1F3FC *Applause*	00:03:11.22	00:03:15.00
		😄	U+1F603 *Laughing*	00:05:00.04	00:05:01.01
Hospital	00:05:21.16 - 00:06:30.11	👣	U+1F463 *Steps*	00:05:53.00	00:06:01.06

Clip 2 (Total timecode: 00:06:30.12 - 00:10:15.00)

Scene Name	Timecode of scene	Emoji (D1)	Text (D2)	TC In	TC out
Interview	00:06:30.12 - 00:08:12.07	📞	U+1F4F3 *Phone vibrating*	00:07:09.22	00:07:11.05
		😄	U+1F603 *Laughs*	00:07:13.11	00:07:14.11
Beach	00:08:12.08 - 00:08:27.06	🌊	U+1F30A *Ocean waves*	00:08:12.22	00:08:16.22
		🎵	U+1F3B6 *Music*	00:08:16.24	00:08:20.24
Hallway	00:08:27.07 - 00:10:15.00	👣	U+1F463 *Steps*	00:10:01.18	00:10:05.18
		🔊	U+1F50C, U+26A1 *Loud noise*	00:10:12.03	00:10:14.14

Table 9: Clips used in pre-pilot 2 actions (CCMA & RBB)

Demographic questionnaires, IPQ questionnaire and preference questionnaires in Catalan were also prepared as online forms.

5.3.4. Experimental protocol

The experimental protocol developed as follows:

- Participants are welcomed and ImAc project and test is presented (face-to-face)
- Ethical clearance: participants sign informed consent forms (paper copies)
- Participants fill in a demographic questionnaire (online)
- User interface pilot action See 4.3
- Presentation modes: task 1 (subtitle positioning). Participants are requested to watch the two *I, Philip* clips, with two positioning systems. Order of presentation of the positioning system is randomised across participants, but the clip always follows a chronological order because otherwise the action could not be understood.
 - Participants watch clip 1
 - Participants watch clip 2
- After watching each clip, participants are administered the IPQ questionnaire
- After watching both clips, participants are administered a preference questionnaire
- Presentation modes: task 2 (non-speech information representation). Participants watch two snippets with emojis and text. The order of presentation is randomised across participants and conditions.
- After watching both clips, participants are administered a preference questionnaire
- Participants are thanked

5.3.5. Results

Concerning the positioning system, the comparison of each of the subscales of IPQ questionnaire through a related samples Wilcoxon signed test does not show any significant difference between the two conditions (General presence $Z=-.535$, $p= .592$, ties=9; Spatial presence $Z=-.479$, $p=.632$, ties=3; Involvement $Z=-.724$, $p=.469$, ties=3; Experienced realism $Z=-.178$, $p= .859$, ties=3)

	General Presence	Spatial Presence	Involvement	Experienced Realism
Always Visible	6	5.4	3.88	3.50
Fixed Position	5.50	5.2	3.88	3.50

Table 10: Median values obtained in IPQ questionnaire: always visible with arrow vs fixed positioned with arrow (CCMA)

In terms of preferences, 10 users out of 12 (83.3%) prefer the always visible with arrow, the reasons being mainly related to the fact that they do not miss the content because they know who is speaking and where to look at, feeling “as if I hear normally”. As one participant put it, “in the real world, if a person is speaking and I do not look at him, I cannot get the information. I always want to get all information even I do not look at who is speaking”. Fixed positioned subtitles, on the contrary, forces to move the head repeatedly in order to follow the information. The two users who prefer fixed position indicate that in this way, each speaker has its own voice and subtitles are easier to read. In terms of improvements, they suggest

aspects related to the subtitling features (more information, music, noises, colour, etc.) and to the device (“HMD devices should be improved”), but they also make some comments on the object of study related to size and position of the subtitles. They also mention that, if two characters are close, the subtitles of one of them are not shown.

When asked how easy it was to read the subtitles, always visible with arrow are assessed with the maximum values (50% choose 6 and 50% choose 7 on a 7-point Likert scale), whilst in the fixed positioned mode the replies are more varied, ranging from 7 to 3. Still, 50% of the participants give a 7 to this system.

When asked how easy it was to find the subtitles, always visible with arrows is considered very easy (all users select either 6 or 7 on a 7-point Likert scales), whereas again the fixed positioned mode gets less consistent results, ranging from 7 (25%) to 2 (12.5%).

When asked how easy it was to find the speaker, always visible subtitles with arrow get better results.

	1 very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7 very easy	Mean	SD	Median
1. How easy was it to read the subtitles in “Always visible with arrow” mode?	-	-	-	-	-	6 50%	6 50%	6.5	0.52	6.5
2. How easy was it to read the subtitles in “Fixed positioned with arrow” mode?	2 16.66%	-	2 6.66%	1 8.33%	-	1 8.33%	6 50%	5	2.45	6.5
3. How easy was it to find the subtitles in “Always visible with arrow” mode?	-	-	-	-	-	4 33.33%	8 66.67%	6.67	0.5	7
4. How easy was it to find the subtitles in “Fixed positioned with arrow” mode?	1 8.33%	2 16.66%	1 8.33%	1 8.33%	-	3 25%	4 33.33%	4.83	2.3	6
5. How easy was it to find the speaker in “Always visible with arrow” mode?	-	-	1 8.33%	-	-	5 41.66%	6 50%	6.25	1.14	6.5
6. How easy was it to find the speaker in “Fixed positioned with arrow” mode?	-	2 16.66%	-	1 8.33%	-	4 33.33%	5 41.66%	5.58	1.9	6

7. How easy was it to understand the representations of sound with emojis?	-	1 8.33%	2 16.66%	1 8.33%	-	3 25%	5 41.66%	5.42	1.9	6
8. How easy was it to understand the representations of sound with text?	-	-	-	-	2 16.66%	1 8.33%	9 75%	6.58	0.8	7
9. How easy was to imagine the sound represented by emojis?	-	2 16.66%	1 8.33%	-	2 16.66%	3 25%	4 33.33%	5.25	1.9	6
10. How easy was to imagine the sound represented by the text?	-	-	-	-	2 16.66%	1 8.33%	9 75%	6.58	0.8	7

Table 11: Results pre-pilot 2 action– Likert scales (CCMA)

Regarding the blinking effect in the arrows, most users liked it (75%) although there was one user who did not even notice, which is a positive aspect, as the mechanisms are aimed at not breaking the immersion in the story. One user suggested including the arrow indicator before related text, and another one suggested to put subtitles in a lower position to avoid covering the scene. In any case, one user expressed that “I think it is great!”

Concerning sound representation, 10 users out of 12 (83.3%) prefer the textual representation because they understand the text better or they are used to text. Some of them even report emojis as being “for kids” and not so serious, an aspect which in fact is assessed positively by one of the users who is in favour of emojis (“It is more fun”). Other reasons for not liking emojis are related to the type of content, the lack of accuracy, the simplicity and the confusion they can create. Users suggested some improvements, related to the lack of arrow indicators in some instances but some of them just thought “it is perfect” or did not actually know what improvements could be made. When asked how easy it was to understand the representations with the two systems on a 7-point Likert scale, 5 users selected 7 (very easy) but the other replies were scattered on the scale, with 1 user selecting a 2 and 2 users selecting a 3, below average. On the contrary, textual representations were considered “very easy” by 9 users (75%). When asked how easy it was to imagine the sound represented by emojis, a similar pattern emerges: text proves very easy (2 users select 5, one user selects 6 and 9 users select 7), whilst emojis prove more difficult (2 select 2, 1 selects 3, 2 select 5, 3 select 6 and 4 select 7). Users think that the text representation does not break their immersion (11 users), but 50% think that emojis break their immersion in the story. In conclusion, emojis are not welcomed by the users and age can be a factor in attributing meaning to them.

5.4. RBB pre-pilot 2 action

The main features of the subtitling pre-pilot 2 action are summarised next:

- **Users:** 12 users.
- **Dates:** May-June 2019.
- **Format:** face-to-face.

The aim was the same as for the CCMA action, as the same test was replicated, changing only the language of the stimuli.

5.4.1. Measures

The same measures that were used for the CCMA test were used for the RBB test, see 5.3.1.

5.4.2. Participants

The same users that took the user interface test participated in the presentation modes test. Their profile is described under 4.4.2

5.4.3. Materials

Both CCMA and RBB used the same materials, the only difference being that at RBB they were translated into German and a specific online form system was used. Please refer to 5.3.3. and, more specifically, Table 9.

5.4.4. Experimental protocol

The same experimental design that was used for the CCMA test was used for the RBB test, the only difference being that German was the language of communication. Please refer 5.3.4

5.4.5. Results

Concerning the positioning system, the comparison of each of the subscales of IPQ questionnaire through a related samples Wilcoxon signed test does not show any significant difference between the two conditions (General presence $Z=-1.186$, $p= .236$, ties=5; Spatial presence $Z=-.358$, $p=.721$, ties=0; Involvement $Z=-1.162$, $p=.245$, ties=0; Experienced realism $Z=-.848$, $p= .396$, ties=4).

	General Presence	Spatial Presence	Involvement	Experienced Realism
Always Visible	6	3.60	4.25	3.50
Fixed Position	5	3.44	4	3.25

Table 12: Median values obtained in IPQ: always visible with arrow vs fixed positioned with arrow (RBB)

In terms of preferences, 9 users out of 12 (75%) prefer the always visible with arrow, the reasons being mainly related to the fact that they do not miss content as they allow the user to look wherever they want and “listen” to content and they are always available. The very fast change of the position of the subtitles from the bottom (off-speaker) to the speaker was very exhausting for their eyes. On the contrary, one user considers that in fixed positioned subtitles are more integrated and intuitive, one user thinks it is more like real life, and another one considers that it is easier to identify the speaker. Additionally, the fixed subtitles are easier to read and do not flicker as it is the case for the always visible subtitles when the user moves the head fast. They liked the colours of the arrow in the fixed subtitles as this helps to identify the speaker and as soon as the user knows which speaker is where, it is easy to move the head in the right direction. Some recommendations were made in relation to the viewing angle, the position of the subtitles (off-speaker subtitles were placed too far at the bottom), the quality of the video and some flickering problems with the subtitles. Overall, the content, the speed of a conversation and the position of the speaker in the field of view are important aspects for the choice between fixed or always visible subtitles. One user explicitly stated that a combination of both modes would be good. Table 13 presents a summary of the results, where always visible with arrow mode subtitles are better valued than the fixed positioned with arrow mode.

	1 very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7 very easy	Mean	SD	Median
1. How easy was it to read the subtitles in "Always visible with arrow" mode?	-	-	2 18.2%	-	1 9.1%	-	8 72.7%	6.09	1.64	7
2. How easy was it to read the subtitles in "Fixed positioned with arrow" mode?	1 9.1%	2 18.2%	1 9.1%	-	4 36.3%	2 18.2%	1 9.1%	4.27	1.95	5
3. How easy was it to find the subtitles in "Always visible with arrow" mode?	-	1 9.1%	-	-	1 9.1%	3 27.2%	6 54.6%	6.09	1.51	7
4. How easy was it to find the subtitles in "Fixed positioned with arrow" mode?	3 27.2%	2 18.2%	2 18.2%	-	2 18.2%	2 18.2%	-	3.18	1.99	3
5. How easy was it to find the speaker in "Always visible with arrow" mode?	2 18.2%	1 9.1%	2 18.2%	-	2 18.2%	1 9.1%	3 27.2%	4.27	2.37	5
6. How easy was it to find the speaker in "Fixed positioned with arrow" mode?	2 18.2%	2 18.2%	2 18.2%	1 9.1%	1 9.1%	2 18.2%	1 9.1%	3.63	2.11	3
7. How easy was it to understand the representations of sound with emojis?	-	-	2 18.2%	1 9.1%	2 18.2%	-	6 54.54%	5.64	1.69	7
8. How easy was it to understand the representations of sound with text?	-	-	-	1 9.1%	-	2 18.2%	8 72.72%	6.54	0.93	7
9. How easy was to imagine the sound represented by emojis?	1 9.1%	3 27.2%	3 27.2%	-	-	1 9.1%	3 27.2%	3.91	2.34	3
10. How easy was to imagine the sound represented by the text?	-	-	2 18.2%	-	-	3 27.2%	6 54.54%	6	1.55	7

Table 13: Results pre-pilot action 2– Likert scales (RBB)

Regarding the blinking effect in the arrows, the question was only posed to 9 users for a technical problem, and most of them liked it (7 out of 9).

Concerning sound representation, only 8 participants replied to this question due to technical problems. There was unanimity in selecting the textual representation of sound (100% of the participants), as it was considered they broke the immersion in the story (62%). The description of sound with text enables more comprehensive and precise information. The interpretation of emojis is very different from user to user and it takes more time to understand the meaning. Table 13 shows that the representation of sound is easier to understand and imagine in terms of mean value (questions 7-10).

5.5. UAB intermediate / pre-pilot 2 actions

UAB carried out two intermediate/pre-pilot actions on subtitling presentation modes. The aim of the first action was to test the methodology and the presentation modes to verify that they were ready enough to be tested with a larger group of users. The information about this action is as follows:

- **Users:** 8 home users (6 hearing and 2 deaf/HoH participants)
- **Dates:** 22.11.2018-28.11.2018
- **Format:** face-to-face

As it will be explained below, results of the previous action compelled us to slightly modify the testing conditions. The information about the main action is as follows:

- **Users:** 40 home users (20 hearing and 20 HoH participants)
- **Dates:** 13.03.2019-24.04.2019
- **Format:** face-to-face

The aim of the action was to gather user feedback on:

- Subtitle positioning: always visible (Figure 68) versus fixed positioned every 120^º (Figure 69), and guiding mechanisms: arrow (Figure 70) versus radar (Figure 71).

Figure 68: Always visible (Spanish)

Figure 69: Fixed positioned every 120° (Spanish)

Figure 70: Arrow (Spanish)

Figure 71: Radar (Spanish)

5.5.1. Measures

The measures chosen were presence and preferences for positioning and guiding mechanisms. For presence, IPQ was used. For preferences, a specific questionnaire was developed for each task. An analysis tool for tracking head movements (CVR Analyze [15]) was also included in the experiments. The head movements were analysed (not eye movements, since no eye-tracking equipment is available for the test) to see if a movement pattern could be identified that could be linked to each specific variable.

Adhoc preference questionnaire - Task on positioning:

1. What system do you prefer to read subtitles in 360° videos?
a) Always visible b) Fixed positioned
2. Please, explain why you prefer the above indicated option.
3. What do you think could be improved, and how?
4. Did you find it easy to find the always visible subtitles? (1 to 7 scale, where 1= very difficult and 7 = very easy).
5. Did you find it easy to find the fixed positioned subtitles? (1 to 7 scale, where 1= very difficult and 7 = very easy).
6. Did you find it easy to read the always visible subtitles? (1 to 7 scale, where 1= very difficult and 7 = very easy).
7. Did you find it easy to read the fixed positioned subtitles? (1 to 7 scale, where 1= very difficult and 7 = very easy).
8. Do you think always visible subtitles obstruct important parts of the image? (1 to 7 scale, where 1= yes, very much and 7 = not at all).
9. Do you think fixed positioned subtitles obstruct important parts of the image? (1 to 7 scale, where 1= yes, very much and 7 = not at all).
10. Do you think that always visible subtitles distract you from the video? (1 to 7 scale, where 1= yes, very much and 7 = not at all).
11. Do you think that fixed positioned subtitles distract you from the video? (1 to 7 scale, where 1= yes, very much and 7 = not at all).
12. Other comments:

Ad-hoc preference questionnaire - Task on guiding mechanisms:

1. Which system do you prefer to indicate the location of the character speaking?
a) Arrow b) Radar
2. Please, explain why you prefer the above-indicated option.
3. What do you think could be improved, and how?
4. Did you find it easy to find the person who speaks with the arrows? (1 to 7 scale, where 1= very difficult and 7 = very easy).
5. Did you find it easy to find the person who speaks with the radar? (1 to 7 scale, where 1= very difficult and 7 = very easy).
6. Did the arrows seem to distract you from what was happening in the video? (1 to 7 scale, where 1= yes, very much and 7 = not at all).

7. Did the radar seem to distract you from what was happening in the video? (1 to 7 scale, where 1= yes, very much and 7 = not at all).

8. Other comments:

5.5.2. Participants

14 male and 26 female users aged between 18 and 70 took part in the tests (sd=14.8, mean=37.4, median=37). 31 users indicated Spanish as main language, 8 indicated Valencian and 3 indicated Catalan. 15 users had university studies, 10 had further education, 8 had secondary education and 7 had primary education. 27 testers defined themselves as hearing, 6 as hearing-impaired and 7 as deaf (although 20 were identified as hard-of-hearing and 20 as hearing [which can be confirmed by the replies of the following question “Age in which your disability began”, which 20 hard-of-hearing users replied accordingly], but this question was subjective; some people with hearing aids considered themselves as hearing). For 2 users the disability started from birth, for 1 user it began from 0 to 4 years old, for 5 users from 5 to 12 years old, for 5 users from 13 to 20 years old, for 5 users from 21 to 40 years old and for 2 users from 41 to 60 years old.

The technical devices that were most often used on a daily basis were mobile phone (38), TV (31), laptop (20), PC (13), tablet (11), game console (4) and radio (1). Most users (33) had never watched VR content before. And some of them have watched it occasionally, only one of them reported to watch VR content once a week. The reasons behind this behaviour were: because they were not interested (3), because they had not had the chance to use it (23), because it was not accessible (3) or other reasons (4). 10 participants did use virtual reality content before. When directly asked if they were interested in VR content, some users (14) were strongly interested in VR content, some of them (14) were interested, some of them (11) were indifferent and one of them was not interested. Five participants owned a device to access VR content (Plastic VR Headsets for smartphone and PlayStation VR).

In terms of content preferences, most of the testers liked news (29), fiction (36), and documentaries (33), while some also liked talk shows (14), sports (17) and cartoons (18). Users activated subtitles depending on their needs and the content. 13 of them stated that they didn't need subtitles, 15 of them stated that depending on the content and 5 of them stated that they always activated subtitles. Regarding how many hours a day they watch subtitled content, 13 participants indicated none, 11 participants indicated less than 1 hour, 7 participants replied 1-2 hours, 8 participants replied 2-3 hours, and one participant indicated 4 hours or more. When asked why they used subtitles, 22 indicated that they helped them understand, 3 participants indicated that they were their only way to have access to the dialogue, 11 participants said that they used them for language learning and 11 participants stated that they never used subtitles.

5.5.3. Materials

Five clips were used in total. All clips were presented without audio, in order to control external variables that could impact results. An acclimatation clip, one-minute long and without subtitles was used for familiarisation purposes.

For the positioning part of the test, two clips from the series *Holy Land* developed by Ryot and Jaunt VR were used. Episode 4 (04:13) and episode 5 (04:58) were chosen. The clips are very similar, therefore, comparable. It is a documentary showing the territories in *Holy Land*, such as Jerusalem, Tel-Aviv, Palestina, etc. The hostess narrates the story of that land and explains socio-cultural facts. There is a voice-off most of the time and only one speaker. In the scenes different locations and landscapes appear, eliciting the viewer to explore.

This documentary whose original language is English was subtitled into Spanish, and two versions were created: Spanish always subtitles, and Spanish fixed positioned every 120° subtitles. Therefore, the stimuli for the tests were:

- A1: *Holy Land 1* - fixed positioned every 120°
- A2: *Holy Land 1* - always visible
- B1: *Holy Land 2* - fixed positioned every 120°
- B2: *Holy Land 2* - always visible

For the guiding mechanisms part of the test, the short film *I, Philip* was used again, as in other tests. It was cut in two parts, in order to have two comparable clips. They were subtitled in Spanish, creating two versions: one with arrows and one with a radar:

- C1: *I, Philip 1* - arrow
- C2: *I, Philip 1* - radar
- D1: *I, Philip 2* - arrow
- D2: *I, Philip 2* - radar

A Samsung Gear VR with Samsung Galaxy S7 was used to show the clips to participants. A 6-second black screen with the text “The test is about to start for...” was included.

All questionnaires (demographic, IPQ and preferences) were prepared in Spanish and presented to participants in Google Forms, accessible on a laptop. Also, questionnaires were reviewed by a professional educational psychologist specialised in teaching oral language to deaf people. She provided valuable feedback about the wording of the questionnaires. She provided suggestions to simplify questions and make them more accessible to hard-of-hearing users.

5.5.4. Experimental protocol

The experimental protocol followed the general framework established for all pilot actions. It was first tested in a pilot test with 8 home users. Different main changes were performed to the test:

- For guiding mechanisms, aut positioning (that is, a strategy consisting of adjusting the field of view to match the position of the targeted speaker by automatically rotating the camera) was discarded, because it was not well-received by users (it caused dizziness and discomfort, and broke immersion). This mechanism was replaced by an improved radar to be tested against arrows.
- One of the clips was discarded, because it did not work well for guiding mechanisms. It was replaced by *I, Philip*.
- Regarding participants, it was decided that only HoH participants whose main language was oral Spanish could participate, in order to have a homogeneous sample.

After the improvements, the main test was implemented as follows:

- Participants are welcomed and ImAc project and test is presented (face-to-face)
- Ethical clearance: participants sign informed consent forms (paper copies)
- Participants fill in a demographic questionnaire (online).
- Participants watch an acclimatation clip
- Presentation modes 1 – positioning. Participants are requested to watch two clips, one with always visible subtitles and one with fixed positioned subtitles. Order of presentation of always visible/fixed positioned is randomised across participants.

- Participants watch clip 1
- Participants watch clip 2
- After watching each clip, participants are administered the IPQ questionnaire
- After watching both clips, participants are administered a preference questionnaire.
- Presentation modes 2 – guiding mechanisms. Participants are requested to watch two clips, one in which the arrow is implemented and one in which the radar is implemented. Order of presentation of arrow/radar is randomised across participants, but the clip always follows a chronological order because otherwise the action could not be understood.
 - Participants watch clip 1
 - Participants watch clip 2
- After watching each clip, participants are administered the IPQ questionnaire
- After watching both clips, participants are administered a preference questionnaire.
- Participants are thanked

5.5.5. Results

Always visible vs fixed positioned every 120°

33 participants (82.5%) preferred the always visible subtitles and 7 participants (17.5%) preferred the fixed positioned subtitles every 120°. According to the participants, the main reasons for having chosen this option is that with the always visible subtitles they had more freedom to look around without missing the subtitle content and the video scenes and in a more comfortable way. The reasons of the users who chose the fixed positioned subtitles every 120° are because they can be read better than the always visible subtitles and they avoided the dizziness effect. Some users suggested to make the “always visible” more static, because the movement sometimes is distracting and hinders readability. It would be great to come with a technical solution to improve that.

Results for the preferential questions can be found in Table 14. Summarising the comparison analyses, it can be concluded that:

- Always visible subtitles (mean=6.01) were considered easier to find than fixed positioned subtitles every 120° (mean=3.92). This difference is statistically significant ($Z=-3.986$, $p=.000$, ties=5).
- Always visible subtitles (mean=5.19) were considered easier to read than fixed positioned subtitles every 120° (mean=4.30). This difference is statistically significant ($Z=-1.919$, $p=.055$, ties=9) (even if the threshold is set at .05, the result can be considered statistically relevant but with a slightly higher margin of error).
- Fixed positioned subtitles every 120° (mean=5.71) were considered slightly less obstructive than always visible subtitles (mean=4.97). This difference is not statistically significant ($Z=-1,123$, $p=.261$, ties=23).
- Always visible subtitles (mean=4.76) were considered less distracting than fixed positioned subtitles every 120° (mean=3.00). This difference is statistically significant ($Z=-2696$, $p=.007$, ties=13).

	1 very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7 - very easy	Mean	SD	Median
1. Did you find it easy to find the always visible subtitles?	1 (2.5%)	-	3 (7.5%)	2 (5%)	1 (2.5%)	1 (2.5%)	32 (80%)	6.32	1.5	7
2. Did you find it easy to find the fixed positioned subtitles?	1 (2.5%)	5 (12.5%)	6 (15%)	13 (32.5%)	7 (17.5%)	2 (5%)	6 (15%)	4.25	1.61	4
3. Did you find it easy to read the always visible subtitles?	2 (5%)	4 (10%)	-	-	6 (15%)	7 (17.5%)	21 (52.5%)	5.72	1.88	7
4. Did you find it easy to read the fixed positioned subtitles?	1 (2.5%)	6 (15%)	5 (12.5%)	6 (15%)	3 (7.5%)	9 (22.5%)	10 (25%)	4.77	1.91	5
	1- yes very much	2	3	4	5	6	7- not at all	Mean	SD	Median
5. Do you think always visible subtitles obstruct important parts of the image?	2 (5%)	4 (10%)	-	4 (10%)	4 (10%)	8 (20%)	18 (45%)	5.5	1.91	6
6. Do you think fixed positioned subtitles obstruct important parts of the image?	-	-	2 (5%)	6 (15%)	5 (12.5%)	9 (22.5%)	18 (45%)	5.87	1.28	6
7. Do you think that always visible subtitles distract you from the video?	4 (10%)	2 (5%)	1 (2.5%)	2 (5%)	4 (10%)	12 (30%)	15 (37.5%)	5.4	1.2	6
8. Do you think that fixed positioned subtitles distract you from the video?	8 (20%)	9 (22.5%)	5 (12.5%)	2 (5%)	4 (10%)	2 (5%)	10 (25%)	3.77	2.33	3

Table 14: Results intermediate action (subtitles) - Likert-scale results Always visible vs fixed positioned (UAB)

The comparison of results from IPQ between the always visible and fixed positioned every 120° are as follows:

- For the spatial scale ($Z=-1.791$, $p=.073$, ties=7), the involvement scale ($Z= -1.229$, $p=.219$, ties=8), and the realness scale ($Z= -0.064$, $p=.949$, ties=14), the test indicated that the difference between results is not statistically significant
- For the presence scale, the test indicated that the difference between results is statistically significant ($Z=-2.694$, $p=.007$, ties=17).

This means that the fixed positioned subtitles every 120° had a negative impact on the presence of participants. According to their comments in the open questions, this could be because they felt less free to explore the 360° scene and claimed to have missed parts of the subtitles content. Moreover, as reported above, participants found more difficult to find and read subtitles in this mode, and also considered them more distracting. Therefore, this extra effort could have caused a negative impact on presence.

	General Presence	Spatial Presence	Involvement	Experienced Realism
Always Visible	4.7	3.74	3.31	2.36
Fixed Positioned	3.95	3.43	3.38	2.49

Table 15: IPQ comparison of always visible vs fixed positioned (UAB)

Arrow vs radar

33 participants (82.5%) preferred arrows and 7 participants (17.5%) preferred the radar as guiding methods. Participants who favoured the arrows argued that this guiding method is more intuitive, direct, comfortable, less invasive and distracting. Also, many participants did not understand how the radar worked. Participants who preferred the radar argued that it gives more accurate and spatial information. A participant suggested that a short explanation about how the radar works before using it could improve the user reception of this mechanism. Also, a couple of participants suggested to move the radar to the center (maybe right below the subtitle) instead of being on the right side in order to improve usability. Some participants (4) stated that they would prefer no guiding mechanisms and that with the colour identification was enough.

Results for the preferential questions can be found in Table 16. Summarising the comparison analyses, it can be concluded that:

- Arrows (mean=5.95) were considered easier to find the speaker than the radar (mean=3.20). The difference is statistically significant ($Z=-4.166$, $p=.000$, ties=10).
- Arrows (mean=6.31) were considered less distracting than the radar (mean=3.04). The difference is statistically significant ($Z=4.125$, $p=.000$, ties=12).

	1 very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7 very easy	Mean	SD	Median
1. Did you find it easy to find the person who speaks with the arrows?	-	1 (2.5%)	1 (2.5%)	3 (7.5%)	4 (10%)	9 (22.5%)	22 (55%)	6.12	1.26	7
2. Did you find it easy to find the person who speaks with the radar?	6 (15%)	8 (20%)	6 (15%)	7 (17.5%)	1 (2.5%)	1 (2.5%)	11 (27.5%)	3.9	2.23	3.5
	1 yes very much	2	3	4	5	6	7 not at all	Mean	SD	Median
3. Did the arrows seem to distract you from what was happening in the video?	-	-	2 (5%)	1 (2.5%)	1 (2.5%)	10 (25%)	26 (65%)	6.42	1.03	7
4. Did the radar seem to distract you from what was happening in the video?	9 (22.5%)	8 (20%)	3 (7.5%)	4 (10%)	3 (7.5%)	-	13 (32.5%)	3.9	2.46	3.5

Table 16: Results intermediate action (subtitles) - Likert-scale results arrow vs radar (UAB)

The comparison of results from IPQ between the arrows and the radar are as follows:

- For the presence scale ($Z = -1.852$, $p = .064$, ties=21), the spatial scale ($Z = -1.000$, $p = .317$, ties=13), and the realness scale ($Z = -1.430$, $p = .153$, ties=7), the test indicated that the difference between results is not statistically significant
- For the involvement scale, the test indicated that the difference between results is statistically significant ($Z = -2.138$, $p = .033$, ties=12).

This means that the arrows system have a better performance than the radar regarding the involvement of participants. According to their comments in the open questions, this could be because some participants did not understand how the radar worked and the arrow was considered more intuitive and direct.

	General Presence	Spatial Presence	Involvement	Experienced Realism
Arrow	4.6	3.66	3.5	2.49
Radar	4.27	3.49	3.27	2.47

Table 17: IPQ comparison of arrow vs radar (UAB)

Head movements

Regarding the CVR Analyzer results, a difference was found when comparing viewing patterns of always visible vs fixed positioned every 120°. With the always visible, the head movements were more scattered, suggesting that participants felt more freedom to look around (see Figures 72 and 73).

Figure 72: Head movements' pattern from *Holy Land* video with fixed positioned subtitles every 120°

Figure 73: Head movements' pattern from *Holy Land* video with always visible subtitles (exactly the same scene above)

When analysing arrows vs radar, no significant difference was found between the two modes. Participants tend to look at speakers faces most of the time.

Figure 74: I, Philip scene with arrows

Figure 75: I, Philip scene with radar

5.6. UAB pre-pilot 2 actions on easy-to-read (I)

The main features of the first subtitling pre-pilot 2 action on easy-to-read are summarized next:

- **Users:** 8 users
- **Dates:** 13.05.2019-06.06.2019
- **Format:** face-to-face

The aim of the action was to gather user feedback on easy-to-read subtitles as compared to subtitles for the deaf and hard-of-hearing.

5.6.1. Measures

The measures chosen were presence and preferences. For presence, IPQ was used. For preferences, a specific questionnaire was developed:

- What system do you prefer for subtitles? SDH/E2R
- Please explain why you prefer the above indicated option.

- Please explain why you did not choose the other option in question 1.
- What do you think could be improved, and how?
- How easy was it to read the subtitles in SDH/E2R? (7-point Likert scale)
- How easy was it to understand the subtitles in SDH/E2R? (7-point Likert scale)
- Do you think you will be able to enjoy 360° videos with this type of subtitles? Explain your answer.

5.6.2. Participants

8 users took part in the test (5 females, 3 male), with ages ranging from 50 to 79 (mean age=70.5). The main language was Spanish and Catalan. Three participants had secondary education, three further education and three university education. Two participants were hearing impaired (disability began after age of 60) and six were hearing.

Regarding technology usage habits, eight participants replied that they used TV on a daily basis, three used PC, three used laptop, eight used mobile phone, four used tablet, and one used radio. When asked how often they watch virtual reality content, only one participant replied yes (occasionally, in a smartphone/smartphone plugged to HMD and in HMD). When asked why they never tried VR content before, seven participants replied because they had not had the chance to use it and only one replied that because he/she was not interested.

When asked whether they were interested in VR content, three replied that they strongly agreed, three replied that they agreed and two replied that they neither agreed nor disagreed. None of the participants owned a VR device to access VR content.

When asked what kind of content they liked to watch on TV or online, participant's replies were as follows:

	I like it very much	I like it	Neither like it nor dislike it	I don't like it	I don't like it at all
News	5	3	0	0	0
Fiction (series, films)	2	2	2	1	1
Talk shows	3	4	0	0	1
Documentaries	5	3	0	0	0
Sports	1	4	2	1	0

Table 18: Participants' watching habits (UAB pre-pilot on Easy-to-Read subtitles)

When asked whether they activate subtitles for each type of content, most participants never activated subtitles for any type of content. Replies can be seen in Table 19.

	Always	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
News	0	1	1	6
Fiction (series, films)	1	0	3	4
Talk shows	0	1	0	7
Documentaries	1	2	0	5
Sports	0	0	2	6
Cartoons	0	0	0	7

Table 19: Subtitle usage for participants at UAB pre-pilot on Easy-to-Read subtitles

When asked why they did not activate subtitles when they are available, all participants replied that they did not want subtitles in all the content, only in certain types of content.

When asked how many hours a day they used subtitles, four participants replied none, two participants replied less than 1 hour, and two participants replied 1-2 hours.

When asked for which purpose they used subtitles, four participants replied that they helped them understand and one participant replied that they used them for language learning; three participants gave other reasons.

5.6.3. Materials

Two excerpts of the opera *Romeo and Juliette* in French were subtitled into Spanish in two different versions: easy-to-read subtitles and standard subtitles for the deaf and hard-of-hearing. In both cases arrows were used as guiding mechanisms.

The stimuli (of about 4 minutes each) were therefore:

- Opera, part 1 in E2R subtitles
- Opera, part 1 in SDH
- Opera, part 2 in E2R subtitles
- Opera, part 1 in SDH

Easy-to-read subtitles were validated with end-users. The following on-line questionnaires were prepared: demographic questionnaire, IPQ questionnaire, and preference questionnaire.

5.6.4. Experimental protocol

The procedure is as follows:

- Participants are welcomed and ImAc project and test is presented (face-to-face)
- Ethical clearance: participants sign informed consent forms (paper copies)
- Participants fill in a demographic questionnaire (online)
- Participants watch clip 1
- Participants watch clip 2 (The order of presentation is balanced across participants.)
- After watching each clip, participants are administered the IPQ questionnaire
- After watching both clips, participants are asked a preference and general feedback questionnaire
- Participants are thanked

5.6.5. Results

A Wilcoxon Signed Ranks test was used to compare the ratings for both subtitle types and found no differences in any IPQ scale (General Presence $Z=-.184$, $p=.854$, ties=4; Spatial Presence $Z=-.639$, $p=.523$, ties=0; Involvement $Z=-.431$, $p=.666$, ties=2; Experienced realism $Z=-1.222$, $p=.222$, ties=0).

Group	General Presence	Spatial Presence	Involvement	Experienced Realism
SDH	5	5	4.63	4.00
E2R	5	5	4.88	3.88

Table 20: Median scores for IPQ subscales (SDH versus E2R)

Regarding preferences, 5 users prefer E2R subtitles and 3 users prefer SDH. When selecting E2R, they indicate that they are shorter and easier to read, they allow you to get more into the story and enjoy the performance better. Those who preferred SDH thought they were more defined and clearer, and the language was more appropriate. One user indicated that since this was the second condition in the test, s/he was more used to reading the subtitles. Some suggestions were made concerning SDH: they should be shorter, easier to read, and reduced as much as possible. Regarding E2R subtitles, users think they are quite good and only one reports that using a more accurate language would be advisable.

	1 very difficult	2	3	4	5 very easy	Mean	SD	Median
1. How easy was it to read the subtitles in SDH?	-	1 (12.5%)	2 (25%)	3 (37.5%)	2 (25%)	3.75	1.03	4
2. How easy was it to read the subtitles in E2R?	-	1 (12.5%)	-	1 (12.5%)	6 (75%)	4.5	1.06	5
3. How easy was it to understand the subtitles in SDH?	-	1 (12.5%)	2 (25%)	3 (37.5%)	2 (25%)	3.75	1.03	4
4. How easy was it to understand the subtitles in E2R?	-	1 (12.5%)	-	-	7 (87.5%)	4.5	1.41	5

Table 21: Likert Scales results – E2R vs SDH

When asked how easy it was to read the subtitles in SDH/E2R, replies show that E2R subtitles (M=4.5) were considered easier to read than SDH subtitles (M=3.75).

When asked how easy it was to understand the subtitles in SDH/E2R, replies show that again E2R subtitles (M=4.5) were easier to understand than SDH subtitles (M=3.75).

Regarding the question, ‘What do you think could be improved, and how?’, participants that favoured E2R subtitles reported that SDH subtitles should be shorter, be made easy to read, text should be reduced as much as possible and should adopt the visibility and readability of the E2R option. Conversely, participants that chose SDH subtitles argued that E2R subtitles should use more accurate language.

Users seemed to welcome E2R subtitles overall because they are easy to read and “you can understand everything”, because they are not as invasive as SDH and because the “eye becomes easily used to subtitles in the E2R format”. Complaints referred to virtual worlds (“I am reluctant to virtual worlds”), not the actual implementation of the subtitles.

5.7. UAB pre-pilot 2 actions on easy-to-read (II)

The main features of the second pre-pilot 2 action on on easy-to-read are summarized next:

- **Users:** 36 users
- **Dates:** October 2019
- **Format:** face-to-face

The aim of the action was to gather user feedback on easy-to-read subtitles as compared to subtitles for the deaf and hard-of-hearing.

5.7.1. Measures

The same measures as in 5.6.1 were used.

5.7.2. Participants

The targeted participants were elderly. Participants were 19 female and 17 male, aged between 62 and 79 (mean age=69.4). All participants were Spanish, and only two reported speaking or understanding French. 20 participants were Spanish-Catalan bilinguals, and 16 only spoke Spanish. Regarding education level, 2 participants (5.6%) reported not having any type of studies, 10 participants (27.8%) had primary education, 7 participants (19.4%) secondary education, 8 participants (22.2%) professional studies and 9 participants (25%) a university degree.

Almost half of the participants reported not having type of impairment but some type of sensory decline. While only two participants used hearing aids, 22 participants reported mild hearing loss and/or visual decline, 11 participants reported having it detected between 41 and 60 years old and 11 participants as of 60. Only one participant declared to have a cognitive decline.

Regarding technology use, 34 participants (94.4%) replied that they use TV on a daily basis, 12 (33.3%) use PC, 16 (44.4%) use laptop, 35 (97.2%) use mobile phone, 16 (44.4%) use tablet, and one (2.8%) uses radio.

None of the participants owns VR equipment and only seven participants are familiar with VR content. 29 participants reported not having had the opportunity to enjoy VR content. 3 participants were very interested in VR content, 12 were interested, 19 participants were neutral. Regarding the type of AV content, animations and sports were the least valued. On the other hand, documentaries and fiction were the most valued. 17 participants claimed that they never use subtitles, two participants claimed that they always use subtitles and 11 participants indicate that they use them sometimes depending on the content and language of the AV content. Regarding the reasons to use subtitles, five participants said to learn languages and 14 said that they used them because subtitles helped them to understand. 17 participants reported not to use subtitles mainly because they do not like them. Within this group it must be mentioned that 5 participants, the ones with the lower study levels, reported that they did not activate the subtitles because their reading speed was too low to follow the subtitles and they feel frustrated and with subtitles miss the visual content.

5.7.3. Materials

The same materials as in 5.6.3 were used.

5.7.4. Experimental protocol

The same protocol as in 5.6.4 was followed.

5.7.5. Results

Planned comparisons (T-test) show that the results of four scales of Presence (General presence, Spatial Presence, Involvement and Experienced Realism) are not different if participants have seen E2R subtitles or SDH subtitles: General Presence $t(34)=-.138$, $p=.891$; Spatial Presence $t(34)=-.361$, $p=.720$; Involvement $t(34)=.803$, $p=.428$; Experienced realism $t(34)=.000$, $p=1$.

Group	General Presence	Spatial Presence	Involvement	Experienced Realism
SDH	4.71	4.91	4.26	3.90
E2R	4.74	4.87	4.41	3.90

Table 22: Median scores for IPQ subscales (SDH versus E2R)

The results obtained regarding preferences were that 19 (52.78%) out of 36 participants preferred E2R subtitles, 16 participants preferred SDH (44.44%), and one participant (2.7%) had no preference. The main reasons for choosing the E2R option were that they are shorter and easier to read than SDH, and that in the SDH subtitles there were some words that they did not understand. When asked 'Why did they do not choose the other option?' the reasons were because SDH subtitles were more dense, longer and more difficult to read. Also, the exposure time ('6 second rule') should be reviewed because some participants reported not having the time to read the subtitles. On the other hand, participants who chose the SDH option argued that SDH were more defined and clearer, and the language, more accurate.

When asked what could be improved, nine participants (25%) reported that there was nothing to be improved and one participant (2.77%) did not know. Three participants (8.33%) reported that the size of the font in both options was perfect, and three participants (8.33%) reported that the quality of the image should be better. Most participants found the use of colours for character identification very helpful and the size of the font very easy to read. Regarding colour, eight participants (22.22%) reported that some colours were difficult to read, especially for the stronger ones, which did not allow them to connect with the visuals. One participant (2.77%) mentioned that there should be more subtitled content in E2R and SDH to compare, another participant (2.77%) did not like the invasiveness of the subtitles, another participant (2.77%) considered that the subtitle should be more centered in the field of view and a last one (2.77%) found the size of the text too big and users should be able to adapt it. For the SDH two participants (5.55%) reported that there were words that they did not understand and two participants (5.55%) stated that the reading times were too fast. For the E2R two participants (5.55%) explained that the subtitles were too fast and another two participants (5.55%) expressed font size seemed larger than SDH.

	1 very difficult	2	3	4	5 very easy	Mean	SD	Median
1. How easy was it to read the subtitles in SDH?	-	1 (2.8%)	6 (16.7%)	5 (13.9%)	24 (66.7%)	4.44	0.87	5
2. How easy was it to read the subtitles in E2R?	-	-	3 (8.3%)	9 (25%)	24 (66.7%)	4.58	0.65	5
3. How easy was it to understand the subtitles in SDH?	-	-	8 (22.2%)	5 (13.9%)	23 (63.9%)	4.42	0.84	5
4. How easy was it to understand the subtitles in E2R?	-	-	1 (2.8%)	9 (25%)	26 (72.2%)	4.69	0.52	5

Table 23: Likert Scales results – E2R vs SDH (main test)

Regarding the closed questions on readability and understandability of both subtitle options: For E2R, 24 participants (66.7%) reported that they were very easy to read, nine participants (25%) stated that they were easy to read and three participants (8.3%) were neutral. For understandability of E2R subtitles, most participants, 26 (72.25%), answered that they were very easy to understand, nine participants (25%) answered that they were easy to understand and only one participant (2.8%) was neutral. Regarding the results for the readability of SDH subtitles, they were slightly lower: 24 participants (66.7%) replied that SDH subtitles were very easy to read, five participants (13.9%) that they were easy to read, six participants (16.7%) were neutral and only one participant (2.8%) that they were difficult to read. For understandability of SDH, most participants (23=63.9%) answered that they were very easy to understand, five participants (13.9%) answered that they were easy to understand and eight participants (22.2%) stayed neutral.

When comparing the feedback provided for the question, ‘Do you think you will be able to enjoy 360° videos with this type of subtitles? Explain your answer’, 34 participants (95.2%) agreed on a positive answer, arguing that subtitles in both cases helped them to understand the plot which was in French language. Only two participants (5.6%) reported that they do not like subtitles. Regarding the type and size of the font, almost all participants 35 (98%) reported that size and font were easy to read and the eye became easily adapted to subtitles in this format. Only one participant (2.8%) reported that it would be a great advantage if the size could be customised. In addition, one participant (2.8%) with primary studies reported not having had the time to read the subtitles.

To conclude, it should be highlighted that, the selected AV contents might have had an impact on preferences and presence results, that are not directly related to the different subtitle modes. It is important to mention that the second video with a more active scene was the most preferred by all participants. According to the feedback received by all participants, aged people are willing to use HMD-VR and have more positive attitudes towards HMD-VR after a first positive experience in immersive AV content.

5.8. Conclusions

Regarding the presentation modes, different possibilities have been assessed by users. Qualitative data have been provided, and preferences have been expressed as summarised in the following tables.

First of all, subtitle position has been assessed in pre-pilot 2 actions and intermediate actions. Preference results are summarised in Table 24.

	Always visible with arrow	Fixed positioned with arrow
CCMA	10 (83.3%)	2 (16.7%)
RBB	9 (75%)	3 (25%)
	Always visible	Fixed positioned every 120 ^o
UAB	33 (82.5%)	7 (17.5%)

Table 24: Results on preferences from pre-pilot 2 actions (CCMA, RBB, UAB): always visible vs. fixed positioned

Secondly, guiding mechanisms in different evolved versions have been tested all along the project: arrow versus radar in pre-pilot 1 actions (see D2.1) and pilot 1, as well as an evolved version of these mechanisms in pre-pilot 2 actions. Results are summarised in Table 25.

	Arrow	Radar
CCMA (Pilot 1)	9 (69.2%)	4 (30.8%)
RBB (Pilot 1)	8 (72.7%)	3 (27.3%)
UAB (Pre-pilot 2 action)	33 (82.5%)	7 (17.5%)

Table 25: Results on preferences: arrow vs. radar

Thirdly, users' views on using emojis and text to represent sound were also gathered in pre-pilot action 2. Table 26 summarises the results for both CCMA and RBB.

	Textual representation of sound	Emoji
CCMA	10 (83.3%)	2 (16.7%)
RBB	8 (100%)	0 (0%)

Table 26: Results on preferences from pre-pilot action 2 (CCMA, RBB): textual representation of sound vs. emoji.

Finally, two tests on easy-to-read subtitles as compared to standard SDH were also performed as pre-pilot 2 actions. Results on preferences are presented in Tables 27 and 28, showing the potential of these innovative E2R subtitles.

	E2R subtitles	Standard SDH
UAB	5 (62.5%)	3 (37.5%)

Table 27: Results on preferences from pre-pilot action 2 (UAB): E2R subtitles vs. standard SDH (I)

	E2R subtitles	Standard SDH	Both
UAB	19 (52.8%)	16 (44.4%)	1 (2.8%)

Table 28: Results on preferences from pre-pilot action 2 (UAB): E2R subtitles vs. standard SDH (II)

In terms of presence, most tests have shown that the different possibilities tested have a similar effect on presence, showing that it is often a matter of preference and that the choice should be given to users. The only exception has been the UAB intermediate test, in which the

fixed positioned subtitles had a negative impact on general presence and the ImAc solution proved better than existing ones.

Overall, pilot actions have allowed gathering valuable qualitative feedback to improve the project developments and have highlighted some relevant challenges in this new environment where accessibility is still lacking.

6. TESTING THE SIGN LANGUAGE PRESENTATION MODES

Presentation modes for SL have been tested in ImAc in different stages (see Table 4 for a whole list and Figure 9 for testing conditions):

- During development:
 - Pre-pilot 1 action at RBB (see D2.1)
 - Pre-pilot 2 action, at RBB
- During implementation:
 - Pilot phase 2 action at RBB (see specific section)

Results from the pre-pilot 2 action reported here, following the same structure as in the other tests:

- General description of the pilot action: users, version, dates and format.
- Measures used, based on framework presented in Figures 12 and 13. If an ad-hoc preference questionnaire is used, it is reproduced in this section.
- Participants' description, summarising the data obtained through the demographic questionnaires. Given that we are within the realm of media accessibility, it was decided to take a wider approach to testing and use different user profiles who claim using subtitles.
- Materials, presenting the different materials and content used for the tests.
- The experimental protocol, which follows the general framework in Figure 14.
- Results, with a discussion of the main results of the pilot action. More specific details, with a thorough reproduction of all replies, are included in the full reports included as annexes.

The full methodology for the SL actions and results are found in the Annexes.

6.1. RBB pre-pilot 2 action

The main features of the RBB pre-pilot 2 action on SL are presented next:

- **Users:** 10
- **Dates:** 06.05.2019-24.05.2019
- **Format:** face-to-face

The aim of the action was to test three aspects:

- Display of signer video: continuous versus non-continuous (Figure 76)
- Presentation of Sign Language only or Sign Language plus subtitles (Figure 77)
- Speaker representation: textual versus emojis (Figure 78)

Figure 76: Display of signer video: continuous (Task 1)

Figure 77: Presentation of Sign Language plus subtitles (Task 2)

Figure 78: Speaker representation: textual versus emojis (Task 3)

6.1.1. Measures

The measures chosen were presence and preferences. For presence, IPQ was used. For preferences, a specific questionnaire was developed for each task:

- What system do you prefer for subtitles? A/B
- Please explain why you prefer the above-indicated option.
- Please explain why you did not choose the other option in question 1.
- What do you think could be improved, and how?
- Other comments.

In Task 2 the following questions were added:

- How easy was it to read all the information with SL and subtitles/ SL only? (7-point Likert scale)
- How easy was it to understand the video with SL and subtitles/SL only? (7-point Likert scale)
- Please indicate your level of agreement with this statement: “I think ‘reading’ SL and ST simultaneously is overwhelming for me” (7-point Likert scale, 1 strongly disagree, 7 strongly agree).

In Task 3 the following questions were added:

- How easy was it to know who was speaking with the textual representation/emoticon representation? (7-point Likert scale)

6.1.2. Participants

10 users took part in the test (6 female and 4 male). Participants were aged between 15 to 51 years (mean age=38.4). Main languages of participants were: German (2) and German SL (8). 3 participants had university studies and 7 reported having secondary education. When asked about their degree of hearing loss, 10 testers declared themselves as deaf and 1 indicated that she/he became deaf very late. Another person stated that she/he deafened and switches between SL and spoken language. For almost all users, the impairment began at birth or below the age of 4, while for 1 user the impairment started between 21 and 40 years. When asked about what technology they use on a daily basis, 10 users reported using smartphone, followed by laptop (9), tablet (6) and TV (5), while PC (3) and HMD (3) were least often used.

When asked how often they watch VR content (for instance, 360° videos) on different devices, only 2 participants declared watching such content occasionally in HMD, 1 participant declared watching such content occasionally in smartphone and on tablet (1).

When asked why they never used VR content or used it only occasionally, 3 participants chose the option: ‘Because it’s not accessible’, 6 participants chose the option ‘Because I have not had the chance to use it’ and 2 participants chose the option ‘Other reasons’, adding that there is not much VR content available or they wouldn’t be able to find it.

When asked to state their level of agreement with the statement: “I am interested in Virtual Reality content (such as 360° videos)”, 3 participants strongly agreed, 4 participants agreed and 3 participants neither agreed nor disagreed. 5 participants did not own a device to access VR content, 3 participants owned such device and 2 participants chose the option ‘I don’t know or I don’t want to reply’.

In terms of the content they like watching the most, 3 participants chose the option ‘news’, 8 participants ‘fiction’, 1 participant ‘Talk shows’, 5 participants ‘Documentaries’, 3 participants ‘Sports’ and 4 participants ‘Cartoons’.

All testers activated subtitles for 'News', 'Fiction' and 'Documentary' genre. Most of the testers activated subtitles for 'Talk shows' (9), 'Sports' (7) and 'Cartoons' (7). When asked about the reason behind not activating subtitles, 5 participants always activated subtitles, 4 participants chose the option 'because the interface is not accessible' and 1 participant who did not always use subtitles declared that she/he only used ST only when lip reading is not possible.

When asked about how many hours a day they watch subtitled content, 5 participants chose the option 1-2 hours a day, 1 participant chose 2-3 hours, 3 participants chose 3-4 hours, and 1 participant declared consuming subtitled content 4 hours or more a day. In the last question ('What do you use subtitles for?'), 7 participants chose the option 'They help me understand', 4 participants 'They are the only way to have access to the dialogue' and 1 participant 'I use them for language learning'.

6.1.3. Materials

Different clips were prepared for the different tasks:

- Task 1: *I, Philip*, split in two clips (5-6 minutes), each with the two conditions: continuous and non-continuous.
- Task 2: Opera *Romeo and Juliette*, split in two parts, each with the two conditions. German SL with arrow and German SL with arrow plus subtitles.
- Task 3: *I, Philip*, pre-selected snippets, in both conditions: text and emoticons.
 - Clip 1 (Total timecode: 00:01:50.02 - 00:05:21.14)
 - Clip 2 (Total timecode: 00:06:30.12 - 00:09:31.00)

Textual	Emoji	
Dave	U+1F468 U+1F3FD	
Andrew	U+1F474 U+1F3FC	
Ted	U+1F468 U+1F3FD U+200D U+1F9B3	
Clariss	U+1F469 U+1F3FC U+200D U+1F9B3	
Felicia	U+1F469 U+1F3FD	
Kristof	U+1F9D4 U+1F3FC	
Clariss	U+1F469 U+1F3FC	

Table 29: Clips used in pre-pilot 2 (RBB)

6.1.4. Experimental protocol

The procedure is as follows:

- Participants are welcomed and ImAc project and test is presented (face-to-face)
- Ethical clearance: participants sign informed consent forms (paper copies)
- Participants fill in a demographic questionnaire (online)
- Participants perform task 1: they watch two clips with the two conditions in a randomised order. After watching each clip, they are administered the IPQ questionnaire. After watching both clips, they are administered a preference questionnaire.
- Participants perform task 2: they watch two clips with the two conditions in a randomised order. After watching both clips, they are administered a preference questionnaire.
- Participants perform task 3: they watch two clips with the two conditions in a randomised order. After watching both clips, they are administered a preference questionnaire.
- Participants are thanked

6.1.5. Results

Concerning the presentation of continuous or non-continuous SL interpreting, median scores for each subscale on the IPQ questionnaire are shown in Table 30.

	General Presence	Spatial Presence	Involvement	Experienced Realism
Continuous	4	3.60	4.13	2.5
Non-Continuous	5	3.60	3.75	2.5

Table 30: IPQ results for continuous versus non-continuous display (RBB)

The comparison of each of the subscales of IPQ questionnaire with the Wilcoxon Signed Ranks test does not show any significant difference between the two conditions (General presence $Z=-.604$, $p= .546$, ties=3 ; Spatial presence $Z=-1.532$, $p=.125$, ties=3 ; Involvement $Z=-.341$, $p=.733$, ties=3; Experienced realism $Z= -.421$, $p= .674$, ties=2).

Concerning the preference questionnaire, data from 9 users are reported as RBB1 data is missing due to a technical error. 6 out of 9 users prefer a non-continuous display, the main reason being that it is easier to concentrate on the video content and not look around freely. Those users who preferred the continuous display expressed that they know for sure that the interpreter is there like it would be in a real-life situation and in this way they are sure that there are no technical problems. Some improvements suggested by the users are that the SL video should be positioned slightly more in the middle as it was too far outside. In this regard, one user proposed to have the SL video in general centrally in the field of view. Another improvement concerned the arrow, which should be in the same colour as the subtitles, to indicate different speakers.

Regarding the second task, six users preferred to use both SL and subtitles, whereas 4 prefer to use SL. It should be stressed out that when participants were recruited, they were asked what they would like to test, either SL or subtitles, and the participants in this group chose SL. Moreover, 8 participants state the German SL is their main language. It was therefore unexpected that such a high number of users would prefer to have two modes simultaneously. One user even stated “for me SL & ST together are ideal. Keep going with the research and development!”, whereas another one stated “Both services at once does not make sense in my eyes. Each user has his needs and should be able to choose one of both services”.

The users expressed that the advantages to have both services together were the colour of the subtitles helped them to identify the speaker and, especially in the opera content, the subtitles transported more information than the SL interpreting. An improvement suggested by users was that the SL video should be slightly more in the middle.

Regarding the last task, a clear majority of 7 users preferred the textual speaker representation and only 3 chose the emojis. The main reason was that the text enables a fast and easy identification of the speaker. Emojis give room for interpretation and the speaker representation was not accurate enough. Table 31 provides a summary of the results of the additional questions posed to participants.

	1- very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7 very easy	Mean	Median	SD
How easy was it to understand the video with Sign Language + subtitles?	-	2 (20%)	-	-	1 (10%)	1 (10%)	6 (60%)	5.7	7	2.05
How easy was it to understand the video with Sign Language only?	-	-	1 (10%)	3 (30%)	-	3 (30%)	3 (30%)	5.4	6	1.5
How easy was it to "read" all the information with Sign Language + subtitles?	-	1 (10%)	-	1 (10%)	1 (10%)	3 (30%)	4 (40%)	5.7	6	1.63
How easy was it to "read" all the information with Sign Language only?	-	-	1 (10%)	1 (10%)	2 (20%)	4 (40%)	2 (20%)	5.5	6	1.27
Please, indicate your level of agreement with this statement: "I think "read" Sign Language and subtitling simultaneously is overwhelming for me."	2 (20%)	2 (20%)	1 (10%)	1 (10%)	1 (10%)	-	3 (30%)	3.9	3.5	2.47

Table 31: Likert scale results – SL pre-pilot 2 action (RBB)

7. TESTING THE AD PRESENTATION MODES

Presentation modes for AD have been tested in ImAc in different stages (see Table 5 for a whole list and Figure 10 for testing conditions):

- During development:
 - Pre-pilot action 1 at RNIB and UAB (see D2.1)
 - Pre-pilot action 2 at RNIB and UAB
- During implementation:
 - Cross-national pilot actions at RNIB and UAB

Results from all actions are reported here, following the same structure as in the other tests:

- General description of the pilot action: users, version, dates and format.
- Measures used, based on framework presented in Figures 12 and 13. If an ad-hoc preference questionnaire is used, it is reproduced in this section.
- Participants' description, summarising the data obtained through the demographic questionnaires. Given that we are within the realm of media accessibility, it was decided to take a wider approach to testing and use different user profiles who claim using subtitles.
- Materials, presenting the different materials and content used for the tests.
- The experimental protocol, which follows the general framework in Figure 14.
- Results, with a discussion of the main results of the pilot action. More specific details, with a thorough reproduction of all replies, are included in the full reports included as annexes.

The full methodology and reports are found in the Annexes: Annex 26 reports on the methodology for pre-pilot action 2, Annex 27 reports on the results at RNIB and Annex 28 on the results at UAB. Annex 29 presents the methodology for the cross-national pilot, and the results are reported in Annexes 30 (RNIB) and 31 (UAB).

7.1. RNIB pre-pilot action 2

The main features of the AD presentation test are as follows:

- **Users:** 5
- **Dates:** 07.05.2019-27.05.2019
- **Format:** face-to-face

The aim was to test the methodology for the cross-national pilot. Three presentation modes, namely Classic, Static, and Dynamic, were considered in the test. Classic mode is a standard option that can be assimilated with standard AD for non-VR media content and audio description is heard from above user's head. In the second type, Static, users will hear audio description from the their left or right side, as if a friend was sitting or standing close to them. The last type is called Dynamic – which means that the sound of AD is placed on the location of the main action or other important elements.

Figure 79: Presentation modes used in RNIB AD pre-pilot action 2

To avoid the terminology having an impact on the test, the conditions were referred to as AD-C, AD-S, and AD-D when presented to the users.

7.1.1. Measures

The measures chosen were presence and preferences. For presence, IPQ was used. For preferences, a specific questionnaire was developed in English:

- Which AD type do you prefer in 360°? Rank the AD modes according to your preferences: 1-preferred mode, 2-second preferred mode, 3-the least preferred mode.
- What system do you prefer for subtitles? A/B
- Please explain why you ranked the AD modes in this way.
- How could AD be improved in this medium?
- Other comments

7.1.2. Participants

The same users as in the other RNIB pre-pilot action 2 took part in the test. Please refer to 4.5.2 for a full description.

7.1.3. Materials

Three episodes from the *Holy Land* series were created with the AD in the three selected modes, as follows:

- *Holy Land*, episode 1, in three conditions: Classic, Static, Dynamic, in English. Length: 05:05
- *Holy Land*, episode 2, in three conditions: Classic, Static, Dynamic, in English. Length: 03:56
- *Holy Land*, episode 3, in three conditions: Classic, Static, Dynamic, in English. Length: 04:01

An audio introduction was also included, so that the user could learn a bit more about the content. Demographic questionnaires, IPQ questionnaire, and preference questionnaire were also available in an online form.

7.1.4. Experimental protocol

The procedure is as follows:

- Participants are welcomed and ImAc project and test is presented (face-to-face).
- Ethical clearance: participants are assigned with an individual participant code and sign informed consent forms (paper copies)
- Participants fill in a demographic questionnaire (online). Participants have time to ask additional questions
- User interface pilot action (see 4.5)
- Participants listen to one general audio introduction and then watch three clips in randomised presentation modes, and reply to IPQ questionnaire after each clip. Finally, they fill in the post-questionnaire (preference questions)
- AST pilot action (see 8.1)
- Participants are thanked

7.1.5. Results

Concerning presence, the median values for IPQ for RNIB, in the three conditions for each subscale are shown in Table 32.

	General Presence	Spatial Presence	Involvement	Experienced Realism
Classic	3.00	2.40	1.50	1.75
Dynamic	1.00	2.20	1.50	0.75
Static	2.00	1.00	1.25	0.75

Table 32: Median values for IPQ in AD pre-pilot action 2 (RNIB)

Non parametric Friedman tests reveal no statistically significant differences between the scores of any subscale between conditions: General presence (Chi-Square(2)= 1.273; N=5; p=.529); Spatial Presence (Chi-Square(2)= 4.500, N=5, p=.105); Involvement (Chi Square(2)= 2.111, N=5, p= .348); Experienced realism (Chi-Square(2)=.111, N=5, z= .946).

Most testers were unable to tell the difference between the different presentation modes despite head movements. When asked what type of AD they prefer, results are as follows (Table 33).

	AD-C	AD-S	AD-D
1 preferred mode	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (20%)
2 preferred mode	5 (100%)	5 (100%)	4 (80%)
3 preferred mode	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)

Table 33: Results on preferences (RNIB): AD modes

However, from qualitative feedback, one could say that replies were random as many expressed difficulties in perceiving the differences. Testers commented that the experience did not feel any different to the experience of watching regular content on TV or cinema. However, one tester commented that they enjoyed listening to the AD coming from different directions. One could assume that the lack of spatial audio within the original soundtrack was the underlying reason for the viewers not being able to differentiate between the different modes but so far there is no evidence to support this theory.

Suggestions for improvements related mainly to the scripting: an audio introduction before each clip, more AD, a better synchronisation or a less monotonous AD were suggestions made. Some users felt that the content type may have an impact, as “it takes time to immerse yourself and when the environment keeps changing, it doesn’t work. For example, in this clip, the background music kept changing – you start to build a picture in your head and then it disappears and then the woman starts talking”. One user also highlighted the need for 3D audio.

Three testers with severe sight loss (blind) felt uncomfortable wearing HMD and asked to remove it several times through the test: they did not see the point as they weren’t engaging with the content visually. On being explained that the HMD was required to track the head movement, they requested for equipment that was lighter and did not pinch or applied less pressure on the area surrounding their eyes.

7.2. UAB pre-pilot action 2

The AD presentation modes test replicated the RNIB test. Its main features are as follows:

- **Users:** 6
- **Dates:** June 2019
- **Format:** face-to-face

The aim was to test the methodology for the cross-national pilot. Three presentation modes, namely Classic, Static, and Dynamic, were considered in the test, as described in section 7.1.

7.2.1. Measures

The same measures as for the RNIB test were used, translated into Catalan and Spanish. See 7.1.1.

7.2.2. Participants

The same users as in the other UAB pre-pilot action 2 took part in the test. Please refer to 4.6.2 for a full description.

7.2.3. Materials

The same three episodes from the *Holy Land* series used for the UK test were used. First of all, they were translated into Catalan and voiced-over by CCMA. Then, the AD in English were translated into Catalan and voiced by a Catalan voice talent. The final materials were: *Holy Land*, episodes 1, 2, and 3.

An audio introduction was also included, so that the user could learn a bit more about the content. Demographic questionnaires, IPQ questionnaire, and preference questionnaire were also available in an online form.

7.2.4. Experimental protocol

The procedure was the same as for the RNIB test described in 7.1.4.

7.2.5. Results

Concerning presence, the median values for IPQ for UAB, in the three conditions for each subscale are shown in Table 34.

	General Presence	Spatial Presence	Involvement	Experienced Realism
Classic	3.00	3.40	3.00	1.75
Dynamic	4.00	3.70	3.00	2.13
Static	4.00	2.70	4.00	2.50

Table 34: Median values for IPQ in AD pre-pilot action 2 (UAB)

Non parametric Friedman tests reveal no statistically significant differences between the scores of any subscale between conditions: General presence (Chi-Square(2)= .200; N=6; p=.905); Spatial Presence (Chi-Square(2)=.087, N=6, p=.957); Involvement (Chi Square(2)=1.810, N=6, p= .405); Experienced realism (Chi-Square(2)=1.00, N=6, z= .607).

When asked what type of AD they prefer, the results are summarised in Table 35.

	AD-C	AD-S	AD-D
1 preferred mode	2 (33.33%)	2 (33.33%)	2 (33.33%)
2 preferred mode	3 (50%)	2 (33.33%)	1 (16.67%)
3 preferred mode	1 (16.67%)	2 (33.33%)	3 (50%)

Table 35: Results on preferences (UAB): AD modes

However, comments show that these results are not representative for various reasons: users could not differentiate the audio treatments and the selection was mainly based on the scripting features (such as the amount of details in the script), not the audio presentation. Regarding the Dynamic mode, none of the users could hear that the AD is coming from different locations, linked to the main actions or main characters appearing at different parts of the scene.

The suggestions for improvement were mostly related to the scripting style: some users would prefer a more detailed AD, and others less detailed in order to listen more to ambient sound or music. Concerning content features, users indicate that the content has a direct impact on immersion, and the following criteria should be fulfilled to increase it: (a) a slower-paced content with less dialogues or narration, so that background noises coming from different parts of the sphere can be heard (4 users), and (b) AD should be clearly hearable from specific locations within the sphere (1 user).

7.3. Cross-national pilot: AD presentation modes (RNIB)

The main features of the AD presentation test are as follows:

- **Users:** 31
- **Dates:** 5.11.2019-30.01.2020
- **Format:** face-to-face

Based on the results of the pre-pilot action 2, and taking into account the interest of users in new scripting approaches, the Classic mode was contrasted in the cross-national to two innovative approaches: the so-called Radio mode and the Extended audio description. The variable that was modified for this test was not sound, as in the pre-pilot action 2, but scripting.

The Classic mode is the same that has been used in the project, and features a standard and neutral narrator.

The Radio mode adopts a more lively approach, in which the narrator adapts the voicing to the situation. For instance, if the narrator is inside a church, she/he will be whispering. If the narrator is in a lively market, she/he may seem excited to go shopping.

In the Extended AD, it is up to the viewer whether to trigger the extended descriptions beyond the first instance. In order to trigger, the viewer would need to tap the mousepad twice after hearing a short beep that would indicate the presence of extended description track. Once triggered, the main video would pause for the duration for the extended description and then continue once it had ended. The duration of tracks varied between 20 – 45 seconds and gave additional information on those aspects of the video that were not crucial for understanding of the story but gave details to build further familiarity with different aspects of the content. For example: the first instance of this mode in the first episode described the main anchor, her attire and the general look - feel of the content.

To avoid the terminology having an impact on the test, the conditions were referred to as AD-C, AD-R, and AD-E when presented to the users.

7.3.1. Measures

The measures chosen were presence and preferences. For presence, IPQ was used. For preferences, a specific questionnaire was developed in English:

- Which AD type do you prefer in 360°? Rank the AD modes according to your preferences: 1-preferred mode, 2-second preferred mode, 3-the least preferred mode.
- Please explain why you ranked the AD modes in this way.
- How could AD be improved in this medium?
- Other comments

7.3.2. Participants

The same participants as in the player interface test. See 4.7.2.

7.3.3. Materials

Three episodes from the *Holy Land* series were created with the AD in the three selected modes, as follows:

- *Holy Land*, episode 1, in three conditions: Classic, Radio, Extended, in English. Length: 05:05
- *Holy Land*, episode 2, in three conditions: Classic, Radio, Extended, in English. Length: 03:56
- *Holy Land*, episode 3, in three conditions: Classic, Radio, Extended, in English. Length: 04:01

An audio introduction was also included, so that the user could learn more about the content. Demographic questionnaires, IPQ questionnaire, and preference questionnaire were also available in an online form. Participants used an HMD for the test.

7.3.4. Experimental protocol

The procedure was the same as in the pre-pilot, as it had worked well:

- Participants are welcomed and ImAc project and test is presented (face-to-face)

- Ethical clearance: participants are assigned with an individual participant code and sign informed consent forms (paper copies)
- Participants fill in a demographic questionnaire (online). Participants have time to ask additional questions
- User interface pilot action
- Participants listen to one general audio introduction and then watch three clips in randomised presentation modes, and reply to IPQ questionnaire after each clip. Finally, they fill in the post-questionnaire (preference questions).
- Audio subtitling pilot action
- Participants are thanked

7.3.5. Results

Concerning presence, the median values for IPQ for RNIB, in the three conditions for each subscale are shown in Table 36.

	General Presence	Spatial Presence	Involvement	Experienced Realism
Radio	4.61	4.32	3.97	3.99
Extended	4.61	4.22	4.22	3.92
Classic	4.32	4.10	3.90	3.83

Table 36: Median values for IPQ cross-national (RNIB)

A non-parametric test was carried to compare the IPQ scores of blind and partially-sighted users, due to difference in participants' number (22 and 9, respectively). The Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U test [16] comparing the results for each subscale did not show any significant difference (all $P > .05$). Therefore, the rest of the tests have been conducted on the whole users' sample ($N=31$) using parametric statistics.

Paired samples statistics T-tests, comparing each subscale result with that of each other did not show any statistically significant difference. The IPQ scale results are not different for each type of audio description. They do not differ in General Presence (all $p > .05$); not for Spatial Presence (all $p > .05$); and neither for Experienced realism (all $p > .05$).

According to these results, the type of AD does not have any effect on the presence for the users of this sample.

When asked what type of AD they prefer, results are as follows (Table 37).

	AD-C	AD-R	AD-E
1 preferred mode	11 (35.5%)	13 (41.93%)	9 (29%)
2 preferred mode	9 (29%)	14 (45.16%)	10 (32.25%)
3 preferred mode	11 (35.5%)	4 (12.9%)	12 (38.70%)

Table 37: Results on preferences in cross-national (RNIB): AD modes

Most participants who rated the Classic mode as their most preferred option commented how much it resembled the service on TV and this was how audio description was meant to sound. However, other participants, mostly occasional viewers of TV programmes and, therefore, occasional users of AD felt this mode lacked the feel of the original content which affected

their enjoyment and immersion. Participants who chose the Radio mode as their most preferred option commented that the experience of listening to this track was much more satisfying as they got a lot more out of it than the Classic mode, particularly when it came to perceiving the feel of the content. It was interesting to note, in contrast to the classic version, a fair majority of the participants who chose this as their preferred option tended to be occasional viewers of TV programmes and therefore AD. Instead, audio content such as radio dramas, talking books and podcasts was their choice of media. However, not all participants found this mode enjoyable or even useful as the standard description offered in the Classic version. They felt it relied heavily on the interpretation of the describer which influenced how they felt about the content.

Most participants felt that whilst Extended AD added to the overall feel of the content, it would probably not work for the content they watched on TV. Among others, reasons cited were that they would find it hard to sustain interest in the content with the additional details and affecting the overall enjoyment of the programme. Gaming, live tours in museums and heritage sites were given as examples of where this presentation mode might work well. However, not all agreed.

Although all the three modes for audio description and the two for audio subtitles delivered an experience consistent with the general expectations of using access features for most end users, none were reported as fully immersive. As 360° format was described as a gamified – somewhat gimmicky experience, participants expected the description to be appropriately striking for that experience. Among other aspects, participants agreed that an immersive soundscape would also impact orientation which is a crucial part of ‘involvement’, knowing where the action is happening. Traditional 360 experiences for sighted audiences rely heavily on viewers responding to sounds as it generates higher level of immersion as one if involved in the video. Therefore, the same rules apply to people with sight loss which may be achieved by spatial audio.

7.4. Cross-national pilot: AD presentation modes (UAB)

The main features of the AD presentation test are as follows:

- **Users:** 31
- **Dates:** January-February 2020
- **Format:** face-to-face

7.4.1. Measures

The same measures as for the RNIB test were used, with documents into Catalan and Spanish. See 7.3.1.

7.4.2. Participants

The same participants as in the player interface test. See 4.8.2.

7.4.3. Materials

The same three episodes from the *Holy Land* series used for the UK test were used. The audio descriptions in English were translated into Catalan and voiced by a Catalan voice talent. The final materials were: *Holy Land*, episodes 1, 2, and 3.

An audio introduction was also included in Catalan, so that the user could learn a bit more about the content. Demographic questionnaires, IPQ questionnaire, and preference questionnaire were also available in an online form.

7.4.4. Experimental protocol

The procedure was the same as in the UK cross-national pilot (see 7.3.4.).

7.4.5. Results

30 replies were obtained from participants. One was not correctly recorded. Concerning presence, the median values for IPQ for UAB, in the three conditions for each subscale are shown in Table 38.

	General Presence	Spatial Presence	Involvement	Experienced Realism
Radio	4.70	4.55	5.04	3.54
Extended	4.73	4.64	4.86	3.63
Classic	4.73	4.62	4.97	3.40

Table 38: Median values for IPQ cross-national (UAB)

A paired samples t-test was used in order to compare the scores on each subscale across the different types of AD. None of these comparisons gave a statistically significant difference (all $p > .05$). Table 39 presents the results obtained by each user type (blind/partially sighted) in each IPQ subscale, with the p value of each comparison. Coloured rows show significant differences.

		General presence	Spatial presence	Involvement	Experienced realism
Radio	Blind	3.83	3.9167	4.8750	3.1458
	Partially sighted	5.28	4.9778	5.1528	3.8056
	$p=$	0.040	0.087	0.640	0.280
Extended AD	Blind	3.83	4.0333	4.5208	3.3750
	Partially sighted	5.33	5.0444	5.0833	3.8056
	$p=$	0.036	0.087	0.313	0.529
Classic AD	Blind	3.50	3.5500	4.6667	2.7292
	Partially sighted	5.56	5.3333	5.1806	3.8472
	$p=$	0.004	0.004	0.332	0.075

Table 39: IPQ results for blind and partially sighted users (UAB, cross-national)

A one-way ANOVA comparing the results of blind vs partially-sighted users shows that there are significant differences in General Presence across all types of AD. Scores are higher for partially sighted users. In addition, for Classic AD, scores for spatial presence are also significantly higher for partially-sighted users. There is also a trend to significance for Radio Drama and Extended AD ($p = .087$).

When asked what type of AD they prefer, results are as follows (Table 40).

	AD-C (Classic)	AD-R (Radio)	AD-E (Extended)
1 preferred mode	10 (32.25%)	8 (25.8%)	13 (41.93%)
2 preferred mode	10 (32.25%)	11 (35.48%)	10 (32.25%)
3 preferred mode	11 (35.48%)	12 (38.70%)	8 (25.8%)

Table 40: Results on preferences in cross-national (UAB): AD modes

Classic AD was the preferred option for 10 participants. Some users expressed the reasons behind their choice. One user found the visual information in this AD type more complete, and two users said that this AD type allowed them to imagine the sphere better. Four users said that the level of visual details in AD-R is not sufficient and two other users commented that the scripting style of AD-R does not resemble AD, but it is more like a separate narration. UAB15 said that listening to AD-C was like listening AD in standard TV (and for this content another type of scripting is better) - this person assessed better the script in AD-R.

Three participants liked the three modes equally. Two users commented positively on ambient sounds in AD-R which made the experience more realistic and one participant commented positively on the emotive language in this type of AD.

17 participants commented positively on AD-E, the reasons being the possibility to interact with the content or the possibility to listen more at will, get more details or feeling more immersed. One participant said that extended AD should include audio description, but not titbits (such information should be provided only in the video).

The improvements in AD that participants proposed include:

- being oriented towards the described places, characters and objects (4 participants),
- having extended ADs (7 participants),
- having spatial sound (2 participants),
- having ambient sounds (2 participants) more in the front line, and
- to feel more present in the content, one participant suggested to integrate an information about the weather, temperature or textures in the script of AD.

One participant suggested how extended AD could be improved. This participant would like extended AD to be more integrated with the video, so that the main video is not cut so abruptly. To this end, participant suggested that extended AD could start and end with ambient sounds/music present in the main video. Two participants commented that the 'bell' sound signaling extended AD is not distinctive enough and proposed to change it, or to introduce it first in audio introduction, so that users know which sound to expect. One participant would like to have a possibility to adjust the sound of AD. The additional comments of 5 participants suggest that those participants would need to have more senses involved to feel more present in the storyworld.

7.5. Conclusions

It is important to highlight that the focus for both the pre-pilot actions 2 at RNIB and UAB was not so much on getting results with such a small sample but rather than on testing the methodology and seeing whether the test was feasible. Overall the methodology proved useful but there were some setbacks concerning the AD presentation modes. Many users could not actually perceive the difference between the audio presentations initially tested in the project (Classic, Dynamic, Static) and actually focused more on the specificities of the script. This

showed their interest on scripting. It also rose some concerns about what content is more suitable for what type of audio treatment.

Considering this situation, the AD presentation modes were reconsidered for the cross-national pilot. Building on user feedback, the final AD presentation modes that were tested were:

- Classic AD mode
- Radio AD mode
- Extended AD mode

This approach proved useful, and the cross-national shed some light on user preferences and presence. Concerning presence, and taking into account the IPQ questionnaire, the presence experienced in the three AD presentation modes was not statistically significant in any of the two pilot actions, hence proving that it makes sense to incorporate all three modes and let users choose according to their preferences. The only statistically significant difference was found in the users from Barcelona, where partially sighted felt more immersed in terms of general presence than sighted users. However, this effect was found in all three conditions. In terms of spatial presence, Classic AD also seemed to work better with partially-sighted participants. In any case, these results support the statement that users should be given the possibility to choose.

Concerning preferences, Table 41 summarises the results of both pilots.

	AD-C (Classic)		AD-R (Radio)		AD-E (Extended)	
	RNIB	UAB	RNIB	UAB	RNIB	UAB
1 preferred	11 (35.5%)	10 (32.25%)	13 (41.93%)	8 (25.8%)	9 (29%)	13 (41.93%)
2 preferred	9 (29%)	10 (32.25%)	14 (45.16%)	11 (35.48%)	10 (32.25%)	10 (32.25%)
3 preferred	11 (35.5%)	11 (35.48%)	4 (12.9%)	12 (38.70%)	12 (38.70%)	8 (25.8%)

Table 41: Results on preferences in cross-national (RNIB-UAB): AD modes

In the UK, AD-Radio the first preferred mode was the Radio mode, whilst in Spain it was the Extended audio description. It should be noted, though, that the voice talents were different and they were watching different versions (English/Catalan) of the same content, hence a strict comparison is not possible, as there may be other factors that influence the results such as the voicing or the actual word choice.

In the UK, the preference for Classic, Radio or Extended description was somewhat linked to the type of content they watched. Viewers with greater interest in documentaries or audio content in general tended to the radio drama mode or even the extended description. However, regular drama or film viewers leaned towards the familiar classic mode for audio description. In Spain, this aspect was not mentioned in the questionnaire, and the preference for the Extended version seemed to be linked to the feeling of being there and the possibility to activate this option according to the user's preference.

It is evident from the feedback gathered during this pilot that the preference for specific format depends on the level of sight loss, the type of sight condition, genre of content and other creative elements such as type voice, intonation, delivery etc.

Lastly, participants in the UK with significant sight loss repeated their desire to enjoy these experiences without HMD as they found them unnecessary and isolating.

8. TESTING THE AST PRESENTATION MODES

Presentation modes for AST have been tested in ImAc in different stages (see Table 5 for a whole list and Figure 10 for testing conditions):

- During development:
 - Pre-pilot action 1 at RNIB and UAB (see D2.1)
 - Pre-pilot action 2 at RNIB and UAB
- During implementation:
 - Cross-national pilot action at RNIB and UAB

Results from both actions are reported here, following the same structure:

- General description of the pilot action: users, version, dates and format
- Measures used, based on framework presented in Figures 12 and 13. If an ad-hoc preference questionnaire is used, it is reproduced in this section.
- Participants' description, summarising the data obtained through the demographic questionnaires. Given that we are within the realm of media accessibility, it was decided to take a wider approach to testing and use different user profiles who claim using subtitles.
- Materials, presenting the different materials and content used for the tests.
- The experimental protocol, which follows the general framework in Figure 14.
- Results, with a discussion of the main results of the pilot action. More specific details, with a thorough reproduction of all replies, are included in the full reports included as annexes.

Full methodology for pre-pilot 2 is in Annex 26, and reports are available in Annexes 27 (RNIB) and 28 (UAB). Methodology for the cross-national is found in Annex 29, and reports in Annex 30 (RNIB) and 31 (UAB).

8.1. RNIB pre-pilot action 2

The main features of the AST presentation test are as follows:

- **Users:** 5
- **Dates:** 07.05.2019-27.05.2019
- **Format:** face-to-face

The aim was to test the methodology for the cross-national pilot. Two presentation modes, namely Classic, and Dynamic, were considered in the test. Classic mode is a standard option in which audio subtitling is heard from above user's head. The last type is called Dynamic – which means that the sound of AST is placed on the location of the speaker.

Figure 80: Presentation modes used in RNIB AST test

To avoid the terminology having an impact on the test, the conditions were referred to as AD-C, and AD-D when presented to the users.

8.1.1. Measures

The measures chosen were presence and preferences. For presence, IPQ was used. For preferences, a specific questionnaire was developed in English:

- Which type of AST do you prefer in 360°? AST-C/AST-D
- Explain in your own words why you prefer the option chosen in the first question.
- What system would you prefer?
 - Audio subtitles with no subtitles on screen.
 - Audio subtitles with subtitles on screen that can be enlarged.
 - I would like to select when I want subtitles on screen and when not.
- Would you like to have an AD together with the AST?
 - Yes
 - No
 - It depends on the content.
- Explain in your own words your choice in the previous question.
- How could audio subtitles be improved in this medium?
- Other comments

8.1.2. Participants

The same users as in the other RNIB pre-pilot action 2 took part in the test. Please refer to 4.5.2 for a full description.

8.1.3. Materials

The content chosen for the AST test was an Opera clip was cut in two parts: clip 1 (00:00 - 03:44) and clip 2 (03:44 - 08:29). A short audio introduction was also created. It gave the general overview of two clips. The audio introduction was integrated in the player and participants listened to it before watching the first clip.

The AST were produced using the RNIB synthetic voice, and a human voice was used for the audio introduction.

Demographic questionnaires, IPQ questionnaire, and preference questionnaire were available in English in an online form.

8.1.4. Experimental protocol

The procedure is as follows:

- Participants are welcomed and ImAc project and test is presented (face-to-face)
- Ethical clearance: participants sign informed consent forms (paper copies)
- Participants fill in a demographic questionnaire (online)
- User interface pilot action
- AD pilot action.
- Participants watch two audio subtitled clips in randomised presentation modes, and reply to IPQ questionnaire after each clip
- Participants reply to preference questionnaire
- Participants are thanked

8.1.5. Results

Concerning presence, the median values for IPQ for RNIB, in the two conditions for each subscale are shown in Table 42.

	General Presence	Spatial Presence	Involvement	Experienced Realism
Classic	.00	.60	2.50	.25
Dynamic	2.00	1.40	1.75	.75

Table 42: Median values for IPQ: AST pre-pilot action 2 (RNIB)

The Wilcoxon signed ranks test does not show any difference for either condition: General presence ($Z=-1.342$, ties=3, $p=.180$); Spatial presence ($Z= -.542$, ties=0, $p=.588$); Involvement ($Z= -.356$, ties= 1, $p= .715$), Experienced realism ($Z= -.412$, ties= 0, $p= .680$)

Similar to the response for audio description, most of the testers could not tell the difference between the different presentation modes for audio subtitles with the exception of one tester who felt the classic mode was more immersive than the dynamic. They simply stated choosing one random option because the “had to choose an answer” to proceed. Therefore, results are not presented in a Table format as they lack validity.

Some of the testers felt that this treatment might have worked better had it been used for documentaries in a foreign language with audio description rather than on an opera content. One tester stated that, while watching the opera, they wanted to listen to the music.

On the issue of having audio subtitles together with subtitles, there was an equal split between the number of testers who did not want any subtitles on screen and testers who wanted the choice to be able to turn it off and on. One tester wanted subtitles that can be enlarged.

Most users, except for one, stated that depending on the content they would like to have an AD together with the AST.

Some suggestions related to the user personalisation of the volum settings and to the features of the text-to-speech voice, which some users would like to be “more enthusiastic” and “less bored”.

Given the responses, it is evident that further work is needed to explore how a documentary in 360° with stereo sound can be made immersive for audio description and audio subtitling users.

8.2. UAB pre-pilot action 2

The main features of the AST presentation test are as follows. They replicated the RNIB test.

- **Users:** 5
- **Dates:** June 2019
- **Format:** face-to-face

The aim was to test the methodology for the cross-national test. Two presentation modes, namely Classic, and Dynamic, were considered in the test, as in the RNIB action.

8.2.1. Measures

The measures chosen were presence and preferences. For presence, IPQ was used. For preferences, the English questionnaire presented in 7.2.1 was translated into Spanish and Catalan.

8.2.2. Participants

The same users as in the other UAB pre-pilot action 2 took part in the test. Please refer to 4.6.2 for a full description.

8.2.3. Materials

The content chosen for the AST test was the same Opera clip as in the RNIB test, presented in 7.1.3. The English version was translated into Spanish by UAB and voiced by a text-to-speech female voice provided by Verbio.² The same clips as for the RNIB AST test were produced.

The English audio introduction was also translated into Spanish and voiced by a voice talent at CCMA. Demographic questionnaires, IPQ questionnaire, and preference questionnaire were available in Spanish in an online form.

8.2.4. Experimental protocol

The procedure followed RNIB's protocol described in 8.1.4.

8.2.5. Results

Concerning presence, the median values for IPQ for UAB, in the two conditions for each subscale are shown in Table 43.

	General Presence	Spatial Presence	Involvement	Experienced Realism
Classic	2.50	2.70	3.63	1.63
Dynamic	2.50	3.00	4.25	1.63

Table 43: Median values for IPQ: AST pre-pilot action 2 (UAB)

² We would like to thank Verbio for providing the text-to-speech excerpts to ImAc project.

The Wilcoxon signed ranks test does not show any difference for either condition: General presence ($Z=-1.000$, ties=5, $p=.317$); Spatial presence ($Z= -1.069$, ties=3, $p=.285$); Involvement ($Z= -.954$, ties= 0, $p= .340$); Experienced realism ($Z= .000$, ties= 1, $p= 1.000$).

4 testers chose AST-C and 2 testers chose AST-D. However, their selection seemed to be more motivated by the video content and audio subtitles, rather than audio treatment. One user complained that the audio subtitling was not hearable and suggested higher volumes for the AST as well as a better intonation. Overall, it seems that they were not able to perceive the differences and, moreover, they were generally not able to locate the action based on sound cues in the Dynamic mode. However, one user could perceive the difference and indicated that thanks to the music you feel more immersed.

When consuming content with audio subtitles, 66.7% of participants would prefer to select when subtitles should be visible on screen, and the rest would prefer audio subtitles with no subtitles on screen. When asked if they would prefer to listen to AD together with AST, most participants (66.7%) stated that it would depend on the content. In Opera, for instance, some users do not like the AD to cover the singing and are more in favour of an audio introduction.

Some suggestions made by the users related to the prosodic features of the voice and the volume, as well as the overlapping with the sung passages. Other users were satisfied, saying that they like audio subtitles very much (UAB4) and were happy with the Dynamic option (UAB1). Some other comments referred to the acoustic elements in the video content, and to the quality of the translations.

8.3. Cross-national pilot: AST presentation modes (RNIB)

The main features of the AST presentation test are as follows:

- **Users:** 31
- **Dates:** 5.11.2019-30.01.2020
- **Format:** face-to-face

Considering user feedback in the pre-pilot action 2, it was decided to test two conditions: audio subtitling only, and audio subtitling with audio description, both with the same sound features. For coding purposes, we will refer to these modes as AST and AST-AD. In all cases a human voice was used.

8.3.1. Measures

The measures chosen were preferences. Due to the results of the pre-pilot action 2, it was decided not to test presence with the IPQ questionnaire and only ask a question about their perceived presence. The same questionnaire from the pre-pilot action was adapted considering the new modes, as follows:

- Which type of AST do you prefer in 360°? AST/AST-AD
- Explain in your own words why you prefer the option chosen in the first question.
- What system would you prefer?
 - Audio subtitles with no subtitles on screen.
 - Audio subtitles with subtitles on screen that can be enlarged.
 - I would like to select when I want subtitles on screen and when not.
- How could audio subtitles be improved in this medium?
- In what excerpt did you feel more present?

- Only AST
- AST-AD
- I did not feel present in any of them
- I felt equally present in both
- Other comments:

8.3.2. Participants

The same participants as in the player interface and the AD cross-national test. See 4.7.2.

8.3.3. Materials

The content chosen for the AST test was an Opera clip, cut in two parts: clip 1 (00:00 - 03:44) and clip 2 (03:44 - 08:29). A short audio introduction was also created. It gave the general overview of two clips. The audio introduction was integrated in the player and participants listened to it before watching the first clip.

The AST in the two modes and the audio introductions were produced using human voices.

Demographic questionnaire and preference questionnaire were available in English in an online form.

8.3.4. Experimental protocol

The procedure is as follows:

- Participants are welcomed and ImAc project and test is presented (face-to-face)
- Ethical clearance: participants sign informed consent forms (paper copies)
- Participants fill in a demographic questionnaire (online)
- User interface pilot action
- AD pilot action
- Participants watch two audio subtitled clips in randomised presentation modes and reply to the preference questionnaire
- Participants reply to preference questionnaire
- Participants are thanked

8.3.5. Results

23 participants (74.2%) stated that they preferred a combination of the two with only 8 participants (25.8%) preferring audio subtitles on their own. When asked in which mode of the two did they feel more present, 11 participants (35%) said they preferred a combination of audio description and audio subtitles. 9 participants (29%) said they did not feel present in either of the two formats. 8 participants (25%) said they preferred only audio subtitles, and 3 participants (10%) said they felt equally present in both.

There was a clear preference for both AD and AST to be provided, but some participants offered other potential solutions that had not been explored in this test. Participants with greater interest in opera and musical content in general had significantly different feedback to participants familiar with the content of the clips used. Whilst some participants wanted to enjoy the music, others wanted a radio-mode version of the dialogues.

On the subtitles specifically, when asked if they would want subtitles in audio only or with on-screen subtitles in text, 14 participants (45.2%) said they would not want subtitles on-screen. Another 13 participants (41.9%) also stated that they would want the option to select whether to have on-screen subtitles in text. 4 (12.9%) said they would want on-screen subtitles that could be enlarged. The preference for subtitles in audio or text was largely dependent on the type and level of sight loss. More significant loss meant audio was the preferred format.

8.4. Cross-national pilot: AST presentation modes (UAB)

The main features of the AST presentation test are as follows:

- **Users:** 31
- **Dates:** January-February 2020
- **Format:** face-to-face

8.4.1. Measures

The same measures as in the UK cross-national test were used. See 8.3.1.

8.4.2. Participants

The same participants as in the player interface and the AD cross-national test. See 4.8.2.

8.4.3. Materials

The same materials as in the UK cross-national test were used (see 8.3.3.), translated in all cases into Spanish.

8.4.4. Experimental protocol

The same protocol as in the UK cross-national test were used. See 8.3.4.

8.4.5. Results

16 participants (55.2%) preferred the AST option, while 13 participants chose AST with AD (44.8%). Participants who chose the AST option indicate that this type of narration allows users to follow dialogues in real time, follows the libretto more closely and allows users to listen only to the original dialogues without additional interpretation. Some participants felt distracted when listening to the AST-AD. On the contrary, those selecting the AST-AD option stated that they felt more immersed in the original content and liked the fact that the narration is provided in larger chunks instead of having the video “cut” by frequent audio subtitles. The fact that the AST-AD included more details was also appreciated.

10 participants reported feeling more present when only AST were used (34.5%), although 9 participants felt equally presented in both (31%) and 8 participants in the AD-AST combination (27.6%). Two participants (6.9%) reported not feeling present in any of them. When asked about their preference on how to visualise the subtitles on screen, 13 participants (44.8%) indicated they would prefer audio subtitles with no subtitles on screen (45% of those participants were partially sighted and 55% were blind). 16 participants (55.2%, mostly partially sighted) said they would like to be able to choose, and none requested audio subtitles with subtitles that can be enlarged.

Possible improvements suggested by the participants are: (a) to make the AST track adjustable by the user and independent from the original soundtrack, (b) to have extended AD in the

videos with audio subtitles to learn more about the clothes and other details; (c) to have different voices for different characters, and (d) to have the AST read with another intonation.

8.5. Conclusions

The pre-pilot 2 actions at RNIB and UAB allowed to test two AST modes based on audio features, but this did not prove a successful approach. Some audio issues were found with the conditions presented to the participants. The differences in the audio treatment were difficult to perceive in this type of content by some users. Moreover, in the UK they were not familiar with opera AST, which raised some concerns. This is why this approach was revised based on the user feedback gathered, and two new alternatives were tested in the cross-national: AST only versus AST with AD. The methodology was also revised and it was decided not to use the IPQ questionnaire for this test for practical reasons, in order to avoid increasing tiresome of the participants. The focus was on preferences. Results are summarised in the following table.

		RNIB	UAB
Preference	AST	8 (25.8%)	16 (55.2%)
	AST-AD	23 (74.2%)	13 (44.8%)
More immersed in...	AST	8 (25.8%)	10 (34.5%)
	AST-AD	11 (35.5%)	8 (27.6%)
	Equally in both	3 (9.7%)	9 (31%)
	In none	9 (29%)	2 (6.9%)
How to visualise subtitles on screen?	AST with no subtitles on screen	14 (45.2%)	13 (44.8%)
	Possibility to choose	4 (12.9%)	16 (55.2%)
	Subtitles on screen that can be enlarged	13 (41.9%)	0 (0%)

Table 44: Summary of results for AST tests (UAB and RNIB)

Results show that preferences and self-reported immersion differ across countries, which may be due to the different stimuli and voices used, but also may be related to cultural factors, different habits or practices in accessible opera production. In this regard, any comparison should be taken cautiously as the source file was the same (an opera excerpt), but the access services were produced with different voices and different languages. It should be highlighted that opera audio subtitling and audio description is a reality in Spain, but users in the UK are not so used to this practice. This may explain the lower numbers in the UK when assessing AST only and, especially, when indicating that none of the modes allowed them to feel immersed. In this regard, despite the focus on scripting, in the UK most participants reiterated the need for an immersive soundscape for greater immersion regardless of whether the content was provided with audio description only or a combination of both audio description and audio subtitles.

In any case, beyond individual and group preferences, what data seem to show is that both approaches (AD/AST-AD) have a place in the production of accessible content, depending on various factors such as type of sight loss, content type and previous experience.

9. PILOT PHASE 2: GERMAN AND SPANISH PILOTS

Pilot phase 2 included an open pilot in Germany and an open pilot in Spain. The ImAc player with accessible content was published on RBB and CCMA's website in order to see how users actually interacted with the immersive content. The focus was on subtitles and, additionally in the German pilot, on German Sign Language. Tables 45 and 46 provide an overview of the overall reach of the pilot. In total, the created and/or adapted 360° videos with access services were watched up to 1,360 times, reaching 428 visualisations in the German pilot, 788 in the Spanish pilot, and the 144 remaining ones from the General ImAc branches. This means an average of over 40 videos watched per day, which is a quite relevant result. Up to seven 360° videos were watched more than 100 times, as shown in Table 46, reaching two of them (*360° Abdenschau* and *El Telenotícies per dins*) over 200 visualisations. Out of these 1,360 videos, 48 were consumed in VR mode (32 in the Spanish pilot, 14 in the German pilot, and 2 in the general branches of the ImAc player).

Player Branch	Videos watched
<i>General ImAc branches</i>	144
http://imac.i2cat.net/player/	109
http://imac.i2cat.net/playertest/	35
<i>German pilot</i>	428
http://imac.i2cat.net/player_de/	382
http://imac.i2cat.net/player_en/	46
<i>Spanish pilot</i>	788
HbbTV Multi-Screen Scenario	155
Web-based Multi-Screen Scenario	249
360° Video Portal	384
TOTAL	1,360

Table 45: Total videos watched, per pilot and player branch

Content	Count
El Telenotícies per dins	260
360° Abdenschau	216
Polònia 360	185
Making of FAQs	130
Täter Opfer Polizei	121
I, Philip	120
Cuinant en 360°	111
Diada de Santa Jordi	64
Liceu Opera Piece 1	59
Òpera Romeo i Juliette al Liceu	41
Desconcert "Leyre"	20
Desconcert "Havanna"	14
Holy Land Episode 4	13
Liceu Opera Piece 2	4
Rapzember	2
Total	1,360

Table 46: Number of times each 360° video has been watched

The ImAc open pilots reached 827 users (313 users from the German pilot, 233 users from general Imac branches, and 281 users from the Spanish pilots), in 1,319 sessions (821 from the German pilot plus general branches, and 498 sessions from the Spanish pilot).

The specific details of each pilot are presented next. Results from the General ImAc branches are presented in the German pilot section.

9.1. German pilot phase 2 (RBB)

Links to open pilot websites:

English:

<https://rbb-online.de/imac-user-test> and <https://rbb-online.de/imac-user-tests>

German:

<https://rbb-online.de/imac-nutzertest> and <https://rbb-online.de/imac-nutzertests>

These websites are linking to the ImAc portal in German http://imac.i2cat.net/player_de/ and English http://imac.i2cat.net/player_en/.

9.1.1. Measures

Three different measurement tools were used in the open pilots: Google Analytics; and *ad-hoc* communication system and database to track Quality of Service (QoS) and Quality of Experience (QoE) related metrics; and a questionnaire about the consumption experience. Note that the metrics from the two measurement tools were **ONLY** registered if the visiting user gave their consent through a popup shown when accessing the ImAc portal/player for the first time, by using cookies. This is shown in the next two figures.

Figure 81: Data privacy text and ask for consent on tracking the user behavior and QoS metrics

Google Analytics

Google Analytics is a web analytics service offered by Google that allows tracking the traffic and users' activity for websites, and even for mobile apps.

This service has been used in ImAc to register all accesses to the different player branches and the associated pages, as well as to track the usage of all offered services and options, by tagging the associated controls. In particular, the following information has been tracked for the open pilot:

- Player Branches
 - Access URL (i.e. from what player URL each user accesses the ImAc portal / player)
- Info about users
 - Random ID (the IP addressed is NOT registered)
 - Access time
 - Region
 - Type of device used (and even brand and screen resolution for mobile devices)
 - Operating System used
 - Browser used and languages
- Users' Activity / Behavior
 - Sessions per user, pages views and pages per session, and bounce rate
 - Session duration
 - New user or returning user, and recurrence distribution
 - Acquisition Information (i.e. from where the users access the ImAc portal/player)
 - Users Flow (i.e. from what regions the different branches are accessed)
- Users' Activity when using the ImAc portal / player
 - Events Flow: from what parts / options to what parts / option the users go
 - The portal options and settings used.
 - The contents selected for consumption
 - The player services, options and setting used, both in VR mode and in traditional mode.

The next definitions will allow a better understanding of the collected metrics:

- Users: Users who have initiated at least one session during the data collection period.
- New Users: The number of first-time users during the selected data collection period.
- Sessions: Total number of sessions in the data collection period. A session is the period of time a user is actively engaged with the website, app, etc.
- Bounce Rate: The percentage of single-page sessions in which there was no interaction with the page. A bounced session has a duration of 0 seconds.
- Pages/Session (Average Page Depth): The average number of pages viewed during a session. Repeated views of a single page are counted.
- Unique Events: A count of the number of times an event with a specific category/action/label value was seen at least once within a session.

NOTE: Two different Google Analytics accounts were used in the open pilot. One was created and operated by i2CAT, as technical coordinator of the pilot. This account registers (if users consent) the information from the player releases used in the German pilot, embedded with the RBB website, **but also from other player releases**. However, CCMA showed concerns with that decision, and decided to use their already existing Google Analytics account, as service provider, only for the Spanish pilot.

QoS / QoE metrics logging

In addition to Google Analytics, i2CAT developed a communication system that allows registering key QoS and QoE related metrics in a server hosted at i2CAT premises. The core functionalities of the end-to-end logging system are described in Montagud et al. 2019 [17]. On the one hand, the system registers QoE metrics by using the Application Programming Interface (API) of the DASH reference player [18], which is a core component of the ImAc player. On the other hand, the system registers further relevant metrics, and all the interaction with the player elements / controls.

In conjunction, the following data is registered:

- Unique Session ID
- Viewing mode: VR o Traditional
- URL of ImAc player branch (CCMA, RBB, ImAc general...)
- URL of MPD for the selected content (i.e. selected video)
- Global time / NTP Date
- DASH related metrics, for each segment
 - Startup delay (i.e. delay since pressing play and watching the video)
 - Quality level for each DASH (video) segment
 - Buffer Fullness level
 - Throughput (i.e. effective bandwidth)
- Video Evolution
 - Media Time (this can then be mapped with the absolute / NTP Date time). From this information, the playout duration and smoothness can be calculated.
 - Playout Controls (Play, Pause, Seek...)
 - If multi-screen session: Asynchrony with other devices in the same session
- Viewing Patterns (latitude, longitude)
- Player Menu Interactions (Settings...)
- Access Services interactions
 - ST Service (including all its settings and personalization features)
 - SL Service (including all its settings and personalization features)

- AD Service (including all its settings and personalization features)
- AST Service (including all its settings and personalization features)

NOTE: In order to track all this information, a JSON message with the format shown below is sent every 0.5s from the player to the logging server, via websockets.

```
{"vr":false,"calculatedDiff":0,"msId":"","playerUrl":"http://imac.i2cat.net/player_de/player/#3",
"url":"https://imac.gpac-licensing.com/imac_content/pilot_1/RBB_lphilip/stream.mpd","quality":11,"mediaTime":789.515291,
"currentBufferLevel":62.485,"averageThroughput":75192.5,"messageType":"INFO","date":1583923539870,
"sessionId":"6f9a3928-a99f-4b80-aa9e-d4b5c9f5e0ea","contentId":"3","viewLon":"0","viewLat":"0","viewZ":"-1",
"viewY":"0","viewX":"0"}
```

NOTE: Please, note that all the above listed metrics and information are not strongly related to the ImAc main goals. However, it was decided to register all this information to create a valuable dataset that will allow the research community to be aware and better understand how users receive and interact with 360° videos in an open (i.e. not controlled) environment. Processing the whole amount of data would had required large efforts. Therefore, the deliverable is focused on the key ImAc related statistics.

Questionnaire

Additionally, a questionnaire was created and included to gather qualitative data. The questionnaire is available from the pilot portal and additionally a link was integrated in a pop-up which appears after the end of a video, asking to the user if she/he wants either watch more videos (redirect to pilot website) or to give feedback through an online questionnaire. It contains the following questions translated into German: https://lamapoll.de/ImAc_Feedback_Pilot2

1. Age:
2. I define myself as...
 - a. A hearing person
 - b. A person with hearing loss
3. Have you watched 360 contents before? Yes/No
4. How did you watch the 360 content? PC/HMD/tablet/mobile phone
5. Did you use the subtitles? Yes/No
If yes, how much did you like... (5-point Likert scale) / I did not use it
 - i. Arrow (menu under indicator)
 - ii. Radar (menu under indicator)
 - iii. Size personalisation
 - iv. Position personalisation
 - v. Background personalisation
 - vi. Subtitle control with mouse/controller
6. Did you use Sign Language? Yes/No
If yes, how much did you like... ((5-point Likert scale) / I did not use it
 - i. Arrow (menu under indicator)
 - ii. Radar (menu under indicator)
 - iii. Size personalisation
 - iv. Position personalisation
 - v. Display of subtitles and SL together

- vi. Name of speaker under SL video window
 - vii. SL interpreter only visible when someone is speaking (menu under Dynamic)
 - viii. The drag-and-drop functionality of the SL interpreter
7. How easy to use was the player? (5-point Likert scale: very difficult-very easy)
 8. Would you recommend the player to your friends? Yes/No.
- If you want, you can give us additional feedback here.

9.1.2. Participants

According to Google Analytics, up to 285 users accessed to the German version of the RBB portal/player (*/player_de* release) and up to 28 users accessed to the English version of the RBB portal/player (*/player_en* release), which together results in **313 users for the German pilot**. 284 of these users accessed from Germany. In **total, 546 users** accessed the different portal/player branches excluding CCMA's data. More details about the users, their activity and behavior will be provided in the results sub-section.

Regarding the questionnaire, 31 replies were obtained. These included 20 hearing persons (65%) and 11 persons with hearing loss (35%), who had generally watched 360° contents before (68%), on a PC (77%) but also on an HMD (14%), on a tablet (10%) and on a mobile phone (16%). Mean age was 41.

All these data are referred to the period from February 17th to March 17th.

9.1.3. Materials

A portal and a player version in German and in English were prepared to run the open pilot, as mentioned before. The portal included the following materials:

- the questionnaire described under measures,
- an introduction with information about the project,
- an introduction to the test: what they will be able to see and how they can access the content and
- data protection and ethical information.

The contents that were available in the German open pilot were:

- **360° Abendschau**, with subtitles in German and German Sign Language.
- **I, Phillip**, with subtitles in German (and other languages such as English, Spanish, German) and German Sign Language.
- **Täter | Opfer | Polizei**, with subtitles in German and English and German Sign Language.

We had in total four different pilot websites which as due to restricted rights concerning the *Täter | Opfer | Polizei* content and the provision of an English and German version. The *Täter | Opfer | Polizei* content had been produced within the framework of Hyper360 (EU-project, Horizon 2020, no. 761934) and the aim was to have an interactive experience in which the user is in the role of a crime scene investigator. The user by itself can choose the path through the video by selecting different elements of photos with hints and linked 360° videos and imbedded 2D video. In ImAc we used a linear version with imbedded videos and images.

The time plan of the pilot in Hyper360 was not in line with the pilot plan in ImAc and the editorial department decided that they did not want a publication of the linear version before the release of the interactive version. Therefore, we had a pilot website with only *I, Philip* and *360° Abendschau* and another one with all three videos (URL with “s” in the end). The latter were only used in the direct communication with user associations. In all other promotion activities, we use the URL or the pilot website with the two videos only.

The portal and player were also connected to Google Analytics and the QoS/QoE logger.

9.1.4 Experimental protocol

The approach taken was that of an open pilot, in which any user was invited to visit the website and watch on their own accessible 360° videos in the ImAc player on the device of their choice. Many dissemination actions were conducted with the goal of maximizing the reach of the open pilot. These actions were mainly performed by IRT and RBB in Germany and included:

- information of the pilot on dedicated websites about the accessibility services at RBB as well as “DasErste”
- an article on www.pressebox.de
- information distributed via existing mailing lists of user associations, testers from the target group recruited for tests as well as contacts related to VR, AR and XR and other broadcasters
- tweets using the rbb innovation account, IRT presse and IRT lab including direct tweets addressed to multipliers in the area of accessibility topics

Additionally, the project communication channels were also used. For the German open pilot, the focus was on subtitles and German Sign Language. When users landed on the webpage, on the upper half of the page (Figure 82) they found information on the ImAc project, on the specific test, on the player features, as well as a brief guide on how to view the content on different devices: Android tablet, PC, VR glasses or Android smartphone, either along or in conjunction with VR glasses. They were given an email address to send any question or information request, and a link to the questionnaire.

Figure 82: RBB open pilot: website I (2 videos)

On the bottom part of the page (Figure 83), they were given access to two content (one fictional, one non-fictional) with subtitles and German Sign Language.

360° ABENDSCHAU

To start the player, please click on the image.

The 360° video of the Abendschau takes the viewer into the editorial world and makes it possible to be in the middle of the buzzing capital or to sit directly next to the director.

Audio: Deutsch
 [=] subtitles: Deutsch
 [>] sign language: Deutsch
 Link: rburl.de/abnden

I, PHILIP

To start the player, please click on the image.

23 years after Philip K. Dick's death, in 2005, David Hanson, a young engineer in robotics, revealed his first android with human form, 'Phil'. 'I, Philip' immerses you in the memories of what could be the last love affair of the writer. But aren't these memories the fruit of the imagination of an android which learned, little by little, how to become a human?

Co-production: Arte France & Okio Studios

Audio: English
 [=] subtitles: English, Español, Deutsch, Català
 [>] sign language: Deutsch
 Link: rburl.de/philen

Figure 83: RBB open pilot: website II (2 videos)

The only difference on the pilot website with three videos is the access to the *Täter | Opfer | Polizei* video on the upper part instead of an information about the project. Everything else is the same.

INNOVATION PROJECTS

360° VIDEO ACCESSIBILITY

- TEST NOW! ▼
- WHAT IS DIFFERENT ON THIS PLAYER? ▼
- FEATURES IN THE PLAYER ▼
- A BRIEF GUIDE ▼
- QUESTIONNAIRE ▼

Alle anzeigen

TÄTER | OPFER | POLIZEI

To start the player, please click on the image.

Be involved in the investigation of a fictional criminal case and support the experts from the police in their work. Find out for yourself who the perpetrator is by means of interviews and confirmed clues.

Audio: Deutsch
 [=] subtitles: Deutsch, English
 [>] sign language: Deutsch
 Link: rburl.de/polien

Figure 84: RBB open pilot: website I (3 videos)

9.1.5 Results

The results are presented in three different sub-sections for: Google Analytics, QoS/QoE logger and questionnaires.

9.1.5.1 Google Analytics Results

Figure 85 shows an overview of the audience who visited all the ImAc portal/player branches, excluding the CCMA's ones, from February 17th to March 17th. A total number of 546 users were collected, from which 313 users visited the player releases for the German pilot in both German (*/player_de*, 285 users) and English (*/player_en*, 28 users). The evolution of users per day is also shown. The number of visits was quite variable, and strongly influenced by the launched dissemination actions, with three days having more than 60 visitors. The total number of sessions, average number of sessions per user, total page views, average number of pages per session, and the average session duration are also displayed in the figure. From the total number of users, almost 80% of them were new visitors and the rest were returning ones.

Figure 85: Audience overview

Geographics

Figure 86 shows the countries from which users visited the ImAc services, along with the top 10 countries with higher number of visitors, and their activity. As expected, Germany was the country with higher number of visitors, but many users from Spain were also collected, as the pilot was also disseminated (mainly re-tweets) by Spanish partners, and the other player branches are also included in these statistics.

Figure 87 shows the distribution of German visitors, along with the statistics from top 10 cities, and the same information is provided from Spanish users in Figure 88, just as complementary information. The top 10 browser languages for all visitors are detailed in Figure 89. This also gives an idea of the native language of the visitors, that may differ from the geographical area from where they accessed the player branches.

Figure 86: Visitors from worldwide and top-10 countries

Figure 87: German users

Figure 88: Spanish users

Figure 89: Browsers language

Technology Used

The type of software and consumption devices used was also registered. Figure 90 shows the top 10 most used web browsers, while Figure 91 indicates the types of devices used, along with their average activity. The statistics about the Operating Systems (OS) of the used non-mobile and mobile devices are provided in Figure 92. In addition, Figures 93 and 94 provide information about the most used mobile devices and their screen resolutions, respectively. In conjunction, these statistics are a proof of evidence that the player runs well on different types of devices, with OS, and software and hardware resources.

Browser	Users	% Users
1. Chrome	224	41.03%
2. Firefox	99	18.13%
3. Samsung Internet	81	14.84%
4. Safari	64	11.72%
5. Edge	32	5.86%
6. Internet Explorer	30	5.49%
7. Android Webview	9	1.65%
8. Safari (in-app)	5	0.92%
9. Opera	1	0.18%
10. PC	1	0.18%

Figure 90: Browsers used

Device Category ?	Acquisition			Behaviour		
	Users ? ↓	New Users ?	Sessions ?	Bounce Rate ?	Pages/Session ?	Avg. Session Duration ?
	546 % of Total: 100.00% (546)	513 % of Total: 100.00% (513)	821 % of Total: 100.00% (821)	25.70% Avg for View: 25.70% (0.00%)	3.77 Avg for View: 3.77 (0.00%)	00:05:23 Avg for View: 00:05:23 (0.00%)
1. desktop	361 (66.00%)	335 (65.30%)	559 (68.09%)	23.61%	4.25	00:06:17
2. mobile	165 (30.16%)	159 (30.99%)	235 (28.62%)	29.79%	2.82	00:03:43
3. tablet	21 (3.84%)	19 (3.70%)	27 (3.29%)	33.33%	2.07	00:01:08

Figure 91: Types of devices used

Operating System	Users	% Users
1. Windows	286	52.29%
2. Android	132	24.13%
3. Macintosh	54	9.87%
4. iOS	53	9.69%
5. Linux	21	3.84%
6. (not set)	1	0.18%

Operating System	Users	% Users
1. Android	132	70.97%
2. iOS	53	28.49%
3. Windows	1	0.54%

Figure 92: Operating systems: non-mobile devices (Up) and mobile devices (down)

Mobile Device Info ?	Acquisition			Behaviour		
	Users ? ↓	New Users ?	Sessions ?	Bounce Rate ?	Pages/Session ?	Avg. Session Duration ?
	186 % of Total: 34.07% (546)	178 % of Total: 34.70% (513)	262 % of Total: 31.91% (821)	30.15% Avg for View: 25.70% (17.32%)	2.74 Avg for View: 3.77 (-27.13%)	00:03:27 Avg for View: 00:05:23 (-35.83%)
1. (not set)	82 (44.09%)	78 (43.82%)	112 (42.75%)	10.71%	3.85	00:05:37
2. Apple iPhone	39 (20.97%)	39 (21.91%)	42 (16.03%)	61.90%	1.57	00:00:26
3. Apple iPad	10 (5.38%)	10 (5.62%)	14 (5.34%)	21.43%	2.00	00:00:46
4. Samsung SM-G950F Galaxy S8	6 (3.23%)	5 (2.81%)	8 (3.05%)	12.50%	1.62	00:03:26
5. Samsung SM-A520F Galaxy A5 (2017)	3 (1.61%)	3 (1.69%)	3 (1.15%)	0.00%	3.67	00:04:33
6. Xiaomi Mi A2 Lite	3 (1.61%)	3 (1.69%)	25 (9.54%)	52.00%	2.08	00:03:48
7. Cubot Quest	2 (1.08%)	1 (0.56%)	2 (0.76%)	50.00%	1.00	00:00:00
8. Samsung SM-G973F Galaxy S10	2 (1.08%)	2 (1.12%)	2 (0.76%)	50.00%	2.50	00:02:53
9. Xiaomi Mi 9T Pro	2 (1.08%)	1 (0.56%)	4 (1.53%)	0.00%	1.75	00:07:42
10. Xiaomi Mi A1	2 (1.08%)	1 (0.56%)	2 (0.76%)	50.00%	1.00	00:00:00

Figure 93: Mobile devices used

Screen Resolution	Users	% Users
1. 800x450	66	34.74%
2. 375x667	18	9.47%
3. 360x640	11	5.79%
4. 375x812	11	5.79%
5. 768x1024	11	5.79%
6. 320x568	6	3.16%
7. 800x451	6	3.16%
8. 414x896	5	2.63%
9. 360x760	4	2.11%
10. 396x810	4	2.11%

Figure 94: Screen resolutions – mobile devices

Data Acquisition

This part provides statistics about the entry points from where the users accessed/found the ImAc services. Figure 95 shows the main countries from where users accessed the player releases. As expected, the whole set of German users accessed the release for the German pilot (*/player_de*), and the public release of the player (*/player*) registered visitors from different countries.

Figure 95: Users flow

NOTE: The visitors registered from Ireland correspond to the adoption of the player, which is open-source and released on Github, by the recently granted EU TRACTION project, with which a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) is being prepared. Although this is not directly related to the German pilot, it is a nice proof of evidence of the impact and outputs from ImAc, in terms of dissemination, knowledge transfer and exploitation.

Figure 96 provides an overview of the acquisition channels, including direct visits (i.e. directly typing the URL), from Social Media posts, referral from other websites, and organic search (e.g. by using search engines, like Google).

Figure 96: Acquisition overview

Figure 97 details the top 10 entry points (i.e. source / mediums) from where all the player branches were accessed. Figure 98 details the top 10 direct links. It corroborates that 285 (*/player_de*) + 28 (*/player_en*) users visited the releases for the German pilot, as highlighted in red. It should be highlighted the */imacmaster* release is used for internally testing latest

features, the */ImAc-master* one is the one used in the TRACTION project, and the ones listed in positions 7 and 10 refer to the Spanish cross-national tests, which were still ongoing when the open pilot was launched.

Source/Medium ?	Acquisition			Behaviour		
	Users ? ↓	New Users ?	Sessions ?	Bounce Rate ?	Pages/Session ?	Avg. Session Duration ?
	546 % of Total: 100.00% (546)	513 % of Total: 100.00% (513)	821 % of Total: 100.00% (821)	25.70% Avg for View: 25.70% (0.00%)	3.77 Avg for View: 3.77 (0.00%)	00:05:23 Avg for View: 00:05:23 (0.00%)
1. (direct) / (none)	517 (94.52%)	492 (95.91%)	756 (92.08%)	25.79%	3.80	00:05:24
2. imac-project.eu / referral	10 (1.83%)	4 (0.78%)	30 (3.65%)	20.00%	3.13	00:05:39
3. t.co / referral	7 (1.28%)	7 (1.36%)	7 (0.85%)	71.43%	1.57	00:01:51
4. m.facebook.com / referral	6 (1.10%)	6 (1.17%)	6 (0.73%)	66.67%	1.83	00:00:22
5. google / organic	4 (0.73%)	2 (0.39%)	19 (2.31%)	5.26%	5.11	00:07:31
6. euc-word-edit.officeapps.live.com / referral	1 (0.18%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.12%)	0.00%	3.00	00:08:50
7. github.com / referral	1 (0.18%)	1 (0.19%)	1 (0.12%)	0.00%	5.00	00:01:55
8. youtube.com / referral	1 (0.18%)	1 (0.19%)	1 (0.12%)	0.00%	1.00	00:00:01

Figure 97: Acquisition- source/medium

Landing Page ?	Acquisition			Behaviour		
	Users ? ↓	New Users ?	Sessions ?	Bounce Rate ?	Pages/Session ?	Avg. Session Duration ?
	517 % of Total: 94.69% (546)	492 % of Total: 95.91% (513)	756 % of Total: 92.08% (821)	25.79% Avg for View: 25.70% (0.36%)	3.80 Avg for View: 3.77 (0.80%)	00:05:24 Avg for View: 00:05:23 (0.28%)
1. /player_de/player/	285 (50.18%)	276 (56.10%)	350 (46.30%)	36.86%	1.89	00:03:27
2. /player/	114 (20.07%)	98 (19.92%)	152 (20.11%)	25.00%	2.70	00:02:53
3. /imacplayer/	25 (4.40%)	21 (4.27%)	56 (7.41%)	14.29%	10.55	00:12:25
4. /player_en/player/	21 (3.70%)	19 (3.86%)	23 (3.04%)	30.43%	2.61	00:03:00
5. /playertest/	19 (3.35%)	10 (2.03%)	33 (4.37%)	0.00%	3.06	00:02:18
6. /ImAc-master/	13 (2.29%)	13 (2.64%)	25 (3.31%)	0.00%	5.08	00:07:31
7. /adtest_catlow/player/	10 (1.76%)	9 (1.83%)	10 (1.32%)	0.00%	3.50	00:09:11
8. /imacplayer/player/	9 (1.58%)	6 (1.22%)	10 (1.32%)	0.00%	17.90	00:26:57
9. /player_en/	7 (1.23%)	5 (1.02%)	9 (1.19%)	11.11%	5.78	00:11:03
10. /asttest_catlow/player/	6 (1.06%)	6 (1.22%)	6 (0.79%)	0.00%	3.83	00:12:47

Figure 98: Direct acquisition

Figure 99 summarizes the acquired entries from Social Media channels, while Figure 100 reflects to what player release (*/player*) these entries went. This unfortunately confirms that Google did not track the accesses to the */player_de* and */player_en* releases from the dissemination actions on Social Media from German partners (RBB and IRT), which had however a quite high reach. However, the activity during media consumption from these entries was registered by both Google Analytics and the QoE logger.

Social Network ?	Acquisition			Behaviour		
	Users ? ↓	New Users ?	Sessions ?	Bounce Rate ?	Pages/Session ?	Avg. Session Duration ?
	14 % of Total: 2.56% (546)	14 % of Total: 2.73% (513)	14 % of Total: 1.71% (821)	64.29% Avg for View: 25.70% (150.14%)	1.64 Avg for View: 3.77 (-56.38%)	00:01:05 Avg for View: 00:05:23 (-79.81%)
1. Twitter	7 (50.00%)	7 (50.00%)	7 (50.00%)	71.43%	1.57	00:01:51
2. Facebook	6 (42.86%)	6 (42.86%)	6 (42.86%)	66.67%	1.83	00:00:22
3. YouTube	1 (7.14%)	1 (7.14%)	1 (7.14%)	0.00%	1.00	00:00:01

Figure 99: Acquisition from social networks

Figure 100: Social users flow

Users Behavior

The concrete activity and behavior of the new and returning visitors is summarised in Figure 101. Their level of engagement can be inferred from Figure 102, given the duration of their sessions. These data are referred to all visitors.

User Type ?	Acquisition			Behaviour		
	Users ? ↓	New Users ?	Sessions ?	Bounce Rate ?	Pages/Session ?	Avg. Session Duration ?
	546 % of Total: 100.00% (546)	513 % of Total: 100.00% (513)	821 % of Total: 100.00% (821)	25.70% Avg for View: 25.70% (0.00%)	3.77 Avg for View: 3.77 (0.00%)	00:05:23 Avg for View: 00:05:23 (0.00%)
1. New Visitor	513 (79.66%)	513 (100.00%)	513 (62.48%)	28.65%	3.01	00:04:06
2. Returning Visitor	131 (20.34%)	0 (0.00%)	308 (37.52%)	20.78%	5.02	00:07:30

Count of Sessions ?	Sessions ?	Page Views ?
1	513	1,546
2	107	623
3	48	241
4	27	151
5	19	60
6	14	58
7	9	44
8	7	25
9-14	20	145
15-25	10	21
26-50	16	65
51-100	5	19
101-200	26	94

Figure 101: Statistics for and behavior of new and returning visitors

Session Duration ?	Sessions ?	Page Views ?
0-10 seconds	306	333
11-30 seconds	71	161
31-60 seconds	67	175
61-180 seconds	126	363
181-600 seconds	133	511
601-1800 seconds	81	550
1801+ seconds	37	999

Figure 102: Level of engagement, specified in terms of the duration of the sessions

Users Activity

Figure 103 shows the global users' activity in terms of interactions with the portal and player, i.e. events. It also details the number of sessions with at least on event, and the average number of events per session. The lower part of the figure also indicates the number for each Event Category: *Settings of the portal*; *Player launching* (i.e. once a content is selected for its consumption from the portal); and.

Figure 103: Events overview

Figure 104 provides an overview of the number of events for the 360° videos having gathered a higher number of events. However, it should be noted that this event is registered from the standard ImAc portal, so unfortunately these statistics could not be captured for the German pilot, which has used gateway portals at the RBB broadcaster’s premises. However, this information is not lost, but can be more accurately processed by using the information from the QoE logger. In the case of the Spanish pilot, these data can be obtained from both registration systems.

	Event Label ?	Total Events ?	Unique Events ?
0	Liceu Opera Piece 1	291 % of Total: 4.05% (7,182)	195 % of Total: 5.78% (3,374)
1	Liceu Opera Piece 2		
2	360° Abendschau		
3	I,Philip		
4	Desconcert “Leyre”	139 (47.77%)	67 (34.36%)
5	Desconcert “Havana”	65 (22.34%)	48 (24.62%)
6	Holy Land Ep.4	20 (6.87%)	20 (10.26%)
7	Rapzember	11 (3.78%)	9 (4.62%)
8	Täter I Opfer I Polizei	10 (3.44%)	9 (4.62%)
9	Òpera Romeo i Juliette al Liceu	8 (2.75%)	7 (3.59%)
10	El Telenotícies per dins	7 (2.41%)	7 (3.59%)
11	Cuinant en 360	6 (2.06%)	5 (2.56%)
12	Diada de Sant Jordi	5 (1.72%)	5 (2.56%)
13	Making of FAQs		
14	Polònia 360		

Figure 104: Overview of events per content

Figure 105 gathers the events from the portal settings that were used more than once. The meaning of all Event Labels listed in this figure is provided in Table 47. As expected, the language change options were the most used, but the voice interaction feature was also accessed many times (18).

Event Label ?	Total Events ?	Unique Events ?
	714 % of Total: 9.94% (7,182)	319 % of Total: 9.45% (3,374)
1. en	553 (77.45%)	216 (67.71%)
2. ca	63 (8.82%)	39 (12.23%)
3. de	46 (6.44%)	28 (8.78%)
4. btn_voice_on	18 (2.52%)	4 (1.25%)
5. es	6 (0.84%)	5 (1.57%)
6. btn_ls	5 (0.70%)	5 (1.57%)
7. btn_ind_arrow	2 (0.28%)	2 (0.63%)
8. btn_ind_radar	2 (0.28%)	2 (0.63%)
9. btn_st_outline	2 (0.28%)	1 (0.31%)
10. btn_stsize_M	2 (0.28%)	2 (0.63%)

Figure 105: Overview of portal settings events

Event Label	Meaning
en	Main language has been set to English
ca	Main language has been set to Catalan
de	Main language has been set to German
btn_voice_on	Voice control has been activated
es	Main language has been set to Spanish
btn_ls	Player menu has been set to enlarged size
btn_ind_arrow	Indicator has been set to arrow
btn_ind_radar	Indicator has been set to radar
btn_st_outline	An outline is added to the subtitles
btn_stsize_M	Subtitle size has been set to middle size

Table 47: Meaning of the event labels for the portal settings

The events referred to interactions with the player were clearly the most frequent (no registration restrictions apply here, so these events were registered for all branches). In particular, 5,403 events were registered when using the player in non-VR mode, and 774 when using VR mode. Figure 106 lists the player interaction events that were used more than 10 times during the open pilot. The meaning of the listed Event labels in the figures is detailed in Table 48. They are not deeply analysed and clustered for the German pilot in this sub-section, because their analysis and correlation are easier by making use of the QoE logger data, which is presented in the next subsection. Figure 107 shows the statistics for the player language change events, while Figure 108 lists the most used player interaction events in VR mode (i.e. when wearing an HMD). In this case, the filter has been applied to events used more than 5 times to provide a wider sample, as the number of events in this category is lower than for the general case.

Event Label ?	Total Events ?	Unique Events ?
	6,177 % of Total: 86.01% (7,182)	2,860 % of Total: 84.77% (3,374)
1. settings-button	606 (9.81%)	181 (6.33%)
2. disable-st-button	458 (7.41%)	219 (7.66%)
3. back-button	386 (6.25%)	83 (2.90%)
4. trad-menu-background	366 (5.93%)	125 (4.37%)
5. disable-sl-button	348 (5.63%)	181 (6.33%)
6. play-button	322 (5.21%)	143 (5.00%)
7. pause-button	291 (4.71%)	148 (5.17%)
8. play-progress	290 (4.69%)	46 (1.61%)
9. background-progress	225 (3.64%)	82 (2.87%)
10. settingsST	220 (3.56%)	89 (3.11%)

11.	settingsGeneral	194 (3.14%)	112 (3.92%)
12.	forward-seek-button	133 (2.15%)	43 (1.50%)
13.	show-st-button	129 (2.09%)	71 (2.48%)
14.	settingsIndicator	127 (2.06%)	77 (2.69%)
15.	subtitlesShowPositions	117 (1.89%)	52 (1.82%)
16.	zoom-button	110 (1.78%)	31 (1.08%)
17.	disable-ad-button	102 (1.65%)	50 (1.75%)
18.	show-sl-button	99 (1.60%)	67 (2.34%)
19.	settingsSL	96 (1.55%)	57 (1.99%)
20.	enhanced-menu-button	77 (1.25%)	59 (2.06%)
21.	back-seek-button	76 (1.23%)	20 (0.70%)
22.	tradoptionmenubackground	74 (1.20%)	30 (1.05%)
23.	settingsIndicatorRadar	67 (1.08%)	50 (1.75%)
24.	settingsIndicatorArrows	61 (0.99%)	44 (1.54%)
25.	traditional-menu-button	60 (0.97%)	50 (1.75%)
26.	plus-volume-button	59 (0.96%)	21 (0.73%)
27.	disable-ast-button	57 (0.92%)	30 (1.05%)
28.	subtitlesSpeakerButton	51 (0.83%)	32 (1.12%)
29.	(not set)	48 (0.78%)	27 (0.94%)
30.	subtitlesBottomButton	47 (0.76%)	28 (0.98%)
31.	subtitlesLanguage	44 (0.71%)	32 (1.12%)
32.	signerPosition	42 (0.68%)	31 (1.08%)
33.	slider-progress	42 (0.68%)	18 (0.63%)
34.	subtitlesTopButton	42 (0.68%)	25 (0.87%)
35.	subtitlesBackground	38 (0.62%)	28 (0.98%)
36.	minus-volume-button	31 (0.50%)	8 (0.28%)
37.	signerLargeSizeButton	30 (0.49%)	20 (0.70%)
38.	signerSize	29 (0.47%)	24 (0.84%)
39.	subtitlesSceneButton	28 (0.45%)	22 (0.77%)
40.	subtitlesSizes	28 (0.45%)	22 (0.77%)

51. seek-progress	16 (0.26%)	8 (0.28%)
52. settingsPointerSize	16 (0.26%)	13 (0.45%)
53. signerRightButton	15 (0.24%)	12 (0.42%)
54. resetUserProfileButton	14 (0.23%)	10 (0.35%)
55. settingsVoiceControl	14 (0.23%)	12 (0.42%)
56. mute-volume-button	13 (0.21%)	13 (0.45%)
57. settingsAD	13 (0.21%)	12 (0.42%)
58. signerSmallSizeButton	12 (0.19%)	10 (0.35%)
59. subtitlesLargeSizeButton	11 (0.18%)	10 (0.35%)
60. subtitlesSemitrans	11 (0.18%)	9 (0.31%)

Figure 106: "Interaction with Player" events used more than 10 times

Event Label	Meaning
en	Main language has been set to English
ca	Main language has been set to Catalan
de	Main language has been set to German
es	Main language has been set to Spanish
settings-button	Open the main settings menu options
disable-st-button	Enable subtitles
back-button	Return to the previous menu view
trad-menu-background	Player menu has been clicked
disable-sl-button	Enable Sign Language
Play-button	Pause the content
Pause-button	Play the content
Play-progress	The progress bar has been clicked
Background-progress	The progress bar background has been clicked
SettingsST	Open the subtitle settings menu options
settingsGeneral	Open the general settings menu options
Forward-seek-button	Content playback goes forward 5 seconds
Show-st-button	Disable subtitles
settingsIndicator	Open indicator menu options
subtitlesShowPositions	Open subtitle position menu options
Zoom-button	Zoom button has been clicked
Disable-ad-button	Enable audio description
Show-sl-button	Disable Sign Language
settingsSL	Open Sign Language menu options
Enhanced-menu-button	Change traditional menu view to enhanced menu view
Back-seek-button	Content playback goes back 5 seconds
tradoptionmenubackground	Options menu has been clicked
settingsIndicatorRadar	Enable the radar indicator
settingsIndicatorArrows	Enable the arrows indicator
Traditional-menu-button	Change enhanced menu view to traditional menu view
Plus-volume-button	Increase the volume
Disable-ast-button	Enable audio subtitles
subtitlesSpeakerButton	Put subtitles in front of the speaker
subtitlesBottomButton	Put the subtitles at the bottom of the screen
subtitlesLanguage	Open the subtitle language menu
signerPosition	Open the Sign Language position menu options

Event Label	Meaning
Slider-progress	Slider progress option has been clicked in progress bar
subtitlesTopButton	Put the subtitles at the top of the screen
subtitlesBackground	Open the subtitles background menu options
Minus-volume-button	Decrease the volume level
signerLargeSizeButton	Change the size of the Sign Language to large size
signerSize	Open the Sign Language size menu options
subtitleSceneButton	Put the subtitles evenly spaced every 120 degrees
subtitlesSizes	Open subtitles sizes menu options
Seek-progress	Seek in the progress bar
settingsPointerSize	Open pointer size menu options
signerRightButton	Put the Sign Language at the right of the field-of-view
signerLeftButton	Put the Sign Language at the left of the field-of-view
resetUserProfileButton	Reset all settings and restore the default settings
settingsVoiceControl	Open voice control menu options
Mute-volume-button	Mute volume
settingsAD	Open audio description menu options
signerSmallSizeButton	Change the size of the Sign Language to small size
signerMediumSizeButton	Change the size of the Sign Language to medium size
subtitlesLargeSizeButton	Change the size of the subtitles to large size
subtitlesSemitrans	Put a semi-transparent background box to the subtitles

Table 48: Meaning of the listed events labels

Event Label ?	Total Events ?	Unique Events ?
	668 % of Total: 9.30% (7,182)	288 % of Total: 8.54% (3,374)
1. en	553 (82.78%)	216 (75.00%)
2. ca	63 (9.43%)	39 (13.54%)
3. de	46 (6.89%)	28 (9.72%)
4. es	6 (0.90%)	5 (1.74%)

Figure 107: Player menu language change events

Event Label [?]	Total Events [?]	Unique Events [?]
	774 % of Total: 10.78% (7,182)	447 % of Total: 13.25% (3,374)
1. settings-button	83 (10.72%)	35 (7.83%)
2. disable-st-button	82 (10.59%)	45 (10.07%)
3. disable-sl-button	63 (8.14%)	33 (7.38%)
4. back-button	48 (6.20%)	15 (3.36%)
5. settingsGeneral	44 (5.68%)	32 (7.16%)
6. settingsIndicatorRadar	35 (4.52%)	26 (5.82%)
7. play-button	33 (4.26%)	16 (3.58%)
8. settingsIndicator	33 (4.26%)	28 (6.26%)
9. trad-menu-background	32 (4.13%)	17 (3.80%)
10. settingsST	24 (3.10%)	8 (1.79%)
11. background-progress	23 (2.97%)	9 (2.01%)
12. pause-button	22 (2.84%)	11 (2.46%)
13. settingsSL	20 (2.58%)	13 (2.91%)
14. signerLargeSizeButton	19 (2.45%)	11 (2.46%)
15. signerSize	13 (1.68%)	11 (2.46%)
16. subtitlesShowPositions	13 (1.68%)	6 (1.34%)
17. forward-seek-button	11 (1.42%)	5 (1.12%)
18. signerMediumSizeButton	11 (1.42%)	5 (1.12%)
19. subtitlesTopButton	9 (1.16%)	5 (1.12%)
20. signerPosition	8 (1.03%)	4 (0.89%)
21. settingsIndicatorArrows	7 (0.90%)	7 (1.57%)
22. show-sl-button	7 (0.90%)	5 (1.12%)
23. signerLeftButton	7 (0.90%)	4 (0.89%)
24. subtitlesBottomButton	7 (0.90%)	4 (0.89%)
25. tradoptionmenubackground	7 (0.90%)	3 (0.67%)
26. plus-volume-button	6 (0.78%)	3 (0.67%)
27. disable-ad-button	5 (0.65%)	4 (0.89%)
28. minus-volume-button	5 (0.65%)	2 (0.45%)
29. show-st-button	5 (0.65%)	4 (0.89%)
30. signerSmallSizeButton	5 (0.65%)	4 (0.89%)

Figure 108: “Interaction with Player” events in VR mode used more than 5 times

9.1.5.2 QoS/QoE Logger Results

Selected videos and duration

Table 49 provides a summary of the amount of times each video was watched in the German pilot. As expected, the *Täter | Opfer | Polizei*, the *360° Abendschau* and the *I, Philip* videos were the most visited, because were the ones advertised on the RBB. However, other three 360° videos (*Rapzember*, *Desconcert "Leyre"* and *Opera 1*) were also watched 5 times, probably directly from the */player_de* portal.

Table 50 provides a summary of the distribution of the amount of time during which each video was watched. Interestingly, it can be seen that short videos were watched almost completely quite frequently, but it did not happen for longer ones, like *Täter | Opfer | Polizei* and *I, Philip*. Note that the video watching experience can be longer than the duration of the video if playback control commands (e.g. pauses, seeks...) are issued. This happened few times for some videos.

Very similar trends, but with a lower number of videos selected, occurred for the English version of the portal and player for the German pilot, as can be seen in Tables 51 and 52. The lower number can be justified because: 1) the English version was released after having launched the open pilot, in order to provide a more intuitive alternative to non German speakers (even though the menu language of the player can be dynamically changed); and 2) the German version was more intensively disseminated.

Content	Count
360° Abendschau	171
I, Philip	106
Täter Opfer Polizei	100
Total	377 (+5)

Table 49: Total videos watched in */player_de*

Content	Duration (s)	0-5%	5-25%	35-30%	50-75%	75-100%	100-200%	>200%	Total
Täter Opfer Polizei	1755	60 (60%)	27 (27%)	3 (3%)	2 (2%)	3 (3%)	3 (3%)	2 (2%)	100 (100%)
I, Philip	884	45 (42%)	40 (38%)	9 (8%)	2 (2%)	1 (1%)	6 (6%)	3 (3%)	106 (100%)
360° Abendschau	106	8 (5%)	23 (13%)	30 (18%)	17 (10%)	18 (11%)	58 (34%)	17 (10%)	171 (100%)
Total		113 (30%)	90 (24%)	42 (11%)	21 (6%)	22 (6%)	67 (18%)	22 (6%)	377 (100%)

Table 50: Distribution of durations of the video watching experience for each video in */player_de*

Content	Count
360° Abendschau	26
Täter Opfer Polizei	10
I, Philip	3
Total	37

Table 51: Total videos watched in */player_en*

Content	Duration (s)	0-5%	5-25%	35-30%	50-75%	75-100%	100-200%	>200%	Total
Täter Opfer Polizei	1755	7 (70%)	2 (20%)	1 (10%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	10 (100%)
I, Philip	884	2 (76%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	6 (0%)	1 (33%)	9 (100%)
360° Abendschau	106	1 (4%)	10 (38%)	7 (27%)	1 (4%)	1 (4%)	5 (19%)	1 (4%)	171 (100%)
Total		10 (33%)	12 (28%)	8 (17%)	1 (4%)	1 (2%)	5 (11%)	1 (4%)	39 (100%)

Table 52: Distribution of durations of the video watching experience for each video in /player_en

Interactions with the menu elements

Table 53 details the amount of interactions with the player menu elements for each of the 360° videos for /player_de. The legend for the events reported in the first row of the table is:

- BSeek and FSeek: Seek Backward and Forward
- VPB: Interactions with the Progress Bar
- ST: Subtitles enable (eST) and disable (dST)
- SL: Sign Language enable and disable
- AD: Audio Description enable and disable
- AST: Audio Subtitles enable and disable
- Enhanced: Activation of the Enhanced-Accessibility variant of the Menu

To contribute to a better understanding of this information, a screen capture of the ImAc player menu is provided in Figure 109.

It can be seen that the interactions with the playback control menu elements were quite frequent, especially with regard to the interactions with the progress bar (150 usages out of 377 videos). Regarding the usage of access services, the next key statistics can be summarized:

- Subtitles were activated 139 times, and only deactivated 36 times.
- Sign Language was activated 121 times, and only deactivated 48 times.
- Audio Description and Audio Subtitles were not available for these clips.

More detailed statistics about the specific interactions with the settings and options for the access services presentation will be provided in the next sub-section.

Besides, it can be seen that the “Settings” sub-menu was used for most of the video watching sessions, and that the “Zoom” and “Enhanced Menu” features were also quite frequently used (50 and 40 times, respectively).

Table 54 provides the same information for /player_en. The percentages of playback control interactions, activation/deactivation of access services (ST and SL), and with the settings button were still noteworthy, but in this case the “Zoom” and “Enhanced Menu” features were not used.

Content	Play	Pause	BSeek	FSeek	VPB	eST	dST	eSL	dSL	Settings	Zoom	Enhanced	Total
Täter Opfer Polizei	26	13	6	2	53	32	7	29	11	56	8	9	252
I, Philip	35	22	0	38	22	26	3	27	10	61	18	13	275
360° Abendschau	66	44	23	4	75	81	26	65	27	100	24	18	553
Total	127	79	29	44	150	139	36	121	48	150	50	40	1080

Table 53: Interaction with the menu in /player_de

Figure 109: Screenshot of the ImAc player menu

Content	Play	Pause	BSeek	FSeek	VPB	eST	dST	eSL	dSL	Settings	Zoom	Enhanced	Total
Täter Opfer Polizei	1	1	0	16	0	5	1	5	1	3	0	0	33
I, Philip	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
360° Abendschau	3	2	0	1	2	9	3	3	0	10	0	0	33
Total	4	3	0	17	2	9	4	8	1	13	0	0	66

Table 54: Interaction with the menu in /player_en

Interactions with the Sub-Menu Elements

General Settings

Table 55 provides statistics regarding the interactions with the “General Settings” section of the player menu (see Figure 110), when using /player_de. The legend for the entries in the first row of this table (menu section and options) is indicated next:

- Gen: button to access the General Settings
- Lang: Set Language, with the German (Ger), English (Eng), Spanish (Esp) and Catalan (Cat) options
- V.C.: Voice Control, with the On and Off options
- P.S.: Pointer Size, with the Small (Sm), Medium (Md) and Large (Lg) options
- U.P.: User Profile, with the Save and Reset options
- Ind: Indicator, with the None, Arrow, and Radar options.

Content	Gen	Lang	Eng	Esp	Ger	Cat	V.C.	On	Off	P.S.	Sm	Md	Lg
Täter Opfer Polizei	25	3	2	0	0	0	4	4	2	2	0	0	2
I, Philip	21	3	1	0	0	0	3	1	1	2	0	0	0
360° Abendschau	28	5	2	0	0	0	3	0	0	5	0	0	0
Total	74	11	5	0	0	0	10	5	3	9	0	0	2

Content	U.P	Reset	Save	Indi	None	Arrow	Radar	Total
Täter Opfer Polizei	2	0	0	14	1	9	10	80
I, Philip	1	0	0	16	0	11	6	66
360° Abendschau	3	0	0	21	1	13	5	86
Total	6	0	0	51	2	33	21	232

Table 55: Interactions with general settings in /player_de

It can be seen that the “Settings menu” was opened quite frequently, 74 times, which is around 25% of the total videos watched. The Language Change feature was not used so often and was basically used to change the menu language to English. Voice Control was activated 5 times, and the Pointer Size menu was checked 5 times, but only set twice to the Large size. The “User Profile” sub-menu was checked 6 times, but no settings were used in that sub-menu. The “Indicator” feature was used quite frequently (51 times), from where arrows (31) and radar (21) were activated with a noteworthy frequency. This reflects the usefulness of this feature, and that arrows are commonly preferred to the radar, although some users still prefer the radar and find it useful.

Table 56 provides the same statistics when using /player_en.

Figure 110: General settings menu

Content	Gen	Lang	Eng	Esp	Ger	Cat	V.C.	On	Off
Täter Opfer Polizei	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
I, Philip	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
360° Abendschau	6	2	2	1	0	0	0	0	0
Total	9	2	2	1	0	0	0	0	0

Content	P.S.	S	M	L	U.P.	Reset	Save	Indi	None	Arrow	Radar	Total
Täter Opfer Polizei	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	2	1	9
I, Philip	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
360° Abendschau	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	4	0	3	1	21
Total	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	7	0	5	2	30

Table 56: Interactions with general settings in /player_en

Subtitle Presentation Options

Table 57 provides statistics regarding the interactions with the Subtitle Presentation features and options of the ImAc player (see Figure 111), when using its German version (/player_de). The legend for the entries in the first row of this table (menu section and options) is indicated next:

- ST: Menu Control to open the Subtitles Settings.
- Size: Subtitles Size, with Small (S), Medium (M), and Large (L) options.
- Bcgd: Background, with Semi-transparent background box (Semi), and Outline (Out) options.
- Pos: Position or Presentation modes, with Top (T), Bottom (B), Fixed to Speaker (Spk), and Evenly Spaced every 120° (x3) options.
- E2R: Easy-to-Read Subtitles, with On and Off options.

As can be seen in the table, the ST settings menu was opened with a noteworthy frequency (68 times). The language sub-menu was however opened few times (15), and the language was basically set to English, and it seems that back to German, because the number of events for both options are the same. Note that the subtitles languages were only available in these two languages, so that is why the other languages were not activated. Regarding the Subtitles Size, that feature was used 16 times, and it seems that users prefer the larger size. Likewise, the Background sub-menu was opened 21 times, and it seems that the users slightly preferred the Outline mode. Regarding the Subtitles Position, that sub-menu was opened 41 times, and users preferred the Bottom option. It is also remarkable that the Subtitles attached to the speaker were activated 21 times, but the evenly spaced every 120° mode was not activated any time.

Table 58 provides the same statistics the English version of the player (/player_en).

Content	ST	Lang	Eng	Esp	Ger	Cat	Size	S	M	L	Bckg	Semi	Out
Täter Opfer Polizei	17	5	3	0	2	0	4	1	2	2	2	0	0
I, Philip	18	2	1	0	1	0	4	2	0	2	3	1	1
360° Abendschau	33	8	0	0	1	0	8	2	3	4	16	4	6
Total	68	15	4	0	4	0	16	5	5	8	21	5	7

Content	Pos	T	B	Spk	X3	E2R	On	Off	Total
Täter Opfer Polizei	11	3	6	5	0	0	0	0	63
I, Philip	12	0	1	7	0	1	0	0	56
360° Abendschau	20	5	9	12	0	0	0	0	131
Total	43	8	16	24	0	1	0	0	250

Table 57: Interactions with subtitle presentation features and options in /player_de

Figure 111: Subtitle presentation options

Content	ST	Lang	Eng	Esp	Ger	Cat	Size	S	M	L	Bckg	Semi	Out
Täter Opfer Polizei	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
I, Philip	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
360° Abendschau	3	5	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0
Total	3	5	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0

Content	Pos	T	B	SpK	X3	E2R	On	Off	Total
Täter Opfer Polizei	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
I, Philip	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
360° Abendschau	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	11
Total	0	11							

Table 58: Interactions with subtitle presentation features and options in /player_en

Sign Language Presentation Options

Table 59 provides statistics regarding the interactions with the Sign Language Presentation features and options of the ImAc player (see Figure 112), when using its German version (/player_de). The legend for the entries in the first row of this table (menu section and options) is indicated next:

- SL: Menu Control to open the Sign Language Settings.
- Size: Subtitles Size, with Small (S), Medium (M), and Large (L) options.
- Pos: Position, with Right (R) and Left (L) options.
- Dyn: Dynamic presentation mode (i.e. dynamically showing / hiding the SL video based on the speakers' activity), with On / Off options.

As can be seen in the table, the SL settings menu was opened 31 times, which is a bit more than 10% of the watched videos. The language sub-menu was also opened few times, and the SL language was never changed. This is logical, as no option for this was shown to the users, due to the fact that only one SL language (German SL, gsg) was provided, and the player does not show the menu elements for the unavailable features/options. The SL video size was changed few times (8), with a slight preference for larges sizes, and the Dynamic Presentation feature was used more frequently, with both the On / Off options being used (that feature was activated by default when starting the player).

Regarding the English version of the player (/player_en), although the SL service was activated few times (8), the personalization features for such a service were not used any time.

Content	SL	Lang	Eng	Esp	Ger	Cat	Size	S	M	L
Täter Opfer Polizei	7	3	0	0	0	0	4	1	1	4
I, Philip	12	2	0	0	0	0	2	1	0	0
360° Abendschau	12	6	0	0	0	0	2	1	1	2
Total	31	11	0	0	0	0	8	3	2	6

Content	Pos	R	L	Dyn	On	Off	Total
Täter Opfer Polizei	4	2	3	2	2	2	35
I, Philip	5	1	2	5	5	5	40
360° Abendschau	5	0	3	8	8	8	56
Total	14	3	8	15	15	15	131

Table 59: Interactions with Sign Language presentation features and options in /player_de

Figure 112: Sign Language presentation options

9.1.5.3 Questionnaire results

As far as the questionnaire is concerned, 81% of those replying it reported having used the subtitles. When asked about the different subtitle features, their assessment on a 5-point scale when asked if they liked different features is as follows:

	1	2	3	4	5	I did not use it	Mean	SD	Median
Arrow	1 (4%)	-	2 (8%)	7 (28%)	7 (28%)	8 (32%)	4.5	1.41	5
Radar	1 (4%)	1 (4%)	3 (12%)	8 (32%)	4 (16%)	8 (32%)	4.2	1.8	5
Size personalisation	2 (8%)	1 (4%)	4 (16%)	6 (24%)	6 (24%)	6 (24%)	4	1.85	5
Position personalisation	1 (4%)	2 (8%)	3 (12%)	4 (16%)	11 (44%)	4 (16%)	4.66	1.15	5
Background personalisation	3 (12%)	1 (4%)	5 (20%)	4 (16%)	4 (16%)	8 (32%)	3.28	2.13	5
Move subtitles with mouse/controller	1 (4%)	-	5 (20%)	6 (24%)	5 (20%)	8 (32%)	4.33	1.63	5

Table 60: Questionnaire results for subtitling (RBB open pilot)

Most users liked the arrow better than the radar, which still got positive values. Size, position, background personalisation and the mouse/controller moving function received generally

positive feedback, mostly above 3 and in many cases in the 4-5 range. Users were especially satisfied with the possibility to personalise the size of the subtitles.

Regarding Sign Language, 17 participants reported having used it (54%). When asked about the different SL features, their assessment on a 5-point scale is the following:

	1	2	3	4	5	I did not use it	Mean	SD	Median
Arrow	1 (5.9%)	-	-	4 (23.5%)	6 (35.3%)	6 (35.3%)	4.43	1.51	5
Radar	2 (11.8%)	-	-	5 (29.4%)	3 (17.6%)	7 (41.2%)	3.40	2.19	5
Size personalisation	2 (11.8%)	1 (5.9%)	2 (11.8%)	4 (23.5%)	3 (17.6%)	5 (29.4%)	3.40	2.19	5
Position personalisation	2 (11.8%)	-	2 (11.8%)	2 (11.8%)	8 (47.1%)	3 (17.6%)	4.20	1.68	5
Display of subtitles and SL together	1 (5.9%)	1 (5.9%)	2 (11.8%)	3 (17.6%)	6 (35.3%)	4 (23.5%)	4.42	1.51	5
Name of the speaker under SL video window	2 (11.8%)	-	-	3 (17.6%)	9 (52.9%)	3 (17.6%)	4.27	1.61	5
SL interpreter only visible when someone is speaking	2 (11.8%)	-	3 (17.6%)	2 (11.8%)	4 (23.5%)	6 (35.3%)	3.66	2.06	5
The drag-and-drop functionality of the SL interpreter	2 (11.8%)	-	1 (5.9%)	3 (17.6%)	5 (29.4%)	6 (35.3%)	3.86	1.95	5

Table 61: Questionnaire results for SL (RBB open pilot)

Data show that all ImAc implementations were welcomed by users, who assessed it majoritarily with values above average. The arrow, the position personalisation and the name of the speaker under the SI video window were especially welcomed by participants.

When asked how easy it was to use the player on a 5-point Likert scale, results were very positive, with most participants selecting 4 or 5 on a 5-point Likert scale and only 1 out of 29 (3.4%) selecting a low value.

1 Very difficult	2	3	4	5 Very easy	Mean	SD	Median
1 (3.4%)	0	7 (24.1%)	13 (44.8%)	8 (27.6%)	3.9	0.9	4

Table 62: Player evaluation (RBB open pilot)

Finally, when asked if they would recommend the player to a friend, 80% gave a positive reply. Unfortunately, the remaining 20% did not provide qualitative feedback in the open text field in order to understand their reasons.

Overall, qualitative feedback at the end was very positive, and only minor technical problems were reported. For instance, one participant indicated: "I'm not a technical skilled person. That's why I'm so happy to be able to participate here and support you. I was surprised how easy I got in here. For me, it must be as easy to use as possible, and what you are offering now

already corresponds to my expectations. It is important for me that in the future all broadcasts are subtitled or signed in this way. Keep going!”

9.2 Spanish pilot phase 2 (CCMA)

Link to open pilot: <https://www.ccma.cat/experiencia-immersiva-accessible/>

9.2.1 Measures

User tracking metrics were obtained by following the same approach as in the German pilot. See 9.1.1 for more details. Regarding the questionnaire, it was the same as in the German pilot, translated into Catalan, but did not include the questions on Sign Language, as this was not offered as a service, and included added questions on the specificities of the Catalan pilot, as follows:

1. Age:
2. I define myself as...
 - a. A hearing person
 - b. A person with hearing loss
3. Have you watched 360 contents before? Yes/No.
4. How did you watch the 360 content? PC/HMD/tablet/mobile phone
5. Did you use the subtitles? Yes/No
If yes, how much did you like... (5-point Likert scale) / I did not use it
 - i. Arrow (menu under indicator)
 - ii. Radar (menu under indicator)
 - iii. Size personalisation
 - iv. Position personalisation
 - v. Background personalisation
 - vi. Subtitle control with mouse/controller
6. Did you like having the traditional content on the main screen and a 360 immersive content on a second device? Yes/ No /I didn't use it
7. How easy to use was the player? (5-point Likert scale: very difficult-very easy)
8. Would you recommend the player to your friends? Yes/No
9. If you want, you can give us additional feedback here.

9.2.2 Participants

A total of 498 sessions were recorded for the CCMA open pilot from 281 users. 268 of these users were located in Spain. More details about the users, their activity and behavior will be provided in the results sub-section. Regarding the questionnaire, 44 replies were obtained until 17th March. These included 33 hearing persons (75%) and 11 persons with hearing loss (25%), who had generally watched 360° contents before (72.7%), on a PC (56.8%) or HMD (54.5%), but also on a tablet (36.4%) and a smartphone (40.9%). Mean age was 47.

9.2.3 Materials

The following materials were prepared:

- The questionnaire described under measures
- An introduction to the project and to each test
- Data protection and ethical information

The contents that were available in the Spanish open pilot were:

- ***El Telenotícies per dins***: 360º and traditional productions with accessibility services (ST)
- ***Making of FAQs***: 360º and traditional productions with accessibility services (ST)
- ***Diada de Sant Jordi***: 360º and traditional productions ready with accessibility services (ST)
- ***Cuinant en 360º***: 360º and traditional productions with accessibility services (ST)
- ***Romeo i Juliette al Liceu***: 360º production and traditional productions with accessibility services (ST)
- ***Polònia 360***: 360º and traditional productions with accessibility services (ST)
- ***Desconcert 'Leyre'***: 360º production with accessibility services (ST)
- ***Desconcert 'Havanna'***: 360º production with accessibility services (ST)

9.2.4 Experimental protocol

The approach taken was that of an open pilot, in which any user was invited to visit the website and watch accessible contents on the ImAc player in a free visit. For the Spanish open pilot, the focus was on subtitles.

In order to guarantee more feedback from users with hearing loss using virtual reality glasses, CCMA offered the possibility to welcome users in their premises to perform the open test. In this case, the test conditions were exactly the same, hence data from the 8 users who visited the CCMA premises for the tests are presented integrated with the rest of the open pilot.

Many dissemination actions were conducted with the goal of maximizing the reach of the open pilot. These actions included:

- Announcement of the pilot in TV3 News on Sunday February 23rd, introduction of the presenters and a video that includes an interview with a user with hearing loss.
- One-page report on a newspaper of wide diffusion in Catalonia explaining the project and the open pilot (March 9th).
- Press release to media on TV, accessibility services and broadcasters.
- Information distributed via existing mailing lists of user associations, testers from the target group recruited for tests, as well as contacts related to VR.
- Entries in social media such as Twitter and Facebook from CCMA and TV3 accounts.
- Additionally, the project communication channels were also used.

When users landed on the webpage, they found a short introduction on the project (Figure 113).

Mira el “making of” d’un telenotícies com mai fins ara: des de dues pantalles, en 360° i d’una forma accessible.

Ho podràs fer gràcies al [projecte ImAc](#), una iniciativa d’àmbit europeu en què participa la CCMA, i que treballa per fer accessibles experiències immersives aprofitant el potencial de les noves tecnologies.

Si ho vols provar, tens diverses opcions: des de dos dispositius amb navegador web (que utilitza el reproductor de vídeo d’i2cat), des d’una televisió HbbTV 2.0.1 i un mòbil Android o des d’unes ulleres de realitat virtual.

Figure 113: CCMA open pilot: website I

They were then given three possibilities. First of all, a Web-based 360° Companion Screen experience, allowing to watch a content on two or more devices synchronously (Figure 114). The linear version of the selected video was played out on the first device, and the 360° versions on the companion devices, with the freedom to choose the desired device (VR or traditional). When clicking on the orange box, they were given data privacy information and then they were given specific instructions on how to proceed. That service was offered via a URL from CCMA, with a an “origen” parameter “main” for the main screen and “companion” for the companion screens, after the base URL.

EMPARELLA 2 DISPOSITIUS AMB NAVEGADOR WEB

Un cop tinguis emparellats els dos dispositius, tria des de la segona pantalla un dels vídeos que t’oferim. El veuràs en dues pantalles de manera sincronitzada; a la segona, de manera immersiva 360° i accessible.

VIU L’EXPERIÈNCIA IMMERSIVA

Figure 114: CCMA open pilot: website II

Secondly, the HbbTV 360° Companion Screen experience, allowing to watch synchronously the linear content on an HbbTV television and the 360° content on an Android mobile phone with the embedded ImAc player (Figure 115). In this case, they were requested to go to the CCMA HbbTV service, where instructions were available. The HbbTV with the embedded player accessed a URL from CCMA, with an “origen” parameter “app” after the base URL.

EMPARELLA LA TELEVISIÓ I EL MÒBIL

Si vols viure l'experiència immersiva en el format televisió + mòbil, per una banda necessites una televisió connectada a internet amb tecnologia HbbTV 2.0.1., i per l'altra, un dispositiu mòbil Android.

Si disposes d'aquests dispositius, entra al servei d'HbbTV de TV3 i trobaràs les instruccions per participar en aquesta experiència.

Figure 115: CCMA open pilot: website III

Finally, the 360° Video Portal experience, where they were given the possibility to watch content with virtual reality glasses but also with the device of their choice. (Figure 116). When clicking on the orange box, they were redirected to a portal, where 8 different 360° contents were available. That service was offered via a URL from CCMA, with an "origen" parameter "360" after the base URL.

VIU UNA EXPERIÈNCIA ACCESSIBLE AMB ULLERES VR

Si disposes d'unes ulleres de realitat virtual, també podràs gaudir de vídeos immersius en 360° accessibles.

Accedeix a la pàgina de vídeos immersius, connecta les ulleres VR i reproduueix un dels vídeos.

SELECCIONA UN VÍDEO

Figure 116: CCMA open pilot: website IV

At the bottom of the page, they were given access to a general feedback questionnaire (Figure 117).

AJUDA'NS A MILLORAR!

Aquesta experiència forma part del projecte europeu ImAc. Per tal de millorar l'accessibilitat a les noves tecnologies (i específicament a les experiències immersives), és important que responguis al formulari. Durada estimada : 2 minuts.

DONANS LA TEVA OPINIÓ

Aquest projecte ha rebut finançament de la Unió Europea dins del programa Horizon 2020 de recerca i innovació, sota l'acord de subvenció núm. 761974.

Projecte coordinat per la Fundació i2cat, Centre de Recerca i Innovació.

Figure 117: CCMA open pilot: website V

9.2.5 Results

The results are presented in different sub-sections: section 9.2.5.1 reports on the Google Analytics. Section 9.2.5.2 reports on the QoS/QoE and 9.2.5.4 reports on the questionnaires.

9.2.5.1 Google Analytics Results

This sub-section provides the aggregated results from the three Spanish pilot experiences. Figure 118 shows an overview of the audience who visited all the CCMA portal/player branches from February 17th to March 17th. A total number of 281 users were collected, from which 268 users visited the player releases for the Spanish pilot in Catalan. The evolution of users per day is also shown. The number of visits was quite variable, and strongly influenced by the launched dissemination actions. The total number of sessions, average number of sessions per user, total page views, average number of pages per session, and the average session duration are also displayed in the figure. From the total number of users, 74.2% of them were new visitors and the rest were returning ones.

Figure 118: Audience overview Spanish pilot

Geographics

Figure 119 shows the countries from which users visited the ImAc services, along with the countries with higher number of visitors, and their activity. As expected, Spain was the country with higher number of visitors.

Figure 119: Visitors from worldwide countries

Figure 120 shows the distribution of Spanish visitors, along with the statistics from top 10 cities. The top 10 browser languages for all visitors are detailed in Figure 121. This also gives an

idea of the native language of the visitors, that may differ from the geographical area from where they accessed the player branches.

Figure 120: Spanish users

Figure 121: Browser languages – Spanish pilot

Technology used

The type of software and consumption devices used was also registered. Figure 122 shows the top 10 most used web browsers, while Figure 123 indicates the types of devices used, along with their average activity. The statistics about the Operating Systems (OS) of the used non-mobile and mobile devices are provided in Figure 124 and 125. In addition, Figures 126 and 127 provide information about the most used mobile devices and their respective screen resolutions. In conjunction, and like in the German pilot, these statistics are a proof of evidence that the player runs well on different types of devices, OS, and software and hardware resources.

Browser		Users	Users
URLs d'IMAC		281 % of Total: 5.94% (4,728)	281 % of Total: 5.94% (4,728)
1.	Chrome	165	58.72%
2.	Safari	41	14.59%
3.	Android Webview	37	13.17%
4.	Firefox	20	7.12%
5.	Edge	6	2.14%
6.	Samsung Internet	4	1.42%
7.	Opera	3	1.07%
8.	Internet Explorer	2	0.71%
9.	Safari (in-app)	2	0.71%
10.	Supermedium	1	0.36%

Figure 122: Browsers used – Spanish pilot

Device Category ?	Acquisition			Behaviour		
	Users ? ↓	New Users ?	Sessions ?	Bounce Rate ?	Pages/Session ?	Avg. Session Duration ?
URLs d'IMAC	281 % of Total: 5.94% (4,728)	257 % of Total: 5.54% (4,643)	498 % of Total: 7.92% (6,286)	19.68% Avg for View: 40.74% (-51.70%)	3.41 Avg for View: 5.54 (-38.43%)	00:06:39 Avg for View: 00:04:48 (38.64%)
1. desktop	133 (47.16%)	116 (45.14%)	200 (40.16%)	13.00%	3.97	00:07:56
2. mobile	128 (45.39%)	123 (47.86%)	228 (45.78%)	26.75%	2.64	00:04:10
3. tablet	21 (7.45%)	18 (7.00%)	70 (14.06%)	15.71%	4.36	00:11:01

Figure 123: Types of devices used – Spanish pilot

Operating System		Users	Users
URLs d'IMAC		281 % of Total: 5.94% (4,728)	281 % of Total: 5.94% (4,728)
1.	Windows	112	39.72%
2.	Android	109	38.65%
3.	iOS	40	14.18%
4.	Macintosh	18	6.38%
5.	Linux	3	1.06%

Figure 124: Operating systems non-mobile devices

Operating System	Users	Users
URLs d'IMAC	149 % of Total: 3.15% (4,728)	149 % of Total: 3.15% (4,728)
1. Android	109	73.15%
2. iOS	40	26.85%

Figure 125: Operating systems mobile devices

Mobile Device Info	Acquisition			Behaviour		
	Users	New Users	Sessions	Bounce Rate	Pages/Session	Avg. Session Duration
URLs d'IMAC	149 % of Total: 3.15% (4,728)	141 % of Total: 3.04% (4,643)	298 % of Total: 4.74% (6,286)	24.16% Avg for View: 40.74% (-40.70%)	3.04 Avg for View: 5.54 (-45.17%)	00:05:47 Avg for View: 00:04:48 (20.57%)
1. Apple iPhone	28 (18.79%)	28 (19.86%)	35 (11.74%)	34.29%	2.34	00:01:57
2. Apple iPad	12 (8.05%)	11 (7.80%)	15 (5.03%)	40.00%	2.13	00:00:58
3. Huawei ANE-LX1 P20 Lite	7 (4.70%)	6 (4.26%)	20 (6.71%)	20.00%	2.25	00:03:53
4. (not set)	6 (4.03%)	6 (4.26%)	11 (3.69%)	9.09%	3.55	00:06:17
5. Samsung SM-G950F Galaxy S8	6 (4.03%)	4 (2.84%)	31 (10.40%)	12.90%	6.10	00:15:31
6. Huawei ALP-L09 Mate 10	5 (3.36%)	5 (3.55%)	8 (2.68%)	50.00%	1.88	00:02:22
7. LG LM-G710 G7 ThinQ	5 (3.36%)	5 (3.55%)	8 (2.68%)	0.00%	2.25	00:04:08
8. Xiaomi Mi A1	5 (3.36%)	5 (3.55%)	5 (1.68%)	0.00%	5.80	00:07:06
9. Samsung SM-A520F Galaxy A5 (2017)	4 (2.68%)	3 (2.13%)	13 (4.36%)	23.08%	2.00	00:02:53
10. Samsung SM-G973F Galaxy S10	3 (2.01%)	3 (2.13%)	4 (1.34%)	0.00%	3.50	00:06:13

Figure 126: Mobile devices used

	Screen Resolution	Users	% Users
1.	360x640	29	18.24%
2.	768x1024	13	8.18%
3.	360x760	9	5.66%
4.	375x667	9	5.66%
5.	360x720	6	3.77%
6.	360x740	6	3.77%
7.	375x812	6	3.77%
8.	393x851	6	3.77%
9.	412x892	6	3.77%
10.	414x896	6	3.77%

Figure 127: Screen resolutions – mobile devices

Data Acquisition

This part provides statistics about the entry points from where the users accessed/found the ImAc services.

Figure 128 provides an overview of the acquisition channels, including direct visits (i.e. directly typing the URL), from Social Media posts, referral from other websites, and organic search (e.g. by using search engines, like Google).

Figure 128: Acquisition overview

Figure 129 details the top 10 entry points (i.e. source / mediums) from where all the player branches were accessed.

Landing Page ?	Acquisition			Behaviour		
	Users ? ↓	New Users ?	Sessions ?	Bounce Rate ?	Pages/Session ?	Avg. Session Duration ?
URLs d'IMAC	274 % of Total: 5.80% (4,728)	255 % of Total: 5.49% (4,643)	487 % of Total: 7.75% (6,286)	19.10% Avg for View: 40.74% (-53.13%)	3.38 Avg for View: 5.54 (-39.04%)	00:06:43 Avg for View: 00:04:48 (40.20%)
1. /apps/mobils/recerca/imac/i2cat/imac_tv3_sincroApp/index.html (P)	135 (37.71%)	118 (46.27%)	194 (39.84%)	6.70%	4.20	00:07:00
2. /apps/mobils/recerca/imac/i2cat/imac_tv3_sincroApp/player/?id=0&origen=companion/ (P)	50 (13.97%)	45 (17.65%)	62 (12.73%)	32.26%	2.23	00:04:49
3. /_serveis/statics/apps/mobils/recerca/imac/i2cat/imac_tv3_sincroApp/player/index.html?id=0&origen=app/ (P)	18 (5.03%)	15 (5.88%)	21 (4.31%)	9.52%	2.81	00:06:40
4. /apps/mobils/recerca/imac/i2cat/imac_tv3_sincroApp/player/?id=5&origen=companion/ (P)	17 (4.75%)	10 (3.92%)	21 (4.31%)	47.62%	1.81	00:04:16
5. /apps/mobils/recerca/imac/i2cat/imac_tv3_sincroApp/player/?id=3&origen=companion/ (P)	14 (3.91%)	7 (2.75%)	23 (4.72%)	56.52%	1.65	00:03:52
6. /apps/mobils/recerca/imac/i2cat/imac_tv3_sincroApp/player/?id=1&origen=companion/ (P)	12 (3.35%)	7 (2.75%)	13 (2.67%)	0.00%	3.77	00:10:44
7. /apps/mobils/recerca/imac/i2cat/imac_tv3_sincroApp/player/?id=0&origen=app/ (P)	11 (3.07%)	9 (3.53%)	11 (2.26%)	9.09%	4.00	00:09:54
8. /_serveis/statics/apps/mobils/recerca/imac/i2cat/imac_tv3_sincroApp/player/index.html?id=5&origen=app/ (P)	8 (2.23%)	6 (2.35%)	15 (3.08%)	13.33%	2.87	00:03:11
9. /apps/mobils/recerca/imac/i2cat/imac_tv3_sincroApp/player/?id=0&origen=main/ (P)	8 (2.23%)	6 (2.35%)	9 (1.85%)	22.22%	2.11	00:08:02
10. /apps/mobils/recerca/imac/i2cat/imac_tv3_sincroApp/player/?id=1&origen=main/ (P)	8 (2.23%)	5 (1.96%)	9 (1.85%)	44.44%	1.89	00:08:13

Figure 129: Acquisition – source / medium

Source/Medium ?	Acquisition			Behaviour		
	Users ? ↓	New Users ?	Sessions ?	Bounce Rate ?	Pages/Session ?	Avg. Session Duration ?
URLs d'IMAC	281 % of Total: 5.94% (4,728)	257 % of Total: 5.54% (4,643)	498 % of Total: 7.92% (6,286)	19.68% Avg for View: 40.74% (-51.70%)	3.41 Avg for View: 5.54 (-38.43%)	00:06:39 Avg for View: 00:04:48 (38.64%)
1. (direct) / (none)	274 (97.51%)	255 (99.22%)	487 (97.79%)	19.10%	3.38	00:06:43
2. google / organic	3 (1.07%)	2 (0.78%)	3 (0.60%)	33.33%	1.00	00:00:03
3. 193.104.51.238:8080 / referral	2 (0.71%)	0 (0.00%)	6 (1.20%)	66.67%	5.83	00:03:54
4. ccma.experiencecloud.adobe.com / referral	1 (0.36%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.20%)	0.00%	3.00	00:08:39
5. confluence.tv3.cat / referral	1 (0.36%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.20%)	0.00%	13.00	00:04:29

Figure 130: Direct acquisition

Figure 131 summarises the acquired entries from Social Media channels, while Figure 132 reflects to what player release these entries went. The activity during media consumption from these entries were registered by both Google Analytics and the QoE logger.

Social Network	Sessions	% Sessions
1. Twitter	28	90.32%
2. Facebook	3	9.68%

Figure 131: Acquisition from social networks

Figure 132: Social users flow

Users Behavior

The concrete activity and behavior of the new and returning visitors is summarised in Figure 133. Their level of engagement can be inferred from Figure 134, given the duration of their sessions. These data are referred to all visitors.

User Type ?	Acquisition			Behaviour		
	Users ? ↓	New Users ?	Sessions ?	Bounce Rate ?	Pages/Session ?	Avg. Session Duration ?
URLs d'IMAC	281 % of Total: 5.94% (4,728)	257 % of Total: 5.54% (4,643)	498 % of Total: 7.92% (6,286)	19.68% Avg for View: 40.74% (-51.70%)	3.41 Avg for View: 5.54 (-38.43%)	00:06:39 Avg for View: 00:04:48 (38.64%)
1. New Visitor	256 (74.20%)	257 (100.00%)	257 (51.61%)	18.29%	3.25	00:05:38
2. Returning Visitor	89 (25.80%)	0 (0.00%)	241 (48.39%)	21.16%	3.59	00:07:43

Count of Sessions ?	Sessions ?	Page Views ?
1	257	836
2	69	197
3	32	76
4	30	88
5	18	66
6	11	24
7	10	41
8	7	29
9-14	29	119
15-25	25	131
26-50	4	24
51-100	6	69
101-200	0	0
201+	0	0

Figure 133: Statistics and behavior of new and returning visitors

Session Duration ?	Sessions ?	Page Views ?
0-10 seconds	144	154
11-30 seconds	28	57
31-60 seconds	36	87
61-180 seconds	103	301
181-600 seconds	90	350
601-1800 seconds	67	407
1801+ seconds	30	344

Figure 134: Level of engagement, specified in terms of the duration of the sessions

Users Activity

Figure 135 shows the global users' activity in terms of interactions with the portal and player, i.e. events. It also details the number of sessions with at least one event, and the average number of events per session. The lower part of the figure also indicates the number for each Event Category: *portal configuration*; *Player launching* (i.e. once a content is selected for its consumption from the portal); and *player configuration*.

Figure 135: Events overview

Figure 136 provides an overview of the number of events for the 360° videos having gathered a higher number of events. This information can be more accurately processed by using the information from the QoE logger (see next sub-section).

0: El Telenotícies per dins
1: Making of FAQS
2: Diada de Sant Jordi
3: Cuinant en 360
4: Opera Romeo i Juliette al Liceu
5: Polònia
6: Desconcert Leyre
7: Desconcert Havanna

Event Label ?	Total Events ?	↓ Unique Events ?
URLs d'IMAC	335 % of Total: 6.59% (5,083)	250 % of Total: 12.16% (2,056)
1. 0	96 (28.66%)	73 (29.20%)
2. 5	91 (27.16%)	57 (22.80%)
3. 1	45 (13.43%)	37 (14.80%)
4. 3	35 (10.45%)	23 (9.20%)
5. 2	19 (5.67%)	18 (7.20%)
6. 4	19 (5.67%)	15 (6.00%)
7. 7	16 (4.78%)	14 (5.60%)
8. 6	14 (4.18%)	13 (5.20%)

Figure 136: Overview of events per content

Figure 137 shows the events from the portal settings that were used more than once. The meaning of all Event Labels listed in this figure is provided in Table 46. As expected, the language change options were the most used.

Event Label ?	Total Events ?	↓ Unique Events ?
URLs d'IMAC	541 % of Total: 10.64% (5,083)	227 % of Total: 11.04% (2,056)
1. ca	521 (96.30%)	214 (94.27%)
2. btn_st_outline	4 (0.74%)	2 (0.88%)
3. btn_st_box	3 (0.55%)	1 (0.44%)
4. btn_ind_arrow	2 (0.37%)	2 (0.88%)
5. btn_stsize_L	2 (0.37%)	1 (0.44%)
6. btn_stsize_M	2 (0.37%)	1 (0.44%)
7. btn_stsize_S	2 (0.37%)	1 (0.44%)
8. btn_ls	1 (0.18%)	1 (0.44%)
9. btn_pointer_L	1 (0.18%)	1 (0.44%)
10. btn_stpos_down	1 (0.18%)	1 (0.44%)

Figure 137: Overview of portal settings events

The events referred to interactions with the player were clearly the most frequent. In particular, 2,923 events were registered when using the player in non-VR mode, and 1,134 when using VR mode. Figure 138 lists the player interaction events that were used more than 10 times during the open pilot. The meaning of the listed Event labels in the figures is detailed in Table 48. Figure 139 shows the statistics for the player language change events, while Figure 140 lists the most used player interaction events in VR mode (i.e. when wearing an HMD). In this case, the filter has been applied to events used more than 5 times to provide a wider sample, as the number of events in this category is lower than for the general case.

Event Label [?]	Total Events [?]	Unique Events [?] ↓
URLs d'IMAC	4,057 % of Total: 79.82% (5,083)	1,493 % of Total: 72.62% (2,056)
1. pause-button	412 (10.16%)	146 (9.78%)
2. play-button	335 (8.26%)	130 (8.71%)
3. trad-menu-background	437 (10.77%)	129 (8.64%)
4. disable-st-button	199 (4.91%)	101 (6.76%)
5. settings-button	343 (8.45%)	95 (6.36%)
6. background-progress	283 (6.98%)	84 (5.63%)
7. settingsGeneral	140 (3.45%)	70 (4.69%)
8. back-button	233 (5.74%)	52 (3.48%)
9. settingsIndicator	110 (2.71%)	52 (3.48%)
10. settingsST	99 (2.44%)	50 (3.35%)
11. settingsIndicatorArrows	92 (2.27%)	48 (3.22%)
12. forward-seek-button	397 (9.79%)	46 (3.08%)
13. play-progress	78 (1.92%)	27 (1.81%)
14. zoom-button	88 (2.17%)	26 (1.74%)
15. settingsIndicatorRadar	29 (0.71%)	25 (1.67%)
16. enhanced-menu-button	23 (0.57%)	22 (1.47%)
17. show-st-button	30 (0.74%)	22 (1.47%)
18. subtitlesShowPositions	35 (0.86%)	21 (1.41%)
19. back-seek-button	94 (2.32%)	20 (1.34%)
20. plus-volume-button	58 (1.43%)	18 (1.21%)
21. slider-progress	46 (1.13%)	18 (1.21%)
22. disable-sl-button	24 (0.59%)	16 (1.07%)
23. subtitlesBackground	31 (0.76%)	16 (1.07%)
24. tradoptionmenubackground	24 (0.59%)	16 (1.07%)
25. subtitlesLanguage	17 (0.42%)	15 (1.00%)
26. subtitlesSizes	24 (0.59%)	14 (0.94%)
27. subtitlesTopButton	19 (0.47%)	14 (0.94%)
28. settingsPointerSize	18 (0.44%)	13 (0.87%)
29. subtitlesOutline	25 (0.62%)	13 (0.87%)
30. traditional-menu-button	13 (0.32%)	13 (0.87%)

31.	seek-progress	20 (0.49%)	12 (0.80%)
32.	subtitlesLargeSizeButton	20 (0.49%)	12 (0.80%)
33.	disable-ad-button	23 (0.57%)	11 (0.74%)
34.	subtitlesBottomButton	28 (0.69%)	11 (0.74%)
35.	settingsVoiceControl	14 (0.35%)	10 (0.67%)
36.	disable-ast-button	14 (0.35%)	8 (0.54%)
37.	mute-volume-button	13 (0.32%)	8 (0.54%)
38.	settingsMenuPointerLarge	8 (0.20%)	8 (0.54%)
39.	subtitlesSceneButton	16 (0.39%)	8 (0.54%)
40.	subtitlesSemitrans	7 (0.17%)	7 (0.47%)
41.	subtitlesLanguageCatButton	7 (0.17%)	6 (0.40%)
42.	minus-volume-button	56 (1.38%)	5 (0.33%)
43.	settingsLanguages	9 (0.22%)	5 (0.33%)
44.	settingsUserProfile	6 (0.15%)	5 (0.33%)
45.	subtitlesSpeakerButton	6 (0.15%)	5 (0.33%)

Figure 138: "Interaction with Player" Events Used more than 10 times

Event Label ?	Total Events ?	Unique Events ?
URLs d'IMAC	521 % of Total: 10.25% (5,083)	214 % of Total: 10.41% (2,056)
1. ca	521 (100.00%)	214 (100.00%)

Figure 139: Player menu language change events

Event Label [?]	Total Events [?] ↓	Unique Events [?]
URLs d'IMAC	1,134 % of Total: 22.31% (5,083)	317 % of Total: 15.42% (2,056)
1. settings-button	149 (13.14%)	19 (5.99%)
2. pause-button	127 (11.20%)	17 (5.36%)
3. play-button	121 (10.67%)	18 (5.68%)
4. back-button	91 (8.02%)	15 (4.73%)
5. trad-menu-background	74 (6.53%)	17 (5.36%)
6. disable-st-button	58 (5.11%)	20 (6.31%)
7. settingsGeneral	53 (4.67%)	18 (5.68%)
8. forward-seek-button	50 (4.41%)	5 (1.58%)
9. settingsIndicator	49 (4.32%)	18 (5.68%)
10. settingsIndicatorArrows	45 (3.97%)	17 (5.36%)
11. background-progress	39 (3.44%)	8 (2.52%)
12. settingsST	28 (2.47%)	11 (3.47%)
13. plus-volume-button	21 (1.85%)	4 (1.26%)
14. subtitlesBottomButton	21 (1.85%)	6 (1.89%)
15. subtitlesShowPositions	15 (1.32%)	7 (2.21%)
16. settingsIndicatorRadar	14 (1.23%)	11 (3.47%)
17. subtitlesSceneButton	12 (1.06%)	4 (1.26%)
18. show-st-button	10 (0.88%)	7 (2.21%)
19. subtitlesBackground	9 (0.79%)	4 (1.26%)
20. subtitlesTopButton	9 (0.79%)	5 (1.58%)

21. disable-ast-button	8 (0.71%)	2 (0.63%)
22. subtitlesOutline	8 (0.71%)	4 (1.26%)
23. voiceControlOnButton	8 (0.71%)	3 (0.95%)
24. settingsVoiceControl	7 (0.62%)	4 (1.26%)
25. disable-ad-button	6 (0.53%)	2 (0.63%)
26. settingsPointerSize	6 (0.53%)	4 (1.26%)
27. tradoptionmenubackground	6 (0.53%)	3 (0.95%)
28. back-seek-button	5 (0.44%)	3 (0.95%)
29. disable-sl-button	5 (0.44%)	3 (0.95%)
30. settingsLanguages	5 (0.44%)	2 (0.63%)
31. subtitlesLanguage	5 (0.44%)	4 (1.26%)
32. subtitlesSizes	5 (0.44%)	3 (0.95%)
33. zoom-button	5 (0.44%)	3 (0.95%)

Figure 140: "Interaction with Player" Events in VR mode used more than 5 times

9.2.5.2 QoS/QoE Logger Results

This section provides the results from the QoS/QoE logger for the Spanish pilot, but clustered for each of the three offered experiences.

Selected videos and duration

Table 63 provides a summary of the amount of times each video was watched in the Spanish pilot.

Content	HbbTV 360° Companion Screen	360° Video Portal	Web-based 360° Companion Screen	Count
El Telenotícies per dins	44	115	69	260
Polònia 360	38	92	38	185
Making of FAQs	30	60	29	130
Cuinant en 360°	21	45	28	111
Diada de Sant Jordi	10	28	11	64
Òpera Romeo i Juliette al Liceu	12	16	4	41
Desconcert "Leyre"	--	15	--	41
Desconcert "Havanna"	--	11	--	14
Total	155	382	179 (+70 linear)	718 (+70 linear)

Table 63: Distribution of durations of the video watching experience for each 360° video service (Spanish pilot)

Table 64 provides a summary of the distribution of the amount of time during which each video was watched. It has been represented separately, for each one of the scenarios that CCMA has proposed. For the multi-screen experiences, the results are provided for the 360º videos watched on the companion devices.

Note that the video watching experience can be longer than the duration of the video if playback control commands (e.g. pauses, seeks...) are issued. This happened few times for some videos.

Web-based 360º Companion Screen

Content	Duration (s)	0-5%	5-25%	25-50%	50-75%	75-100%	100-200%	>200%	Total
El Telenotícies per dins	864	49 (71%)	9 (13%)	1 (1%)	3 (4%)	2 (3%)	3 (4%)	2 (3%)	69 (100%)
Diada de Sant Jordi	511	4 (36%)	6 (55%)	1 (9%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	11 (100%)
Òpera Romeo i Juliette al Liceu	509	1 (25%)	1 (25%)	2 (50%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	4 (100%)
Making of FAQS	606	19 (66%)	6 (21%)	3 (10%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (3%)	0 (0%)	29 (100%)
Cuinant en 360º	510	9 (32%)	15 (54%)	1 (4%)	1 (4%)	1 (4%)	1 (4%)	0 (0%)	28 (100%)
Polònia 360º	215	18 (47%)	11 (29%)	3 (8%)	1 (3%)	3 (8%)	1 (3%)	1 (3%)	38 (100%)
Total		100 (56%)	48 (27%)	11 (6%)	5 (3%)	6 (3%)	6 (3%)	3 (2%)	179 (100%)

HbbTV 360º Companion Screen

Content	Duration (s)	0-5%	5-25%	25-50%	50-75%	75-100%	100-200%	>200%	Total
El Telenotícies per dins	864	23 (52%)	14 (32%)	3 (7%)	0 (0%)	4 (9%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	44 (100%)
Diada de Sant Jordi	511	1 (10%)	5 (50%)	3 (30%)	1 (10%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	10 (100%)
Òpera Romeo i Juliette al Liceu	509	2 (17%)	4 (33%)	4 (33%)	1 (8%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (8%)	12 (100%)
Making of FAQS	606	9 (30%)	7 (23%)	4 (13%)	4 (13%)	2 (7%)	4 (13%)	0 (0%)	30 (100%)
Cuinant en 360º	510	4 (19%)	12 (57%)	0 (0%)	2 (10%)	2 (10%)	1 (5%)	0 (0%)	21 (100%)
Polònia 360º	215	10 (26%)	18 (47%)	6 (16%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	4 (11%)	0 (0%)	38 (100%)
Total		49 (32%)	60 (39%)	20 (13%)	8 (5%)	8 (5%)	9 (6%)	1 (1%)	155 (100%)

360º Video Portal

Content	Duration (s)	0-5%	5-25%	25-50%	50-75%	75-100%	100-200%	>200%	Total
El Telenotícies per dins	864	50 (43%)	40 (35%)	11 (10%)	6 (5%)	2 (2%)	5 (4%)	1 (1%)	115 (100%)
Diada de Sant Jordi	511	11 (39%)	9 (32%)	3 (11%)	1 (4%)	0 (0%)	4 (14%)	0 (0%)	28 (100%)
Òpera Romeo i Juliette al Liceu	509	8 (50%)	4 (25%)	1 (6%)	1 (6%)	0 (0%)	0 (12%)	0 (0%)	16 (100%)
Making of FAQS	606	23 (38%)	38 (18%)	7 (12%)	3 (5%)	1 (2%)	7 (12%)	1 (2%)	60 (100%)
Cuinant en 360º	510	17 (38%)	14 (31%)	3 (7%)	1 (2%)	4 (9%)	3 (7%)	3 (7%)	45 (100%)
Polònia 360º	215	20 (22%)	26 (28%)	10 (11%)	7 (8%)	5 (5%)	20 (22%)	4 (4%)	92 (100%)
Desconcert "Leyre"	272	1 (7%)	5 (33%)	2 (13%)	3 (20%)	3 (20%)	0 (0%)	1 (7%)	15 (100%)
Desconcert "Havana"	252	3 (27%)	3 (27%)	2 (18%)	1 (9%)	2 (18%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	11 (100%)
Total		133 (35%)	119 (31%)	39 (10%)	23 (6%)	17 (4%)	41 (11%)	10 (3%)	382 (100%)

Table 64: Distribution of durations of the video watching experience for each 360º video service (Spanish pilot)

Interactions with the menu elements

Table 65 details the amount of interactions with the player menu elements for each of the 360º videos. The legend for the events, also reported separately for each one of the scenarios, in the first row of the table is:

- BSeek and FSeek: Seek Backward and Forward
- VPB: Interactions with the Progress Bar
- ST: Subtitles enable (eST) and disable (dST)
- Enhanced: Activation of the Enhanced-Accessibility variant of the Menu

To contribute to a better understanding of this information, a screen capture of the ImAc player menu is provided in Figure 141.

It can be seen that the interactions with the playback control menu elements were quite frequent, especially with regard to the interaction with the subtitles. Regarding the use of access services, subtitles were one of the most activated feature in all the scenarios. The 360º Video portal was where users interacted more, with 72 activations and 11 deactivations of subtitles, while in the Web-based Companion Screen subtitles were only activated 9 times and deactivated 2 times. In total, they were activated 149 times, and only deactivated 27 times.

More detailed statistics about the specific interactions with the settings and options for the access services presentation will be provided in the next sub-section.

Besides, it can be seen that the "Settings" sub-menu was used for many of the video watching sessions, and that the Web-based 360º scenario is the one with less interaction.

Web-based 360° Companion Screen

Content	Play	Pause	BSeek	FSeek	VPB	eST	dST	Settings	Zoom	Enhanced	Total
El Telenotícies per dins	8	10	0	3	3	4	0	11	3	0	42
Diada de Sant Jordi	2	1	0	2	0	1	0	1	0	0	7
Òpera Romeo i Juliette al Liceu	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Making of FAQS	6	5	2	4	3	0	0	1	0	2	23
Polònia	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3
Cuinant en 360°	1	4	0	0	0	4	2	4	0	2	17
Total	18	22	2	9	6	9	2	17	3	4	92

HbbTV 360° Companion Screen

Content	Play	Pause	BSeek	FSeek	VPB	eST	dST	Settings	Zoom	Enhanced	Total
El Telenotícies per dins	12	17	2	15	0	7	0	9	0	1	63
Diada de Sant Jordi	2	5	0	26	0	2	0	6	2	0	43
Òpera Romeo i Juliette al Liceu	4	9	0	1	0	19	2	10	0	0	45
Making of FAQS	14	20	2	5	0	28	4	17	15	2	107
Polònia	12	22	11	5	1	4	0	6	5	0	66
Cuinant en 360°	7	9	12	3	0	8	8	4	6	2	59
Total	51	82	27	55	1	68	14	52	28	5	383

360° Video Portal

Content	Play	Pause	BSeek	FSeek	VPB	eST	dST	Settings	Zoom	Enhanced	Total
El Telenotícies per dins	51	44	12	155	13	17	4	27	18	3	344
Diada de Sant Jordi	2	1	0	28	0	3	0	11	4	2	51
Òpera Romeo i Juliette al Liceu	5	9	0	0	0	1	0	4	6	1	26
Making of FAQS	15	13	0	15	1	5	2	13	6	0	70
Polònia	42	47	0	2	2	30	3	60	5	5	196
Cuinant en 360°	27	24	2	7	3	8	1	24	2	0	98
Desconcert "Leyre"	0	3	0	0	0	7	1	15	3	2	31
Desconcert "Havana"	2	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	3
Total	144	141	14	207	19	72	11	154	44	13	819

Table 65: Interaction with the Menu for each 360° video service (Spanish pilot)

Figure 141: Screenshot of the ImAc player menu

Interactions with the Sub-Menu Elements

General Settings

Table 66 provides statistics regarding the interactions with the “General Settings” section of the player menu (see Figure 142). The legend for the entries in the first row of the table (menu section and options) is indicated next:

- Gen: button to access the General Settings
- Lang: Set Language, with the German (Ger), English (Eng), Spanish (Esp) and Catalan (Cat) options
- V.C.: Voice Control, with the On and Off options
- P.S.: Pointer Size, with the Small (S), Medium (M) and Large (L) options
- U.P.: User Profile, with the Save and Reset options
- Ind: Indicator, with the None, Arrow, and Radar options.

Web-based 360° Companion Screen

Content	Gen	Lang	Eng	Esp	Ger	Cat	V.C.	On	Off
El Telenotícies per dins	6	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Diada de Sant Jordi	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Òpera Romeo i Juliette al Liceu	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Making of FAQs	1	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	0
Cuinant en 360°	2	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
Polònia	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	10	1	0	0	0	1	3	1	0

Content	P.S.	S	M	L	U.P.	Reset	Save	Ind	None	Arrow	Radar	Total
El Telenotícies per dins	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0	2	1	15
Diada de Sant Jordi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	3
Òpera Romeo i Juliette al Liceu	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Making of FAQs	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	4
Cuinant en 360º	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	6
Polònia	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	4	1	28

HbbTV 360º Companion Screen

Content	Gen	Lang	Eng	Esp	Ger	Cat	V.C.	On	Off
El Telenotícies per dins	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Diada de Sant Jordi	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Òpera Romeo i Juliette al Liceu	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Making of FAQs	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cuinant en 360º	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Polònia	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	20	2	0						

Content	P.S.	S	M	L	U.P.	Reset	Save	Ind	None	Arrow	Radar	Total
El Telenotícies per dins	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	6	0	2	2	22
Diada de Sant Jordi	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	3	0	3	0	11
Òpera Romeo i Juliette al Liceu	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	2	0	2	0	10
Making of FAQs	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
Cuinant en 360º	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	5
Polònia	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	8	1	0	4	0	0	0	51	2	33	21	232

360º Video Portal

Content	Gen	Lang	Eng	Esp	Ger	Cat	V.C.	On	Off
El Telenotícies per dins	13	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Diada de Sant Jordi	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Òpera Romeo i Juliette al Liceu	3	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Making of FAQS	8	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
Cuinant en 360º	7	0	0	0	0	0	3	5	1
Polònia	24	2	1	0	0	1	2	0	0
Desconcert "Leyre"	5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Desconcert "Havana"	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	63	2	1	0	0	1	7	5	1

Content	P.S.	S	M	L	U.P.	Reset	Save	Ind	None	Arrow	Radar	Total
El Telenotícies per dins	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10	0	10	1	34
Diada de Sant Jordi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	5
Òpera Romeo i Juliette al Liceu	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	6
Making of FAQS	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	6	0	4	3	23
Cuinant en 360º	3	1	0	3	0	0	0	5	0	4	2	34
Polonia	2	1	1	0	2	0	2	23	0	23	6	90
Desconcert "Leyre"	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	0	3	2	15
Desconcert "Havana"	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	5	2	1	3	3	0	2	51	0	46	14	207

Table 66: Interaction with general settings for each 360º service (Spanish pilot)

It can be seen that the "Settings menu" was opened quite frequently, mostly in the 360º Video Portal (63 times) rather than on the HbbTV 360º Companion Screen (20 times) and the Web-based 360º Companion Screen (10 times). The Language Change feature was not used so often. The Pointer Size menu was checked 14 times, and 7 times was set to the Large size. The "User Profile" sub-menu was checked 3 times, and settings were saved twice. The "Indicator" feature was used quite frequently (108 times), from where arrows (83 times) and radar (36 times) were activated with a noteworthy frequency. This reflects the usefulness of this feature, and that arrows are commonly preferred to the radar, although some users still prefer to select the radar.

Figure 142: General settings menu

Subtitle Presentation Options

Table 67 provides statistics regarding the interactions with the Subtitle Presentation features and options of the ImAc player (see Figure 143). The legend for the entries in the first row of this table (menu section and options) is indicated next:

- ST: Menu Control to open the Subtitles Settings.
- Size: Subtitles Size, with Small (S), Medium (M), and Large (L) options.
- Bcgd: Background, with Semi-transparent background box (Semi), and Outline (Out) options.
- Pos: Position or Presentation modes, with Top (T), Bottom (B), Fixed to Speaker (Spk), and Evenly Spaced every 120° (x3) options.
- E2R: Easy-to-Read Subtitles, with On and Off options.

As can be seen in the table, the ST settings menu was opened with a noteworthy frequency. Again, the 360° Video Portal presents more activity than the other two scenarios. The language sub-menu was entered 15 times. Regarding the subtitle size, this feature was used 11 times, and user selected the larger size more frequently. Likewise, the background sub-menu was opened 26 times, but no a clear preference towards using a semi-transparent background text or an outline can be observed. Regarding the subtitle position, the sub-menu was opened 74 times, and the preferred option seems to be bottom, but the other options were also selected. It is also remarkable that the subtitles attached to the speaker were activated only 3 times, but the evenly spaced every 120° mode was never activated.

Web-based 360º Companion Screen

Content	ST	Lang	Eng	Esp	Ger	Cat	Size	S	M	L	Bckg	Semi	Out
El Telenotícies per dins	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Diada de Sant Jordi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Òpera Romeo i Juliette al Liceu	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Making of FAQS	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cuinant en 360º	2	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	3	1
Polònia	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	4	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	3	1

Content	Pos	T	B	SpK	X3	E2R	On	Off	Total
El Telenotícies per dins	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
Diada de Sant Jordi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Òpera Romeo i Juliette al Liceu	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Making of FAQS	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cuinant en 360º	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9
Polònia	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	0	11							

HbbTV 360º Companion Screen

Content	ST	Lang	Eng	Esp	Ger	Cat	Size	S	M	L	Bckg	Semi	Out
El Telenotícies per dins	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Diada de Sant Jordi	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Òpera Romeo i Juliette al Liceu	6	3	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	2	0	0	0
Making of FAQS	13	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	2	1	1
Cuinant en 360º	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Polònia	4	2	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	2	0	0
Total	25	6	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	2	4	1	1

Content	Pos	T	B	SpK	X3	E2R	On	Off	Total
El Telenotícies per dins	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Diada de Sant Jordi	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Òpera Romeo i Juliette al Liceu	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	17
Making of FAQS	5	3	1	1	0	0	0	0	29
Cuinant en 360º	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
Polònia	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	10
Total	8	5	1	1	0	0	0	0	59

360º Video Portal

Content	ST	Lang	Eng	Esp	Ger	Cat	Size	S	M	L	Bckg	Semi	Out
El Telenotícies per dins	11	2	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	4	0	2
Diada de Sant Jordi	5	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	1
Òpera Romeo i Juliette al Liceu	2	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1
Making of FAQS	8	0	0	0	0	0	3	1	0	3	1	1	1
Cuinant en 360º	3	1	0	0	0	0	2	0	1	2	2	1	2
Polònia	14	3	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	6	3	7
Desconcert "Leyre"	6	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	2
Desconcert "Havana"	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	49	9	0	0	0	1	8	1	1	7	21	5	7

Content	Pos	T	B	SpK	X3	E2R	On	Off	Total
El Telenotícies per dins	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	25
Diada de Sant Jordi	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	9
Òpera Romeo i Juliette al Liceu	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6
Making of FAQS	5	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	27
Cuinant en 360º	2	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	17
Polònia	8	7	16	1	0	0	0	0	67
Desconcert "Leyre"	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12
Desconcert "Havana"	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	17	10	20	2	0	0	0	0	163

Table 67: Interactions with subtitle presentation features and options for each video service (Spanish pilot)

Figure 143: Subtitle presentation options

9.2.5.3 Questionnaire

As far as the questionnaire is concerned, 68.8% of those replying it reported having used the subtitles. When asked about the different subtitle features, their assessment on a 5-point scale when asked if they liked different features is as follows:

	1	2	3	4	5	I did not use it	Mean	SD	Median
Arrow	-	-	6 (20%)	10 (33.3%)	13 (43.3%)	1 (3.3%)	4.25	0.79	4
Radar	5 (16.7%)	6 (20%)	7 (23.3%)	4 (13.3%)	5 (16.7%)	3 (10%)	2.92	1.38	3
Size personalisation	-	1 (3.3%)	4 (13.3%)	15 (50%)	9 (30%)	1 (3.3%)	4.10	0.77	4
Position personalisation	-	3 (10%)	4 (13.3%)	13 (43.4%)	9 (30%)	1 (3.3%)	3.96	0.94	4
Background personalisation	-	1 (3.3%)	5 (16.7%)	13 (43.4%)	9 (30%)	2 (6.7%)	4.07	0.81	4
Move subtitles with mouse/controller	-	4 (13.3%)	7 (23.3%)	6 (20%)	11 (36.7%)	2 (6.7%)	3.86	1.11	4

Table 68: Questionnaire results (CCMA open pilot)

Most users liked the arrow, and to a lesser extent, the radar, but in both cases the values are above average. Size, position and background personalisation, as well as moving the subtitles with mouse/controller, received positive feedback, mainly on the 4-5 point range.

When asked if they liked having the traditional content on a main screen and an immersive 360 content on a second device, 28 (68.18%) replied positively, only 2 (4.5%) replied negatively, and 10 (27.26%) reported not having used this feature.

When asked how easy it was to use the player on a 5-point Likert scale, results were very positive, with most participants selecting 4 or 5 on a 5-point Likert scale.

1 Very difficult	2	3	4	5 Very easy	Mean	SD	Median
1 (2.3%)	1 (2.3%)	11 (25%)	19 (43.2%)	12 (27.3%)	3.9	0.9	4

Table 69: Player evaluation (CCMA open pilot)

Finally, when asked if they would recommend the player to a friend, 90.9% replied positively, and only 9.1% did not. Qualitative feedback at the end was very positive. For instance:

- “A very good option that allows you to enjoy more”.
- “Motivating and pleasant experience, teleporting to distant realities, seeing again in more detail a content that you have already seen, and being able to see in such a small space as the screen of a smartphone large spaces regardless of the direction you use”
- “A new experience that is very useful for persons with disabilities”.

Some room for improvement was found in the ImAc player instructions and on the saving preference function. It was also observed that older people found it more difficult to follow the subtitles on two devices, and that some users preferred this mode for a second viewing of the content.

9.3 Conclusions

In total, the 360^o videos in the open pilots were watched up to 1,360 times, reaching 428 visualisations in the German pilot, 788 in the Spanish pilot and the remaining 144 coming from the general ImAc branches. This means an average of 40 videos watched per day. Overall, more than 800 users were reached.

Data show that in the German pilot subtitles were activated 139 times, and only deactivated 36 times, whereas Sign Language was activated 121 times, and only deactivated 48 times. In the Spanish pilot, the subtitles were activated a total of 149 times and deactivated 27 times on the three different offered scenarios.

Although the contents of the pilots were different, it is worth highlighting that questionnaires allowed gathering very positive feedback on ImAc developments. 90.9% of the participants answering the questionnaire at CCMA and 80% at RBB would recommend the ImAc player to a friend. When asked how easy it was to use, most values for both the German and the Spanish pilot are on the top range: 4-5 points on a 5-point Likert scale. Actually, it is interesting to see that the percentages are almost identical:

- 27.27% of the users in the CCMA open pilot answering this question and 27.59% in the RBB pilot select the maximum value, 5 points.
- 42.18% at CCMA and 44.83% at RBB select 4 points.
- 25% at CCMA and 24.14% at RBB select 3 points.

Regarding subtitling, 68.8% of users at CCMA and 81% at RBB report having used the subtitles, with positive assessments of all the features, especially the arrow. Participants using Sign Language in the RBB action (54%) also assessed positively the ImAc implementations in this access service. Open comments are encouraging and praise the ImAc developments, as they allow having new experiences.

10 CONCLUSIONS

The purpose of ImAc pilots (German pilot, Spanish pilot, cross-national pilot) was to introduce to a panel of users the tools and services developed for creating and consuming 360° contents and to gather qualitative measurements and feedback about their experience. Pilot actions developed in different phases have allowed to test:

- four tools (Accessibility Content Manager, subtitling editing tool, audio description editing tool, Sign Language editor tool)
- one innovative approach to setting the angle via glasses,
- the player interface with different user profiles, and
- different presentation modes for accessibility services (subtitling, Sign Language interpreting, audio description, audio subtitling).

In WP2, 77 users contributed to define user scenarios, needs and requirements through different ImAc actions (see D.21).

In WP5, the number of users involved in the actions is above 1,100 (Table 65).

Pilot actions have been used in ImAc as a mainly qualitative tool to get user feedback on their needs and requirements regarding different implementations or possibilities. Agile tests with more reduced samples have been prioritised in the initial phases to inform technological developments. Overall, pilot actions have been a central element in the user-centric approach taken in the ImAc project and have provided input on:

- Professional tools features
- Player interface features
- Presentations modes for ST: comfort field of view, positioning, guiding mechanism, non-speech information, and easy-to-read subtitles
- Presentation modes for SL: comfort field of view, guiding mechanisms, display of signer video, combination of SL with ST, and speaker representation through text or emoticons
- Presentation modes for AD: Classic, Static, and Dynamic presentation modes; Classic, Radio, and Extended presentation modes
- Presentation modes for AST: Classic and Dynamic presentation modes; AST only, and AST-AD presentation modes

Pilot actions	User profile	Number of users
ACM (first and second iteration)	Professionals	7 + 27
Subtitling editor	Professionals	27+ 16
Audio description editor	Professionals	24+ 24
Sign Language editor	Professionals	6
Focus groups: subtitling angle with editor and glasses	Professionals	4 + 6
	TOTAL	141
Subtitling pilot phase 1 in Germany, user interface and presentation modes	Home users	12
Subtitling pilot phase 1 in Spain, user interface and presentation modes	Home users	13
Subtitling pre-pilot 2 action in Spain	Home users	12
Subtitling pre-pilot 2 action, Germany	Home users	12
Intermediate subtitling action, in Spain	Home users	48
Easy-to-read action, in Spain (I)	Home users	8
Easy-to-read action, in Spain (II)	Home users	36
SL pre-pilot 2 action, in Germany	Home users	10
AD/AST pre-pilot action 2 in the UK	Home users	5
AD/AST pre-pilot action 2 in Spain	Home users	6
Cross-national in the UK	Home users	31
Cross-national in Spain	Home users	30
	TOTAL	223
German open pilot (pilot phase 2),	Home users	313
General ImAc branches (pilot phase 2, analysed under German open pilot)	Home users	233
Spanish open pilot (pilot phase 2)	Home users	281
	TOTAL	827

Table 65: Users involved in pilot actions

Some of the main contributions are:

- The ImAc player is an innovative tool, and the different interaction possibilities it offers (voice control, accessible menu) receive positive assessments by participants.
- The ImAc tools are also unique. Professional user tests have allowed to improve the tools but, most importantly, have provided innovative input on professional user preferences in a new environment. An innovative method of setting the angle by means of a virtual reality controller has been developed and tested, with positive feedback.
- Guiding mechanism such as the arrow developed by ImAc have been welcome by users.
- Users have also expressed a preference for the textual representation of non-speech information rather than emojis.
- The ImAc solution for positioning subtitles (always visible) proved to be more effective in terms of presence than standard solutions used in other environments (fixed positioned every 120°).
- ImAc has created innovative easy-to-read subtitles, and it has been demonstrated that they are preferred by certain sections of the population.
- ImAc test participants prefer to use both German Sign Language and subtitles.
- New presentation modes for AD and AST have been tested in ImAc, pointing at the relevance and challenges of audio and scripting styles in immersive environments.

Across the different actions, many users have valued the easiness of the tools and interfaces developed in ImAc. This has been possible thanks, in many cases, to the involvement of user associations across countries, to which the ImAc project is thankful. Users have generally been fascinated by the possibilities and challenges opened by immersive media and have provided useful feedback on the solutions proposed by the ImAc project to respond to a clear societal need: the need to provide access to immersive media to all, regardless of our capabilities.

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12 ANNEXES

In the annexes we have reproduced the documents with the methodology for each test and the reports as they were generated during the project, with minimal changes in the formatting. They include raw data for the different pilot action.

To make the annexes shorter, SUS, IPQ and demographic questionnaires have been moved to independent annexes and reference has been made to them in the document.

ANNEX 1. ACCESSIBILITY CONTENT MANAGER METHODOLOGY (FIRST ITERATION: DEVELOPMENT)

1. What to test?

- ACM: <http://imac.gpac-licensing.com/acm/>

2. Methodology: overview

- **Research tools:** questionnaire
- **Measures:** usability and preferences
- **Participants:** 3-4 professional content managers and related professionals
- **Materials:** web editor, 360° video (*Polònia*), subtitle file, and user guide
- **Experimental protocol:** users will be asked to perform certain tasks and then report on the usability and preferences through an online questionnaire
- **Reporting:** results will be included in a report created by UAB. This will be done exporting data from the Google Form, so partners do not need to create a specific reporting document.
- **Please make sure you test the experimental protocol below before the actual pilot action and that you have all materials and ethical forms ready.**

3. Methodology: experimental protocol

- **Welcome and ethical clearance:** users are welcome and sign information sheets and consent forms. They are available under WP1/Project Management/0Deliverables/D1.2. Ethical Considerations/Ethical forms: information and consent forms. Please remember to sign them and provide original copies to UAB.
- **Short presentation by facilitator:** the facilitator gives a short presentation on the main features of the ACM, and provides participants a quick user's guide. The guide is available here: <https://drive.google.com/open?id=1OGkDhg74zcanWDi-yWAKK7cHMnB-vF7y>
- **Tasks.** Participants are asked to perform a series of tasks individually on a computer where the materials are available. Please make sure that the video file name and the subtitle file name is different for every user if they are interacting with the ACM at the same time. Suggested names for CCMA: Polonia_CCMA_P1, Polonia_CCMA_P2, etc. (where P is participant) Suggested names for RBB: Polonia_RBB_P1, Polonia_RBB_P2, etc (where P is participant) Please provide the following written instructions to participants.

Thanks for agreeing to take part in this test. We kindly ask you to please perform the following tasks using the video and subtitle file provided. When you finish, you will be asked to reply to a questionnaire.

1. Create a new asset.
2. Upload a video.
3. Create a subtitling task.
4. View report.
5. Duplicate an asset.
6. Create a subtitling task in more than one language.
7. Assign the subtitling task to a user.
8. Upload an existing subtitle file to the asset.
9. Delete an asset.
10. Recover an asset from the Bin.

Once you finish, please reply to questionnaire available on this link: <https://goo.gl/forms/5tQ9uEShqVMC3IzB2>

4. Questionnaire

It will be provided to the participants using an online form, but is included below for reference.
<https://goo.gl/forms/5tQ9uEShqVMC3lzB2>

1. Sex: female/male/other/I prefer not to reply
2. Age: (open numeric field)
3. Please describe your current job: (open field)
4. For how long have you been working in the field of access services? (open field)
5. What content management software do you normally use? (open field)
6. After performing the previous tasks, please score the accessibility content manager.

SUS, see Annex 43

7. Now please reply to the following questions in your own words.

- What did you like most about the accessibility content manager?
- What did you like less about the accessibility content manager?
- What do you think could be improved, and how?
- What missing functionalities did you find?
- Was it intuitive? Yes / No. If not, why?
- Other comments.

ANNEX 2. ACCESSIBILITY CONTENT MANAGER METHODOLOGY (SECOND ITERATION: IMPLEMENTATION)

1. What and when to test?

- Usability for ACM: <https://imac.gpac-licensing.com/acm/>
- Timeline: July 2019.

2. Methodology: overview

- **Research tools:** online questionnaire.
- **Measures:** usability and preferences.
- **Participants:** experts in content management. We should aim at 30 to get statistically relevant results; otherwise it will be qualitative data. RBB and CCMA will let us know how many users they can involve. CCMA will not be giving a compensation.
- **Language of the test:** English.
- **Materials:** ACM, 360° video (*Polònia by CCMA*) and subtitle file. Quick user guide: https://drive.google.com/open?id=1KwNRcn_HZPntUNKI7G3Qmanzm7NXBC72
- **Duration:** 45 minutes
- **Experimental protocol:** users will be asked to perform certain tasks and then report on the usability and preferences through an online questionnaire.
- **Reporting:** results will be included in a report. This will be done exporting data from the Google Form.
- **Please make sure you test the experimental protocol below before the actual pilot action and that you have all materials and ethical forms ready.**

3. Methodology: experimental protocol

- **Online test:** the users will access this test online, via email plus Google Forms/Other internal tools, and there will be no supervision or facilitators involved. The test will include different steps (some info will be in the email, and some other in the online form, see the table below):

Section	Description	Where?
Section 1	Welcome and presentation of the ImAc project and the test.	E-mail
Section 2	Ethical clearance: information sheet and consent form to be approved by the participant. Please remember that if you give a compensation, the ethical forms are different. Please let UAB know and we will provide the forms.	Google Form: https://forms.gle/7oo6A8MdiFngGqj9
Section 3	Reading the user guide. The participants will have to read the provided user guide for the ACM.	The updated guide is available here: https://drive.google.com/open?id=1KwNRcn_HZPntUNKI7G3Qmanzm7NXBC72
Section 4	Performing the tasks.	See below.
Section 5	Filling in the questionnaires.	Google Form: https://goo.gl/forms/0Wdiupb50qqSGlei1
Section 6	Thank participants.	In the email.

- **Materials.** The video to be used will be “Polònia” by CCMA. The video will be in low resolution to avoid overloading the server and make the subtitling task smoother.
- **Recruitment & User Code Assignment.**

Participants will be recruited via contacts, by email/social networks, etc. The test has been designed in English so that professionals from different countries can participate. Once the list of participants is final, they will be contacted by email to provide instructions and access to the online form and web editor.

Different users (Px-Px) will be created with the role of content manager. The login information will be provided by email to the users. Then, they will access the ImAc ACM.

This user name will be the user code that they will need to enter in the questionnaire when requested.

- **Contact:**

To conduct the test, professional content managers (who have previously agreed on participating) will be contacted by email:

Subject: Test for ImAc ACM - Instructions

Dear participant,

First of all, many thanks for participating in our study.

One of the main objectives of ImAc is the development of a content manager with the aim of managing the procedure of access service production for 360° media, that is for the production of subtitles (ST), sign language (SL) and audio description (AD) files. You can upload content, assign production tasks to access service producers (professionals or service providers of access service content), check the access service files produced and so on.

The **aim** of the test is to gather feedback from professional users like you regarding the ImAc web ACM for 360° content and access services that we have developed. This feedback will enormously help us to improve the tool and make it better for professional content managers to use it in the future.

This test is built in relation to ImAc (Immersive Accessibility) project. The goal of ImAc project is to explore how accessibility services (such as subtitles, audio description, or sign language) can be integrated with immersive media. <http://www.imac-project.eu/>

This test will approximately take **45 minutes**.

YOUR USER CODE IS: PXX.

These are the steps that you need to follow **in this order**:

1) Give your consent to participate in this test by filling this form and clicking on YES. <https://forms.gle/7oo6A8MdiFngGqj9>

2) Perform a few tasks with the subtitle editor.

1. Please first read the User Guide to get familiar with the tool: <https://drive.google.com/open?id=13mgI2QpsAOkR0qubN3L2HtB0N3AazOX>
2. Now read the instructions and proceed with the test:

We kindly ask you to please perform the following tasks using the video and subtitle file provided. When you finish, you will be asked to reply to a questionnaire.

1. Access ACM : <https://imac.gpac-licensing.com/acm/>
2. Create a new asset.
3. Upload a low quality video.
4. Create a subtitle instance.
5. Duplicate an asset.
6. Create subtitle instances in more languages.

- | |
|--|
| <ol style="list-style-type: none">7. Assign the subtitling instance to a subtitler.8. Upload an existing subtitle file to the asset.9. Delete an asset.10. Restore an asset from the Bin.11. View reports. |
|--|

This is your login information:

- User:
 - Password:
3. Tell us about yourself and your experience with the editor by replying to the following questionnaire: <https://goo.gl/forms/OWdiupb50qqSGlei1>
 4. Let us know by email that you have finished the test so that we can confirm that your data has been correctly registered.

The test will be open from today until (add date). You can proceed with the test any time during this time frame but you should do it **in just one session**.

If you have any question or technical issue, please feel free to contact me at any time.

Please, confirm that you have received this email and that you understand the instructions.

Thank you again for your collaboration!

All the best,

- **Tasks.** Participants are asked to perform a series of tasks individually on their own computers. They will need to access the ImAc ACM and perform the requested tasks. Please make sure that the video file name and the subtitle file name is different for every user if they are interacting with the ACM at the same time.

Suggested names for CCMA: Polonia_CCMA_P1, Polonia_CCMA_P2, etc. (where P is participant)

Suggested names for RBB: Polonia_RBB_P1, Polonia_RBB_P2, etc (where P is participant)

The written instructions are provided to participants by email.

REPORTING (after the tests)

Upload your report one week after the tests under Google Drive under **IMAC_SHARED_FOLDER/ WP5/ T5.1./ 2 PROFESSIONAL USER TESTS - 2019 / ACM EDITOR / PARTNER REPORTS**

It must follow the template available in the same folder.

Questionnaire

It will be provided to the participants using an online form, but is included below for reference

1. **Please select where you are performing this test:**
2. **Sex:**
3. **Age:**
4. **Please, describe your current job:**
5. **For how long have you been working in the field of access services?**
6. **What content management software do you normally use, if any?**

ANNEX 3. ACCESSIBILITY CONTENT MANAGER REPORT (FIRST ITERATION: DEVELOPMENT) (CCMA/RBB/UAB)

1. General information

- **ACM tested:** <http://imac.gpac-licensing.com/acm/>
- **Partner responsible for tests:** UAB.
- **Date of test:** July 2018
- **Research tool:** online questionnaire (Google forms)
- **Link to online form:** <https://goo.gl/forms/5tQ9uEShqVMC3lzB2>
- **Measures:** usability and preferences
- **Participants:** 7
- **User guide:** <https://drive.google.com/open?id=1OGkDhg74zcanWDi-yWAKK7cHMnB-vF7y>

2. Demographic profile of participants

In the first part of the online questionnaire, participants were asked to answer to six demographic questions.

- Demographics for users:
7. **Please select where you are performing this test:** (3) 'RBB', (4) 'CCMA'
 8. **Sex:** (2) 'Female', (5) 'Male'
 9. **Age:** '43', '31', '46', '60', '55', '50', '59'
 10. **Please, describe your current job:** (2) 'Project engineer', 'Innovation', 'Engineer', 'TV station', 'Broadcast manager', 'Research manager', 'Accessibility manager'.
 11. **For how long have you been working in the field of access services?** '9', '5', '3', '15', '10', '28', '5'
 12. **What content management software do you normally use, if any?** 'None', 'Confluence (as Wiki), Wordpress (CMS for websites)', 'Adobe AEM, WP, VPMS...', 'Anglatecnic Fingertext', 'Our own' (reply provided by CCMA participant), 'Anglatecnic', 'Eventually content management software user, but with high acknowledge about content management'.

Summary: Seven participants took part in the test (2 females and 5 males), with ages ranging 31-60. The participants had technological expertise and experience in the field of access services (varying from 3 years to 28 years). However, as only a reduced number of participants took part in this test, its results cannot be extrapolated to a wider population. Participants declared using different content management software in their daily work (Confluence, Wordpress, Adobe AEM, WP, VPMS, Fingertext and others).

3. System Usability Scale (SUS) results

3.1. Scores (question by question)

1 – strongly disagree / 5 – strongly agree

SUS statements	1	2	3	4	5
1. I think that I would like to use this system frequently	0 (0%)	3 (42,9%)	2 (28,6%)	2 (28,6%)	0 (0%)
2. I found the system unnecessarily complex	0 (0%)	3 (42,9%)	3 (42,9%)	1 (14,3%)	0 (0%)
3. I thought the system was easy to use	1 (14,3%)	2 (28,6%)	2 (28,6%)	2 (28,6%)	0 (0%)
4. I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system	2 (28,6%)	3 (42,9%)	1 (14,3%)	1 (14,3%)	0 (0%)
5. I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	0 (0%)	2 (28,6%)	0 (0%)	5 (71,4%)	0 (0%)
6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	0 (0%)	1 (14,3%)	3 (42,9%)	2 (28,6%)	1 (14,3%)
7. I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly	0 (0%)	2 (28,6%)	2 (28,6%)	2 (28,6%)	1 (14,3%)
8. I found the system very cumbersome to use	1 (14,3%)	2 (28,6%)	2 (28,6%)	2 (28,6%)	0 (0%)
9. I felt very confident using the system	1 (14,3%)	1 (14,3%)	4 (57,1%)	1 (14,3%)	0 (0%)
10. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system	2 (28,6%)	3 (42,9%)	1 (14,3%)	1 (14,3%)	0 (0%)

3.2. Summary

The SUS average score is **54.6** (below average, as the average is 68). This score is not a percentile ranking.

The graph below shows how the SUS scores associate with the percentile ranks and letter grades³. The red line specifies where the ACM is at this moment.

³ Sauro, J. 2011. Measuring usability with the System Usability Scale (SUS). Retrieved from <http://www.measuringu.com/sus.php>

The letter grade is D, and the obtained score corresponds to the percentile rank: 17-19%⁴.

4. Results from open preference questions

4.1. Results (question by question)

1. What did you like most about the accessibility content manager?

- P1: Clear arrangement.
- P2: Clear icons, not too much unnecessary text.
- P3: Clean style.
- P4: The look of the WEB GUI.
- P5: Quick responsive.
- P6: The look and the possibility to manage all videos from one screen.
- P7: Looks visually nice and intended to be intuitive.

2. What did you like less about the accessibility content manager?

- P1: The virtual folder structure/paths for assets.
- P2: Could look more modern, I was able to add videos to assets, that already got a video inside.
- P3: UI Interaction.
- P4: Still too many bugs. Icons don't always reflect the State in an easy way (for example green icons to edit accessibility content when accessibility content has not still been created). Uploaded subtitle files did not allow editing from the subtitle editor.
- P5: Video treatment... too slow or not enough refresh.
- P6: Most of action are manage with mouse, it's not clear to use.
- P7: Still to be completed some functionalities and inconsistencies.

3. What do you think could be improved, and how?

- P1: The subtitle handling. It is not instantly clear what and how many subtitles are pre-defined in the asset.
- P2: Video upload: 2 progress bars that show the same state, multiple upload of videos in assets.
- P3: Tooltips, cleaner integration.
- P4: I still see too many bugs, as for example the upload of subtitles did not work for twice, but it did work after refreshing the webpage. The ASSETS webpage allows two different presentations (as box or as lines), but after every action the presentation returns to "box" look, so it does not allow to personalise the ASSETS presentation.
- P5: Html screen refresh code.
- P6: Some icons must be more visible, more colours to distinguish different matters.
- P7: Some inconsistencies.

4. What missing functionalities did you find?

- P1: None.
- P2: Edit the subtitles in a WYSIWYG editor; set thumbnail for the video (lot of black screens in the beginning, not easy to filter the right asset), An indicator for open tasks, like indicators on iOS for mails etc.
- P3: No.
- P4: I missed the possibility to add more than one subtitler at the same time for a subtitling job. When multiple subtitles assets are active, it's not easy to discern which subtitle is chosen to be edited.
- P5: Seek video timeline doesn't work properly.
- P6: Still very first version.
- P7: As the software is in development I found too many functionalities that must be improved.

5. Was it intuitive?

- P1: Yes.
- P2: Yes.

⁴ Sauro, J. & Lewis, J. R. 2016. *Quantifying the user experience: Practical statistics for user research*. Amsterdam: Morgan Kaufmann, p. 203-204.

P3: No.

P4: Yes.

P5: No.

P6: Yes.

P7: Yes.

6. If you answered 'no' in the previous question, please write why:

P5: Too many options to do same work.

P7: Yes but could be improved.

Other comments:

P2: Login: You cannot click on the eye icon to show your password; upload time of the video is not right, add icon for assign the subtitles is not clear / wrong position).

P3: 1 & 2. Video Upload --- There is already a download icon while uploading the file, which is a bit disconcerting. What does ProgrammeID mean, is it mandatory?

Detailed Preview – what is the idea behind. Within the preview popup there are 3 “?” or “!”?

P4: I still see too many details to be improved, so the usability could be fine once these improvements are resolved, but not before.

P5: A lot of improvements needed.

P7: The software is still under development and have to be improved.

4.2. Summary

Participants positively assessed the look (icons, arrangement, style, not too much unnecessary text, responsiveness) and the possibility to manage all videos from one screen in the Accessibility Content Manager.

The virtual folder structure, adding videos, paths for assets, UI interaction, icons (which should be more accurate), video treatment (which was deemed too slow), managing actions with mouse and other inconsistencies and some functionalities that need to be completed were assessed less positively in the open questions.

Among the things that could be improved, participants enumerated integration, the assets webpage, html screen refresh code, the subtitle handling, some icons that must be more visible, video upload, tooltips, more colours to distinguish different matters and other inconsistencies.

When asked about the missing functionalities, participants provided the following responses: edit the subtitles in a WYSIWYG editor, an indicator for open tasks, the possibility to add more than one subtitle, set thumbnail for the video, seek video timeline. Most of the participants deemed the Accessibility Content Manager intuitive (71,43%).

Participants who provided the answer ‘no’ in the question about the intuitiveness of the Accessibility Content Manager provided the following responses when asked about why they consider the system unintuitive: ‘too many options to do the same work’, ‘yes but could be improved’.

Among other comments, assigning subtitles, video upload, preview, uploading time of the video, difficulties with login appeared. All in all, participants consider that, as the Accessibility Content Manager is under development, further improvements are needed.

ANNEX 4. ACCESSIBILITY CONTENT MANAGER REPORT (SECOND ITERATION: IMPLEMENTATION) (CCMA)

1. General information

- **ACM tested:** <http://imac.gpac-licensing.com/acm/>
- **Partner responsible for tests:** CCMA
- **Date of test:** September-October 2019
- **Research tool:** online questionnaire (Google forms)
- **Link to online form:** <https://drive.google.com/open?id=1NWcOkJX0Jw0zW8EtgAFVG62GiQAxqga-raudcaWnHIQ>
- **Measures:** usability and preferences
- **Participants:** 13
- **User guide:** https://drive.google.com/open?id=1KwNRcn_HZPntUNKI7G3Qmanzm7NXBC72

2. Demographic profile of participants

- **Demographics for users:**
 1. **This is the second ImAc ACM test. Did you take part in the first ImAc ACM test?** 1 Yes, 12 No.
 2. **Please select where you are performing this test:** 13 CCMA.
 3. **Sex:** 4 female, 9 male.
 4. **Age:** 28y (1), 31y (1), 40y (1), 41y (1), 42y, 43y (3), 44y (3), 45y (1), 58y.
 5. **Please, describe your current job:** Scrum Master (2), Documentarist, Software Engineer, Head of Software Department, Head of Content Management, Information Manager, Programmer, Audiovisual Researcher, Analyst-Programmer, Software Developer, New's director assistant, documentalist.
 6. **For how long have you been working in the field of access services?** Never (3), 3y (2), 4y(1),4-5y, 5y, 10y, 13y,17y,18y,21y.
 7. **What content management software do you normally use, if any?** Deliverty, SharePoint, None, Own Development (2), Mam (2), Drupal, Digion (1), Jira, Confluence, Agile, no one, creating subtitles.

Summary: CCMA gathered the answers from 13 professionals in this action. One of the participants took part in the first ImAc ACM test in July 2018. 4 females and 9 males took part in the test, aged between 28 and 58 years. Participants have professional experience with content management, as their reported professions include: documentarist, head of content management, or information manager. 10 participants (76.92%) have broad experience in the field of access services, ranging from 3-21 years.

3. System Usability Scale (SUS) results

3.1. Scores (question by question)

SUS statements	1–strongly disagree	2	3	4	5 -strongly agree
1. I think that I would like to use this system frequently	-	2	5	6	-
2. I found the system unnecessarily complex	6	4	2	1	-
3. I thought the system was easy to use	-	1	2	7	3
4. I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system	7	4	1	-	1
5. I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	-	-	3	10	-
6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	4	6	3	-	-
7. I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly	-	-	1	8	4
8. I found the system very cumbersome to use	5	8	-	-	-
9. I felt very confident using the system	-	2	3	6	2
10. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system	7	4	1	-	1

3.2. Summary

The SUS average score is **74.42** (above average, as the average is 68).

The graph below shows how the SUS scores associate with the percentile ranks and letter grades. The red line specifies where the ACM is at this moment.

The letter grade is **B**, and the obtained score corresponds to the percentile rank: 70-79%.

4. Results from open preference questions

4.1. Results (question by question)

1. What did you like most about the accessibility content manager?

CCMA_ACM09: The asset list

CCMA_ACM06: Es una bona eina per les persones amb discapacitat auditive (It's a nice tool for people with hearing impairments)

CCMA_ACM16: Very easy to use and familiar

CCMA_ACM06: It's quite usable and intuitive

CCMA_ACM05: It's usable and intuitive, not very complex

CCMA_ACM18: Intuitive

CCMA_ACM15: User experience. It's very easy to understand and to use

CCMA_ACM11: Few screen transitions, all in one area allows quick work

CCMA_ACM02: Very quick / The icons are quite easy to understand (the meaning I mean)

CCMA_ACM17: Elements, buttons and menus distributed on a classic way, clean UI

CCMA_ACM08: It's clear, simple and it's really fast to work with.

CCMA_ACM13: On asset information you can see quickly all parts of the asset: video, subtitles, audio description.

CCMA_ACM14: Simplicity and the idea of Reports

CCMA_ACM12: "Well structured interface. The buttons in asset card are always visible, and it's very easy to identify which parts are available or missing and it's easy to add metadata or upload new files."

2. What did you like less about the accessibility content manager

CCMA_ACM09: There was some button that didn't work out

CCMA_ACM06: Res (Nothing)

CCMA_ACM16: I need to do some hover around icons to know the functionality

CCMA_ACM06: I can't find anything wrong given a one sample test. A major volume might bring me some opinions about it

CCMA_ACM05: I can't report any disfunction given one single test sample. I would need a larger amount of samples to figure it out. Furthermore, I do not work with the material for which this test is intended, therefore it is difficult for me to evaluate if it would be useful to me.

CCMA_ACM18: Few options

CCMA_ACM15: The view of the information actions (the screen with green letters)

CCMA_ACM11: "Small metadata form, on the right side, to work in case you need to fill a big amount of data. The sequence of clicking to select an asset and after this your mouse for applying an action pressing on action icon desired is not the best in case of usability. It is better if you apply selection and action on the same place in the screen in case it is possible."

CCMA_ACM02: The colours, in general the appearance is boring. Icons are too small. There are not help guide

CCMA_ACM17: Some functionalities (delete, copy) are repeated on the screen and at first seems difficult to understand where they're going to apply (I'm not sure if I'm deleting the folder or I'm going to bin folder)

CCMA_ACM08: In general, it's ok.

CCMA_ACM13: I have found difficult to see the different labels (Assets, Bin, Reports). Once I can see them, then ok.

CCMA_ACM14: The folder hierarchy view and the folder tree management

CCMA_ACM12: "The folder tree is poor and it's not very comfortable. The searcher should be improved. There should be interaction between player, ST, AD and SL."

3. What do you think could be improved, and how?

CCMA_ACM09: I didn't know how to manage to copy an asset, although I followed the steps. And it didn't work out to add a subtitle in a different language.

CCMA_ACM06: D'aquest sistema de subtitulació, res (From this subtitling system, nothing).

CCMA_ACM16: Icons

CCMA_ACM06: Same answer from above

CCMA_ACM05: The same answer from above

CCMA_ACM18: Video player

CCMA_ACM15: The information screen when you perform an action. I didn't see the first actions

CCMA_ACM11: An improve point would be make bigger the edition form area. The sequence of clicking to select an asset and after this your move mouse for applying an action pressing on action icon desired is not the best in case of usability. It is better if you apply selection and action on the same place in the screen in case it is possible. Use of contextual actions on the select target would be a good option.

CCMA_ACM02: Icons bigger (there are a lot of space without information, it can be used for it) It would be better that manual will be linked in to the page, at least. Or FAQs. There are aspects related with usability, for example, you close a screen with different icons "close" or "X"

CCMA_ACM17: Feedback (Upload subtitles for more than one language took me minutes because I didn't understand what was going on with the uploaded file). Language dropdown in subtitles card seems the way to upload subtitles to another language. Delete functionality usually is related with a previous choose of the element/s that will be deleted. In some places delete functionality applies to the element displayed in the card, and I was afraid of broke something clicking on a enabled delete button without a previous selection. I was searching for "save" button at the bottom of the card, and took me some time to find it between "close" and "edit" (close button at the same level of "save" or "delete" results me confusing)

CCMA_ACM08: When you are editing an asset and you move to another asset or another section, you can't lose the changes. The system should let you know that changes won't be saved. In ""vídeo instace"" section, you can't click on the keyframes. It would be more usefull if you could click and navigate to the point on the vídeo. It would be easier if the language of the interface would be available in other languages.

CCMA_ACM13: Distribution of different elements on the view. Labels more visible and the different views buttons of the assets integrated on the results, no up-right of the screen.

CCMA_ACM14: The folder tree

CCMA_ACM12: The design and the functionalities of the interface. Player with the subtitles integrated, ... Add new features to the searcher for example search on specific fields.

4. What missing functionalities did you find?

CCMA_ACM09: There was no pop-up window or similar stuff for copying an asset neither adding subtitles.

CCMA_ACM06: Més facilitat en accedir o suprimir els subtítols (It could be easier to access or delete subtitles).

CCMA_ACM16: nothing

CCMA_ACM06: Same answer from above

CCMA_ACM05: The same answer from above

CCMA_ACM18: Keyframes, navigation

CCMA_ACM15: Drag and drop

CCMA_ACM11: Use of contextual menus to create and edit folders. Use of contextual menus to edit and delete assets. Icons are all together and is a little mess and overwhelming. I think a better idea would be to separate asset actions from the sorting and view options for searching results for example. It is a better option to offer filtering options in the searching area. The sorting options could be offered in the results area.

CCMA_ACM02: I was looking for the "botton" to generate the different languages subtitles in sequences (like in catalan case). I can't understand very well which is the purpose of the content manager. Only assign text files with images?

CCMA_ACM17: Nothing

CCMA_ACM08: Maybe, search form can be improved. It would be possible to look at and Advanced search.

CCMA_ACM13: When you create a new asset, I would like to have more metadata fields to enrich the asset.

CCMA_ACM14: Asset Metadata and Asset Functionalities

CCMA_ACM12: The design and the functionalities of the interface. Player with the subtitles integrated, ... Add new features to the searcher for example search on specific fields. Subtitles editor missing?

5. Was it intuitive?

- a. No (3).
- b. Yes (10).

6. If you answered 'no' in the previous question, please write why:

CCMA_ACM02: In fact, icons are quite intuitive but not the applications. For example, I didn't understand exactly the function of reports. Maybe is because I didn't expect something... But, for example, when you do double click on video, it would be much better that the player was in on or, at least, you see a keyframe. If not, you can think that there is no video.

CCMA_ACM17: Some buttons seems placed in a level that not matches the standard way (close button is in the same level and position of save button). If I put a "delete" button in a general toolbar, I expect a previous choose of elements that will be deleted, and in subtitles card that "rule" is not applied

7. Other comments:

CCMA_ACM11: I tested the create folder option and I found that when you create a folder for the first time on a empty tree is created a duplicate folder with the same name (test in my case).

4.2. Summary

The participants remark that the ACM user interface is clean, intuitive, easy and familiar to use.

Even though the general opinion is good, some improvements have been suggested basically related to the screen's presentation, colours, size of labels and icons on the page. In addition, some participants would like to have a link to the user manual or a faqs section.

Also in order to avoid losing the work done, pop ups advising to save your work would be another useful improvement. Some features could be enhanced, such as search on specific fields, or the navigation in the video via key frames.

ANNEX 5. ACCESSIBILITY CONTENT MANAGER REPORT (SECOND ITERATION: IMPLEMENTATION) (RBB)

1. General information

- **ACM tested:** <http://imac.gpac-licensing.com/acm/>
- **Partner responsible for tests:** RBB
- **Date of test:** August – September 2019
- **Research tool:** online questionnaire (Google forms)
- **Link to online form:** <https://drive.google.com/open?id=1NWcOkJX0Jw0zW8EtgAFVG62GiQAxqga-raudcaWnHIQ>
- **Measures:** usability and preferences
- **Participants:** 14
- **User guide:** https://drive.google.com/open?id=1KwNRcn_HZPntUNKI7G3Qmanzm7NXBC72

2. Demographic profile of participants

In the first part of the online questionnaire, participants were asked to answer to six demographic questions.

Demographics for users:

1. **This is the second ImAc ACM test. Did you take part in the first ImAc ACM test?** Yes:2, No: 12
2. **Please select where you are performing this test:** RBB
3. **Sex:** female: 7, male: 6, other: 0, I prefer not to reply: 1
4. **Age:** 32: 1, 34: 1, 37: 1, 39: 1, 42:1, 43: 1, 44: 1, 46: 2, 47: 1, 48: 1, 51: 1, 54: 1, no input: 1
5. **Please, describe your current job (multiple answers):** Editor: 4, Engineer: 4, Project Manager: 6, System Administrator: 1
6. **For how long have you been working in the field of access services?** 6 years: 5, 10 years: 1, 2 years: 5, other: 3
7. **What content management software do you normally use, if any (multiple answers)?** Adobe AEM: 10, Wordpress: 5, Blue Orange: 1, tailor made systems: 1, none: 1

5. System Usability Scale (SUS) results

3.1. Scores (question by question)

SUS statements	1–strongly disagree	2	3	4	5 -strongly agree
1. I think that I would like to use this system frequently	0	1	10	1	2
2. I found the system unnecessarily complex	3	6	5	0	0
3. I thought the system was easy to use	0	1	1	10	2
4. I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system	9	4	1	0	0
5. I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	0	2	3	9	0
6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	2	6	3	3	0
7. I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly	1	0	1	8	4
8. I found the system very cumbersome to use	4	6	2	2	0
9. I felt very confident using the system	1	2	4	6	1
10. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system	7	6	0	1	0

3.2. Summary

The SUS average score is **70.36** (above average, as the average is 68). This score is not a percentile ranking.

The graph below shows how the SUS scores associate with the percentile ranks and letter grades. The red line specifies where the ACM is at this moment.

The letter grade is C, and the obtained score corresponds to the percentile range: 41-59.

6. Results from open preference questions

4.1. Results (question by question)

1. What did you like most about the accessibility content manager?

- rbbtest_am01: All instances are available within the asset via tabs.
- rbbtest_acm08: clean look, simple actions, see mostly what has happened, easy upload
- rbbtest_acm06: Drag & Drop, Icons
- rbbtest_acm11: easy to understand
- rbbtest_acm10: easy to use
- rbbtest_acm04: easy to use, tooltips, good icons
- rbbtest_acm02: Icons helps to describe the functionality behind it, feedback from the system
- rbbtest_acm14: It was relatively easy to use
- rbbtest_acm07: Leichte Handhabung, selbsterklärend (Easy handling, self-explanatory)
- rbbtest_acm13: mouse over to get explanations for icons, all information concerning the asset at one place
- rbbtest_acm15: Quick UI feedback
- rbbtest_acm05: simple interface
- rbbtest_acm03: the concept of distributed editors
- rbbtest_acm09: Video-Asset war deutlich sichtbar (video-asset was clear visible)

2. What did you like less about the accessibility content manager?

- rbbtest_acm02: Colour theme, why do you use green icons and blue links? Font too small, missing filtering options (filter by name, filter by status...)
- rbbtest_acm15: Colours
- rbbtest_acm04: navigation in 360 player, file browser and editor on the same page felt unfamiliar - e.g. in google drive you would need to open a file to edit it.
- rbbtest_am01: Obviously I was able to delete a folder, but still create new assets in it. After saving, they ended up in the bin. From there they could not be restored and did not get any information why. After I uploaded a subtitle file for the first time, ACM said: 'An instance with same language has been found. Continue to replace it or cancel otherwise.' How could that be?
- rbbtest_acm08: On a wide screen, the functions of the left were far away from the functions of the right the drag and drop field as little small
- rbbtest_acm: Some bugs by using it
- rbbtest_acm13: some functionalities like bin are available on different levels and it is not always immediately obvious to which part they belong
- rbbtest_acm03: The action buttons & icons are quite small since i've got lots of empty space on my screen
- rbbtest_acm14: the icons/buttons for managing the folder were in a completely different area than those for managing individual assets. This caused some mistakes, i.e. I tried to use the folder buttons, because I didn't see the others first
- rbbtest_acm11: The tasks I had to do were very easy and rudimentary therefore I can't answer this question.
- rbbtest_acm05: usability
- rbbtest_acm09: Verbindung zwischen Top-Navigation und Assets nicht intuitiv (Connection between top navigation and assets not intuitive)
- rbbtest_acm07: Zu viele Metadaten werden mir angezeigt. Die Icons sind nicht eindeutig. (Too much metadata is being displayed. The icons are not unique.)

3. What do you think could be improved, and how?

- rbbtest_acm05: doubleclick on folders unusual, creating new folder > two folder with same name, icons for 'new asset' and 'import from ftp' misunderstanding, different levels of functionality: delete and duplicate, move should be on Asset, bin/trash folder should be in asset folder structure (windows like), changing asset view grid/list leads to top-folder >irritating
- rbbtest_acm02: Add filter, stay in the same colour range, use different font sizes
- rbbtest_acm09: Erklärungen der Funktion mittels Mouse-over, d.h. schnell und im System graphische Verbesserungen wegen Punkt 2. (Explanation of the function by means of mouse-over, i.e. fast and graphical improvements in the system due to point 2.)
- rbbtest_acm10: Fit to desktop (some functions could not be seen by me), Explain texts by mouse over, not easy to upload titles in another language, bugs by uploading a video (I could not name the video and either not save it)
- rbbtest_acm03: Get rid of 'Accept' dialog
- rbbtest_acm08:
 - I like when you drag an item over the application and there is an overlay and you can place the file everywhere and not just in a small box
 - I thought I could just drag and drop a video, but I got an error message, I realised I have to select a file name first, why does it not take the filename the file has and you can change it if you want
 - save button was quite far away, I would prefer it on the end of the page
 - When I copied the ST file first I did not see where it is, but after I found it in the drop down list, it was easy to understand
 - there was first the button add subtitler and than it was called producer, I was first little confused if its the same
 - when I deleted the ST file it jumps to the information section, why? would like to stay where I am
 - I had trouble with deleting a ST file: I deleted the first uploaded file (German), I did not find it in the bin, then I uploaded it again, but the system said it's it does not work, then I deleted every ST and tried from the start, but then it seems the file was still there, The system said its there already, so I had some errors following trying to fix it, I never saw any file in the bin
- rbbtest_acm04: Navigation in 360° player is not intuitive, up/down is upside down. should be like youtube.
- rbbtest_am01: Open an asset with just one click. Arrange the icons regarding 'asset organisation', e. g. 'New asset', 'Copy asset' etc., more next to the asset space. In the upper right corner they are too far away. Offer an option to maximise the detailed asset view. I do not know what the 'Reports' view is for. Maybe some more explanations would help.
- rbbtest_acm15: Screen layout. Elements are sometimes long way away from each other.
- rbbtest_acm13: show only the asset on which I'm working on and enhance the area for the asset information, this avoids to much scrolling and makes it more clearer
- rbbtest_acm14: When I named the created file, the field remained red, so I thought there must be a mistake, but I didn't know what could be wrong and the system didn't tell me either. When I saved it, it was accepted, so apparently nothing was wrong? In the bin it was not always obvious which file or folder was currently selected. After I had grasped the concept, it was consistent and clear
- rbbtest_acm06: I don't know
- rbbtest_acm07: Kann ich nicht beurteilen (I can't judge)
- rbbtest_acm11: I need to know more about other accessibility content manager to answer this.

4. What missing functionalities did you find?

- rbbtest_acm08: nothing I can thing of
- rbbtest_acm14: an undo-button would be nice, even though all actions could be undone in individual ways
- rbbtest_acm11: Based on my easy tasks I couldn't imagine other functionalities.
- rbbtest_acm02: Ctrl+Click doesn't work to select more assets, Grouping them would be great add collaborative features, maybe add flags or so, that I know the language of the assets subtitles in the preview

- rbbtest_acm07: Den Rückgängig Button (undo button)
- rbbtest_acm: Design functionalities (?) for titles...
- rbbtest_acm05: drag and drop from assets
- rbbtest_acm09: konnte nicht die zweite UT-Datei finden (für die zweite Sprache) (could not find the second ST file (for the second language))
- rbbtest_acm04, rbbtest_acm03, rbbtest_am01, rbbtest_acm13, rbbtest_acm15: none
- rbbtest_acm06: After the short test, I can not rate it.

5. **Was it intuitive?** Yes: 10, No: 4

6. **If you answered 'no' in the previous question, please write why:**

- rbbtest_acm08: I think the functionality was mostly easy to use, but you need to know what the icons mean, I had to look that up few times in the manual
- rbbtest_acm09: Ich habe das Manual nicht gelesen, also versucht, intuitiv zu arbeiten. Das gelang mir nicht. Die Buttons sind zu weit entfernt vom Video-Asset, ich konnte schwer einen Zusammenhang erkennen. Die Icons der Buttons waren selbsterklärend - bis auf Radiergummi (erkannt als Gießkanne :-)) (I didn't read the manual, so I tried to work intuitively. I couldn't do that. The buttons are too far away from the video asset, I could hardly see a connection. The icons of the buttons were self-explanatory - except for the eraser (recognized as a watering can :-))
- rbbtest_acm13: it is the first time I use this system and it was not completely possible to do the tasks without reading the manual beforehand
- rbbtest_acm05: see above better usability
- rbbtest_acm14: I answered yes, it is intuitive, because I felt that I would get along after some playing around, but it was not necessarily always obvious what to do and how

Other comments:

- rbbtest_acm02: Step 10. 'Mache die Löschung rückgängig.' (Restore an asset from the Bin.) didn't work during testing. Also when I duplicate the asset, the subtitle also duplicates, so step 6. 'Erstelle eine weitere Untertitel-Instanze für mindestens eine andere Sprache.' (Create subtitle instances in more languages.) was a little bit confusing
- rbbtest_acm09: Vermutlich wäre der Test anders ausgefallen, wenn andere Assets vorhanden gewesen wären. Dann hätte ich mich vermutlich an einem Beispiel orientieren können. (Probably the test would have been different if other assets had been available. Then I could probably have followed an example.)
- rbbtest_acm04: video duration always was 00:00:00, Subtitle editor opens in a new tab - no link back to the content management - have to refresh cms page to see changes from subtitle editor
- rbbtest_acm03: Why does the UI show subtitle filename including IDs?
- rbbtest_acm05, rbbtest_acm08, rbbtest_acm07, rbbtest_am01, rbbtest_acm13, rbbtest_acm10, rbbtest_acm11: none

4.2. Summary

ACM tool got very positive feedback, it was regarded as being intuitive in usage, especially the mouse-over-tooltips, drag-and-drop features and the overall UI feedback.

Improvements can be seen in regards with the screen layout and the distribution of icons and work areas. The addition of an undo functionality was mentioned twice.

Minor problems can be linked to functional failures of the system.

ANNEX 6. SUBTITLING EDITOR METHODOLOGY (FIRST ITERATION: DEVELOPMENT)

1. What to test?

- Subtitle Editor: <http://imac.gpac-licensing.com/editor/videos.php>
- Access: each participant will have their exclusive user and password.

2. When?

From 17th July to 31st July.

3. Methodology: overview

- **Research tools:** online questionnaires (Google Forms).
- **Measures:** usability and preferences.
- **Participants:** 30 professional subtitlers from different countries.
 - **Recruitment criterion:** professional subtitlers who professionally subtitle audiovisual content.
- **Language of the test:** English.
- **Materials:** subtitle editor and 360° video (*Life On Mars: At Home In The Habitat | The Daily 360 | The New York Times*).
- **Experimental protocol:** users will be asked to perform certain tasks and then report on the usability and preferences through an online questionnaire.
- **Reporting:** results will be included in a report created by UAB. This will be done exporting data from the Google Form.
- **Please make sure you test the experimental protocol below before the actual pilot action and that you have all materials and ethical forms ready.**

4. Methodology: experimental protocol

- **Online test:** the users will access this test online, via email plus Google Forms, and there will be no supervision or facilitators involved. The test will include different steps (some info will be in the email, and some other in the Google Forms, see the table below):

Section	Description	Where?
Section 1	Welcome and presentation of the ImAc project and the test.	E-mail
Section 2	Ethical clearance: information sheet and consent form to be approved by the participant.	Google Form: https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSfNnUf6nezRDjJ-m4v_rnhb-3KOB5v4qpLd0fgo_xCjkb2A/viewform?c=0&w=1&usp=mail_form_link
Section 3	Demographic questionnaire.	Google Form: https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSeOX3vbXmQgApjROu4zw7RK5IYeZNRASMFheRZrAngsTjNc6A/viewform?c=0&w=1
Section 4	The following items will be introduced: - Quick User Guide - The participants	E-mail (link to PDF): - Quick User Guide: https://drive.google.com/open?id=1y2

	will be asked to read the Quick User Guide before performing the requested tasks. - Login information to access the subtitle editor. - Tasks to be performed.	d6khGiJ0RkoK6FNRH7SoD61EvL2A3r - Instructions sheet: https://drive.google.com/open?id=1noc9D0FNx705sVcShhN71Agfu_u-1D6S
Section 5	SUS questionnaire & Preference questionnaire.	Google Form: https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSciWulXXCKnP8TuZD7NmdufvPsbql692nqPOZTfFGdZaThQbg/viewform?c=0&w=1
Section 6	Thank participants and follow up.	Section included in the Google Form from Section 5.

- **Materials.** The video to be used will be Life On Mars: At Home In The Habitat | The Daily 360 | The New York Times (https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zqK_tm9IBHs). The duration of the video is 00:04:46. The video will be in low resolution to avoid overloading the server and make the subtitling task smoother.

- **Recruitment & User Code Assignment.**

We will recruit participants via contacts, by email/social networks, etc. The test has been designed in English so that professionals from different countries can participate. Once we have a list of participants, we will contact them by email to provide instructions and access to the online form and web editor.

We will create 30 different users (P01-P30) with the role of subtitler and each user will be assigned a video (same video for all users). The login information will be provided by email to the users. Then, they will access the ImAc subtitle editor and they will only have access to one video in the Editor module.

This user name will be the user code that they will need to enter in the different questionnaires when requested.

- **Contact:**

To conduct the test, professional subtitlers (who have previously agreed on participating) will be contacted by email:

Subject: Test for ImAc subtitle editor - Instructions

Dear participant,

First of all, many thanks for participating in our study.

The **aim** of the test is to gather feedback from professional users like you regarding the ImAc web subtitle editor for 360° content that we have developed. This feedback will enormously help us to improve the tool and make it better for professional subtitlers to use it in the future.

This test is built in relation to ImAc (Immersive Accessibility) project. The goal of ImAc project is to explore how accessibility services (such as subtitles, audio description, or sign language) can be integrated with immersive media. <http://www.imac-project.eu/>

This test will approximately take **30 minutes**.

YOUR USER CODE IS: PXX.

These are the steps that you need to follow **in this order**:

1) Give your consent to participate in this test by filling this form and clicking on YES.
https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSfNnUf6nezRDjJ-m4v_rnhb-3K0B5v4qpLd0fgo_xCjBk2A/viewform?c=0&w=1&usp=mail form link

2) Provide some information about yourself, by replying to the following questionnaire:
<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSeOX3vbXmQgApjROu4zw7RK5IYeZnrASMFheRzrAngsTjNc6A/viewform?c=0&w=1>

3) Perform a few tasks with the subtitle editor.

1. Please first read the Quick User Guide to get familiar with the tool:
<https://drive.google.com/open?id=1y2d6khGiJ0RkoK6FNRH7SoD61EvL2A3r>

2. Now read the instructions and proceed with the test:
https://drive.google.com/open?id=1noc9D0FNx705sVcShhN71Agfu_u-1D6S

This is your login information:

- User: / Password:

4) Tell us about your experience with the editor by replying to the following questionnaire:
<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSciWulXXCKnP8TuZD7NmdufvPsbql692nqPOZTffGdZaThQbg/viewform?c=0&w=1>

5) Let us know by email that you have finished the test so that we can confirm that your data has been correctly registered.

The test will be open from today until the 31st of July. You can proceed with the test any time during this time frame but you should do it **in just one session**.

If you have any question or technical issue, please feel free to contact me any time.

Please, confirm that you have received this email and that you understand the instructions.

Thank you again for your collaboration!

All the best,

- **Tasks.** Participants are asked to perform a series of tasks individually on their own computers. The material will be available in the subtitle editor. They will need to access the subtitle editor and perform the tasks in the video that has been assigned to them.

The duration of the video is 00:04:46, but the professionals will be requested to subtitle from 00:00:00 to 00:01:11.

The instructions will be provided in a PDF document available here:
https://drive.google.com/open?id=1noc9D0FNx705sVcShhN71Agfu_u-1D6S

5. Questionnaires

Questionnaires will be provided to the participants using online forms.

Demographic questionnaire addressed to professional users (see Annex 45).

SUS (see Annex 43)

PREFERENCES

Now please reply to the following questions in your own words.

11. What did you like most about the subtitle editor?
12. What did you like less about the subtitle editor?
13. What do you think could be improved, and how?
14. Did you miss any functionality? If yes, can you tell us which?
15. Do you find the feature for setting the angle for the subtitle easy to use? Explain why.
16. Were the preview modes useful for you? Explain why.
17. Do you think it will take you longer to subtitle videos in 360°? Why?
18. Do you think 360° videos will impact your work as a subtitler?
19. Other comments:

ANNEX 7. SUBTITLING EDITOR METHODOLOGY (SECOND ITERATION: IMPLEMENTATION)

Methodology for web editor - Subtitle Editor

1. What to test?
 - Subtitle Editor: <https://imac.gpac-licensing.com/editor/videos.php>
 - Access: each participant will have their exclusive user and password.
2. When?: July-August 2019.
3. Methodology: overview
 - **Research tools:** online questionnaires (Google Forms).
 - **Measures:** usability and preferences.
 - **Participants:** we should aim at a minimum of 30 (15 x partner) to get statistically relevant results; otherwise it will be qualitative data. In pilot 1 we gathered results from 27 subtitlers.
 - **Recruitment criterion:** professional subtitlers who professionally subtitle audiovisual content.
 - **Language of the test:** English, but they can subtitle into their language.
 - **Materials:** subtitle editor and 360° video (*I, Philip*)
 - **Experimental protocol:** users will be asked to perform certain tasks and then report on the usability and preferences through an online questionnaire.
 - **Reporting:** results will be included in the template report.
 - **Please make sure you test the experimental protocol below before the actual pilot action and that you have all materials and ethical forms ready.**
4. Methodology: experimental protocol
 - **Online test:** the users will access this test online, via email plus online forms, and there will be no supervision or facilitators involved. The test will include different steps (some info will be in the email, and some other in the Google Forms, see the table below):

Section	Description	Where?
Section 1	Welcome and presentation of the ImAc project and the test.	E-mail
Section 2	Ethical clearance: information sheet and consent form to be approved by the participant. Please remember that if you give a compensation, the ethical forms are different. Please let UAB know and we will provide the forms.	Google Form: https://goo.gl/forms/ltQPbCFR1mWR4XRw1
Section 3	Demographic questionnaire.	Google Form: https://goo.gl/forms/UcIKWdf8yqOKa3H23
Section 4	The following items will be introduced: - User Guide - The participants will be asked to read the User Guide before performing the requested tasks. - Login information to access the subtitle editor. - Tasks to be performed.	E-mail (link to PDF): - User Guide: https://drive.google.com/open?id=1vR3xiLZepah5v7vIL_eFF4L8VHnNJEEO

		- Instructions sheet: https://drive.google.com/open?id=1JiAi8Cy0fcifiN2m7fvaYKwK9FmrU58
Section 5	SUS questionnaire & Preference questionnaire.	Google Form: https://goo.gl/forms/LGJXYIW5tCtiNsql1
Section 6	Thank participants.	Section included in the Google Form from Section 5.

- **Materials.** The video to be used will be “I, Philip” by ARTE. The video will be in low resolution to avoid overloading the server and make the subtitling task smoother.
- **Recruitment & User Code Assignment.**
Participants will be recruited via contacts, by email/social networks, etc. The test has been designed in English so that professionals from different countries can participate. Once the list of participants is final, they will be contacted by email to provide instructions and access to the online form and web editor.
XXX different users (PXX-PXX) will be created with the role of subtitler and each user will be assigned a video (same video for all users). The login information will be provided by email to the users. Then, they will access the ImAc subtitle editor and they will only have access to one video in the Editor module.
This user name will be the user code that they will need to enter in the different questionnaires when requested.
- **Contact:**
To conduct the test, professional subtitlers (who have previously agreed on participating) will be contacted by email:

Subject: Test for ImAc subtitle editor - Instructions

Dear participant,

First of all, many thanks for participating in our study.

The **aim** of the test is to gather feedback from professional users like you regarding the ImAc web subtitle editor for 360° content that we have developed. Please note that the quality of the produced subtitles will not be taken into account. This feedback will enormously help us to improve the tool and make it better for professional subtitlers to use it in the future.

This test is built in relation to ImAc (Immersive Accessibility) project. The goal of ImAc project is to explore how accessibility services (such as subtitles, audio description, or sign language) can be integrated with immersive media. <http://www.imac-project.eu/>

This test will approximately take **60 minutes**.

YOUR USER CODE IS: PXX

These are the steps that you need to follow **in this order**:

- 1) Give your consent to participate in this test by filling this form and clicking on YES. <https://goo.gl/forms/ltQPbCFR1mWR4XRw1>
- 2) Provide some information about yourself, by replying to the following questionnaire: <https://goo.gl/forms/UclKWdf8yqOKa3H23>

3) Perform a few tasks with the subtitle editor.

1. Please first read the User Guide to get familiar with the tool:
https://drive.google.com/open?id=1vR3xiLZepah5v7vL_eFF4L8VHnNJECO
2. Now read the instructions and proceed with the test:
https://drive.google.com/open?id=1JiAi8Cy0fcifiN2m7fvaYKwK9Fmr_U58

This is your login information:

- User:
- Password:

4) Tell us about your experience with the editor by replying to the following questionnaire:
<https://goo.gl/forms/LGJXYIW5tCtiNsql1>

5) Let us know by email that you have finished the test so that we can confirm that your data has been correctly registered.

The test will be open from today until (add date). You can proceed with the test any time during this time frame but you should do it **in just one session**.

If you have any question or technical issue, please feel free to contact me at any time.

Please, confirm that you have received this email and that you understand the instructions.

Thank you again for your collaboration!

All the best,

- **Tasks.** Participants are asked to perform a series of tasks individually on their own computers. The material will be available in the subtitle editor. They will need to access the subtitle editor and perform the tasks in the video that has been assigned to them.

The instructions will be provided in a PDF document available here:

https://drive.google.com/open?id=1JiAi8Cy0fcifiN2m7fvaYKwK9Fmr_U58

REPORTING (after the tests)

Upload your report one week after the tests under Google Drive under **IMAC_SHARED_FOLDER/ WP5/ T5.1./ 2 PROFESSIONAL USER TESTS - 2019 / SUB EDITOR / PARTNER REPORTS**

It must follow the template available in the same folder

Questionnaires

Questionnaires will be provided to the participants using online forms.

Demographic questionnaire addressed to professional users (Annex 45)

SUS (see Annex 43)

PREFERENCES

Now please reply to the following questions in your own words.

11. What did you like most about the subtitle editor?
12. What did you like less about the subtitle editor?
13. What do you think could be improved, and how?
14. Did you miss any functionality? If yes, can you tell us which?
15. Do you find the feature for setting the angle for the subtitle easy to use? Explain why.
16. Were the preview modes useful for you? Explain why.
17. Do you think it will take you longer to subtitle videos in 360°? Why?
18. Do you think 360° videos will impact your work as a subtitler?
19. Other comments:

ANNEX 8. SUBTITLING EDITOR REPORT (FIRST ITERATION: DEVELOPMENT) (UAB)

1. General information

- **Subtitle Editor tested:** <http://imac.gpac-licensing.com/editor/>
- **Version tested:** 23
- **Partner responsible for tests:** UAB
- **Date:** from 17/07/2018 to 31/07/2018
- **Research tool:** online questionnaires (Google Form)
- **Link to online forms:**
 - Consent form: <https://drive.google.com/open?id=1SjZc68N-A1Dxmv9QWq3KjyFRxQRfY5ZTrOVZEL6JbU>
 - Demographic questionnaire: https://drive.google.com/open?id=1ugcgtoR1qOPGi3SEqV_ZPRDkff8fpRS1s7XnSWLQDYI
 - Post-questionnaire: https://drive.google.com/open?id=17-ez_gUITZKRudEWvXdG3xpp55Oc1TdWbZsnWii0l7w
- **Measures:** usability and preferences
- **Participants:** 27 professional subtitlers
- **User guide:** <https://drive.google.com/open?id=1y2d6khGiJ0RkoK6FNRH7SoD61EvL2A3r>

2. Demographic profile of participants

In the demographic questionnaire, participants were asked to give 18 responses.

1. **Sex:** a) Female (20=74%); b) Male (7=26%); c) Other (0=0%); d) I prefer not to reply (0=0%).
2. **Age:** 24 (1=3.7%); 25 (1=3.7%); 26 (1=3.7%); 28 (1=3.7%); 29 (3=11.1%); 30 (2=7.4%); 31 (1=3.7%); 32 (1=3.7%); 35 (1=3.7%); 36 (4=14.9%); 38 (1=3.7%); 41 (2=7.4%); 42 (3=11.1%); 43 (2=7.4%); 44 (1=3.7%); 45 (1=3.7%); 48 (1=3.7%).
3. **Main language:** Catalan (1=3.7%); Catalan, Spanish (1=3.7%); Croatian (1=3.7%); English (3=11.1%); Spanish (16=59.3%); Spanish, Basque (1=3.7%); Spanish, Catalan (1=3.7%); Polish (2=7.4%); Romanian (1=3.7%).
4. **Please, describe your current job:** Associate lecturer and freelance translator / proofreader (1=3.7%); Associate Professor in Translation Studies in the University of Leeds Centre for Translation Studies (1=3.7%); Audiovisual translator (4=14.8%); Audiovisual Translator, Subtitler, Audio describer (1=3.7%); Freelance subtitler (1=3.7%); Freelance Subtitler (Translator and QCer) (1=3.7%); Freelance translator / assistant professor at university / bookseller (1=3.7%); Freelance translator and subtitler (mainly videogame-related) (1=3.7%); I am a ESO English teacher, also do some translations from time to time (1=3.7%); I'm a freelancer EN>ES translator. I work mostly in videogame localisation and audiovisual translation (especially for TV shows and movies for streaming services). (1=3.7%); Lecturer (1=3.7%); Lecturer and subtitler (1=3.7%); PhD research student, freelance subtitler (1=3.7%); PhD Researcher in Media Accessibility (1=3.7%); Researcher (2=7.4%); Spanish lector and audiovisual translator (1=3.7%); Subtitling Project Coordinator (1=3.7%); Supertitles and subtitles for opera (1=3.7%); Translator (5=18.6%).
5. **Have you ever subtitled a 360° video?** Yes (1=3.7%); No (26=96.3%).
6. **For how long have you been working in the field of subtitling?** 1 month (1=3.7%); 1 year (2=7.4%); 2 years (2=7.4%); 3-4 years (3=11.1%); 4 years (1=3.7%); 5 years (3=11.1%); 6 years (1=3.7%); 7 years (1=3.7%); 8 years (2=7.4%); 9 years (1=3.7%); 10 years (3=11.1%); 13 years (1=3.7%); 15 years (2=7.4%); 17 years (1=3.7%); 18 years (1=3.7%); 20 years (2=7.4%).
7. **How many hours of subtitling have you produced in your professional life?** a) Less than 50 hours (4=14.8%); b) 51-150 hours (4=14.8%); c) 151-300 hours (3=11.1%); d) More than 300 hours (16=59.3%).
8. **In what language or languages do you normally subtitle?** Catalan and Spanish (4=14.8%); Croatian and English (1=3.7%); English and Spanish (4=14.8%); English (2=7.4%); English, Polish

- (1=3.7%); French & Spanish very occasionally. Mostly English. (1=3.7%); From English or German into Spanish (1=3.7%); Polish (1=3.7%); Romanian (1=3.7%); Spanish (9=33.4%); Spanish and Italian (1=3.7%); Spanish, Basque, English (1=3.7%).
- 9. What software do you normally use?** Acme Digital (FAB/WinCAPS-like proprietary software) (1=3.7%); Aegisub (1=3.7%); Aegisub, Subtitle and VisualSubSync (1=3.7%); Aegisub, Subtitle Workshop. I also produced subtitles for theatre productions using Microsoft Power Point. (1=3.7%); EZTitles (3=11.2%); EZTitles, Swift and Aegisub (1=3.7%); Fab Subtitler (1=3.7%); FAB Subtitler, but recently I have mostly used a web-based tool provided by my client. (1=3.7%); FAb, Subtitle Edit (1=3.7%); FabSub, Aegisub (1=3.7%); I don't usually localize subtitles, I use templates. (1=3.7%); in-house software (1=3.7%); Internal software of the companies or Eztitles (1=3.7%); Online platforms: TED, Amara, YouTube (1=3.7%); Proprietary cloud software (Sfera, Originator...) (1=3.7%); Provided by the client (1=3.7%); Quantum WinCAPs, in house software for live subtitles (1=3.7%); Software from the agencies I work for, not commercial (1=3.7%); Spot, FAB and Subtitle Workshop (1=3.7%); Subtitle Edit, Subtitle Workshop, Aegisub (1=3.7%); Subtitle Workshop (1=3.7%); Subtitle Workshop, Annotation Edit and client-specific software (1=3.7%); Swift Create (1=3.7%); VICOM (1=3.7%); Wincaps, Swift, Jayex (1=3.7%).
- 10. Please indicate your level of studies.** a) Primary education (0=0%); b) Secondary education (0=0%); c) Further education (1=3.7%); d) University (26=96.3%).
- 11. If you replied "Further education" or "University" in the previous question, please specify.** A degree in Translation and Interpreting and a master's degree in Audiovisual Translation (1=3.7%); Bachelor's Degree in Translation and Interpreting - Universitat Jaume I (1=3.7%); Currently registered in a PhD in Translation Studies. Have MAs in Linguistics and in Audiovisual Translation (1=3.7%); Degree in Translation, Master in TAV (1=3.7%); Degree on Translation and Interpreting (2=7.4%); English Literature and Linguistics; Translation and Technologies postgraduate (1=3.7%); English studies (2=7.4%); Spanish Philology (not finished). Others. (1=3.7%); I have a BA in English Studies, an MA in Audiovisual Translation and an MA in New Technologies Applied to Translation (1=3.7%); Licenciatura and Master en Traducción e Interpretación (1=3.7%); Licenciatura en Traducción e Interpretación. (1=3.7%); MA in Audiovisual Translation and Localization (1=3.7%); Máster en TAV (UAB) and Doctorat en Traducció i Estudis Interculturals (UAB) (1=3.7%); Master in audiovisual translation (1=3.7%); Master's degree (2=7.4%); Master's Degree in Audiovisual and Videogames Translation (1=3.7%); MSc in Scientific, Technical and Medical Translation with Translation Technology (1=3.7%); PhD (1=3.7%); PhD in Computer-Assisted Language Learning, MA in Translation Studies, BA in English and French (1=3.7%); PhD in Philology, University of Vienna (1=3.7%); PhD in Translation and Language Sciences (UPF) (1=3.7%); Translation and interpreting (1=3.7%); UGR/Universidad de Valencia (degree), ISTRAD (MA) (1=3.7%); Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona (PhD in Media Accessibility) (1=3.7%).
- 12. If you have received specific training on subtitling, please indicate it here.** No training (3=11.1%); 3D subtitling (1=3.7%); A few undergraduate subjects, an intensive course at CenTraS, ATRAE's online courses on SDH... (1=3.7%); Audiovisual translating course in "Calamo y Cran" (1=3.7%); "Dubbing and Subtitling Courses (90 hours) + AVT Course (60 hours) (1=3.7%)"; During the degree and master we had different subjects to learn subtitling (1=3.7%); During the MA in AVT and in-house training (1=3.7%); I have received specific training on subtitling in UOC postgraduate in Translation and Technologies (1=3.7%); I learned from experience (1=3.7%); Informal training - learnt from shadowing a professional (1=3.7%); MA in Audiovisual Translation (5=18.6%); Máster en TAV + 3 years in house in a subtitling company (1=3.7%); Posgrado en Traducción Audiovisual (UAB), specific training in two subtitling companies where I worked for 6 months and almost 10 years. (1=3.7%); post degree (1=3.7%); Yes. Subtitling and audiodescription. (1=3.7%); Subtitling courses (1=3.7%); Subtitling module in MA in Audiovisual Translation and Localization (1=3.7%); Various courses with university colleagues who run subtitling departments (participation was just for fun). (1=3.7%); Yes (1=3.7%); Yes, a course (6 ECTS). (1=3.7%); Yes, during M.A. Studies and Postgraduate Studies (1=3.7%).
- 13. What devices do you use on a daily basis? Multiple replies are possible.** a) TV (21=77.7%); b) PC (17=62.9%); c) Laptop (23=85.2%); d) Mobile phone (27=100%); e) Tablet (9=33.3%); f) HMD (0=0%); g) Other (0=0%).

14. How often do you watch virtual reality content (for instance, 360° videos)?

	Never	Occasionally	At least once a month	At least once a week	Every day
In smartphone	(12=44.4%)	(14=51.8%)		(1=3.8%)	
On a tablet	(27=100%)				
On a PC	(14=51.8%)	(12=44.4%)	(1=3.8%)		
In smartphone plugged to HMD	(23=85.2%)	(4=14.8%)			
In HMD	(23=85.2%)	(3=11.1%)	(1=3.7%)		

15. If you have never used virtual reality content such as 360° videos or only occasionally, please indicate why. Multiple answers are possible. a) Because I am not interested. (3=11.1%); b) Because it is not accessible. (4=14.8%); c) Because I have not had the chance to use it. (16=59.3%); d) Other reasons. (5=18.5%) Please explain:

- Because some virtual reality devices, like HMD, are expensive and because virtual reality content uses to use a lot of data. (1=3.7%)
- Given the kind of 360 videos I have come across so far, the real world is much more interesting to me. (1=3.7%)
- I used it (1=3.7%)
- I watch occasionally because I'm still learning to use my virtual reality device (1=3.7%)
- I don't actively seek this kind of content and I have only found it "accidentally" online in the form of virtual tours of museums, buildings and such. (1=3.7%)

16. Please state your level of agreement with the following statement: "I am interested in virtual reality content (such as 360° videos)." a) I strongly agree (3=11.1%); b) I agree (13=48.2%); c) Neither agree nor disagree (7=25.9%); d) Disagree (4=14.8%); e) Strongly disagree (0=0%).

17. Do you own any device to access virtual reality content? a) Yes (If yes, which one? _____) (7=25.9%); b) No (15=55.6%); c) I don't know or I don't want to reply (5=18.5%).

18. If you replied "yes" to the previous question, please specify which device(s). BOBOVR Z4 (1); HTC Vive (1); If 360° videos are virtual reality content, I have accessed to those through PC, laptop and smartphone (1); PlayStation VR (1); Smartphone (2); Smartphone, Pc (1).

Summary: Twenty-seven participants took part in the test (20 females and 7 males), with ages ranging 24-48. Their main languages are Catalan, Spanish, Croatian, English, Basque, Polish and Romanian. Their jobs are mainly AVT translators, subtitlers for different kind of products, university lecturers and researchers. Only one participant has subtitled a 360° video before. They presented a varying experience in the field of subtitling (varying from 1 month to 20 years). 16 participants have produced more than 300 hours of subtitled content, 3 participants have produced between 151 and 300 hours of subtitled content, 4 participants have produced between 51 and 150 hours and 4 participants have produced less than 50 hours. Participants usually subtitle in Catalan, Spanish, Croatian, English, Polish, French, Romanian, Italian or Basque. Participants declared using different subtitling software (FAB, WinCAPS, Aegisub, VisualSubSync, Subtitle Workshop, EZTitles, Swift, Subtitle Edit, TED, Amara, YouTube, Spot, VICOM, Jayex, proprietary software from clients, among others). 26 participants have studies of university level and 1 participant has further education. Some participants have a degree or master's degree on translation and interpreting studies (or languages degrees), some of them specializing in Audiovisual Translation and some of them have PhD studies. 24 participants have received specialized training on subtitling in MAs, specialized courses or training.

When asked about which devices they used on a daily basis, all participants agreed on using mobile phones; 23 participants use laptops; 21 participants use TVs, 17 participants use PCs; and 9 of them use tablets. When asked about how often they watch virtual reality content, none of the participants have watched VR content on a tablet, 23 participants have never watched VR content in a smartphone plugged to HMD or in HMD; some (14) occasionally watch VR content in a smartphone, 12 participants on a PC, 4 in a smartphone plugged to HMD and 3 in HMD; 1 participant watches VR content on a PC at least once a month, and 1 participant in an HMD; finally, 1 participant watches VR content in

smartphone at least once a week. When asked to explain why they have never used virtual reality content such as 360° videos or only occasionally, 3 participants replied that they are not interested, 4 participants replied that it is not accessible, 16 participants replied that they have not had the change to use it, and others gave other reasons regarding the expensive price, difficulties to use the technology or the lack of appealing contents. When asked to state their level of agreement with the statement “I am interested in virtual reality content (such as 360° videos)”, 3 participants replied that they strongly agree, 13 replied that they agree, 7 that they neither agree nor disagree and 4 of them disagree. Finally, when asked if they own any device to access virtual reality content, 15 participants replied that they don’t, 5 replied that they don’t know or prefer not to reply and 7 replied that they do (including BOBVR Z4, HTC Vive, PC, laptop, smartphone and PlayStation VR).

7. System Usability Scale (SUS) results

3.1. Scores (question by question)

1 – strongly disagree, 5 – strongly agree

SUS statements	1	2	3	4	5
1. I think that I would like to use this system frequently	3 (11.1%)	4 (14.8%)	11 (40.8%)	8 (29.6%)	1 (3.7%)
2. I found the system unnecessarily complex	5 (18.5%)	10 (37.1%)	7 (25.9%)	4 (14.8%)	1 (3.7%)
3. I thought the system was easy to use	1 (3.7%)	6 (22.2%)	4 (14.8%)	14 (51.9%)	2 (7.4%)
4. I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system	8 (29.6%)	12 (44.5%)	5 (18.5%)	0 (0%)	2 (7.4%)
5. I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	0 (0%)	6 (22.2%)	9 (33.3%)	10 (37.1%)	2 (7.4%)
6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	4 (14.8%)	10 (37.1%)	11 (40.7%)	2 (7.4%)	0 (0%)
7. I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly	2 (7.4%)	2 (7.4%)	7 (30%)	8 (29.6%)	8 (29.6%)
8. I found the system very cumbersome to use	2 (7.4%)	5 (18.5%)	8 (29.6%)	10 (37.1%)	2 (7.4%)
9. I felt very confident using the system	0 (0%)	8 (29.6%)	8 (29.6%)	11 (40.8%)	0 (0%)
10. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system	9 (33.3%)	3 (11.1%)	10 (37.1%)	4 (14.8%)	1 (3.7%)

3.2. Summary

The SUS average score is **59.5** (below average, 68 or more is considered above average).

The graph below shows how the SUS scores associate with the percentile ranks and letter grades and the red line specifies where the ImAc subtitle editor is at this moment.

The letter grade is D+, and our score corresponds to the percentile rank: 29-30%.

8. Results from open preference questions

4.1. Results (question by question)

11. What did you like most about the subtitle editor?

P31: The fact that it is cloud-based.

P24: Once I had read the user manual, I found that most of the controls were very easy to get accustomed to.

P16: It's intuitive and easy to use.

P34: The reading speed thermometer, I think it's better than a set CPS limit.

P18: Font of the subtitles.

P20: La visión global del editor. (ENG: Global interface of the editor).

P33: The angle setting tool was very easy to use. I also thought changing speaker's colors was very easy.

P36: Is quite user-friendly and straightforward.

P22: Useful to be able to see 360 but think the setting of the angle is very subjective and a little unscientific/impressionistic in how it can be set.

P12: 3D subtitle positioning.

P5: Fast editing options.

P14: The new feature to set the angle.

P4: The fact that you can subtitle 360° videos, it's very clever. It asks before deleting a subtitle for good, which is nice. Setting up colors and changing the region is very easy.

P17: The possibility of setting current angle.

P8: Uso fácil e intuitivo. (ENG: It is easy to use and intuitive).

P7: It is very clearly designed and organized, the different sections well distributed on the screen, visually balanced and everything you need is at hand.

P23: Being an online system is appealing.

P32: The clear easy-to-use interface, and to be able to navigate the 360 video directly with the mouse.

P13: The interface is nice and clear.

P1: The angle and region features.

P37: La simplicidad y practicidad de la pantalla de edición. Me gusta también el indicador de legibilidad, el listado de subtítulos y, sobre todo, la opción de buscar y reemplazar. (ENG: The simplicity and practicality of the edition screen. I also like the thermometer, the subtitle list, and specially, the look and replace option).

P11: I love being able to move in 360 degrees. Once I got used to the keys for jumping to different subtitles and timecodes, they were fine. The frame keys are essential. The layout was fine. If a few of the features below could be tweaked, it would be quite smooth to work with.

P9: Ease to change color of speaker and region on the screen.

P40: Once you learn how to use it, is easy and even fun.

P6: The video editor and the preset regions.

P29: Easy to use.

P3: Its versatility for subtitle placement.

12. What did you like less about the subtitle editor?

P31: When you spot, the editor doesn't automatically bring up the next subtitle to be spotted.

P24: I found the timing of the subtitles in Edit mode to be very difficult to get right. Everything else felt very simple and intuitive but I consistently kept getting the timings wrong. When I played things back in either of the two preview modes, I had to keep on making changes to the timings.

Also, the Fast Backward and Step Backward functionality seemed not to work when I was subtitling my video. The other buttons did work, however.

P16: I'm not used to 360 so that confused me a bit.

P34: The time-code buttons and manual editing of time-codes are very time-consuming with this type of videos.

P18: I don't quite understand the usefulness of the regions. I didn't use it. Also, I don't understand the reading speed thermometer. There should be an indication how fast my subtitles are in wpm or cps. I don't trust the system doing the thinking for me.

P20: Demasiadas funciones. (ENG: Too many options).

P33: The navigation was very imprecise and not very user friendly. Some shortcuts weren't working for me, like playing the video back and forward (and I'm using Windows 7). Because of this, it was very difficult to set the timecodes correctly.

P36: The black box that appears when putting the cursor on top of one of the video controls is a bit annoying because it covers the time codes. It could go on the bottom part instead.

P22: It would take a lot longer to subtitle something for this type of video and the assumption that subtitles would be moving depending on the action can be disturbing for the audience.

P12: Lack of sound spectrum to identify shot changes.

P5: Some options were unavailable.

P14: That you must change between edit and view to see the subtitles while playing the video.

P4: I had many issues with the subtitle angles (I would set them up, but for some reason they wouldn't stay that way).

P17: Generally, it doesn't have many useful options other subtitling software have.

P8: Cuando insertas un subtítulo nuevo, te mueve el anterior y los tiempos de este. (ENG: When you enter a new subtitle, it takes you to the previous one and to its timecode).

P7: The shortcuts assigned by default. They're scattered all over the keyboard, which makes timing and playing quite inefficient and "jumpy". They should consist of simpler keystrokes and concentrate around the same area (using the numeric keypad + cursor and editing keys is the best option). I know they are customizable, but anyway, I think any program should provide by default a configuration that allows for optimal performance.

P23: The interface is cumbersome, and I personally think the basic premise is not very user-friendly: I think the subtitle should always be visible and follow the reader's eyes rather than it being placed fairly arbitrarily by the subtitler.

P32: Some technical issues that happened during the process: the video became a black screen several times (audio was still playing), the subtitle numbers in the "Subtitle list" did not match those of the editor.

P13: The video buttons did not work for me (moving backwards and forwards) and the shortcuts did not work, either. Also, when doing the spotting, I had to move from the editor to the subtitle list and this make my work really slow and not so precise as I'd like. It was also difficult to change time codes manually.

P1: The fact that it's quite difficult to have enough freedom to break subtitle lines as I want to. I noticed that especially when I applied the different regions: line breaks would automatically change, and I was not happy with the final layout.

Another factor that I think I didn't figure out quickly during the experiment is to be able to control the number of characters per line in a more precise way, especially when working with two lines.

P37: He tenido que estudiarme bien el manual y al principio me ha costado un poco pillarle el truco. Pero, supongo, que ha sido por motivos personales, ya que no estoy acostumbrada a utilizar este tipo de editores. En mi trabajo diario sincronizo en directo y no tengo que insertar parámetros de entrada y salida en el momento de la edición (y mucho menos de ángulo). (ENG: I had to study the user guide thoroughly and at the beginning it took me a while to get used to it and use it properly. But, I guess, that has been because of personal reasons, since I am not used to use this kind of editors. In my daily job I synchronize subtitles live and I don't have to insert any timecode IN or OUT when I am editing (and much less set the angle).

P11: By editing naturally, I inserted subtitles before the instructions came. I know I ended up with one or two subtitles that were double numbered, and which therefore would not play. I couldn't find a solution to this issue, which was frustrating as I don't like sending in something (as a subtitler or for a test) that is not correct. I was aware that some of my subtitles were fast, but I needed a thermometer scale / wpm reading - can we ever get to full red bar? I was using a laptop and the function key commands didn't function - I would have preferred to be working on a computer with a separate mouse and keyboard. That would have made it easier for me. When I moved from frame to frame, I couldn't hear the sound (i.e. p-p-p-a-a-r..). This is essential to me when I work, and it made my timecodes very slow and clunky to start with.

P9: You must push a button to go to the next subtitle, it's not automatic.

P40: The first time I changed from edit to preview, the video went black and it was impossible to fix, I had to go back to load it again.

P6: The absence of a waveform to spot and set subtitles quickly. The IN/OUT buttons are not that precise.

P29: Not enough functionalities to properly edit the subtitles.

P3: The fact that subtitles are locked in the editing mode, i.e. there is no correspondence with the video. This makes the spotting harder.

13. What do you think could be improved, and how?

P31: The above, plus some unusual shortcuts - the shortcuts for in and out times of subtitles doesn't make sense to me. You should be able to just hold space bar for as long as you want the subtitle to last.

P24: I think it would be very helpful to 1) have the current time in the video displayed much closer to the video itself (at the top or bottom of the video itself).

P16: Maybe make the shortcuts editable so that you can set your own.

P34: Time-coding features (see next answer). I also think that it would be better if subtitle boxes only appear at the IN time-code, and not earlier (that is, I think they should go with the video).

P18: There should be a default position for the speaker. The red icon with the arrow should be made more prominent and more visible as it seems to be an important part. Could you also explain what Lat and Lon mean exactly?

P20: Lo anterior y lo posterior expuesto. (ENG: Which has been explained above and below).

P33: TC setting should be more intuitive (I always prefer having a visual timecode where you can see when a speaker is talking), the navigation bar for the video was very slow as well.

P36: It would be very useful to be able to listen to the audio when moving the frames forward or backward. This way it would be possible to know when a word starts or finishes.

P22: Not sure if subtitles are the best way to localize such content. Voice over would be much more appropriate, in my view. For the burnt-in text, editing the video in its original environment with the translated text would be the most appropriate.

P12: More like Aegisub, less like Amara.

P5: Make sure all options are running.

P14: I think that when you are on Edit mode you should be able to click on play and see the subtitles changing with the video.

P4: It should be possible to see the subtitle flow within the Edit mode, so that we don't need to be switching to Preview to be able to see if we timed them correctly and then back to Edit if anything needs changing. I also think the arrow that tells the viewer that they need to look elsewhere is not sufficiently clear/visible.

P17: Adding many more functions.

P8: La forma de insertar los subtítulos y el cómo colocarlos en el ángulo que deseas, ya que uno de ellos se ha colocado bien pero el otro aunque he hecho lo mismo no me ha dejado. (ENG: The way in which you insert the subtitles and the angle that you want to, since I have set the angle for one subtitle properly, but I did the same for another one and I couldn't).

P7: Some major issues with the video: when 3D-navigating while playing it, it went black and I had to reload it to continue with my work. The fast/slow rewind didn't work; this should be fixed. Also, every time you reload a video, the autosave option toggles off, which is minor but kind of annoying, when you already switched it on in the first place. Duration of each subtitle is a useful piece of information that is missing. Adding the numeric wpm/cps count to the thermometer would be helpful. The subtitle list would benefit of showing the actual text segmentation. Subtitles are inserted before the current subtitle, when the usual logic in other applications is doing it after (or, some have a specific "insert before or after" option).

P23: Apart from the basic premise mentioned above, here are some specific functionalities: Step backward and Fast backward didn't seem to work. The way subtitles were presented was counter-intuitive, with the first subtitle not necessarily being no 1 in the list (especially if subtitles were timed in and out later on, or if they were inserted afterwards). The buttons for Previous and Next subtitle are also rather confusing - Next is more like New subtitle. Insert subtitle inserts the subtitle before the current one rather than after it (this is again confusing) but for some reason it times it until the Out

point of the previous subtitle... The segmentation in the R3 (or all smaller, for that matter) layout(s) is also strange - two lines easily become three without any obvious reason.

P32: I would add accurate reading speed values along with the thermometer.

P13: A sound wave would be very useful to the spotting. It's also good that you can have the spotting while you are editing and don't have to move to the subtitle list.

P1: The thermometer is useful, but I would like to have the option to have a more exact indicator.

Finally, I didn't quite get it how to personalize regions, although I know it's for advanced users.

The instructions are useful, but it's necessary to play around to get familiarize and understand how to apply everything.

I was using a Mac laptop and I think it would be useful to create all shortcuts for this system as well.

P37: Creo que si se estableciera el ángulo con el ratón, botón derecho y un clic sobre el vídeo facilitaría la edición. Por otro lado, aunque se puede cambiar el estilo global, ¿se podrían dar formato (por ejemplo, cursivas y negritas) para solo unas palabras de un subtítulo y no en su totalidad? ¿Podría, en un subtítulo de dos líneas, especificar colores diferentes para cada línea (por ejemplo, si intervinieran dos personajes a la vez)? (ENG: I think that if you could set the angle with the mouse, right-clicking on the video, that would make editing easier. Also, although you can change the global style, is it possible to format (for example, italics and bold) just some words in a subtitle and not the entire subtitle? Is it possible in a subtitle with two lines to specify different colors for each line (for example, if two characters intervene at the same time?).

P11: Really, see my answer to 12. The 'worst' feature (or where my skill was most lacking) was when my subtitles got hidden because I had two of the same number. To correct would have meant starting again and in the test situation, I chose not to. In a professional situation, this would be painful!

P9: The green buttons on the left, to move through the subtitles, should be down the editor, below the timeline codes and text.

P40: Some sort of automatic alignment would be great because there where fragments where the angle was just a little bit different and the "jumps" in the video in forced preview where uncomfortable to see instead of having a smooth transition. The popup info from the control buttons covered the time codes, it should appear somewhere else. A sound wave would be really useful to make the timecodes more accurate.

P6: Mentioned before.

P29: Segmentation in the Subtitle List (or it's ill-segmented on purpose?).

P3: - When you write over the character limit in a line, it breaks in two, but it does not react when you delete the extra characters. It stays split.

- The fast backward and step backward buttons did not work for me (Mac user).

- It would be nice to be able to add a subtitle by just clicking on the empty box below the subtitle being edited, and to choose whether you want to add it before or after.

- Is it possible to undo an action? It did not work for me.

- The segmentation in the subtitle list does not match the one in the actual subtitles.

- I would place the Save button further from the Exit button, just in case.

14. Did you miss any functionality? If yes, can you tell us which?

P24: No, I think all the key functionality I would require is available in the tool.

P16: Automatic separation by 3-4 frames between subtitles.

P34: Maybe having a sound wave would be a better way for introducing time-codes in a more accurate manner.

P18: Shot change detection, audio wave, keyboard shortcuts, spellcheck, automatic error detection.

P20: Sí. La definición del código de tiempos. El timing en la pantalla. (ENG: Yes. The time code definition. The timing on screen).

P33: The visual timecode.

P36: See question 13.

P22: The curvature of the original burnt-in text cannot be done, at least I didn't find a way, with the subtitle editor.

P12: *functionality / Sound spectrum.

P5: Wind back option was unabled.

P14: Yes, it would be nice to have a sound wave. It would be easier to set the timing codes and calculate the frames between subtitles.

Also, when you click the keyboard for undoing something it should also apply for the timing changes not only the textual changes.

It would be nice that you can change things on Preview mode if then they are not applicable. The option should be on grey, so you don't change it and then see it has not changed.

P4: It would be useful to be able to split a subtitle in two within the timing.

P17: Autocalculating time-out from the time-in of the following subtitle, you cannot see how many characters you have per line, reading speed is in words per seconds instead of cps, you have to move to another subtitle before you see if the color is green or red, you don't have a shortcut to jump backwards or forwards five seconds while you play de video, no sound while you go backwards or forwards frame by frame...

P7: Yes, several. Here's a summarized list, I'm providing further details by e-mail: subtitle block selection on the subtitle list; move words up and down between subtitle lines; customizable short video jump (forth and back); video jump to current subtitle TC IN, TC OUT and angle from the edit mode; characters-per-line counter; add and subtract frames to TC IN and TC OUT; set current in-cue modifying previous out-cue; split subtitles; merge subtitles.

Details by email

ImAc Comments – P7

BUGS / IMPROVEMENTS

The functions Alt F5 and F6 do not work, while F7 and F8 work.

I would put the video and editing times of subtitles in the numeric keyboards. Now, hand movement is very scattered in the keyboard (keys to function play and cursor for timing; it's what we are going to do the most, and your hand has to be constantly jumping, not just your right hand, but also your left-hand needs to continuously go from Alt for the video to Shift for the timing: it is very uncomfortable).

Sometimes, the thermometer is not automatically updated when you change the times of the subtitle, you must go to the next subtitle and then go back to the previous one to check if the characters limitation is OK.

The subtitles in the subtitles list do not appear segmented, the sentences are complete, without reflecting the segmentation.

When you insert a subtitle between two existing subtitles, it inserts it before the selected subtitle, when the most usual logic in other software is that the software inserts the subtitle after.

Suddenly, after having edited several subtitles without changing the angle of the video, the screen went black when I tried to change it. It happened more times, it seems that it happens when you do it during the play mode. It does not get fixed when you press stop. You must load the app again in the browser (F5). When doing so, the auto-save option goes back to "deactivated".

The auto-save option is deactivated each time the video loads, both if you press F5 or if you go back to the main menu.

At the beginning, it is a bit difficult to understand how to define regions.

MISSING FUNCTIONALITIES

You cannot select several subtitles at the same time (it is useful to delete or apply styles)

Option to move up and down the words in the line.

Option to make the video jump to the TC IN, TC OUT or angle for a specific independent subtitle from the edit mode, with its corresponding shortcut.

A count for characters per line is missing. The information of total characters is not always relevant (maybe only in the case of subtitles of long duration, it serves to warn you that your text is too long, even if the speed is correct, and then you need to create a new subtitle). What really matters is how many characters I can put according to the duration of each subtitle (and that information is given by the thermometer), not according to a general maximum. At the beginning, the change of color of the thermometer is misleading, because it only indicates that you are getting closer to 0 from 75, but as subtitlers that does not matter to us, if in a subtitle of 1 second of duration, we will never go to 0 because it's been a while that the thermometer has turned into red. What really helps you is the count for the characters per line, to avoid going over that limitation, that right now you cannot know in this editor (the subtitle break is automatic, and that parameter is not customizable).

Adding and subtracting frames one by one from the time rectangle (not just inputting the number with the keyboard), and its corresponding shortcut.

Option to set TC IN and at the same time modify the TC OUT of the previous subtitle, so that you don't have to go back to the previous subtitle and manually modify the TC OUT.

There is a moment when the thermometer line disappears, and I understand is when you have reached the ideal specified speed; that can be misleading, maybe it should always be a fine line just in the middle, so that the user does not think that the thermometer is not working.

It would be great that the thermometer also showed the reading speed in numbers, not just changing the color, and that this information appeared in each subtitle, apart from the angle, the region and the character.

It would also be nice to have the duration of each subtitle apart from TC IN and OUT.

That the reading speed would be measured in cps instead of (or apart from) wps.

A customizable short jump to navigate the video is needed (especially since the functions of moving forward/backward do not work), it is cumbersome to go back and look for the moment in which characters start talking.

Option to segment subtitles. The best solution would be that it also did an automatic duration distribution according to the quantity of text inside each subtitle.

Option to merge subtitles.

OTHER

Typo in the transcription: it says electric centers, but the correct transcription is electric sensors.

P23: Splitting lines where I want them and the subtitles actually staying that way.

P32: Maybe some kind of feature that allows to quickly set up subtitle TCs.

P13: It was difficult for me to change time codes manually. It would be also good to have the typical shortcuts (like cut, or undo) included in the editor.

P1: It could be useful (but it's not vital either) to have a wave display/detector to do the spotting of subtitles.

P37: No, cuanto más simple, más fácil y rápido de utilizar. (ENG: No, the simpler the better and easier to use).

P11: Frame-by-frame sound.

P9: Sure, the one that you can see what you are doing when subtitling instead of going to forced or free preview.

P40: To be able to jump to previous/next subtitle when in preview mode.

P6: Mentioned before.

P29: Audio wave to see when the characters start/stop speaking (useful for inserting precise TC in/out); shortcuts for find and replace; shot/scene changes indicators.

P3: It would be very useful to be able to customize the speed limit of the reading thermometer. And perhaps also showing the reading speed at any given time.

15. Do you find the feature for setting the angle for the subtitle easy to use? Explain why.

P31: Yes, it is very easy, but I wouldn't use numbers such as R1 and R2, I would put a small screen that would immediately show you where the subtitle goes.

P24: Yes, it was relatively simple.

P16: It's easy to do, but it does confuse me a bit, as I don't know how to use it from a philosophical point of view XD

P34: Yes, I think it's pretty straightforward. It could be easier to have a button to copy & paste the same angle to other subs, though.

P18: I don't think it's very easy to use as the red icon is not exactly intuitive. Should I see no arrow, just the red shape? That's what I was aiming for. So, I think I would need some guidelines to know how to set subtitles in 360 videos, as I hadn't done it before.

P20: Sí, es otra función más. (ENG: Yes, it's another function).

P33: Yes, it seems very easy because you just need to remember to center the camera on the speaker/text on screen whenever you add a subtitle.

P36: Yes. You just must move the cursor.

P22: Not very easy and doubt the level of precision needed can be achieved with this.

P12: Setting the angle is not complex; making the system remember this preference is slightly more cumbersome

P5: Not very easy.

P14: Yes, this is the easiest part to use because it is very graphic.

P4: Easy enough to set, but it doesn't seem to stay that way.

P17: Yes, it's quite straightforward.

P8: Sí y no, ya que es fácil de integrarlo pero no siempre funciona como quieres. (ENG: Yes and not, since it is easy to integrate it, but it does not always work as you want to).

P7: Yes, it is very straightforward and intuitive.

P23: It takes some getting used to, but it can be used in the end.

P32: Yes, I find it easy to use because first you move "inside" the video to see exactly where you want to place the subtitle. And then, just one click and you have the angle set.

P13: Not really. I've tried using it, but the results were quite weird. I'm not sure I've understood the concept, as when I did the preview, the original inserts also seemed to be moving, but anyway, I've tried to do my best.

P1: Yes, it is. Maybe it would be good to have an option to apply the same angle of consecutive subtitles.

P37: Ha sido moderadamente fácil. Ver respuesta a la pregunta 13. (ENG: It's been moderately easy. See response in question 13).

P11: Yes, it was very logical. However, while looking for the woman, I wasn't sure how far round I had moved, so a clearer dial may help. I ended up labelling her as offscreen. Again, working with a mouse and different keyboard might have helped here.

P9: No, it's on the left, I think should be easier nearer the temperature thermometer.

P40: It was really easy, you just need to locate the correct angle and press the button, although finding the correct angle with just the mouse was a little bit difficult sometimes. I must confess I didn't use the arrows.

P6: Yes. The regions and the possibility of setting also moving the video editors are useful. It is just a move and a click :)

P29: Fairly easy, quite straightforward with the arrow, gives an idea of how it works.

P3: Yes, but I find the buttons too time consuming. I would prefer to move in 5-10 ° increments than in just 1°. The arrow is a bit confusing around the 180 (135-225) and the 360 ° (315-45).

16. Were the preview modes useful for you? Explain why.

P31: Preview mode is always useful.

P24: Yes, they gave me the rapid ability to review my work and correct any errors or make desired changes.

P16: Yes. I liked that a lot. I think it is nice to be able to see the subtitles from different points of view.

P34: Both are useful. The forced one helped me see if the angle was correct and the free one is really useful to navigate the video in the same way as the final viewers.

P18: However, when I previewed my subs and changed to the edit mode to correct the angle, the video preview went black and I couldn't revise the angle, as all I could see was black screen. Free preview also resulted in black screen. When I changed it to forced preview, I could see the screen again. In the end, I'm not sure if my angle is correctly set.

P20: Sí, pero tienes que familiarizarte con el editor al fin y al cabo. (Yes, but you must get use the editor at the end of the day).

P33: Forced view gave some stuttering issues, but free preview was fine.

P36: I think that the editing and preview modes could be integrated. This way it would be able to edit and preview the subtitled video without having to change the mode.

P22: OK.

P12: Watching 3D videos in 2D makes it harder to judge.

P5: Yes, they help to get a general idea of the subtitling work.

P14: Yes, but I think the edit mode and the preview mode should just be one.

P4: Yes, that way I could see whether the subtitles were correctly timed.

P17: Yes, especially the second one (forced), because you can edit while watching the subtitles

P8: Sí, sobre todo el que te pone justamente donde has puesto los subtítulos para comprobar que están ahí bien insertados. (ENG: Yes, especially the forced perspective to check if you have insert the subtitles correctly).

P7: Yes, preview is fundamental in subtitling and, in the case of 360° videos, the possibility of locking and unlocking angle is useful to check whether you did it right (locked) and to be able to freely preview the video (unlocked) as a normal viewer would do.

P23: Yes, though they were initially out of the page and so not obviously visible.

P32: They were useful as I wanted to know how the user experience would be, and also to check TCs, subtitle positions, etc.

P13: They were useful, but it's not useful to have to change to preview every time you are doing the spotting.

P1: Yes, but I didn't find out in the instructions that when using the forced mode, I can go to the image and the subtitle, and then edit it. It would be good to specify it. When I was in the edit mode, I found it hard to go to the timing of specific subtitles to edit them.

P37: Sí, porque en el modo forzado se puede verificar la exactitud del trabajo que estoy realizando y en el modo libre se puede comprobar la experiencia real que tendrá el usuario. (ENG: Yes, because in the forced perspective you can verify the accuracy of you the work you are doing and in the free mode you can check the real experience that the user will have).

P11: Yes - I needed them to check my timecodes as I was having difficulty with accurate cueing. Being able to override a timecode by typing it in would have been helpful, as would seeing changes in speed as you type/edit. I realized I had to key in the new in and out timecodes to apply them.

P9: It's useful but it would be more useful integrated in the tool.

P40: Yes, they were useful because I was able to fix or relocate subtitles really easy and to see the final output being able to make changes in edit mode.

P6: Yes, although I mainly use the editor and free view.

P29: yes, they are necessary! a subtitler needs to see how the subtitles are presented on the screen. although I am not sure if we need two types of "previews".

P3: I find the movement in the forced preview too abrupt.

17. Do you think it will take you longer to subtitle videos in 360°? Why?

P31: I am not sure.

P24: Yes, because there is the angle to take into account and also, perhaps, more considerations regarding the positioning of the subtitles.

P16: Not necessarily. Subtitling is subtitling. I would need to get used to 360° videos and understand what is expected from me, but technically is as easy as any other subtitles.

P34: Yes. You need more time to navigate the whole video and see if there's on screen text that needs subtitling, for instance.

P18: Yes - as you need to adjust the angle.

P20: Es otra función más a añadir. Debería ser algo automático. (ENG: It is another function to add. It should be something automatic).

P33: I will say that I am mostly used to working in videos where the timecodes are already set, so I only must worry about translation and little else. But I think this would take me more time than if I were using a regular subtitling software like FAB.

P36: Yes. Setting the angles will be also important here.

P22: Definitely.

P12: Definitely so. There is at least one extra parameter to input; therefore, subtitling would take longer, if only slightly per line.

P5: Yes, because it's something new.

P14: Yes, because you must set the angle.

P4: Yes, if only to find the source of the audio! Apart from that, it's probably not a lot more time-consuming if the angles can be set up correctly and independently for each subtitle.

P17: Yes, you must set the angle and move around to see if there are any inserts.

P8: Sí, por lo de la localización de los subtítulos, pero con esto más pulido disminuiría mucho el tiempo. (Yes, because of the localization of the subtitles, but once the software is polished that should decrease the time a lot).

P7: Yes, a bit longer because there's a new parameter to add (angle) for every subtitle, which implies an extra time for the 3D navigation, but luckily angle doesn't need to change for every subtitle. It will also depend on the editing style of each video, but yes, by definition, an extra action requires extra time, even if sometimes only an extra second or less.

P23: Yes, because of all the looking around for the person speaking, positioning subtitles, etc.

P32: Not that much, as long as we have access to editors like this one.

P13: Yes, it will, if you must take care of position of subtitles and angles.

P1: Maybe at the beginning if you are not familiarized with the system, but then I think it would not take too much extra time, it's just the fact of applying the angles. It would be good to offer more options for angle editing.

P37: Sí, porque hay que especificar más parámetros. (ENG: Yes, because you must specify more parameters).

P11: Yes, but not as long as it took me this time round. Once I was familiar with the software, I began to speed up. I think being able to drag the 360 degrees (which I couldn't do on the laptop) would mean that there isn't a huge difference in time needed.

P9: I think it will take a little bit longer requiring setting the right angle, but not too much.

P40: Probably yes, because finding the right angle to make a smooth transition to the next one is more complex than I thought.

P6: Yes, although it may be just a matter of time of getting use to the app. Either way, looking for the people talking will always be more time-consuming.

P29: Yes, I think it will, mainly because you must set the angles for each subtitle, decide on the region, etc. My concern are shot/scene changes - how should we approach them in such videos? In the same way as in regular ones?

P3: Definitely. Because of the added factor.

18. Do you think 360° videos will impact your work as a subtitler?

P31: I am not sure it makes a big difference.

P24: Over time, yes. I believe we will all have to learn how to include the subtitling of 360-degree subtitles into our skillset. This will take time and effort if we want to remain up-to-date and marketable within our industry.

P16: I don't think so.

P34: In the future, maybe. If only agencies knew the work they entail... (one can dream).

P18: Difficult to say.

P20: Como digo, es otra función más a añadir. (ENG: As I said, it's another function to add).

P33: I don't think so.

P36: I guess so, but, probably, in the future.

P22: Not at the moment.

P12: Undoubtedly yes. I was already familiar with the NYT 3D project and started to wonder back in 2012 how 360° subtitle positioning should be normalized.

P5: Not sure.

P14: We will have to change a bit the procedure but with the right tools it shouldn't be hard.

P4: Yes, I have already been contacted about this kind of subtitle.

P17: Yes. I would demand that the scripts should also include inserts, so that you don't need to move around looking for them.

P8: Si ganan mucho terreno en el campo, sí. (ENG: If this content is mainstreamed, then yes).

P7: I think it will in a not-so-far future, yes.

P23: In the future, yes.

P32: I had never worked with them before, but I would like to in the future. So, I think it could be positive for my work as a subtitler.

P13: I don't think so.

P1: Yes.

P37: No creo que afecte a mi trabajo actual de forma inmediata. Pero, tal vez, sí lo haga cuando crezca la demanda y grabación de espectáculos en 360º para su retransmisión o venta. (ENG: I don't think it will impact my current work immediately. But, maybe, then the demand and creation of 360º content increases, yes).

P11: I would love to have this as regular functionality.

P9: I am not sure. I wouldn't mind if it were.

P40: It will depend on the market and the demands of the consumers.

P6: Yes, as it is helpful for many areas in audiovisual translation.

P29: Definitely. It will change the way we are working now - different requirements for subtitles, different time needed to perform the task. Besides not everybody will be able to work on such files (e.g. people with health problems mentioned in the consent form or people with old PCs/laptops etc.)

P3: Perhaps, but I really have no clue.

19. Other comments:

P24: Overall, the tool seemed simple to use once I had read the instruction manual and started to play around with it for about 30 minutes.

P34: I think you're doing a great job with this! :)

P18: It would be nice to have the sound on while moving forwards and backwards in the video frame by frame. Fast backward button does not work.

P20: Me ha resultado imposible set el timing. (ENG: It was impossible to set the timing).

P36: It would be interesting to experience this on a virtual reality device.

P22: As mentioned above, I do not believe subtitling is the optimum way of localisation such content. However, congratulations on your research and looking forward to receiving updates on your findings/publications. Thank you for the opportunity!

P14: Thank you for this opportunity. Although there are things to improve, I think the par of setting the angle is a very good idea in these videos.

P17: I spent around 1,5 hours doing the test (reading instructions, getting used to the software, translating) and I was told it would be done in 30 minutes. I think that should be improved in future tests you carry on.

P8: Muchas gracias por dejarme participar y mucho ánimo, ¡es una herramienta muy buena! (ENG: Thank you so much for letting me participate and keep up the good work, it is a very good tool!)

P7: Congratulations, this is an excellent tool and field of research. So even if, as mentioned above, there's room for improvement, it's already really good. Keep up the good work!

P23: It was an interesting exercise, which however actually lasted quite a bit longer than advertised - I have spent 89 minutes on it so far.

P13: I'm not quite happy with my spotting, but I didn't have quite time and I found the software not so easy to use.

P37: Gracias por darme la oportunidad de probar esta nueva herramienta. (ENG: Thank you for giving me the chance to try this new tool).

P11: Feel free to ask me to expand on anything if you need me to.

P9: It's a nice tool! I will change the organization of buttons. I like the interface.

P40: I think this is a great system to subtitle these videos and I hope it to be a success if the demand is enough.

P29: First of all, awesome work! Congratulations!

Some comments/ideas below :-)

Please check the shortcuts for Polish - when I wanted to insert a Polish letter "ą", I got a pop-up window informing me that it's a shortcut for something.

I guess this may also be an issue for other languages with non-standard letters.

Also, I had a problem with video buffering - but it may just be my computer (too old). So, the TCs in/out in my test are VERY approximate. I did the test anyway as I wanted to finish the task and check out all the functions.

When I was jumping to different subtitles, the program allowed me to jump just to the text. The video wasn't moving. I am not sure if that's because of my buffering problem or that's a general rule? In general, when jumping to different subtitles, the video should "jump with me" (so that when I edit the sub and I hit "play", I can see the change right away).

Quite a lot of colors available. Not too many? Viewers usually get lost with more than four.

More basic options for editing the subtitles would be useful like move sub left/right etc.

What about the spell check function? Will it be just the one available in the browser or you are planning something more?

Any quality check functions? Like a report when I am done? To see whether all my subtitles are correct, or some things should be improved (e.g. too many characters per line, wrong reading speed etc.).

4.2. Summary

The replies for this questionnaire were very different and specific among participants, so it is recommended to carefully look at them one by one, because all ideas can be interesting to implement in a new version. However, for the sake of clarity, we will try to summarise the most relevant ideas in this section.

What participants **like the most** was that the tool was cloud based/online, it seemed to be easy and intuitive for most of them, they also liked the "set the angle" option, and the interface.

What participants **like the less** was the configuration for the default shortcuts, they considered them uncomfortable, and need to be customised but also, they are requesting a more comfortable default setting. They did not like the buttons "Fast backward" and "Step backward" not to work properly. A functional frame by frame button to navigate the video is needed. Some users did not like the speed thermometer. They think that it is important to get the characters per line limit and also think that the thermometer should work with the parameter of cps (characters per second) rather than (or apart from) wps (words per second). Participants did not like that the fact that they had to change modes in order to edit the subtitles, they would rather prefer to have the editing and preview modes integrated. Some users reported that the video went black several times and that they needed to load the video again to fix this issue. Some participants did not like not having enough freedom to break subtitle lines as you want to. Also, they reported that going to the next subtitle should be an automatic action.

When asked about **what could be improved**, most participants referred to the shortcuts, as explained above. Also, some would like to listen to the audio when moving frames forwards or backwards. As explained before, subtitlers would like to be able to preview the video in the edit mode or edit the video in the preview mode, either way, but both functionalities should be integrated to facilitate spotting. Some participants discussed the possibility of improving the arrow in the preview/edit mode, it should be more visible. Also, some users complained about the fact that the auto-save option was deactivated each time they pressed F5 to load the video or went back to the main menu. The software should remember this setting. Also, participants complained about the fact that the subtitles in the subtitle list are not shown with the actual segmentation. They would like to have the subtitles in the subtitle list properly segmented. Some participants replied that the pop-up information from the control buttons covered the time codes and that was distracting. Some users suggested to include general actions (and its corresponding shortcuts) such as undo, copy, paste, cut, etc. If the undo option is not implemented, it should be.

When asked about any **missing functionalities**, most participants requested to have a sound wave to improve accuracy when spotting. Also, a participant requested an automatic separation by 3-4 frames between subtitles. Some participants asked about the possibility to include a spellchecker or QA (quality assurance) functionalities. Also, some participants think that segmentation needs to be customisable and more flexible (not automatically done by the editor based on the thermometer parameters).

Regarding the **“set the angle” option**, most users thought it was easy to use (also sometimes did not work properly), and some users find it difficult. Some participants highlighted that the arrow could be improved and be more visible. Some participants also raised their concerns regarding the level of precision and accuracy of this functionality. A participant suggested that it would be good to have an option to apply the same angle to consecutive subtitles. Also, some participants wonder what to do when the speaker is offscreen. An angle option for off-screen voices needs to be implemented. Finally, a participant suggested that would prefer to move in 5-10° increments rather than in just 1°. The arrow is a bit confusing around the 180 (135-225) and the 360° (315-45).

As far as the **preview modes**, as explained before, participants think these modes are useful, but they would like to be able to edit subtitles in the preview mode or be able to preview subtitles in the edit mode. These functions should be integrated for an optimal spotting process.

When participants were asked about **the impact of subtitling 360° videos on the job of a subtitler**, different opinions were presented. Some are not sure about it, others think that subtitling will take longer since they have to set the angle for the subtitle, and others think that it should not take longer or have any impact if you have the right tools and software for it. In general, subtitlers are a bit worried about the time-consuming tasks that this type of subtitling can bring. Also, some of them thought that subtitling is not the right way to localize 360 videos (but this is not relevant because subtitling for the deaf and hard of hearing will always be necessary to access audiovisual content).

Finally, in the section **“Other comments”** an important issue was raised by one participant: “Please check the shortcuts for Polish - when I wanted to insert a Polish letter “ą”, I got a pop-up window informing me that it's a shortcut for something.

I guess this may also be an issue for other languages with non-standard letters.” We need to check that at least all European languages characters are accepted by the editor.

ANNEX 9. SUBTITLING EDITOR REPORT (SECOND ITERATION: IMPLEMENTATION) (CCMA)

1. General information

- **Subtitle Editor tested:** <http://imac.gpac-licensing.com/editor/>
- **Partner responsible for tests:** CCMA
- **Date:** August – September 2019
- **Research tool:** online questionnaires (Google Form)
- **Measures:** usability and preferences
- **Participants:** 6 professional subtitlers
- **User guide:** https://drive.google.com/open?id=14FpkFbDsc8phKhyzXgRmz_qP-zg4VtS2

2. Demographic profile of participants

In the demographic questionnaire, participants were asked to give 18 responses.

1. **This is the second ImAc subtitle editor test. Did you take part in the first ImAc subtitle editor test?**
Yes (3) No (3)
2. **Sex:** a) Female (4); b) Male (2); c) Other (0); d) I prefer not to reply (0).
3. **Age:** 23 (1), 36 (1), 44 (1), 47 (1), 49 (1), 51(1)
4. **Main language:** Spanish (1), Catalan (1), Spanish/Basque (1)
5. **Please, describe your current job:** Subtitler (2), Audiovisual translator (4)
6. **Have you ever subtitled a 360º video?** Yes (1); No (5).
7. **For how long have you been working in the field of subtitling?**
29 years (1), 19 years (2), 10 years (1), 3 years (1), 1.5 years (1)
8. **How many hours of subtitling have you produced in your professional life?** a) Less than 50 hours (1); b) 51-150 hours (1); c) 151-300 hours (0); d) More than 300 hours (4).
9. **In what language or languages do you normally subtitle?**
Spanish (5), English (3), Catalan (1), German (1), French (1) Basque (1), Latin American (1)
10. **What software do you normally use?**
Fab Subtitler Pro (1), Diferits (1), Multisub (1), Swift Create (1), Subtitle Workshop (1),Aegisub (2), Amara (1), Subtitle Edit (1), The one of my company (1)
11. **Please indicate your level of studies.** a) Primary education (0); b) Secondary education (0); c) Further education (0); d) University (6).
12. **If you replied "Further education" or "University" in the previous question, please specify.**
 - UNED
 - Catalan Philology
 - Audiovisual Translation Master
 - MA in Audiovisual Translation (Universidad Autónoma de Barcelona), PhD candidate (Universidad Jaume I)
 - Master's degree
 - Translation and Interpreting Degree at the University of Granada
13. **If you have received specific training on subtitling, please indicate it here.**
 - Training on subtitling during the master
 - I was trained in-house many years ago, when no subtitling courses were available in Argentina.
 - Master's degree in Audiovisual Translation
 - Aula SIC course
14. **What devices do you use on a daily basis? Multiple replies are possible.** a) TV (4); b) PC (5); c) Laptop (4); d) Mobile phone (5); e) Tablet (1); f) HMD (0); g) Other (0).

15. How often do you watch virtual reality content (for instance, 360° videos)?

	Never	Occasionally	At least once a month	At least once a week	Every day
In smartphone	2	3	0	0	1
On a tablet	4	2	0	0	0
On a PC	1	4	0	0	1
In smartphone plugged to HMD	6	0	0	0	0
In HMD	5	1	0	0	0

- 16. If you have never used virtual reality content such as 360° videos or only occasionally, please indicate why. Multiple answers are possible.** a) Because I am not interested. (5); b) Because it is not accessible. (0); c) Because I have not had the chance to use it. (0); d) Other reasons. (0) Please explain:
- 17. Please state your level of agreement with the following statement: "I am interested in virtual reality content (such as 360° videos)." a) I strongly agree (3); b) I agree (2); c) Neither agree nor disagree (1); d) Disagree (0); e) Strongly disagree (0).**
- 18. Do you own any device to access virtual reality content?** a) Yes (If yes, which one? _____) (XX); b) No (3); c) I do not know or I do not want to reply (3).
- 19. If you replied "yes" to the previous question, please specify which device(s).**

Summary: In this second ST Editor test 6 professional users (4 women, 2 men) have participated, 3 of them did also participate in the first one. Only one of the participants has worked with 360° content subtitling, but all of them have a large experience in the field of subtitling. They are familiar with 9 different subtitle editors and usually work in 7 different languages, but mostly in Spanish. The most used devices by the participants are TV sets, PC's and smartphones, but they do not use them for 360° content consumption. Until now, they were not very interested in this content consumption, although a change of opinion can be shown in their responses.

3. System Usability Scale (SUS) results

3.1. Scores (question by question)

SUS statements	1 – strongly disagree	2	3	4	5 – strongly agree
1. I think that I would like to use this system frequently	0	1	0	3	2
2. I found the system unnecessarily complex	2	2	2	0	0
3. I thought the system was easy to use	0	2	1	2	1
4. I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system	2	0	4	0	0
5. I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	0	1	2	1	2
6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	2	2	2	0	0
7. I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly	0	1	1	2	2
8. I found the system very cumbersome to use	2	1	3	0	0
9. I felt very confident using the system	0	1	3	1	1
10. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system	2	2	2	0	0

3.2. Summary

The SUS average score is **69.17** (above average, as the average is 68). This score is not a percentile ranking.

The graph below shows how the SUS scores associate with the percentile ranks and letter grades. The red line specifies where the subtitle editor is at this moment.

The letter grade is C, and the obtained score corresponds to the percentile rank: 41-59.

4. Results from open preference questions

4.1. Results (question by question)

Please notice that question “What do you think could be improved, and how” was not included for a technical problem

11. What did you like most about the subtitle editor?

- CCMA_ST08: The fact that it is 360 degrees.
- CCMA_ST09: The option of easily placing subtitles in a certain area. The option of assigning colours to each character. The option of personalizing short cuts.
- CCMA_ST10: It was easy to use.
- CCMA_ST17: The easy access to time codes, setting regions and styling of subtitle texts.
- CCMA_ST12: Looks like the one I am used to.
- CCMA_ST16: Being able to set the speaker's location

12. What did you like less about the subtitle editor?

- CCMA_ST08: Everything is very small (screen, icons).
- CCMA_ST09: Not being able to hear the sound when moving frames forward or backwards. Even though the sound wave is useful to know where an utterance starts approximately, I think it is also useful to be able to hear the sound when moving the frames one by one.
- CCMA_ST10: There was a delay with the video, and the quality was not good, so I could not be completely sure of who was talking, but that could be my Internet connection, I suppose.
- CCMA_ST17: The opacity regarding the minimum duration of subtitles and their minimum separation. I could not find out a solution for the indicated errors regarding the time codes.
- CCMA_ST12: At first sight, according to the manual, it seems complex. The part I subtitled did not.
- CCMA_ST16: Free preview did not synchronise TCs properly

13. What do you think could be improved, and how?

- CCMA_ST08: Everything is all right, except for what was said above.
- CCMA_ST09: It would be useful to be able to scroll subtitles using the mouse's scroll wheel. It should be possible to be able to preview the subtitles even if there are errors in them.

- CCMA_ST10: I think the guide is not clear enough. I was not sure what a region was, how it was supposed to be used (Does the client tell you if they want raised subtitles, for example?) In addition, I think it could have maximum duration function as well (Is it the one that appears first in the General Settings?)
- CCMA_ST17: Read answer 12. It could be improved indicating more clearly the minimum duration of subtitles as well as the possibility of including the dialogue of two people in the same subtitle and how to do it regarding the setting of regions and angles.
- CCMA_ST12: The access. The interface is quite complex for a non-expert user.
- CCMA_ST16: TC sync.

14. Did you miss any functionality? If yes, can you tell us which?

- CCMA_ST08: None.
- CCMA_ST09: The option of assigning colors to each character when two of them speak in one same subtitle.
- CCMA_ST10: No. It's quite complete.
- CCMA_ST17: Yes: the possibility of include a dialogue of 2 different speakers in the same subtitle.
- CCMA_ST12: No.
- CCMA_ST16: Subtitle file upload and download

15. Do you find the feature for setting the angle for the subtitle easy to use? Explain why.

- CCMA_ST08: It may be easy, although I have not managed to handle it well.
- CCMA_ST09: I could not preview the subtitles so I don't know if I set the angles properly.
- CCMA_ST10: Yes. It's very visual.
- CCMA_ST17: I think so. If I did it well, I found easy the use of the mouse to explore the different positions through the dot in the screen.
- CCMA_ST12: I did not use the angle.
- CCMA_ST16: Yes. You just need to move the frame to place it right below the speaker's face.

16. Were the preview modes useful for you? Explain why.

- CCMA_ST08: Previous modes are always useful.
- CCMA_ST09: They should have been, but I could not use them because some of my subtitles had errors.
- CCMA_ST10: They are useful because you can analyze the "finished product."
- CCMA_ST17: I could not really use them because I could not fix the errors indicated by the TCs.
- CCMA_ST12: Quite useful, even the part I subtitled was not complicated. .
- CCMA_ST16: Yes, so that I could see if 360° settings were in the right place.

17. Do you think it will take you longer to subtitle videos in 360°? Why?

- CCMA_ST08: Not really.
- CCMA_ST09: Yes, at the beginning, but I think I would get used to it.
- CCMA_ST10: Maybe a little longer because of the angles, but not that longer.
- CCMA_ST17: Only at the beginning. I think that it is a question of practice and obviously knowledge about certain functions (minimum duration and separation of subtitles)
- CCMA_ST12: Yes. According the user manual, this mode is more complex.
- CCMA_ST16: I think there would be two different tasks: first subtitling, then adapting format to 360°: voice over mode, speaker's location, angle, alignment, regions, character...

18. Do you think 360° videos will impact your work as a subtitler?

- CCMA_ST08: It is an improvement.
- CCMA_ST09: I think it's an exciting and interesting option for the future.
- CCMA_ST10: I hope so.
- CCMA_ST17: Definitely. It is the first time I have tried this method and I find it really interesting and fun.
- CCMA_ST12: No.
- CCMA_ST16: Yes

19. Other comments:

- CCMA_ST08: The page froze several times during the process.
- CCMA_ST09: I would be happy to receive any updates about this new editor.
- CCMA_ST17: I would like to find out more about the use of this method and its application. I really want to improve subtitling my skills with this type of subtitling.
- CCMA_ST16: I would love to continue helping improve the software. I conducted research on smartwatch subtitling, applying speed reading systems and Optimal Recognition Point for the human eye. Please, contact me for further reference.

4.2. Summary

Users liked the ST editor in general. Some of them highlight the easy use and customisation options offered by the editor, such as editor shortcuts and easy access to TC. However, some users commented on some problems in audio monitoring by frames, and also TC synchronisation. The possibility of including the dialogue of 2 speakers in the same subtitle was one of the suggestions made by the users. Preview modes are welcome as an easy way to verify the work done, especially when assigning angles to subtitles. Even the participants were not used to work with 360° content, they liked it and think it is exciting and very interesting. They comment that as soon as you practice, it will not take you much longer to create 360 subtitles than 2D.

ANNEX 10. SUBTITLING EDITOR REPORT (SECOND ITERATION: IMPLEMENTATION) (RBB)

1. General information

- **Subtitle Editor tested:** <http://imac.gpac-licensing.com/editor/>
- **Partner responsible for tests:** RBB
- **Date:** August – September 2019
- **Research tool:** online questionnaires (Google Form)
- **Measures:** usability and preferences
- **Participants:** 10
- **User guide:** https://drive.google.com/open?id=14FpkFbDsc8phKhyzXgRmz_qP-zg4VtS2

2. Demographic profile of participants

In the demographic questionnaire, participants were asked to give 18 responses.

1. **This is the second ImAc subtitle editor test. Did you take part in the first ImAc subtitle editor test?**
Yes (0) No (10)
2. **Sex:** a) Female (6); b) Male (4); c) Other (0); d) I prefer not to reply (0).
3. **Age:** 48, 31, 34, 40, 29, 29, 43, 39, 38, 25.
4. **Main language:** German 5, Russian 2, Slovak 2, Spanish 1
5. **Please, describe your current job:** Subtitling for the hard of hearing: 7, Subtitling editor-in-chief: 1, audiovisual translator:1, University lecturer: 1.
6. **Have you ever subtitled a 360° video?** Yes (0); No (10).
7. **For how long have you been working in the field of subtitling?** 3 years: 1, 1 year: 1, 14 years: 8.
8. **How many hours of subtitling have you produced in your professional life?** a) Less than 50 hours (1); b) 51-150 hours (5); c) 151-300 hours (0); d) More than 300 hours (4).
9. **In what language or languages do you normally subtitle (multiple answers)?** English: 7, Russian: 2, German: 5, Slovak: 2, Spanish: 1
10. **What software do you normally use (multiple answers)?** Aegishub:3, Bellenuit: 1, FAB: 3, EZTitles: 3, Subtitle Edit: 1, Sublime: 1, Wincaps/Screen: 6, Swift: 1, Spot: 1, various Freeware: 1
11. **Please indicate your level of studies.** a) Primary education (0); b) Secondary education (0); c) Further education (0); d) University (10).
12. **If you replied "Further education" or "University" in the previous question, please specify.**
B.A. in English Studies, M.A. in Audiovisual Translation
Economics
I've two higher degrees in science (BS + MS)
I have Master's degree in study program English Language and Culture and Slovak Language and Culture (study field Translation and Interpreting).
Master of Arts in conference interpreting
MA and PhD. in Translation and Interpreting
MA degree
MA in Translation
Postgraduate Diploma of Translation and Interpreting, Master of Audiovisual Translation: Localisation, Subtitling and Dubbing (candidate)
University of Leeds, MA Audiovisual Translation Studies
13. **If you have received specific training on subtitling, please indicate it here.**
At University
At university we had seminars on subtitling for two semesters.
In my masters I visited an optional course about audiovisual translation
Inhouse Respeaking and Subtitling Training (Macquarie University - Sydney)
M.A., IMS London (now part of BTI), NDR
Training provided in professional environment (by some of the clients)
University of Leeds, MA Audiovisual Translation Studies

14. What devices do you use on a daily basis? Multiple replies are possible. a) TV (5); b) PC (6); c) Laptop (8); d) Mobile phone (9); e) Tablet (4); f) HMD (4); g) Other (0).

15. How often do you watch virtual reality content (for instance, 360° videos)?

	Never	Occasion-ally	At least once a month	At least once a week	Every day
In smartphone	6	3	1	0	0
On a tablet	8	2	0	0	0
On a PC	5	5	0	0	0
In smartphone plugged to HMD	8	2	0	0	0
In HMD	8	1	0	1	0

16. If you have never used virtual reality content such as 360° videos or only occasionally, please indicate why. Multiple answers are possible. a) Because I am not interested. (0); b) Because it is not accessible. (1); c) Because I have not had the chance to use it. (8); d) Other reasons. (0) Please explain:

17. Please state your level of agreement with the following statement: "I am interested in virtual reality content (such as 360° videos)." a) I strongly agree (4); b) I agree (4); c) Neither agree nor disagree (2); d) Disagree (0); e) Strongly disagree (0).

18. Do you own any device to access virtual reality content? a) Yes (If yes, which one? _____) (3); b) No (6); c) I don't know or I don't want to reply (1).

19. If you replied "yes" to the previous question, please specify which device(s).

Samsung Gear VR

Lenovo Explorer Mixed Reality Headset

VR-Brille von Renkforce

We have a HMD to watch with a smartphone, but I haven't used it yet.

9. System Usability Scale (SUS) results

3.1. Scores (question by question)

SUS statements	1 – strongly disagree	2	3	4	5 – strongly agree
1. I think that I would like to use this system frequently	1	1	4	3	1
2. I found the system unnecessarily complex	3	4	1	1	1
3. I thought the system was easy to use	0	0	5	3	2
4. I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system	3	5	1	1	0
5. I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	1	0	3	4	2
6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	3	5	2	0	0
7. I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly	1	2	2	3	2
8. I found the system very cumbersome to use	2	0	5	2	1
9. I felt very confident using the system	0	3	2	4	1
10. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system	3	2	0	3	2

3.2. Summary

The SUS average score is 62.50 (below average, as the average is 68). This score is not a percentile ranking.

The graph below shows how the SUS scores associate with the percentile ranks and letter grades. The red line specifies where the subtitle editor is at this moment.

The letter grade is D, and the obtained score corresponds to the percentile range: 16-34.

10. Results from open preference questions

4.1. Results (question by question)

11. What did you like most about the subtitle editor?

- rbbtest_st09: I loved that I could set characters, regions, alignments and angle very easily.
- rbbtest_st07: I'm sorry to say that I much prefer the subtitle editor I work with every day.
- rbbtest_st10: Interface and quick navigation in terms of TCs, identification of characters and basic functions
- rbbtest_st01: It's easy to work with and you have a good overview of all Features.
- rbbtest_st14: Simple interface and good distribution of elements. Short learning curve easy to find your way around.
- rbbtest_st04: That the buttons said what they do
- rbbtest_st11: The fact that it's the only tool in existence capable of subtitling 360 videos.
- rbbtest_st13: The interface is pretty straightforward. I like that it has a lot of subtitling software features.
- rbbtest_st12: The main point, I guess, the 360 degree aspect.
- rbbtest_st02: The responsive user interface. All buttons were marked with the corresponding short cuts.

12. What did you like less about the subtitle editor?

- rbbtest_st04: I could not integrate two different characters in one subtitle. So I had to separate them and then the subtitle was too short. In the end, I had to erase two of them, as it would not work otherwise. The graph with the subtitles is a bit small, it is hard to see the frames.
- rbbtest_st07: I couldn't use all the navigation options I usually have in our subtitle programme. And I prefer to work directly in the subtitle in the video, not in a field below, and to apply and see any changes directly in the subtitle, not in separate menus. And after a certain number of subtitles the list on the right hand side jumps when clicking through the subtitles. That's something that I didn't like.
- rbbtest_st13: Maybe, it's due to my slow Internet or computer speed, but sometimes the editor would work slowly. I didn't like the fact that there was no clear indication of each line's length (only the total one).

- rbbtest_st02: No audio while rewinding/forwarding subs. Makes working cumbersome when due to a small work window the wave form is small. Some functions missing: splitting two lines of a sub within the same sub (line break). Only one colour per sub -> Different colours in the same sub would be great.
- rbbtest_st14: Not being able to know exactly what the error is when a subtitle appears in red. You can work it out, but it would be good if the system told you what the issue is. I didn't like the fact that you can not preview without having fixed the errors. There were two that I couldn't fix (I think they were both related to the minimum time on screen, even though they were very short sentences), so in the end, I was unable to see a preview. This was a bit frustrating.
- rbbtest_st10: Probably I would need more time to get used to the editor, but for me it was hard to figure out the processes in the final check of the subtitles, playing the videos with subtitles was not allowed before correcting the mistakes, but it was hard to identify/correct those if the video would not be played. But maybe I just did not notice something in settings or instructions.
- rbbtest_st12: That you have to correct all the "errors" before previewing it? Errors were not clear to me.
- rbbtest_st01: The play button looks too similar to the move-forward button. That confused me.
- rbbtest_st11: The UI design, for sure. Not to be too critical, but it feels like it was created by a specialist who lacks knowledge in professional subtitling — what the standards are and what a professional subtitler would expect to see in a tool. There's lots of wasted screen real estate, while the important elements (like the waveform) are given very little space (why not extend it through the whole screen width at the bottom?) Some things that I don't need to see at all times are there, etc. My recommendation would be to take a look at several professional subtitling tools' UI designs (you can download their trials if you don't have access to the full versions), and then try to replicate the best aspects of those UIs in your Editor. In my opinion, EZTitles has the best UI, so it might be a good place to start.
- rbbtest_st09: When there was an error, I struggled to find out what the error is, because there were 3 options. I would appreciate if the program would tell me what specific error to correct.

13. Did you miss any functionality? If yes, can you tell us which?

- rbbtest_st11: You cannot set hotkeys to the numpad keys on your keyboard, which is inconvenient. I could not find a way to remove the characters and regions that I added (what if I change my mind?) The subtitle list doesn't indicate the subtitles' TC violations, character, region and angle. All this information is necessary for me to be able to see how things are at a glance. The waveform is too small for comfort, and I can't zoom it in or out. A large number of useful hotkeys are missing in the tool, especially the ones related to timecoding (e.g. "In-time +1 frame"). See: <http://www.eztitles.com/download.php?file=169> (page 455 onward).
- rbbtest_st10: Easier way of playing/replaying the video with subtitles which were already made.
- rbbtest_st02: I haven't really checked it but can you use bold fonts and italics?
- rbbtest_st01: I miss the function to jump to certain video- or subtitle-places by shortcut.
- rbbtest_st13: Indication of each line's length. Indication of subtitling speed as characters per second.
- rbbtest_st04: It did not work to go back with ctrl. Z and always something else happened. If I was in the wrong subtitle and set the TC, I could not just simply go back and had to delete and redo subtitles again. I also could not see a back arrow. When I want to start preview mode, I have to deal with the errors and correct them. Sometimes the subtitle was one frame too short and I tried to work it out with the subtitles around it, but as I could not integrate two characters in one, so it stayed too short. Here it would be good to have the option: ignore problem and still get into the preview mode.
- rbbtest_st07: Perhaps I missed this functionality in the manual, but I would have liked to jump to the In-Timecode of a specific subtitle for example.
- rbbtest_st12: Sound during single frame stepping. Two speakers in one subtitle?
- rbbtest_st09: When I clicked on the specific timed subtitle in the right column, the program did not transfer me to the exact time of the subtitle in the video. I appreciate, that it works in preview mode.
- rbbtest_st14: Yes. I really missed a timeline view (like in WinCAPS) and being able to adjust TC by extending subtitles easily in a timeline. Also, I found it cumbersome to go to a particular frame in

the video. You can use the 'find' function, but I would've liked to be able to just select a subtitle and see that exact point in the video.

14. Do you find the feature for setting the angle for the subtitle easy to use? Explain why.

- rbbtest_st10: Hard to judge since this was the first time to use it. For me it would definitely require more insight into the philosophy of subtitling immersive environments, but I would not say it was too complicated - technically speaking.
- rbbtest_st02: No, not really. I was unsure where the position of the marker dot should be. In the middle of a speaker? On his or her head? Well below him?
- rbbtest_st07: Not really. For example, I would have liked to be able to save several positions, not just one, and paste them where necessary.
- rbbtest_st11: Takes a minute to get used to it, but it's pretty easy to use.
- rbbtest_st13: The feature is easy to use, but I feel that I need more theoretical knowledge of 360 subtitling to use it mindfully.
- rbbtest_st04: Yes, as the description was on the buttons and it is easy to move around the colourful spot
- rbbtest_st09: Yes, it was easy. I liked that I could set the angle not only by buttons, but also by moving the mouse.
- rbbtest_st01: Yes, it's easy to handle with only one click.
- rbbtest_st14: Yes, setting the angle was easy, but I wish I could see the dot moving. It took several attempts to find the right spot, because you don't see what the exact angle is until you click on the set button. So I kept going back and forth a few times. I got the hang of it in the end, though.
- rbbtest_st12: Yes.

15. Were the preview modes useful for you? Explain why.

- rbbtest_st04: A preview is definitely useful. I did not get the difference between the two preview modes.
- rbbtest_st14: As much as I tried, I just couldn't adjust two of the subtitles. This prevented me from using the preview modes, unfortunately.
- rbbtest_st12: Cannot tell. I would need more time to get used to the software.
- rbbtest_st10: NO (mentioned above in no.12)
- rbbtest_st11: The free preview mode seems a bit useless to me, but the forced one is good for checking if your angles are where they should be.
- rbbtest_st07: The preview mode is always helpful to get an idea whether you really like the timing in the end, but I prefer the editor to change to a larger window for that.
- rbbtest_st02: While using the forced preview mode I came across error messages telling me that something about the timecodes was wrong. I tried to fix them but from my point of view they did not need any fixing in the first place.
- rbbtest_st01: Yes, it is easier to find possible mistakes.
- rbbtest_st09: Yes, it was very useful, because I could see if I have set the right timing.
- rbbtest_st13: Yes, they were. I could see what subtitles would look like in reality, with all possible settings. This can't be bad.

16. Do you think it will take you longer to subtitle videos in 360°? Why?

- rbbtest_st07: At the moment, yes. Maybe that would change in a more integrated editor and with frequent usage.
- rbbtest_st10: The whole area is new to me, therefore it is hard to judge. On the other hand, it indeed has a great potential.
- rbbtest_st09: Well, sometimes I will need to look for a speaker, so it will take me a bit longer, but I guess it will not be much longer.
- rbbtest_st11: Whether it'll take me longer depends entirely on how good the tool is in terms of usability and functionality. The way things are currently, it will definitely take me longer.
- rbbtest_st01: Yes, a little, you have to set the angle.

- rbbtest_st04: Yes, as you have to align the position of the speaker
- rbbtest_st13: Yes, because I've never done it before and I've never watched content in this setting. Plus, the lack of clear guidelines is a bit confusing.
- rbbtest_st12: Yes, because you have to set the angles.
- rbbtest_st02: Yes. Getting used to the whole angle thing is quite a task at the beginning. Plus it always takes some time to get used to a new subs editor especially if you're not familiar with the key shortcuts (which may be different from the shortcuts you know by hard from your go-to-sub editor)
- rbbtest_st14: Yes. I bit longer given the extra step of setting the angle. Also, I'm not sure if it was my internet connection, but the video was very slow to play and kept getting stuck. This made the process very slow.

17. Do you think 360° videos will impact your work as a subtitler?

- rbbtest_st02: Depends if there is a market for it. I can't really tell at the moment.
- rbbtest_st12: I hope so.
- rbbtest_st04: If I will work in this field, yes, definitely
- rbbtest_st13: It's too early to say that it will. But I suppose it might happen.
- rbbtest_st09: Maybe I would need to learn how to work with new software, but I do not see any other changes right now.
- rbbtest_st01: No, I don't.
- rbbtest_st10: No.
- rbbtest_st07: Not yet, but perhaps one day.
- rbbtest_st11: Well, if I start receiving such projects, surely my work will be impacted :)
- rbbtest_st14: Yes. The time added, to an already lengthy subtitling process, will impact my work, but I think this type of material will present great opportunities in the industry.

18. Other comments:

- rbbtest_st11: I think this editor is a good step forward, but there's lots of work ahead before it becomes up to a professional standard — particularly in its UI design. I look forward to where you take this tool in the future.
- rbbtest_st14: I wish there was a function to set the language and run a spelling check in Spanish. Perhaps it already exists, but I couldn't find a way to set this up.
- rbbtest_st01: None.
- rbbtest_st04: some commands are with "alt" and if you don't type them fast enough, the program wants to open "file"
- rbbtest_st13: Thank you for your hard work!
- rbbtest_st12: The test is too short to actually get to know all the features and to be really able to evaluate them.

4.2. Summary

The ImAc subtitle editor was seen as being in very good shape. Testers mentioned especially the good UI overview, the ease-of-use, quick navigation and responsiveness.

Testers also recognised that not all common subtitling functionalities are implemented. They demanded line length indicator and better timecode relevant interconnectivity.

Setting angles for subtitles was unknown and completely new task, although navigating in the sphere was obviously easy and as was setting the actual angle.

The preview possibility also got positive feedback. It was mostly seen as being useful and helping to check subtitle placement in time and sphere.

Most of the testers were quite aware of the fact that producing 360 subtitles will take a little bit longer than in plan 2D videos. Especially navigation in the sphere and setting the angles were named.

ANNEX 11. AUDIO DESCRIPTION EDITOR METHODOLOGY (FIRST ITERATION: DEVELOPMENT) (UAB)

1. What to test?

- Audio description Editor (dynamic AD): <https://imac.gpac-licensing.com/editor/videos.php>
- Access: Each participant will have their own exclusive user and password.

2. When?

- From 24th September 2018 to 30th September 2018.

3. Methodology: overview

- **Research tools:** online questionnaires (Google Forms).
- **Measures:** usability and preferences.
- **Participants:** 30 professional audio describers from different countries.
 - **Recruitment criterion:** audio describers who professionally audio describe audiovisual content.
- **Language of the test:** English. The audio descriptions can be written in any language.
- **Materials:** AD editor and 360° video [private_content]
- **Experimental protocol:** users will be asked to perform certain tasks and then report on the usability and preferences through an online questionnaire.
- **Reporting:** results will be included in a report created by UAB. This will be done exporting data from the Google Form.
- **The current methodology will be tested by UAB with three users.**

4. Methodology: experimental protocol

- **Online test:** the users will access this test online, via email plus Google Forms, and there will be no supervision or facilitators involved. The test will include different steps (some info will be in the email, and some other in the Google Forms, see the table below):

Section	Description	Where?
Section 1	Welcome and presentation of the ImAc project and the test.	E-mail
Section 2	Ethical clearance: information sheet and consent form to be approved by the participant.	Google Form: https://goo.gl/forms/tKew4U7B1DrICJAX2
Section 3	Demographic questionnaire.	Google Form: https://goo.gl/forms/BnmYgnF4GBbYnRNn2

Section	Description	Where?
Section 4	The following items will be introduced: - Quick User Guide - The participants will be asked to read the Quick User Guide before performing the requested tasks. - Login information to access the AD editor. - Tasks to be performed.	E-mail (link to PDF): - Quick User Guide: https://drive.google.com/open?id=1FUuuva-s-slckFoUyBDi qpDnikTSUYVW - Instructions sheet: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1AtxD7jjPi6p8V8cYAvZ0l3ht_0pJ58Dc/view?usp=sharing
Section 5	SUS questionnaire & Preference questionnaire.	Google Form: https://goo.gl/forms/lq3ZSl tOYYcoA5o03
Section 6	Thank participants and follow up.	Section included in the Google Form from Section 5.

- **Materials.** The video to be used will be [private_content]. The duration of the video is 00:05:38. The video will be in low resolution (720s) to avoid overloading the server and make the audio describing task smoother.

- **Recruitment & User Code Assignment.**

We will recruit participants via contacts, by email/social networks, etc. The test has been designed in English so that professionals from different countries can participate. Once we have a list of participants, we will contact them by email to provide instructions and access to the online form and web editor.

We will create 30 different users (P01-P30) with the role of audio describer and each user will be assigned a video (same video for all users). The login information will be provided by email to the users. Then, they will access the ImAc AD editor and they will only have access to one video in the Editor module.

This user name will be the user code that they will need to enter in the different questionnaires when requested.

- **Contact:**

To conduct the test, professional audio describers (who have previously agreed on participating) will be contacted by email:

Subject: Test for ImAc AD editor - Instructions

Dear participant,

First of all, many thanks for participating in our study.

The **aim** of the test is to gather feedback from professional users like you regarding the ImAc web AD editor for 360° content that we have developed. This feedback will enormously help us to improve the tool and make it better for professional audio describers to use it in the future.

This test is built in relation to ImAc (Immersive Accessibility) project. The goal of ImAc project is to explore how accessibility services (such as subtitles, audio description, or sign language) can be integrated with immersive media. <http://www.imac-project.eu/>

This test will approximately take **45 minutes**.

YOUR USER CODE IS: PXX AD.

These are the steps that you need to follow **in this order**:

1. Give your consent to participate in this test by filling this form and clicking on YES.

<https://goo.gl/forms/tKew4U7B1DrICJAX2>

2. Provide some information about yourself, by replying to the following questionnaire:

<https://goo.gl/forms/BnmYgnF4GBbYnRNn2>

3) Perform a few tasks with the AD editor.

1. Please first read the Quick User Guide to get familiar with the tool:

<https://drive.google.com/open?id=1FUuuva-s-slckFoUyBDi qpDnikTSUYVW>

2. Now read the instructions and proceed with the test:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1AtxD7jjPi6p8V8cYAvZ0l3ht_0pJ58Dc/view?usp=sharing

3. This is your login information:

- User: PXX
- Password:

4) Tell us about your experience with the editor by replying to the following questionnaire:

<https://goo.gl/forms/lq3ZSltoYYcoA5o03>

5) Let us know by email that you have finished the test so that we can confirm that your data has been correctly registered.

The test will be open from today until the 30th of September. You can proceed with the test any time during this time frame but you should do it **in just one session**.

If you have any question or technical issue, please feel free to contact me any time.

Please, confirm that you have received this email and that you understand the instructions.

Thank you again for your collaboration!

All the best,

- **Tasks.** Participants are asked to perform a series of tasks individually on their own computers. The material will be available in the AD editor. They will need to access the AD editor and perform the tasks in the video that has been assigned to them.

The duration of the video is 00:05:38, but the professionals will be requested to AD from 00:00:00 to 00:01:10.

The instructions will be provided in a PDF document available here:

https://drive.google.com/file/d/1AtxD7jjPi6p8V8cYAvZ0l3ht_0pJ58Dc/view?usp=sharing

5. Questionnaires

Questionnaires will be provided to the participants using online forms, but is included below for reference.

Demographic questionnaire addressed to professional users (Annex 45)

SUS (see Annex 43)

PREFERENCES

Now please reply to the following questions in your own words.

1. What did you like most about the AD editor?
2. What did you like less about the AD editor?
3. What do you think could be improved, and how?
4. Did you miss any functionality? If yes, can you tell us which?
5. Do you find the feature for setting the angle for the AD easy to use? Explain why.
6. Were the preview modes useful for you? Explain why.
7. Do you think it will take you longer to AD videos in 360°? Why?
8. Do you think 360° videos will impact your work as an audio describer?
9. Other comments:

ANNEX 12. AUDIO DESCRIPTION EDITOR METHODOLOGY (SECOND ITERATION: IMPLEMENTATION) (UAB)

1. What to test?

- Audio description Editor (dynamic AD): <https://imac.gpac-licensing.com/editor/videos.php>
- Access: Each participant will have their own exclusive user and password.

2. When?

- September 2019.

3. Methodology: overview

- **Partners performing the tests:** UAB, with support from CCMA in performing the internal test.
- **Research tools:** online questionnaires (Google Forms).
- **Measures:** usability and preferences.
- **Participants:** we should aim at 30 professional audio describers to get statistically valid data and a comparable number of users with the first round of tests.
 - **Recruitment criterion:** audio describers who professionally audio describe audiovisual content.
- **Language of the test:** English. The audio descriptions can be written in any language.
- **Materials:** AD editor and 360° video (private content) and user guide.
- **Experimental protocol:** users will be asked to perform certain tasks and then report on the usability and preferences through an online questionnaire.
- **Reporting:** results will be included in a report.
- Partners should test the methodology works with ideally 2 users before performing the test. In any case, the methodology has been tested for pilot 1, so no changes are expected.

4. Methodology: experimental protocol

- **Online test:** the users will access this test online, via e-mail plus Google Forms, and there will be no supervision or facilitators involved. The test will include different steps (some info will be in the e-mail, and some other in the Google Forms, see the table below):

Section	Description	Where?
Section 1	Welcome and presentation of the ImAc project and the test.	E-mail
Section 2	Ethical clearance: information sheet and consent form to be approved by the participant.	Google Form: https://goo.gl/forms/C7Ey50uXBf7K1I6E3
Section 3	Demographic questionnaire.	Google Form: https://forms.gle/ChGDeR3AbsmPaGYD8
Section 4	The following items will be introduced: - Quick User Guide - The participants will be asked to read the Quick User	E-mail (link to PDF): - Quick User Guide: https://drive.google.com/open?id=1wp9Th3kTDk0-AywMAutqM0y-

Section	Description	Where?
	Guide before performing the requested tasks. - Login information to access the AD editor. - Tasks to be performed.	2eW5MooA - Instructions sheet: https://drive.google.com/open?id=17u_6BkZy3EMBoTK1nxF-9iZRNPY33Tne
Section 5	SUS questionnaire & Preference questionnaire.	Google Form: https://forms.gle/LnQ4wRVazQNCbUa4A
Section 6	Thank participants and follow up.	Section included in the Google Form from Section 5.

- **Materials.** The video to be used will be (Private content).

(<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WqCH4DNQBUA>). The duration of the video is 00:05:38 but the excerpt selected to be audio described is shorter.

The video will be in low resolution (720s) to avoid overloading the server and make the audio describing task smoother.

- **Recruitment & User Code Assignment.**

Participants will be contacted by UAB, with support from CCMA. The test has been designed in English so that, if needed, professionals from different countries can participate. Once a list of participants is available, they will be contacted by e-mail and instruction will be provided on how to access the online forms and web editor.

30 different users (P1 2019-P30 2019), or as many as necessary, will be created with the role of audio describer and each user will be assigned a video (same video for all users). The login information will be provided by e-mail to the users. Then, they will access the ImAc AD editor and they will only have access to one video in the Editor module.

This user name will be the user code that they will need to enter in the different questionnaires when requested.

- **Contact:**

To conduct the test, professional audio describers (who have previously agreed on participating) will be contacted by email:

Subject: Instructions for ImAc AD editor study

Dear participant,

Many thanks for participating in our study.

The aim of our study is to gather feedback from professional audio describers like you on the AD editor for 360° content that has been developed within the ImAc project. Please note that the quality of the produced audio description will not be taken into account. Your feedback will help us to ensure that this editing tool meets the needs of professional users.

The aim of ImAc is to propose tested solutions on how access services can be integrated with immersive media. To learn more, visit: <http://www.imac-project.eu/>

This test will take **1 hour**.

Your login to the editor:

User code: PXX 2019

Please, follow these steps in order:

1. Give your informed consent:
<https://goo.gl/forms/C7Ey50uXBf7K1l6E3>
2. Reply to the questions about yourself, by filling in this questionnaire:
<https://forms.gle/ChGDeR3AbsmPaGYD8>
3. Read the user guide:
<https://drive.google.com/open?id=1wp9Th3kTDk0-AywMAutqM0y-2eW5MooA>
4. Read the test instructions and proceed with the test:
https://drive.google.com/open?id=17u_6BkZy3EMBoTK1nxF-9iZRNPY33Tne
5. Fill in the questionnaire: <https://forms.gle/LnQ4wRVazQNCbUa4A>
6. Confirm by e-mail that you have finished the test.

The test will be open from today until (date pending). You complete the test any time during this time frame but, please, do it in **one session**.

If you have any questions, please contact me by e-mail. Please, confirm that you have received this e-mail. All the best,

- **Tasks.** Participants are asked to perform a series of tasks individually on their own computers. The material will be available in the AD editor. They will need to access the AD editor and perform the tasks in the video that has been assigned to them.

The duration of the video is 00:05:38, but the professionals will be requested to AD from 00:03:30 to 00:04:20.

The instructions will be provided in a PDF document available here:

https://drive.google.com/open?id=17u_6BkZy3EMBoTK1nxF-9iZRNPY33Tne

5. Questionnaires

Questionnaires will be provided to the participants using online forms.

Demographic questionnaire addressed to professional users (Annex 45), **SUS** (Annex 43).

PREFERENCES

Now please reply to the following questions in your own words.

11. What did you like most about the AD editor?
12. What did you like less?
13. What do you think could be improved, and how?
14. Did you miss any functionality? If yes, which one?
15. Do you find the feature for setting the angle for the AD easy to use? Explain why.
16. Were the preview modes useful for you? Explain why.
17. Do you think it will take you longer to audio describe videos in 360°? Why?
18. Do you think 360° videos will impact your work as an audio describer?
19. Other comments:

ANNEX 13. AUDIO DESCRIPTION EDITOR REPORT (FIRST ITERATION: DEVELOPMENT) (UAB)

1. General information

- **AD Editor tested:** <https://imac.gpac-licensing.com/editor/videos.php>
- **Version tested:** 26.
- **Partner responsible for tests:** UAB.
- **Date:** from 22/09/2018 to 14/10/2018 .
- **Research tool:** online questionnaires (Google Form).
- **Link to online forms:**
 - Consent form: <https://goo.gl/forms/tKew4U7B1DriCJAX2>
 - Demographic questionnaire: <https://goo.gl/forms/BnmYgnF4GBbYnRNn2>
 - Post-questionnaire: <https://goo.gl/forms/lq3ZSlT0YYcoA5o03>
- **Measures:** usability and preferences.
- **First and second set of testing:** Two sets of testing were performed, the first one between 24.09-12.10.2018, aiming at different countries, and the second one between 3.10-19.10, aiming at US respondents thanks to a cooperation with the US. Taking into account that the reduced number of participants (3) completed the test in the second set, the results of both sets will be presented together, using the code US for the second set. Demographic data related to the first set of testing is presented in section 2 and demographic data of the second can be found in section 3.
- **Participants:** 31 professional audio describers started the first set of testing, but only 21 finished it. 3 participants completed the second set of testing.
- **User guide:**
 - <https://drive.google.com/open?id=1FUuuva-s-slckFoUyBDi qpDnikTSUYVW>
- **Instructions:**
 - https://drive.google.com/file/d/1AtxD7jjiPi6p8V8cYAvZ0l3ht_OpJ58Dc/view?usp=sharing

2. Demographic profile of participants: first set of testing

Number of participants who finished the pre-questionnaire: 31.

Number of participants who finished the test: 21.

10 dropped the test, the reasons being technological for 3 participants (9.67%), personal for 3 (9.67%), and unknown for 4 (12.9%).

Answers of the participants who finished the test in the first set are presented below:

- **Sex:** a) Female (14=66.67%); b) Male (6=28.6%); c) Other (0=0%); d) I prefer not to reply (1=4.8%).
- **Age:** 25 (1=4.8%); 26 (2=9,5%); 27 (2=9.5%); 30 (1=4.8%); 31 (2=9,5%); 33 (3=14.29%); 34 (1=4.8%); 35 (2=9,5%); 36 (1=4.8%); 41 (1=4.8%); 43 (1=4.8%); 47 (1=4.8%); 50 (1=4.8%); 60 (1=4.8%); 64 (1=4.8%).
- **Main language:** Spanish (6=28.6%); Catalan & Spanish (2=9,5%); Bosnian (1=4.8%); English (3=14.29%); Polish (3=14.29%); Dutch (2=9,5%); Swedish (1=4.8%), Catalan (1=4.8%), German (2=9.5%).
- **Please, describe your current job:** PhD researcher (2=9,5%); Freelance translator and audio describer (1=4.8%); Audio Describer (1=4.8%), Actor, Filmmaker, Standardized Patient trainer (1=4.8%); Audio visual translator, audio describer and subtitler (1=4.8%); Audio description researcher and practitioner (1=4.8%); Product manager (1=4.8%); Financial corporation (1=4.8%); academic tutor (1=4.8%); Assistant professor, freelance translator and bookseller in a bookshop (1=4.8%); Access Advisor (1=4.8%); Audio Describer/Visual interpreter An Organizer of AD in Sweden Syntolkning Nu (1=4.8%); Managing Director (1=4.8%); project manager with French language (1=4.8%); 1. President of the Association "Novis" which introduced practice of AD in cultural activities of Bosnia and Herzegovina in 2017 that did not exist before. Currently working on

the projects that will secure AD as a continuous practice for one theatre house and one cinema in Sarajevo making them able to have their regular repertoar adapted for blind and visually impaired persons. 2. Manager of the Studio Chelia (sound post production studio) (1=4.8%); Translation Project Manager (1=4.8%); profesora y audiodescriptora (1=4.8%); freelance audiodescriber for film and TV (1=4.8%); Audiodescriber amd Language Teacher (1=4.8%); Audio describer (1=4.8%); freelancer audio describer and subtitler (1=4.8%).

- **Have you ever audio described a 360º video?** Yes (2=9.5%); No (19=90.5%).
- **For how long have you been working in the field of AD?** 3 years (1=4.8%); About 1 year (1=4.8%); 9 years (2=9.5%); less than a year (1=4.8%); Since 2012 (1=4.8%); 8 years (1=4.8%); 21 years (1=4.8%); 2 years (4=19%); 13 years (2=9.5%); 4 years (1=4.8%); around 30 years (1=4.8%); 11 years (1=4.8%); 1.5 year (1=4.8%); 6.5 years (1=4.8%); 12 years (1=4.8%); 5 years (1=4.8%).
- **How many hours of audio description have you produced in your professional life?** a) Less than 50 hours (6=28.6%); b) 51-150 hours (4=19%); c) 151-300 hours (4=19%); d) More than 300 hours (7=33.33%).
- **In what language or languages do you normally audio describe?** Catalan (1=4.8%); Spanish (5=4.8%); English (2=9.5%); Dutch (1=4.8%); English, Polish (Polish, English) (2=9.5%); Spanish and Catalan (Catalan or Spanish) (2=9.5%); Swedish (1=4.8%); Dutch, English (1=4.8%); Bosnian and Croatian (1=4.8%); Polish (2=9.5%); German (2=9.5%); Catalan, amb sometimes in English (1=4.8%).
- **What software do you normally use?** Word/Fingertext (1=4.8%); Aegisub (1=4.8%); paper script and pencil/eraser (1=4.8%); -- (1=4.8%); FAB (1=4.8%); Subtitling software (1=4.8%); Free (1=4.8%); Microsoft Word (None. I produce a script in Word) (Microsoft Office, Best player) (word y reproductor de vídeo VLC u otros) (4=19%); Subtitle Workshop (I've never had to record my own ADs) (1=4.8%); none (2=9.5%); Audition for movies and Word for theatre (1=4.8%); WinCaps, Annotation Edit, ProTools, Earcatch (1=4.8%); Google docs (1=4.8%); f4 (1=4.8%); Fingertext (1=4.8%); - (1=4.8%); Swift ADePT (1=4.8%).
- **Please indicate your level of studies.** a) Primary education (0=0%); b) Secondary education (2=9.5%); c) Further education (1=4.8%); d) University (18=85.7%).
- **If you replied "Further education" or "University" in the previous question, please specify.** PhD (1=4.8%); Master's degree, almost a PhD (1=4.8%); Studies theatre performance in college (1=4.8%); master (1=4.8%); Comunicación Audiovisual (1=4.8%); PhD in Translation Studies (PhD in Translation) (2=9.5%); no (non) (2=9.5%); Linguistic and Russian Philology (1=4.8%); John Paul II Catholic University of Lublin, Poland (1=4.8%); UPF (Journalism), UAB (Translation) (1=4.8%); MA (Sound Design) (1=4.8%); Jagiellonian University (1=4.8%); Academy of Performing Arts Sarajevo (Dramaturgy department) (1=4.8%); MA in International Business Relations and Linguistics - translation and intercultural communication (1=4.8%); doctora en traducción e interpretación (1=4.8%); Sociology (MA), Comparative Literature (ongoing) (1=4.8%); Classical Philology (Greek amb Latin) (1=4.8%); Accessibilty at University of Hildesheim (1=4.8%); Bachelor of International Studies (Languages), MA (Translation and Interpreting Studies), Graduate Diploma (Publishing) (1=4.8%).
- **If you have received specific training on audio description, please indicate it here.** Workshop (1=4.8%); No (1=4.8%); I trained under my AD manager in Australia at The SubStation company (1=4.8%); course on AD (1=4.8%); FPO Audiodescripción para cine y televisión (1=4.8%); Module in audiovisual translation, including AD (1=4.8%); Yes (3=14.3%); Master in Audiovisual Translation and other courses in the UK, Germany... (1=4.8%); Just attended some seminars (1=4.8%); I have educate over 250 persons in Sweden and soon some more i Finland (1=4.8%); training during conferences (1=4.8%); university course (2 years) (1=4.8%); Training organized by Association "Zamisli" (Zagreb, Croatia) (1=4.8%); University course, extracurricular activities with specialists) (1=4.8%); 3-days-beginners-workshop by people from BR (Bayrischer Rundfunk) (1=4.8%); I trained on AD with the feedback of users from TV3 programs, and with some instructions taken from foreign AD (1=4.8%); - (1=4.8%); I trained under my AD manager in Australia at The SubStation company (1=4.8%); Training from Deborah Lewis (Weekend) and apprenticeship then continuing professional development (1=4.8%).
- **What devices do you use on a daily basis? Multiple replies are possible.** a) TV (13=61.9%); b) PC (12=57.1%); c) Laptop (18=85.7%); d) Mobile phone (20=95.2%); e) Tablet (7=33.3%); f) HMD (1=4.8%); g) Other (1=4.8%).

- **How often do you watch virtual reality content (for instance, 360° videos)?**

	Never	Occasionally	At least once a month	At least once a week	Every day
In smartphone	10 (47.6%)	10 (47.6%)	1 (4.8%)	-	-
On a tablet	15 (71.4%)	6 (28.6%)	-	-	-
On a PC	9 (42.8%)	11 (52.4%)	1 (4.8%)	-	-
In smartphone plugged to HMD	18 (85.7%)	2 (9.5%)	1 (4.8%)	-	-
In HMD	17 (80,95%)	3 (14.3%)	-	1 (4.8%)	-

- **If you have never used virtual reality content such as 360° videos or only occasionally, please indicate why. Multiple answers are possible.** a) Because I am not interested. (5=23,8%); b) Because it is not accessible. (3=14.3%); c) Because I have not had the chance to use it. (11=52.4%); d) Other reasons. (2=9.5%) Please explain:
no suelo acceder a estos contenidos, creo que hay poco, aunque me ha sorprendido al entrar en este proyecto. (1=4.8%)
No reply (1=4.8%)
- **Please state your level of agreement with the following statement: “I am interested in virtual reality content (such as 360° videos).”** a) I strongly agree (3=14.3%); b) I agree (8=38.1%); c) Neither agree nor disagree (7=33.33%); d) Disagree (1=4.8%); e) Strongly disagree (2=9.5%).
- **Do you own any device to access virtual reality content?** a) Yes (If yes, which one? _____) Yes (7=33.3%); b) No (10=47.6%); c) I don't know or I don't want to reply (4=19%).
- **If you replied "yes" to the previous question, please specify which device(s).** Smartphone (3); Google Cardboard (1); Virtual reality glasses and virtual reality headset (1); Laptop (2); PC (1); Oculus Go (1); VR SHINECON Virtual Reality Glasses (1); TV (1).

Summary

The profile of 21 participants who finished the test, and whose data are considered for the analysis, is as follows:

Twenty-one participants completed the test (14 females and 6 males; 1 - prefer not to reply), with ages ranging 25-64. Their main languages are Catalan, Spanish, Bosnian, English, Dutch, Polish, German and Swedish.

Their jobs are mainly AVT translators, freelance audio describers, PhD researchers, academic professors and project managers. Only two participants have audio described a 360° video before. They presented a varying experience in the field of AD (varying from less than 1 year to around 30 years). 7 participants have produced more than 300 hours of AD content, 4 participants have produced between 151 and 300 hours of AD content, 4 participants have produced between 51 and 150 hours and 6 participants have produced less than 50 hours. Participants usually audio describe in Catalan, Spanish, German, Bosnian and Croatian, English, Polish, Swedish and Dutch. Participants declared using different AD and ST and software as well as video players for producing AD (Fingertext, Aegisub, FAB, Best player, Subtitle Workshop, Audition, WinCaps, Annotation Edit, ProTools, Earcatch, Google docs, F4, Swift ADePT). Many participants used Microsoft Word for writing the script.

18 participants have studies of university level, 1 participant has further education and 2 participants had secondary education. Some participants have MA in translation and interpreting studies (or languages degrees), some of them specialising in Audiovisual Translation and some of them have PhD

studies. Most of the participants have received specific training on AD: during workshops, in their companies, during courses on AD, modules in university courses on audiovisual translation, MA studies, seminars, training during conferences and trainings organised by associations.

When asked about which devices they use on a daily basis, almost all participants (20) agreed on using mobile phones; 20 participants use mobile phones; 18 participants use laptops; 13 participants use TVs, 12 participants use PCs; 7 of them use tablets; 1 of them uses HMD and one participant chose the option "other".

When asked about how often they watch virtual reality content, 18 have never watched VR content in a smartphone plugged to HMD; some (2) occasionally watch VR content in a smartphone plugged to HMD and one watches VR content in such a way at least once a month. 17 participants have never watched VR content in HMD, 3 use HMD occasionally and 1 participant uses HMD at least once a week. 11 participants consume VR content in smartphone occasionally (10) or at least once a month (1). 6 participants use occasionally tablets to consume VR content and, regarding PC, 11 participants use this device occasionally and 1 participant at least once a month to access such content.

When asked to explain why they have never used virtual reality content such as 360° videos or only occasionally, 5 participants replied that they are not interested, 3 participants replied that it is not accessible, 11 participants replied that they have not had the change to use it, and two participants chose the option "other reasons". One of them provided an additional comment: "no suelo acceder a estos contenidos, creo que hay poco, aunque me ha sorprendido al entrar en este proyecto" ("I don't normally access these contents, I think there are just a few, although I have been surprised when accessing the project").

When asked to state their level of agreement with the statement "I am interested in virtual reality content (such as 360° videos)", 3 participants replied that they strongly agree, 8 replied that they agree, 7 that they neither agree nor disagree, 1 of them disagree and 2 of them strongly disagree. Finally, when asked if they own any device to access virtual reality content, 10 participants replied that they don't, 4 replied that they don't know or prefer not to reply and 7 replied that they do (including smartphone, Google cardboard, Laptop, Tablet, Virtual reality glasses and virtual reality headset, PC, Oculus Go, VR SHINECON Virtual Reality Glasses and TV).

The profile of the 10 participants who did not finish the test is as follows:

9 females and 1 male did not complete the test, with ages ranging 32-74 (58, 35, 36, 64, 70, 52, 32, 40, 74, 70). Their main languages are Catalan, Polish, Spanish (2), English (5) and German. Their responses in relation to their jobs are the following: "Audio Describer" (3); "Academic teacher"; "Translator and high-school professor"; "Retired"; "AD Commentator", "Presenter, Press – Officer"; "Project Manager"; "Audio Describer/AD Consultant" and "Head of Production- Adelaide Fringe (production manager of a small team overseeing all Fringe managed events). Adelaide Fringe is the 2nd largest un-curated Fringe festival in the world. Fringe managed events are large-scale public engagement projects across the 5 weeks of the festival".

Only one participant of those who have not finished the test has audio described a 360° video before. They presented a varying experience in the field of AD, varying from 1 month 19 years (3 years (2), 4 years, 19 years, 18 years (2), 12 years (2), 1 month, 7 years). 5 participants have produced more than 300 hours of AD content, 2 participants have produced between 151 and 300 hours of AD content and 3 participants have produced less than 50 hours. They usually audio describe in Catalan, Spanish (1); Polish (1), English (5), Spanish (2) and German (1).

These 10 participants provided the following responses when asked about the software used for the production of AD: "Fingertext Audio Description Editor"; "I don't use software"; "None"; "None (live work in theatres) - have previously used Swift Adept"; "None"; "I do Live AD – Software "Artecast"; "Garage Band"; "Word Processing"; "Audacity for prerecorded information"; "Starfish". Of all them graduated from the University. These are the responses that they provided when asked to specify their education: "Filologia Catalana (UB)", "Màster en Traducció Audiovisual (UAB)"; "PhD"; "Traductora Técnico-Científico y Literaria en Inglés / Magíster en Literaturas Comparadas"; "BA Hons English and American Literature"; "BA Dip ED. MSSc"; "Arts"; "BA. Translation & Interpreting; Postgraduate Studies"; "Bachelor of Dramatic Art/ Production"; "University".

Most of these participants have received specific training on AD in MA studies or during trainings. These are the responses provided by them to this question: "Màster en Traducció Audiovisual (UAB)"; "No" (2); "Postítulo en Textos Audiovisuales y Accesibilidad"; "Yes"; "Have Open College Network Level 3 certificate"; "Yes", "Audiodescription for the means of media and communication"; "Yes"; "Yes in 2011 conducted in Adelaide by Willie Elliott (Audio description trainer from Grey Eye - at the time, for the UK) through Access 2 Arts in Adelaide. 5 day course; Training at National Theatre London and at Red Bee."

When asked about which devices they use on a daily basis, almost all participants who completed the pre-questionnaire (9) agreed on using laptops and mobile phones (9); 6 participants use tablets; 5 participants use TVs; and 1 participant uses PC.

When asked about how often they watch virtual reality content, 6 have never watched VR content in a smartphone and 4 occasionally watch VR content by means of this device. All of them have never watched VR content in HMD or on smartphone plugged to HMD, 1 participant uses occasionally tablet to consume VR content and 2 participants use PC occasionally to access such content.

When asked to explain why they have never used virtual reality content such as 360° videos or only occasionally, 6 participants out of 10 reported that they have never had chance to use it, 1 answered "I am not interested", 1 "Because it is not accessible" and 2 participants have not provided their reply to this question, without adding any additional comments.

When asked to state their level of agreement with the statement "I am interested in virtual reality content (such as 360° videos)", 4 participants replied that they agree, 2 that they strongly agree and 4 that they neither agree nor disagree.

Finally, when asked if they own any device to access virtual reality content, 7 participants replied that they don't, 3 replied that they do. When asked to specify which type of device they have, they provided the following responses: "smartphone", "Tablet and PC", "Smart TV", "At a previous place of employment we used google cardboard (headset) and mobile phone".

Three out of these 10 participants did not complete the test because of technological reasons. For one participant (P28 AD), the visualisation of the videos was not possible. This participant could only hear the sound, but was not able to see any image in the video. This participant was using iMac. The second participant who did not complete the test (P19 AD), reported that his/her microphone did not work with the software and that the software kept freezing on his or her laptop. The third participant (P26 AD) specified that this technology was too difficult for him/her. His/her profile was an aged participant (70 years old), who worked for 18 years in the field of AD, but never watched virtual reality content on any device. The challenge of audio describing the 360° video could therefore result from unfamiliarity with this medium. Furthermore, when asked about the usage of software, this person responded "non", declaring not using any software while producing AD.

3. Demographic profile of the participants: second set of testing (US)

3 participants completed the test in the second set.

Answers of the participants who finished the test in the second set are presented below:

1. **Sex:** a) Female (1=33.33%); b) Male (2=66.67%); c) Other (0=0%); d) I prefer not to reply (0=0%).
2. **Age:** 36 (1=33.33%); 47 (1=33.33%); 64 (1=33.33%).
3. **Main language:** English (3=100%).
4. **Please, describe your current job:** Description Supervisor at Captionmax (1=33.33%); Oversee media accessibility for major internet media and technology company. (1=33.33%); Audio Describer (1=33.33%).
5. **Have you ever audio described a 360° video?** Yes (2=66.67%); No (1=33.33%).
6. **For how long have you been working in the field of AD?** 6+ years (1=33.33%); 28 years (1=33.33%); 18 years (1=33.33%).
7. **How many hours of audio description have you produced in your professional life?** a) Less than 50 hours (1=33.33%); b) 51-150 hours (0=0%); c) 151-300 hours (0=0%); d) More than 300 hours (2=66.67%).

8. **In what language or languages do you normally audio describe?** English (3=100%).
9. **What software do you normally use?** Swift Adept, Starfish, Pro Tools (1=33.33%); CADET, QuickTime, 3Play Media (1=33.33%); company-developed description software (1=33.33%).
10. **Please indicate your level of studies.** a) Primary education (0=0%); b) Secondary education (0=0%); c) Further education (0=0%); d) University (3=100%).
11. **If you replied "Further education" or "University" in the previous question, please specify.** Master of Fine Arts in Creative Writing (1=33.33%); University of Southern California, BA, Broadcast Journalism (1=33.33%); BS in Biology; MS in Science Journalism (1=33.33%).
12. **If you have received specific training on audio description, please indicate it here.** Internal company training (1=33.33%); WGBH Descriptive Video Service (Yes, from WGBH Descriptive Video Service; Trained at WGBH Descriptive Video Service) (2=66.67%).
13. **What devices do you use on a daily basis? Multiple replies are possible.** a) TV (2=66.67%); b) PC (2=66.67%); c) Laptop (3=100%); d) Mobile phone (3=100%); e) Tablet (1=33.33%); f) HMD (0=0%); g) Other (0=0%).
14. **How often do you watch virtual reality content (for instance, 360° videos)?**

	Never	Occasionally	At least once a month	At least once a week	Every day
In smartphone	2 (66.67%)	1 (33.33%)	-	-	-
On a tablet	2 (66.67%)	1 (33.33%)	-	-	-
On a PC	1 (33.33%)	2 (66.67%)	-	-	-
In smartphone plugged to HMD	3 (100%)	-	-	-	-
In HMD	3 (100%)	-	-	-	-

15. **If you have never used virtual reality content such as 360° videos or only occasionally, please indicate why. Multiple answers are possible.** a) Because I am not interested. (1=33.33%); b) Because it is not accessible. (0=0%); c) Because I have not had the chance to use it. (1=33.33%); No reply (1=33.33%).
16. **Please state your level of agreement with the following statement: "I am interested in virtual reality content (such as 360° videos)."** a) I strongly agree (1=100%); b) I agree (0=0%); c) Neither agree nor disagree (2=66.67%); d) Disagree (0=0%); e) Strongly disagree (0=0%).
17. **Do you own any device to access virtual reality content?** a) Yes (If yes, which one? _____) Yes (1=33.33%); b) No (1=33.33%); c) I don't know or I don't want to reply (1=33.33%).
18. **If you replied "yes" to the previous question, please specify which device(s).** Google Cardboard + iPhone (1)

Summary:

The profile of 3 participants who finished the test, and whose data are considered for the analysis, is as follows:

Three participants completed the test (1 female and 2 males), with ages ranging 36-64. Their main languages are English. Their jobs are audio description supervisors or audio describers. All of the participants had studies of university level: MA in Creative Writing, BA in Broadcast Journalism and MS in Science Journalism.

When asked about which devices they use on a daily basis, all participants (3) agreed on using mobile phones and laptops; 2 participants use PCs and TV and 1 participant uses tablet.

When asked about how often they watch virtual reality content, all of the participants have never watched VR content in a smartphone plugged to HMD or in HMD. 1 participant consumes VR content in smartphone occasionally, 1 participant uses occasionally tablet to consume VR content and, regarding PC, 2 participants use this device occasionally.

When asked to explain why they have never used virtual reality content such as 360° videos or only occasionally, 1 participant replied that he/she is not interested, 1 participant replied that they have not had the change to use it, and another participant did not provide answer to this question.

When asked to state their level of agreement with the statement “I am interested in virtual reality content (such as 360° videos)”, 2 participants replied that they neither agree or disagree and one participant replied that he/she strongly agrees.

Finally, when asked if they own any device to access virtual reality content, 1 participant replied that he/she don’t, 1 participant replied that he/she don’t know or prefer not to reply and 1 replied that they do (Google Cardboard + iPhone).

4. System Usability Scale (SUS) results from both sets of testing

4.1. Scores (question by question)

1 – strongly disagree, 5 – strongly agree

SUS statements	1	2	3	4	5
1. I think that I would like to use this system frequently	1 (4.17%)	6 (25%)	11 (45.83%)	4 (16.67%)	2 (8.33%)
2. I found the system unnecessarily complex	4 (16.67%)	7 (29.2%)	9 (37.5%)	4 (16.67%)	0 (0%)
3. I thought the system was easy to use	1 (4.17%)	4 (16.67%)	6 (25%)	11 (45.83%)	2 (8.33%)
4. I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system	10 (41.67%)	5 (20.83%)	4 (16.67%)	3 (12.5%)	2 (8.33%)
5. I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	1 (4.17%)	7 (29.2%)	10 (41.67%)	2 (8.33%)	4 (16.67%)
6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	2 (8.33%)	10 (41.67%)	9 (37.5%)	2 (8.33%)	1 (4.17%)
7. I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly	2 (8.33%)	4 (16.67%)	8 (33.33%)	8 (33.33%)	2 (8.33%)
8. I found the system very cumbersome to use	6 (25%)	4 (16.67%)	6 (25%)	5 (20.83%)	3 (12.5%)
9. I felt very confident using the system	5 (20.83%)	6 (16.67%)	5 (20.83%)	7 (29.2%)	1 (4.17%)
10. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system	4 (16.67%)	10 (41.67%)	2 (8.33%)	4 (16.67%)	4 (16.67%)

4.2. Summary (from two sets of testing)

The SUS average score is **55.9** (below average, 68 or more is considered above average).

The graph below shows how the SUS scores associate with the percentile ranks and letter grades and the red line specifies where the ImAc AD editor is at this moment.

The letter grade is D, and the obtained score corresponds to the percentile rank: 15-34%.

5. Results from open preference questions from two sets of testing

Results are presented question by question, and then followed by a summary of the replies. The following codes are used: PX Pilot AD (participants from the pilot who have been analysed as part of the first set of tests as the methodology did not change), PX AD (participants from the first set of tests) and USX (participants from the US test).

5.1. Results

What did you like most about the AD editor?

P1 Pilot AD: Aesthetically it was sort of appealing.

P2 Pilot AD: Its simplicity.

P1 AD: You can perform the whole process of AD (also recording).

P2 AD: It is available online.

P5 AD: The possibility of seeing the whole sphere (the arrows allowing you to see everything).

P7 AD: To see almost everything in the same screen.

P9 AD: It is quite easy, it has shortcuts and everything is visible and easily accessible on one page (segments, controls).

P11 AD: Layout.

P13 AD: The vision in the monitor, because it's so clear to use. Yo [sic] can view the video at the same time that yo [sic] write amb [sic] record.

P14 AD: After the first couple of minutes it turned out to be quite intuitive. Still, sometimes I had to use the manual. I like the list of subtitles on the right and how easily you can go back to a segment.

P15 AD: No reply.

P16 AD: It's simple and intuitive.

P18 AD: To create AD segments and AD moves.

P21 AD: Simple and intuitive.

P23 AD: Script and audio integrated in one software.

P27 AD: It was very intuitive and I liked the multiple ways of navigating the visuals.

P31 AD: Mover la flecha para el ángulo ("Move the arrow to the angle").

P33 AD: It's [sic] interface is very clear and easy to understand.

P36 AD: The clear layout and easy-to-understand functions. The recording function was very straightforward also.

P37 AD: To be able to set an angle; however [sic], I'm not sure that the sound then really came from the direction?

P38 AD: One interface for video and text.

US1 AD: Navigation of video and ability to tag locations.

US7 AD: The ease of setting the desired viewing angle for 360.

US5 AD: The user interface is straightforward and relatively easy to use. It's similar to other AD systems I'm familiar with.

What did you like less about the AD editor?

P1 Pilot AD: The fact that, when you record, the video starts before you actually have to speak.

P2 Pilot AD: That there are a lot of buttons with arrows.

P1 AD: Difficulties to learn the shortcuts (lack of usage, I guess). It wasn't clear that in order to listen to your recordings you need to be in preview mode. Also, apart from the mark for [sic] reading speed, you don't know exactly your reading speed and that would be [sic] very interesting to have in any AD editor. I couldn't see the video in free preview.

P2 AD: I had some problems using it.

P5 AD: I liked it in general.

P7 AD: Miss undo, Timeline in picture I use iMac so I need another [sic] browser.

P9 AD: A Segment List is exactly the same as a central section - it should be limited to the real list of segments with TCs only. Also, I could not hear my recordings - probably I have problems with my microphone. But maybe this is why I do not see any difference between neither short and long test nor free and forced preview.

P11 AD: A lot of functions and buttons.

P13 AD: you don't know when to start recording. You'd need something like a colour line that changes colour when you have to start. It seems that it is not possible to put 2 or more segments at the same time, or sharing time, from different points of view. For me it wasn't [sic] easy to discover how to listen to all these [sic] segments. Maybe you have to discover the points of view from those the audiodescriber do his descriptions, and [sic] for me it is very difficult to find when you are [sic] looking the video.

P14 AD: The recording part: I think the icons and settings are not so clear (I wasn't sure if the recording is saved or not).

P15 AD: No reply.

P16 AD: Video, audio and playback.

P18 AD: Shortcuts. They're not intuitive.

P21 AD: No direct HMD output for reference / check.

P23 AD: Sticky to use, has not flow.

P27 AD: Nothing about the recording worked for me- there was an obvious glitch, the frames started moving around. I could not hear playback and needed to go back and forth between frames and the

preview and edit modes and still it didnt [sic] work. Also as I was trying to adjust the AD sections in terms of timing I found that part hard to control.

P31 AD: Los controles manuales de vídeo (“Manual video controls”).

P33 AD: The position of a countdown square. When looking at it to start the recording, its position (down to the right side of a page) makes it hard to have your eye on the text that you need to start reading.

P36 AD: I found the shortcuts very difficult to use because I am used to the shortcuts I currently use in Swift. I kept reaching for the number pad.

P37 AD: Not very intuitively; not very pictorial icons; few optins [sic] to navigate smoothly between the various parts of the Editor.

P38 AD: Navigation.

US1 AD: Inability to review completed work, with described locations appearing on a map.

US5 AD: Some of the video and recording controls did not work as desired. More on that below. Also, it wasn't clear whether there should be a minimum separation between descriptions.

US7 AD: Some of the buttons were too similar and too close together - easy to get mixed up.

What do you think could be improved, and how?

P1 Pilot AD: The shortcuts are hard on the hands, not easy nor practical. Kind of painful, at least in my keyboard.

P2 Pilot AD: The going backwards and forwards along the video. I use Mac and maybe that is the problem with the video moving.

P1 AD: Adding the actual reading speed, not just the lights. Also being able to set up your own shortcuts (I read you're planning that, but even for the test... It's very difficult to get used to new shortcuts just for one test, so I eventually used the mouse and I guess the AD would have been better being able to use the shortcuts I'm used to).

P2 AD: Sometimes the buttons get frozen or they reply with delay.

P5 AD: Nothing to mention.

P7 AD: Move sound/text by mouse.

P9 AD: More room in the central section.

P11 AD: No reply.

P13 AD: May be it woult [sic] be better to have some fixed points of view from those you can do the descriptions. If not, I think it would be difficult for the user to find where are the hidden descriptions. For me i'ts [sic] difficult to understand that the descriptions are going with the movie, because some of them are going at the same time.

P14 AD: The quality of the video made it hard to recognize some details.

P15 AD: No reply.

P16 AD: Better playback features. Scrolling back to change timing does not work well.

P18 AD: Shortcuts/ How the AD recording controls works/ The arrow position. It's not very clear when the video has the 2D position, I mean, the standard position.

P21 AD: See 12.

P23 AD: The usability. Maybe been not a web editor.

P27 AD: Recording- have playback in the recording section for retakes creating AD segments, I'd like to see them on a visual timeline even if its vertical because I think mine overlapped as I was having a hard time changing the times. Playback- I wasn't able to get the playback to

work. It started playing after I pressed stop or wouldn't play at all. It seems like it would be good if it didn't have glitches.

P31 AD: Me gustaría que los controles play, pause, avanzar retroceder tuvieran los mismos controles (o que se pudieran editar) que otros editores de vídeo, se me hace muy raro no poder darle a la barra espaciadora para parar o alt+flecha para avanzar y retroceder, eso me hacía perder tiempo y no poderme meter en el proyecto. Pondría asset details debajo y segment controls arriba, es decir, intercambiaría sus sitios.

("I would like if the controls 'play', 'pause', 'go forward and backward' would be the same (or could be edited) as in other video editors. I find it very strange not being able to click on spacebar to stop or alt + arrow to move forward and backward, that made me lose time and not being able to focus on the project.

I would put asset details below and segment controls up, that is, I would exchange their sites.")

P33 AD: Countdown square could be placed closer to the segment text.

P36 AD: The frame jumping I found difficult to use. It also wasn't clear if it was necessary to activate the shortcut key several times repeatedly or just once to activate a command.

P37 AD: Better icons; more ways to go through; more effective player; full [sic] screen; better video quality; free settable shortcuts!

P38 AD: Navigation and Interface could be easier to use (less buttons).

US1 AD: Playback of completed work seems difficult.

US5 AD: The "step backward" and "fast backward" functions did not play the video as they moved, making it difficult to tell how far back I was moving. And there was some delay on the playback of recordings -- they did not play at the in-time, but rather 1-3 seconds late, causing some of the more tightly timed ones not to play at all.

US7 AD: Make the view control arrows and segment up down buttons distinct (not both arrows) and separate them spacially.

Did you miss any functionality? If yes, can you tell us which?

P1 Pilot AD: I find the bar with the cpm unnecessary and not very practical. Just a number turning red would suffice.

P2 Pilot AD: No reply.

P1 AD: Actual reading speed. Also, the sound quality of the recording seems improvable.

P2 AD: A waveform to indicate when a charater [sic] starts / finishes to speak and a timeline to show where exactly the video is.

P5 AD: No.

P7 AD: To use earphone during recording.

P9 AD: Yes. I could not find a button when I wanted to restart the video.

P11 AD: No reply.

P13 AD: The functions of go and stop by the keys didn't work; when you want to stop, you go to the start. And when you want to use the screen controls, the overwrite covers the time codes, and that makes the work hard.

P14 AD: No.

P15 AD: No reply.

P16 AD: Jumping back 5 tot 10 frames at a time. Synchrony between AD segments and video (if you click on segment, then de video also jumps to this timecode).

P18 AD: Maybe a key/button to go to a exactly [sic] TC. (I think I didn't find it).

P21 AD: An option to export the script to a text file for professional recording.

P23 AD: No.

P27 AD: A visual editor on a timeline for the AD sequences. I realize this is complex. One thing I am not clear on is if there can be simultaneous [sic] AD segments placed depending on where the user is facing.

P31 AD: Quizá una que se pudieran ver las líneas que equivalen al sonido, en los editores de vídeo tipo sony vegas viene y es muy útil para que la AD no interfiera con diálogos u otros sonidos de la película. Por ejemplo, cuando la chica coge la grabadora y suspira, me gustaría ver dónde exactament está ese suspiro para meter antes la AD.

("Perhaps one in which you could see the lines corresponding to sound, used in in such video editors as sony vegas. It shows and it is very useful to ensure that AD does not interfere with dialogues or other sounds in the film. For example, when the girl picks up the recorder and sighs, I would like to see exactly where that sigh is to write the AD before.")

P33 AD: No.

P36 AD: I missed being able to join or separate descriptions, and at the same time add or subtract timecodes.

P37 AD: No reply.

P38 AD: No.

US1 AD: How to play back recordings and get overview of complete work.

US5 AD: The keyboard shortcuts could be simpler, and the fading of program audio could be smoother, with more options for levels.

US7 AD: I'm used to using sound and dialogue cues rather than In times only. I find it helpful to see the dialogue cue that leads into a description.

Do you find the feature for setting the angle for the AD easy to use? Explain why.

P1 Pilot AD: Yes, it's just a button.

P2 Pilot AD: Yes, I have done it with the pointer directly on the video.

P1 AD: It was easy, but in this case, most actions only occurred in one angle, so it was not of much use.

P2 AD: Yes, it is easy to sent the angle. However, most of the time I did not really change it. I did not think it was necessary. Maybe if I had seen a 360 film with the sound around I would understand it better. At this moment, however, I can imagine how the sound in such a film works and that it strongly affects the whole viewing experience. But I am not quite sure if AD should be made part of the film in the same way as the sound coming from the film. What comes to my mind is the analogy with subtitles - the viewer is aware they are not part of the film, but they are a necessary supplement. For the moment it is difficult for me to imagine.

P5 AD: I have not used it, the video used for the test did not require audio describing in 360.

P7 AD: Didn't get it to work.

P9 AD: Yes. I can just choose a preferred angle with my mouse and then set it with one click.

P11 AD: Yes, it was very easy to use.

P13 AD: Not so much, because there are many points of view, and there are only some of them with descriptions. And if you don't pass exactly over that described point you lose the information that is there.

P14 AD: Yes, it was quite intuitive.

P15 AD: No reply.

P16 AD: Yes, but on my laptop, the screen of the video regularly became completely back after trying to set the angle. The sound remained but the image disappeared.

P18 AD: It's a bit challenging. Tecnically [sic], I consider it easy to use, the problem is which angle is the most important to describe.

P21 AD: Yes, just 1 key command. But I would like to have more freedom. The tutorial tells me we need an angle for each segment. I would like to have an angle only for very important situations.

P23 AD: Yes, easy to use, but don't understand how will be the result for the final user.

P27 AD: After I figured it out, yes.

P31 AD: No tengo muy claro si lo he hecho bien ("I'm not sure if I did it right").

P33 AD: Yes.

P36 AD: I found the function easy but I wasn't sure if the idea was to have simultaneous descriptions for the same timecodes. If a non-sighted person could access each recording, surely several recordings could be attached to a single in/out timecoded description. This made the writing of AD complicated in my mind because I wasn't sure if I should do several descriptions or choose an angle and describe only that angle for the time.

P37 AD: Yes; I just used the mouse and clicke [sic] the button to set it.

P38 AD: No, I didn't understand it.

Were the preview modes useful for you? Explain why.

P1 Pilot AD: Not really. They didn't start exactly on time, there was a delay.

P2 Pilot AD: Yes, one allows you to move, the other one makes you see your fixed angles.

P1 AD: I couldn't [sic] see the video in the free preview mode.

P2 AD: No reply.

P5 AD: Yes, because it avoids you omitting information.

P7 AD: I see a movie etc several time befor [sic] starting write my script.

P9 AD: No. I could not hear myself and I did not see any difference between them.

P11 AD: No, because it did not work properly.

P13 AD: Not at all. When I put the preview modes, I could listen to only few descriptions. It seems that you have to make the descriptions in temporary order, amb [sic] it would be more useful that the program had the fuction [sic] of ordering them. When I did the descriptions, I nedded [sic] to view the scene from different points of view, and it would be very difficult to do in strict temporary order. So, for me it would be very important that the program could do it for us.

P14 AD: Yes, I could check if everything is in time.

P15 AD: No reply.

P16 AD: I think they are useful, but my video screen went black when trying them.

P18 AD: No reply.

P21 AD: Yes, although the forced preview.

P23 AD: Yes, essential for can go on.

P27 AD: They didn't work- it did not preview for me.

P31 AD: No reply.

P33 AD: Preview modes were useful but confusing. I've recorded total of 8 segments and I've checked each of them after recording with short and long test and they worked. Afterwards, when I did forced and free preview, some of the segments were not played. I couldn't find the logic in "losing" some of the recorded segments, I was not sure at the end if some of the segments were not previewed because of the type of the preview or because I did something wrong during the recording process.

P36 AD: Because I tried to create simultaneous descriptions, the preview modes weren't terribly helpful as the recordings didn't play back. If you only need consecutive descriptions, the preview modes would be helpful.

P37 AD: The "fееe" [sic] one didn't show the video, just blackscreen; the other was cool.

P38 AD: Yes to see the Timing of the takes.

US1 AD: No reply.

US5 AD: Yes, but even in the "free preview" mode, I was not able to change angle. When I tried, the video would go black, although it would continue playing.

US7 AD: I wasn't always able to hear my recordings play and the video had a delay that I think made the timing not quite correct. But mostly it was useful to see the final and make corrections.

Do you think it will take you longer to audio describe videos in 360°? Why?

P1 Pilot AD: Yes, because you have to choose the right angle.

P2 Pilot AD: Yes, cause you take into consideration many other things that you won't think of in a regular content.

P1 AD: Yes. You need to check all the angles to see if something is happening there.

P2 AD: No.

P5 AD: Yes, because there will be more content to describe (not this case).

P7 AD: No It [sic] the same when we do live AD of theatre, musicals and Song Contest. I very interested in hove to use special goggles. This film I decided what to see. When a person use goggles how can we help them to explain what they are looking at.

P9 AD: Yes because there is far more to describe, to choose what to describe, how to set an angle... more choices.

P11 AD: Yes, a bit longer. You need to focus on more features and think carefully what you should describe.

P13 AD: Yes, because there is infinite points of view of every scene. That is why I propose to reduce the points of view from where to do the description.

P14 AD: Yes, because there are more details to describe.

P15 AD: No reply.

P16 AD: Yes. You need time to check the best angle to describe. It requires different information selection and wording.

P18 AD: Of course, because there're more visual information to describe, to analyze and to focus on more images.

P21 AD: Depends on the content.

P23 AD: Maybe, I'm not familiarized with this tech.

P27 AD: Well if we can have description in 360 or on various points in the same moment in time then yes naturally. 360 to me seems to be closer to theatre which I believe takes longer to get right than film because there is more to consider.

P31 AD: Supongo que sería acostumbrarse, pero sí, tardaría más porque adaptar el ángulo es una función más ("I guess it is a matter of getting used to it, but yes, it would take longer because adapting the angle is another function").

P33 AD: Yes. Because of all possible options for choosing the angle for AD.

P36 AD: I think it will take a lot longer as you need to consider all angles. Perhaps some kind of standard should be developed so AD'ers know when/where/what to describe.

P37 AD: The question seems rather self-explanatory ;) Because I have more to do.

P38 AD: yes, but only in the beginning. I think it needs time to learn the program and the characteristics of 360 videos.

US1 AD: Yes - infinite number of points to describe, decision-making as to what is relevant needs guidance.

US5 AD: Yes, because setting the angle is an extra step.

US7 AD: Yes, due to the need to check the angles.

Do you think 360° videos will impact your work as an audio describer?

P1 Pilot AD: I usually translate live television, so I don't think so, but who knows.

P2 Pilot AD: No reply.

P1 AD: Yes, it's a whole new approach.

P2 AD: Not really.

P5 AD: For sure, more content will have to be audio described.

P7 AD: Well hard to say. I like the idea and need to see more of it.

P9 AD: I am only a beginner but I think yes.

P11 AD: Probably yes.

P13 AD: Maybe those kind of videos will open my mind to note different points of view in every scene of a film.

P14 AD: Yes.

P15 AD: No reply.

P16 AD: No.

P18 AD: Yes. In a positive way, because I'd be more efficient, and I'd be able to offer a new way to understand audiovisual products.

P21 AD: Yes.

P23 AD: No, I would adapt.

P27 AD: Completely, because the applications are so vast and as a filmmaker this work with AD excites me very much.

P31 AD: Mucho, es muy interesante ("A lot, it is very interesting").

P33 AD: Yes.

P36 AD: I am not so concerned about the virtual component as feeling comfortable with the software. That would take some getting used to. The 360-degree videos would change the way I work as an AD'er but as with everything, practice makes perfect.

P37 AD: Not in the next years.

P38 AD: Maybe in the next years.

US1 AD: Yes - so many more options and innovations!

US5 AD: Probably in the future. I've described a few short 360 projects within the past year, but it's not very widespread yet. And I also don't understand how the audio would play from different locations for the end user, unless they're in a theater or have a home theater system with multiple audio sources. But for web-based content, where one is most likely listening via headphones or computer speakers, 360 seems like a purely visual experience. I'm sure future development will eventually prove me wrong!

US7 AD: Yes, with more VR films released, it will become necessary to describe them and be faithful to 360's nuances.

Other comments

P1 Pilot AD: I would strongly suggest that you don't choose the shortcuts yourself. Every audio describer knows what's [sic] best for their fingers, wrists and keyboards. Let them customise them.

P2 Pilot AD: No reply.

P1 AD: No reply.

P2 AD: I tried more than 5 times to record the AD. I hope it is recorded, but I could not play it, I did not hear anything. There was no way I could check it. I am sorry, I rather awful at technology and usually need someone to show me how to use it - a few times. But thank you for allowing me to have a try at IMAC.

P5 AD: The choice of the video might not be the best one to test this editor because the action is always happening in the same place.

P7 AD: [Private_content] was lovely to work with. The music was important to hear so it's a fight with AD, what to listen to. You can always contact me if you will hear more. Thank you for your understanding that allowed me this extra time. Hope you will have a nice weekend.

P9 AD: This program is amazing, keep doing great work, I was happy to help :)

P11 AD, P13 AD, P14 AD, P15 AD: No reply.

P16 AD: Nice work.

P18 AD: To have shortcuts similar than other editors would be easier to manage faster the AD 360° editor.

P21 AD: Will there be a possibility to write adaptive AD as well? I think that will be very useful for 360° videos / games.

P23 AD: I only use to make scripts, we use professional voices, maybe for this I'm not familiarized with this part of the workflow.

P27 AD: I'd love to use it again without the glitches. Thanks for the opportunity to try this out.

P31 AD, P33 AD: No reply.

P36 AD: It certainly is an adjustment as an AD'er to think about 360-degree videos. It opens up a whole new way of thinking about video and accessibility. I wouldn't feel comfortable taking on a job like this without proper instructions from the client and/or relevant training.

P37 AD: Good work, has potential and is in a way fun; but for real working, it's rather too clumsy right now. But the reason may be that, for this short test, it wasn't useful for me to remember shortcuts, so I did it without; maybe with shortcuts it works better.

P38 AD: Stepping back and forwards in the video didn't work so well.

US1 AD: It's great to see this tool. I would like to understand better how to output and review completed work.

US5 AD: No reply.

US7 AD: I sometimes forgot to put it back in Edit mode in order to make changes. If you could make the change between modes more distinctive somehow that would be helpful. Time wise it took me at least twice as long as was recommended. Took me a while to get the feel for it.

5.2. Summary

It is recommended to carefully look at particular replies obtained from the participants, as each reply points to different aspects of the software. The summary in this section will provide the most relevant and most frequent comments.

Participants **appreciated the most** that the whole process of producing AD, including recording, takes place in a single piece of software. Many comments referred to interface, which was described by participants as “very clear”, “simple”, “easy to use” and “easy to understand”. One of the comments (P9 AD) pointed to the fact that all the most important functions are displayed on one page, which facilitates the production of AD: “It is quite easy, it has shortcuts and everything is visible and easily accessible on one page (segments, controls)”. It was also appreciated that the software is available online. Also setting of the angle was assessed positively (US7 AD, US1 AD)

Many of the responses in the second question, which asked participants about **the elements that they liked less**, pointed to the problems encountered in the recording and preview modules. For some participants the recording and preview modes were not working properly, as described later in this summary. Also, some participants reported that the video was freezing.

Regarding shortcuts, the replies suggest that most of the participants would prefer a different, more intuitive configuration, or they would like to customise the shortcuts themselves. Regarding the recording, one response suggested that a line which would change its colour would be helpful to know when to start recording. One comment also suggested that it would be helpful to preview the produced AD in HMD.

When asked about **what could be improved**, many of the replies pointed to the shortcuts, recording controls and preview. One response suggested that better playback features would be needed, without the need to scroll back to change time codes (P16 AD). Some participants also reported that some buttons were frozen or they would be replying with delay. Additionally, some of the responses suggest that better video quality to see all the details would be needed.

Regarding **missing functionalities**, the responses suggest that the following features could be implemented: a waveform to indicate when a character starts or finishes speaking, jumping back to 5-10 frames at a time, synchrony between AD segments and video (if you click on segment, then the video also jumps to this timecode), an option to export the script to a text file for a professional recording, being able to join or separate descriptions, and at the same time add or subtract timecodes. US5 AD suggested also that more options for the fading of program audio could be added.

Regarding the **“set the angle” option**, most participants (75%) found it easy to use. However, one participant reported that the screen on her or his laptop would regularly turn black after trying to set the angle: the sound would remain, but the image disappeared. One response (P21 AD) suggests that this participant would prefer to set the angle only for very important situations, and not for all AD segments: “Yes, just 1 key command. But I would like to have more freedom. The tutorial tells me we need an angle for each segment. I would like to have an angle only for very important situations.”

As far as the **preview modes** are concerned, some of the participants did not encounter any problems while using them (e.g. P2 Pilot AD: “Yes, one allows you to move, the other one makes you see your fixed angles”), but for 50% participants one or both preview modes were not working properly (e.g. P16 AD: “I think they are useful, but my video screen went black when trying them”) or they could not see the difference between free and forced mode (e.g. P9 AD: “No. I could not hear myself and I did not see any difference between them”). Two participants (P33 AD and P13 AD) reported that not all of the recorded segments played in the preview mode.

When asked about whether it takes longer to audio describe videos in 360°, most of participants (79.2%) replied positively, as there are more visual details to describe, 360° content require more thorough content selection and the angles need to be set for every AD segment.

Regarding the impact of audio describing 360° videos on their AD practice, participants presented varying opinions. 58.3% of the participants consider, however, that it will impact on their work in the years. Participants who replied positively to this question, mentioned the following reasons: (1) the application for this medium is vast, (2) it is a whole new approach for the production of AD.

Finally, in the section **“Other comments”**, additional comments were made regarding the shortcuts, which in opinion of the participants should be customisable, as it would be easier to manage faster the AD 360° editor. Also, some participants reported some technological issues: problems with the recording (P2 AD) and problems playing the video (P38 AD): “stepping back and forwards in the video didn't work so well”. One participant (US7 AD) added a comment about the Edit mode: “I sometimes forgot to put it back in Edit mode in order to make changes. If you could make the change between modes more distinctive somehow that would be helpful.” Another participant (US1 AD) commented on the review: “I would like to understand better how to output and review completed work.”

5.3. Additional report

Apart from completing the test, US1 AD provided the following report on the usability of the AD Editor:

“In general, I found the tool quite straight-forward and usable (and familiar, as I have used the similar CADET accessibility tool from WGBH NCAM).

Here are some suggested changes:

- Scrub bar: most video editing tools make use of a video scrub bar below the video controls and you have included one as well, but it is not very responsive or accurate, perhaps because the video is hosted externally. If the video was available locally, perhaps the scrub bar would work better.
- Time code look-up: When navigating by time code, it would be handy if the cursor would land directly in the seconds field, the most likely place one would begin to search
- It would also be helpful if I could type numbers right into the time code read-out in the left-hand video control area rather than having to click on the small clock to open the time code search function
- Moving between described segments: it would be nice if I could click in the segment window in the center of the screen to go directly to that time and place in the video, instead of having to use the "next segment" arrows.
- Reading speed thermometer - I don't quite understand how this is used
- Having to jump from the left-hand to the center to the right-hand columns is a bit tedious.
- Tool tips cover time code read-out: in the left-hand column, if I leave my cursor over one of the video controls, the opaque tool tip blocks the time code read-out - it would be nice if the tool tip would time out or be semi-transparent
- I tried recording a segment but don't know where that recording is - it didn't play out when I rewind and played back
- When I play back the video after entering some descriptions, it would be good if the segments I described stepped down in the center column and if the video would shift to the location of the thing I was describing, and playback the recorded description.
- Upon playback, could the point of view move to where something was described, using the longitude and latitude markers.
- Can the text be read back via synthesis or does my voice have to be recorded?
- The tool tip for the "first segment" reads "fist segment"
- The key combos are all Windows-centric and while the tool works on a Mac, it would be good to give instructions for the Mac keys to use (i.e., fn instead of alt)
- It would be nice to see an overview map of some sort that showed where in space and when in time descriptions have been added. Maybe a sort of exploded globe (Mercator map projection), perhaps toggling between a flattened sphere for showing location and a timeline showing timing.
- Is there a full-screen mode, to get a "big picture" of the completed work [sic] to review?"

ANNEX 14. AUDIO DESCRIPTION EDITOR REPORT (SECOND ITERATION: IMPLEMENTATION) (UAB)

1. General information

- **AD editor tested:** <https://imac.gpac-licensing.com/editor/videos.php>
- **Version tested:** 46
- **Partner responsible for tests:** UAB
- **Date:** from 01/08/2019 to 18/09/2019
- **Research tool:** online questionnaires (Google Form)
- **Link to online forms:**
 - Consent form: <https://goo.gl/forms/C7Ey50uXBf7K1I6E3>
 - Demographic questionnaire: <https://goo.gl/forms/Cimx6qDUadE5GjEG2>
 - Post-questionnaire: <https://goo.gl/forms/d0edMXrUNzhzrs1>
- **Measures:** usability and preferences
- **Participants:** 24 professional audio describers took part in the test (42 participants filled in the pre-questionnaire, but 24 participants completed the post-questionnaire)
- **User guide:** <https://drive.google.com/open?id=1wp9Th3kTDk0-AywMAutqM0y-2eW5MooA>
- **Instructions for participants:** https://drive.google.com/open?id=17u_6BkZy3EMBoTK1nxF-9iZRNPY33Tne

2. Demographic profile of participants:

- Number of end users: 24
- Demographics for users
 1. **Did you take part in the first test of the ImAc AD editor?** "Yes" (7=29.2%), "No" (17=70.8%).
 2. **Sex:** "female" (18=75%), "male" (5=20.83%), "other" (0=0%), "I prefer not to reply" (1=4.17%).
 3. **Age:** 24, 25, 26, 27 (2), 28 (2), 34 (2), 36 (2), 37 (2), 38, 44 (3), 47, 49, 53, 55, 61, no response (2).
 4. **Main language:** English (3), German (3), Greek (1), Spanish (7), Russian (2), Slovak (2), Cantonese (Chinese) (1), Catalan (2), Dutch (2), Spanish and Catalan (1).
 5. **Please, describe your current job:** "PhD Researcher in AD", "audio describer" (3), "subtitlist and PhD candidate in AD", "access consultant", "audiovisual translator and audiodescriber [anonymized]", "AV translator, audio describer, accessibility division manager", "(...) freelance English-Slovak translator (...)", "(...) audiodescriptor autónomo [anonymized]", "subtitler, audio describer and quality checker", "professor", "university lecturer + AVT practitioner", "assistant professor of translation", "audio description trainer & audio describer", "translator", "research assistant, translator, audio describer", "predoctoral researcher", "university lecturer", "AD editor, subtitler, project manager", "accessibility consultant", "translator for [anonymized] and freelance audiodescriber", "associate professor, audio describer, translator", "university assistant professor, freelance translator, bookseller".
 6. **Have you ever audio described a 360º video?** "Yes" (2=8.33%), "No" (22=91.67%).
 7. **How long have you been working in the field of AD?** "1 year" (4), "1.5 years", "2 years", "3 years" (2), "4 years (4)", "5 years", "6 years (2)", "9 years" (2), "10 years" (2), "12 years", "About 12 years", "14 years", "5 years (as creator of ADs), 10 years (as researcher of ADs)", "19 years".
 8. **How many hours of audio description have you produced in your professional life?** "Less than 50 hours" (13=54.17%), "51-150 hours" (3=12.5%), "151-300 hours" (3=12.5%), "More than 300 hours" (5=20.83%).
 9. **In what language or languages do you normally audio describe?** "English" (3), "German" (3), "Greek" (1), "Catalan and Spanish" (6), "Russian", "Russian, English", "Slovak" (2), "Spanish" (4), "Cantonese" (1), "Dutch" (2).
 10. **What software do you normally use when writing AD for films, TV programs or other videos?** "Apple Final Cut Pro X" (1), "Advantage Audio Description" (1), "company developed description software"(1), "Subtitle Workshop to time and compose scenario or Live Describe" (1), "None" (3), "MS Word" (4), "MS Word, Subtitle Workshop" (1), "Aegisub" (1), "Word, Adobe Premier, Format Factory y Google para las búsquedas" (1), "Softel ADePT" (1), "Subtitling software" (1), "I

do not do video AD" (1), "Aegisub, Microsoft Word" (1), "Text editor" (1), "Fingertext" (1), "Quantum (Wincaps)" (1), "vlc player, Word" (1), "Startit, Word" (1), "Subtitle Workshop and Microsof Word"(1).

- 11. Do you record your AD?** "Yes" (7=29.17%), "No" (13=54.17%), "Other" (4=16.67%) ("recording is mainly done in studios", "Yes but with professional narrators", "No entiendo la pregunta" (I don't understand the question), "we have a studio here and record our ADs in-house").
- 12. Please indicate your level of studies.** "Primary education" (0), "Secondary education" (0), "Further education" (2=8.33%), "University" (22=91.67%).
- 13. If you replied "Further education" or "University" in the previous question, please specify.**
 "PhD doctorate level" (1); "teacher's degree German and English" (1); "BS in Biology; MS in Science Journalism" (1); "Bachelor and Master's degree in Translation, ongoing PhD studies in AD in Greek" (1); "Translation, Journalism" (1); "Ph.D. in Russian from [anonymized]; Specialist's Degree in Philology and Education from [anonymized]" (1); "[anonymized] Linguistic University, [anonymized] Medical University" (1); "(...) Translation and interpreting" (1); "Licenciatura en Direcció Cinematogràfica" (1); "Bachelor of International Studies (Languages), Master of Arts (Translation and Interpreting) and Graduate Diploma of Publishing" (1); "PhD" (2), "MA and PhD in Translation and Interpreting" (1); "PhD in Translation" (1); "masters" (1); "MA in Professional Translation [anonymized]" (1); "Audiovisual Translation" (1), "Licenciatura en Filologia Catalana, Màster en Traducció Audiovisual, Màster en formació del professorat d'educació secundària" (1); "MA in Translation / PhD in Translation Studies" (1); "Translation studies" (1); "Licenciada en Humanitats [anonymized], Tècnica en Empreses i Activitats Turístiques" (1), "Master in English Literature & Master in Translation (English - French)" (1); "PhD in Translation Studies (with a thesis on AD)" (1); "PhD in Audio Description (1)".
- 14. If you have received specific training on audio description, please indicate it here.**
 "No" (1), "several on the job courses while being employed" (1), "on the job training" (1), "One course of AVT during my Master's Degree in Science of Translation (part of the course was AD)" (1), "AD seminar at [anonymised]" (1), "Two online courses in AD from [anonymised]" (1), "Training courses in [anonymised]" (1), "At university we had seminar of audiovisual translation where we covered the basics of the audio description creation" (1), "Un curso de dos meses en la empresa para la que trabajo" (1) (A two-month course at the company where I work), "yes - through my work" (1), "1 course at the MA level" (1), "[anonymised] basic AD training and training sessions with practitioners [anonymised]" (1), "One module on film AD within a course in AVT in the MA in Translation at [anonymised]" (1), "PhD in audio description, AD research" (1), "yes" (1), "Courses on audio description as part of MA program, workshop on live audio description" (1), "I have" (1), "Màster en traducció Audiovisual" (1), "several courses and workshops, training by and exchange with experienced colleagues" (1), "None" (1), "I had a course "Media Accessibility" at university and wrote a thesis on audio description" (1), "Workshop" (1), "Several specialisation courses" (1).
- 15. What devices do you use on a daily basis? Multiple replies are possible.** "TV" (13=54.17%), "PC" (17=70.83%), "Laptop" (21=87.5%), "Mobile phone" (22=91.67%), "Tablet" (10=41.67%), "HDM" (0), "Other" (1).

16. How often do you watch virtual reality content (for instance, 360° videos)?

	Never	Occasionally	At least once a month	At least once a week	Every day
In smartphone	15 (62.5%)	8 (33.33%)	1 (4.17%)		
On a tablet	20 (83.33%)	4 (16.67%)			
On a PC	17 (70.83%)	7 (29.17%)			
In smartphone plugged to HMD	22 (91.67%)	2 (8.33%)			
In HMD	22= (91.67%)	2 (8.33%)			

17. If you have never used virtual reality content such as 360° videos or only occasionally, please indicate why. Multiple answers are possible.

"Because I am not interested" (5=20.83%), "Because it is not accessible" (1=4.17%), "Because I have not had the chance to use it" (18=75%), Other (1=4.17%): "I am busy with other projects and don't have enough time for it. But I would love to use it more", no reply (2=8.33%).

18. Please state your level of agreement with the following statement: "I'm interested in Virtual Reality content (e.g. 360° videos)." "I strongly agree" (2=8.33%), "I agree" (10=41.67%), "Neither agree nor disagree" (9=37.5%), "I disagree" (3=12.5%), "I strongly disagree" (0).

19. Do you own any device to access Virtual Reality content?

"Yes" (2=8.33%), "No" (18=75%), "I don't know or I don't want to reply" (4=16.67%).

20. If you replied "yes" to the previous question, please specify which device(s).

"Buro VR glasses", "Mobile phones and iPads".

Summary:

24 participants completed the test (18 female – 75%, 5 male – 20.83%, 1 participant preferred not to reply to this question – 4.17%), with ages ranging 24-61. 7 participants (29.2%) completed the test in the previous version of the editor.

The main languages of the participants were Spanish (8), English (3), German (3) and Catalan (3). Their professions were mostly: researcher/professor, audio describer, PhD candidate, translator, project manager and accessibility consultant.

Only 2 participants (8.33%) taking part in the study audio described a 360° video before. When asked how long they have worked in the field of AD, participants provided varying replies: from 1 year to 19 years. More than half of participants produced less than 50 hours of AD in their professional life (13=54.17%) and 5 participants (20.83%) produced more than 300 hours of audio description. Participants provide AD in the following languages: Catalan and Spanish (6), English (4), Spanish (4), German (3), Russian (2), Slovak (2), Dutch (2) and Cantonese (1).

14 participants (58.33%) reported using software when producing AD. 10 participants use text editors when producing AD (41.67%).

7 participants (29.17%) record their ADs and 13 participants (54.17%) do not record it themselves (4 participants – 16.67% ask other professionals to record their ADs).

22 participants (91.67%) had university level education (mostly in Translation Studies) and 2 participants (8.33%) reported having further education. 22 participants (91.67%) received a specific training on AD.

The responses of participants confirm their technological potential: 13 participants (54.17%) use TV, 17 participants (70.83%) PC, 21 participants (87.5%) laptop, 22 participants (91.67%) mobile phone, 10 participants (41.67%) tablet. None of participants uses a head-mounted display on a daily basis.

When asked about how often they watch virtual reality content, most of participants (22=91.67%) reported never watching VR content is a smartphone plugged to HMD or in HMD. 9 participants (37.5%) consume VR content in smartphone at least once a month or occasionally. 4 participants (16.67%) consume VR content occasionally on a tablet and 7 on PC (29.17%).

When asked for reasons behind not using VR content or using it only occasionally, most of the participants (18=75%) replied that they have not had the chance to use it, 5 participants (20.83%) pointed to the lack of interest in such content and 1 participant (4.17%) pointed to lack of accessibility of such content.

When asked to state their level of agreement with the statement "I am interested in virtual reality content (such as 360° videos)", 2 participants (8.33%) strongly agree, 10 participants agree (41.67%), 9 participants neither agree or disagree (37.5%) and 3 participants disagree (12.5%).

Finally, when asked if they own any device to access VR content, only 2 participants (8.33%) provided an affirmative answer to this question, further specifying that they use Buro VR glasses and mobile phones/iPads.

3. System Usability Scale (SUS) results:

3.1. Scores (question by question)

1 – strongly disagree, 5 – strongly agree

SUS statements	1	2	3	4	5
1. I think that I would like to use this system frequently	1 (4.17%)	7 (29.17%)	5 (20.83%)	5 (20.83%)	6 (25%)
2. I found the system unnecessarily complex	6 (25%)	7 (29.17%)	5 (20.83%)	6 (25%)	0 (0%)
3. I thought the system was easy to use	4 (16.67%)	2 (8.33%)	3 (12.5%)	12 (50%)	3 (12.5%)
4. I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system	8 (33.33%)	4 (16.67%)	5 (20.83%)	5 (20.83%)	2 (8.33%)
5. I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	0 (0%)	5 (20.83%)	5 (20.83%)	9 (37.5%)	5 (20.83%)
6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	9 (37.5%)	7 (29.17%)	6 (25%)	2 (8.33%)	0 (0%)
7. I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly	1 (4.17%)	1 (4.17%)	8 (33.33%)	8 (33.33%)	6 (25%)
8. I found the system very cumbersome to use	7 (29.17%)	6 (25%)	4 (16.67%)	5 (20.83%)	2 (8.33%)
9. I felt very confident using the system	4 (16.67%)	7 (29.17%)	6 (25%)	5 (20.83%)	2 (8.33%)
10. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system	6 (25%)	4 (16.67%)	4 (16.67%)	6 (25%)	4 (16.67%)

3.2. Summary:

The SUS average score is **60.52**.

The graph below shows how the SUS scores associate with the percentile ranks and letter grades and the red line specifies where the ImAc AD editor is at this moment.

The letter grade is D, and the obtained score corresponds to the percentile rank: 15-34%.

4. Results from open preference questions:

4.1. Results question by question

11. What did you like most about the AD editor?

P12: I liked the fact that it was 360 video. Although I have no experience in audio describing 360 videos, I appreciate the level of innovation in creating this tool. However, it was a steep learning curve for me, particularly regarding the placing of the field of vision. I had never encountered this before in AD. I thought the segment list was a novel idea. However inputting all the time codes was rather time consuming because I had to revise them constantly.

P15 2019: sound curve of video provided.

P10 2019: The buttons for each function are well placed and easy to identify. Visually appealing. Error correction in Forced previous was surprisingly easy to use.

P1 2019: The program was really easy to use. I use PremierePro to integrate descriptions, so this was extremely simple compared to that. I think that for people that are familiar with subtitle software, learning AD editor will be a walk in the park, since the idea behind it is pretty much the same.

P13 2019: It's complete and accurate, and it allows writing and voice recording in an efficient way.

P5 2019: The interface was well thought out. I took me very little time to get accustomed to it.

P2 2019: I liked the speed thermometer. It helps to adjust the AD script.

P33 2019: I liked that I could record the AD right away. The possibility to change the angle is pretty cool as well.

P36 2019: Es sencillo de utilizar y muy práctico si quieres hacer el trabajo completo de escribir el guion y locutarlo. (It's easy to use and very practical if you want to complete the whole process of audio description; write the script and record it.)

P11 2019: The well-integrated 360 video within the software. It was easy to view all angles quickly.

P34 2019: It is easy to use.

P6 2019: I liked the extra options we normally do not have when creating AD - or we do have them, but the potential of this system could make things easier.

P37 2019: The layout of the user interface and the buttons included in it are simple and easy to understand.

P4 2019: The user interface: video in the centre, AD script/list on the right.

P24 2019: Being able to customise the shortcuts and choosing where the audio comes from.

P46 2019: I think it's quite intuitive to use which I liked very much. Also, the user interface is very clear.

P25 2019: The time-coding system.

P52 2019: Els comandaments bàsics i els shortcuts m'han semblat adequat. És senzill aprendre a fer servir les funcions bàsiques. (I found the basic commands and shortcuts adequate. It's easy to learn how to use the basic functions.)

P8 2019: The clear layout.

P49 2019: Possibility of precise timing.

P32 2019: The possibility of having all the devices in one for a piece of AD.

P31 2019: The blue and yellow colours made it easy to see how the recorded AD fit in the video. The part that shows you the overview of the script (upper right) is also very handy. And I liked being able to record myself and listen to how it fit in the video.

P53 2019: The view is adaptable to the actual screen.

P28 2019: The integration of every AD step.

12. What did you like less?

P12: It took me a while to get used to operating the system as I had no previous experience using it. Usually I work on Final Cut Pro, which I find more intuitive. You can see where the audio is overlaid which makes it easier (visually- speaking) to sync up the audio with the visuals. Also, I think it would be useful if you could automatically hear your audio description rather than having to force a preview constantly.

P15: text of AD segment not fully displayed and needed to be scrolled down for recording (but might be my not mastering the thing...).

P10: I'd like to be able to create and use audio cues as well as in times. Had trouble arranging so that I could see all functions on Laptop. Couldn't find where to adjust description field window and size of text. Can you set to dip audio for all or do you have to do each segment?

P1: I think it was an issue of my PC, but the toolbar that had to do with recording the description and inserting it was not complete, which lead me to omit adding recordings to the test. Also, it was very slow, but, again, this was probably a personalised issue and not a problem of the program itself.

P13: Too complex for me altogether!

P5: The way my computer responded to it. I got stuck at one point and had to refresh and redo some work.

P2: Everything was fine.

P33: I did not like the fact, that when I click on the timed segment, the program would not transfer me to that exact time in the video.

P36: Algunos botones los cambiaría de lugar porque los he pulsado varias veces sin querer. Tiene un fallo en el sonido porque cuando abres el editor de corte no aparece la duración del audio. No he entendido porqué me daba fallos en algunos bocadillos por la separación entre bocadillos. (I would change the location of some of the buttons because I pressed them accidentally several times. There's an error in the sound because when I open the editor, the duration of the audio does not appear. I did not understand why errors appear in certain segments due to the separation between AD segments.)

P11: I would like to hear where audio begins/ends to decide exactly when to time in and out. I couldn't hear the audio when jumping frame to frame, which was an inconvenience.

P34: Two technical issues complicated the AD process: 1. I had trouble recording my AD. Actually, I am not sure if my voice was recorded. The system indicated that it was but I could not hear it back. Therefore, I could not play with the sync functions of the program. 2. The video froze 5 times while preparing the AD.

P6: I did not have any particular difficulties, but also I think a video with more spoken sections would provide more opportunities to test some of the functions.

P37: The video started to fail. It would freeze and then disappear from the editor. I would close the editor and reopen the task, and the video would play again. After recording the AD segments and playing them to review them, if I closed the editor and reopened it (I had to do it when the video started to fail), the recordings would be gone. This is why there are no recordings. I tried several times, but there was no way I could save them properly. The forward and backwards video controls are not synchronized with the video, which makes navigating the video confusing and these functions not as useful as they could be.

P4: Commonly used buttons should be added: delete, replay, preview (see below).

P24: It takes a while to get used to it.

P46: I had some trouble with the audio recording. I think I would need more time to get familiar with it.

P25: The recording system.

P52: Hi ha diverses funcions que encara no he entès per què serveixen i m'ha donat la sensació que em creaven més confusió que facilitats. El programa se m'ha penjat diverses vegades i, tot i que la qualitat del vídeo no era massa bona, la reproducció no era òptima. (potser és el meu ordinador, ho hauria de provar amb un altre). En gravar, el fragment de veu es comprimia. (There are several functions that I have not yet understood and it has given me the feeling that they created me more confusion than helped. The program froze several times and, although the quality of the video was not too good, the reproduction was not optimal. (maybe it's my computer, I should try it with another one). When recording, one fragment was cut.)

P8: The recording function. Even after various tries I did not understand how I could record my AD and when I tried, I don't think it recorded because I couldn't hear my recording. Also, I wasn't sure if the 'auto save' function worked properly, because when I chose to describe a scene from a certain VoF angle and later returned to it, the angle didn't save automatically.

P49: The editor needs some time to get used to. Since this was my first attempt at using it I was struggling. Also, not everything was displayed correctly, several buttons were not displayed at all (for example Long Test and Short Test, so I could not check my recordings). I suppose once you have used it a few times and get the hang of it, it's fine.

P32: That sometimes it went off for no reason and part of what I did was lost.

P31: The shortcuts are a little complicated to get the hang of, but after a while it does get easier.

P53: The idle option.

P28: The fact that I didn't know the shortcuts (although you could personalise them) and the fact that I could do the final preview, it would work. It would show the image nor my voice. However it's promising.

13. What do you think could be improved, and how?

P12: I think the timeline could be more prominent. This would help with identifying the time codes. Also, a sounded count down to recording might be useful. Although after a while I got used to the colour system for recording.

P15: I have only used the mousepad, probably shortcuts make usage easier

P10: Adjustable text and window sizes. Audio cue field to go along with in times. ability to print a script

P1: I think it would be a good idea to have more space for the video itself and have the fields (e.g. the segment field on the right and the box of options below) as an "abbreviation", so you could open it when you need to. This would lead to a much "cleaner" interface.

P13: The blue dot, for location angle, was hard for me to control and find the exact place.

P5: Can't think of anything.

P2: What about adding automatic voices to voice the AD? It would be very useful for describing short videos (e.g. social media videos), thus making the process quicker and cheaper.

P33: The thing I mentioned above.

P36: Mejorar el tema de los errores (o quizás explicarlo más), solucionar el problema del sonido al que me he referido antes y cambiar algún botón de lugar. (Improve the issue of errors (or maybe explain it more), solve the problem of the sound that I referred to earlier and change the locations of some buttons.)

P11: An error message showed up for my timing and even when I had fixed it, the message didn't go away without refreshing the button. Having this automated would be helpful

P34: Here's a list of the potential improvements that I would make: 1. Fix video-freezing issues. 2. Introduce a new functionality to test mic and headphones when beginning to work on a new project. 3. The video box might be too small. I would include an option to visualize it full-screen or, even better, an option that allows the user to undock the video window. This way it could be made larger and it could be positioned wherever the user prefers. 4. Include an option that allows silencing the video while

recording the AD. I found it very distracting to receive audio input while trying to concentrate on reading and recording. 5. Create a pop-up window showing the whole text of the segment that needs to be read when the recording button is pressed. I was only able to see 8 words at a time and had to be scrolling down often while recording, which was both distracting and uncomfortable. 6. Add a function to download the recorded AD sound files once they are ready.

P6: I had problems playing the video in the system although I tried on more computers (probably the file was too big). The bigger problem from practical point of view then was that the slow/fast backward play functions did not work very well - not moving image. This function could always be very helpful, so maybe this could be improved in case of videos in higher quality.

P37: Please see the prior comment.

P4: 1. It would be nice if 'Delete audio', 'Replay audio' and 'Preview video' buttons for the clip I have just recorded can be added. 2. SEGMENT LIST box should allow editing. Sometime, it's easier to go through the script all at once for modifying timecode. I tried changing timecode in the box, but the timecode kept changing to something else automatically and I didn't know why. 3. To be frank, I tried but I couldn't preview the clip with AD I've recorded. In fact, I didn't even know if my AD has been recorded successfully.

P24: Maybe a short explicative video could have been used to show how it works.

P46: See below.

P25: The interface made it difficult to control the recording settings.

P52: Crec que és necessari més temps i més pràctica per familiaritzar-se amb una aplicació com aquesta i poder-ne extreure conclusions. No puc basar la meva opinió en un sol ús de l'aplicació i amb un sol format de producte. (I think it takes more time and more practice to get acquainted with an application like this and to be able to draw conclusions. I cannot base my opinion on a single use of the application and with one format of the product only.)

P8: I think the recording could be made a bit easier?

P49: I could only comment on this after having used the editor several times, as, for now, I don't know which problems occurred due to me not knowing the software and which are actual flaws of the software.

P32: A tutorial video would be great or a presential class.

P31: Maybe an easier way of navigating the 360° video. Using the arrows + Alt feels a bit slow.

P53: Maybe something more easy when moving the angles of the video. It could come back to the centred when you start a new AD segment.

P28: Everything should work perfectly and it doesn't right now.

14. Did you miss any functionality? If yes, which one?

P12: It would be good if you could separate the AD from the original audio. This would make it easier to clear up any glaring mistakes.

P15: seeing the whole AD segment text in one box without having to scroll.

P10: It would be great if you could navigate using the segment list, rather than just the up down arrows.

P1: As I stated above, I did not have access to the recording bar. I only had the record button, so I did not know how to stop the recording and pin it to the segment.

P13: No, on the contrary, I would say...

P5: No.

P2: No.

P33: I would appreciate if the text of my segments appear in the video. I know it is not program for subtitling, but it would help me to see if I set up right timing.

P36: yo utilizo la rueda del ratón para manejar el vídeo cuando quiero ir un poco más hacia delante o hacia atrás. (I use the mouse wheel to forward or go backward in the video.)

P11: I always use the number pad on my keyboard for playing and pausing. I found not having those shortcuts frustrating because of muscle memory but I think you can customise, so that would simply require some adjustments.

P34: Explained above.

P6: Not really.

P37: I thought that I could record several segments from different angles for the same video segment, and so this is what I did initially. However, when I proceeded to check the time codes, the editor identified these alternative ADs as errors, and so I picked one (the best) angle possible and deleted the others.

P4: See above.

P24: no.

P46: I'm not quite sure if I just didn't find it but I wanted to preview the whole video with audio description. In the preview mode, only the first AD-segment was played.

P25: A more user-friendly recording interface.

P52: El mateix que a la pregunta anterior. Cal rodar molt més una aplicació per extreure'n conclusions relacionades amb la funcionalitat i poder veure quines funcions cal millorar i com. És un procés. (The same as the previous question. I would need to use the application much more to draw my conclusions related to the functionality and to see what functions should be improved and how. It is a process.)

P8: See question 13.

P49: Again, I would have to have worked more with this software to be able to answer.

P32: Being able to add everything to see it together.

P31: not especially.

P53: No.

P28: The possibility of choose the type of narration speed in characters per second (not words per minute), as we usually do in Spain.

15. Is the feature of setting the angle for the AD easy to use? Explain why.

P12: I had real difficulty with this. I don't really think I successfully managed to use it correctly. Might need some training on how to use this in future.

P15: was puzzled by it, seemed easy, but then in a preview mode the angle shifted without my checking why.

P10: Yes, easy to maneuver the view, then pin with the description segment.

P1: I was afraid it would be confusing, but turns out that even for someone with no experience with 360 videos, like me, it was really easy and understandable.

P13: No (see answer 13). However, it seems to me the most important!

P5: Yes. Because it's quite intuitive.

P2: Yes.

P33: Yes, it is quite easy. Just hovering with my mouse and 2 clicks.

P36: Sí, es muy fácil de usar. El único problema que veo es que, si te equivocas, no sé como puedes comprobarlo. (Yes, it's very easy to use. The only problem I see is that, if you make a mistake, I do not know how you can check it.)

P11: I think it was, yes.

P34: Yes. However, it would be nice if the angle location could be automatically introduced by the program. For instance, the system could detect the field of view when the user begins writing the AD and fill the angle location box automatically.

P6: For me not very much, but this might be related to me not being very much used to 360 environments.

P37: Yes, because it is easy to set the desired angle in the video and then to associate it to the AD segment. It is a simple process.

P4: Okay

P24: yes.

P46: At the beginning, I had some trouble to set the angles because I didn't really understand the explanation in the user guide but that was probably my fault.

P25: Yes. You just have to choose the angle you want to use and you can easily "stamp" it.

P52: No, no he sabut fer-ho. (No, I did not know how to do it.)

P8: Choosing the angle is easy because you can just use the mouse, but saving it was more complicated.

P49: It is fairly easy to use.

P32: A little confusing to understand if it's the AD sound place or the image perspective.

P31: Yes, it's quite easy. You just move the field of view where it should be (easy to see with the blue dot) and then click the button.

P53: It was ok, but I would like it to come back to centre for every segment.

P28: Yes, no problem at all.

16. Were the preview modes useful for you? Explain why.

P12: Yes, but I found it frustrating that you couldn't edit in the preview mode. You would have to go back and it would slow the whole editing process down. It would be great if you could hear the AD with the video throughout not just in the preview mode.

P15: I always find previews useful, but did not quite delve into their differences.

P10: Yes - very easy and helpful. Had no trouble correcting problems with forced preview and then viewing final product with full preview.

P1: I did not use them, since I did not get to finish the test.

P13: Yes, I used the Forced preview and it worked. However, I didn't understand the difference between the Forced and the Free preview...

P5: I could check my work in its entirety.

P2: I am afraid I haven't used them.

P33: I liked that when I click on the segment at these modes, the program transfers me at the exact time of the segment in the video. I appreciate that I could hear the AD right away.

P36: Me parece muy útil para conocer los fallos. (I find them useful to check the errors.)

P11: I found them useful but without delving too deeply, I wasn't sure the differences were between each preview mode.

P34: Not in my case. Both showed an error with timing codes that I could not make sense of. Everything seemed OK but the preview kept saying that I had unordered TC values.

P6: I could not get to use them because the system still indicated some mistakes and did not allow me to do the preview at all. Pointing out the mistakes is a good thing, but maybe it still should allow describer to do the preview, maybe also to be able to better identify and understand the mistakes which were made. In my case, the problems were mainly related to TCS, but the practice in our region does not have

any rules about these (system/software wise). The software we use just offer the possibility of recording the script and the duration and length of parts of the script are judged by the describer. Therefore having this system checking my TCS based on subtitling rules (I suppose) surprised me. And the truth is I was lazy to redo them afterwards :) But still, it makes me wonder if this is a thing that should be checked by the software and not let you see the preview in case of AD. Therefore I also could not do much of final corrections and adjustments. Also I am used to do the recording in the end and it would help me if the text could be automatically viewed in the video. Maybe there is such a setting but I just did not realize...

P37: I could not preview, as my recordings were not saved.

P4: No. See answer 3 to Q13

P24: yes, to check the drafts.

P46: I thought the video would automatically change angle when watched in the forced preview mode but it didn't. I had to click on every segment to "see" the angle. Also, I thought all the recorded AD segments would be played, but it was only the first one. This would have been helpful.

P25: They did not make much of a difference.

P52: No els he sabut fer anar correctament. (I did not know how to use them correctly.)

P8: Yes, because they allowed me to try out my descriptions.

P49: Don't know any previous modes.

P32: I loved how easy it is to record and listen/see the images.

P31: Yes, the forced preview mode is very useful, because it allows you to see where the angle should be changed earlier or later, while also giving you an overview of the recorded AD. I didn't use the free preview much, because I preferred seeing how the angles + AD worked together.

P53: Yes, you can check the work.

P28: They sound useful, though they only worked the first time. After that, the system would show my voice nor the image.

17. Do you think it will take you longer to audio describe videos in 360°? Why?

P12: Yes, because you need to take in the whole scene and not just parts of it. For example, (private content) friends were in the back of the car playing instruments while she was in the front seat playing her ukulele. I didn't realise this at the beginning. It took me a few sittings to realise who (private content) was motioning to.

P15: yes, as one might have to search for the important content to be included in the description.

P10: Slightly longer because I think I would need to do the writing on the first pass, then assign the direction on the second review.

P1: Yes, because there are more than one images you'll have to describe. I think that it would take more time to read the film, since you have to navigate in it and find out of a 360 view what has to be described, then choose timecodes, set angles, insert descriptions.

P13: Not necessarily, as long as I get used to this editor. Maybe it could take slightly longer, but I guess this depends more on the difficulty of a video rather than whether it is in 360° or not.

P5: Just a little. Because I would have to set the angle.

P2: If such a software is used, the process of audio description won't take long time.

P33: Yes, it is one more thing I would need to pay attention to.

P36: No creo que tome más tiempo. (I do not think that it takes more time.)

P11: I think so, definitely because you need to familiarise yourself with many of the angles before deciding which is the most important scene to focus on. With practice though, it could become more streamlined I'm sure.

P34: Yes. In this case, for instance, I looked at the video several times from different angles to find out how many people were in the car in each scene, who they were, etc.

P6: In this moment yes, but I am not that familiar with immersive environments neither as a user or describer.

P37: If the goal is not to create alternative ADs for the same video segment from different angles, it will not take much longer. With practice, exploring the possible angles and choosing the most appropriate (from which more visual elements can be observed) will be done fast.

P4: Yes because I need to watch the video in different angles first before scripting.

P24: Yes, because all angles need to be checked.

P46: I don't know. As this was the first time I worked on a 360° video, it took me quite some time. But maybe this will change if I get used to it.

P25: Very likely. It takes longer to prioritise information in a 360° video.

P52: Depèn del vídeo i de com sigui l'AD. Si només describem allò que passa en un dels angles, pot portar més feina perquè s'ha de veure el mateix fragment diverses vegades per "escollir" allò que ens sembla més rellevant de tot el que està passant. Si es descriuen diversos fragments simultàniament, que s'activen segons on enfoqui l'espectador/oient, també, ja que s'ha de gravar per duplicat o triplicat. (It depends on the video and on the AD. If we only describe what happens in one of the angles, it can take more work because the same fragment has to be seen several times to "choose" what seems to be most relevant from everything that is happening. If several fragments are described simultaneously, they are activated according to where the spectator/listener looks and there are two or three simultaneous recordings.)

P8: Yes, because you have to check the full 360° content before you can determine what you want to describe.

P49: Yes. There is more to describe.

P32: It think it's going to be longer because, apart from the usual decisions, I will need to decide about where the AD comes in each case and also related to the perspective.

P31: It might take me longer in the beginning (getting used to the software and choosing the angles), but I think it might not take that much longer when you get the hang of the software. You would still 'lose' some time choosing the angles of course.

P53: Of course, you have to either decide the angle or ignore some angles...

P28: There's normally more information, at least you have to check all over.

18. Do you think 360° videos will impact your work as an audio describer?

P12: Certainly, I think if this content is the way forward audio description should be able to keep abreast of this through innovative technology such as this. I can imagine that this would be useful in VR gaming.

P15: no idea.

P10: Yes, we have had more come our way, and it is useful to consider how best to integrate the AD for this new format.

P1: I believe that a new video trend will create much more workload for the describers in the future. Practically, I think that describers will learn to deal with this different type of videos the same way they approach AD in other AV material, e.g. theater. Each medium has its own features and characteristics that call for a more personalised approach. Personally, in Greece we hardly have AD for regular filmic bodies, so I do not think that this trend will impact our work any time soon.

P13: Maybe, I don't know.

P5: I believe it's very likely.

P2: It will, because such videos become popular and we will have to catch up with the progress.

P33: I do not think it will be a very big impact. Maybe I will need to learn how to use new software and I will spend more time audio describing these types of videos, but apart from that I can not see any impact.

P36: Es algo que nunca me había planteado. (It has never crossed my mind.)

P11: At this point I don't think so but I'm sure as they become more common, probably. It's an adjustment to go from a fixed plane to having to orient yourself around a 360-degree space to decide what content is the most paramount in the descriptions.

P34: Since I don't work as an audio describer anymore, I don't think so.

P6: Not for now, at least not in our region.

P37: The effect of this type of video in the AD professional practice will depend on the increase in their production and demand. Professionals should discuss, if they have not done so yet, the extra amount of work involved in it and the appropriate rates.

P4: Yes.

P24: yes.

P46: I think 360° videos will gain popularity in the future and thus more and more 360° videos will be produced. So, maybe in the future it will impact my work.

P25: Not very much.

P52: No crec que ho facin en gran mesura. (I do not think they will have a great impact.)

P8: Not in the near future, since the offer is still so limited. But in the future, they might change my work. But since they require much more work (checking where the narrative elements are, trying to figure out the complete course of the narrative from the 360° content, etc.) producers and clients will have to realize that this is also going to be more expensive, although the amount of AD is going to stay exactly the same.

P49: Don't know.

P32: Absolutely, and it is not the future but the present already.

P31: At the moment no, because either I work live, or I write scripts that are recorded by someone else.

P53: It would if they were regularly consumed.

P28: Not now.

19. Other comments:

P12: Fascinating exercise and project. Would recommend training in this though so that audio describers can be able to learn the skills for this new technology and have the confidence to use it. I'd recommend organising a workshop on this either on its own or in parallel with an AV conference. I would certainly sign up!

P15: none

P10: I participated in the last test, and I found this version much easier to use. I was able to master most of the functions without going back and forth to the manual, whereas last time I was a bit confused. Very well marked and placement of most used buttons is excellent.

P1: I would only like to say thank you for creating something so helpful to describers. AD takes a long time, since it is a very complex procedure, so it would be amazing not to have to spend so much time on the technical side of it.

P13: I would definitely need some technical training and previous practice in order to be able to use this editor for my work.

P5: I really like the editor. I wasn't comfortable recording the AD myself. I usually write the script and professional voice actors record it.

P2: Thank you for this software. I am looking forward to using it in my work.

P33: It is very interesting, please, keep working on it. :) Good luck!

P36: No tengo claro cuál es la utilidad para las personas ciegas saber en qué ángulo está mirando en el vídeo. (I do not know why it is useful for blind people to know what angle they are watching in the video.)

P11: I think it's a very exciting era and having a tool that addresses 360-degree videos - which are here to stay - is very cool. I look forward to hearing more about how the tool progresses.

P34: This platform is being advertised as a tool to audio describe 360° videos. However, it could actually be used with traditional videos as well since most of its functionalities would be useful for audio describers working with regular audiovisual products.

P6: I also did the test for SDH and to me it seems the functions came bit more clear and useful. Some of the settings as well. But this might be very subjective, of course. Fingers crossed with everything and looking forward to hear more about ImAc :)

P4: Thank you for your work.

I think this IMAC project will help audio describers in the future if it's improved. The user interface is more professional and better than the current technologies/software (e.g. YouDescribe) I have tried.

P24. --

P46: This was very interesting to me, thank you!

P25: I did not see the AD segment audio controls the same way as they were shown in the manual. This made it more difficult to manage the recording.

P52: Faria falta més interacció amb l'editor per poder-ne ajustar els paràmetres a una funcionalitat òptima. (More interaction would be needed with the editor to be able to adjust the parameters optimally.)

P8: None.

P49: No other comments.

P32: I am very happy to be part of this research because it has given me the opportunity to think about how much 360° videos are changing the perception and the descriptions, together with all the possibilities it opens.

P53: No-

P28: As any new software you don't feel confident until you've used it a lot. I'd try to use it to be more familiar with it.

4.2. Summary

This section summarizes the most important comments, but it is recommendable to read carefully all the participants' comments included in the section above.

Responses obtained in the first question indicate that participants appreciated the most the following features of the editor: visual design and the layout of the user interface (P5, P10, P37, P4, P46, P8), the fact that the buttons for each function are well-placed and easy to identify (P10, P37, P52), being able to complete the whole process of producing AD in one single piece of software (P28, P31, P32, P33), being able to customise the shortcuts (P24, P52), the 'setting angle' option (P24, P33), sound wave (P15), speed thermometer (P2), the blue/yellow colours which help to see how the recorded AD fit in the video (P31).

Some participants accessed the usability of the editor positively in their comments, for example:

'The program was really easy to use' (P1);

'It's complete and accurate, and it allows writing and voice recording in an efficient way' (P13);

'Es sencillo de utilizar y muy práctico si quieres hacer el trabajo completo de escribir el guion y locutarlo (P36) (it is easy to use and very practical if you want to complete the whole process of writing the script and recording it);

'It is easy to use' (P34);

"I think it's quite intuitive to use which I liked very much" (P46).

Regarding the features/functions that the participants appreciated less and which could be improved, the following were mentioned in comments: the text of AD segments is not fully displayed and needed to be scrolled down for recording (P12, P15, P34); adjustable text and windows sizes (P10); when clicking on the timed segment, the video should jump to this exact time (P33). Other possible improvements could be related to: adding synthetic voice to voice the AD (P2), an option to visualise the video full screen (P34), improving the functions forward and go backward (P6, P37), an option to print the script (P10), a sounded count down (P12).

Regarding missing functionalities, participants would like to navigate using the segment list (P10) and the possibility to choose narration speed in 'characters per second' (not 'words per minute) (P28).

17 participants (70.83%) found the 'Setting angle' function easy to use.

Regarding the preview modes, 11 participants (45.83%) assessed the preview modes positively in their comments: (P5, P8, P10, P11, P13, P24, P31, P32, P33, P53, P36). Some participants did not use the preview options due to unordered TC values (P6, P34) or problems during recording: (P1, P4, P28, P37).

13 participants (54.17%) (P28, P53, P32, P49, P8, P25, P24, P4, P34, P12, P15, P1, P11) consider that it will take more time to describe 360° videos than standard videos because a describer needs to watch the whole scene when selecting content. 1 participant (P52) considers that it will depend of the video, but it will probably take more time to decide which visual elements are the most relevant. 3 participants (12.5%) (P5, P10, P33) consider that it will take slightly longer to write AD than in standard 2D because the angles need to be assigned after writing the scripts, but they also consider than it can be completed fast with practice. 4 participants (16.67%) (P13, P31, P6, P46) consider that it will not take necessarily longer to describe such videos once a describer is accustomed to the new video format and the software. 3 participants (12.5%) (P2, P36, P37) consider that the process of audio describing 360° videos will not take longer time than when providing AD to standard content.

8 participants (33.33%) (P32, P4, P24, P12, P10, P5, P2, P1) consider that 360° videos will impact their work as an audio describer, 4 participants (16.67%) (P15, P13, P36, P49) do not have an opinion on that question. 5 participants (20.83%) (P11, P37, P46, P8, P53) consider that such content can have impact on their professional life once such videos become more common. 6 participants (25%) (P33, P34, P6, P25, P52, P31, P28) does not consider that this new format will have an impact on their professional life.

The problems related to recording functions (P34, P37, P46, P8) or displaying the video (P32, P34, P37, P28, P32, P52) may be due to the PCs used by participants taking part in the test, or to the lack of experience in recording AD (only 13 participants –54.17% reported recording AD in their practice).

For some participants (P1, P10, P49) several buttons (such as long test or short test) were not displayed correctly which may be due to performing the test with lower screen resolution than necessary. Although one participant (P13) deemed the editor "too complex", this response may be related to the profile of this audio describer, who is 61 years old, does not use any software for producing AD and never audio described a 360° video before.

4 participants (P12, P24, P49, P52) reported that it took them a while to get used to the program as they had no previous experience of using it. Such factors as lack of familiarity with the new format of 360° videos and the new software, age (question 3 in the pre-questionnaire), usage of AD editors (question 10), not being accustomed to record AD (question 11), and the fact that most participants described the 360° video for the first time (question 6) may explain lower score in SUS questionnaire. This was expressed by several participants in the following comments:

'I would definitely need some technical training and previous practice in order to be able to use this editor for my work.' (P13);

I really like the editor. I wasn't comfortable recording the AD myself. I usually write the script and professional voice actors record it' (P5);

'As any new software you don't feel confident until you've used it a lot. I'd try to use it to be more familiar with it' (P28);

'A tutorial video would be great or a presential class' (P32).

ANNEX 15. METHODOLOGY FOR SIGN LANGUAGE EDITOR

1. What to test?

- SL Editor: https://imac.gpac-licensing.com/editor_test/videos.php
- Access: Each participant will have their own exclusive user and password. The test will be online, but RBB will invite Deaf participants to perform the test on their premises.

2. When?

Initial approach: editors and guides (ANGLA) ready end of May. Internal tests by broadcasters to check the tools are ready: first week of June. Then, professional tests if the tools are ready.

Final decision: the tests will take place during the third week of October. The onsite test (deaf participants) will take place on 25.10.2019, the online test (hearing participants) can start on 22.10.2019.

3. Methodology: overview

- **Research tools:** online questionnaires (Lamapoll).
- **Measures:** usability and preferences.
- **Participants:** the aim is to gather 30 participants to get statistically relevant data.
 - **Recruitment criterion:** SL interpreters who professionally interpret audiovisual content.
- **Language of the test:** English. The SL can be provided in any language. The participants will provide SL interpretation in German, based on the ST file in German.
- **Materials:** SL editor and 360° video (edit of "TOP" - crime scene investigation". English and German subtitle files will be available and loaded in the SL editor before the test.
- **Experimental protocol:** Participants will be asked to translate the video excerpt into their sign language. They will be given the choice to use English or German subtitles as support. Then, participants will be asked to report on the usability and preferences through an online questionnaire.
- **Reporting:** results will be included in a report created by RBB. This will be done exporting data from the Lamapoll.
- **The current methodology should be tested before the actual test.**

4. Methodology: experimental protocol

- **Test:** the test will be performed online, and users will be offered a short introduction. Support will be given by email. To facilitate participation of Deaf German users, the same experimental procedure will be followed at RBB premises, where a sign language interpreter will be available.

Section	Description	Where?
Section 1	Welcome and presentation of the ImAc project and the test.	E-mail/welcome
Section 2	Ethical clearance: information sheet and consent form to be approved by the participant.	Online: https://forms.gle/5fWTJ8GgyvJgRwAW9

Section	Description	Where?
Section 3	Demographic questionnaire.	Online: https://forms.gle/LqxjkurD17Lhctb39
Section 4	The following items will be introduced: - Video tutorial - The participants are asked to watch a video tutorial before the test. - Quick User Guide - The participants will be asked to read the Quick User Guide before performing the requested tasks. - Login information to access the SL editor. - Instructions sheet - Tasks to be performed.	- Video tutorial: English version: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1k97nCXb-2aaEEFQ4BFgntiV-576EeqB_/view?usp=sharing German version: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1GU_AchLSAmfGmXM06s2Ewapp6hEoEhXM/view?usp=sharing - Quick User Guide: https://drive.google.com/open?id=1jeU3p8ae-z6hzEN70CROQ23bt_B1ZelvB - Instructions sheet: https://drive.google.com/open?id=1gjVXWTjF5EMtGsGNBcwPKVIKZLqvpZdh
Section 5	SUS questionnaire & Preference questionnaire.	Online: https://forms.gle/t58hPHrpWBFKbKZYA
Section 6	Thank participants and follow up.	

- **Materials.** The video to be used will be an edit of “TOP” crime scene investigation. The duration of the video is 00:01:33. The video will be in low resolution (720s) to avoid overloading the server and make the interpreting task smoother.
- **Recruitment & User Code Assignment.**

Participants will be contacted by RBB. The test has been designed in German and English so that, if needed, professionals also from other countries can participate. Once a list of participants is available, hearing editors will be contacted by email. German Deaf interpreters will be invited to RBB to give them support, but the procedure will be exactly the same.

30 different users (P01-P30) will be created with the role of SL interpreter and each user will be assigned a video (same video for all users). The login information will be provided by e-mail to the users. Then, they will access the ImAc SL editor and they will only have access to one video in the Editor module.

This user name will be the user code that they will need to enter in the different questionnaires when requested.

- **Contact:**

To conduct the test, professional SL interpreters (who have previously agreed on participating) will be contacted by email.

Sample email:

Subject: Instructions for ImAc SL editor study

Dear participant,

Many thanks for participating in our study.

The aim of our study is to gather feedback from professional SL interpreters on the SL editor for 360° content that has been developed within the ImAc project. Your feedback will help us to ensure that this editing tool meets the needs of professional SL interpreters.

The aim of ImAc is to propose tested solutions on how access services can be integrated with immersive media. To learn more, visit: <http://www.imac-project.eu/>

The on-site test will take 2,5 **hours**.

Your login to the editor:

User code: RBB PXX

Password:

Please, follow these steps in order:

1. Give your informed consent: <https://forms.gle/5fWTJ8GgyvJgRwAW9>
2. Reply to the questions about yourself, by filling in this questionnaire: <https://forms.gle/LqxjkurD17Lhctb39>
3. Watch the video tutorial before doing the test to understand the project and how the tool works. You can find the English version here <https://drive.google.com/open?id=1y41hESKQAKgFzxXGagasP7LjWlvt-i8> and the German version (subtitled) here: <https://drive.google.com/open?id=19ZOpMMGBuHvZpKPHJhWnx2nPzzb7bKJD>
4. Read the user guide for more details on the usages of the SL editor: https://drive.google.com/open?id=1jeU3p8ae-z6hzEN70CROQ23bt_B1ZelvB
5. Read the test instructions and proceed with the test: <https://drive.google.com/open?id=1gjVXWTjF5EMtGsGNBcwPKVIKZLqvpZdh>
6. Fill in the questionnaire: <https://forms.gle/t58hPHrpWBFKbKZYA>
7. Confirm by e-mail that you have finished the test.

The test will be open from today until the (ADD DATE). You complete the test at any time during this time frame but, please, do it in **one session**.

If you have any questions, please contact me by e-mail. Please, confirm that you have received this e-mail.

All the best,

- **Tasks.** Participants are asked to perform a series of tasks individually on their own computers. The material will be available in the SL editor. They will need to access the SL editor and perform the tasks in the video that has been assigned to them.

The duration of the video is 1 minute 33 seconds, but the professionals will be requested to interpret from 00:04:01 to 01:27:24. The instructions will be provided in a document available here: <https://drive.google.com/open?id=1gjVXWTjF5EMtGsGNBcwPKVIKZLqvpZdh>

5. Questionnaires

Demographic questionnaire addressed to professional users (Annex 45)

SUS (Annex 43)

PREFERENCES

Now please reply to the following questions in your own words.

11. What did you like most about the SL editor?
12. What did you like less?
13. What do you think could be improved, and how?
14. Did you miss any functionality? If yes, which one?
15. Do you find the feature for setting the angle for the SL instances easy to use? Explain why.
16. Were the preview modes useful for you? Explain why.
17. Do you think it will take you longer to interpret videos in 360°? Why?
18. Do you think 360° videos will impact your work as a SL interpreter?
19. Other comments:

ANNEX 16. SIGN LANGUAGE EDITOR REPORT (RBB)

1. General information:

- **SL Editor tested:** https://imac.gpac-licensing.com/editor_teest/videos.php
- **Version tested:** 54
- **Partner responsible for tests:** RBB
- **Date:** 25th October 2019
- **Research tool:** online questionnaires (LamaPoll)
- **Link to online forms:**
 - Consent form: https://lamapoll.de/ImAc_Professional_Consent
 - Demographic questionnaire: https://lamapoll.de/ImAc_Professional_SL-Demographic_DE
 - Post-questionnaire: https://lamapoll.de/ImAc_Professional_SL-Feedback_DE
- **Measures:** usability and preferences
- **Participants:** 6
- **Methodology:**
<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1XAnpBLjGHOrmjEo9hGBg4OQqgIF8UYtubrKVAaEUg1o/edit>
- **User guide:** <https://drive.google.com/open?id=1363Cwyf9CjglEmfLH5rStrlseGI5Xx36>
- **Instructions for participants:**
<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1QLtwJY6DAYDjC34QsEW4X-lqqICOB7LriCJgRE9gQ6E/edit?usp=sharing>

2. Demographic profile of participants:

- Number of end users: 6
- Link to responses:
https://drive.google.com/open?id=1nNep_HeRTDWMaOCrQrRH7qSJA-ezspim-
- Demographics for users
 1. Sex: 3 "female", 3 "male", 0 "other", 0 "I prefer not to reply"
 2. Age: 31, 2x39, 40, 41, 61
 3. Main language: 4xGerman, 4x German sign language of which 2 replied to have German and German sign language as their main language
 4. Please, describe your current job: 1 x assistant of management, editor, 4 x sign language interpreter, 1 x research assistant
 5. Have you ever interpreted a 360° video? "Yes", 6 x "No".
 6. How long have you been working in the field of SL? 1x4 years, 3x9 years, 1x2 years, 1x six month
 7. How many hours of SL have you produced in your professional life? 3x "Less than 50 hours", 0 x "51-150 hours", 1x "151-300 hours", 2x "More than 300 hours".
 8. In what language or languages do you normally interpret? 6 x German Sign Language, 1x international sign, 1x gesture accompanying German sign language
 9. What software do you normally use when interpreting films, TV programs or other videos? 2 x didn't answer, 1x Adobe or Finalcut, 1 x App (Linon Media), 1x Finalcut and iMovie, 1x didn't now, other persons are setting everything up
 10. Please indicate your level of studies. 0 "Primary education", 1 x "Secondary education", 0 "Further education", 5x"University".
 11. If you replied "Further education" or "University" in the previous question, please specify. 1x bachelor degree from university of applied sciences, 2x degree as German sign language interpreter, 1x hearing technology and audiology, 1x further education
 12. If you have received specific training on sign language interpreting, please indicate it here. 1 x didn't reply, 1x certified by state German sign language interpreter University of Hamburg, 1x certified by state German sign language, 1 x sign language interpreter
 13. What devices do you use on a daily basis? Multiple replies are possible. 5x"TV", 4x"PC", 6x"Laptop", 5x"Mobile phone", 2x"Tablet", 0 xHDM", 1x"Other".
 14. How often do you watch virtual reality content (for instance, 360° videos)?

	Never	Occasionally	At least once a month	At least once a week	Every day
In smartphone	6	0	0	0	0
On a tablet	6	0	0	0	0
On a PC	5	1	0	0	0
In smartphone plugged to HMD	6	0	0	0	0
In HMD	6	0	0	0	0

15. If you have never used virtual reality content such as 360° videos or only occasionally, please indicate why. Multiple answers are possible. 0x“Because I am not interested”, 2x“Because it is not accessible”, 5x“Because I have not had the chance to use it”.
16. Please state your level of agreement with the following statement: “I’m interested in Virtual Reality content (e.g. 360° videos).”

“I strongly agree”,	“I agree”	“Neither agree nor disagree”	“I disagree”	“I strongly disagree”
2	2	2	0	0

17. Do you own any device to access Virtual Reality content? “Yes”, 3x“No”, 3x“I don’t know or I don’t want to reply”.
18. If you replied “yes” to the previous question, please specify which device(s). 0

3. System Usability Scale (SUS) results:

Link to the results from the postquestionnaire: <https://drive.google.com/drive/u/1/folders/1Q9a2Gp3nPQB04VYWI9dJwc8xgErvhhnS>

3.1. Scores (question by question)

- 1 – strongly disagree
5 – strongly agree

SUS statements	1	2	3	4	5
1. I think that I would like to use this system frequently	0 (0,00%)	0 (0,00%)	3 (50,00%)	2 (33,33%)	1 (16,67%)
2. I found the system unnecessarily complex	0 (0,00%)	1 (16,67%)	2 (33,33%)	2 (33,33%)	1 (16,67%)
3. I thought the system was easy to use	2 (33,33%)	2 (33,33%)	1 (16,67%)	1 (16,67%)	0 (0,00%)
4. I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system	0 (0,00%)	1 (16,67%)	1 (16,67%)	1 (16,67%)	50,00%
5. I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	0 (0,00%)	66,67%	2 (33,33%)	0 (0,00%)	0 (0,00%)
6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	0 (0,00%)	0 (0,00%)	4 (66,67%)	2 (33,33%)	0 (0,00%)
7. I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly	1 (16,67%)	0 (0,00%)	3 (50,00%)	1 (16,67%)	1 (16,67%)
8. I found the system very cumbersome to use	1 (16,67%)	0 (0,00%)	4 (66,67%)	0 (0,00%)	1 (16,67%)
9. I felt very confident using the system	2 (33,33%)	1 (16,67%)	3 (50,00%)	0 (0,00%)	0 (0,00%)
10. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system	0 (0,00%)	0 (0,00%)	2 (33,33%)	2 (33,33%)	2 (33,33%)

3.2. Summary:

The SUS average score is **39.17**.

The graph below shows how the SUS scores associate with the percentile ranks and letter grades⁵ and the red line specifies where the ImAc SL editor is at this moment.

The letter grade is **F**, and the obtained score corresponds to the percentile rank: **0-14**⁶.

The excel spreadsheet with scores calculations can be consulted here: <https://drive.google.com/open?id=1Ms-cB6qll0api4TvgVQHtgUmZ4lkhkhE>

4. Results from open preference questions:

4.1. Results question by question

What did you like most about the SL editor?

RBB SL OS 01: it is possible to do the sign language interpreting of 3D-videos including all important details by themselves

RBB SL OS 02: multiple elements

RBB SL OS 03: didn't know what to say

RBB SL OS 04: I can't answer useful as I was not able to use the editor

RBB SL OS 05: To set angle to German sign language interpreter to show position of speaker

RBB SL OS 06: clear structure of controls

What did you like less?

RBB SL OS 01: there are a lot of elements on the UI

RBB SL OS 02: subtitles

RBB SL OS 03: initially complex operation

RBB SL OS 04: I can't answer useful as I was not able to use the editor

RBB SL OS 05: it was not possible to shorten the sign language interpreter video segment, additionally there were some problems with the software

RBB SL OS 06: function (elements) partly overlaps e.g. play (of main video and sign language interpreter video). It is not clear which is the right one for certain functionalities.

⁵ Sauro, J. 2011. Measuring usability with the System Usability Scale (SUS). Retrieved from <http://www.measuringu.com/sus.php>

⁶ Sauro, J. & Lewis, J. R. 2016. *Quantifying the user experience: Practical statistics for user research*. Amsterdam: Morgan Kaufmann, p. 203-204.

What do you think could be improved, and how?

RBB SL OS 01: It would be better to open and close different UI section, editor must be more stable (e.g. with the preview function).

RBB SL OS 02: cut video segments in which the sign language interpreter doesn't interpret

RBB SL OS 03: mark TC-in in green and TC-out in red, you should be able to edit (cut) the timeline of the video

RBB SL OS 04: no answer

RBB SL OS 05: that you need to sign first, the signed videos can be shortened, and the segments can then be adjusted there.

RBB SL OS 06: design of the control elements (e.g. in the video field the playback button looks like the 'rotate right' button - maybe separate playback controls from controls to change the field of view, functionalities not yet optimal

Did you miss any functionality? If yes, which one?

RBB SL OS 01: no answer

RBB SL OS 02: switch on camera,too much text, rather more elements

RBB SL OS 03: see answer to previous question

RBB SL OS 04: no answer

RBB SL OS 05: Positioning where the sign language video can be placed in the image, the cutting function of the sign language video

RBB SL OS 06: cut/ specify segments of the interpreting video (e.g. if interpreting longer than segment, then interpreting window is black and you don't see how far you have to extend the segment).

Is the feature of setting the angle for the SL instances easy to use? Explain why.

RBB SL OS 01: no answer

RBB SL OS 02: at the beginning I didn't understand how it works, later on I did understand

RBB SL OS 03: Yes. It's actually sufficient, as it's offered.

RBB SL OS 04: no answer

RBB SL OS 05: no, there were problems with the system, and it was unclear to me how it could be handled after I recorded the videos. It works best step by step...

RBB SL OS 06: no, not self-explanatory. Only when you know is it simple.

Were the preview modes useful for you? Explain why.

RBB SL OS 01: it needs a good PC to watch the video in real time

RBB SL OS 02: no answer

RBB SL OS 03: Yes.

RBB SL OS 04: no answer

RBB SL OS 05: I unfortunately didn't use it

RBB SL OS 06: Yes. quality of control of angles and segments possible

Do you think it will take you longer to interpret videos in 360°? Why?

RBB SL OS 01: I think once you understand the editor, it's a very good tool for translating sign language well and quickly

RBB SL OS 02: no, it depends on the text (subtitles), whether it is simple or difficult to understand.....

RBB SL OS 03: Yes, because of the setting of the position. This will be a difficult process but should be solvable.

RBB SL OS 04: no answer

RBB SL OS 05: yes, interpreting much more depends on the position of the speaker, it needs to be checked several times and the video needs to be recorded again to adapt it

RBB SL OS 06: Yes, because of the angles and the orientation

Do you think 360° videos will impact your work as a SL interpreter?

RBB SL OS 01: I don't know, how much does the audience use VR media

RBB SL OS 02: It won't much effect my daily work as an interpreter. For the deaf, however, interpreting 360° videos are a further step towards participation.

RBB SL OS 03: Yes, because you have to make some changes in sign language communication (definition of position of speaker).

RBB SL OS 04: no

RBB SL OS 05: concerning language yes, you need to use other expressions without influencing the position (not easy)

RBB SL OS 06: not yet

Other comments

RBB SL OS 01: I think the usage of the tool is easy to learn. Both technically skilled persons and laymen could use it. I'm not technically skilled, it would take a little longer for me, but it's more or less a very easy to use tool.

RBB SL OS 02: nice to learn new things, I think it should be further developed

RBB SL OS 03: Thank you, that you invited me for the test.

RBB SL OS 04: I was an unsuitable person for the test, I'm very sorry.

RBB SL OS 05: no comments

RBB SL OS 06: The manual could be written more understandable and easier.

4.2. Summary

According to the users' comments, the workflow to produce sign language video segments for 360° videos with the ImAc editor tool is different from the production for usual video or TV content. It needs basic understanding in 360 video and its specific implications for working on it and consuming such media type. Also, enhanced skills are needed, in media recording and especially the preparation work in defining viewing angles, the segments and the position of the speakers, which all in all is a complex process.

Most of the users need some time to get used to the main functionalities of the editor tool and they appreciated that the tool can be quickly be learnt. Concerning the user interface some users would like to have a clearer structure of the controls and would like to close / open control sections, and a more stable behavior of the tool.

ANNEX 17. METHODOLOGY FOR SETTING THE ANGLE TEST

The aim of the focus group is to gather input from professional users on two methods that allow to set the subtitling angle: the ImAc subtitling editing tool, and a new approach developed by IRT in which the professional sets the angle with a controller pad while wearing virtual reality glasses.

1. Methodology overview

- **What?** Methods for setting the subtitling angle: subtitling editor versus virtual reality glasses.
- **How?** Focus group.
- **When?** January-February 2020.
- **Where?** IRT (Germany) and UAB (Barcelona). Room arranged so that all participants can see each other.
- **Participants:**
 - 5-6 professional subtitlers (the suggested number for this test is 5 but taking into account there are usually drop-outs, we advise to invite 6). It is important that they have not taken part in previous ImAc editor tests or workshops, so that they have the same knowledge about the tool.
 - 3 facilitators: facilitator 1 will be managing the focus group, keep the discussion on track, and make sure every participant is heard; facilitator 2 will be taking notes and drafting the conclusions; facilitator 3 will be providing technical support. When taking notes, please remember to anonymise the data and refer to participants with the same code consistently (P1, P2, P3, P4, P5).
- **Language of the test:** materials in English, focus group development in the native language of the participants.
- **Materials:** one computer per participant with access to subtitling editor, subtitling guide, one clip in English with already created subtitles. Consent form and demographic questionnaire ready. VR glasses "Oculus Quest" including right hand controller and positioning app (that is tested) installed. Printed guide for VR positioning tool.
- **Content used:** Interview scene from the clip "I, Philip" (time: 6:40 - 8:20); duration: 1:40 minutes
- **Reporting:** results will be included by the partner responsible (IRT in Germany, UAB in Barcelona) in a report template created by UAB. UAB will integrate the results in the final deliverable. Original signed ethical consent forms will need to be given to UAB.

2. Methodology: steps

- Opening: welcome. Briefly present the ImAc project, the aim of the focus group and its development. Ask participants to read and sign the consent form, and fill in demographic questionnaire. Length: 15 minutes.
 - Consent form (also available in other languages):
<https://docs.google.com/document/d/13gNsg6N8kAzsETgWwWtHQ2Ub1eOhHHcsA2Xlzw5ynSc/edit>
 - Demographic questionnaire:
<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSdojGSu3XLQhd8WE6aAN0kAo4FdHrxn0PM-q3aIS2CenG2w/viewform>
- Subtitling editing tool presentation, focusing on setting the angle only. Length: 7 minutes.
- Presentation of alternative method for setting the angle: 8 minutes.
- Participants are then allowed to freely set the angle with the subtitling editing tool on a computer. At the same time they are shown on a one-to-one basis the alternative method and are allowed to test it for 2 minutes each. Length: 5 minutes x 5 = 25 (+ buffer). 30 minutes.
- Focus group discussion: focus group discussion about the two methods, following the suggested list of questions below. Length: 30 minutes.
- Wrap up: summarise focus group conclusions, read them aloud and have them approved by the focus group. Length: 15 minutes.

Total: 1h 50 minutes. Participants should be invited to a 2-hour focus group in case it needs to be expanded.

Suggested list of questions for the focus group discussion:

- What do you like best about the two solutions?
- What do you like less about the two solutions?
- How do you think they could be improved?
- Which one would you prefer to use in your professional life, and why?
- Apart from setting the speaker position, are there other subtitle parameter you could imagine to perform in the HMD app?
- Do you have any suggestions?

Demographic questionnaire addressed to professional users (Annex 45)

ANNEX 18. REPORT ON SETTING THE ANGLE TEST (IRT)

1. General information:

- Partner responsible: IRT
- Place and date: 11.02.2020, IRT (Munich, Germany)

2. Demographic of the focus group participants:

- Sex: 4 male, 2 female
- Age: 25, 27, 31, 37, 42, 43
- Main language: German
- Current job: Subtitler (4), TV editor (1), Editor subtitling (1)
- Have you ever subtitled a 360° video? Yes (0), No (6).
- For how long have you been working in the field of subtitling? In years: 1.5, 8, 10, 12, 12
- How many hours of subtitling have you produced in your professional life? Less than 50 (0), 51-150 (1), 151-300 (0), More than 300 (5)
- In what language or languages do you normally subtitle? German
- What software do you normally use when subtitling films, tv or other videos? FAB subtitler
- Please indicate your level of studies: primary education (0), secondary education (0), further education (0), university (6).
- If you replied Further education or University, please specify. Translation (2), PhD Linguistics (1), Master of Arts (1), Economy (1), Sociology (1)
- If you have received specific training on subtitling, please indicate it here. Internship (1), no answer (5)
- What devices do you use on a daily basis? TV(4), PC(5), Laptop(5), Mobile Phone(4), Tablet(2), HMD(0), Other
- How often do you watch VR content (for instance, 360° videos)?

	Never	Occasionally	At least once a month	At least once a week	Every day
In smartphone	4	2	-	-	-
On a tablet	5	1	-	-	-
On a PC	5	1	-	-	-
In smartphone plugged to HMD	5	1	-	-	-
In HMD	5	1	-	-	-

- If you have never used VR content such as 360° videos or only occasionally, please indicate why. Multiple answers are possible. Because I am not interested (2). Because it is not accessible (2). Because I have not had the chance to use it (2). Other (0).
- Please state your level of agreement with the following statement: "I am interested in VR content (such as 360° videos). I strongly agree (0), I agree (2), neither agree nor disagree (3), disagree (1), I strongly disagree (0).
- Do you own any device to access VR content? Yes (1), no (4), I don't know or I don't want to reply (1).
- If you replied "yes" to the previous question, please specify which device(s). VR glasses

3. Summary of discussion:

a) What do they like best about the two solutions?

Note: during the discussion, both positive and negative aspects were mentioned when comparing the two methods, a strict separation of the two questions was not kept.

P2 – How can we judge these two very different methods? The web editor works different from the FAB environment we are used to. Our comments may be different when compared to FAB where I work a lot faster.

P5 – Yes, learning the shortcuts will take a while. Maybe it doesn't make sense at this stage to compare using the mouse and web editor vs the glasses.

P2 – Both tools are not fully developed. A lot depends on how they would evolve.

(Facilitator: Since the VR prototype is not an editor tool but only tests the authoring method for one property, we understand that a direct comparison is difficult. Please try to comment on the aspects you liked or disliked about the two methods)

P6 – The web version is intuitive and quick. When this method would be fully developed, authoring would probably also be fast enough for professional purposes.

P5 – Regarding the workflow, I assume setting the position in the web environment is faster. But the glasses have potential.

P4 – I think just editing the position with the glasses is faster.

P3/2 – Yes, agree.

P6 – How long could you work with the glasses, a whole day?

P5 – If I would write the subtitle and set the times, then I could set the position in the same process. If I would have to put on and off the glasses that takes time. An additional step in the workflow will slow it down.

All – Yes, setting the position in a separate step will take time.

P2 – Wearing the glasses more than two hours will be difficult. But editing a short clip is not a problem. In general, I assume one would need more breaks. How long are 360° videos typically?

(Facilitator: Often, 360° clips are shorter than for instance a typical movie.)

P2 – I think I could work with the glasses maybe 10-15 minute before a break.

P6 – But it might also be something we would get used to. It is not that different from staring at a PC screen the whole day. If the technology gets better, it might be possible to work a reasonable amount of time with it.

P1 – Wearing glasses might also help to avoid disturbance from outside. Maybe we just need to get used to it. The best way might be a mixture with AR.

P1 – The orientation in the glasses is definitely better.

All – Agree.

P1 – You can easily look around in 360. It would be great if you could write on a real keyboard while wearing the glasses.

b) What do they like less about the two solutions?

P1 – Setting the position in the web takes three steps. It would be better to just click on the woman here. Why do I need to enable a subtitle for setting the speaker position?

P2 – The web interface is too difficult, too many steps to unlock some functionality.

(Facilitator: If the speaker cannot be located, for instance in case of an off-speaker or the robot in the demo content, the position must not be set.)

P1 – Ok, that's true, but three steps, it's too cumbersome. I could click on a person while pressing a button. Or If I could change the default behaviour, maybe even depending on the speaker color.

All – Yes, agree. Using a key+click would probably be fine.

P5 – We work a lot with double speed. The sound is processed so that it's not pitched, it just runs faster. That is an important feature missing in both apps.

All – Yes, we mostly work in double speed.

P2 – Jumping within the timeline using a shortcut with 3 keys is not good. Using the joystick in the VR app is a lot better.

P5 – Yes that's true.

c) How they could be improved?

All – improvements were already mentioned in the discussion (above)

P5 – In the VR app I was trying to set the position while the person was speaking. But it didn't work, it paused at the end of the subtitle anyway. It would be better if I could set the position while the video is running and only pause when I didn't set the position in time.

d) Which one do they prefer in the professional life, and why?

All – Currently only the web editor could be used, because the VR app cannot edit subtitles (text, timing, colors).

e) Apart from setting the speaker position, are there other subtitle parameters you could imagine performing in the HMD app?

All – Ideas for that were already mentioned in the discussion.

P6 – Setting the timecode would be difficult, because when the speaker starts talking, it is too late to set the TC IN cue.

P1 – It would be difficult to work frame accurate with glasses, but long scenes without cuts would work, e.g. live shows or non-premium content.

P2 – When the keyboard would be visible within the glasses, it may be possible to combine both methods.

P1 – Yes, like a head-up display that is visible in the video.

P5 – Can a keyboard be connected to the glasses, that would be nice. But you need to put it on your lap, because you need to be able to turn around.

P2 – Or maybe it would be possible to see my desktop environment when I need it through the glasses. Is that possible?

(Facilitator: Do you mean like a virtual representation of the desktop?)

P2 – Yes, but with a real keyboard.

P5 – In this example that we saw there weren't any cuts. Setting subtitle frame accurate wouldn't be so important there. In combination with an audio envelope curve shown in the glasses as a timeline, one could estimate when a speaker becomes active.

All – Yes, that might work. But it depends on the content. For some, we have to work frame accurate.

f) Do you have any suggestions?

P5 – Maybe in the future it would be possible to use speech recognition to automatically create and time subtitles.

P5 – Is it possible to use AI, like face detection to suggest the speaker position automatically and even follow the speaker if the person is moving? Maybe the speaker could even be identified by his voice.

P1 – For a quality control, the VR application only might be sufficient. I mean when text and timing is already done, maybe automatically. If you could mark a subtitle whenever you find an issue and edit it later on the PC that would work.

(Facilitator: Would you require a VR preview for the quality control of produced subtitles? What if the subtitles would have different line breaks in VR and TV?)

P1 – VR preview not necessarily needed, no.

P7 – Maybe more experience is needed how important VR preview is.

P1 – Different line breaks in VR and TV is a no-go in my opinion.

All – Agree!

P1 – For a quality control step, I think the glasses are better.

P5 – I Agree. In any case I would need editing functions in the glasses.

P6 – I think it would be good to set error marker in the glasses and fix them afterwards on a PC.

4. Approved conclusions by participants:

The participants found that the two authoring methods cannot be compared directly and additionally neither of them compare to the applications that they use. Thus, the question “which one would you prefer” cannot be answered directly.

Both methods have their advantages:

- The VR glasses are easy to use and pointing at a speaker is very intuitive.
- In the tested web editor implementation, the positioning requires three steps: 1. Mark subtitle as a ‘positioned subtitle’; 2. Drag & drop video such that speaker is positioned in the center; 3. Click button to set the angle. – That is a very time-consuming process and a lot slower than the solution with VR glasses
- POTENTIAL ADVANTAGE: The web editor as well as other classic environments have the advantage that setting the speaker’s position might be ‘just another mouse click’ during the authoring process. (setting speaker location should be easier to integrate in authoring process).
- The orientation within the 360° scene is better in the VR glasses application.
- The VR controller is more comfortable to use than the mouse.
- The participants would prefer VR glasses for a quality check process (i.e. when only minor corrections need to be done).

At the current stage, participants could only use the web editor in their professional live, because the VR glasses application lacks relevant features for subtitle authoring.

The participants liked a lot the idea to use VR glasses for editing 360° content.

The participants discussed about possibilities to combine a classic subtitle editor with VR glasses when it comes to 360° content and suggested various approaches:

- One idea would be to project assistive items like a keyboard or even the entire desktop environment into the VR glasses. This could be temporary (e.g. desktop environment for a specific authoring step) or permanent (e.g. a virtual keyboard for a visual feedback of a real keyboard that is attached as input device to the VR glasses application)
- The participants could imagine that a non-premium production or a production where most of the text is already available (e.g. via speech to text algorithms) could be realized using VR glasses only (assuming that additional features are available in the VR application). In that case, a virtual object showing the audio envelope curve would be very helpful to set timing for subtitles.

- Another idea is to add a marker functionality in the VR app that allows to mark subtitles with issues that cannot be fixed directly in the app. The issue could be handled afterwards on a PC.

The participants made concrete suggestions for improvements:

- One of the main missing features in both applications is the possibility to play the video with higher speed (e.g. 2x real time).
- In the web editor, the speaker position should be set via a simple mouse click, maybe pressing a keyboard button simultaneously (e.g. ctrl+click → set position; click → grab&drag video for rotation)
- In the VR app, the user should be able to position the subtitle while the video is running (in order to avoid auto-pause and accelerate the process).

The participants assume that it would be more difficult to realize exact timing of subtitles within VR glasses application. Accurate timing is important for them in higher quality productions.

The participants assume that one would get used to use VR glasses for a limited amount of time (e.g. time for authoring a 360° video of about 10 minutes length), but more “recovering time” is needed than for a PC screen. One participant could imagine that one would get used to even longer usage times with VR glasses.

ANNEX 19. REPORT ON SETTING THE ANGLE TEST (UAB)

1. General information:

- Partner responsible: UAB
- Place and date: Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, 27.02.2020

2. Demographic of the focus group participants:

- Sex: 2 male, 2 female
- Age: 28, 28, 29, 27
- Main language: Spanish/Catalan, Spanish/Catalan, Catalan, Catalan
- Current job: Associate Lecturer, Audiovisual translator, Audiovisual Translator and teacher, Audiovisual translator and subtitler
- Have you ever subtitled a 360° video? Yes (0), No (4).
- For how long have you been working in the field of subtitling? 5 years, 5 years, 5 years, 3.5 years.
- How many hours of subtitling have you produced in your professional life? Less than 50 (1), 51-150 (1), 151-300 (0), More than 300 (2)
- In what language or languages do you normally subtitle? Spanish and Catalan, Spanish and Catalan, Spanish and Catalan, Spanish.
- What software do you normally use when subtitling films, TV or other videos? Aegisub, StartIT, Subtitle Workshop, Subtitle Edit
- Please indicate your level of studies: primary education (0), secondary education (0), further education (0), university (4).
- If you replied Further education or University, please specify. PhD, Master in Audiovisual Translation (UAB) and Master in Investigation in Translation and Interpreting (UJI), Master's in Audiovisual Translation, Bachelor Degree in Translation and Interpreting
- If you have received specific training on subtitling, please indicate it here. Master in Translation Studies, The Master mentioned above, Subtitling for the Hard-of-Hearing & Subtitling courses, Some subjects in my Bachelor Degree in Translation and Interpreting
- What devices do you use on a daily basis? TV(2), PC(4), Laptop(4), Mobile Phone(4), Tablet(2), HMD(0), Other
- How often do you watch VR content (for instance, 360° videos)?

	Never	Occasionally	At least once a month	At least once a week	Every day
In smartphone	3	1	-	-	-
On a tablet	4	-	-	-	-
On a PC	3	1	-	-	-
In smartphone plugged to HMD	4	-	-	-	-
In HMD	4	-	-	-	-

- If you have never used VR content such as 360° videos or only occasionally, please indicate why. Multiple answers are possible. Because I am not interested (1). Because it is not accessible (1). Because I have not had the chance to use it (2). Other (0).
- Please state your level of agreement with the following statement: "I am interested in VR content (such as 360° videos). I strongly agree (3), I agree (0), neither agree nor disagree (1), disagree (0), I strongly disagree (0).
- Do you own any device to access VR content? Yes (0), no (4), I don't know or I don't want to reply (0).
- If you replied "yes" to the previous question, please specify which device(s).

3. Summary of discussion:

a) What do you like best about the two solutions?

P2- The VR glasses app is much faster as long as you have seen the video before. Actually, I would watch a scene, anticipate who will speak and then you can set the angle very fast. Difficulty: if I don't have prior knowledge of who will speak and when, as I have no previous knowledge of who has spoken, you get lost and it's slower. What you see helps you as long as you have a previous reference of who's speaking. If you could not watch the scene in advance, it would go well as well because it is very fast to set the angle. But if there're more than two or three people, it would be more complex. Sometimes you click the button so fast because it's so quick and you set the wrong angle. It would be great to correct those mistakes immediately (for example, with one controller you set the angle and with the other you undo the action in case of mistakes).

P1- same as above

P3- same as above

P4- if you can first create subtitles with a traditional editor, it helps a lot more because you have already seen it. And then, set the angle with the new method [VR glasses], which is much faster [than the editor].

P3- with the editor, you have to look for the speaker manually navigating the video and with the controllers [in the VR app] you just click it and that's it. Subtitlers, we are used to traditional subtitling editors on a computer. But once you have all the subtitles created, then you can set the angle in the VR glasses and that's better.

P1- if there are three people, you lose time looking at who's talking and undoing, etc.

About the online editor:

P1- I had a little trouble moving the camera with the online editor. The program has the opposite direction (to go up, you have to go down). It's hard to get the direction of the mouse.

P3- it's a matter of getting used to it. Every company has a different subtitle editor, so you have to learn it. It's the first time. It's not bad. Setting the angle with the editor is a bit harder than with the VR glasses, but it's good.

P2- It is very significant that none of us have ever worn VR glasses before and we've all gone much faster [to set the angle with the VR app]. It also depends on whether the timing and segmentation is done or not before you go to the VR glasses. I don't know how this would apply to virtual reality. It helps me a lot, for example, the abbreviations and shortcuts because we are very used to it and it's quick. Maybe we could use shortcuts also with the VR glasses? For example, some features such as reading speed or segmentation.

P3- And timing.

P4- two very different jobs: translator/subtitler and another profile (which can be someone different). This other profile would set the angle only with the VR glasses.

P2- Maybe, during the review phase, one can set the angles. During the final review.

P4- But think about a film that lasts 1 hour and a half. You have to watch the film, then timecode the subtitles, translate the content and then set the angles again. Maybe it's a little bit too much.

P2- Maybe you could also do it with the VR glasses: you have all the subtitles in the editor because I can see where I am in the video and then set the ones that you're interested in. Or slip it by scenes.

P2- Maybe you could do some parts of the film where there are only two speakers with the VR glasses because it's quicker, and for those parts with more speakers you do it in the editor. You would have the possibility to choose depending on your preferences.

P3- Maybe you see in the video that you have made a mistake. It would be good to have the possibility to directly go to that specific part.

P4- It was not working very well with Mac. When you guys clicked on a subtitle, did the editor took you to that part of the video?

All: No.

P4- When you're reviewing, when you click on a subtitle, the editor should take you to the speaker that you have set the angle.

(facilitator: this is the forced preview, which you haven't tried).

P4- If there is no such option, it should take you to where you have set the angle.

P2- another option that may be done in the long run would be to have an option to always set the same angle for a given character if it is a static scene where the speakers are not moving. And it would be useful to be able to filter all the scenes with that specific angle, so that you can easily spot if you have made a mistake. There are X number of subtitles with this specific angle, and you can review them all in a row.

(facilitator: there is an option to copy an angle from one subtitle to another)

P2- especially for static scenes, the subtitles could be filtered by angles and you could do the review much faster.

P2- it's very good to do it that way if it's static enough. However, in an action movie, it wouldn't be as useful.

(facilitator: fast action movies/scenes have not been tested yet).

b) What do you like less about the two solutions?

P1- reverse navigation (reverse mouse) in the editor, but it is a matter of practice.

P2- I didn't realize about the reverse navigation in the editor.

P4- When you click a subtitle to see if it's OK, it should take you to the speaker, to see if the angle that you have set is correct.

Proposal: by double clicking on the subtitle, the editor should take you to the specific moment in the video and previously set angle.

P2- sometimes the editor crashed, it was bumpy, maybe because of the connection.

P2- Also, you had to select subtitle by subtitle so that they would appear on the video. I would prefer an option that you can select either if you want to check subtitle after subtitle or another option to review everything.

P3- During the review, the subtitle didn't move in the video. It happened the same to me.

P2- when you press play, you only get the subtitles you're editing.

(this can be done in the forced preview and free preview, which has not been taken into account)

ALL: Oh, okay.

P4- It would be very helpful to have on the subtitle list some kind of mark that indicated if the subtitle has an assigned angle or not.

P3- there is one thing on the left on the editor but having the indicator on the list would be great.

c) How do you think they could be improved?

All – We've already mentioned some improvements.

P3- I have worked very well. The editor is very good and very intuitive

P2- I agree.

P3- I was very excited with the VR glasses on, maybe because we associate it with a videogame. We would have to get more used to it.

P2- This is very good because this technology has many applications. There would be many possibilities if you could edit the subtitles during the review with the VR glasses. For example, you could mark the subtitles and then they would appear on the editor. So the VR app and the editor would be connected, maybe.

P3- The two options (editor/VR) complement each other.

P2- You could mark subtitles with potential problems during the review phase with the VR glasses, and then you go to the editor to those specific subtitles and edit them.

P3- This would save a lot of time.

d) Which one would you prefer to use in your professional life, and why?

They all agree that the perfect solution would be a combination of both.

P3- Like testers in video games, we would need to check the subtitles in the VR glasses to see if there are any issues. Therefore, we would need to use the VR glasses to test if the subtitles can be properly seen. To see what the viewers would see.

P2- If the VR glasses would be intuitive and fast, maybe we could work directly there.

P4- Do you mean subtitling from the VR glasses?

P2- Yes, using technology like Dragon, voice recognition.

P2- It sounds very futuristic, but I would haven't imagined what we have tested today!

P4 – Maybe we could use voice commands to tell the VR app: Start subtitle, end subtitle, etc. And then we could post-edit the subtitles with a more traditional keyboard.

P1- Yes, it's faster with voice commands.

(facilitator: you are used to use templates in your professional life, so maybe you could directly provide a spoken translation that would be written on the VR screen)

They all agree.

e) Apart from setting the speaker position, are there other subtitle parameters you could imagine performing in the HMD app?

We have already mentioned several:

--review the time codes

--mark the subtitles with errors so that then they can be reviewed with the editor

P3- Undo

P2-Have an autosave option.

P2-For SDH creation, this system is even better, more intuitive, because you create your subtitles based on the dubbed audio.

P3-We should also include options to indicate the non-speech information. Maybe you could somehow mark the device where the sound is coming from.

P1- Yes, mark the source of the sound.

P2-Another application, but maybe this is more personal (because I do many creative subtitles), is for karaoke subtitles. For example, that I could use the pointer to follow and fill the subtitle as the song progresses (karaoke effect), it could work.

P2- For SDH, it would be nice to have a drop-down menu and that with X number of clicks you could assign a certain colour for each character.

P4-In Instagram Stories, there's this technology that you can indicate the app "who is whom" in a video and assign text tags, and if the person moves in the video, then the text tag moves with the person. Maybe, this same technology could be used for this subtitling VR app. So you would mark a speaker and then the technology would recognize the face or the clothes or the colours (I don't know exactly how it works), and then the angle would be set automatically (for example, this character that I have marked moves and the angle for the subtitle moves as the character moves, and we could also say that that specific character is blue (for the subtitle) and it would also be automatically set for the rest of the video).

P3-We could have different styles for the different characters

P2- Or for example, with the voice the editor could know "who is whom" and then the colours for identification would be set automatically. And then you have the option to change those automatically set colours when necessary.

P2- Then, the subtitlers could focus on the linguistic aspects of subtitles and the technical part (time codes, segmentation, setting the angle) would be automatized.

P2- We have the general settings (for example, go to the next scene, frames per second, etc.) with voice interaction.

Discussion regarding how they could do all the subtitling work with the VR app.

P2- Not sure if we could spend 8 hours working with the VR glasses, we should try.

ALL-For now, we would go with a combination of editor and VR glasses. In the future, we will see.

P2- It would be great to have someone who knows about telecommunications because we could talk to them and tell them what we need, and they could tell us if that's feasible or not. We need to check all these ideas with the engineers.

f) Do you have any suggestions?

We have already made many suggestions!

P4- They need to polish the editor for MAC users.

P2-Would there be any problem with the VR glasses OS and the editor? Can they be connected? It would be great that the VR glasses and the editor were connected so that the changes that are done in one are seen in the other.

(facilitator: the VR glasses have their own OS, but I guess they could be connected with an online server)

P2- One last possibility: so the subtitler and the simulator (or the person checking the VR glasses) would work at the same time. The simulator would say OK there's a mistake in subtitle X, and then the subtitler would fix that in the editor, and the simulator could see the change in real time.

4. Approved conclusions by participants:

Participants are very satisfied with the tools. The editor is intuitive, and the VR glasses open many possibilities. Even though none of the participants had used the editor or had ever used VR glasses before, in general they didn't find any issues. They believe that it is great that the subtitler is able to choose which option they prefer (editor/VR glasses). The group believes that a good solution would be to create the subtitles in a traditional editor and set the angle with the VR glasses app.

It is suggested that there could even be two different professional profiles (subtitler and simulator), and that they could work simultaneously: if the simulator detects an error in a subtitle with the VR glasses, the subtitler corrects it in real time in the editor.

They also express that ideally in the future the subtitler could focus on linguistic and creative issues.

They propose some suggestions for improving the VR glasses app:

- that one controller is used to set the angle and the other is used to undo the previous action or includes other shortcuts for other actions;
- that, in static fragments, certain scenes can be filtered, and the same angle can always be set for certain characters, so that these fragments can be directly reviewed;
- that you can mark the subtitles with the VR controller in the VR app and that this mark goes to the subtitle list (to know what to check, etc.) in the editor, and you can go directly to the marked subtitles from the editor and review them;
- to include an "auto-safe mode".

They propose some improvements for the editor:

- reverse navigation (reverse mouse) has led to some problems, but they admit it's a matter of practice;
- make sure that the editor works properly with Mac and doesn't get bumpy (in one case it did, maybe because of the connection);
- possibility of reviewing subtitle by subtitle and possibility of reviewing everything;
- that, when you click on a subtitle, it takes you to the specific character and angle;
- that, in static fragments, certain scenes can be filtered out and the same angle can always be established for certain characters, so that these fragments can be reviewed directly;
- that subtitles where the angle is not marked are automatically identified.

Participants consider the possibilities opened up by the VR glasses:

- Inclusion of speech recognition technology so that they can subtitle with the VR glasses and then post-edit with the editor. This opens up many possibilities in captioning for the deaf, where one could automate the inclusion of non-speech information, the inclusion of colors (perhaps with a different number of clicks), or the automatic marking of the source of the sound (for example, a telephone).
- Possibility that the pointer automatically resets the music in creative karaoke-type subtitles (possibility to fill in the subtitle for karaoke)
- Ability to apply Instagram technology that allows you to select a person, assign a text tag, and make the text follow the person if they move in the video. The program could recognize the characters and automatically assign the angle, with the option to uncheck it when desired.

The participants note that it is necessary to see how the technology of virtual reality evolves and to evaluate the viability of doing a whole working day with VR glasses. In any case, it is a question of habit and of seeing the evolution of the technology.

Overall, they consider that the collaboration between developers and professional subtitlers is necessary, so that the tools respond to the needs of subtitlers.

ANNEX 20. METHODOLOGY FOR SUBTITLING PILOT PHASE 1: PLAYER INTERFACE AND PRESENTATION MODES

1. What will be tested? (summary)

The purpose of the pilots (German pilot and Spanish pilot) is to introduce a panel of users of subtitling services to the developed solution for consuming fully accessible 360° contents and, at the same time, to gather qualitative measurements and feedback about the user experience when consuming those services in an immersive environment.

PART 1. USER INTERFACE.

Access to ImAc player and access services for usability and user preferences on the version available on September 19th. The traditional menu will be tested for subtitles.

PART 2. PRESENTATION MODES.

Arrow vs radar for immersion, user preferences and usability.

2. When?

- German Pilot: 15/10-19/10
- Spanish Pilot: 01/10-19/10

3. Who?

- German pilot: RBB
- Spanish pilot: CCMA

4. Stimuli

- Desconcert (CCMA) - Video 2 - Desconcert 1
 - Test: Part 1. User interface.
 - Description: musical concerts.
 - Genre: musical
 - Original language: Catalan
 - Duration: around 5/6 minutes (although, no need to watch it completely).
 - Link:
 - http://84.88.32.46/imacpilot1_part2/
 - All modes and services to be tested (subtitles) must be implemented.
- I, Philip (RBB)
 - Test: Part 2. Presentation modes.
 - Description: 23 years after Philip K. Dick's death, in 2005, David Hanson, a young engineer in robotics, revealed his first android with human form, "Phil". "I, Philip" immerses you in the memories of what could be the last love affair of the writer. But aren't these memories the fruit of the imagination of an android which learned, little by little, how to become a human?
 - Genre: Sci-Fi, drama
 - Original language: English
 - Duration: 12:26 (until the credits), to be split in two clips
 - Link: http://84.88.32.46/imacpilot1_part1/
 - Access services needed:
 - GER subtitles with arrow
 - GER subtitles with radar
 - CAT subtitles with arrow
 - CAT subtitles with radar

IDENTIFICATION CODES FOR THE STIMULI

- A1: I, Philip part 1 - with arrow
- A2: I, Philip part 1 - with radar
- B1: I, Philip part 2 - with arrow
- B2: I, Philip part 2 - with radar

5. Methodology: overview

- **Aim:** gather data from users about 1) their experience with the ImAc Player and access services, replying to questions regarding usability and preferences; 2) their experience with different presentation modes, replying to questions regarding immersion, preferences and usability.
- **Experimental protocol:** users will be asked to perform certain tasks while they watch different stimuli, and then report on the usability, preferences and immersion through digital questionnaires with closed and open questions.
- **Research tools:** digital questionnaires (Google Forms). The questionnaires will be digital in order to facilitate data processing. The questionnaires will be translated into German/Catalan/any other needed language by each partner responsible for the pilot (CCMA and RBB). SUS and IPQ translations will be provided by UAB.
- **Measures:** usability, preferences and presence (immersion).
- **Participants:** we should aim at 30 participants with hearing loss. Minimum per partner: 15. Recruitment will be done via associations/organisation and/or at partners' discretion.
- **Duration:** approx. 90 minutes.
- **Language of the test:** German/Catalan (depending on the territory).
- **Materials:** HMD, tablet, computer and clips.
- **Facilitators:** two facilitators will be needed. One facilitator will be the leader (welcoming participants, explaining the project, explaining the test) and another facilitator will assist the sessions (by providing the digital questionnaires and helping filling them in, providing technical assistance with the different devices, etc.).
- **Test accessibility:** adequate measures must be taken by tests organisers (CCMA, RBB) so that communication with persons with hearing loss is fluent.
- **Reporting:** results will be included in a report created by each partner. This will be done exporting data from the Google Form. A template will be provided. All feedback must be translated into English by the partners responsible for the pilots (RBB and CCMA).
- **Testing the methodology by RBB and CCMA:** please make sure you test the experimental protocol below before the actual pilot action. If the methodology needs to be improved based on this previous test, let UAB know. It is important that both RBB and CCMA use the same methodology.
- Please make sure that you have all materials and ethical forms ready before the test.

6. Methodology: experimental protocol

PLANNING

Introduction	15 min
Part 1 - User interface	25 min
Part 2 - Presentation modes	40 min
Farewell and thanks	5 min
Buffer time	5 min
Total	90 min

WORKFLOW

LATIN SQUARE FOR ALL PARTICIPANTS (if more than 15, repeat from the beginning).

Each participant will follow a different order to avoid the order of presentation affecting the results.

Participant	User interface	User interface	Presentation modes	Presentation modes
RBB1/CCMA1	Task 1 (HMD)	Task 2 (tablet)	A1	B2
RBB2/CCMA2	Task 2 (tablet)	Task 1 (HMD)	A2	B1
RBB3/CCMA3	Task 1 (HMD)	Task 2 (tablet)	A1	B2
RBB4/CCMA4	Task 2 (tablet)	Task 1 (HMD)	A2	B1
RBB5/CCMA5	Task 1 (HMD)	Task 2 (tablet)	A1	B2
RBB6/CCMA6	Task 2 (tablet)	Task 1 (HMD)	A2	B1
RBB7/CCMA7	Task 1 (HMD)	Task 2 (tablet)	A1	B2
RBB8/CCMA8	Task 2 (tablet)	Task 1 (HMD)	A2	B1
RBB9/CCMA9	Task 1 (HMD)	Task 2 (tablet)	A1	B2
RBB10/CCMA10	Task 2 (tablet)	Task 1 (HMD)	A2	B1
RBB11/CCMA11	Task 1 (HMD)	Task 2 (tablet)	A1	B2
RBB12/CCMA12	Task 2 (tablet)	Task 1 (HMD)	A2	B1
RBB13/CCMA13	Task 1 (HMD)	Task 2 (tablet)	A1	B2
RBB14/CCMA14	Task 2 (tablet)	Task 1 (HMD)	A2	B1
RBB15/CCMA15	Task 1 (HMD)	Task 2 (tablet)	A1	B2

INTRODUCTION (15 min)

Who?	What?	How long?
Lead facilitator	Welcome the participants, who will individually attend the test. Please assign a participant code when they arrive, so that they can enter that code in each online questionnaire. Codes should be as follows: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- For RBB: RRB1, RBB2, RBB3, RBB4, etc.- For CCMA: CCMA1, CCMA2, CCMA3, CCMA4, etc.	1 min
Lead facilitator	Explain the project (if unknown to the participant), the aim of the test and the procedure .	5 min
Assistant facilitator	Provide the participant with the consent form for ethical clearance. You can find the last version here: https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1X5Nj9KxkpFVvwEuKfK6XVgz0VFUSzUOS Provide signed original consent forms to UAB (next meeting or send by snail mail).	3 min
Assistant facilitator	Provide the participant with the digital demographic questionnaire to be filled in (access to a computer/laptop will be needed): <ul style="list-style-type: none">• ENG: https://goo.gl/forms/o2B4dLHhk2M3Bxrk1• GER: https://goo.gl/forms/E5el8lqtvt8qOtlg1• CAT: https://goo.gl/forms/KSfjmnPIGXJOW8j32	6 min

In the following sections, the different parts of the test will be explained, including tasks and measures.

PART 1. USER INTERFACE (25 min)

- **Measures:** usability and preferences
- **Participants:** minimum of 15 per partner
- **Materials:**
 - **Devices:** the test will be performed with an HMD and a tablet.
 - **Player:**
 - Link to the player: http://84.88.32.46/imacpilot1_part2/
 - Only traditional menu will be tested.
 - **Clip:** Desconcert with subtitles.
- **Room:** make sure the atmosphere is comfortable for the participants, with an adequate room arrangement.

Previous to task (5 min)

The lead facilitator will roughly explain to the users how the ImAc Player/Menu works (you have to look down to open the menu, you have to press that button from the controller to select the different options, you will find options to play/pause, volume control, accessibility services, etc.) and advise during the test if necessary.

IMPORTANT: Please randomise the order in which you perform TASK 1 and 2, to avoid a learning effect that could have a negative impact on the results. Please follow the Latin Square provided above.

TASK 1 - Test with HMD. Duration: 10 min.

Participants will receive the **instructions on paper** before starting the test and the lead facilitator will clarify any doubt before starting the test.

1. After some seconds, please pause the video.
2. Please, play the video again.
3. Please change the volume.
4. Please, open the menu and activate subtitles in your own language.
5. Please, randomly personalise subtitles, using all available options.

After TASK 1 is finished, participants will be asked by the assistant lead to fill in the following questionnaire (SUS):

ENG: <https://goo.gl/forms/6fRIEAZYMtmGJNpw1>

GER: <https://goo.gl/forms/gohpTNTToOIXpF99f1>

CAT: <https://goo.gl/forms/lwMD97vzoCwvxdXg1>

TASK 2 - Test with tablet. Duration: 10 min.

Participants will receive the **instructions on paper** before starting the test and the lead facilitator will clarify any doubt before starting the test.

1. After some seconds, please pause the video.
2. Please, play the video again.
3. Please, change the volume.
4. Please, open the menu and activate subtitles in your own language.
5. Please, randomly personalise subtitles, using all available options.

After TASK 2 is finished, participants will be asked by the assistant lead to fill in the following questionnaire (SUS):

ENG: <https://goo.gl/forms/pGWN0BWkQmj6G1sx1>

GER: <https://goo.gl/forms/e38pxNnJal2tqGOD3>

CAT: <https://goo.gl/forms/1CUUmNwUthIFaG522>

After both tasks, participants will be asked to reply open questions about both systems.

ENG: <https://goo.gl/forms/pYpQWzh4mlPrmiyj1>

GER: <https://goo.gl/forms/Tka8apnoJl9fRqoE2>

CAT: <https://goo.gl/forms/L7BHkx51ZH6k4yuZ2>

PART 2. PRESENTATION MODES (40 min)

- **Measures:** preferences, presence and usability
- **Participants:** minimum of 15 per partner
- **Materials:**
 - **Device:** the test will be performed with an HMD.
 - **Player:**
 - Link to the player: http://84.88.32.46/imacpilot1_part1/
 - **Stimuli:** Two comparable clips (A, B) with 2 conditions (1, 2) for each presentation mode tested, so that participants can watch both conditions in different but comparable clips to avoid a learning effect.
 - I, Philip:
 - 2 comparable clips, 6-7 min each. Both parts contain different speakers in different positions to test the presentation mode (guiding to speaker).
- **Room:** make sure the atmosphere is comfortable for the participants, with an adequate room arrangement

Introduction (5 min)

The lead facilitator will explain the aim of this part: testing two different presentation modes to guide the user to the speaker. There will be two presentation modes: an arrow integrated in the subtitle that will indicate where to look for the speaker and radar which will always be present. After watching the clips, they will be asked to answer a set of questions.

The order of presentation of the stimuli will be balanced across participants. A latin square protocol in which the presentation mode is tested with two conditions (arrows versus radar).

Order of presentation (please repeat up to the number of agreed participants): Please follow the Latin Square provided above.

TASK 3. ARROW vs RADAR. Duration: 40 min.

- 1) The participants will be asked to watch the two randomised clips. Please follow the order specified in the Latin Square provided above.
- 2) The participant will have to watch 2 clips (A, B) with the randomised variables (1) arrow and 2) radar). After watching **each clip**, participants will have to reply to the IPQ (presence) questionnaire to gather feedback about immersion. Please don't share technicalities with participants, only tell them they will be asked to reply some questions in the following forms:
 - a) Arrow - I, Philip:
ENG: <https://goo.gl/forms/SZZvMDW4bqfrvhhT2>
GER: <https://goo.gl/forms/92v9knhVak84pirM2>
CAT: <https://goo.gl/forms/eAsV2viwGjg52Oa63>
 - b) Radar - I, Philip:
ENG: <https://goo.gl/forms/2RRqBiADarz8UZfo2>
GER: <https://goo.gl/forms/Jt0hRAxvWyWAgMOV2>
CAT: <https://goo.gl/forms/DcOXVOB0q3egAmfL2>

IMPORTANT: Please make sure that you provide the correct IPQ questionnaire to participants depending on the order in which they are visualising the clips.

- 3) After watching **the two clips**, the participants will be asked to provide feedback about preferences and usability:
ENG: <https://goo.gl/forms/aHmBrORo9Ew6Lr6T2>
GER: <https://goo.gl/forms/AgDluDiaO0lja9yS2>
CAT: <https://goo.gl/forms/MQo142qG3zXwKAa23>

FAREWELL AND THANKS to participants (1 min)

REPORTING (after the tests)

Upload your report one week after the tests under Google Drive.

It must follow the template available in the same folder.

7. Questionnaires

Questionnaires will be provided to the participants using online forms, but is included below for reference.

Demographic questionnaire for home users – Version 1 (annex 46)

SUS (Annex 43)

Open questions after SUS:

More questions...

Please, reply the open questions with your own words. The aim of these questions is to gather feedback to improve the ImAc Player and the access to the accessibility services.

11. Did you use the setting "Indicator"? Yes/No
12. What was the function of "Indicator"?
13. Did you use the setting "Area"? Yes/No
14. What was the function of "Area"?
15. Which other subtitle personalisation options did you use?
16. What did you like most about the ImAc Player?
17. What did you like less about the ImAc Player?
18. What do you think could be improved, and how?
19. Did you miss any options? If yes, can you tell us which?
20. Other comments:

IPQ (Immersion) (Annex 44)

PREFERENCES & USABILITY

Please provide some feedback about your experience with the clips and the subtitles

Please reply to the questions with your own words.

1. When directions need to be indicated, what system do you prefer?
 - a) Arrows
 - b) Radar
2. Please, explain why you prefer the above indicated option.
3. Please explain why you did not choose the other option in question 1).
4. What do you think could be improved, and how?
5. Would you implement another system to guide you to the user?
6. How easy was it to identify who was speaking on the clip with the arrow system?
 - 1- Very difficult
 - 5- Very easy
7. How easy was it to identify who was speaking on the clip with the radar system?
 - 1- Very difficult
 - 5- Very easy
8. Do you think you will be able to enjoy 360° videos with these type of subtitles? Explain your answer.

ANNEX 21. SUBTITLING PILOT PHASE 1 REPORT: PLAYER INTERFACE AND PRESENTATION MODES (CCMA)

1. General information

- Partner responsible: CCMA
- Place and date: 01.10.2018 / 17-19.10.2018
- Access service(s) discussed: subtitling.

2. Demographic questionnaire

- Number of end users: 13
- Demographics for users.

1.	Sex	7 male 6 female 0 other 0 prefer not to reply
2.	Age	19, 25, 27, 30, 31, 35, 44, 50 (x2), 55, 62, 63, 66
3.	Main language of the participants:	Spanish (3x), Catalan (x6), Catalan & Sign Language in Catalan (x1) Sign Language in Catalan (x3)
4.	Level of studies	0 no studies 2 primary education 3 secondary education 2 further education 6 university
5.	I define myself as a..."	8 deaf person 5 hearing impaired person 0 deaf-blind person
6.	Age in which your disability began	8 From birth 1 0-4 2 5-12 0 13-20 1 21-40 0 41-60 1 More than 60
7.	What technology do you use on a daily basis? You can select more than one.	12 TV 5 PC 10 Laptop 13 Mobile Phone 6 Tablet 1 Head Mounted Display (HMD) 1 other: Sennheiser magnetic induction loop, video game console

8. How often do you watch virtual reality content (for instance, 360° videos)?

	Never	Occasion-ally	At least once a month	At least once a week	Every day
In smartphone	2	11			
On a tablet	9	4			
On a PC	11	2			
In smartphone plugged to HMD	9	2	2		
In HMD	8	3	2		

9.	If you have never used virtual reality content such as 360° videos or only occasionally, please indicate why. Multiple answers are possible.	<p>0 Because I am not interested</p> <p>3 Because it is not accessible</p> <p>6 Because I have not had the chance to use it</p> <p>4 Other reasons:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● I've seen ● Yes, I've seen ● Yes, I've seen VR contents ● Because no...
10.	Please state your level of agreement with the following statement: "I am interested in virtual reality content (such as 360° videos)."	<p>5 Strongly agree</p> <p>8 Agree</p> <p>0 Neither agree nor disagree</p> <p>0 Disagree</p> <p>0 Strongly disagree</p>
11.	Do you own any device to access virtual reality content?	<p>4 Yes</p> <p>8 No</p> <p>1 I don't know or I don't want to repl</p>
12.	If you replied "yes" to the previous question, please specify which device(s).	<p>1 HMD</p> <p>1 PlaystationVR & Oculus Gear</p> <p>1 Smartphone & Tablet</p> <p>1 Cardboard</p>

13. Do you like watching the following types of content on television or online?

	I like it very much	I like it	Neither like it nor dislike it	I don't like it	I don't like it at all
News	10	2	1		
Fiction (series, films)	8	4	1		
Talk shows	6	4	2	1	
Documentaries	6	5	2		
Sports	2	5	3	2	1
Cartoons	0	2	7	3	1

14. When subtitling is available, do you activate it for the following type of content?

	Always	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
News	10	1		2
Fiction (series, films)	11		2	
Talk shows	8	2	1	2
Documentaries	11		1	1
Sports	7	1	4	1
Cartoons	8	2	2	1

15.	If it is available and you do not activate it, please select the reasons why.	<p>3 Because the interface is not accessible</p> <p>2 Because I don't want subtitling in all the content, only in certain types of content</p> <p>8 Other reasons:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4x I always activate • 1x I always activate. If there are no subtitles, then I don't watch content • 1x because in sports subtitle is over statistics and results, and hides important information • 1x because interface not accessible or because I want subtitles for language learning • 1x Because they don't subtitle Spanish film
16.	How many hours a day do you watch subtitled content?	<p>1 None</p> <p>1 Less than 1 hour</p> <p>2 1-2 hours</p> <p>5 2-3 hours</p> <p>2 3-4 hours</p> <p>2 4 hours or more</p>

17.	What do you use subtitles for?	<p>2 They help me understand</p> <p>4 They are my only way to have access to the dialogue</p> <p>1 I use them for language learning</p> <p>6 Other:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 3x For the first two reasons (help me understand & my only way to have access to the dialogue) ● 1x They help me to understand & Language Learning ● 1x They are my only way to have access to dialogue & Language Learning ● 1x They help me understand (but I prefer to use Sign Language to keep more attention to video)
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Summary

7 male and 6 female users aged between 19 and 66 took part in the tests. 6 users indicated Catalan as mother tongue, 3 indicated Spanish, 3 indicated sign language in Catalan and 1 user indicated both Catalan & sign language also in Catalan. Most of the users had at least a secondary education or higher. 8 testers saw themselves as deaf and 5 as hearing impaired. For almost all users, the impairment began at birth or below the age of 4, while for only 1 user the impairment started over 60 years.

The technical device used most often on a daily basis was a smartphone (13 users), followed by TV (12 users) and laptop (10 users), while tablet had less use (6 users) and PC was the least often used (5 users). HMD was used by only one user, while another user indicated the use of a Sennheiser magnetic induction loop & a video game console. Nine of the users had never watched VR content before, mostly because they were not interested or had not had the chance to. When directly asked if they were interested in VR content, all of the testers agreed. The majority of the users did not own a device to access VR content, while 4 users owned some kind of device (cardboard, HMD, tablet, smartphone, Oculus Gear or Playstation game console).

In terms of content preferences, the majority of the testers liked news, fiction, talk shows and documentaries, while some also liked sports, and cartoons. Almost all of them used subtitles for all types of content. There was an even distribution between 0 and more than 4 hours among the testes in terms of how many hours a day they consume subtitled content and the majority of the testers used ST because it is their only way of accessing the dialogues.

3. PART 1 - Task 1 & 2

a) SUS – HMD

SUS statements	1	2	3	4	5
1. I think that I would like to use this system frequently		1	2	5	5
2. I found the system unnecessarily complex	3	6	3	1	
3. I thought the system was easy to use		4	1	4	4
4. I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system	5	3	3	1	1
5. I found the various functions in this system were well integrated		3	1	5	4
6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	3	2	7	1	
7. I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly		3	3	5	2
8. I found the system very cumbersome to use	3	5	2	3	
9. I felt very confident using the system		1	2	5	5
10. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system	6	2	2	2	1

The SUS average score is **68.8 (above average, 68 or more is considered above average).**

The graph below shows how the SUS scores associate with the percentile ranks and letter grades and the red line specifies where the ImAc Player - HMD is at this moment.

The letter grade is C and our score corresponds to the percentile rank: 46-50%.

b) SUS – Tablet

SUS statements	1	2	3	4	5
1. I think that I would like to use this system frequently	1	1	3	3	5
2. I found the system unnecessarily complex	8	4	1		
3. I thought the system was easy to use				4	9
4. I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system	9	3		1	
5. I found the various functions in this system were well integrated			2	5	6
6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	7	3	2	1	
7. I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly			2	5	6
8. I found the system very cumbersome to use	6	4	1	2	
9. I felt very confident using the system				5	8
10. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system	8		3	2	

The SUS average score is **82.9** (**above average**, 68 or more is considered above average).

The graph below shows how the SUS scores associate with the percentile ranks and letter grades and the red line specifies where the ImAc Player - Tablet is at this moment.

The letter grade is A and our score corresponds to the percentile rank: 90-95%.

c) Open questions – General

11.	Did you use the setting “Indicator”?	13 Yes
12.	What was the function of “Indicator”?	<p>CCMA1: It serves to indicate where the voice comes from.</p> <p>CCMA2: Arrow indicating where the sound is subtitled</p> <p>CCMA3: To set the type of indicator, which allows signaling from where the sound comes from.</p> <p>CCMA4: To know who is talking.</p> <p>CCMA5: Position the transmitter.</p> <p>CCMA6: Put the voices of the actors in the direction they are, regardless of where you look with the glasses.</p> <p>CCMA7: From where you talk / Position from where the voice speaks or comes out</p> <p>CCMA8: Shows an arrow where the person speaking speaks. There are more options.</p> <p>CCMA9: To know who speaks</p> <p>CCMA10: The cursor to activate the functions</p> <p>CCMA11: To know and where to speak, who to speak.</p> <p>CCMA12: Serve the digital button by clicking on the configuration tools.</p> <p>CCMA13: Arrow, radar and without, I think very well, but the radar should separate a bit more with the subtitles</p>
13.	Did you use the setting “Area”?	9 Yes / 4 No
14.	What was the function of “Area”?	<p>CCMA1: No.</p> <p>CCMA2: In a circular space the position that we are seeing is presented and where the emission of the sound is located.</p> <p>CCMA3: Allows you to configure the visual field of the menu and subtitles.</p> <p>CCMA4: To be more focused.</p> <p>CCMA5: To focus more on the view in a certain area of the screen.</p> <p>CCMA6: Place the directions of the menus in a visual field, regardless of where you look with the glasses.</p> <p>CCMA7: Adjust the viewing of subtitles within your field of vision.</p> <p>CCMA8: Shows a point inside or outside the viewing area. The tip is the person speaking.</p> <p>CCMA9: -</p> <p>CCMA10: I have not appreciated the difference.</p> <p>CCMA11: ---</p> <p>CCMA12: Place the subtitles in the area of the screen that can be viewed more comfortably.</p> <p>CCMA13: I like this feature because some people like it closer or close</p>

15. Which other subtitle personalisation options did you use?

CCMA1: Change language, size, position on screen, indicator.

CCMA2: Size, situation, language

CCMA3: The large font control

CCMA4: All options, less easy reading.

CCMA5: All less easy reading.

CCMA6: Size, language, position and background.

CCMA7: All

CCMA8: ---

CCMA9: Size

CCMA10: Transparent and solid

CCMA11: All except area

CCMA12: Text format, size, area.

CCMA13: Average size, contrast and average position.

16. What did you like most about the ImAc Player?

CCMA1: Images in 360°.

CCMA2: The ability to choose as a subtitle and immersion in space

CCMA3: The letter of the subtitles. The function of the indicators is very useful.

CCMA4: This is a new experience, a new feeling that I liked.

CCMA5: The flexibility that allows the configuration of subtitles (moving head and subtitles are always there) and the location of the issuer (indicator).

CCMA6: Provides a new, more extensive and personalized view of the contents. I think it's a good tool for the future. Good usability

CCMA7: Customizing Subtitles.

CCMA8: The simplicity of the options and the comprehensive facility.

CCMA9: Subtitles

CCMA10: Sound quality, quick options

CCMA11: Subtitling, immersion sensation

CCMA12: Accessibility of subtitles to the contents.

CCMA13: When I use the tablet it is more comfortable than virtual visual, but in general I like it a lot because I have never seen this project!

17. What did you like less about the ImAc Player?

CCMA1: The difficulty to activate / deactivate with the cursor (HMD) and with the finger (Tablet)

CCMA2: It may take a while to find the pointer to select

CCMA3: The yellow dot disappears when I am not focusing the field where the menu bar is.

CCMA4: yellow pointer.

CCMA5: The yellow dot to select (it needs a lot of precision).

CCMA6: The need to move the body or head 360° to see everything.

CCMA7: The indicator, the graph.

CCMA8: Design.

CCMA9: With glasses it is difficult to find a yellow spot

CCMA10: The indicator

CCMA11: Everything else

CCMA12: The caption outline does not look great. It would be necessary to change the color of white to the other yellow. The indicator should be improved, which is not used on the entire screen.

CCMA13: When I use visual reality I do not feel comfortable when I want to click on the menu bar.

18. What do you think could be improved, and how?

CCMA1: It could be improved by making the buttons larger and the cursor visible.

CCMA2: Access to the menu.

CCMA3: Allow the yellow dot to be visible whenever the visible menu is.

CCMA4: The pointer, when moving, appears outside of my visual field.

CCMA5: "- The option to enable / disable subtitles is not visible.

- The subtitles in the SUPERIOR position should go higher on all devices.
- The cursor should be visible during the active menu (visible on the entire screen). "
CCMA6: "Reducing the need to move the body and the 360° head ... Maybe 180 ° was possible?
The small size, for me, is the most appropriate. Large size occupies too much screen. "
CCMA7: Yes. The user made a drawing proposal. It would eliminate the gray triangle of vision and replace it with an eye.
CCMA8: Design more attractive or customizable. The items seemed pretty good to me. letters in other colors, according to screen backgrounds.
CCMA9: Yellow spot always visible
CCMA10: The indicator changes its size outside the menu bar, the larger the farthest and the smaller the smaller.
CCMA11: Language signs (LSC)
CCMA12: Answer itself 7
CCMA13: "Propose a yellow dot in the proximity of the menu bar. (It provides a drawing that we have attached to the paper copy.) The subtitle must lower a bit more."

19. Did you miss any options? If yes, can you tell us which?

CCMA1: No.
CCMA2: Subtitle color changes to adapt to different environments and case of several people talking.
CCMA3: More types of subtitles sizes (the large font option should have the smaller font option). Also have a thicker contour. Have an option where the user can decide where to place the subtitles, to move the menu bar (in glasses).
CCMA4: A Zoom option is missing from the menu.
CCMA5: Lots of options.
CCMA6: No.
CCMA7: Yes, choose color
CCMA8: Colors (letters). Curious or not if "sing", intonation ...
CCMA9: No
CCMA10: Option of visual quality, option to visualise. The file size or visual resolution.
CCMA11: No
CCMA12: ---
CCMA13: Missing Catalan sign language.

20. Other comments:

CCMA1: It is great to be able to enjoy subtitles in 360° content.
CCMA2: I find it a very useful and easy to use tool that will be of frequent use in the near future. Thanks for making it accessible.
CCMA3: No.
CCMA4: Very good experience.
CCMA5: Subtitles are too focused, just at the center of the visual field, hindering the image. Consequently, they should have a transparent, not black background.
CCMA6: Being a concert I could not see how it works with dialogues ... text colors, read speed, etc.
CCMA7: Improve the indicator with radar
CCMA8:
CCMA9: -
CCMA10: The radar is a little uncomfortable, but it is useful.
CCMA11: Everything ok.
CCMA12: ---
CCMA13: -

4. PART 2 – Task 3

a) IPQ – Arrow (I, Philip)

IPQ Question	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
In the computer generated world I had a sense of "being there".			1	1		6	5
Somehow I felt that the virtual world surrounded me.			1		2	5	5
I felt like I was just perceiving pictures.	5	3	3	1		1	1
I did not feel present in the virtual space.					3	7	3
I had a sense of acting in the virtual space, rather than operating something from outside.	1		1	2	1	5	3
I felt present in the virtual space.			1	1	2	5	4
How aware were you of the real world surrounding while navigating in the virtual world? (i.e. sounds, room temperature, other people, etc.)?	1	2		5	3	2	
I was not aware of my real environment.	1	2	2	2	1	3	2
I still paid attention to the real environment.	4	3		2	1	3	
I was completely captivated by the virtual world.		1	1		2	4	5
How real did the virtual world seem to you?	1	4	2	3	2	1	
How much did your experience in the virtual environment seem consistent with your real world experience ?	1	1	3	1	3	3	1
How real did the virtual world seem to you?		2	3	1	3	4	
The virtual world seemed more realistic than the real world.	2	5	4	1		1	

b) IPQ – Radar (I, Philip)

IPQ Question	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
In the computer generated world I had a sense of "being there".				2	2	7	2
Somehow I felt that the virtual world surrounded me.			2	1	1	5	4
I felt like I was just perceiving pictures.	4	1	3	1	1	2	1
I did not feel present in the virtual space.			2	1	3	5	2
I had a sense of acting in the virtual space, rather than operating something from outside.			1	3	1	5	3
I felt present in the virtual space.			2	1	2	6	2
How aware were you of the real world surrounding while navigating in the virtual world? (i.e. sounds, room temperature, other people, etc.)?	1	3	2	2	4	1	
I was not aware of my real environment.		1	2	2	2	4	2
I still paid attention to the real environment.	4	2		1	2	4	
I was completely captivated by the virtual world.		1	1		3	4	4
How real did the virtual world seem to you?	2	2	1	4	3	1	
How much did your experience in the virtual environment seem consistent with your real world experience ?			4	4	2	2	1
How real did the virtual world seem to you?		2	3	3	2	2	1
The virtual world seemed more realistic than the real world.		7	4	1	1	1	

Median table for IPQ questionnaire results, where SP = Spatial presence, INV = Involvement, and REAL = Experienced Realism.

Language	Symbol	SP	INV	REAL
Catalan	Arrow	5.60	4.00	3.50
	Radar	5.80	4.75	3.50

Comparison of Arrow vs Radar in Catalan users per Scale

Test: Related Samples Wilcoxon Signed Rank test

SP = Spatial Presence.

A Wilcoxon Signed-Ranks test indicated that the ranks of Arrow and Radar for Spatial Presence scale are not statistically different ($Z=36.5$, $p=.094$)

INV = Involvement

A Wilcoxon Signed-Ranks test indicated that the ranks of Arrow and Radar for Involvement scale are not statistically different ($Z=22$, $p=.952$)

REAL = Experienced Realism

A Wilcoxon Signed-Ranks test indicated that the ranks of Arrow and Radar for Experienced Realism scale are not statistically different ($Z=28.5$, $p=.918$)

SUMMARY: There is no significant difference in terms of presence between the arrow and the radar.

Comparison German vs Catalan users per scale and symbol

Test: Independent Samples Mann-Whitney U Test

The distribution of Arrow for Spatial Presence is the same across categories of Language (Mann-Whitney $U=73.00$; $p=.648$)

The distribution of Arrow for Involvement is different across categories of Language (German: 3,7; Catalan: 4). (Mann-Whitney $U=102.00$; $p=.021$)

The distribution of Arrow for Experienced Realism is the same across categories of Language (Mann-Whitney $U=61.00$; $p=.832$)

The distribution of Radar for Spatial Presence is the same across categories of Language (Mann-Whitney $U=83.50$; $p=.257$)

The distribution of Radar for Involvement is different across categories of Language (German: 2,62; Catalan: 4,75). (Mann-Whitney $U=110.00$; $p=.004$)

The distribution of Radar Experienced Realism is the same across categories of Language (Mann-Whitney $U=60,50$; $p=.784$)

SUMMARY: There is a difference between the level of involvement between Catalan and German users, but not related to the variables arrow vs radar.

c) Preferences & Usability (arrow and radar)

1. When directions need to be indicated, what system do you prefer?

a) Arrow	b) Radar
9	4

2. Please, explain why you prefer the above indicated option.

CCMA1: Because the arrow does not bother and, in a simple way, indicates the direction.

CCMA2: It is a simple, clear and unambiguous option and it is easy to locate.

CCMA3: Why is it more aesthetic and discreet? Both options are good.

CCMA4: Because I automatically know where and who you are talking about.

CCMA5: Easier, intuitive and coupled to captions, which is where you look. Although it does not specify who talks if more than one person is together.

CCMA6: The radar is more complete. You indicate dialogues of more than one person. And you identify with different colors.

CCMA7: Arrows distract less but there can not be both things at the time.

CCMA8: The search for the person who spoke has made me more relevant and with less latency to search for it with the arrow. The arrow "directs" me.

CCMA9: Agile

CCMA10: Radar occupies visual space and is annoying.

CCMA11: It bothers me in circles (radar) but sometimes I need to use radar

CCMA12: It helps me more where exactly the person is talking.

CCMA13: Because I feel more real and the radar helps me visual orientation.

3. Please explain why you did not choose the other option in question 1).

CCMA1: Because the radar annoys me. The gray round was too intrusive.

CCMA2: Maybe you give too much information, it's good to know where we look and where the transmitter is, but the simplicity of the arrow helps to pay attention to the text and the image in a more natural way.

CCMA3: Why is the radar right in the visible area and covers a bit?

CCMA4: Because I confused myself several times.

CCMA5: Because it has a greater complexity since the issuer's location with regard to your field of view must be processed.

CCMA6: Although the arrow is simpler than the radar, the arrow gives you less information. It's more basic. The radar is more advanced.

CCMA7: The radar distracts but it is a very good option.

CCMA8: I have to do "two steps": look up the point and find out what my area was.

CCMA9: More difficult to find who talks

CCMA10: It is uncomfortable and distracted.

CCMA11: The above, and also the arrow simpler and easier

CCMA12: It does not help me much where the voice that arises and makes me doubt where to find the voice.

CCMA13: Because the arrows are joining the subtitles and does not give me comfort.

4. What do you think could be improved, and how?

CCMA1: The radar could be smaller.

The radar must separate a little more from the subtitles (more behind)

The radar must be smaller, with more 3D design, more blurry, more diluted when they do not speak (adds an explanatory graph in the printed version of the questionnaire) "

CCMA2: I think it's fine as well.

CCMA3: Yes, make a more discrete, smaller radar and place it on one side of the visible area of the user.

CCMA4: The truth is that I would not know it.

CCMA5: The radar is much more useful (more than the arrow) for the exact location of the transmitter, but it could be more transparent and with the visual field of the motionless person.

CCMA6: "The radar is very large (the size may be smaller). Long texts with large print costs too much to read."

CCMA7: Yes, improving and giving radar option to the arrows.

CCMA8: I find the arrow is more direct. Facilitates the information. It's simpler. The radar is more complex but also useful.

CCMA9: -

CCMA10: Improving depends on the likes of each user by configuration.

CCMA11: All right

CCMA12: It would be necessary to incorporate the vibrations of the sounds / noises since I feel nothing.

CCMA13: "The arrow puts the back or left of the screen.

5. Would you implement another system to guide you to the user?

CCMA1: right now no.

CCMA2: No, because it can be too invasive. I like to know what they say despite being looking elsewhere.

CCMA3: No.

CCMA4: No.

CCMA5: No, there are very good options both.

CCMA6: Radar I like it as it is posed. The arrow is too simple. Maybe put the system of names of the speaker and the text ... it could go well according to which people.

CCMA7: Yes.

CCMA8: Put the subtitles in the address where they are spoken. That the subtitles find the person who speaks.

CCMA9: It is also

CCMA10: By intermittent arrows if the talking character is not focused.

CCMA11: No

CCMA12: No, it's fine just like it is.

CCMA13: The radar itself, the arrows not because the arrows do not put the colors that are related to the colors of the subtitles. Radar is perfect!

6. How easy was it to identify who was speaking on the clip with the arrow system?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5- very easy
	2	2	3	6

7. How easy was it to identify who was speaking on the clip with the radar system?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5- very easy
	3	3	2	5

8. Do you think you will be able to enjoy 360° videos with these types of subtitles? Explain your answer.

CCMA1: Yes. I found them useful.

CCMA2: I think they would enjoy them a lot. I only find that it is a personal experience, difficult to share and isolates some of the environment. Maybe it's the only handicap that I see.

CCMA3: Yes, because in this way I can know who speaks, where the sound comes from, etc ...

CCMA4: Yes, it is a good option to integrate and be more attentive.

CCMA5: Yes. These subtitles are very well adapted to the great mobility that allow this type of content.

CCMA6: Yes, no problem. Its vision is very comfortable. But whenever there is more quality or resolution in the images. Uncomfortable to know that I am losing myself behind ... Perhaps instead of turning to me continuously to see what happens behind, it would be possible to project with a visual head of 180° (more comfortable for the viewer) than not 360°.

CCMA7: Not as much as you thought, it tires the view of having distractions or thinking about where to go. It must be simpler.

CCMA8: Yes, I think the subtitles were a long way ahead and the person further away. I do not know if it is possible to put the subtitles further on where the person is. The color letter also facilitated when it came to indicating which person spoke. I think that colors are associated very quickly, rather than putting the name of the person.

CCMA9: If it's new

CCMA10: Yes, but changing the position of the subtitles.

CCMA11: Yes, because they help me locate the characters.

CCMA12: Yes, I enjoy getting into the virtual world in an accessible way.

CCMA13: Yes, I am enjoying but I am a little apprehensive because I feel that the subtitles are near the middle of the screen.

5. Conclusions

a) User interface

The user interface is well-received by all of users, because it offers the possibility to access to Immersive 360° videos adding the accessibility services adapted to this new environment.

Most users have expressed their disagreement with the solution developed with the yellow pointer that is used to access the interface menus. The main reason is the difficulty that it represents using it because it disappears constantly, which leads to the absolute disorientation of the user.

One of the users has even made a graphical proposal on how to implement the solution, recommending that the pointer is always active at a comfortable distance from the menu.

Some users have had difficulty finding the switch to activate / deactivate the subtitles, although they have previously been explained in detail how the interface works.

Some users disagreed with the different colour of the arrow and recommended to use the same color as the subtitle.

But in general terms the users feel happy with the results and would like to repeat in new tests.

b) Presentation modes

Most of the users preferred the arrow indicator, as it is simple and easy to understand. No differences in terms of presence have been reported, according to IPQ results.

However, some users have shown much more interest with the radar, as this allows them to have much more accurate information about the position of the speakers.

The users felt that the radar was too big and interfered when trying to enjoy the video, but they agree it's quite interesting to use this indicator, and some improvements in the design would definitely help. Some users proposed improvements which were contrasted with the interviewers through the help of hand painted graphs on a blackboard.

All users were really interested in ImAc subtitles implementation for immersive 360° contents, the felt very satisfied with the first results and expressed a great desire to collaborate in the future developments through the contribution of ideas.

ANNEX 22. SUBTITLING PILOT PHASE 1 REPORT: PLAYER INTERFACE AND PRESENTATION MODES (RBB)

1. General information

- Partner responsible: RBB
- Place and date: Potsdam, 27./28.9.2018, 15.-19.10.2018
- Access service(s) discussed: *subtitling*.

2. Demographic questionnaire

- Number of end users: 12
- Demographics for users.

1.	Sex	5 male 7 female 0 other 0 prefer not to reply
2.	Age	36, 37, 40, 41 (3x), 46, 52, 54, 56, 59, 63
3.	Main language of the participants:	German (5x), German sign language (6x), Serbian (2x) NB: 1 user selected both German sign language and German
4.	Level of studies	0 no studies 2 primary education 4 secondary education 3 further education 3 university
5.	I define myself as a..."	7 deaf person 4 hearing impaired person 0 deaf-blind person 1 other: Cochlear implant (user is deaf)
6.	Age in which your disability began	6 From birth 4 0-4 0 5-12 0 13-20 0 21-40 2 41-60 0 More than 60
7.	What technology do you use on a daily basis? You can select more than one.	9 TV 6 PC 9 Laptop 11 Mobile Phone 6 Tablet 0 Head Mounted Display (HMD) 1 other: hearing aid

8. How often do you watch virtual reality content (for instance, 360° videos)?

	Never	Occasionally	At least once a month	At least once a week	Every day
In smartphone	10	1			1
On a tablet	11				1
On a PC	11				1
In smartphone plugged to HMD	11	1			
In HMD	11	1			

9.	If you have never used virtual reality content such as 360° videos or only occasionally, please indicate why. Multiple answers are possible.	4 Because I am not interested 0 Because it is not accessible 7 Because I have not had the chance to use it 4 Other reasons: • Because it is rare • Perhaps in the future with other content • No time and it is not important to me • I am not the type that sits in front of a TV the whole day
10.	Please state your level of agreement with the following statement: "I am interested in virtual reality content (such as 360° videos)."	5 Strongly agree 2 Agree 5 Neither agree nor disagree 0 Disagree 0 Strongly disagree
11.	Do you own any device to access virtual reality content?	1 Yes 8 No 3 I don't know or I don't want to reply
12.	If you replied "yes" to the previous question, please specify which device(s).	Tablet

19. Do you like watching the following types of content on television or online?

	I like it very much	I like it	Neither like it nor dislike it	I don't like it	I don't like it at all
News	7	7			
Fiction (series, films)	10	2			
Talk shows	2	4	2	2	2
Documentaries	7	3	1		1
Sports	5	1	3	2	1
Cartoons	3	1	4	1	3

20. When subtitling is available, do you activate it for the following type of content

	Always	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
News	8	3		1
Fiction (series, films)	10	1		1
Talk shows	7	2		3
Documentaries	8	3		1
Sports	9	1	1	1
Cartoons	8	1		3

15.	If it is available and you do not activate it, please select the reasons why.	0 Because the interface is not accessible 3 Because I don't want subtitling in all the content, only in certain types of content 9 Other reasons: • I always use them (7x) • Because sometimes I understand well enough just like that (2x) NB: RBB5 wanted to select "because the interface is not accessible" and the second option which was not possible and decided that option two is more important
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16.	How many hours a day do you watch subtitled content?	1 None 2 Less than 1 hour 1 1-2 hours 3 2-3 hours 3 3-4 hours 2 4 hours or more
17.	What do you use subtitles for?	4 They help me understand 4 They are my only way to have access to the dialogue 0 I use them for language learning 2 Other: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Because I am deaf • To understand everything • Currently no use of subtitles • Option 1 and 2 • Option 1, 2 and 3 NB: RBB5 wanted to select reason 1 and 2 which was not possible and decided that option one is more important

Summary

7 female and 5 male users aged between 36 and 63 took part in the tests. 5 users indicated German as mother tongue, 6 indicated German sign language and 2 users indicated Serbian. Most of the users had at least a secondary education or higher. 7 testers saw themselves as deaf, 5 as hearing impaired, one user had a cochlear implant. For almost all users, the impairment began at birth or below the age of 4, while for 2 users the impairment started between 41 and 60 years.

The technical device used most often on a daily basis was a smartphone (11 users), followed by TV and laptop (both 9 users), while tablet and PC were least often used (both 6 users). HMDs were not used by any of the testers. Almost all of the users had never watched VR content before, mostly because they were not interested or had not had the chance to. When directly asked if they were interested in VR content, most of the testers agreed while some were not sure. The majority of the users did not own a device to access VR content.

In terms of content preferences, the majority of the testers liked news, fiction and documentaries, while some also liked sports, talk shows and cartoons. Almost all of them used subtitles for all types of content. The smaller group of testers that did not always use subtitles explained that they only use ST for certain types of content or that they sometimes understand well enough without ST. There was an even distribution between 0 and more than 4 hours among the testes in terms of how many hours a day they consume subtitled content and the majority of the testers used ST because it is their only way of accessing the dialogues.

3. PART 1 - Task 1 & 2

a) SUS + Open questions – HMD

SUS statements	1	2	3	4	5
1. I think that I would like to use this system frequently		1	2	1	8
2. I found the system unnecessarily complex	9	1	1		1
3. I thought the system was easy to use	2	1		2	7
4. I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system	8	1		1	2
5. I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	2 (1 is probably an error and should be 5)		1	1	7
6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	7	2	1		2
7. I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly	2				10
8. I found the system very cumbersome to use	8		2		2
9. I felt very confident using the system	2	1	1	2	6
10. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system	7	1	3		1

The SUS average score is **77.3** (above average, 68 or more is considered above average).

The graph below shows how the SUS scores associate with the percentile ranks and letter grades and the red line specifies where the ImAc Player - HMD is at this moment.

The letter grade is B+, and our score corresponds to the percentile rank: 80-84%.

RBB9: only tested very shortly on the HMD

b) SUS + Open questions – Tablet

SUS statements	1	2	3	4	5
1. I think that I would like to use this system frequently	2		1	3	6
2. I found the system unnecessarily complex	7	3	1		1
3. I thought the system was easy to use	2		1	2	7
4. I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system	6	1	1		4
5. I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	1		1	3	7
6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	6	1	2	1	2
7. I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly	2				10
8. I found the system very cumbersome to use	10				2
9. I felt very confident using the system	3			1	8
10. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system	8	1	1		2

The SUS average score is **75.4 (above average, 68 or more is considered above average)**. The graph below shows how the SUS scores associate with the percentile ranks and letter grades and the red line specifies where the ImAc Player - Tablet is at this moment.

The letter grade is B, and our score corresponds to the percentile rank: 70-79%.

11.	<u>Did you use the setting "Indicator"?</u>	10 Yes 2 No
12.	<u>What was the function of "Indicator"?</u>	RBB1: Arrow was clear, the others weren't so clear. After trying the options, the function was clear, the arrow was very important (NB: it turned out later

		<p>that the user had not understood what the indicators were meant for)</p> <p>RBB2: The term itself is not clear, but it gets clear with trying</p> <p>RBB3: I did not understand the term, should be translated to Easy to Read. After trying, I understood the function of the radar.</p> <p>RBB4: At first it was not clear, when trying the radar I understood the function. The second time (HMD) it was immediately clear.</p> <p>RBB5: At first it was not clear what the indicator means. After trying I understood that it guides to the speaker.</p> <p>RBB6: At first, I didn't understand what indicator means. This functionality seems to be superfluous even after trying it out.</p> <p>RBB7: It was not clear what the indicator means. The term itself doesn't explain the functionality.</p> <p>RBB8: It was not clear what the indicator means and only by selecting the different options I had an idea about the functionality.</p> <p>RBB9: It was not clear. If I had selected the option, I might have understood but I did not want to try it out because the device was not mine. With my own device I would have tried.</p> <p>RBB10: I did not understand.</p> <p>RBB11: It shows where the speaker is, but that was only clear after trying. A better word might be "Anzeiger"/"Hinweiser" (NB: these German words basically mean "indicator")</p> <p>RBB12: The term was not clear, only after trying it was clear that it is a function to lead to the speaker</p>
<u>13.</u>	<u>Did you use the setting "Area"?</u>	<p>11 Yes</p> <p>1 No</p>
<u>14.</u>	<u>What was the function of "Area"?</u>	<p>RBB1: The function becomes clear by trying it out, only the word "area" does not make the function clear (NB: it seems that the user thinks she just changed the size of the ST with this function)</p> <p>RBB2: The term itself makes me think it refers to the position of the subtitle. When trying it out, it becomes clear. (NB: it seems that the user thinks she just changed the size of the ST with this function)</p> <p>RBB3: I did not understand it. (NB: the option was used unconsciously.)</p> <p>RBB4: I did not really understand it. The font went smaller and went up a bit. "Area" refers to right/left top/bottom for me.</p> <p>RBB5: I don't know.</p> <p>RBB6: I did not really understand it. (NB: User tested the different settings.) I recognized a difference in the ST but I still didn't know what the benefit of this setting.</p> <p>RBB7: I did not really understand it. It could be the area to show the subtitles together with the background.</p> <p>RBB8: Change of size of the subtitles</p> <p>RBB9: I didn't know what it means. I thought it might be access to different content but I didn't think it had anything to do with subtitles.</p> <p>RBB10: I didn't understand but I just tried, then the size of the ST changed.</p> <p>RBB11: Not really</p> <p>RBB12: It wasn't clear, even after trying.</p>

15. Which other subtitle personalisation options did you use?

RBB1: Size, Area, Language, Easy to read, Position, Loudness, Play/Pause. (NB: In the HMD, the user did not find the on/off button to switch on the subtitles and needed help by the facilitator. The user asked how she could close the menu, only managed after help by the facilitator. On the tablet, the user did not find on/off button, even though the tablet was tested after the HMD. The user did not notice the function "Background" among the many options)

RBB2: Size, Area, Language, Position, Loudness, Play/Pause

RBB3: Loudness, Play/Pause, Size, Position, Background, Language, Sign Language (NB: The user did not find the on/off button on the HMD (tested first) and needed help by the facilitator. The user switched on the signer because the function was there.)

RBB4: All other functions.

RBB5: Loudness, Play/Pause, indicator, size, background, position (preferred the subtitle bottom) (NB: the user did not find the on/off button to switch on the subtitles and needed help by the facilitator and additionally switched on the sign language service)

RBB6: pause / play video, open subtitle menu (NB: User need help to find the on/off button), size, position, background, indicator, area (is the same as size: small and large), language

RBB7: The user tried every option, but not all functionalities were clear only the ones which are familiar from the TV subtitle service. (NB: Tester needed help to activate the subtitles)

RBB8: activate subtitles, position, background, size, indicator, area, play/pause video, (NB: HMD: The tester opened the menu without difficulties but didn't see the menu the menu bar immediately and tried again to open the menu by moving down the head)

RBB9: pause / play video, loudness, size, background, area language – only selected the categories but didn't try the different options (NB: Tester needed help to activate the subtitles)

RBB10: Play/pause, loudness, position (NB: Tester needed help to activate the subtitles; HMD: The tester opened the menu without difficulties but didn't see the menu the menu bar immediately and tried again to open the menu by moving down the head)

RBB11: All options were used.

RBB12: All functions were used (NB: Tester needed help to activate the subtitles)

16. What did you like most about the ImAc Player?

RBB1: Controller worked very well, the menu was easy, a lot of setting options

RBB2: I liked the subtitles and the look of the player. The subtitles moved with me when I moved my head (HMD).

RBB3: That I could switch on subtitles and change their position.

RBB4: That there are so many personalisation options.

RBB5: That there are so many options to customise the subtitles (size, background, language).

RBB6: All the settings are shown in only one level of the menu – very clear.

RBB7: That there are so many options to customise the subtitles. I liked the word by word translations and the small and compact area in which the subtitles are presented.

RBB8: Subtitles always follow the head movement, the experience was amazing, I liked the subtitle background and size, and terms were clear in the menu

RBB9: I liked the subtitles, but I didn't see them clearly (NB: sight problems, tester saw 2 subtitles)

RBB10: I liked the subtitles.

RBB11: All the significant customisation options are available. There is a speaker indicator.

RBB12: It's a normal menu just like I know them.

17. What did you like less about the ImAc Player?

RBB1: Nothing negative, all the necessary functions were there (HMD). Menu cannot be zoomed; on/off button: it was not clear if the button has to be pressed or it is a sliding button (tablet).

RBB2: 360° video was rather unfamiliar

RBB3: The audio functions (tester is deaf).

RBB4: The opened menu did not go away once a function was selected. Therefore the menu obscured the subtitles and the video. Maybe it could close automatically but then again this might also have disadvantages, e.g. someone wants to select more personalisation options.

RBB5: Tablet: It was difficult to switch on / off the subtitles. HMD: It was cumbersome to close the accessibility menu. Both devices: In general is the menu too small. The term "Zeichensprache" is wrong; it should be "Gebärdensprache".

RBB6: The subtitles should be fixed to the field of view, especially horizontally. Subtitles should be activated as soon as I select an option in the subtitle menu, e.g. language. I didn't recognise the on/off button.

RBB7: HMD: I didn't like that the subtitles followed my head movement. Tablet: The menu was too small and it was cumbersome to select an option.

RBB8: The content wasn't very suitable for deaf people.

RBB9: Nothing

RBB10: Nothing

RBB11: Nothing

RBB12: On/off button was difficult to find.

18. What do you think could be improved, and how?

RBB1: Better feedback for on/off button, button should be similar to "sliding button" as in iPhone

RBB2: Quality of the video was not very good (HMD). I could not detect the menu after opening it, it was too much integrated into the video (HMD).

RBB3: The tablet was good. In the HMD the signer and the subtitles were too wide apart, they should be wider apart if they are used together.

RBB4: Personalise the colours of the subtitles.

RBB5: Switch on/off subtitles by selecting the abbreviation "UT". Zooming functionality for menu or customize size in the settings. HMD: Close accessibility submenu by "clicking" outside the menu.

RBB6: See question 17. Indicator and area are not a good choice to describe the functionality behind it.

RBB7: It should be customizable if the subtitles are a one-to-one translation or an easy to read version. I would like to have simultaneous subtitles to the spoken word. (NB: She mentioned that the subtitles were too fast in the first video clip and thus maybe had the feeling that the provided subtitles were one-to-one translation of the spoken word without any simplification as it is done in the TV service)

RBB8: Display both subtitles and sign language, different fonts, add genre of music, better description of music or sound in subtitles (e.g. vibration for sounds or music)

RBB9: Nothing

RBB10: Nothing.

RBB11: The menu does not open at the same position as the blue loading circle – this was inconvenient. The contrast of grey/white was not ideal. It should be possible to move the radar by drag/drop to move it away from the video image.

RBB12: The on/off button should be on the right side of "Subtitles" not on the left.

19. Did you miss any options? If yes, can you tell us which?

RBB1: Zooming function, Menu should be bigger, was difficult to see, difficult to select with finger (tablet).

RBB2: No.

RBB3: No, I was surprised by the amount of options.

RBB4: Personalise the colours of the subtitles.

RBB5: No

RBB6: See question 18.

RBB7: Visualisation of music, e.g. spectrum, especially for concerts

RBB8: Display both subtitles and sign language interpreter

RBB9: Subtitles should already be activate by default when video is playing

RBB10: No.

RBB11: Changing the colours of the ST or at least deselect certain colours in case a user has a visual impairment for certain colours. Also the colour of the menu itself should be customisable.

RBB12: No.

20. Other comments:

RBB1: No.

RBB2: The HMD is not so comfortable.

RBB3: Well done.

RBB4: No.

RBB5: User asked if it is possible to connect the hearing aid with the VR glasses as it is uncomfortable to wear headphones with a hearing aid.

RBB6: No

RBB7: No

RBB8: Enhance the experience for music and sounds with vibrations

RBB9: No

RBB10: No

RBB11: No

RBB12: No

4. PART 2 – Task 3

a) IPQ – Arrow (I, Philip)

Results from only 10 users could be gathered, as one user (RBB 10) felt uncomfortable using HMD and in one test (RBB11) there were technical problems.

IPQ Question	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
In the computer generated world I had a sense of "being there".	1	1	1			1	6
Somehow I felt that the virtual world surrounded me.	2						8
I felt like I was just perceiving pictures.	8						2
I did not feel present in the virtual space.	3	1		2			4
I had a sense of acting in the virtual space, rather than operating something from outside.	4	1		1		3	1
I felt present in the virtual space.		2				2	6
How aware were you of the real world surrounding while navigating in the virtual world? (i.e. sounds, room temperature, other people, etc.)?	6	1	2				1
I was not aware of my real environment.	6	2			1		1
I still paid attention to the real environment.	2	3		1		1	3
I was completely captivated by the virtual world.	1			1	1	1	6
How real did the virtual world seem to you?	6	2			1		1
How much did your experience in the virtual environment seem consistent with your real world experience?	1	1		3	1	2	2

IPQ Question	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
How real did the virtual world seem to you?	4	1	1	1	1		2
The virtual world seemed more realistic than the real world.	6			2	1		1

b) IPQ – Radar (I, Philip)

Results from only 10 users could be gathered, as one user (RBB 10) felt uncomfortable using HMD and in one test (RBB11) there were technical problems.

IPQ Question	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
In the computer generated world I had a sense of "being there".	1				1	2	6
Somehow I felt that the virtual world surrounded me.		1		1		2	6
I felt like I was just perceiving pictures.	6	1		1			2
I did not feel present in the virtual space.	5	1	1	1			2
I had a sense of acting in the virtual space, rather than operating something from outside.	1			2		1	6
I felt present in the virtual space.		1		2		2	5
How aware were you of the real world surrounding while navigating in the virtual world? (i.e. sounds, room temperature, other people, etc.)?	7	2					1
I was not aware of my real environment.	6	1				1	2
I still paid attention to the real environment.	2	1		1		1	5
I was completely captivated by the virtual world.	2				2	2	4
How real did the virtual world seem to you?	3	1	3				3
How much did your experience in the virtual environment seem consistent with your real world experience ?	2			1	1	4	2
How real did the virtual world seem to you?	6			1			3
The virtual world seemed more realistic than the real world.	5			1	1	1	2

Median table for IPQ questionnaire results, where SP = Spatial presence, INV = Involvement, and REAL = Experienced Realism.

Language	Symbol	SP	INV	REAL
German	Arrow	4.70	3.37	3.62
	Radar	5.30	2.62	3.87

Comparison of Arrow vs Radar in German users per Scale

Test: Related Samples Wilcoxon Signed Rank test

SP = Spatial Presence.

A Wilcoxon Signed-Ranks test indicated that the ranks of Arrow and Radar for Spatial Presence scale are not statistically different ($Z=21$, $p=.858$)

INV = Involvement

A Wilcoxon Signed-Ranks test indicated that the ranks of Arrow and Radar for Involvement scale are not statistically different ($Z=3.5$, $p=.276$)

REAL = Experienced Realism

A Wilcoxon Signed-Ranks test indicated that the ranks of Arrow and Radar for Experienced Realism scale are not statistically different ($Z=12.5$, $p=.799$)

SUMMARY: There is no significant difference in terms of presence between the arrow and the radar.

Comparison German vs Catalan users per scale and symbol

Test: Independent Samples Mann-Whitney U Test

The distribution of Arrow for Spatial Presence is the same across categories of Language (Mann-Whitney $U=73.00$; $p=.648$)

The distribution of Arrow for Involvement is different across categories of Language (German: 3,7; Catalan: 4). (Mann-Whitney $U=102.00$; $p=.021$)

The distribution of Arrow for Experienced Realism is the same across categories of Language (Mann-Whitney $U=61.00$; $p=.832$)

The distribution of Radar for Spatial Presence is the same across categories of Language (Mann-Whitney $U=83.50$; $p=.257$)

The distribution of Radar for Involvement is different across categories of Language (German: 2,62; Catalan: 4,75). (Mann-Whitney $U=110.00$; $p=.004$)

The distribution of Radar for Experienced Realism is the same across categories of Language (Mann-Whitney $U=60,50$; $p=.784$)

SUMMARY: There is a difference between the level of involvement between Catalan and German users, but not related to the variables arrow vs radar.

Preferences & Usability (arrow and radar).

Results from 11 participants were gathered, as one participant (RBB10) felt uncomfortable using the HMD. RBB11 input is based on the User interface test, as there were technical problems and could not watch "I, Philip".

1. When directions need to be indicated, what system do you prefer?

a) Arrow	b) Radar
8	3

2. Please, explain why you prefer the above indicated option.

RBB1: I am used to it and it is better. It might be important but the colour coding of the subtitles (including the introduction of who the speaker is) helps a lot already.

RBB2: The arrow points directly in the direction of the speaker

RBB3: The arrow was immediately clear (but the radar was good as well).

RBB4: Clear information

RBB5: The radar was immediately clear and it was possible to identify the position of the speaker very fast.

RBB6: The arrow is concise and didn't distract. Very clear.

RBB7: The arrow was immediately clear and a good help to find the speaker.

RBB8: The arrow was clear and I immediately understood where the speaker is located.

RBB9: With the radar it was clearer where the speaker is (arrow was good as well).

RBB11: Radar is better for something like a panel discussion, a situation with many speakers (arrow is good as well).

RBB12: Radar is independent of the text, more modern, more intuitively comprehensible

3. Please explain why you did not choose the other option in question 1).

RBB1: It was new to me, visually rather disturbing

RBB2: It was visually disturbing, in the middle of the screen. The link between speaker and position wasn't very clear.

RBB3: It was visually disturbing, a bit too big and it distracted me. It was new and I had to get used to it.

RBB4: I had to orient myself first. Later I had an even better feeling for spatiality than with the arrow.

RBB5: The arrow was not precise enough at least when more than two speakers are there.

RBB6: The radar disturbs the view and is too complex. It distracts more than the arrow.

RBB7: The radar didn't exactly match the speaker position. The illustrated area was too wide. (NB: I think the concept of visualising the field of view was not understood by the tester and she mentioned that she was more aware of the different colours for the speakers.)

RBB8: The radar was not clear at the beginning. If I used it more often, I assume that I would get used to it and then it might be an alternative to the arrow.

RBB9: The arrow is better when there are many speakers (radar was good as well).

RBB11: The arrow is better for few speakers, it is immediately clear.

RBB12: The arrow was very close to the text.

4. What do you think could be improved, and how?

RBB1: I was not aware that I was the person that is speaking (I, Philip).

RBB2: No

RBB3: The arrow should be there before a person starts speaking. Otherwise it is difficult to follow fast dialogues, even with the radar.

RBB4: With very fast dialogues it gets confusing to follow the speakers, even with the arrow. A larger field of view would be better (to overview more speakers at a time).

RBB5: Nothing

RBB6: It is confusing that the subtitles follow each head movement. Subtitles should only follow when turning the head and be fixed in the horizontal position.

RBB7: I didn't immediately understand that I was the person who is speaking. This should be added to the subtitles.

RBB8: The subtitles were too fast in the dialog between the journalists, the inventor and Philip so that I missed some content. It is possible to rewind the video but that is cumbersome with opening the menu and using rewind several times. It should be possible to choose between different answers and thus to change the plot.

RBB9: The colour should be displayed outside the radar

RBB11: It should be possible to move the radar by drag/drop to move it away from the video image. It would be nice to see the depth of a speaker in the radar, how far away in the room he is.

RBB12: Nothing

5. Would you implement another system to guide you to the user?

RBB1: No

RBB2: No, the arrow was ideal.

RBB3: No, this is all very new for me.

RBB4: Maybe adjusting the field of view to see more speakers at a time.

RBB5: No

RBB6: Perhaps the voices coming more from left or right depending on their position.

RBB7: No

RBB8: No

RBB9: No

RBB11: Just like in football games: an arrow above the speaker shows who is speaking.

RBB12: No

6. How easy was it to identify who was speaking on the clip with the arrow system?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5- very easy
	2	3	3	3

7. How easy was it to identify who was speaking on the clip with the radar system?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5- very easy
1	4	2	1	3

8. Do you think you will be able to enjoy 360° videos with these types of subtitles? Explain your answer.

RBB1: Yes, I like it a lot.

RBB2: Yes, not all the time but once in a while. It is nice to be pulled into the virtual world, "being there".

RBB3: Maybe once in a while, not regularly. I was totally "in there".

RBB4: Yes, because it is something new. One feels "inside", really being there.

RBB5: Yes, because it was an amazing experience.

RBB6: Yes, because it reflects reality more intensely than a two-dimensional image. It depends on what is shown (crime thriller rather not, I want to have the distance there). Nature or animal videos would be nice. Music concert, so that one sits in the auditorium.

RBB7: It was very exhausting to consume subtitles in 360° content and thus I couldn't enjoy the experience. Maybe other content is more interesting, e.g. documentaries.

RBB8: Yes, because I'm interested in it and I could follow the content with the subtitles.

RBB9: No, the HMD is very uncomfortable together with my glasses and it is too heavy so that my neck hurts. Maybe if the device was lighter.

RBB11: Yes, when I am alone I can enjoy that and immerse into the content.

RBB12: Not in this video quality and the weight of the HMD disturbs a lot. This prevents me from immersing into the video.

5. Conclusions

Observations by facilitator and assistant: We recognised that the usage of the HMD was uncomfortable for users wearing glasses, cochlear implants or hearing aids. The users wearing the last two devices asked explicitly if it is possible to stream the audio directly to their device. The consequence was that the users either tried to use the headphones and their hearing aids together or just take off the hearing aids. The same applied for the glasses. Additionally, some users mentioned that the HMD is too heavy and it is not comfortable to wear it longer.

All users didn't use 360° content in an HMD before the test and were mainly amazed by the experience. They mentioned that they would like to see documentaries or concerts. The low video quality in comparison to standard resolution of TV content together with the weight and fit of the device were another reason why the user would not use an HMD on a regular basis. We could see that the users were partially part of the story and reacts with body movement if something comes nearer or in conversation with "I, Philip" a tester shakes his head for no.

Although all testers didn't use an HMD before was it easy for them to learn the usage of the controller to select an option in the menu and the large number of personalisation options was positively evaluated. The specific options like indicator and area for the usage in an HMD were not clear immediately. The testers got an idea about the functionalities once they tried them. We assume that this is part of a learning procedure and we should maybe revise the current wording. The main problem for all users was to locate the on/off button and to find the menu once it was opened as it was not in all cases in the field of view or the contrast was not high enough.

The usage on the tablet was mainly difficult because the size of the menu was too small and we propose to use the enhanced accessibility menu for tablets and smartphones to avoid this problem. Please find all details below.

a) User interface

Tasks: Almost all the testers completed the tasks of the UI test without problems. However, 8 users had great difficulties in finding the on/off button for the subtitles and needed help with this task. It thus seems to be necessary to change the position of the on/off button in the accessibility interface.

Indicator/area: Most of the users tried out all the ST settings, including "indicator" and "area". Both of these terms were not clear for the users, but at least the indicator was understood by most of them after trying. The area setting was not understood by any user because most of them only recognised the change in font size. We therefore conclude that the wording for these functions should be revised and we doubt the benefit of the area function.

Positive feedback: What the testers liked most about the player were the amount of personalisation settings and the clear design of the menu.

Negative feedback: Two users did not like the subtitles following their head movements (especially when tilting the head but also when turning the head) and two users found it difficult to find the menu in the HMD after opening it. Furthermore, it bothered many users that they did not find the on/off button and that the menu was very small on the tablet, which made it very difficult to select the

options. Instead of adding a zooming function (as suggested by one user), we conclude that it might be necessary to show the enhanced accessibility interface in tablets by default.

Improvements: One user suggested that the ST-submenu is closed by clicking somewhere outside the menu in the HMD (NB: this is already the case in the tablet mode). One user asked for a better (or adjustable) contrast in the menu (not white/grey).

Missing functionalities: Two users would like to be able to customise the ST colour (e.g. for visual impairments regarding certain colours). Two users wanted to display subtitles and signer at the same time. One user had the idea to drag/drop the radar to a different position if it obscured an important area of the video. One user asked for a better “translation” of sound and music, e.g. with vibrations or visualisations such as spectra.

b) Presentation modes

Arrow vs. radar: The majority of the users preferred the arrow because it was immediately clear and easy to understand. Those few users who preferred the radar liked it because it gave them a good overview and found it especially suitable for many speakers at the same time.

The majority of the testers did not like the radar because it was not intuitive and visually disturbing.

No differences in terms of presence have been reported, according to IPQ results.

Improvements: Two users asked for a better way to understand that an off-voice is speaking. A few testers found it difficult to follow fast conversations and suggested that either the arrow is displayed before a person starts speaking or that the field of view can be enlarged in order to have a better overview. One user asked for a drag/drop function for the radar to move it away in case it obscures the video. One user had the idea to also display the depth of speakers in the radar (at least relative to each other).

Other ideas: There were two ideas for other guiding mechanisms: indicating the speaker position via audio (3D audio) or showing an arrow above the speakers (similar to football analysis videos).

Enjoyment: Most users thought they could enjoy 360° videos with subtitles but not too often and depending on the content. A few users found the HMD uncomfortable or not technically satisfying.

ANNEX 23. METHODOLOGY FOR SUBTITLING PRE-PILOT 2 ACTIONS

1. What will be tested? (summary)

The purpose of the experiment is to gather users' feedback on the usability of the interface as well as users' feedback on immersion and preferences in relation to two presentation modes for subtitles in cinematic virtual reality:

PART 1. USER INTERFACE.

Access to ImAc Player and access services for usability and user preferences. The traditional menu will be tested for subtitles, both in tablet and HMD modes.

PART 2. PRESENTATION MODES.

1. Subtitles presentation (immersion and preferences):
 - Always visible with arrow
 - Fixed positioned with arrow
2. Non-speech information (preferences):
 - Emojis
 - Text

1. When?

- German Pilot: from 1st March to 7st June.
- Spanish Pilot: from 1st March to 7^t June.

2. Who?

- German pilot: RBB
- Spanish pilot: CCMA

3. Stimuli

- Desconcert 1 (Leyre)
 - Test: Part 1. User interface.
 - Description: musical concerts.
 - Genre: musical
 - Original language: Catalan
 - Duration: around 5/6 minutes (although, no need to watch it completely).
 - Link to player:
 - Ger: <https://imac.gpac-licensing.com/test-ui-ger/>
 - Cat: <https://imac.gpac-licensing.com/test-ui-cat/>
 - All modes and services to be tested (subtitles) must be implemented.
- I, Philip
 - Test: Part 2. Presentation modes.
 - Description: 23 years after Philip K. Dick's death, in 2005, David Hanson, a young engineer in robotics, revealed his first android with human form, "Phil". "I, Philip" immerses you in the memories of what could be the last love affair of the writer. But aren't these memories the fruit of the imagination of an android which learned, little by little, how to become a human?
 - Genre: Sci-Fi, drama
 - Original language: English
 - Duration: 12:26 (until the credits), to be split in two clips for Task 2 and pre-selected snippets for Task 3 (https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1f1P9_r9-97cDIBTeK4vhFxrhyM0evv9SVI8baMZDaY/edit#gid=0)
 - Link:

- Ger: <https://imac.gpac-licensing.com/pilot-test1/>
 - Cat: <https://imac.gpac-licensing.com/pilot-test1cat/>
- Access services needed:
 - * Arrow with blinking effect everywhere.
 - * Unicode emojis / Only for sounds.
 - GER subtitles – Always visible with arrow
 - GER subtitles – Fixed positioned with arrow
 - CAT subtitles – Always visible with arrow
 - CAT subtitles – Fixed positioned with arrow
 - GER subtitles – emoji (always visible with arrow)
 - GER subtitles – text (always visible with arrow)
 - CAT subtitles – emoji (always visible with arrow)
 - CAT subtitles – text (always visible with arrow)

IDENTIFICATION CODES FOR THE STIMULI FOR PART 2

- A1: I, Philip part 1 – Always visible with arrow
- A2: I, Philip part 1 – Fixed positioned with arrow
- B1: I, Philip part 2 – Always visible with arrow
- B2: I, Philip part 2 – Fixed positioned with arrow
- C1: I, Philip snippet 1 – emoji (always visible with arrow)
- C2: I, Philip snippet 1 – text (always visible with arrow)
- D1: I, Philip snippet 2 – emoji (always visible with arrow)
- D2: I, Philip snippet 2 – text (always visible with arrow)

4. Methodology: overview

- **Aim:** gather data from users about 1) their experience with the ImAc Player and access services, replying to questions regarding usability and preferences; 2) their experience with different presentation modes, replying to questions regarding immersion and preferences.
- **Experimental protocol:** users will be asked to perform certain tasks while they watch different stimuli, and then report on the usability, preferences and immersion through digital questionnaires with closed and open questions.
- **Research tools:** digital questionnaires (Google Forms or internal tools). The questionnaires will be digital in order to facilitate data processing. The questionnaires will be translated into German/Catalan/Spanish. SUS and IPQ translations will be provided by UAB.
- **Measures:** usability, preferences and presence (immersion).
- **Participants:** Recruitment will be done via associations/organisation and/or at partners' discretion.
 - For Part 1 – User interface, 10 x each partner (total=20 users). Hard-of-hearing participants, no Sign Language.
 - For Part 2 – Presentation modes, 10 x each partner (total=20 users). Hard-of-hearing participants, no sign language.
- **Duration:** approx. 90 minutes.
- **Language of the test:** German/Catalan/Spanish (depending on the territory).
- **Materials:** HMD, tablet, computer and clips.
- **Facilitators:** two facilitators will be needed. One facilitator will be the leader (welcoming participants, explaining the project, explaining the test) and another facilitator will assist the sessions (by providing the digital questionnaires and helping filling them in, providing technical assistance with the different devices, etc.).
- **Test accessibility:** adequate measures must be taken by tests organisers (CCMA, RBB) so that communication with persons with hearing loss is fluent.
- **Reporting:** results will be included in a report created by each partner. This will be done exporting data from the Google Form. A template will be provided. All feedback must be translated into English by the partners responsible for the pilots (RBB and CCMA).

- **Testing the methodology by RBB and CCMA:** please make sure you test the experimental protocol below before the actual pilot action. If the methodology needs to be improved based on this previous test, let UAB know. It is important that both RBB and CCMA use the same methodology.
- Please make sure that you have all materials and ethical forms ready before the test.

5. Methodology: experimental protocol

PLANNING

Introduction	15 min
Part 1 - User interface	25 min
Part 2 - Presentation modes	40 min
Farewell and thanks	5 min
Buffer time	5 min
Total	90 min

WORKFLOW

LATIN SQUARE FOR ALL PARTICIPANTS (if more than 10, repeat from the beginning).

Each participant will follow a different order to avoid the order of presentation affecting the results.

Participant	User interface	User interface	Subtitles presentation	Subtitles presentation	Non-speech information	Non-speech information
RBB1/CCMA1	Task 1 (HMD)	Task 2 (tablet)	A1	B2	C1	D2
RBB2/CCMA2	Task 2 (tablet)	Task 1 (HMD)	A2	B1	C2	D1
RBB3/CCMA3	Task 1 (HMD)	Task 2 (tablet)	A1	B2	C1	D2
RBB4/CCMA4	Task 2 (tablet)	Task 1 (HMD)	A2	B1	C2	D1
RBB5/CCMA5	Task 1 (HMD)	Task 2 (tablet)	A1	B2	C1	D2
RBB6/CCMA6	Task 2 (tablet)	Task 1 (HMD)	A2	B1	C2	D1
RBB7/CCMA7	Task 1 (HMD)	Task 2 (tablet)	A1	B2	C1	D2
RBB8/CCMA8	Task 2 (tablet)	Task 1 (HMD)	A2	B1	C2	D1
RBB9/CCMA9	Task 1 (HMD)	Task 2 (tablet)	A1	B2	C1	D2
RBB10/CCMA10	Task 2 (tablet)	Task 1 (HMD)	A2	B1	C2	D1

INTRODUCTION (15 min)

Who?	What?	How long?
Lead facilitator	<p>Welcome the participants, who will individually attend the test. Please assign a participant code when they arrive, so that they can enter that code in each online questionnaire. Codes should be as follows:</p> <p>For RBB: RRB1, RRB2, RRB3, RRB4, etc.</p> <p>For CCMA: CCMA1, CCMA2, CCMA3, CCMA4, etc.</p>	1 min
Lead facilitator	<p>Explain the project (if unknown to the participant), the aim of the test and the procedure.</p>	5 min
Assistant facilitator	<p>Provide the participant with the consent form for ethical clearance. You can find the last version here: https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1X5Nj9KxkpFVvwEuKFk6XVgz0VFUSzUOS If compensation is provided, please use the version here: https://drive.google.com/open?id=11k6zNWiKjikTILn5tJjnXCiNFNrKeXFC Provide signed original consent forms to UAB (next meeting or send by snail mail).</p>	3 min

<u>Who?</u>	<u>What?</u>	<u>How long?</u>
Assistant facilitator	Provide the participant with the digital demographic questionnaire to be filled in (access to a computer/laptop will be needed): ENG: https://goo.gl/forms/hKWdXBox0UYCxIWv2 GER: https://goo.gl/forms/U6lgJek5BziszW0Or2 CAT: https://goo.gl/forms/ohpcqsUcv8GiyrYK2 ES: https://goo.gl/forms/Niru8eZaP1U5rfu12	6 min

In the following sections, the different parts of the test will be explained, including tasks and measures.

PART 1. USER INTERFACE (25 min)

- **Measures:** usability and preferences
- **Participants:** 10 per partner
- **Materials:**
 - **Devices:** the test will be performed with an HMD and a tablet. If when testing the methodology this proves too challenging, it can be revised.
 - **Player:**
 - Link to the player:
 - Ger: <https://imac.gpac-licensing.com/test-ui-ger/>
 - Cat: <https://imac.gpac-licensing.com/test-ui-cat/>
 - Only traditional menu will be tested.
 - **Clip:** Desconcert with subtitles.
- **Room:** make sure the atmosphere is comfortable for the participants, with an adequate room arrangement.

Previous to task (5 min)

The lead facilitator will roughly explain to the users how the ImAc Player/Menu works (you have to look down or do consecutive clicks on the controller to open the menu, you have to press that button from the controller to select the different options, you will find options to play/pause, volume control, accessibility services, etc.) and advise during the test if necessary.

IMPORTANT: Please randomise the order in which you perform TASK 1 and 2, to avoid a learning effect that could have a negative impact on the results. Please follow the Latin Square provided above.

TASK 1.1 - Test with HMD. Duration: 10 min.

Participants will receive the **instructions on paper** before starting the test and the lead facilitator will clarify any doubt before starting the test.

- 0) Select the “Desconcert 1 - Leyre” video from the initial webpage and press “Play”.
- 1) After some seconds, please pause the video.
- 2) Please, play the video again.
- 3) Please change the volume.
- 4) Please, open the menu and activate subtitles in your own language.
- 5) Please, randomly personalise subtitles, using all available options.

After TASK 1.1 is finished, participants will be asked by the assistant lead to fill in the following questionnaire (SUS):

- ENG: <https://goo.gl/forms/ejbWGyBYdQQbMvfl1>
GER: <https://goo.gl/forms/P0wBd7AKUZW3yk2n2>
CAT: <https://goo.gl/forms/YpacRoX6lyWZ4x3S2>
ES: <https://goo.gl/forms/eZzPDDXwISt7Eebq1>

TASK 1.2 - Test with tablet. Duration: 10 min.

Participants will receive the **instructions on paper** before starting the test and the lead facilitator will clarify any doubt before starting the test.

- 0) Select the “Desconcert 1 - Leyre” video from the initial webpage and press “Play”.
- 1) After some seconds, please pause the video.
- 2) Please, play the video again.
- 3) Please change the volume.
- 4) Please, open the menu and activate subtitles in your own language.
- 5) Please, randomly personalise subtitles, using all available options.

After TASK 1.2 is finished, participants will be asked by the assistant lead to fill in the following questionnaire (SUS):

ENG: <https://goo.gl/forms/PAh25zmUernI9JH83>
GER: <https://goo.gl/forms/FJfr9kWsFe5eSuZf1>
CAT: <https://goo.gl/forms/74J1xW3aNJ3xpINA3>
ES: <https://goo.gl/forms/ILn5cdhfndsiUj913>

After both tasks, participants will be asked to reply open questions about both systems.

ENG: <https://goo.gl/forms/wjXGLo0hSqG7hKR11>
GER: They will use their own tool.
CAT: <https://goo.gl/forms/KOIVMN1yoOrRJ4Ep2>
ES: <https://goo.gl/forms/oPDONRYh14B9yaib2>

Suggestion for open questions:

1. Were you able to activate the subtitles without any help?
 - a) Yes
 - b) No
2. Were you able to select the language of the subtitles without any help?
 - a) Yes
 - b) No
3. Which other personalisation options did you use?
4. Were you able to activate/deactivate the preview for the personalisation settings without any help?
 - a) Yes
 - b) No
5. Was the preview of the personalisation settings helpful for you?
6. What did you like most about the ImAc player?
7. What did you like less about the ImAc player?
8. What do you think could be improved and how?
9. Did you miss any options? If yes, can you tell us which?
10. Other comments:

PART 2. PRESENTATION MODES (40 min)

- **Measures:** preferences and immersion
- **Participants:** 10 per partner
- **Materials:**
 - Device: the test will be performed with an HMD.
 - Player:
 - Link to the player:
 - Ger: <https://imac.gpac-licensing.com/pilot-test1/>
 - Cat: <https://imac.gpac-licensing.com/pilot-test1cat/>

- **Stimuli:** Two comparable clips (A, B) with 2 conditions (1, 2) + two comparable clips (C, D) with 2 conditions (1,2) for each presentation mode tested, so that participants can watch both conditions in different but comparable clips to avoid a learning effect.
 - I, Philip:
 - 2 comparable clips, 6-7 min each.
 - 2 comparable snippets.
- **Room:** make sure the atmosphere is comfortable for the participants, with an adequate room arrangement

Introduction (5 min)

The lead facilitator will explain the aim of this part: testing two different subtitle presentation and two different modes to display non-speech information. There will be two subtitle presentation: always visible with arrow and fixed positioned with arrow. And two modes to display non-speech information: text and emojis. After watching the clips, they will be asked to answer a set of questions.

The order of presentation of the stimuli will be balanced across participants. A Latin square protocol in which the presentation mode is tested with two conditions.

Order of presentation (please repeat up to the number of agreed participants): Please follow the Latin Square provided above.

TASK 2. Always with arrow VS Fixed positioned with arrow. Duration: 25 min.

1. The participants will be asked to watch the two randomised clips. Please follow the order specified in the Latin Square provided above.
2. The participant will have to watch 2 clips (A, B) with the randomised variables: (1) always visible with arrow and (2) fixed positioned with arrow. After watching **each clip**, participants will have to reply to the IPQ (presence) questionnaire to gather feedback about immersion. Please don't share technicalities with participants, only tell them they will be asked to reply some questions in the following forms:
 - a. Always visible with arrow - I, Philip:
 - ENG: <https://goo.gl/forms/lw0I4OaMMqI58ENe2>
 - GER: <https://goo.gl/forms/s67NXXJhgObfRVbk2>
 - CAT: <https://goo.gl/forms/e8YQaMcYrU9ACnOs2>
 - ES: <https://goo.gl/forms/MiufUUW3BpzsU5P13>
 - b. Fixed positioned with arrow - I, Philip:
 - ENG: <https://goo.gl/forms/w7HuWQVWdDpE9Kkq1>
 - GER: <https://goo.gl/forms/VnqmvDQCbXTLhyu02>
 - CAT: <https://goo.gl/forms/VwNWEfk0mfAygKmQ2>
 - ES: <https://goo.gl/forms/pL6wyaGAERWoxHI62>

IMPORTANT: Please make sure that you provide the correct IPQ questionnaire to participants depending on the order in which they are visualising the clips.

3. After watching **the two clips**, the participants will be asked to provide feedback about preferences and usability:
 - ENG: <https://goo.gl/forms/32FRbCfsjxJICTE63>
 - ES: <https://goo.gl/forms/OUScpBjrT1IBrp1y1>
 - CAT: <https://goo.gl/forms/AQRUqziAb2ZH4scA3>
 - GER: To be created by RBB in their internal tool.

1. What system do you prefer for subtitles?
 - a) Always visible with arrow
 - b) Fixed positioned with arrow
2. Please, explain why you prefer the above indicated option.
3. Please explain why you did not choose the other option in question 1).

4. What do you think could be improved, and how?
5. How easy was it to **read** the subtitles in “Always with arrow” mode?
 - 1- Very difficult
 - 7- Very easy
6. How easy was it to **read** the subtitles in “Fixed positioned with arrow” mode?
 - 1- Very difficult
 - 7- Very easy
7. How easy was it to **find** the subtitles in “Always visible with arrow” mode?
 - 1- Very difficult
 - 7- Very easy
8. How easy was it to **find** the subtitles in “Fixed positioned with arrow” mode?
 - 1- Very difficult
 - 7- Very easy
9. How easy was it to **find** the speaker in “Always visible with arrow” mode?
 - 1- Very difficult
 - 7- Very easy
10. How easy was it to **find** the speaker in “Fixed positioned with arrow” mode?
 - 1- Very difficult
 - 7- Very easy
11. Did you like the blinking effect in the arrows?
 - a) Yes
 - b) No
12. Other comments:

TASK 3. EMOJI vs TEXT. Duration: 15 min.

- The participants will be asked to watch the two randomised clips. Please follow the order specified in the Latin Square provided above.
 - The participant will have to watch 2 clips (C, D) with the randomised variables (1) emoji and 2) text). After watching **the two clips**, the participants will be asked to provide feedback about preferences:
 - ENG: <https://goo.gl/forms/RmmS38elbjlySIJD2>
 - ES: <https://goo.gl/forms/YmhQ2zeDvOmhgENu2>
 - CAT: <https://goo.gl/forms/OJGPzpLX0D63X2b12>
 - GER: To be created by RBB in their internal tool.
1. What system do you prefer for the sounds representation?
 - a) Emoji
 - b) Text
 2. Please, explain why you prefer the above indicated option.
 3. Please explain why you did not choose the other option in question 1).
 4. What do you think could be improved, and how?
 5. How easy was it to **understand** the representations of sound with emojis?
 - 1- Very difficult
 - 7- Very easy
 6. How easy was it to **understand** the representations of sound with text?
 - 1- Very difficult
 - 7- Very easy
 7. How easy was to **imagine** the sound represented by emojis?
 - 1- Very difficult
 - 7 - Very well
 8. How easy was to **imagine** the sound represented by the text?
 - 1- Very difficult
 - 7 - Very well
 9. Did the text representation for sounds break your immersion in the story?
 - Yes
 - No

10. Did the emojis representation for sounds break your immersion in the story?

Yes

No

11. Other comments:

FAREWELL AND THANKS to participants (1 min)

REPORTING (after the tests)

Upload your report one week after the tests under Google Drive under **IMAC_SHARED_FOLDER/ WP5/ T5.1./ 2 PRE PILOT ACTIONS - 2019 / END USER - SUB / PARTNER REPORTS.**

It must follow the template available in the same folder.

6. Questionnaires

Questionnaires will be provided to the participants using online forms, but is included below for reference.

Demographic questionnaire for home users – Version 1 (Annex 46)

SUS (Annex 43)

Open questions after SUS:

More questions...

Please, reply the open questions with your own words. The aim of these questions is to gather feedback to improve the ImAc Player and the access to the accessibility services.

11. Were you able to activate the subtitles without any help?
 - a) Yes
 - b) No
12. Were you able to select the language of the subtitles without any help?
 - a) Yes
 - b) No
13. Which other personalisation options did you use?
14. Were you able to activate/deactivate the preview for the personalisation settings without any help?
 - a) Yes
 - b) No
15. Was the preview of the personalisation settings helpful for you?
16. What did you like most about the ImAc player?
17. What did you like less about the ImAc player?
18. What do you think could be improved and how?
19. Did you miss any options? If yes, can you tell us which?
20. Other comments:

IPQ (Immersion) (Annex 44)

ANNEX 24. SUBTITLING PRE-PILOT 2 ACTIONS REPORT (CCMA)

General information

- Partner responsible: CCMA
- Place and date: Barcelona, 13.05.19 – 06.06.19
- Access service(s) discussed: subtitling.
- Demographic questionnaire
- Number of end users: 12

Demographics for users

1.	Sex	5 7 0 0	male female other prefer not to reply
2.	Age	72,66,62,71,65,44,26,28,67,63,63,32	
3.	Main language of the participants:	Catalan (10), Spanish (1), Catalan/Spanish (1)	
4.	Level of studies	0 2 5 2 3	no studies primary education secondary education further education university
5.	I define myself as a..."	7 5 0	deaf person hearing impaired person deaf-blind person
6.	Age in which your disability began	4 1 2 2 1 2 0	From birth 0-4 5-12 13-20 21-40 41-60 More than 60
7.	What technology do you use on a daily basis? You can select more than one.	11 8 4 11 7	TV PC Laptop Mobile Phone Tablet

8. How often do you watch virtual reality content (for instance, 360° videos)?

	Never	Occasionally	At least once a month	At least once a week	Every day
In smartphone	10	2	---	---	---
On a tablet	10	1	1	---	---
On a PC	9	1	2	---	---
In smartphone plugged to HMD	10	2	---	---	---
In HMD	9	3	---	---	---

9.	If you have never used virtual reality content such as 360° videos or only occasionally, please indicate why. Multiple answers are possible.	0 0 11	Because I am not interested. Because it is not accessible. Because I have not had the chance to use it. Other: (CCMA6) I use HMD
10.	Please state your level of agreement with the following statement: "I am interested in virtual reality content (such as 360° videos)."	5 6 1 0 0	I strongly agree I agree Neither agree nor disagree Disagree Strongly disagree
11.	Do you own any device to access virtual reality content?	5 7 0	Yes No I don't know or I don't want to reply
12.	If you replied "yes" to the previous question, please specify which device(s).		CCMA5 : Smartphone CCMA6 : HMD Samsung Gear, Play station VR CCMA10 : HMD CCMA11 : Tablet CCMA12 : PC, Smart TV

13. Do you like watching the following types of content on television or online?

	I like it very much	I like it	Neither like it nor dislike it	I don't like it	I don't like it at all
News	6	6	---	---	---
Fiction (series, films)	7	5	---	---	---
Talk shows	3	2	4	3	---
Documentaries	6	6	---	---	---
Sports	6	3	2	1	---
Cartoons	1	3	5	3	---

When subtitling is available, do you activate it for the following type of content?

	Always	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
News	11	---	---	1
Fiction (series, films)	11	---	---	1
Talk shows	8	2	---	2
Documentaries	11	---	---	1
Sports	8	2	1	1
Cartoons	8	2	---	2

15.	If it is available and you do not activate it, please select the reasons why.	1 11	Because the interface is not accessible. Other: CCMA(1,2,3,5,8,9,10,12) : Always activated. CCMA7: Because subtitles in Sports hides the result (football and basketball) CCMA11 : I only activate subtitles in certain contents
-----	---	---------	--

16.	How many hours a day do you watch subtitled content?	1	None
		1	Less than 1 hour
		3	1-2 hours
		4	2-3 hours
		1	3-4 hours
		2	4 hours or more
17.	What do you use subtitles for?	3	They help me understand
		8	They are my only way to have access to the dialogue
		1	I use them for language learning

Summary:

5 male and 7 female users aged between 26 and 72 took part in the tests. 10 users indicated Catalan as mother language, 1 indicated Spanish and 1 user indicated both Catalan and Spanish. Most of the users had at least a secondary education or higher. 7 testers saw themselves as deaf and 5 as hearing impaired. 4 users began disability from birth, 1 user between 0-4, 2 users between 5-12, 2 user between 13-20, 1 user between 21-40 and 2 users between 41-60.

The devices most used on a daily basis were smartphone (11 users) and TV (11 users), but also PC (8 users), Tablet (7 users) and Laptop (4 users). Most of the users had never watched VR content before, mostly because they had not the chance to. When directly asked if they were interested in VR content, 11 users agreed. The majority of the users did not own a specific device to access VR content. Most of them use smartphones, tablets and Smart TV. Particularly, 1 user owns Samsung Gear device and Play Station VR.

In terms of content preferences, the majority of the testers liked news, fiction, documentaries, and sports. Almost all of them use subtitles for all types of content. There was an even distribution between 1 and more than 4 hours among the testers in terms of how many hours a day they consume subtitled content and the majority of the testers used ST because it is their only way of accessing the dialogues.

PART 1 – Task 1 (Usability)

SUS – HMD

SUS statements	1	2	3	4	5
1. I think that I would like to use this system frequently	1	2	4	3	2
2. I found the system unnecessarily complex	4	5	1	2	---
3. I thought the system was easy to use	--	1	4	4	3
4. I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system	3	6	2	1	---
5. I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	1	---	---	4	7
6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	5	3	3	---	1
7. I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly	---	1	4	4	3
8. I found the system very cumbersome to use	2	5	3	1	1
9. I felt very confident using the system	---	1	---	8	3
10. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system	3	3	4	2	---

The SUS average score is 70.62 (above average, 68 or more is considered above average).

The graph below shows how the SUS scores associate with the percentile ranks and letter grades and the red line specifies where the ImAc player is at this moment.

The letter grade is C, and our score corresponds to the percentile rank: 41-59%.

SUS – Tablet

SUS statements	1	2	3	4	5
1. I think that I would like to use this system frequently	---	1	---	4	7
2. I found the system unnecessarily complex	8	4	---	---	---
3. I thought the system was easy to use	---	---	---	4	8
4. I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system	7	5	---	---	---
5. I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	---	---	1	5	6
6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	7	2	2	1	---
7. I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly	---	---	1	5	6
8. I found the system very cumbersome to use	9	1	---	1	1
9. I felt very confident using the system	---	---	---	3	9
10. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system	5	3	3	1	---

The SUS average score is 86.25 (above average, 68 or more is considered above average).

The graph below shows how the SUS scores associate with the percentile ranks and letter grades and the red line specifies where the ImAc player is at this moment.

The letter grade is A, and our score corresponds to the percentile rank: 96-100%.

The SUS scores obtained for the HMD interface are significantly higher for Tablet (86.25) than for HMD (70.62). $Z = -2.364$, $P = .018$, ties=1.

Open questions

1. Were you able to activate the subtitles without any help?
11 Yes
1 No
2. Were you able to select the language of the subtitles without any help?
10 Yes
2 No
3. Which other personalisation options did you use?
CCMA1: font size, position, subtitle on/off, background
CCMA2: position, background, subtitle.
CCMA3: position, size, language, indicator: arrow and radar
CCMA4: indicator: arrow and radar, position, size, background
CCMA 5: position, size, language, indicator: arrow and radar
CCMA 6: size, indicator: arrow and radar
CCMA 7: background
CCMA 8: position, language, background
CCMA 9: menu, language
CCMA 10: position, indicator: arrow and radar
CCMA 11: indicator: radar and arrow
CCMA 12: indicator: arrow and radar, position, language, background
4. Were you able to activate/deactivate the preview for the personalisation settings without any help?
11 Yes
1 No
5. Was the preview of the personalisation settings helpful for you?
9 Yes
1 No
CCMA2: I like it this way
CCMA9: It was a little bit difficult.
6. What did you like most about the ImAc player?
CCMA1: At 360°, can see the singer at my feet
CCMA2: I can ask for the most advisable options
CCMA3: Everything is Ok
CCMA4: Everything is Ok
CCMA5: I like the sharpness
CCMA6: I like the radar indicator
CCMA7: Everything is Ok
CCMA8: The interface is simple and minimalist
CCMA9: The image
CCMA10: The feeling of being inside and understanding the subtitles
CCMA11: Freedom of movements, You can look where ever you want.
CCMA12: Quick response. Easy to use.
7. What did you like less about the ImAc player?
CCMA1: Tablet is Ok, but I do not like so many head movements on HMD
CCMA2: All to movement to select options
CCMA3: Everything is Ok
CCMA4: I do not like the radar indicator
CCMA5: Everything is Ok
CCMA6: Button sensitivity
CCMA7: Nothing

CCMA8: You need much time to customize settings. Too many options.
CCMA9: Nothing
CCMA10: I feel uncomfortable with HMD
CCMA11: I feel uncomfortable with HMD. Isolate, individual.
CCMA12: I like it, but may is not so real.

8. What do you think could be improved and how?

CCMA1: HMD weight.
CCMA2: Give more information of what is displayed
CCMA3: The radar indicator should always indicate the angle you look at.
CCMA4: Do not know.
CCMA5: Not have to lower so much your head to activate the menu
CCMA6: Add sensibility settings
CCMA7: The menu bar should not be fixed so that it does not cover subtitles when you want to make any changes or settings. Increase the thickness of the subtitles with outline.
CCMA8: Simplicity to make a default configuration for next views. Improve the subtitles icon [=]
CCMA9: As my first experience, it is perfect.
CCMA10: HMD has been improved, but the fasten system is uncomfortable.
CCMA11: Everything is quite good.
CCMA12: Do not know.

9. Did you miss any options? If yes, can you tell us which?

CCMA1: No
CCMA2: An option to describe additional sounds or voices.
CCMA3: No
CCMA4: No
CCMA5: No
CCMA6: A Help button could be useful
CCMA7: It would be interesting that you can use the arrow indicator to move up/down (north/south)
CCMA8: No
CCMA9: No
CCMA10: None.
CCMA11: Subtitles colours
CCMA12: No

10. Other comments:

CCMA1: It is annoying to wait for the menu to start.
CCMA3: I like it.
CCMA11: You know which language is on when you see the first text. Also the radar indicator is much on the right, better more centered.

PART 2

TASK 2

IPQ – Always visible with arrow (I, Philip)

IPQ Question	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1. In the computer generated world I had a sense of "being there".	---	---	2	2	2	2	4
2. Somehow I felt that the virtual world surrounded me.	---	---	1	2	2	2	5
3. I felt like I was just perceiving pictures.	6	3	1	1	0	1	0
4. I did not feel present in the virtual space.	---	1	2	2	1	2	4
5. I had a sense of acting in the virtual space, rather than operating something from outside.	---	---	---	3	3	1	5
6. I felt present in the virtual space.	---	---	1	1	3	2	5
7. How aware were you of the real world surrounding while navigating in the virtual world? (i.e. sounds, room temperature, other people, etc.)?	---	---	3	3	---	4	2
8. I was not aware of my real environment.	3	3	1	2	2		
9. I still paid attention to the real environment.	4	2	1	1	2	1	1
10. I was completely captivated by the virtual world.	---	---	2	---	2	3	5
11. How real did the virtual world seem to you?	1	3	1	1	2	4	---
12. How much did your experience in the virtual environment seem consistent with your real world experience ?	1	1	2	2	2	4	---
13. How real did the virtual world seem to you?	1	---	2	3	3	2	1
14. The virtual world seemed more realistic than the real world.	3	4	---	2	1	1	1

Fixed positioned with arrow (I, Philip)

IPQ Question	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1. In the computer generated world I had a sense of "being there".	---	1	1	2	2	3	3
2. Somehow I felt that the virtual world surrounded me.	---	1	---	3	1	4	3
3. I felt like I was just perceiving pictures.	6	2	1	1	2	---	---
4. I did not feel present in the virtual space.	---	---	1	2	2	4	3
5. I had a sense of acting in the virtual space, rather than operating something from outside.	---	---	---	5	1	2	4
6. I felt present in the virtual space.	---	---	1	2	3	2	4
7. How aware were you of the real world surrounding while navigating in the virtual world? (i.e. sounds, room temperature, other people, etc.)?	---	2	1	1	4	2	2
8. I was not aware of my real environment.	2	1	---	3	1	3	2
9. I still paid attention to the real environment.	3	---	2	3	---	4	---
10. I was completely captivated by the virtual world.	---	1	3	---	2	3	3
11. How real did the virtual world seem to you?	1	2	2	2	1	4	---
12. How much did your experience in the virtual environment seem consistent with your real world experience ?	---	2	4	2	1	1	2
13. How real did the virtual world seem to you?	1	2	2	---	4	3	---
14. The virtual world seemed more realistic than the real world.	1	3	4	1	2	1	---

Median scores for each subscale on the IPQ questionnaire, for both Always Visible Arrow and Fixed Position conditions

	General Presence	Spatial Presence	Involvement	Experienced Realism
Always Visible	6	5.4	3.88	3.50
Fixed Position	5.50	5.2	3.88	3.50

The comparison of each of the subscales of IPQ questionnaire does not show any significant difference between the two conditions (General presence $Z=-.535$, $p= .592$, ties=9; Spatial presence $Z=-.479$, $p=.632$, ties=3; Involvement $Z=-.724$, $p=.469$, ties=3; Experienced realism $Z= -.178$, $p= .859$, ties=3)

Preferences & Usability (always vs fixed)

1. What system do you prefer for subtitles?

a) Always visible with arrow	b) Fixed positioned with arrow
10	2

2. Please, explain why you prefer the above indicated option.

CCMA1: always visible: I know who is speaking and where to look at.

CCMA2: always visible: I can see what is happening from different points of view.

CCMA3: always visible: You do not miss content.

CCMA4: fixed positioned: Each speaker has its own "voice"

CCMA5: always visible: You always know where to look at and do not spend time looking for the word.

CCMA6: always visible: It helps to locate easily the character.

CCMA7: always visible: This way, you always know what they say

CCMA8: always visible: Just to avoid missing dialogue.

CCMA9: fixed positioned: Easier to read

CCMA10: always visible: More comfortable

CCMA11: always visible: In fixed positioned, you can not read all the text

CCMA12: always visible: It seems as if I hear normally

3. Please explain why you did not choose the other option in question 1).

CCMA1: fixed positioned avoids body language.

CCMA2: fixed positioned is too static.

CCMA3: because of the loss of information.

CCMA4: It is not so personal

CCMA5: You lose reading time and words.

CCMA6: subtitles better accompanied with head movement in real time

CCMA7: Because you lose "x" time searching who is speaking and you have less time to read.

CCMA8: Arrow indicator appears when you are out of the angular position so you lose information.

CCMA9: It is difficult to follow

CCMA10: If the image is moving, it is logical that subtitle also moves.

CCMA11: The fact that subtitles go with the person means that you can not continue the conversation at different times ... and this makes you realize that you are having a virtual world test.

CCMA12: In the real world, if a person is speaking and I do not look at him, I can not get the information. I always want to get all information even I do not look at who is speaking

4. What do you think could be improved, and how?

CCMA1: I don't know

CCMA2: More information, music, noises, and so...

CCMA3: Fixed positioned text is centered in the display big. It should be smaller and positioned lower.

CCMA4: I don't know

CCMA5: I like the options that I use normally.

CCMA6: Depending on each character, it would be great the possibility of improving customization of subtitles colour.

CCMA7: When you move searching the subtitles, subtitles should move in "scroll" in the opposite direction of the user's movement.

CCMA8: Improve the precision of the deflection angle. Identify what I'm talking about.

CCMA9: I don't know .

CCMA10: HMD devices should be improved. More comfortable.

CCMA11: Always use "Always visible" option.

CCMA12: Fixed positioned subtitles are in a wrong position, too low and they do not allow to see the image correctly.

5. How easy was it to read the subtitles in “always visible with arrow” mode?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7- very easy
	---	---	---	---	6	6

6. How easy was it to read the subtitles in “fixed positioned with arrow” mode?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7- very easy
2	---	2	1	---	1	6

7. How easy was it to find the subtitles in “always visible with arrow” mode?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7- very easy
---	---	--	---	---	4	8

8. How easy was it to find the subtitles in “fixed positioned with arrow” mode?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7- very easy
1	2	1	1	---	3	4

9. How easy was it to find the speaker in “always visible with arrow” mode?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7- very easy
---	---	1	---	---	5	6

10. How easy was it to find the speaker in “fixed positioned with arrow” mode?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7- very easy
---	2	---	1	---	4	5

11. Did you like the blinking effect in the arrows?

9 Yes
3 No

12. Other comments:

CCMA1: Fixed positioned, I think is not a suitable position.
 CCMA2: Arrow indicator should appear before related text.
 CCMA7: I did not notice the blinking effect.
 CCMA8: Subtitles should be in a lower position so they do not cover scenario.
 CCMA9: This is my first experience. Do not know how to improve it. I think is great!

TASK 3

Preferences (emoji vs text)

1. What system do you prefer for the sounds/feelings representation?

a) Emoji	b) Text
2	10

2. Please, explain why you prefer the above indicated option.

CCMA1: text: I already see that the character is smiling or crying.
 CCMA2: text: I understand text better. Emoji seems for kids...
 CCMA3: text: I like emoji, but I am used to text.
 CCMA4: text: I am used to text.
 CCMA5: text: Text seems to be more serious.
 CCMA6: emoji : Gives you the possibility to add links to more content.
 CCMA7: text: You get more information.
 CCMA8: text: It has always been done this way.
 CCMA9: text : It is more real.
 CCMA10: emoji : It is more fun

CCMA11: text : You can understand text better.
 CCMA12: text : I think with text you can refine what you are feeling.

3. Please explain why you did not choose the other option in question 1).

CCMA1: text: Emoji are for kids..
 CCMA2: text: Emoji could be fine for cartoon or content for kids.
 CCMA3: text: I am used.
 CCMA4: text: In my opinion text is better. I think could adapt myself to emoji easily..
 CCMA5: text: I do not like emoji in this context
 CCMA6: emoji : Text limits to create links to more information, but it is also comfortable.
 CCMA7: text: Emoji are for children and are not accurate.
 CCMA8: text: emoji are simple and maybe confused
 CCMA9: text : emoji are not suitable for informative text. They are not usual.
 CCMA10: emoji : Text is classic and maybe not so agile.
 CCMA11: text : You can understand words better.
 CCMA12: text : Emoji are generic.

4. What do you think could be improved, and how?

CCMA1: Sometimes arrow indicators are missing.
 CCMA2: Sentences jump from one character to another and are not clear.
 CCMA3: Sound presentation (text o emoji) should be displayed all the time.
 CCMA4: I think it is perfect.
 CCMA5: I do not know
 CCMA6: There should be several play modes, such as one with extra content that you could select by the cursor.
 CCMA7: Emoji do not understand.
 CCMA8: Insert arrow indicator to locate where the sound comes from.
 CCMA9: I think it is perfect.
 CCMA10: I do not know
 CCMA11: Always keep text on display. Remove redundancies. If you hear music do not put music symbol.
 CCMA12: I do not know

5. How easy was it to understand the representations of sound/feelings with emoji?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7- very easy
---	1	2	1	---	3	5

6. How easy was it to understand the representations of sound/feelings with text?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7- very easy
--	---	---	---	2	1	9

7. How easy was to imagine the sound represented by emoji?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7- very easy
---	2	1	---	2	3	4

8. How easy was to imagine the sound represented by the text?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7- very easy
---	---	---	---	2	1	9

9. Did the text representation for sounds break your immersion in the story

1 Yes
 11 No

10. Did the emoji representation for sounds break your immersion in the story? –

6 Yes
 6 No

11. Other comments:

CCMA1: No emoji needed. Not serious. Emoji can distract. Perhaps disabled people that include slowness.

CCMA2: More sound indicators are needed, such as breathing and tone of voice.

CCMA9: A great experience to me.

CCMA11: Sometimes text is redundant.

Conclusions

Task 1 – User interface

The user interface is welcome by the users, and the ones that participated before were very happy with this improved version.

Almost all were able to activate subtitles, after the interviewer's explanation.

Sometimes the users were confused trying to set language, the doubt was to change language in the main page or in the accessibility menu.

Most of them agreed with the settings, but here are some comments :

Radar is more accurate now, compared to last pilot.

Using HMD is difficult to enter menu. You must low your head in excess. Better if only a click is needed.

When menu is displayed, subtitles are behind. It is difficult to verify you have correct settings.

Task 2 – Subtitles : always visible vs fixed on speaker

A majority of users (10 vs 2) preferred the always visible subtitles. The main reasons were that they don't want to miss information, they are easy to read and are more comfortable.

Some users expressed that the fixed subtitles forces to move the head repeatedly in order to follow the conversation.

Improvements:

If 2 characters are close, subtitles of one of them are not shown.

Task 3 – Sound representation : textual vs emoji

Most of the users preferred textual representation of sound. Some users agreed it was not serious and they thought hat the look is for kids. The description of sound with text is easy to understand, emoji could have different meanings depending on user's age.

ANNEX 25. SUBTITLING PRE-PILOT 2 ACTIONS REPORT (RBB)

Report for subtitle pre-pilot test 2

General information

- Partner responsible: RBB
- Place and date: 06.05.19 – 24.05.19
- Access service(s) discussed: *subtitling*.
- Demographic questionnaire
- Number of end users: 12

Demographics for users

1.	Sex	8 4 0 0	male female other prefer not to reply
2.	Age	29, 30, 44, 61, 42, 33, 21, 47, 16, 40, 40	
3.	Main language of the participants:	German sign language (4x), German (8x), Swiss sign language (1x)	
4.	Level of studies	1 1 0 4 6	no studies primary education secondary education further education university
5.	I define myself as a..."	5 6 0 1	deaf person hearing impaired person deaf-blind person other: RBB9: minor hearing loss
6.	Age in which your disability began	6 4 0 0 1 1 0	From birth 0-4 5-12 13-20 21-40 41-60 More than 60
7.	What technology do you use on a daily basis? You can select more than one.	5 4 6 12 6 0 1	TV PC Laptop Mobile Phone Tablet Head Mounted Display (HMD) Other: RBB1: ebook reader

8. How often do you watch virtual reality content (for instance, 360° videos)?

	Never	Occasionally	At least once a month	At least once a week	Every day
In smartphone	9	1	1	1	
On a tablet	9	1	2		
On a PC	11		1		
In smartphone plugged to HMD	10	2			
In HMD	9	3			

9.	If you have never used virtual reality content such as 360° videos or only occasionally, please indicate why. Multiple answers are possible.	0 3 6 4	Because I am not interested. Because it is not accessible. Because I have not had the chance to use it. Other reasons: RBB1not much content, not common and expensive; RBB3: no interesting content known, RBB4: I'm waiting for AR glasses for ST, RBB6: I've never tried it
10.	Please state your level of agreement with the following statement: "I am interested in virtual reality content (such as 360° videos)."	2 6 3 0 0	I strongly agree I agree Neither agree nor disagree Disagree Strongly disagree
11.	Do you own any device to access virtual reality content?	3 8 1	Yes No I don't know or I don't want to reply
12.	If you replied "yes" to the previous question, please specify which device(s).		RBB3: Apple iPad, RBB1: smartphone and tablet

13. Do you like watching the following types of content on television or online?

	I like it very much	I like it	Neither like it nor dislike it	I don't like it	I don't like it at all
News	6	3	2	1	
Fiction (series, films)	7	5			
Talk shows	2	3	3	2	2
Documentaries	6	4		1	1
Sports	3	3	2	2	2
Cartoons	1	7	2	1	1

14. When subtitling is available, do you activate it for the following type of content?

	Always	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
News	11			1
Fiction (series, films)	11		1	
Talk shows	8	2		2
Documentaries	10			2
Sports	9	2		1
Cartoons	10	1		1

15.	If it is available and you do not activate it, please select the reasons why.	1 0 11	Because the interface is not accessible. Because I don't want subtitling in all the content, only in certain types of content. Other: RBB1: maybe only nice video without speaking person, RBB2, RBB4, RBB5, RBB6, RBB7, RBB8, RBB11: I always use subtitles, RBB9: I can hear pretty well. RBB10: shortened sentences and fast subtitles, RBB12: I don't watch talk shows
16.	How many hours a day do you watch subtitled content?	1 2 3 5	None Less than 1 hour 1-2 hours 2-3 hours

		1 0	3-4 hours 4 hours or more
17.	What do you use subtitles for?	8 1 1 1	They help me understand They are my only way to have access to the dialogue I use them for language learning Other: RBB3, RBB11: wanted to select all reasons, RBB6: I'm deaf and can only follow the content with subtitles

PART 1 – Task 1 (Usability)

SUS – HMD

SUS statements	1	2	3	4	5
1. I think that I would like to use this system frequently		1	4	2	5
2. I found the system unnecessarily complex	2	7	3		
3. I thought the system was easy to use				8	4
4. I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system	4	5		1	2
5. I found the various functions in this system were well integrated			3	3	6
6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	4	2	3	2	1
7. I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly				2	10
8. I found the system very cumbersome to use	2	4	2	1	3
9. I felt very confident using the system			1	6	5
10. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system	6	4		1	1

The SUS average score is 74.79 (above average, 68 or more is considered above average).

The graph below shows how the SUS scores associate with the percentile ranks and letter grades and the red line specifies where the ImAc player is at this moment.

The letter grade is B, and our score corresponds to the percentile rank: 70-79%.

SUS – Tablet

SUS statements	1	2	3	4	5
1. I think that I would like to use this system frequently		2	1	4	5
2. I found the system unnecessarily complex	1	3	6	1	1
3. I thought the system was easy to use		1	6	3	2
4. I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system	3	2	1	6	
5. I found the various functions in this system were well integrated		4	4	3	1
6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	3		3	6	
7. I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly				1	11
8. I found the system very cumbersome to use	3	3	3	2	1
9. I felt very confident using the system		2	1	7	2
10. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system	3	3	4	2	

The SUS average score is 63.96 (below average, 68 or more is considered above average).

The graph below shows how the SUS scores associate with the percentile ranks and letter grades and the red line specifies where the ImAc subtitle editor is at this moment.

The letter grade is C-, and our score corresponds to the percentile rank: 35-40%.

A Wilcoxon signed ranks test comparing the SUS ratings for HMD and Tablet shows statistical differences between them ($Z=-2.091$; $p = .036$).

Open questions

1. Were you able to activate the subtitles without any help?
 - 7 Yes
 - 4 No
2. Were you able to select the language of the subtitles without any help?
 - 2 Yes
 - 10 No
3. Which other personalisation options did you use?
 - RBB1: font size, colour? – Comment from interviewer: this functionality is not included, position
 - RBB2: font size, position, background
 - RBB3: font size, position, background
 - RBB4: position, size, background
 - RBB5: position, background, size, language, indicator: arrow and radar
 - RBB6: sound on/off, pause, size
 - RBB7: size, position, background
 - RBB8: size, position, language, indicator and background
 - RBB9: position
 - RBB10: size, position
 - RBB11: position, indicator: radar and arrow, area: small and large
 - RBB12: size, position, background
4. Were you able to activate/deactivate the preview for the personalisation settings without any help?
 - 5 Yes
 - 7 No
5. Was the preview of the personalisation settings helpful for you?
 - 4 Yes
 - 6 No,
 - RBB4: I didn't recognised it
 - RBB6: I don't need this feature.
 - RBB5: no answer

RBB9: no answer
RBB11: Changes should be visible immediately!
RBB12: I didn't use it

6. What did you like most about the ImAc player?

RBB1: Emojis and subtitles fixed to speaker
RBB2: change position to top
RBB3: subtitles are always in the field of view
RBB4: the settings menu to change the presentation and see all the changes
RBB5: I liked the menu, it opens in a fixed position and it is easy to open and close it
RBB6: nothing special
RBB7: looks great
RBB8: the 360° experience, a lot of settings to personalise subtitles
RBB9: player was similar to other ones
RBB10: 3D presentation, 360°, real situation, menu
RBB11: subtitles always visible and follow the head movement, 360° experience, to have the possibility to look around
RBB12: it is possible to open and close the menu

7. What did you like less about the ImAc player?

RBB1: open the menu by looking to the floor
RBB2: to change the volume you need to click for each level change
RBB3: old-fashioned design, dark
RBB4: button to activate/deactivate subtitles was not clear. Why was it not under settings?
RBB5: nothing
RBB6: settings for language are under accessibility and not in the subtitle menu I expected it under subtitles
RBB7: nothing
RBB8: nothing
RBB9: inconsistency in language settings
RBB10: video quality
RBB11: large menu was disturbing; cross to close the menu was too small
RBB12: setting for subtitle language was too complex to find (Netflix solution would be better)

8. What do you think could be improved and how?

RBB1: just one click on the controller to pause the video and open the menu
RBB2: language settings should be under another menu item
RBB3: wording for settings, especially accessibility, indicator, no blinking arrows, subtitles are flickering,
RBB5: menu could be nicer and clearer, subtitle should not be displayed behind the menu
RBB6: open the menu with one click on the controller or directly with a button at the VR glasses, tablet: open menu by tapping on the screen as it is in Netflix
RBB7: icon for subtitles is not good, better to add "UT"
RBB8: nothing
RBB9: language settings
RBB10: quality of video, language settings for subtitles should be under subtitle menu
RBB11: size of menu should be adjustable; another way to open the menu; allow scrolling in menu; size, colour and font of subtitles should be adjustable; automatic change of subtitle background according to video content; subtitles: more description about emotions e.g. loud or angry - feelings in brackets; same symbol and wording for language of menu and accessibility
language is difficult: subtitle language, the cross to close the menu was too small
RBB12: same solution for subtitle language as Netflix

9. Did you miss any options? If yes, can you tell us which?

RBB2: change colour for subtitles
RBB3: open menu without nodding one's head
RBB4: integration into TV services
RBB5: no

- RBB6: no
- RBB7: additional information???
- RBB8: help or short explanation for each menu item would be good
- RBB9: skip video by chapter
- RBB10: colour of subtitles, scale size in percentage – refined settings
- RBB11: colour, size and font of subtitle should be adjustable
- RBB12: no

10. Other comments:

RBB3: programming error: 1) preview functionality: after 2 seconds the video continue (comment of the interviewer: tester pauses the video to do the settings and after the preview the video starts again, tester expected that the video still pauses), 2) separation of accessibility settings from subtitles menu is not comprehensible 3) term accessibility is not appealing and expedient

RBB4: the isolated usage is strange and prevents the communication with other people especially when someone reads from the lips to understand the content

RBB7: subtitles should not disappear behind the menu, didn't find the subtitles language in the menu, symbol for music: contrast was not high enough – critical for people with colour blindness, in general you can quickly get used to anything

RBB9: subtitles under accessibility is not logical

RBB10: nice design of subtitles

PART 2

TASK 2

IPQ – Always visible with arrow (I, Philip)

RBB11: didn't fill in the questionnaire

IPQ Question	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1. In the computer generated world I had a sense of "being there".		1	2	1	1	1	5
2. Somehow I felt that the virtual world surrounded me.	1	1	2	1	1	2	3
3. I felt like I was just perceiving pictures.	4	2			1	2	2
4. I did not feel present in the virtual space.	2	3	2	1	0	2	1
5. I had a sense of acting in the virtual space, rather than operating something from outside.	6	2			2	1	
6. I felt present in the virtual space.	1	2		2	2	3	1
7. How aware were you of the real world surrounding while navigating in the virtual world? (i.e. sounds, room temperature, other people, etc.)?	1		2	2		1	5
8. I was not aware of my real environment.	3	3	1	2	2		
9. I still paid attention to the real environment.	1	4	1	1	1	3	
10. I was completely captivated by the virtual world.			1		3	3	4
11. How real did the virtual world seem to you?	2	2	4			2	1
12. How much did your experience in the virtual environment seem consistent with your real world experience ?	1	2	1	3	1	2	1
13. How real did the virtual world seem to you?	1	4				3	3
14.The virtual world seemed more realistic	4	4				3	

IPQ Question	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
than the real world.							

Fixed positioned with arrow (I, Philip)

IPQ Question	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1. In the computer generated world I had a sense of "being there".	1	2			3	2	3
2. Somehow I felt that the virtual world surrounded me.		2	1	1	2	2	3
3. I felt like I was just perceiving pictures.	2	2	2		1	3	1
4. I did not feel present in the virtual space.	3		3		1	2	2
5. I had a sense of acting in the virtual space, rather than operating something from outside.	5	2	1	1	1	1	
6. I felt present in the virtual space.	3	1			4	2	1
7. How aware were you of the real world surrounding while navigating in the virtual world? (i.e. sounds, room temperature, other people, etc.)?	1	1	2			3	4
8. I was not aware of my real environment.	4	2	1		3		1
9. I still paid attention to the real environment.	2		3			5	1
10. I was completely captivated by the virtual world.		2			1	6	2
11. How real did the virtual world seem to you?	2		1	1	1	5	1
12. How much did your experience in the virtual environment seem consistent with your real world experience ?	3				3	4	1
13. How real did the virtual world seem to you?	1	2	1	2	2	1	2
14.The virtual world seemed more realistic than the real world.	5	2	2		1	1	

Mean scores for each subscale on the IPQ questionnaire, for both Always Visible Arrow and Fixed Position conditions

	General Presence	Spatial Presence	Involvement	Experienced Realism
Always Visible	5.27	3.4364	4.0227	3.4318
Fixed Position	4.8182	3.4909	3.7500	3.0909

Median scores:

	General Presence	Spatial Presence	Involvement	Experienced Realism
Always Visible	6	3.60	4.25	3.50
Fixed Position	5	3.44	4	3.25

The comparison of each of the subscales of IPQ questionnaire does not show any significant difference between the two conditions (General presence $Z=-1.186$, $p= .236$; Spatial presence $Z=-.358$, $p=.721$; Involvement $Z=-1.162$, $p=.245$; Experienced realism $Z= -.848$, $p= .396$)

Preferences & Usability (always vs fixed)

1. What system do you prefer for subtitles?

a) Always visible with arrow	b) Fixed positioned with arrow
9	3

2. Please, explain why you prefer the above indicated option.

- RBB1: fixed positioned: it was easier to identify the speaker
- RBB2: always visible: you did not miss content
- RBB3: always visible: you can look where you want to and "listen" to any content
- RBB4: fixed positioned: subtitles are more integrated, more intuitive to follow conversation
- RBB5: always visible: otherwise I miss content, I would like to explore freely the 360° scene without missing any content, the colour of the arrow helps to understand who is speaking
- RBB6: always visible: speaker identification with colours is good. good to have both options to choose from
- RBB7: always visible: subtitles follow head movement, and with the help of the arrows I know where the speaker is
- RBB8: always visible: it is easier to allocate the subtitles to the speaker and the colour also helped
- RBB9: always visible: subtitles are always available
- RBB10: always visible: is more comfortable as I don't need to move the head constantly
- RBB11: always visible: I didn't miss any content
- RBB12: fixed to speaker: is more like in real life

3. Please explain why you did not choose the other option in question 1).

- RBB1: always visible subtitles is more for hearing users, but is also okay for the translation from another language
- RBB2: the subtitles were already gone when I had the speaker in my field of view
- RBB3: subtitles from OFF-speaker were placed on the carpet. Fixing the subtitles creates barriers, because you cannot move freely in the room. You can't follow the subtitles as fast as the dialogues are.
- RBB4: confusing – arrow should only disappear when the speaker is completely out of the field of view
- RBB5: miss content and could not move freely
- RBB6: subtitles always visible are better for dialogues so that you don't miss any content, VR glasses: subtitles bottom centered, tablet: subtitles fixed to speaker, video excerpt is important
- RBB7: too many visual impressions, I missed subtitles and it was exhausting
- RBB8: subtitles at the bottom and then fixed to the speaker in a very fast way, this is exhausting for the eyes
- RBB9: I missed subtitles
- RBB10: I missed some subtitles
- RBB11: I need to move the head a lot and missed some subtitles especially when the speakers are far apart and they speak quickly
- RBB12: I don't like it so much to have the subtitles all the time as this disturbs the viewing experience

4. What do you think could be improved, and how?

- RBB1: viewing angle is generally too wide
- RBB2: partly the subtitles were displayed very low

RBB3: determining and adjusting the anatomically optimal position for subtitles; video quality too bad: it was not possible to read lips; subtitles were placed too far at the bottom; subtitles were flickering

RBB4: noting

RBB6: subtitles together with arrow and additionally name of the speaker

RBB7: quality of presentation of the subtitles

RBB9: for subtitles fixed to speaker: it would be better if the arrows were displayed earlier to prepare the user that someone will be speaking soon and I have more time to change my field of view

RBB10: set colours for subtitles for (supporting) actors

RBB11: subtitles in always visible were flickering with the head movement, it was more comfortable to read the fixed subtitles at the speaker; it would be good to add an arrow on top of the speaker very briefly when the speaker is in my field of view to show that this person is speaking, a combination of always visible and fixed subtitles would be good, (additional explanation by interviewer: it was not possible to complete the whole test because the user gave a lot of feedback and we ran out of time)

5. How easy was it to read the subtitles in “always visible with arrow” mode?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7- very easy
		2		1		8

6. How easy was it to read the subtitles in “fixed positioned with arrow” mode?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7- very easy
1	2	1		4	2	1

7. How easy was it to find the subtitles in “always visible with arrow” mode?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7- very easy
	1			1	3	6

8. How easy was it to find the subtitles in “fixed positioned with arrow” mode?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7- very easy
3	2	2		2	2	

9. How easy was it to find the speaker in “always visible with arrow” mode?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7- very easy
2	1	2		2	1	3

10. How easy was it to find the speaker in “fixed positioned with arrow” mode?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7- very easy
2	2	2	1	1	2	1

11. Did you like the blinking effect in the arrows? – 2 didn’t answer as we were not aware of this new question and added it for tester RBB4

7 Yes

2 No ; RBB3: he explicitly said that he didn’t like the blinking effect so interviewer counted this as no afterwards

12. Other comments:

RBB3: Hearing is omnipresent and therefore assistance should always be present.

RBB4: maybe better to have subtitles only bottom centered? So one has more time to explore the 360° scene

RBB6: important are colours and introduction of the name of the speaker (in the opening credits) with brackets, arrow in colour also helps to lead to the right speaker

RBB7: subtitles should not flicker or be blurry, change of colours could be a problem for colour blind people – would be good to have this as one option in the settings, fonts should be adjustable, I didn’t recognize the blinking effect of the arrows

- RBB9: I sometimes missed subtitles; the spatial allocation of the subtitles is pointless as I identify the speaker with the colours
 RBB10: additional settings would be helpful
 RBB11: I liked the explanation of the sound

TASK 3

Preferences (emoji vs text)

1. What system do you prefer for the sounds/feelings representation?

a) Emoji	b) Text
2	9

2. Please, explain why you prefer the above indicated option.

- RBB1: emojis: visual, more comprehensible, more perceptible
 RBB2: text: clearer and more constant
 RBB3: text: greater variety of expressions
 RBB4: text: more comprehensive representation of sounds, e.g. what kind of footsteps or which music
 RBB5: text: it was clearer and easier to understand
 RBB6: text: I'm used to it; text is an original description and clearer to understand
 RBB7: emojis: funny, easily detectable
 RBB8: text: easier to understand and more comfortable
 RBB9: text: more serious
 RBB10: text: clear meaning
 RBB 12: text: I'm used to it

3. Please explain why you did not choose the other option in question 1).

- RBB1: text: not visual enough first read and then understand
 RBB2: emojis: not clear and very silly, you cannot recognize well
 RBB3: less expressions, one-dimensional
 RBB4: graduations with emojis are very limited
 RBB5: emojis are translated differently by users, so the meaning is different
 RBB6: emojis can be interpreted; do not give as much information as text
 RBB7: text: boring
 RBB8: you have to pay too much attention and think a lot about the meaning
 RBB9: too playful
 RBB10: I have to recognize the meaning of the emojis.
 RBB 12: funny

4. What do you think could be improved, and how?

- RBB1: emojis larger, integrate accents
 RBB2: describe sound in text as specifically as possible
 RBB3: It is questionable how emojis can represent hearing impressions. The language offers an enormous range.
 RBB4: -
 RBB5: -
 RBB6: -
 RBB7: combine both emojis and text
 RBB8: -
 RBB9: italic font would be good too, to differentiate it from the spoken word
 RBB10: it should be adjustable so that the user can select according to his/her preference
 RBB12: -

5. How easy was it to understand the representations of sound/feelings with emojis?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7- very easy
		2	1	2		6

6. How easy was it to understand the representations of sound/feelings with text?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7- very easy
			1		2	8

7. How easy was to imagine the sound represented by emojis?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7- very easy
1	3	3			1	3

8. How easy was to imagine the sound represented by the text?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7- very easy
		2			3	6

9. Did the text representation for sounds break your immersion in the story? – added this question for RBB4 – we were not aware of this question before

8 Yes
0 No

10. Did the emojis representation for sounds break your immersion in the story? – added this question for RBB4 – we were not aware of this question before

5 Yes
3 No

11. Other comments:

RBB4: language and text must have priority, the presentation of sounds should not be overloaded

RBB5: -

RBB7: I know emojis from my smartphone

RBB10: show both settings at the beginning

Conclusions

User interface

Most of the users were able to activate the subtitles although it was possible only with trying out the available buttons. Additional remark by interviewer: Some of the users recognised the explanation for the different icons in the settings menu and were afterwards able to select the right one for subtitles. Consequently, we propose to add the abbreviations to the icons for the services and it would also be good to have them already at the ImAc portal.

The majority of the users needed intensive help to find the language settings for the subtitles. Comment by interviewer: The users always started with the subtitles menu and were confused that they couldn't find the language settings there. Afterwards they tried "general" as well as "accessibility" menu and were confused that they both contain language settings with the same icon.

The preview functionality was mainly important for the usage on the tablet as the activated subtitles are behind the menu. Most of the users found this feature just by trying available functionalities. This preview is not necessary for most of the users and one user explicitly said that all changes should be visible immediately.

In general, all users liked the variety of personalisation settings.

Improvements/criticism:

Open the menu by one click / tap on the touch screen

Settings for language: the language settings for subtitles should be in the subtitle menu

Subtitles should not open behind the menu

Preview: after 2 seconds the video continue although it was paused before the users activated the preview (comment of the interviewer: tester paused the video to do the settings and after the preview the video started again, tester expected that the video still pauses)

Add abbreviation of service to the icon

Task 1 – subtitles always visible vs fixed on speaker

A clear majority of the users preferred the always visible subtitles. The main reasons were that they don't want to miss content and the very fast change of the position of the subtitles from the bottom (off-speaker) to the speaker was very exhausting for the eyes.

Some users expressed that the fixed subtitles were positive to have a clear identification of the speaker and it is a more intuitive way to follow the conversation. Additionally, the fixed subtitles are easier to read and don't flicker as it is the case for the always visible subtitles when the user moves the head fast. They liked the colours of the arrow in the fixed subtitles as this helps to identify the speaker and as soon as the user knows which speaker is where, it was easy to move the head in the right direction.

In general, the content, the speed of a conversation and the position of the speaker in the field of view are important aspects for the choice between fixed or always visible subtitles. One user explicitly stated that a combination of both modes would be good.

Improvements:

Off-speaker subtitles were placed too far at the bottom

Task 2 – sound representation textual vs emojis

There was a clear majority for the textual representation of sound. The description of sound with text enables more comprehensive and precise information. The interpretation of emojis is very different from user to user and it takes more time to understand the meaning.

ANNEX 26. METHODOLOGY FOR AUDIO DESCRIPTION/ AUDIO SUBTITLING PRE-PILOT ACTIONS 2

1. **What to test?**

- Three pilot actions will be performed:
 - **Interface interaction (menu)** (Test 1). Link to the player: <https://imac.gpac-licensing.com/playertest/>
 - **Three AD presentation modes** (Test 2) AD-C, AD-S, AD-D. Please notice that the end users will not know whether the mode they are testing is Classic, Static or Dynamic, but we use these codes (C-S-D) because it will be easier for the researcher to identify what questionnaire to administer.
 - **Two AST presentation modes** (Test 3) AST-C and AST-D.

2. **When?**

From 1st May 2019 to 1st July 2019.

3. **Methodology: overview**

- **Partners responsible for the test:** RNIB (UK), UAB (Spain).
- **Research tools:** online questionnaires (Google Forms).
- **Measures:** Presence (IPQ questionnaire), preferences (open and closed questions) and usability (SUS questionnaire).
- **Participants:** 10 participants with sight loss will take part in the study. From a methodological point of view, the sample should be as balanced as possible: 5 blind and 5 low vision is what we should aim at.
- **Language of the experiment:** English (RNIB), Catalan and Spanish (UAB).
- **Experimental protocol:** The study will be individual testing, comprising 3 actions. In each test, users will be asked to perform certain tasks and then report on immersion, preferences and/or usability through online questionnaires.
- **Reporting:** RNIB and UAB will include the results on a report template provided by UAB: https://docs.google.com/document/d/1FaajncfdJldtJUztiVLW3qqL6Lx_F_c5tFsxru7yUJo/edit Please download it, fill it in and upload it under WP5/T5.1/End users AD/ Partners Reports adding UAB or RNIB to the file name.
- **The current methodology will be tested by UAB and RNIB previous to the test.**
- **Recruitment:** Participants will be recruited via user associations, personal contacts and social networks, if necessary.
- **Duration:** approx. 90 minutes.
- **Facilitator:** One facilitator will be involved. The facilitator will be the leader (welcoming participants, explaining the project, explaining the test) and will assist the sessions (by providing the online questionnaires and helping to fill them in, providing technical assistance with the devices, etc.).

4. **Methodology: experimental protocol**

The experiment will include three different tests. A within subject design will be used. In Test 2, each participant will see three clips in the following order: clip 1 (Episode 1), clip 2 (Episode 2) and clip 3 (Episode 3). An audio introduction will be played at the beginning of the test, prior to the clips (NOT before each clip). The presentation modes (AD-C, AD-S and AD-D) will be randomized across participants. In Test 3, each participant will see 2 clips. The order of the clips will be: part 1 followed by part 2, but the presentation modes will be randomized (AST-C, AST-D)

	Description	Links	Time
Introduction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Welcome and presentation of the ImAc project, the aim of the experiment and the procedure (5 minutes) Fill in a consent form and a demographic questionnaire (10 minutes). Each participant is assigned with an individual participant code. Each participant needs to enter that code in online questionnaires. Codes for RNIB: RNIB1, RNIB2... Codes for UAB: UAB1, UAB2... Explain 360° videos and HMD, if unknown to a participant (1 minute). Ask participants if they have any questions (5 minutes or buffer time). 	<p>Provide the participant with the consent form for ethical clearance. Include the name of the researcher performing the test. You can find the last version here. Feel free to use an oral recorded version or a written version but provide originals to UAB. https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1X5Nj9KxkpFVwvEuKfk6XVgz0VFUSzUOS</p> <p>If you pay a compensation, the forms are under WP1/Deliverables/D1.2. Ethical forms/ Ethical forms if compensation is provided (April 2019)</p> <p>Demographic questionnaire:</p> <p>CAT https://forms.gle/tkVeNpuQxfiqbjDT6</p> <p>EN https://forms.gle/HZosuWN1QGJqRxJ7</p> <p>ES https://forms.gle/3GZBFmRDLZeioGmJ6</p>	20 minutes
Test 1: Interface interaction (menu)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participants are asked to complete a few tasks in the menu in HMD. Participants are asked to fill in the SUS questionnaire. Participants are asked to fill in the additional preference questionnaire. 	<p>SUS(CAT): https://forms.gle/8dJJ5kvzyXXvnrgs8</p> <p>SUS (EN): https://forms.gle/PqnongggJDEoSkvfZ</p> <p>SUS (ES) https://forms.gle/HCKTn795oK65aHPzZ</p> <p>Additional preference questionnaire:</p> <p>CAT https://forms.gle/ooZjmusbUEsr5VFtZ</p> <p>EN https://forms.gle/3Yq9rQuX3LbPwH2V6</p> <p>ES https://forms.gle/xZDE9QWqT45Sfdpc6</p>	20 minutes

<p>Test 2: AD</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participants are asked to watch three videos with AD modes in a randomized order in HMD. They listen to the one general audio introduction. After each video, participants reply to IPQ questionnaire. Participants are asked to fill in the post-questionnaire (preference questions). <p>Important: before watching each video, participants are advised to move their head around to have a full experience.</p>	<p>IPQ AD-C (CAT) https://forms.gle/ZjfmbxXzGSUpj9sCA IPQ AD-S (CAT) https://forms.gle/yivjHr8UgnGG4NPv5 IPQ AD-D (CAT) https://forms.gle/5MjhBWTsn8KGP Hvp7</p> <p>IPQ AD-C (EN) https://forms.gle/jXjppexsnaJTPxHR9 IPQ AD-S (EN) https://forms.gle/ei2YFjPHZKmpcFA3A IPQ AD-D (EN): https://forms.gle/oAnwSHwK2xRBpy7k6</p> <p>IPQ AD-C (ES) https://forms.gle/1XrP6tytGNLjXbU27 IPQ AD-S (ES) https://forms.gle/HHrQRp8EwaHEoeu37 IPQ AD-D (ES) https://forms.gle/13PaB7TjzHSvWzmc7</p> <p>Post-questionnaire (CAT) https://forms.gle/qSrNn539H9nx39XK9 Post-questionnaire (EN) https://forms.gle/dJAoaYjk5v8k2GM76 Post-questionnaire (ES) https://forms.gle/gPEMNe2CDgRUE6EK7</p>	<p>40 minutes</p>
<p>Test 3: AST</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participants are asked to watch parts of a video (part 1, part 2), with AST modes in a randomized order in HMD. They listen to one general audio introduction. After each video, participants fill in the IPQ questionnaire. Participants are asked to fill in the post-questionnaire (preference questions). <p>Important: before watching each video, participants are advised to move their head around to have a full experience.</p>	<p>IPQ AST-C (CAT) https://forms.gle/rLg6TYDyvsqAo8Fi6 IPQ AST-D (CAT) https://forms.gle/NvPPCx6eZtfWnGXJ7</p> <p>IPQ AST-C (EN): https://forms.gle/rDYpw59RUpehz4N19 IPQ AST-D (EN): https://forms.gle/MQ4RZQpt8kNS3xVN6</p>	<p>30 minutes</p>

		IPQ AST-C (ES) https://forms.gle/WWC9ib1y1H3k1eFy7 IPQ AST-D (ES) https://forms.gle/WEyV1ubGREjusKkz9 Post-questionnaire (CAT) https://forms.gle/z9w9fhScNSWcxEKu5 Post-questionnaire (EN) https://forms.gle/va7MqKLCvHxq1SMN7 Post-questionnaire (ES) https://forms.gle/EVGabot6bM9RfZvz9	
Farewell	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participants are thanked. Further contact with researchers is provided. 		5 minutes
Total time (5 minutes of buffer time included in each stage of the experiment): 115 minutes Total time without buffer time: 95 minutes.			

- **Materials.**

Online questionnaires (Google forms) to facilitate data processing, HMD, laptop and video clips.

- The video used in Task 1 will be *Holy Land* (episode 4). Link: <http://84.88.32.46/test-ad/>
- The videos used in Task 2 will be *Holy Land* (episodes 1-3). Links:
 - Episode 1: <https://www.jauntvr.com/title/16ffdc9b81>
 - Episode 2: <https://www.jauntvr.com/title/b4c0c8bb90>
 - Episode 3: <https://www.jauntvr.com/title/0f9930d2cf>
- The video used in Task 3 will be "Opera" (Spain and UK):
 - Clip 1: 00:00 - 03:44 (until "No eres más que un cobarde")
 - Clip 2: 03:44 - 08:29 (beginning "No me conoces, Tybalt, tus insultos...")

In all three tasks, participants will be shown the clips by means of an HMD (Oculus Go).

A 30-second black screen will be included at the beginning of each video to ensure that the participants watch the video without any interruptions from the very beginning.

All materials, including questionnaires and forms, should be prepared prior to the experiment.

- **Previous to the experiment**

Facilitator should ensure that the atmosphere is comfortable for the participants, with an adequate room arrangement.

- **Introduction**

- **Test 1: interface interaction (menu)**

- **Measures:** Usability
- **Participants:** 10 (5+ 5)
 - Blind users will be using voice control
 - Partially sighted users will be using high-contrast accessible UI of the ImAC player.

- **Materials:** *Holy Land*, episode 4, in Voice of God.
- **Devices:** the test will be performed with an HMD (Oculus Go) and Amazon Echo.
- **Player:** <https://imac.gpac-licensing.com/playertest/>
- **Clip:** *Holy Land* (Episode 4). Link: <http://84.88.32.46/test-ad/>

Users will be asked to interact with the menu in an HMD and fill in the post-questionnaire.

Participants will be asked to carry out the following set of tasks:

- **Open the player**
 - **Command:** ImAc open
Response: ImAc opening
- **Find content**
 - **Command:** ImAc list videos
Response: 1 video *Holy Land* Episode 4
- **Play content**
 - **Command:** ImAc play video
Response: *Holy Land* Episode 4 playing
- **Turn audio description on/off**
 - **Command:** ImAc audio description on
Response: Audio description, on
- **Volume up/ volume down**
 - **Command:** ImAc volume up or ImAc volume 8 (the volume goes from 1-10)
Response: "Ok, how about this? Volume 8)
 - **Command:** ImAc volume down or ImAc volume 5
Response: Ok, how about this? Volume 5
- **Pause content**
 - **Command:** ImAc pause video
Response: Ok, paused
 - **Command:** ImAc play video
Response: Ok, playing
- **Move backward and forward**
 - **Command:** ImAc skip back 20 seconds
Response: Ok, skipped back
 - **Command:** ImAc skip forward 20 seconds
Response: ok, skipped 20 seconds
- **Stop content**
 - **Command:** ImAc stop video
Response: Stopping video
- **Close ImAc player**
 - **Command:** Close ImAc Player
Response: Ok, bye bye/Ok, see you later

Post-questionnaires: After the task is completed, users will be asked to fill in the SUS questionnaire and a preference questionnaire (5 minutes):

- SUS (CAT): <https://forms.gle/8dJJ5kvzyXXvnrgs8>
- SUS (EN): <https://forms.gle/PqnongggJDEoSkvf7>
- SUS (ES): <https://forms.gle/HCKTn795oK65aHPz7>

Additional preference questionnaire:

- CAT: <https://forms.gle/ooZimusbUEsr5VFt7>
- EN: <https://forms.gle/3Yq9rQuX3LbPwH2V6>
- ES: <https://forms.gle/xZDE9QWqT45SfDpc6>

- **Test 2: AD presentation modes**

- **Measures:** Presence and preferences
- **Participants:** 10 (5 + 5)
- **Materials:**
 - **Device:** The test will be performed with an HMD
 - **Clips:** Three comparable clips (*Holy Land*, episodes 1-3).
English test: each episode (1-3) will be produced in three AD versions.
Catalan test: the episodes (1-3) and the three AD presentation modes will be translated into Catalan by UAB and voiced by CCMA.
One audio introduction will be provided for all videos at the beginning, providing a broader context to participants.

Previous to the tasks (5 minutes):

The facilitator will explain this part of the experiment: testing 3 different AD presentation modes.

Tasks:

First of all, an audio introduction will be played. Then, the videos will be presented in the following order: clip 1 (Episode 1), clip2 (Episode 2), clip 3 (Episode 3). The presentation modes (AD-C, AD-S and AD-D) will be randomized across participants.

Participants are asked to watch three videos (see Latin square below) and answer IPQ questionnaire after each clip. Before watching each video, participants are advised to move their head around to have a full experience.

Important: please make sure to provide the correct IPQ questionnaire to participants, depending on the order in which they visualize the clips.

Links:

- IPQ AD-C (CAT): <https://forms.gle/ZjfmBxXzGSUpj9sCA>
- IPQ AD-S (CAT): <https://forms.gle/yivjHr8UgnGG4NPv5>
- IPQ AD-D (CAT): <https://forms.gle/5MjhBWTSN8KGPVp7>
- IPQ AD-C (EN): <https://forms.gle/jXippexsnaJTPxHR9>
- IPQ AD-S (EN): <https://forms.gle/ei2YFjPHZKmpcFA3A>
- IPQ AD-D (EN): <https://forms.gle/oAnwSHwK2xRBpy7k6>
- IPQ AD-C (ES): <https://forms.gle/1XrP6tytGNLjXbU27>
- IPQ AD-S (ES): <https://forms.gle/HHrQRp8EwaHEoeu37>
- IPQ AD-D (ES): <https://forms.gle/13PaB7TjzHSvWzmc7>

After the tasks: participants are asked to answer preference questions in the post-questionnaire. Links:

- Post-questionnaire (CAT): <https://forms.gle/qSrNn539H9nx39XK9>
- Post-questionnaire (EN): <https://forms.gle/dJAoaYjk5v8k2GM76>
- Post-questionnaire (ES): <https://forms.gle/gPEMNe2CDgRUE6EK7>

Latin square for AD test:

Participant	Videos		
Blind users			
RNIB1/UAB1	Episode 1, AD-C	Episode 2, AD-S	Episode 3, AD-D
RNIB2/UAB2	Episode 1, AD-S	Episode 2, AD-D	Episode 3, AD-C
RNIB3/UAB3	Episode 1, AD-D	Episode 2, AD-C	Episode 3, AD-S
Partially sighted			
RNIB4/UAB4	Episode1, AD-	Episode 2, AD-S	Episode 3, AD-D

	C		
RNIB5/UAB5	Episode 1, AD-S	Episode 2, AD-D	Episode 3, AD-C
RNIB6/UAB6 (if possible)	Episode 1, AD-D	Episode 2, AD-C	Episode 3, AD-S

- **Test 3: AST presentation modes**

- **Measures:** Presence and preferences
- **Participants:** 10 (5+ 5)
- **Materials:**
 - **Device:** The test will be performed with an HMD
 - **Clips:** Two comparable clips. The order of the clips will be: part 1 followed by part 2, but the presentation modes will be randomized. A general audio introduction will be played at the beginning.
Spanish test: “Opera”, split in two comparable clips. For each clip two AST versions will be produced (AST-C/AST-D). The AST will be voiced by means of one synthetic voice, with a voice-over effect (the original sound will be heard in the background). An audio introduction will be played at the beginning.
UK test: “Opera”, split in two comparable clips. For each clip two AST versions will be produced (AST-C/AST-D). An audio introduction will be played at the beginning.

Before the tasks: The facilitator will explain this part of the experiment: testing 2 different AST presentation modes.

Tasks: Participants are asked to watch two clips (see latin square below) and answer IPQ questionnaire after each clip.

Before watching each video, participants are advised to move their head around to have a full experience.

Links:

- IPQ AST-C (CAT): <https://forms.gle/rLg6TYDyvsqAo8Fj6>
- IPQ AST-D (CAT): <https://forms.gle/NvPPCx6eZtfWnGXJ7>
- IPQ AST-C (EN): <https://forms.gle/rDYpw59RUpehz4N19>
- IPQ AST-D (EN): <https://forms.gle/MQ4RZQpt8kNS3xVN6>
- IPQ AST-C (ES): <https://forms.gle/WWC9ib1y1H3k1eFy7>
- IPQ AST-D (ES): <https://forms.gle/WEyV1ubGREjusKkz9>

After tasks: participants are asked preference questions in the post-questionnaire. Links:

- Post-questionnaire (CAT): <https://forms.gle/z9w9fhScNSWcxEKu5>
- Post-questionnaire (EN): <https://forms.gle/va7MqKLCvHxq1SMN7>
- Post-questionnaire (ES): <https://forms.gle/EVGabot6bM9RfZvz9>

The order of presentation of the stimuli will be balanced across participants. Important: please make sure to provide the correct IPQ questionnaire to participants, depending on the order in which they visualize the clips.

Latin square for AST test:

Participant	Video	
Blind		
RNIB1/UAB1	Part 1, AST-C	Part 2, AST-D
RNIB2/UAB2	Part 1, AST-D	Part 2, AST-C
RNIB3/UAB3	Part 1, AST-C	Part 2, AST-D
Partially sighted		
RNIB4/UAB4	Part 1, AST-D	Part 2, AST-C

RNIB5/UAB5	Part 1, AST-C	Part 2, AST-D
RNIB6/UAB6 (if possible)	Part 1, AST-D	Part 2, AST-C

- **Farewell**

5. Questionnaires

Questionnaires will be provided to the participants using online forms, but is included below for reference:

Demographic questionnaire for home users – Version 1 (see Annex 45)

SUS (Annex 43)

Preference questions for User interaction:

EN

1. What do you like the most about the menu interaction?
2. What do you like less?
3. What do you think could be improved and how?
4. Other comments:

SPA

1. ¿Qué es lo que más le gusta de la interacción del menú?
2. ¿Qué es lo que menos le gusta?
3. ¿Qué se podría mejorar y cómo?
4. Otros comentarios:

CAT

1. Què és el que més li agrada de la interacció amb el menú?
2. Què és el que menys li agrada?
3. Què es podria millorar i com?
4. Altres comentaris:

Post-questionnaire: 2 test

EN

1. Which AD type do you prefer in 360°? Rank the AD modes according to your preferences: 1- preferred mode, 2- second preferred mode, 3 - the least preferred mode.

	1	2	3
• AD-C			
• AD-S			
• AD-D			

2. Please explain why you ranked the AD modes in this way.
3. How could AD be improved in this medium?
4. Other comments:

SPA

1. ¿Qué tipo de AD prefiere en 360°? Puntúe las opciones de AD según sus preferencias: 1- Opción preferida, 2- Segunda opción preferida 3- Opción menos preferida.

	1	2	3
• AD-C			

• AD-S			
• AD-D			

2. Explica por qué ha ordenado sus preferencias de este modo.
3. ¿Cómo se podría mejorar la audiodescripción en este medio?
4. Otros comentarios:

CAT

1. Quin tipus d'audiodescripció prefereix per als vídeos de 360º? Ordeni'ls segons les seves preferències: 1- el que més li agradi, 2 - el segon que més li agradi, 3 - el que menys li agradi.

	1	2	3
• AD-C			
• AD-S			
• AD-D			

2. Explica per què ha ordenat les seves preferències d'aquesta manera.
3. Com es podria millorar l'audiodescripció en aquest mitjà?
4. Altres comentaris:

Post-questionnaire: test 3

EN

1. Which type of audio subtitles do you prefer for 360º videos?
 - AST-C
 - AST-D
2. Explain in your own words why you prefer the option chosen in the first question.
3. What system would you prefer?
 - Audio subtitles with no subtitles on screen
 - Audio subtitles with subtitles on screen that can be enlarged
 - I would like to select when I want subtitles on screen and when not
4. Would you like to have an audio description together with the audio subtitles?
 - Yes
 - No
 - It depends on the content
5. Explain in your own words your choice in the previous question.
6. How could audio subtitles be improved in this medium?
7. Other comments:

SPA

1. ¿Qué tipo de audiosubtítulos prefiere para vídeos de 360º?
 - AST-C
 - AST-D
2. Explique con sus propias palabras por qué prefiere la opción elegida en la primera pregunta.
3. ¿Qué sistema prefiere?
 - Audiosubtítulos sin subtítulos escritos en pantalla
 - Audiosubtítulos con subtítulos escritos que se pueden ampliar en pantalla
 - Me gustaría seleccionar cuándo quiero subtítulos escritos en pantalla o no.
4. ¿Le gustaría tener una audiodescripción junto con los audiosubtítulos?
 - Sí

- No
 - Depende del contenido
5. Explique con sus propias palabras su respuesta en la pregunta anterior.
 6. ¿Cómo se podrían mejorar los audiosubtítulos en este medio?
 7. Otros comentarios:

ANNEX 27. AUDIO DESCRIPTION AND AUDIO SUBTITLING PRE-PILOT ACTIONS 2 REPORT (RNIB)

- Place and date: London, UK 7 May – 27 May 2019
- Access service(s) discussed: audio description and audio subtitling
- Demographic questionnaire
- Number of end users: 5

1.	Sex	3 female and 2 male
2.	Age	Participants were between the ages of 22 to 69 years (22, 33, 35, 43, 69)
3.	Main language of the participants	English
4.	Level of studies	4 – university educated 1 – further education
5.	I define myself as a...”	2 – Partially sighted 3 - Blind
6.	Age in which your disability began	4 – from birth 1 – 13 to 20 years
7.	What technology do you use on a daily basis? You can select more than one.	5 - TV 1 - PC 5 - Laptop 5 – Mobile phone Note - None of the participants selected HMD
8.	How often do you watch virtual reality content (for instance, 360° videos)?	Smartphone – 4 Never and 1 Occasionally Tablet – 5 Never PC – 5 Never Smartphone + HMD – 5 Never HMD – 5 Never
9.	If you have never used virtual reality content such as 360° videos or only occasionally, please indicate why. Multiple answers are possible.	1 – I am not interested 4 – It is not accessible
10.	Please state your level of agreement with the following statement: “I am interested in virtual reality content (such as 360° videos).”	1 - I strongly agree 2 - I agree 2 - Neither agree nor disagree
11.	Do you own any device to access virtual reality content?	2 - Yes 2 - No

		1 – I don't know, or I don't want to reply
12.	If you replied "yes" to the previous question, please specify which device(s).	RNIB 1: Smartphone RNIB 3: iPhone

13. Do you like watching the following types of content on television or online?

	I like it very much	I like it	Neither like it nor dislike it	I don't like it	I don't like it at all
News	1	2	2	0	0
Fiction	2	3	0	0	0
Talk shows	0	0	4	1	0
Documentaries	0	3	1	1	0
Sports	2	0	0	1	2
Cartoons	0	1	1	2	1

14. How many hours a day do you watch audio described content?

Number of hours	Responses
None	1
Less than one hour	1
1-2 hours	2
2-3 hours	1
4 hours or more	0

15. What do you use to access online content?

Assistive technology use	Responses
Magnifier (for example, ZoomText)	1
Screen reader (for example, JAWS, VoiceOver, TalkBack)	1
Both	2
None	1

PART 1 – Usability (SUS – HMD)

SUS statements	1 Strongly disagree	2	3	4	5 Strongly agree
I think that I would like to use this system frequently	0 – 0%	1 – 20%	2 – 40%	2 – 40%	0 – 0%
I found the system unnecessarily complex	3 – 60%	2 – 40%	0 – 0%	0 – 0%	0 – 0%
I thought the system was easy to use	0 – 0%	0 – 0%	0 – 0%	4 – 80%	1 – 20%
I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system	3 – 60%	1 – 20%	0 – 0%	1 – 20%	0 – 0%
I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	0 – 0%	0 – 0%	1 – 20%	3 – 60%	1 – 20%
I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	3 – 60%	2 – 40%	0 – 0%	0 – 0%	0 – 0%
I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly	0 – 0%	0 – 0%	1 – 20%	0 – 0%	4 – 80%
I found the system very cumbersome to use	2 – 40%	2 – 40%	0 – 0%	1 – 20%	0 – 0%
I felt very confident using the system	0 – 0%	1 – 20%	0 – 0%	1 – 20%	3 – 60%
I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system	2 – 40%	2 – 40%	1 – 20%	0 – 0%	0 – 0%

System Usability Scale (SUS) results for blind users testing voice interaction:

The SUS average score is **78.125**

The graph below shows how the SUS scores associate with the percentile ranks and letter grades and the red line specifies where the ImAc AD editor is at this moment.

The letter grade is B+, and the obtained score corresponds to the percentile rank: 80-84%.

System Usability Scale (SUS) results for blind users testing the menu interaction:

The SUS average score is **84.375**

The graph below shows how the SUS scores associate with the percentile ranks and letter grades and the red line specifies where the ImAc AD editor is at this moment.

The letter grade is A+, and the obtained score corresponds to the percentile rank: 96–100%.

3.1 Open questions

3.1.1 What do you like the most about the menu interaction?

RNIB 1	I like how simple it is to use, Alexa understood my commands and was quick to response. It was easy to play and pause a video and turn the volume up and down.
RNIB 2	Known quantity and straight forward
RNIB 3	Intuitive, makes sense
RNIB 4	Very straightforward, easy to grasp, smart speaker is responsive
RNIB 5	Colour contrast, white in black is easy to see. Liked different sizes of menu. Like the size increase of the pointer.

3.1.2 What do you like less?

RNIB 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I didn't like that you couldn't turn AD off when the video was paused. - Phrasing did not come naturally to me. - If there were more videos, would it list videos by number, names? - It didn't say how long the video was - or how many minutes left in the video?
RNIB 2	Nothing that I can think of
RNIB 3	Doesn't have any audible beeps to tell you whether it's on or off while using it
RNIB 4	I don't like the extra step of repeating 'ask ImAc to' each time - before each command
RNIB 5	Would like to have tick to indicated what is selected. Maximum and Minimum have similar shape, Low and High would be better alongside icons.

3.1.3 What do you think could be improved and how?

RNIB 1	I would like to use more natural language. Others see above.
RNIB 2	Syntax needs to be improved - turning it off could be said in a few different ways
RNIB 3	Introduce a wake-up beep. For privacy, audio feedback - Alexa - to be streamed through headphones/ player
RNIB 4	Skip back and forward any big chunks
RNIB 5	System crashed several times while testing. More accessible way to enter the player interface before the player was hard to see.

3.1.4 Other comments

RNIB 1	We started the test with the high-contrast interface but had to switch to spoken menus as the tester was unable to use it independently. (Tester is partially sighted and a regular user of magnification and audio description)
RNIB 2	No
RNIB 3	No
RNIB 4	No
RNIB 5	No

PART 2: Audio Description Presentation Modes

Audio Description Classic Presentation (IPQ)

IPQ Questions	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
In the computer-generated world I had a sense of "being there".	1		1	1	1	1	
Somehow, I felt that the virtual world surrounded me.	1			2	1		1
I felt like I was just perceiving pictures.	2	1			1		1
I did not feel present in the virtual space.	2		3	1	1		
5. I had a sense of acting in the virtual space, rather than operating something from outside.	1	1	1		1	1	
I felt present in the virtual space.	1	1		1	1	1	
How aware were you of the real world surrounding while navigating in the virtual world? (i.e. sounds, room temperature, other people, etc.)?	3	1				1	
I was not aware of my real environment.	3	1				1	
I still paid attention to the real environment.	1	2			1		2
I was completely captivated by the virtual world.			2		5	2	
How real did the virtual world seem to you?		1	1	1	1	1	
How much did your experience in the virtual environment seem consistent with your real-world experience?	3			1	1		
How real did the virtual world seem to you?	1	2	1		1		
The virtual world seemed more realistic than the real world.	2	1		1		1	

Audio Description Static Presentation (IPQ)

IPQ Questions	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
In the computer-generated world I had a sense of "being there".	2		1	1		1	
Somehow, I felt that the virtual world surrounded me.	2	1		1		1	

I felt like I was just perceiving pictures.	1			1	1	1	1
I did not feel present in the virtual space.	3	1			1		
I had a sense of acting in the virtual space, rather than operating something from outside.	3	1		1			
I felt present in the virtual space.	2	1	1			1	
How aware were you of the real world surrounding while navigating in the virtual world? (i.e. sounds, room temperature, other people, etc.)?	1	3				1	
I was not aware of my real environment.	1	4					
I still paid attention to the real environment.		1			1	1	2
I was completely captivated by the virtual world.	3	1				1	
How real did the virtual world seem to you?		1	1			1	2
How much did your experience in the virtual environment seem consistent with your real-world experience?	3	1			1		
How real did the virtual world seem to you?	1	3			1		
The virtual world seemed more realistic than the real world.	3	1				1	

4.3 Audio Description Dynamic Presentation (IPQ)

IPQ Questions	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
In the computer-generated world I had a sense of "being there".	1	2	1			1	
Somehow, I felt that the virtual world surrounded me.	1	2	1			1	
I felt like I was just perceiving pictures.	1	1		1	1		1
I did not feel present in the virtual space.	1	2	1				1
I had a sense of acting in the virtual space, rather than operating something from outside.	1	2		1		1	

I felt present in the virtual space.	1	2				2	
How aware were you of the real world surrounding while navigating in the virtual world? (i.e. sounds, room temperature, other people, etc.)?	2	1		1		1	
I was not aware of my real environment.	3	1				1	
I still paid attention to the real environment.		1		1		1	2
I was completely captivated by the virtual world.	2	1		1		1	
How real did the virtual world seem to you?		1			1	1	2
How much did your experience in the virtual environment seem consistent with your real-world experience?	3			1		1	
How real did the virtual world seem to you?	1	2		1	1		
The virtual world seemed more realistic than the real world.	2	1		2			

RNIB comparison: Classic/Static/Dynamic

Median values:

Group	CLASSIC				DYNAMIC				STATIC			
	G1	sp	inv	real	G1	sp	inv	real	G1	sp	inv	real
RNIB	3.00	2.40	1.50	1.75	1.00	2.20	1.50	0.75	2.00	1.00	1.25	0.75

Non parametric Friedman tests reveal no differences between the scores of any subscale between conditions:

General presence (Chi-Square(2)= 1.273; N=5; p=.529); Spatial Presence (Chi-Square(2)= 4.500, N=5, p=.105); Involvement (Chi Square(2)= 2.111, N=5, p= .348); Experienced realism (Chi-Square(2)= .111, N=5, z= .946).

Audio Description Feedback Discussion

Summary

Testers were unable to tell the difference between the different presentation modes despite head movements

Blind testers felt uncomfortable wearing HMD and asked to remove it several times through the test. They did not see the point as they weren't engaging with the content visually

On immersion, testers commented that the experience did not feel any different to the experience of watching regular content on TV or cinema

Comments

Which type of AD do you prefer? Please explain why you ranked the AD modes in this way.

RNIB1: The AD did play and I did move around but none of them seemed very different to each other. They sounded quite similar.

RNIB2: They sounded similar - no difference at all

RNIB3: They all sounded the same so marked all as 2

RNIB4: Basically, in all 3 clips there was no difference in the terminology that was used, scripting style was the same and it sounded the same. It was as one long track.

RNIB5: Having the AD come from different positions made it easier to tell it from the main audio.

How could AD be improved in this medium?

RNIB1: I don't know...

RNIB2: Sound buffered (juddery)

RNIB3: More AD would be good as I'm a visual person and I couldn't visualize enough of it so it wasn't good enough. General lacked setting at beginning of each clip so, an audio introduction before each clip to set the scene e.g., where am I- beach, mountains?

RNIB4: AD felt like monotonous - it felt like an external entity which shouldn't be the case for immersive content

RNIB5: It wasn't in time with the picture.

It wasn't in time with the picture.

Other comments

RNIB2: I expected more from it - lack of colour and immersion

RNIB3: When you're trying to make it immersive, it takes time to immerse yourself and when that environment keeps changing, it doesn't work. For example, in this clip, the background music kept changing - you start to build a picture in your head and then it disappears and then the woman starts talking. I never felt the woman was sitting with me and talking to me which is I guess is important for immersion! Level of vision is quite important for immersion. If your AD is really really good and describes the background so well that I'm not having to think about what it looks like then I'm immersed and not getting distracted.

RNIB4: The main feature was in stereo so far as the music goes but to fully immerse yourself in the feature, it would've been important to get that in 3D. Everything so that means the ambience, the music needs to be immersive. AD can be objective.

Audio Subtitling

5.1 Audio Subtitling Classic Presentation Mode

IPQ Questions	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
In the computer-generated world I had a sense of "being there".	3	1					1
Somehow, I felt that the virtual world surrounded me.	3	1				1	
I felt like I was just perceiving pictures.	1			3			1
I did not feel present in the virtual space.	3	1					1
I had a sense of acting in the	3	1					1

virtual space, rather than operating something from outside.							
I felt present in the virtual space.	3	1					1
How aware were you of the real world surrounding while navigating in the virtual world? (i.e. sounds, room temperature, other people, etc.)?		2	1		1		1
I was not aware of my real environment.	2	1			1		1
I still paid attention to the real environment.	1				2	1	1
I was completely captivated by the virtual world.	2	2		1			
How real did the virtual world seem to you?					2	1	2
How much did your experience in the virtual environment seem consistent with your real world experience?	3	2					
How real did the virtual world seem to you?	3	1			1		
The virtual world seemed more realistic than the real world.	4				1		

5.2 Audio Subtitling Dynamic Presentation Mode

IPQ Questions	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
In the computer-generated world I had a sense of "being there".	2		1		1		1
Somehow, I felt that the virtual world surrounded me.	3	1			1		
I felt like I was just perceiving pictures.	2			2			1
I did not feel present in the virtual space.	2	1			1	1	
I had a sense of acting in the virtual space, rather than operating something from	3			1	1		

outside.							
I felt present in the virtual space.	2		1	1	1		
How aware were you of the real world surrounding while navigating in the virtual world? (i.e. sounds, room temperature, other people, etc.)?	2	2				1	
I was not aware of my real environment.	2	2				1	
I still paid attention to the real environment.		1			1	1	2
I was completely captivated by the virtual world.	2			1	1	1	
How real did the virtual world seem to you?				1	1	1	2
How much did your experience in the virtual environment seem consistent with your real-world experience?	2	1		1		1	
How real did the virtual world seem to you?	2	2	1				
The virtual world seemed more realistic than the real world.	3	1		1			

Median values for IPQ for RNIB, in the three conditions for each subscale:

group	AST-C				AST-D			
	G1	sp	inv	real	G1	sp	inv	real
EN	.00	0.60	2.50	.25	2.00	1.40	1.75	.75

The Wilcoxon signed ranks test does not show any difference for either condition

General presence $Z = -1.342$, ties=3, $p = .180$

Spatial presence $Z = -.542$, ties=0, $p = .588$

Involvement $Z = -.356$, ties= 1, $p = .715$

Experienced realism $Z = -.412$, ties= 0, $p = .680$

5.3 Comments

Explain in your own words why you prefer the option chosen in the first question.

RNIB1: Felt it was a lot louder and I could hear the translation whereas the first one felt like a whisper.

RNIB2: We've selected AST-D only because 'none' is not an option. I preferred neither - this way of presentation did not work for me. Couldn't hear the English at all! Whatever I heard was repetitive in any case.

RNIB3: Felt more immersive and the orchestra sounded better

RNIB4: I chose one in question 1 as we could not proceed with the questionnaire without choosing one.

Do not have a preference for D or C because they sounded identical.

RNIB5: Had to choose an answer.

What system would you prefer?

RNIB2: Audio subtitles with no subtitles on screen

RNIB1: Audio subtitles with subtitles on screen that can be enlarged

RNIB4: Audio subtitles with no subtitles on screen

RNIB3: I would like to select when I want subtitles on screen and when not

RNIB5: I would like to select when I want subtitles on screen and when not

Would you like to have an audio description together with the audio subtitles?

RNIB1: It depends on the content

RNIB2: It depends on the content

RNIB3: It depends on the content

RNIB4: It depends on the content

RNIB5: No

Explain in your own words your choice in the previous question.

RNIB1: It depends on the scenario on what it is. Try and make it more realistic - the voice was fine but it was very quiet.

RNIB2: Not on this but if *Holy Land* was in French then yes

RNIB3: Would want the ability to turn AD on and off depending on how busy the scene is. In an emotional scene the wording will be more important than the AD.

RNIB4: Maybe in a documentary like sea life, then yes but if there's music, then no. So it depends on the content

RNIB5: Want to hear the music.

How could audio subtitles be improved in this medium?

RNIB1: I should be able to change the volume of the subtitles.

RNIB2: It would be very difficult - there are a lot of contrasting priorities

RNIB3: Not moving around. Staying in the same place.

RNIB4: Voice needs to be more enthusiastic. Needs to be integrated into the feature and not added at the end. Not sound as if it was an afterthought. Person reading could sound less bored

Other comments:

RNIB1: Audio introduction was helpful.

RNIB2: Headset got really uncomfortable - head tilting forward by the end. English subtitles were really faint so it distracted from everything else. It was a world of confusion!

RNIB3: The type of voice could make a difference on how the content worked. A whispered voice for instance might clash less with the content and allow the singing to be heard better.

RNIB4: This content was of really poor quality as the audio of the opera was of fairly good quality but the subtitles sounded really bad. Very bored, detached.

RNIB5: Wanted to listen to the music rather than hear subtitles. Prefer to read notes / have notes read out before rather than speech over opera.

Conclusion

Audio Description

Content

Audio description was produced in three presentation modes

- Classic, where the description was centered on the user which made it sound similar to the audio description delivered on TV and cinema
- Static, where the description is anchored next to viewer (or at any other fixed point around) in the scene like a friend sitting right next describing what's happening.
- Dynamic, where the audio description is placed on the action.

Note, all participants were asked to listen to an audio introduction which was under 2 minutes.

The preferred mode

The 5 testers were unable to tell the difference between the three presentation modes despite the head movements which triggered the motion in static and dynamic modes. Although the information within the track was deemed sufficient by one tester, there was consensus that the experience did not in any

way feel immersive or different to the one they experienced when they watched content with audio description on TV. However, one tester commented that they enjoyed listening to the audio description coming from different directions. One could assume that the lack of spatial audio within the original soundtrack was the underlying reason for the viewers not being able to differentiate between the different modes but so far, there is no evidence to support this theory.

In addition to the different modes, testers also said that this audio description sounded too monotonous and lacked any flavor.

Hardware

Three testers with severe sight loss (blind) did not feel comfortable wearing the head mounted displays (HMD). They couldn't see the point as they weren't engaging with the content visually and on being explained that the HMD was required to track the head movement, they requested for equipment that was lighter and did not pinch or applied less pressure on the area surrounding their eyes.

Audio Subtitling

Content

Audio subtitles were presented in two modes:

- Classic, where the audio subtitles were centered in the scene
- Dynamic, where the audio subtitles were centered on the character speaking the dialogue

Similar to the response for audio description, majority of the testers couldn't tell the difference between the different presentation modes for audio subtitles with the exception of one tester who felt the classic mode was more immersive than the dynamic.

Some of the testers felt that this treatment might have worked better had it been used for documentaries in a foreign language with audio description. One tester stated that, while watching the opera, they wanted to listen to the music. On the issue of subtitles in text on screen, there was an equal split between the number of testers who did not want any subtitles on screen and testers who wanted the choice to be able to turn it off and on. One tester wanted subtitles that can be enlarged.

Given the responses, it is evident that further work is needed to explore how a documentary in 360 with stereo sound can be made immersive for audio description and subtitling users.

ANNEX 28. AUDIO DESCRIPTION AND AUDIO SUBTITLING PRE-PILOT ACTIONS 2 REPORT (UAB)

Pre-pilot on AD, AST and interface interaction: report

1. General information

- **Partner responsible:** UAB
- **Place and date:** 11-13 June 2019
- **Access services discussed:** audio description and audio subtitles
- **Research tool:** online questionnaires (Google Form)
- **Methodology:**
<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1MQwROPso6dGZO8CILS9gF4giYwT6a7HSHO6EwC2tR7Q/edit>

2. Demographic questionnaire:

- Number of end users: 6
- Demographics for users:
 1. Sex: "female" (1), "male" (5), "other" (0), "I prefer not to reply" (0)
 2. Age: 27, 26, 34, 31, 23, 28
 3. Main language: Spanish (4), Catalan (1), Spanish and Catalan (1)
 4. Please indicate your level of studies: "no studies" (0), "primary education" (0), "secondary education" (0), "further education" (3), "university" (3).
 5. I define myself as...: "blind person" (2), "partially-sighted person (3)", "other" (1): "Dislèxia i TDH".
 6. Age at which you started losing your sight: "from birth" (1), "0-4" (1), "5-12" (1), "13-20" (3), "21-40"(0), "41-60" (0), "more than 60" (0)
 7. What devices do you use on a daily basis? Multiple replies are possible: "TV" (4), "PC" (1), "Laptop" (4), "Mobile phone" (6), "Tablet" (2), "Head Mounted Display (HMD)", "other" (2): "Llibre electrònic", "Reloj inteligente".
 8. How often do you watch virtual reality content (for instance, 360º videos)?

	Never	Occasionally	At least once a month	At least once a week	Every day
In smartphone	4 (66.67%)	2 (33.33%)			
On a tablet	6 (100%) (100%)				
On a PC	6 (100%)				
In smartphone plugged to HMD	6 (100%)				
In dedicated HMD (ie. Vive, Oculus)	5 (83.33%)	1 (16.67%)			

9. If you have never used virtual reality content such as 360º videos or only occasionally, please indicate why. Multiple answers are possible. "Because I am not interested." (2), "Because it is not accessible." (2), "Because I have not had the chance to use it." (2), "Other reasons."
10. Please state your level of agreement with the following statement: "I am interested in virtual reality content (such as 360º videos)." "I strongly agree" (1), "I agree" (2), "Neither agree nor disagree" (3), "Disagree", "Strongly disagree"

11. Do you own any device to access virtual reality content? “Yes”, “No” (6), “I don’t know or I don’t want to reply”.
12. If you replied "yes" to the previous question, please specify which device(s).
13. Do you like watching the following types of content on television or online?

	I like it very much	I like it	Neither like it nor dislike it	I don't like it	I don't like it at all
News	3 (50%)	2 (33.33%)			1 (16.67%)
Fiction (series, films)	2 (33.33%)	2 (33.33%)	1 (16.67%)		1 (16.67%)
Talk shows		3 (50%)	3 (50%)		
Documentaries	1 (16.67%)	2 (33.33%)	2 (33.33%)	1 (16.67%)	
Sports	3 (50%)		2 (33.33%)		1 (16.67%)
Cartoons		2 (33.33%)	2 (33.33%)	2 (33.33%)	

14. How many hours a day do you watch audio described content? “None” (3), “Less than one hour” (1), “1-2 hours”, “2-3 hours” (2), “3-4 hours”, “4 hours and more”.
15. What do you use to access online content? “Magnifier (for example, ZoomText)” (1), “Screen reader (for example, JAWS, VoiceOver, TalkBack)” (3), “Both” (1), “None” (1).

Summary: 6 participants filled in the demographic questionnaires. They were aged between 23-34 years old. Two participants defined themselves as blind persons, 3 participants as partially-sighted persons and one person chose the option "other". Three participants started to lose their sight between 13-20 years old, one 0-4 years old, one 5-12 years old and another one from birth.

Participants are frequent users of technological devices, such as smartphones, laptops and tablets. When asked about the frequency of watching 360° content, 33% participants reported watching such content occasionally on a smartphone, and one participant (16.67%) by means of head-mounted displays. In the question asking about the reasons behind not consuming such content, two participants chose option “Because I am not interested.”, two “Because it is not accessible.”, and two remaining ones “Because I have not had the chance to use it.” When asked whether they have a device to watch 360° videos, all participants replied negatively.

All participants were familiar with AD. When asked about the frequency of daily AD usage, two participants replied 2-3 hours, three participants none and one participant less than an hour. Three participants are using screen readers on a daily basis, one magnifier, one both, and one none.

In total, 6 participants took part in the pre-pilot test, finishing AD and AST test. 5 participants finished menu interaction test (1 participant could not finish this test due to the technical problems with internet connection). 4 participants tested menu interaction with voice-interaction (Amazon Echo Dot - Alexa). 1 participant tested the menu interaction with accessible menu.

3. Results (test 1): interface interaction

3.1. System Usability Scale (SUS) results for blind users testing voice interaction:

3.1.1. SUS scores (question by question)

1 – strongly disagree

5 – strongly agree

SUS statements	1	2	3	4	5
1. I think that I would like to use this system frequently	0 0%	0 0%	3 60%	0 0%	1 40%
2. I found the system unnecessarily complex	1 25%	1 25%	0 0%	1 25%	1 25%
3. I thought the system was easy to use	0 0%	1 25%	0 0%	2 50%	1 25%
4. I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system	2 50%	0 0%	1 25%	0 0%	1 25%
5. I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	2 50%	2 50%
6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	3 75%	1 25%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%
7. I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly	0 0%	0 0%	2 50%	1 25%	1 25%
8. I found the system very cumbersome to use	1 25%	1 25%	2 50%	0 0%	0 0%
9. I felt very confident using the system	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%	3 75%	1 25%
10. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system	0 0%	4 100%	0 0%	0 0%	0 0%

3.1.2. System Usability Scale (SUS) results:

The SUS average score is **71.88**.

The graph below shows how the SUS scores associate with the percentile ranks and letter grades and the red line specifies where the ImAc AD editor is at this moment.

The letter grade is C+, and the obtained score corresponds to the percentile rank: 60–64%.

3.2. System Usability Scale (SUS) results for partially sighted users testing the menu interaction:

3.1.3. SUS scores (question by question)

1 – strongly disagree

5 – strongly agree

SUS statements	1	2	3	4	5
1. I think that I would like to use this system frequently	0 0 %	0 0 %	1 100%	0 0 %	0 0 %
2. I found the system unnecessarily complex	0 0 %	0 0 %	0 0 %	1 100%	0 0 %
3. I thought the system was easy to use	0 0 %	0 0 %	0 0 %	0 0 %	1 100%
4. I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system	0 0 %	1 100%	0 0 %	0 0 %	0 0 %
5. I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	0 0 %	1 100%	0 0 %	0 0 %	0 0 %
6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	0 0 %	0 0 %	0 0 %	1 100%	0 0 %
7. I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly	0 0 %	0 0 %	0 0 %	1 100%	0 0 %
8. I found the system very cumbersome to use	0 0 %	0 0 %	1 100%	0 0 %	0 0 %
9. I felt very confident using the system	0 0 %	0 0 %	1 100%	0 0 %	0 0 %
10. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system	0 0 %	1 100%	0 0 %	0 0 %	0 0 %

3.1.4. System Usability Scale (SUS) results:

The SUS average score is **52.5**.

The graph below shows how the SUS scores associate with the percentile ranks and letter grades and the red line specifies where the ImAc AD editor is at this moment.

The letter grade is D, and the obtained score corresponds to the percentile rank: 15-34%.

3.2. Preference questions

3.2.1. Preference questions for blind users

1. What do you like the most about the menu interaction?

UAB 1	Permet diverses opcions de navegació amb veu i això ho fa accessible. (It allows several voice navigation options and this makes it accessible.)
UAB 2	Poder donar ordres sense haver-ho de ser manualment. (You can give commands without interacting manually.)
UAB 3	És fàcil i àgil. Executa els comandaments sense problema. (It is easy and smooth. It executes the commands without problem.)
UAB 5	Que pots anar avançant i retrocedint, parar i play el menú, etc. quan vullguis. (You can forward the video and go backward, stop and open the menu, etc. when you want.)

2. What do you like less?

UAB 1	La necessitat de dir "usando portal Imac" fa que les ordres siguin més extenses i, per tant, no sigui tan ràpid. (The need to say "Usando portal Imac" makes the orders more long and therefore not so fast.)
UAB 2	No és del tot precís pel que fa a avançar/rebobinar i els canvis en el volum són tan subtils que no es noten. (It is not entirely accurate in terms of forwarding/moving back and changes in volume are so subtle that they are not noticeable.)
UAB 3	Cal avís auditiu d'Alexa de recepció d'inici de comandament (es pot fer a la configuració d'Alexa). No requereix programació. (There can be an audible information from Alexa after saying the first command (can be activated in Alexa's configuration). No programming required.)
UAB 5	Haver-li de dir Alexa, fes això, fes lo altre.

3. What do you think could be improved and how?

UAB 1	Només veu tinc dubtes que sigui una forma d'interactuar fàcil. Es pot alleugerir eliminant "usando portal Imac". Tenir un ventall més ampli d'opcions. Per exemple, "activa audiodescripció", sense "la" no funciona. (I have doubts if it's an easy way to interact. It can be made simpler by removing "Usando portal Imac". I'd like to have a wider range of options. For example, "active audio description", without "the" does not work.)
UAB 2	Que hi hagués un avís auditiu per saber si Alexa està agafant l'ordre. Més flexibilitat en les ordres. (There should be an audible information to know that Alexa is listening to the command. More flexibility in the orders.)
UAB 3	Que no estigués escoltant tanta estona en acabar cada comandament. Que no calgui fer clic amb el controller abans de reproduir el vídeo. (It [Alexa] should not be listening for so long at the end of each command. No need to click with the controller before playing the video.)
UAB 5	Poder-ho fer tu manualment. Per exemple, si ho estas fent a l'ordinador, que hi hagués un botó de retrocedir o d'avançar, etc. (To be able to do it yourself manually. For example, if you are doing it on the computer, there would be a back or forward button, etc.)

4. Other comments:

UAB 2	Preferiria que fent play no hagués de fer clic a VR, que el vídeo es comencés a reproduir automàticament. (I'd prefer that by playing I don't have to click VR, that the video starts playing automatically.)
UAB 3	Activar amb la veu els AST i canvi d'idioma seria útil. (It would be useful to activate the AST and change the language by voice.)

UAB 5	Està bé. (Everything is fine.)
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3.2.1. Preference questions for partially sighted users

1. What do you like the most about the menu interaction?

UAB6	El que més m'agrada és l'acoplament de l'Alexa amb el sistema, perquè va molt fina. (What I like the most is integration of Alexa with the system, because it functions very well.)
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2. What do you like less?

UAB6	El que menys m'agrada és que l'accessibilitat amb el punteroj no és correcta, s'hauria de donar visibilitat a l'ampliació/minimització de la lletra. I mirar cap avall per obrir el menú és inviabile. (What I like the least is that accessibility with the pointer is not correct, you should give visibility to the enlargement / minimization of the letters. And looking down to open the menu is uncomfortable.)
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3. What do you think could be improved and how?

UAB6	No funciona la opció de subir/bajar volumen con el menú accesible. Pasa del 0 al 100% con dos clics. Para abrir el menú mirar hacia abajo es muy incómodo (hay gente que no puede hacer este movimiento). En la barra de progreso no se puede arrastrar el vídeo hacia adelante o hacia atrás para moverte a la parte donde quieras. Con las flechas para adelante/para detrás sí funciona (tarde como medio segundo en hacerlo). Está mejor implementado el menú de voz que el menú táctil. (The option to increase/decrease volume with the accessible menu does not work. Go from 0 to 100% with two clicks. To open the menu look down is very uncomfortable (there are people who cannot make this move). In the progress bar you cannot drag the video forward or backward to move to wherever you want. With the arrows forward/backward it does work (you need to wait half a second). The voice-interaction is better implemented than the accessible menu.)
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4. Other comments:

UAB 6	En general prefereixo els menús visuals, però en aquest cas la adaptació és molt més bona amb l'Alexa. (In general I prefer the visual menus, but in this case the interaction is much better with Alexa)
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Summary – menu interaction test

Voice-interaction

Comments regarding voice-interaction with the video were generally positive.

One participant commented that when changing the volume with Alexa, the change in sound level is not noticeable enough. One participant noted that moving the video forward/backward should be smoother.

Another participant would like to activate the AST or change the language of AD/AST by means of voice-interaction.

Accessible interface

One participant tested this option during Spanish tests. Although the interface was generally accessed positively, this participant suggested the following improvements to improve its usability:

- It should be possible to adjust the volume with the controller in the Oculus Go.
- It should be possible to move forward/backward the video using the bar.
- Accessible menu should open when looking up (looking down was difficult for that person because of the weight of the glasses).
- This participant commented that the circle appearing on the screen when opening the menu should be larger or more visible.
- The participant also suggested that the button that serves to activate the accessible menu should be larger.

Accessibility of head-mounted display

Participants commented also on accessibility of HMD:

- When playing the video, users need to click on the controller, choosing between VR/non-VR option. For user interface test, they just needed to point the controller in front of themselves and click on the "select" button, but they would prefer that the video plays automatically, without the need to click on the controller.
- The HMD goes to 'sleep' very often because of its movement sensor, which is not accessible for persons with sight loss.

4. Test 2: AD presentation modes

4.1. Results of the IPQ questionnaires

4.1.1. Classic AD mode

IPQ questions	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1. In the computer generated world I had a sense of "being there".	1 (16.7%)	1 (16.7%)	1 (16.7%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.7%)	1 (16.7%)	1 (16.7%)
2. Somehow I felt that the virtual world surrounded me.	1 (16.7%)	1 (16.7%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.7%)	0 (0%)	2 (33.3%)	1 (16.7%)
3. I felt like I was just perceiving pictures.	3 (50%)	1 (16.7%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.7%)	1 (16.7%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
4. I did not feel present in the virtual space.	1 (16.7%)	1 (16.7%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.7%)	1 (16.7%)	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)
5. I had a sense of acting in the virtual space, rather than operating something from outside.	1 (16.7%)	1 (16.7%)	1 (16.7%)	1 (16.7%)	1 (16.7%)	1 (16.7%)	0 (0%)
6. I felt present in the virtual space.	1 (16.7%)	1 (16.7%)	1 (16.7%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.7%)	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)
7. How aware were you of the real world surrounding while navigating in the virtual world? (i.e. sounds, room temperature, other people, etc.)?	1 (16.7%)	0 (0%)	3 (50%)	1 (16.7%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.7%)
8. I was not aware of my real environment.	1 (16.7%)	1 (16.7%)	1 (16.7%)	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.7%)
9. I still paid attention to the real environment.	3 (50%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.7%)	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
10. I was completely captivated by the virtual world.	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.7%)	0 (0%)	2 (33.3%)	1 (16.7%)
11. How real did the virtual world seem to you?	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.7%)	1 (16.7%)	1 (16.7%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.7%)

IPQ questions	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
12. How much did your experience in the virtual environment seem consistent with your real world experience ?	2 (33.3%)	1 (16.7%)	1 (16.7%)	0 (0%)	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
13. How real did the virtual world seem to you?	2 (33.3%)	1 (16.7%)	3 (50%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
14. The virtual world seemed more realistic than the real world.	4 (66.7%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.7%)	1 (16.7%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)

4.1.2. Static AD mode

IPQ questions	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1. In the computer generated world I had a sense of "being there".	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	3 (50%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)
2. Somehow I felt that the virtual world surrounded me.	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)
3. I felt like I was just perceiving pictures.	3 (50%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)
4. I did not feel present in the virtual space.	1 (16.67%)	3 (50%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)
5. I had a sense of acting in the virtual space, rather than operating something from outside.	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)
6. I felt present in the virtual space.	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)
7. How aware were you of the real world surrounding while navigating in the virtual world? (i.e. sounds, room temperature, other people, etc.)?	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)	2 (33.3%)	2 (33.3%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)
8. I was not aware of my real environment.	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)	2 (33.3%)	1 (16.67%)	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)
9. I still paid attention to the real environment.	1 (16.67%)	2 (33.3%)	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
10. I was completely captivated by the virtual world.	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (33.3%)	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)
11. How real did the virtual world seem to you?	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (33.3%)	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (33.3%)
12. How much did your experience in the virtual environment seem consistent with your real world experience ?	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	4 (66.67%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
13. How real did the virtual world seem to you?	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)	2 (33.3%)	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
14. The virtual world seemed more realistic than the real world.	4 (66.67%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)

4.1.3. Dynamic AD mode

IPQ questions	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1. In the computer generated world I had a sense of "being there".	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (33.3%)	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)
2. Somehow I felt that the virtual world surrounded me.	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (33.3%)	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)
3. I felt like I was just perceiving pictures.	2 (33.3%)	2 (33.3%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)
4. I did not feel present in the virtual space.	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)	2 (33.3%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)
5. I had a sense of acting in the virtual space, rather than operating something from outside.	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	2 (33.3%)	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
6. I felt present in the virtual space.	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)
7. How aware were you of the real world surrounding while navigating in the virtual world? (i.e. sounds, room temperature, other people, etc.)?	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	3 (50%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)
8. I was not aware of my real environment.	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)	2 (33.3%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)
9. I still paid attention to the real environment.	2 (33.3%)	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
10. I was completely captivated by the virtual world.	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)
11. How real did the virtual world seem to you?	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (33.3%)	1 (16.67%)
12. How much did your experience in the virtual environment seem consistent with your real world experience ?	2 (33.3%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	3 (50%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
13. How real did the virtual world seem to you?	2 (33.3%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)
14. The virtual world seemed more realistic than the real world.	4 (66.67%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)

Median values

Group	CLASSIC				DYNAMIC				STATIC			
	G1	sp	inv	real	G1	sp	inv	real	G1	sp	inv	real
UAB	3.00	3.40	3.00	1.75	4.00	3.70	3.00	2.13	4.00	2.70	4.00	2.50

UAB COMPARISON: Classic/Static/Dynamic

Non parametric Friedman tests reveal no differences between the scores of any subscale between conditions:

General presence (Chi-Square(2)= .200; N=6; p=.905); Spatial Presence (Chi-Square(2)=.087, N=6, p=.957); Involvement (Chi Square(2)=1.810, N=6, p= .405); Experienced realism (Chi-Square(2)=1.00, N=6, z= .607).

4.2. Results of the AD post-questionnaire

1. Which AD type do you prefer in 360°? Rank the AD modes according to your preferences: 1- preferred mode, 2- second preferred mode, 3 - the least preferred mode.

2. Please explain why you ranked the AD modes in this way.

UAB1	Em costa distingir els tres vídeos. Hi havia poca AD. El criteri ha estat els vídeos que més he gaudit. Hi ha hagut un problema tècnic amb el segon vídeo (AD-S) i això pot haver afectat. (It's hard for me to distinguish the three videos. There was little AD. The criterion has been the videos that I have enjoyed the most. There was a technical problem with the second video (AD-S) and this may have affected.)
UAB2	AD-C era més pausat, anava més acompanyat. Hi havia detalls que m'han fet sentir més captivada. (AD-C was slower, I was more accompanied. There were details that made me feel more captivated.)
UAB3	AD-S: millor so, t'aparta més del so extern. AD-D: molt plana (Better sound, separates you more from the external sound. AD-D: very flat)
UAB4	Veure comentaris. La decisió va en funció dels comentaris sobre el contingut. (See [other] comments. The decision was based on the comments about the content.)
UAB5	Perquè hi havia una millor audiodescripció dels llocs i perquè es podia escoltar el soroll de l'ambient, els carrers, la música. (Because there was a better audio description of places and because you could hear the noise of the environment, streets, music.)
UAB6	Perquè el que m'ha agradat més tenia més detalls que els altres. I m'he fixat en més coses que no hagués vist si no m'hi hagués fixat. (Because what I liked more had more details than the others. And I've noticed more things that I wouldn't have noticed otherwise.)

3. How could AD be improved in this medium?

UAB1	Posant-n'hi més. M'ha fet la sensació que hi havia poca descripció i que en certs moments no sabia què hi havia a la pantalla. (By adding more. It gave me the feeling that there was little description and at certain times I didn't know what was happening on the screen.)
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UAB2	Hi havia massa AD. M'agradaria que em deixessin ser jo qui s'adonés de més detalls. També m'agradaria sentir més música o més so ambiental de l'escena. (There was too much AD. I would like to figure out the details on my own. I would also like to hear more music or more ambient sound from the scene.)
UAB3	Amb un altre material que tingui més elements auditius més enllà de la narració. (With other material that has more auditory elements beyond the narration.)
UAB4	Veü home-dona en funció dels personatges que hi apareixen. (Man-woman voice depending on the characters that appear.)
UAB5	Potser fent una descripció més específica dels llocs. Entenc que no dona temps i clar no li dona temps a descriure més coses. Però tot és molt genèric, molt general. Em faltaven més elements. Que la manera d'explicar-ho fos més específica. El sonido ambiente es muy importante. (Perhaps by creating a more specific description of the places. I understand that there may be not enough time to describe more things. But everything is very general. I missed more elements, more specific way of explaining. The ambient sound is very important.)
UAB6	Lo ideal seria que el so et vingués d'on t'estan explicant. Si has de mirar a l'esquerra, que el so vingui de l'esquerra. Que el so t'ajudi a trobar el que t'estan explicant, dintre del vídeo. (Ideally, the sound should come from the place that is being explained. If you have to look to the left, let the sound come from the left. So that the sound helps you find what they are explaining to you, inside the video.)

4. Other comments:

UAB2	Pel que fa al contingut, no dona temps de gaudir de l'experiència 360º perquè tot canvia molt ràpidament. (Because of the content, it doesn't give time to enjoy the 360º experience because everything changes very quickly.)
UAB3	- AD-D: notava que el so venia de darrere en tots els casos - AD-S: so millor; no noto diferència pel que fa a la immersió. Es noten menys els factors externs. També sento el so des de darrere - Pregunta sobre fotografies: no aplicable a persones cegues. - Al documental no se senten coses com un burro quan se l'esmenta, una persona que s'agenolla, etc. Potser caldria un material amb més elements contrastats. (- AD-D: I noticed that the sound came from behind in all cases - AD-S: better sound; I don't notice any difference with respect to immersion. External factors are less noticeable. I also feel the sound from behind. - Question about photographs: not applicable to blind people. - In the documentary you don't feel things like a donkey when you mention it, a person kneeling down, etc. Perhaps there would be a material with more contrasted elements.)
UAB4	Cal canviar el contingut perquè se sentin altres sons. Hi ha massa veü i poca música. Calen diàlegs i sons reals perquè sembli real. No hi pots entrar si només sents el narrador i la música. Exemple: Callejeros viajeros. A l'AD-D: AD gairebé sempre des de l'esquerra. He notat diferències en el so. (You would need to change the content because other sounds are hearable). There is too much voice and too little music. Dialogues and real sounds would be needed to make it look real. You cannot feel immersed when you hear the narrator and the music. Example: Street travellers. To AD-D: AD almost always heard from the left. I have noticed differences in sound.)
UAB5	No hay diferencias en los tres vídeos, entre los tipos de sonido. Solo se percibe cambios en el contenido de la audiodescripción que es lo que se puede mejorar con más detalles. (There are no differences in the three videos, between the types of sound. You only notice changes in the content of the audio description which could be improved by adding more details.)
UAB6	Està bé que t'expliquin detalls, com per exemple la partició entre homes i dones a l'hora de resar, coses d'aquestes. Si t'ho expliquen ho pots veure més fàcilment.

	(It's good that details are conveyed, such as the division between men and women when at time of praying. If they explain you them, you can notice them more easily.)
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Summary – AD test

Content for this test was produced in three presentation modes: Classic, Static and Dynamic.

In classic sound mode, AD was hearable from above user’s head (it was centered on the user).

In Static sound mode, AD was heard next to the users, at a fixed point, as if a friend was sitting close to the user, describing the events.

In Dynamic sound mode, AD was placed around the sphere on the location of the main action or other important elements.

Before the test, all participants listened to an AI (audio introduction). Its duration was 1-2 minutes and it gave them an overview of the content.

The preferred sound treatment: none of participants was able to perceive clearly the differences between the three sound treatments (despite the head movements). In Dynamic sound mode, they were not able to localize the place of action thanks to the sound. They could not hear that in Classic sound type, AD comes from above their heads, in Static option – as if someone was standing/sitting close to them, and in Dynamic – that AD is located at different points of the sphere, depending on the main action.

Two participants commented in the preference questionnaire that the 360° content needs to be carefully selected for AD. The comments of participants suggest that 360° content with AD should fulfil the following criteria to be immersive:

1. It should have less dialogues or narration and more background sounds coming from different parts of the sphere (such as street noises).
2. AD should be clearly hearable from specific locations within the sphere.

Three participants would prefer a more detailed AD.

5. Test 3: AST presentation modes

5.1. Classic

IPQ questions	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1. In the computer generated world I had a sense of "being there".	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)	2 (33.3%)	1 (16.67%)	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
2. Somehow I felt that the virtual world surrounded me.	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)	3 (50%)	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
3. I felt like I was just perceiving pictures.	3 (50%)	2 (33.3%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
4. I did not feel present in the virtual space.	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)	3 (50%)	0 (0%)	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
5. I had a sense of acting in the virtual space, rather than operating something from outside.	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)	3 (50%)	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
6. I felt present in the virtual space.	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)	3 (50%)	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
7. How aware were you of the real world surrounding while navigating in the virtual world? (i.e. sounds, room temperature,	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	3 (50%)	0 (0%)

IPQ questions	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
other people, etc.)?							
8. I was not aware of my real environment.	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)
9. I still paid attention to the real environment.	2 (33.3%)	2 (33.3%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
10. I was completely captivated by the virtual world.	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)
11. How real did the virtual world seem to you?	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)	2 (33.3%)	2 (33.3%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)
12. How much did your experience in the virtual environment seem consistent with your real world experience ?	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)	3 (50%)	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
13. How real did the virtual world seem to you?	1 (16.67%)	2 (33.3%)	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
14. The virtual world seemed more realistic than the real world.	4 (66.67%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)

5.2. Dynamic

IPQ questions	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1. In the computer generated world I had a sense of "being there".	0 (0%)	2 (33.3%)	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
2. Somehow I felt that the virtual world surrounded me.	0 (0%)	2 (33.3%)	2 (33.3%)	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
3. I felt like I was just perceiving pictures.	3 (50%)	1 (16.67%)	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
4. I did not feel present in the virtual space.	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	3 (50%)	0 (0%)	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)
5. I had a sense of acting in the virtual space, rather than operating something from outside.	0 (0%)	2 (33.3%)	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)
6. I felt present in the virtual space.	0 (0%)	2 (33.3%)	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)
7. How aware were you of the real world surrounding while navigating in the virtual world? (i.e. sounds, room temperature, other people, etc.)?	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)
8. I was not aware of my real environment.	0 (0%)	3 (50%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (33.3%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)
9. I still paid attention to the real environment.	3 (50%)	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
10. I was completely captivated by the virtual world.	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (33.3%)	1 (16.67%)
11. How real did the virtual world seem to you?	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (16.67%)	1 (16.67%)	2 (33.3%)	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)
12. How much did your experience in the virtual environment seem consistent	0 (0%)	2 (33.3%)	1 (16.67%)	2 (33.3%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)

IPQ questions	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
with your real world experience ?							
13. How real did the virtual world seem to you?	0 (0%)	3 (50%)	1 (16.67%)	2 (33.3%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
14. The virtual world seemed more realistic than the real world.	2 (33.3%)	3 (50%)	1 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)

Median values for IPQ for UAB, in the two conditions for each subscale:

group	AST-C				AST-D			
	G1	sp	inv	real	G1	sp	inv	real
ES	2.50	2.70	3.63	1.63	2.50	3.00	4.25	1.63

The Wilcoxon signed ranks test does not show any difference for either condition:

General presence $Z = -1.000$, ties=5, $p = .317$

Spatial presence $Z = -1.069$, ties=3, $p = .285$

Involvement $Z = -.954$, ties= 0, $p = .340$

Experienced realism $Z = .000$, ties= 1, $p = 1.000$

5.3. Results of the AST post-questionnaire

1. Which type of audio subtitles do you prefer for 360° videos?

Blue – AST-C

Red – AST-D

2. Explain in your own words why you prefer the option chosen in the first question.

UAB1	No tapa tanto la música. (It doesn't cover the music so much.)
UAB2	Era más fluido. El otro vídeo era más estático. (It was more fluid. The other video was more static.)
UAB3	El vídeo con AST-D era corto y tenía poco contenido. (The video with AST-D was short and had little content.)
UAB4	Depende de si quieres disfrutar solo de la música o entender la trama. (It depends on whether you want to enjoy the music alone or to understand the plot.)
UAB 5	Los dos me han parecido igual de malos. Porque se oía muy poco el audiosubtítulo, muy bajito. Yo

	<p>que he ido veces al Liceu, hay una pantalla donde se ve el subtítulo y luego tienes la AD que te lo va chivando. Está bien que te lo vaya diciendo, pero estaría bien que estuviera alto. Estaría bien que en una oreja te sonara la AD/AST y en la otra el sonido de la música. O por ejemplo la AD y la música y en el otro los AST- QUE se jugara con los canales para mejorar la experiencia.</p> <p>(I thought both were just as bad. Because the audio subtitles were heard very little, very low. I've been to the Liceu, there's a screen where you can see the subtitle and then you have the AD that tells you about it. It's good that it tells you about it, but it would be good if it would be visible. It would be nice if in one ear you would hear the AD/AST and in the other the sound of the music. Or for example the AD and the music and in the other the AST- that will be played with the channels to improve the experience.)</p>
UAB6	<p>Me han gustado más los primeros porque los segundos se escuchaban flojitos y encima me dio la sensación de que se solapaban con lo que decían los cantantes más que en el otro.</p> <p>(I liked the first one better because the second one were low and on top of that it gave me the sensation that they overlapped with what the singers were saying more than in the other one.)</p>

3. What system would you prefer?

Blue – Audio subtitles with no subtitles on screen

Red – Audio subtitles with subtitles on screen that can be enlarged

Orange – I would like to select when I want subtitles on screen and when not

4. Would you like to have an audio description together with the audio subtitles?

Blue – Yes

Red – No

Orange – It depends on the content

5. Explain in your own words your choice in the previous question.

UAB1	En función de la música, si el AST tapa los pasajes cantados, prefiero que una AD no me tape la música. La audiointroducción es muy útil. (Depending on the music, if AST overlap with sung passages, I prefer that an AD does not cover music. Audio introduction is very useful.)
UAB2	Por ejemplo, en los vídeos sobre ópera me habría gustado ver los subtítulos escritos para pensar yo en una entonación u otra. Para contenidos que ocurran en exteriores me gusta más que me lo vayan explicando. (For example, in the opera videos I would have liked to have seen the written subtitles in order to think of one intonation or another. For contents that take place outdoors, I prefer if they explain it to me.)
UAB3	Creo que se solaparía. Con la audio introducción ya queda claro de qué se trata. (I think it would overlap. With audio introduction it's clear what it's all about.)
UAB4	Porque si vamos a visitar un monumento necesito detalles (p. ej. pinturas), pero en un paisaje quizás no necesito tantos detalles (p. ej. palmeras). Caras de ironía, por ejemplo, también querría saberlas si son relevantes. (Because if we are going to visit a monument I need details (e.g. paintings), but in a landscape perhaps I don't need so many details (e.g. palm trees). Expressions of irony, for example, I would also like to know if they are relevant.)
UAB5	En óperas o obras de teatro donde los actores no se mueven mucho, solo cantan e interpretan, no hace falta la AD. Pero si hay una escena de movimientos (como ahora que luchaban), sí que estaría bien que metieran la AD. En el teatro, no se hace audio introducción, te lo describen sobre la marcha. Es mejor que lo describan sobre la marcha más que la audio introducción, porque si no se haría eterno. (In operas or plays where the actors don't move much, they just sing and perform, there is no need for AD. But if there is a scene of movements (as now that they were fighting), it would be good to have AD. In theatre, there is no audio introduction, they describe it to you as you go along. It's better to describe it on the go rather than by means of audio introduction, otherwise it would very long.)
UAB6	Porque hay veces que con la AD te puedes hacer una idea de lo que está sucediendo, y hay veces que lo necesitas porque uno tiene que verlo. (Because there are times when with AD you can get an idea of what is happening, and there are times when you need it because you have to see it.)

6. How could audio subtitles be improved in this medium?

UAB1	Estoy bastante conforme con los AST-D. (I'm quite satisfied with AST-D.)
UAB2	Entonación y cambio de voz entre personajes femeninos y masculinos. (Intonation and change of voice between female and male characters.)
UAB3	Falta entonación. Son muy planos. Si los pudiera grabar alguien, sería más natural. (Lack of intonation. They are very flat. If the sound could be recorded by a person, it would be more natural.)
UAB4	AST me gusta, más que el doblaje incluso. No sabría cómo mejorarlo. (I like AST, even more than dubbing. I wouldn't know how to improve it.)
UAB5	Subiéndole el volumen. (By increasing its volume)
UAB6	Lo importante sería intentar que no se solapara con lo que están cantando. Sería lo más importante. (The important thing would be to try not to overlap with what they are singing. It would be the most important thing.)

7. Other comments:

UAB1	En los AST-D el volumen era más adecuado (más bajo, para escuchar la música). (In the AST-D the volume was more adequate (it was lower, to listen to the music).)
UAB2	No he notado la diferencia en el sonido entre los dos vídeos. A veces la orquesta tapada el audiosubtítulo y me costaba entenderlo. Quizás haber notado diferencias como en la música 8D sería interesante: sentir la orquesta detrás y que el subtítulo viniera de frente. (I haven't noticed the difference in sound between the two videos. Sometimes the orchestra covered the audio subtitles and it was hard for me to understand it. Perhaps it would be interesting to see the differences as in 8D music: feel the orchestra behind and subtitling coming from the front).
UAB3	Faltan elementos acústicos. (Acoustic elements are missing.)
UAB4	Se nota que el AST viene de arriba y la música de los cantantes de la derecha. La música te hace sentir más dentro de la esfera, más que el vídeo de <i>Holy Land</i> . AST-D viene siempre de la izquierda. AST en volumen bajo hace que no entiendas qué pasa, pero te hace sentir más dentro. (You can see that the AST comes from above and the music of the singers on the right. The music makes you feel more inside the sphere, more than the <i>Holy Land</i> video. AST-D always comes from the left. AST at low volume means you don't understand what's going on, but it makes you feel more inside.)
UAB5	Las traducciones estaban bien hechas. (The translations were well done.)

Summary – AST test:

Audio subtitles (AST) were presented in two sound modes: Classic and Dynamic.

In Classic sound mode, the sound of AST was coming from above users' heads.

In Dynamic sound mode, the sound of AST was located on the main action or other relevant visual elements.

Before listening to the videos, participants listened to an audio introduction (1-2 minutes).

The results concerning the sound modes obtained in AST test are similar to the results from AD test. Participants listening to AST in Classic and Dynamic sound mode were not able to perceive the differences between the two different sound treatments. They were also not able to locate the action based on sound cues in Dynamic mode.

In preference questions, some participants suggested that they would prefer a higher volume of AST, read out with a more noticeable intonation.

When consuming content with audio subtitles, 66.7% of participants would prefer to select when subtitles should be visible on screen.

When asked if they would prefer to listen to AD together with AST, most participants (66.7%) stated that it would depend on the content.

ANNEX 29. METHODOLOGY FOR CROSS-NATIONAL PILOT

1. What to test?

- Three pilot actions will be performed:
 - **Interface interaction (menu)** (Test 1). Links: <http://imac.i2cat.net/voicetest>, http://imac.i2cat.net/voicetest_cat/
 - **Three AD presentation modes** (Test 2) AD-C, AD-R, AD-E. Please notice that the end users will not know whether the mode they are testing is Classic, Radio or Extended, but we use these codes (C-R-E) because it will be easier for the researcher to identify what questionnaire to administer. Links: <http://imac.i2cat.net/adtest/>, http://imac.i2cat.net/adtest_cat/
 - **Two AST presentation modes** (Test 3) AST and AST-AD. Links: <http://imac.i2cat.net/adtest/>, http://imac.i2cat.net/adtest_cat/

2. When?

From 1st October 2019 to January 2020, depending on when stimuli are available.

3. Methodology: overview

- **Partners responsible for the test:** RNIB (UK), UAB (Spain).
- **Research tools:** online questionnaires (Google Forms).
- **Measures:** Presence (IPQ questionnaire), preferences (open and closed questions) and usability (SUS questionnaire).
- **Participants:** 30 participants (per partner) with sight loss will take part in the study: 15 blind and 15 low vision is what we should aim at.
- **Language of the experiment:** English (RNIB), Catalan and Spanish (UAB).
- **Experimental protocol:** The study will be individual testing, comprising 3 actions. In each test, users will be asked to perform certain tasks and then report on immersion, preferences and/or usability through online questionnaires.
- **Reporting:** RNIB and UAB will include the results on a report template provided by UAB: https://docs.google.com/document/d/1c7Xs18XfUCB-VqgYDwsWtVT9z_7usCWEDb8RzrzHyI4/edit
Please download it, fill it in and upload it under WP5/T5.5 Cross-national pilot/Reports/ adding UAB or RNIB to the file name.
- **The current methodology will be tested by UAB and RNIB previous to the test.**
- **Recruitment:** Participants will be recruited via user associations, personal contacts and social networks, if necessary.
- **Duration:** approx. 90 minutes.
- **Facilitator:** One facilitator will be involved. The facilitator will be the leader (welcoming participants, explaining the project, explaining the test) and will assist the sessions (by providing the online questionnaires and helping to fill them in, providing technical assistance with the devices, etc.).

4. Methodology: experimental protocol

The experiment will include three different tests. A within subject design will be used.

	Description	Links	Time
Introduction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcome and presentation of the ImAc project, the aim of the experiment and the procedure (5 minutes) • Fill in a consent form 	<p>Provide the participant with the consent form for ethical clearance. Include the name of the researcher performing the test. You can find the last version here. Feel free to use an oral recorded version or a written version but provide originals to UAB.</p> <p>https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1X5Nj9KxkpFVwvEuKfK</p>	20 minutes

	<p>and a demographic questionnaire (10 minutes).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Each participant is assigned with an individual participant code. Each participant needs to enter that code in online questionnaires. <p>Codes for RNIB: RNIB1, RNIB2...</p> <p>Codes for UAB: UAB1, UAB2...</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explain 360° videos and HMD, if unknown to a participant (1 minute). Ask participants if they have any questions (5 minutes or buffer time). 	<p>6XVgz0VFUSzUOS</p> <p>If you pay a compensation, the forms are under WP1/Deliverables/D1.2. Ethical forms/ Ethical forms if compensation is provided (April 2019)</p> <p>Demographic questionnaire: EN: https://forms.gle/UpM2KA1w5HRifT618 CAT: https://forms.gle/KYKE2VZzygUoEoGJ6</p>	
Test 1: Interface interaction (menu)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participants are asked to complete a few tasks in the menu in HMD. Participants are asked to fill in the SUS questionnaire. Participants are asked to fill in the additional preference questionnaire. <p>Please notice that 15 participants should test the voice interaction and 15 participants should test the enhanced menu.</p>	<p>SUS (EN): https://forms.gle/cqsR1dLXgV9gUnWL8</p> <p>SUS (CAT): https://forms.gle/etvCRUByjWoo9nmG6</p> <p>Additional preference questionnaire: EN: https://forms.gle/xAUctrCZd3BpSySH6 CAT: https://forms.gle/rPQjk4v54Nv39isz6</p>	20 minutes
Test 2: AD	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participants are asked to watch three videos with AD modes in a randomized order in HMD. They all listen to the one general audio introduction. The episode order is the same but the type of AD is randomized. 	<p>EN (AD-C): https://forms.gle/ykx721Q3KPfZyRnm7 EN (AD-R): https://forms.gle/UJGuccWCB25DE2fF6 EN (AD-E): https://forms.gle/n8KJhX22WjyU1d6A6 CAT (AD-C): https://forms.gle/DhNf8x1vWBP8Tx6e8 CAT (AD-R): https://forms.gle/itkYVRVzoA96uZQS9 CAT(AD-E): https://forms.gle/zdj4xAcQxr7bjyRL6</p>	40 minutes

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> After each video, participants reply to IPQ questionnaire. Participants are asked to fill in the post-questionnaire (preference questions). 	Post-questionnaire (EN): https://forms.gle/o84Fza6iy2QASKgy9 Post-questionnaire (CAT): https://forms.gle/ciyB3ej5haLkWi9u5	
Test 3: AST	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participants are asked to watch parts of a video (part 1, part 2), with AST modes in a randomized order in HMD. They listen to one general audio introduction. The order is always the same (part 1 and part 2), but the AST modes are randomized. Participants are asked to fill in a post-questionnaire (preference questions). <p>Important: before watching each video, participants are advised to move their head around to have a full experience.</p>	Post-questionnaire (EN): https://forms.gle/6oLrh8KiwbNuupBB8 Post-questionnaire (ES): https://forms.gle/G7m9r6Mt5VeVsGHT8	30 minutes
Farewell	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participants are thanked. Further contact with researchers is provided. 		5 minutes
<p>Total time (5 minutes of buffer time included in each stage of the experiment): 115 minutes Total time without buffer time: 95 minutes.</p>			

- Materials.**

Online questionnaires (Google forms) to facilitate data processing, HMD, laptop and video clips.

- The video used in Task 1 will be "Holy Land" (episode 4). Link: <http://84.88.32.46/test-ad/>
- The videos used in Task 2 will be "Holy Land" (episodes 1-3). Links:
 - Episode 1: <https://www.jauntvr.com/title/16ffdc9b81>
 - Episode 2: <https://www.jauntvr.com/title/b4c0c8bb90>
 - Episode 3: <https://www.jauntvr.com/title/0f9930d2cf>
- The video used in Task 3 will be "Opera" (Spain and UK):
 - Clip 1: 00:00 - 03:44 (until "No eres más que un cobarde")
 - Clip 2: 03:44 - 08:29 (beginning "No me conoces, Tybalt, tus insultos...")

In all three tasks, participants will be shown the clips by means of a HMD (Oculus Go).

Participants will use the following headphones: SONY MDR-ZX770.

A 30-second black screen will be included at the beginning of each video to ensure that the participants watch the video without any interruptions from the very beginning.

All materials, including questionnaires and forms, should be prepared prior to the experiment.

- **Previous to the experiment**

Facilitator should ensure that the atmosphere is comfortable for the participants, with an adequate room arrangement.

- **Introduction**

- **Test 1: interface interaction (menu)**

- **Measures:** Usability
- **Participants:** 60 (30 per partner)
 - Blind users will be using voice control
 - Partially sighted users will be using high-contrast accessible UI of the ImAC player.
 - **Materials:** Holy Land, episode 4, in Voice of God.
 - **Devices:** the test will be performed with an HMD (Oculus Go) and Amazon Echo.
 - **Clip:** "Holy Land" (Episode 4). Link: <http://84.88.32.46/test-ad/>

Users will be asked to interact with the menu in an HMD and fill in the post-questionnaire.

Participants will be asked to carry out the following set of tasks:

- **Open the player**
 - **Command:** "Open {v}."
 - Response:** "Opening video {v}."
- **Find content**
 - **Command:** "ImAc list videos."
 - Response:** "1 video Holy Land Episode 4."
- **Play content**
 - **Command:** "Play video."
 - Response:** "Playing video."
- **Turn audio description on/off**
 - **Command:** "Audio description on/Audio description off."
 - Response:** "Audio description on/Audio description off."
- **Volume up/ volume down**
 - **Command:** "Volume up/down" or "Volume {x}" (the volume goes from 1-10)
 - Response:** "Ok, how about this?"/"Ok, how about this? Volume {x}"
- **Pause content**
 - **Command:** "Pause video."
 - Response:** "Stopping video."
- **Resume video**
 - **Command:** "Play video."
 - **Response:** "Playing video."
- **Move backward and forward**
 - **Command:** "Skip back (x) seconds."
 - Response:** "Ok, skipped back (x) seconds."

- **Command:** “Skip forward (x) seconds.”
 - Response:** “Ok, skipped forward (x) seconds.”
- **Activate extended AD**
 - **Command:** “Tell me more.”
 - **Response:** “Turning extended description on.”
- **Switch-off extended AD**
 - **Command:** “Take me back.”
 - **Response:** “Turning extended description off.”
- **Zoom features**
 - **Command:** “Zoom in”/“Zoom out.”
 - **Responses:** “Zooming in”/“Zooming out.”
- **Open/close the menu:**
 - **Command:** “Open/Close menu.”
 - **Response:** “Opening/Closing the menu.”
- **Stop content**
 - **Command:** “Close video.”
 - Response:** “Closing video and returning to portal.”

Spanish commands:

- **Open the player**
 - **Command:** “Alexa, abre portal ImAc.”
 - Response:** “Connectado.”
- **Find content**
 - **Command:** “Lista de vídeos.”
 - Response:** “1 vídeo. Holy Land Episode 4.”
- **Play content**
 - **Command:** “Play/Reproduce.”
 - Response:** “Reproduciendo vídeo.”
- **Turn audio description on/off**
 - **Command:** “Activa la audiodescripción/Desactiva la audiodescripción.”
 - Response:** Audiodescripción activada/Audiodescripción desactivada.”
- **Volume up/ volume down**
 - **Command:** “Más alto/Más bajo/Sube el volumen/Baja el volumen.”
 - Response:** “Vale, ¿así mejor?”
- **Pause content**
 - **Command:** “Pausa/para el vídeo.”
 - Response:** “Parando vídeo.”
- **Resume video**
 - **Command:** “Play/Reproduce.”
 - **Response:** “Reproduciendo vídeo.”
- **Move forward and backward**
 - **Command:** “Avanza (x) segundos/Rebobina (x) segundos.”
 - **Response:** “Vale, hemos avanzado (x) segundos/Vale, hemos rebobinado (x) segundos.”
- **Activate/desactivate extended AD**
 - **Command:** “Activa audiodescripción extendida/Desactiva la audiodescripción extendida.”
 - Response:** “Audiodescripción extendida activada/Audiodescripción extendida desactivada.”
- **Open/close the menu:**
 - **Command:** “Abre el menú/Cierra el menú.”

- **Response:** “Abriendo/Cerrando el menú.”
- **Stop content**
 - **Command:** “Cierra vídeo.”
 - Response:** “Cerrando el vídeo y volviendo al menú principal.”

Post-questionnaires: After the task is completed, users will be asked to fill in the SUS questionnaire and a preference questionnaire (5 minutes).

- **Test 2: AD presentation modes**

- **Measures:** Presence and preferences
- **Participants:** 60 (30 per partner)
- **Materials:**
 - **Device:** The test will be performed with an HMD
 - **Link:** <https://imac.gpac-licensing.com/test-ad-2-cat/>
 - **Clips:** Three comparable clips (“Holy Land”, episodes 1-3).
English test: each episode (1-3) will be produced in three AD versions.
Catalan test: the episodes (1-3) and the three AD presentation modes will be translated into Catalan by UAB and voiced by CCMA (male voice, human).
One audio introduction will be provided for all videos at the beginning, providing a broader context to participants.

Previous to the tasks (5 minutes):

The facilitator will explain this part of the experiment: testing 3 different AD presentation modes.

Tasks:

First of all, an audio introduction will be played. Then, the videos will be presented in the following order: clip 1 (Episode 1), clip2 (Episode 2), clip 3 (Episode 3). The presentation modes (AD-C, AD-R and AD-E) will be randomized across participants.

Participants are asked to watch three videos (see Latin square below) and answer IPQ questionnaire after each clip. Before watching each video, participants are advised to move their head around to have a full experience.

Important: please make sure to provide the correct IPQ questionnaire to participants, depending on the order in which they visualize the clips.

After the tasks: participants are asked to answer preference questions in the post-questionnaire.

Latin square for AD test:

Participant	Videos		
Blind users			
RNIB1/UAB1	Episode 1, AD-C	Episode 2, AD-R	Episode 3, AD-E
RNIB2/UAB2	Episode 1, AD-R	Episode 2, AD-E	Episode 3, AD-C
RNIB3/UAB3	Episode 1, AD-E	Episode 2, AD-C	Episode 3, AD-R
RNIB4/UAB4	Episode1, AD-E	Episode 2, AD-R	Episode 3, AD-C
RNIB5/UAB5	Episode 1, AD-C	Episode 2, AD-E	Episode 3, AD-R
RNIB6/UAB6	Episode 1, AD-R	Episode 2, AD-C	Episode 3, AD-E

RNIB7/UAB7	Episode 1, AD-C	Episode 2, AD-R	Episode 3, AD-E
RNIB8/UAB8	Episode 1, AD-R	Episode 2, AD-E	Episode 3, AD-C
RNIB9/UAB9	Episode 1, AD-E	Episode 2, AD-C	Episode 3, AD-R
RNIB10/UAB10	Episode1, AD-E	Episode 2, AD-R	Episode 3, AD-C
RNIB11/UAB11	Episode 1, AD-C	Episode 2, AD-E	Episode 3, AD-R
RNIB12/UAB12	Episode 1, AD-R	Episode 2, AD-C	Episode 3, AD-E
RNIB13/UAB13	Episode 1, AD-C	Episode 2, AD-R	Episode 3, AD-E
RNIB14/UAB14	Episode 1, AD-R	Episode 2, AD-E	Episode 3, AD-C
RNIB15/UAB15	Episode 1, AD-E	Episode 2, AD-C	Episode 3, AD-R
RNIB16/UAB16	Episode1, AD-E	Episode 2, AD-R	Episode 3, AD-C
RNIB17/UAB17	Episode 1, AD-C	Episode 2, AD-E	Episode 3, AD-R
RNIB18/UAB18	Episode 1, AD-R	Episode 2, AD-C	Episode 3, AD-E
RNIB19/UAB19	Episode 1, AD-C	Episode 2, AD-R	Episode 3, AD-E
RNIB20/UAB20	Episode 1, AD-R	Episode 2, AD-E	Episode 3, AD-C
RNIB21/UAB21	Episode 1, AD-E	Episode 2, AD-C	Episode 3, AD-R
RNIB22/UAB22	Episode1, AD-E	Episode 2, AD-R	Episode 3, AD-C
RNIB23/UAB23	Episode 1, AD-C	Episode 2, AD-E	Episode 3, AD-R
RNIB24/UAB24	Episode 1, AD-R	Episode 2, AD-C	Episode 3, AD-E
RNIB25/UAB25	Episode 1, AD-C	Episode 2, AD-R	Episode 3, AD-E
RNIB26/UAB26	Episode 1, AD-R	Episode 2, AD-E	Episode 3, AD-C
RNIB27/UAB27	Episode 1, AD-E	Episode 2, AD-C	Episode 3, AD-R
RNIB28/UAB28	Episode1, AD-E	Episode 2, AD-R	Episode 3, AD-C
RNIB29/UAB29	Episode 1, AD-C	Episode 2, AD-E	Episode 3, AD-R
RNIB30/UAB30	Episode 1, AD-R	Episode 2, AD-C	Episode 3, AD-E

- **Test 3: AST presentation modes**

- **Measures:** Preferences.
- **Participants:** 60 (30 per partner)
- **Materials:**
 - **Device:** The test will be performed with an HMD
 - **Clips:** Two comparable clips. The order of the clips will be: part 1 followed by part 2, but the presentation modes will be randomized. A general audio introduction will be played at the beginning.
 - **Link:** <https://imac.gpac-licensing.com/test-ast-esp/>

Spanish test: “Opera”, split in two comparable clips. For each clip two AST versions will be produced (AST and AST-AD). The AST will be voiced by means of one human voice by CCMA. An audio introduction will be played at the beginning.

UK test: “Opera”, split in two comparable clips. For each clip two AST versions will be produced (AST and AST-AD). An audio introduction will be played at the beginning.

Before the tasks: The facilitator will explain this part of the experiment: testing 2 different AST presentation modes.

Tasks: Participants are asked to watch two clips (see latin square below).

Before watching each video, participants are advised to move their head around to have a full experience.

After tasks: participants are asked preference questions in the post-questionnaire.

Latin square for AST test:

Participant	Video	
Blind		
RNIB1/UAB1	Part 1, AST	Part 2, AST-AD
RNIB2/UAB2	Part 1, AST-AD	Part 2, AST
RNIB3/UAB3	Part 1, AST	Part 2, AST-AD
RNIB4/UAB4	Part 1, AST-AD	Part 2, AST
RNIB5/UAB5	Part 1, AST	Part 2, AST-AD
RNIB6/UAB6	Part 1, AST-AD	Part 2, AST
RNIB7/UAB7	Part 2, AST	Part 1, AST-AD
RNIB8/UAB8	Part 1, AST-AD	Part 2, AST
RNIB9/UAB9	Part 2, AST	Part 1, AST-AD
RNIB10/UAB10	Part 1, AST-AD	Part 2, AST
RNIB11/UAB11	Part 2, AST	Part 1, AST-AD
RNIB12/UAB12	Part 1, AST-AD	Part 2, AST

RNIB13/UAB13	Part 2, AST	Part 1, AST-AD
RNIB14/UAB14	Part 1, AST-AD	Part 2, AST
RNIB15/UAB15	Part 2, AST	Part 1, AST-AD
RNIB16/UAB16	Part 1, AST-AD	Part 2, AST
RNIB17/UAB17	Part 2, AST	Part 1, AST-AD
RNIB18/UAB18	Part 1, AST-AD	Part 2, AST
RNIB19/UAB19	Part 2, AST	Part 1, AST-AD
RNIB20/UAB20	Part 1, AST-AD	Part 2, AST
RNIB21/UAB21	Part 2, AST	Part 1, AST-AD
RNIB22/UAB22	Part 1, AST-AD	Part 2, AST
RNIB23/UAB23	Part 2, AST	Part 1, AST-AD
RNIB24/UAB24	Part 1, AST-AD	Part 2, AST
RNIB25/UAB25	Part 2, AST	Part 1, AST-AD
RNIB26/UAB26	Part 1, AST-AD	Part 2, AST
RNIB27/UAB27	Part 2, AST	Part 1, AST-AD
RNIB28/UAB28	Part 1, AST-AD	Part 2, AST
RNIB29/UAB29	Part 2, AST	Part 1, AST-AD
RNIB30/UAB30	Part 1, AST-AD	Part 2, AST

- **Farewell**

5. **Questionnaires:**

Questionnaires will be provided to the participants using online forms: **Demographic questionnaire for home users – Version 1** (Annex 45), **SUS** (Annex 43), **IPQ** (Annex 44).

Preference questions for User interaction:

EN

1. What do you like the most about the menu interaction?
2. What do you like less?
3. What do you think could be improved and how?
4. Other comments:

CAT

1. Què és el que més li agrada de l'interacció amb el menú?
2. Què és el que menys li agrada?
3. Què es podria millorar i com?
4. Altres comentaris:

Post-questionnaire: 2 test

EN

1. Which AD type do you prefer in 360°? Rank the AD modes according to your preferences: 1- preferred mode, 2- second preferred mode, 3 - the least preferred mode.

	1	2	3
• AD-C			
• AD-R			
• AD-E			

2. Please explain why you ranked the AD modes in this way.
3. How could AD be improved in this medium?
4. Other comments:

CAT

1. Quin tipus d'audiodescripció prefereix per als vídeos de 360°? Ordeni'ls segons les seves preferències: 1- el que més li agradi, 2 - el segon que més li agradi, 3 - el que menys li agradi.

	1	2	3
• AD-C			
• AD-R			
• AD-E			

2. Explica per què has ordena les seves preferències d'aquesta manera.
3. Com es podria millorar l'audiodescripció en aquest mitjà?
4. Altres comentaris:

Post-questionnaire: test 3

EN

1. Which type of audio subtitles do you prefer for 360° videos?
 - AST
 - AST-AD
2. Explain in your own words why you prefer the option chosen in the first question.
3. What system would you prefer?
 - Audio subtitles with no subtitles on screen
 - Audio subtitles with subtitles on screen that can be enlarged
 - I would like to select when I want subtitles on screen and when not
4. How could audio subtitles be improved in this medium?
5. In what excerpt did you feel more present?
 - Only AST
 - AST and AD
 - I did not feel present in any of them
 - I felt equally present in both
6. Other comments:

ES

1. ¿Qué tipo de audiosubtítulos prefiere para vídeos de 360º?
 - AST
 - AST-AD
2. Explique con sus propias palabras por qué prefiere la opción elegida en la primera pregunta.
3. ¿Qué sistema prefiere?
 - Audiosubtítulos sin subtítulos escritos en pantalla
 - Audiosubtítulos con subtítulos escritos que se pueden ampliar en pantalla
 - Me gustaría seleccionar cuándo quiero subtítulos escritos en pantalla o no.
4. ¿Cómo se podrían mejorar los audiosubtítulos en este medio?
5. ¿En qué extracto se sintió más presente?
 - Sólo AST
 - AST y AD
 - No me sentí presente en ningún fragmento
 - Me sentí igual presente en ambos
6. Otros comentarios:

ANNEX 30. CROSS-NATIONAL PILOT REPORT (RNIB)

1. General information

- **Partner responsible:** RNIB
- **Place and date:** London, UK 5.11.2019 – 30.01.2020
- **Access services discussed:** AD and AST
- **Research tool:** online questionnaires (Google Form)
- **Methodology:**
https://docs.google.com/document/d/1d4_1cmErhTJs_xvJXq5s5ZMCpEHecWijpacd_sFUMxA/edit

2. Demographic questionnaire:

- **Number of end users:** 31
 Link to responses:
https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1OaX3bTn13skAst9EtrPJIPv7gkwxu7_J-MhkrVG-gOM/edit#gid=1614339687
 (RNIB 17, 18, 19, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30)
- https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1ZE9RHJoT_yX4pdqrdB-Eo3sta1irG7WZ14-9B5ER8Q/edit#gid=369982870
 (RNIB 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 16, 20, 21)
- **Demographics for users:**
 1. Sex: 17 “male”, 14 “female”, 0 “other”, 0 “prefer not to reply”.
 2. Age: 1 “19”, 1 “22”, 2 “29”, 1 “30”, 2 “32”, 1 “33”, 1 “34”, 2 “35”, 2 “36”, 1 “37”, 1 “38”, 1 “39”, 2 “40”, 1 “41”, 1 “45”, 1 “46”, 1 “47”, 1 “48”, 1 “54”, 1 “55”, 1 “59”, 1 “65”, 2 “66”, 1 “73”, 1 “Prefer not to reply”
 3. Main language of the participants: 28 “English”, 1 “Punjabi”, 1 “South Korean”, 1 “English and German”
 4. Level of finished studies: 0 “no studies”, 0 “primary education”, 0 “secondary education”, 11 “further education”, 20 “university”.
 5. “I define myself as a...” 22 “blind person”, 9 “low vision person”, 0 “deaf person”, 0 “hearing impaired person”, 0 “deaf-blind person”.
 6. Age at which your disability began: 11 “From birth”, 8 “0-4”, 0 “5-12”, 2 “13-20”, 6 “21-40”, 1 “41-60”, 0 “More than 60”, 3 “Prefer not to say”
 7. What devices do you use on a daily basis? Multiple replies are possible: 31 “TV”, 19 “PC”, 20 “Laptop”, 30 “Mobile phone”, 12 “Tablet”, 2 “HMD” Others: ORCAM, Apple Watch, Braille reader, Braille note - Humanware, Bluetooth keyboard, Braille Display
 8. How often do you watch virtual reality content (for instance, 360° videos)?

	Never	Occasionally	At least once a month	At least once a week	Every day
In smartphone	26	3	1	1	0
On a tablet	31	0	0	0	0
On a PC	28	2	0	1	0
In smartphone plugged to HMD	28	2	1	0	0
In dedicated HMD (ie. Vive, Oculus)	29	2	0	0	0

9. If you have never used virtual reality content such as 360° videos or only occasionally, please indicate why. Multiple answers are possible. 0 "Because I am not interested.", 21 "Because it is not accessible.", 22 "Because I have not had the chance to use it.", 4 "Other reasons."
10. Please state your level of agreement with the following statement: "I am interested in virtual reality content (such as 360° videos)." 15 "I strongly agree", 14 "I agree", 2 "Neither agree nor disagree", 0 "Disagree", 0 "Strongly disagree"
11. Do you own any device to access virtual reality content? 17 "Yes", 9 "No", 5 "I don't know or I don't want to reply".
12. If you replied "yes" to the previous question, please specify which device(s).
Gear VR, Playstation + Oculus, Primer and 12 Smartphones/ tablets
13. Do you like watching the following types of content on television or online?

	I like it very much	I like it	Neither like it nor dislike it	I don't like it	I don't like it at all
News	7	14	8	2	0
Fiction (series, films)	13	14	3	1	0
Talk shows	4	10	11	5	1
Documentaries	18	10	3	0	0
Sports	6	6	12	2	5
Cartoons	0	9	12	8	2

14. How many hours a day do you watch audio described content? "None", 5 "Less than one hour", 12 "1-2 hours", 7 "2-3 hours", 1 "3-4 hours", 1 "4 hours and more", 5 "None"
15. What do you use to access online content? 7 "Magnifier (for example, ZoomText)", 19 "Screen reader (for example, JAWS, VoiceOver, TalkBack)", 4 "Both", 1 "None" (or prefer not to say).

Summary:

31 users from across the UK participated in the cross-national pilot. 9 of these 31 were partially sighted and 22 identified as blind. 14 were female and 17 males with ages ranging between 19 - 73 years. 20 participants attended university and 11 had undertaken further education. With the exception of 3, all selected English as their native or main language. Other languages outlined were Punjabi, South Korean and, German and English. TV, laptops, mobile phones, and tablets were the most frequently used devices with a few participants also identifying the following devices that they used frequently: ORCAM, Apple Watch, Braille reader, Braille note - Humanware, Bluetooth keyboard, Braille Display. In response to how often do they watch virtual reality content, most participants answered never with the exception 9 who responded occasionally - 3 on a smartphone and 2 each on PC, smartphone plugged to an HMD and dedicated HMD. 11 participants reported sight loss from birth. On access technology, 7 participants reported using magnification to access content, 19 used screen readers, four used a combination of both for navigation and one who preferred not to answer or none.

3. Results (test 1): interface interaction

3.1. System Usability Scale (SUS) results for blind users testing voice interaction:

Link to the results from the post-questionnaire:

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1wnskiK9NijjaBjXCB9Jlq5vNaqo4tIJknc6y6vwhmjw/edit#gid=1146644260>

3.1.1. SUS scores (question by question)

1 – strongly disagree

5 – strongly agree

Please indicate the number of replies that you have received for each rating: 15

SUS statements	1	2	3	4	5
1. I think that I would like to use this system frequently	0	1 (6.66%)	5 (33.33%)	3 (20%)	6 (40%)
2. I found the system unnecessarily complex	9 (60%)	4 (26.66%)	2 (13.33)	0	0
3. I thought the system was easy to use	0	0	2 (13.33)	6 (40%)	7 (46.66%)
4. I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system	8 (53.33%)	2 (13.33)	2 (13.33)	2 (13.33)	1 (6.66%)
5. I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	0	1 (6.66%)	3 (20%)	4 (26.66%)	7 (46.66%)
6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	10 (66.66%)	2 (13.33)	3 (20%)	0	0
7. I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly	0	0	4 (26.66%)	1 (6.66%)	10 (66.66%)
8. I found the system very cumbersome to use	9 (60%)	1 (6.66%)	5 (33.33%)	0	0
9. I felt very confident using the system	0	0	2 (13.33)	2 (13.33)	11 (73.33%)
10. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system	10 (66.66%)	1 (6.66%)	4 (26.66%)	0	0

3.1.2. System Usability Scale (SUS) results:

The SUS average score is **82.67**.

The graph below shows how the SUS scores associate with the percentile ranks and letter grades⁷ and the red line specifies where the ImAc AD editor is at this moment.

⁷ Sauro, J. 2011. Measuring usability with the System Usability Scale (SUS). Retrieved from <http://www.measuringu.com/sus.php>

The letter grade is A, and the obtained score corresponds to the percentile rank: 90%-95%⁸.

The excel spreadsheet with scores calculations can be consulted here: <https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1D0vn0yJpapUKhQsEWge4g3w1D4aFCHle>

3.2. System Usability Scale (SUS) results for partially sighted users testing the menu interaction:

Link to the results from the post-questionnaire: <https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1wnskiK9NijjaBjXCB9Jlq5vNaqo4tIJKnc6y6vwhmjw/edit#gid=146644260>

3.3.1. SUS scores (question by question)

1 – strongly disagree

5 – strongly agree

Please indicate the number of replies that you have received for each rating: 9

SUS statements	1	2	3	4	5
1. I think that I would like to use this system frequently	0	0	3 (33.33%)	2 (22.22%)	4 (44.44%)
2. I found the system unnecessarily complex	7 (77.77%)	1 (11.11%)	0	1 (11.11%)	0
3. I thought the system was easy to use	1 (11.11%)	0	0	1 (11.11%)	7 (77.77%)
4. I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system	9 (100%)	0	0	0	0
5. I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	0	0	1 (11.11%)	1 (11.11%)	7 (77.77%)
6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	9 (100%)	0	0	0	0
7. I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly	0	0	1 (11.11%)	0	8 (88.88%)
8. I found the system very cumbersome to use	9 (100%)	0	0	0	0
9. I felt very confident using the system	0	0	0	0	9 (100%)
10. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system	9 (100%)	0	0	0	0

3.3.2. System Usability Scale (SUS) results:

The SUS average score is **93.33**

The graph below shows how the SUS scores associate with the percentile ranks and letter grades⁹ and the red line specifies where the ImAc AD editor is at this moment.

⁸ Sauro, J. & Lewis, J. R. 2016. *Quantifying the user experience: Practical statistics for user research*. Amsterdam: Morgan Kaufmann, p. 203-204.

⁹ Sauro, J. 2011. Measuring usability with the System Usability Scale (SUS). Retrieved from <http://www.measuringu.com/sus.php>

The letter grade is A+, and the obtained score corresponds to the percentile rank: 96%-100%¹⁰.

The excel spreadsheet with scores calculations can be consulted here: <https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1D0vn0yJpapUKhQsEWge4g3w1D4aFCHle>

3.4. Preference questions

3.2.1. Preference questions for blind users

1. What do you like the most about the menu interaction?

RNIB1: I don't need to learn anything new...

RNIB3: I can use it independently. Voice assistants are common so there isn't anything new to learn.

RNIB4: I use a Google Home so it's nothing new. It's as one would expect it to be.

RNIB6: It's easy to use - I use it for other things at home.

RNIB7: Easy to use.

RNIB13: I don't like this interaction. I would prefer tactile buttons rather than these. Voiceover interrupts. This is distracting. Why can't I get buttons like regular people. Tactile buttons or arrow keys. Also when I'm listening to something then I have headphones for the experience doesn't work. Am I screaming over the headphones. Swipe commands would also work within app that give me the VR content. Or even add actions to activate AD / skip forward and back to the joy stick. Like the TV remote control which has an AD button.

RNIB9: If it wasn't for needing to repeat, Alexa - ask ImAc, it would have been very straightforward to use.

RNIB10: It's easy to use.

RNIB12: Good idea.

RNIB15: Good when it works.

RNIB16: It was very different to anything I have used before. Unusual way of interacting. though I use Siri on my phone, I have used it to activate my laptop or TV. So it was a new way of interacting. I doubt I will be using a voice assistant much - it's just not what I am used to. I prefer to use gestures and swipes on phone and remotes / buttons for devices.

RNIB19: It's as expected - I use Echo at home, it's not terribly efficient but does make navigation easier.

RNIB20: Easy to use.

RNIB21: Smooth. Easy to learn.

RNIB23: Can just talk without needing buttons.

RNIB24: You don't have to use the wake word every time.

RNIB25: Like the idea of voice control and avoiding the need for buttons.

RNIB26: It's straightforward.

RNIB28: Straightforward and easy commands.

2. What do you like less?

¹⁰ Sauro, J. & Lewis, J. R. 2016. *Quantifying the user experience: Practical statistics for user research*. Amsterdam: Morgan Kaufmann, p. 203-204.

RNIB1: I have to keep linking to the ImAc Player every few seconds. Why can't it remember the context - I'm using the ImAc Player so when I say, play video or pause video, it's for the video in ImAc.

RNIB3: I have to use an extra device which is always an additional hassle.

RNIB4: I prefer the Home - sound quality is much much better and it's also more responsive.

RNIB6: Nothing.

RNIB7: Nothing.

RNIB13: See above - also, VR is a personal experience, I don't want to be screaming over the content only so the Echo can hear me.

RNIB9: Repeating - Alexa - open ImAc every 5 seconds!

RNIB10: I have keep repeating 'Open ImAc' - which is annoying but understand that's characteristic of Echo and nothing to do with this system.

RNIB12: Confusing Trying to listen to video and AD and echo is too much on top.

RNIB15: Alexa keeps disconnecting so it doesn't take further commands.

RNIB16: It does not feel like a secure way of controlling my laptop.

RNIB19: No 'where am I'? I should be able to get a sensible answer if I am lost.

RNIB21: Need to remember all of the instructions.

RNIB23: Difficult to hear the responses from Alexa Had to uncover one ear. Needed to remember the commands and they're different from other devices owned. Had to wake Alexa before giving command.

RNIB24: nothing.

RNIB25: Finds smart assistants very irritating. Having to use watchword and timeout was an issue.

RNIB28: When the Echo doesn't respond.

3. What do you think could be improved and how?

RNIB1: See above.

RNIB3: Not sure...

RNIB4: - Too many commands and remembering them is a task.

-Keep the language natural.

- Play and pause is

RNIB6: Can't think of anything.

RNIB7: No idea.

RNIB13: See above.

RNIB9: See above.

RNIB10: Make it work with Siri and Voiceover so I don't have to switch devices. I don't use the VR glasses so I could use one single device.

RNIB12: Potentially better if integrated. Physical buttons would be far preferable.

RNIB15: Change the timeout.

RNIB16: Integrate with voiceover and siri on my iphone.

RNIB20: No improvement.

RNIB23: Potentially speed up the audio (or AD) for when just listening not watching. Would be nice to be able to change the AD voice (prefer male voices or maybe prefer deeper voices).

RNIB25: Not having to use the watchword each time or removing the timeout.

4. Other comments:

RNIB28: Volume up and down ended up changing the volume of the Echo not the video.

3.2.1. Preference questions for partially sighted users

1. What do you like the most about the menu interaction?

RNIB2: There was no way to change the brightness, can this be introduced?

RNIB5: High contrast is helpful and size of the buttons is good. Easy to navigate.

RNIB8: It's so clear - good colour contrast, no caps, no underlined text, good spacing, moving widget, highlighted.

RNIB11: It's clear what the buttons do.

RNIB14: This is how I want the whole of the VR to be like, so accessible! But still have a few recommendations:

1. Buttons - Add - Change colour when you point towards it so I know it's highlighted. Making it bold doesn't work for my sight.
2. Reaching the x to close the menu is a bit difficult. Is there anyway to make it disappear when I click outside the box?
3. Can I get AD on or AD off? And not just AD.
4. Also, the words AD are just too small. I want them bigger or I want the full audio description written.
5. Time for the video - how much time is left could be bigger.
6. Sliding bar could be bigger
7. Why not have a border around controls because you're relying on colour right now? Lot of people don't see colour. Maybe add the border when you're hovering over it?
8. Make the box of controls bigger? Or stretchable so I can make it bigger. So I hold it at one end and scale to the size I want.
7. I like being able to make the pointer bigger.

RNIB17: It's easy to use - I have sight in one eye so I had to adjust to the 360 view but all in all, ok.

RNIB17: It was like any other player with high contrast and magnification. Easy to use.

RNIB18: It's as expected.

RNIB22: It was easy to use.

RNIB27: Clear and easy to use.

RNIB30: The information it gives the user and the fact that it was easy to understand and use.

2. What do you like less?

RNIB5: I would have preferred to use voice interaction but that requires the use of a different device which does not make sense to me so I chose this. Not sure how this issue can be resolved....

RNIB11: Buttons seem far apart so not always easy to find the button you want.

RNIB14: See above.

RNIB17: Personally black on white would have been better than yellow.

RNIB17: Nothing.

RNIB18: No home button - that would make it easier.

RNIB22: I'm colour blind so the high contrast was helpful but even greater contrast would have been helpful.

RNIB27: Nothing - I cannot use the hardware myself though.

RNIB30: The fact that some of the information wasn't always easy to see.

3. What do you think could be improved and how?

RNIB2: Accessible interface:

- Size of the numbers (volume) is not big enough
 - Yellow pointer is very good size
 - AD button- can just about see it but the text (AD) should be bigger
- Settings
- Text is quite a good size
 - Text should be whiter so it's sharper
 - Good that you hover, the text turns yellow so you know what's been selected.
 - Right now the background is light so the contrast is good but when the background is dark, what happens then. Is there a dark outline? How does it stand out.

RNIB8: 1. Add a slider for the volume. Everything else is really clear.

RNIB11: Would help if the enhanced menu could more easily be reduced in size.

RNIB14: See above - Recommendation about the Oculus controller which isn't relevant here but adding here as FYI: Add an AD button on the controller.

RNIB17: Not sure.

RNIB17: No idea.

RNIB22: See above.

RNIB30: I think a zoom in feature would help. So people who use magnification can navigate with the level of magnification they need.

4. Other comments:

RNIB17: Nothing.

RNIB29: "Alexa has given me independence"

RNIB30: Overall it's a good feature. I look forward to seeing how it will be further developed.

Summary:

ImAc Player – navigation:

Depending on their preference and sight level, participants chose to test the voice led navigation provided through Amazon Echo or the enhanced interface designed with the user requirements of screen magnification users in mind.

Whilst participants found the experience of using the ImAc Player through voice interaction and the enhanced interface satisfactory and overall accessible, specific recommendations were put forth to improve the user experience.

Voice interaction:

Most participants commented that the interaction with the ImAc Player through Amazon Echo was accessible and easy to use. It is worth noting that most participants also admitted to either having tested an Echo previously or using Echo or another voice assistant like Google Home on a regular basis.

"I use a Google Home so it's nothing new. It's as one would expect it to be."

"It's as expected - I use Echo at home, it's not terribly efficient but does make navigation easier."

Anecdotal evidence also suggests that with both iOS and Android now supporting voice interaction through their native voice assistants (Siri and Google Home) and screen readers, growing number of blind and partially users are now accustomed to navigating connected services through voice. However, during the tests, most of the participants also expressed a strong interest in using other navigational mechanisms such as gestures/ swipes and tactile buttons for this experience.

"Though I use Siri on my phone, I have not used it to activate other devices. So, it was a new way of interacting. I doubt I will be using a voice assistant much for this- it's just not what I am used to. I prefer to use gestures and swipes on phone and remotes / buttons for devices."

"When I'm listening to something then I have headphones for the experience, so this doesn't work. Am I screaming over the headphones? Swipe commands would also work within app that give me the VR content. Or even add actions to activate AD / skip forward and back to the joystick. Like the TV remote control which has an AD button."

"VR is a personal experience. I don't want to be screaming over the content only so the Echo can hear me."

Participants also expressed frustration with the need to use specific commands to trigger specific actions.

Example:

Alexa, open ImAc.

Alexa, ask ImAc to list videos

Alexa, ask ImAc to play (xxx) video

Alexa, ask ImAc to pause video

It was widely acknowledged that this was characteristic of the way Echo or voice assistants in general were designed but participants felt that using conversational language instead of the suggested commands would vastly improve the experience.

“It was difficult to hear the responses from Alexa. Had to uncover one ear and then needed to remember the commands and they're different from other devices owned. Had to wake Alexa before giving command.”

“I have keep repeating 'Open ImAc' - which is annoying but understand that's characteristic of Echo and nothing to do with this system.”

“I had to keep linking to the ImAc Player every few seconds. Why can't it remember the context - I'm using the ImAc Player so when I say, play video or pause video, it's for the video in ImAc.”

Some participants also asked if using the same device could be used for consuming content and voice interaction. Example: using Siri to open and navigate BBC iPlayer in combination with VoiceOver.

“I have to use an extra device which is always an additional hassle. Alexa keeps disconnecting so it doesn't take further commands.”

However, it must be noted that even in view of the recommendations, using and navigating the ImAc Player using Echo was popular among most participants who offered to test the player again if the changes they had suggested, particularly on the ability to use conversational language, were to be implemented.

“The information it gives the user and the fact that it was easy to understand makes it a very pleasant experience. Only if it wasn't for needing to repeat, Alexa - ask ImAc, it would have been very straightforward too.”

Enhanced interface:

The enhanced interface was tested by people with low vision and generally, the experience was reported as accessible and easy to use. Even though recommendations were put forth by most testers, it would be useful to confirm these with a wider sample of users with low vision as these might closely relate to personal preferences and requirements for their level of sight.

“It's easy to use - I have sight in one eye so I had to adjust to the 360 view but all in all, ok. High contrast is helpful and size of the buttons is good. Easy to navigate.”

“This is how I want the whole of the VR to be like, so accessible! But still have a few recommendations to make it better. For example, change colour when you point towards the buttons. So, I know it's highlighted. Making it bold doesn't work for my sight.”

In addition, as expressed during the previous focus groups, participants with severe sight loss expressed frustration with the need to wear VR headset which was considered unnecessary and cumbersome.

4. TEST 2: AD PRESENTATION MODES

4.1. Results of the IPQ questionnaires

4.1.1. AD-C mode

Please indicate the number of replies that you have received for each rating: 31

IPQ questions	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1. In the computer generated world I had a sense of "being there".	3 (9.67%)	5 (16.12%)	0	7 (22.58%)	6 (19.35%)	7 (22.58%)	3 (9.67%)
2. Somehow I felt that the virtual world surrounded me.	2 (6.45%)	4 (12.90%)	4 (12.90%)	6 (19.35%)	6 (19.35%)	6 (19.35%)	3 (9.67%)
3. I felt like I was just perceiving pictures.	4 (12.90%)	3 (9.67%)	7 (22.58%)	8 (25.80%)	5 (16.12%)	3 (9.67%)	1 (3.22%)
4. I did not feel present in the virtual space.	1 (3.22%)	5 (16.12%)	3 (9.67%)	7 (22.58%)	8 (25.80%)	5 (16.12%)	2 (6.45%)
5. I had a sense of acting in the virtual space, rather than operating something from outside.	2 (6.45%)	4 (12.90%)	5 (16.12%)	8 (25.80%)	8 (25.80%)	2 (6.45%)	2 (6.45%)
6. I felt present in the virtual space.	1 (3.22%)	2 (6.45%)	3 (9.67%)	9 (29.03%)	4 (12.90%)	10 (32.25%)	2 (6.45%)
7. How aware were you of the real world surrounding while navigating in the virtual world? (i.e. sounds, room temperature, other people, etc.)?	1 (3.22%)	3 (9.67%)	7 (22.58%)	7 (22.58%)	6 (19.35%)	5 (16.12%)	2 (6.45%)
8. I was not aware of my real environment.	1 (3.22%)	3 (9.67%)	10 (32.25%)	5 (16.12%)	6 (19.35%)	4 (12.90%)	2 (6.45%)
9. I still paid attention to the real environment.	3 (9.67%)	7 (22.58%)	3 (9.67%)	6 (19.35%)	6 (19.35%)	4 (12.90%)	2 (6.45%)
10. I was completely captivated by the virtual world.	1 (3.22%)	3 (9.67%)	6 (19.35%)	8 (25.80%)	7 (22.58%)	4 (12.90%)	2 (6.45%)
11. How real did the virtual world seem to you?	3 (9.67%)	7 (22.58%)	3 (9.67%)	9 (29.03%)	4 (12.90%)	4 (12.90%)	1 (3.22%)
12. How much did your experience in the virtual environment seem consistent with your real world experience ?	1 (3.22%)	1 (3.22%)	7 (22.58%)	8 (25.80%)	9 (29.03%)	3 (9.67%)	2 (6.45%)
13. How real did the virtual world seem to you?	1 (3.22%)	2 (6.45%)	5 (16.12%)	10 (32.25%)	9 (29.03%)	1 (3.22%)	3 (9.67%)
14. The virtual world seemed more realistic than the real world.	4 (12.90%)	4 (12.90%)	6 (19.35%)	10 (32.25%)	6 (19.35%)	0	1 (3.22%)

4.1.2. AD-R mode

Please indicate the number of replies that you have received for each rating: 31

IPQ questions	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1. In the computer generated world I had a sense of "being there".	2 (6.45%)	2 (6.45%)	3 (9.67%)	4 (12.90%)	11 (35.48%)	6 (19.35%)	3 (9.67%)
2. Somehow I felt that the virtual world surrounded me.	2 (6.45%)	2 (6.45%)	6 (19.35%)	2 (6.45%)	11 (35.48%)	6 (19.35%)	2 (6.45%)
3. I felt like I was just perceiving pictures.	4 (12.90%)	7 (22.58%)	5 (16.12%)	7 (22.58%)	7 (22.58%)	0	7 (22.58%)
4. I did not feel present in the virtual	1	3	4	3	11	6	3

space.	(3.22%)	(9.67%)	(12.90%)	(9.67%)	(35.48%)	(19.35%)	(9.67%)
5. I had a sense of acting in the virtual space, rather than operating something from outside.	1 (3.22%)	4 (12.90%)	6 (19.35%)	5 (16.12%)	9 (29.03%)	4 (12.90%)	2 (6.45%)
6. I felt present in the virtual space.	1 (3.22%)	2 (6.45%)	5 (16.12%)	5 (16.12%)	9 (29.03%)	7 (22.58%)	3 (9.67%)
7. How aware were you of the real world surrounding while navigating in the virtual world? (i.e. sounds, room temperature, other people, etc.)?	1 (3.22%)	1 (3.22%)	7 (22.58%)	10 (32.25%)	6 (19.35%)	4 (12.90%)	2 (6.45%)
8. I was not aware of my real environment.	1 (3.22%)	4 (12.90%)	7 (22.58%)	5 (16.12%)	8 (25.80%)	2 (6.45%)	4 (12.90%)
9. I still paid attention to the real environment.	2 (6.45%)	6 (19.35%)	4 (12.90%)	7 (22.58%)	7 (22.58%)	3 (9.67%)	2 (6.45%)
10. I was completely captivated by the virtual world.	1 (3.22%)	2 (6.45%)	7 (22.58%)	7 (22.58%)	6 (19.35%)	5 (16.12%)	3 (9.67%)
11. How real did the virtual world seem to you?	4 (12.90%)	4 (12.90%)	6 (19.35%)	9 (29.03%)	6 (19.35%)	1 (3.22%)	1 (3.22%)
12. How much did your experience in the virtual environment seem consistent with your real world experience ?	1 (3.22%)	2 (6.45%)	6 (19.35%)	4 (12.90%)	10 (32.25%)	5 (16.12%)	3 (9.67%)
13. How real did the virtual world seem to you?	1 (3.22%)	1 (3.22%)	6 (19.35%)	10 (32.25%)	6 (19.35%)	4 (12.90%)	3 (9.67%)
14. The virtual world seemed more realistic than the real world.	4 (12.90%)	2 (6.45%)	8 (25.80%)	15 (48.38%)	0	0	3 (9.67%)

4.1.3. AD-E mode

Please indicate the number of replies that you have received for each rating: 31

IPQ questions	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1. In the computer generated world I had a sense of "being there".	3 (9.67%)	1 (3.22%)	2 (6.45%)	7 (22.58%)	8 (25.80%)	6 (19.35%)	4 (12.90%)
2. Somehow I felt that the virtual world surrounded me.	4 (12.90%)	3 (9.67%)	0	7 (22.58%)	9 (29.03%)	4 (12.90%)	4 (12.90%)
3. I felt like I was just perceiving pictures.	5 (16.12%)	6 (19.35%)	8 (25.80%)	3 (9.67%)	5 (16.12%)	1 (3.22%)	3 (9.67%)
4. I did not feel present in the virtual space.	3 (9.67%)	3 (9.67%)	3 (9.67%)	3 (9.67%)	7 (22.58%)	8 (25.80%)	4 (12.90%)

5. I had a sense of acting in the virtual space, rather than operating something from outside.	2 (6.45%)	4 (12.90%)	5 (16.12%)	5 (16.12%)	10 (32.25%)	2 (6.45%)	3 (9.67%)
6. I felt present in the virtual space.	2 (6.45%)	1 (3.22%)	7 (22.58%)	5 (16.12%)	6 (19.35%)	6 (19.35%)	4 (12.90%)
7. How aware were you of the real world surrounding while navigating in the virtual world? (i.e. sounds, room temperature, other people, etc.)?	2 (6.45%)	3 (9.67%)	5 (16.12%)	5 (16.12%)	7 (22.58%)	6 (19.35%)	3 (9.67%)
8. I was not aware of my real environment.	2 (6.45%)	2 (6.45%)	3 (9.67%)	6 (19.35%)	8 (25.80%)	7 (22.58%)	3 (9.67%)
9. I still paid attention to the real environment.	3 (9.67%)	6 (19.35%)	8 (25.80%)	4 (12.90%)	6 (19.35%)	2 (6.45%)	2 (6.45%)
10. I was completely captivated by the virtual world.	2 (6.45%)	2 (6.45%)	4 (12.90%)	6 (19.35%)	6 (19.35%)	8 (25.80%)	3 (9.67%)
11. How real did the virtual world seem to you?	4 (12.90%)	6 (19.35%)	7 (22.58%)	4 (12.90%)	8 (25.80%)	0	2 (6.45%)
12. How much did your experience in the virtual environment seem consistent with your real world experience ?	2 (6.45%)	2 (6.45%)	5 (16.12%)	9 (29.03%)	7 (22.58%)	3 (9.67%)	3 (9.67%)
13. How real did the virtual world seem to you?	2 (6.45%)	0	3 (9.67%)	11 (35.48%)	10 (32.25%)	3 (9.67%)	2 (6.45%)
14. The virtual world seemed more realistic than the real world.	4 (12.90%)	5 (16.12%)	3 (9.67%)	14 (45.16%)	2 (6.45%)	1 (3.22%)	2 (6.45%)

Summary:

Table 1 presents mean values for the comparison of three types of audio description (R – Radio Drama, E – Extended AD and C - Classic) per each scale through the IPQ questionnaire, which measures spatial presence, involvement and experienced realism.

	General presence	Spatial presence	Involvement	Experienced realism
AD-R	4.61	4.32	3.97	3.99
AD-E	4.61	4.22	4.22	3.92
AD-C	4.32	4.10	3.90	3.83

Table 1. Mean values – IPQ.

All statistical analyses have been conducted with SPSS v. 26. Results are the following:

- A non-parametric test was carried to compare the IPQ scores of Blind and Partially users, due to difference in participants number (22 and 9, respectively).

The Independent-Samples Mann-Whitney U test comparing the results for each subscale did not show any significant difference (all $P > .05$). Therefore, the rest of the tests have been conducted on the whole users' sample ($N=31$) using parametric statistics.

- Paired samples statistics T-tests, comparing each subscale result with that of each other did not show any statistically significant difference. The IPQ scale results are not different for each type of audio description. They do not differ in General Presence (all $p > .05$); not for Spatial Presence (all $p > .05$); and neither for Experienced realism (all $p > .05$).

A table displaying the planned comparisons is shown next.

Paired Samples Test									
		Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	RG1 - EG1	0.000	1.713	0.308	-0.628	0.628	0.000	30	1.000
Pair 2	RG1 - CG1	0.290	2.283	0.410	-0.547	1.128	0.708	30	0.484
Pair 3	EG1 - CG1	0.290	2.053	0.369	-0.463	1.043	0.788	30	0.437
Pair 4	Rsp - Esp	0.09677	0.99314	0.17837	-0.26751	0.46106	0.543	30	0.591
Pair 5	Rsp - Csp	0.21935	1.13061	0.20306	-0.19536	0.63407	1.080	30	0.289
Pair 6	Esp - Csp	0.12258	1.35221	0.24286	-0.37341	0.61858	0.505	30	0.617
Pair 7	Rinv - Einv	-0.25000	0.90600	0.16272	-0.58232	0.08232	-1.536	30	0.135
Pair 8	Rinv - Cinv	0.07258	0.98360	0.17666	-0.28821	0.43337	0.411	30	0.684
Pair 9	Einv - Cinv	0.32258	1.05118	0.18880	-0.06299	0.70816	1.709	30	0.098
Pair 10	Rreal - Ereal	0.06452	0.88026	0.15810	-0.25837	0.38740	0.408	30	0.686
Pair 11	Rreal - Creal	0.15323	0.93914	0.16868	-0.19125	0.49771	0.908	30	0.371
Pair 12	Ereal - Creal	0.08871	0.91640	0.16459	-0.24743	0.42485	0.539	30	0.594

Table 2. Planned comparisons for each IPQ subscale across Audio Description types.

According to these results, the type of audio description does not have any effect on the presence for the users of this sample.

4.2. Results of the AD post-questionnaire

1. Which AD type do you prefer in 360°? Rank the AD modes according to your preferences: 1- preferred mode, 2- second preferred mode, 3 - the least preferred mode.

AD-C: 11 – preferred mode, 9 – second preferred mode, 11 – the least preferred mode.

AD-R: 13 – preferred mode, 14 – second preferred mode, 4 – the least preferred mode.

AD-E: 9 – preferred mode, 10 – second preferred mode, 12 – the least preferred mode.

2. Please explain why you ranked the AD modes in this way.

RNIB1: See in comments below.

RNIB2: I like the extended descriptions and the extra bits of info there. I would like these in films. What do the characters look like- what are they wearing. What's happening in the scene around them.

RNIB4: See comments below.

RNIB 5: Classic - this was my favourite. It was the standard description like it's supposed to sound. Radio drama: the presenter was being too cynical. It didn't work for me and I found it intrusive. Too many details that I didn't need. I would rather have heard the crowds to find out that it is crowded than telling me in describing. Now that would be immersive.

Enhanced - the start and stop irritated me and made it boring. It broke the experience for me completely!

RNIB6: Radio and classic – preferred

No echo – sound quality

Extended AD

- Helpful to have a description of the anchor
- This description would be helpful in AI
- Extended AD to be optional only - never mandatory

Male describer

- Didn't like the delivery
- Sounded like the describer was at the site – positive. In the moment. In reality – it feels like someone is with me – so it makes more real.
- Intonation – voice not clear
- Extended description – don't lose the ambience (OBA)
- More description leads to the feeling of being there. But it shouldn't be too much.

Female

- Voice softer – blended. Clearer.
- Complemented the main script – could be because two female voices.
- Harp scene in ep 2 (good description to paint a picture – flowers, gates etc.)

AI

Warmish – setting the scene

EP3

- Remembered the description of the Grotto with the ambience

RNIB7:

Classic

I hated it. Did not give me any information at all. It sounds as if it has been added just to fill up the gap in narration

Extended

This felt as if I'm on a tour of the site and stopped when I wanted more information. This is what I would do in real life

Radio

Perfect. I didn't like the voice or the recording but the concept is perfect. I love listening to talking books and this is what it was like - talking book. Narrating a chapter to me.

RNIB8:

Music on all modes

Needs to be lower - AD should be much (much!) louder.

Enhanced

Extra description is useful. Helps in trying to paint a picture. What's in front, left and right. Binaural effect would add to it. Right now description on TV is flat and that's why I don't use it. This could be made more immersive by adding location sounds. Paint an image – 3-Dimensional.

Classic

Paints a much better picture of the surrounding. Helps visualise. This is more immersive. Tells me a lot more about other people are seeing what's in front of the camera shot.

Radio

drama

Not implemented properly. Starting and stopping doesn't really bother in enhanced but I don't

like the combination of male and female voice. Narrator's voice is much better- why use the male voice at all. It doesn't work. Why aren't we using the narrator? If it's a radio drama- then it should be the same for everyone - no special consideration for blind people.

RNIB9: I like the AI. Sets the mood. But after that there was just too much talking especially in enhanced AD.

On extended AD:
- Some info is good and interesting but most people don't want to know about every gate - every nook and corner.
- "Welcome to the background information" - No need to say it every time
- At times, there is too much info in the enhanced AD
- Don't need to repeat details about landscape, I'm not interested.
- I wouldn't switch use the enhanced AD if it was optional

Classic
- Similar to the one that I would listen to on TV and film. Nothing special.

Radio drama
- Best one out of the three. Hadn't realised it was AD!
- Sentences were short and to the point. Worked with the feel of the programme. But it would depend on the type of programme -
- Radio drama preferred for documentaries and recorded live shows but classic for films and TV shows as you can't match the delivery of actors all the time.

RNIB10:

Classic
I liked it because that's one I'm used to.

Extended
I found it disconcerting. I was given all the information – then the information did not correlate to the action. It was just extra information. I found that it made me work hard. When you watch TV – you don't want to work. AD enhances the movie – you don't expect it to make you work. I wasn't sure what to do with all that extra information.

Radio Drama
I could adjust to it. It worked well. It was incorporated within the actual documentary. Different in the sense that it felt more personal. I'm used to being AD being more impartial. I was confused – is it audio description? It was almost like the presenter and the describer were working together. So there was no distinction. For example – my family will use AD because they know I need it. The last one will incorporate the two – they as sighted people will accept because it was part of the documentary. The intonation made me feel that it was the presenter and not the describer. That's the effect they will get as well. It is hard to pick-up. This might be the answer if I'm watching content with a group of sighted people. I used to it being a side passage and not being integrated into the story.

RNIB11: Clearer description, felt more spatial Immersion felt better on second one.

RNIB12: Disliked any of the presentations. Headset too cumbersome and heavy. Disliked being cut-off from the real-world.

RNIB13: Extended AD
1. Didn't like the bell mode because I can't be bothered to pause it.
2. Breaks my focus and enjoyment. Breaks the flow.
3. Give it at the end - if you want more information and then add it as a soundtrack.

Classic
It was fine - I'm used to it. Nothing special

Radio

Liked it because it gave me a lot more information in a more informal way which worked for me.

RNIB14:

Extended

1. Extended will work for a game - it might be useful. In a film or a drama, I don't like it.
2. Don't like the bell. Make it available across the episode. So when I wanted to know more - I can just tap the screen and this will be activated soon as it's available.
3. I want it to be immersive so it's a fade in and out. Add sound effects.

Classic

Pair of cozy slippers - I'm so used to it.

Radio

It's the Netflix feel but the mix didn't work for me. It's too quiet.

RNIB15: Liked the level of detail given in the classic version. Sound levels on the Radio version were all over the place.

RNIB16: I want detail in descriptions and to be able to hear the descriptions clearly. When the AD talks about a "black and white mural" I want to know what it's of. When it mentions the protester throwing a bunch of flowers I want to know what kind of flowers.

RNIB16:

Classic

- Lack of description – needed more explanation
- Voice was fine – the fact that you heard background noises as good but they disappear when the description comes in.
- Feels disjointed – there are too many stories within the story....

Radio

Drama

- Made so much more sense – it was description of things by a person who was at the scene
- Looking at things and not being all serious like the main anchor who was boring
- It seemed more real
- Explain why there is a sound of the bazaar which you don't get in the other versions
- It almost feels like a first person account. Felt like I am there...
- Better production quality is needed – of course.

Extended

- It makes the whole thing longer – but here I had to listen it for research, normally I wouldn't trigger it unless I was really curious
- Not s good commentary anyway – if this was an audio book, I would be rally angry with it.
- Every time the person says – thank you for joining me behind the scene. Make the opening interesting

I do like the music but you hear random noises that don't make sense in that scene. It was a commentary – that's all.

RNIB17:

Extended

descriptions

- Audio description is interrupted by the first extended AD
- Some unnecessary information was included for example 140 acres – this needs more explanation from a visual point of view
- The starting and stopping interrupted my flow – but its good that the default is not on. So, if I didn't want to listen to it and I won't have to...
- This may work well for a tour of the gallery or as tour guide.

Classic

description

- Absolutely fine. No surprises. Most practical one to produce. It's one we listen to on TV.

Radio

description

- I like this format but this might be some production issues i.e., adding anything at the end will never like it's part of the production. Or maybe it can. Sounds good. Best of the three but

needs better production quality.
- Maybe if the action is happening on the left – then the volume could be slightly louder on your left. So that’s an indication because I don’t want the sound to come from the left only! That would be jarring.

RNIB18: Classic

- Lack of description – needed more explanation
- Voice was fine – the fact that you heard background noises as good but they disappear when the description comes in.
- Feels disjointed – there are too many stories within the story....

Radio Drama

- Made so much more sense – it was description of things by a person who was at the scene
- Looking at things and not being all serious like the main anchor who was boring
- It seemed more real
- Explain why there is a sound of the bazaar which you don’t get in the other versions
- It almost feels like a first person account. Felt like I am there...
- Better production quality is needed – of course.

Extended

- It makes the whole thing longer – but here I had to listen it for research, normally I wouldn’t trigger it unless I was really curious
- Not a good commentary anyway – if this was an audio book, I would be really angry with it.
- Every time the person says – thank you for joining me behind the scene. Make the opening interesting
I do like the music but you hear random noises that don’t make sense in that scene.
It was a commentary – that’s all.

RNIB19: Classic

- Exactly what I was expecting
- Clashed with the music and with commentary
- Wild track – trying to work out whether I should be listening to chatter in the background or the main description
- The voice was clear – it was like I was expecting.

Radio

- Trebly effect did not work – so the echo we added did not work – it was distracting
- Description is more personal – got more from it. Felt like I was listening to an audio book than a music video
- It was good because I understood more here but this wouldn’t work in a film or a drama
- 3 monkeys game has a guide that tells you what’s happening so I got a better idea of what was on the screen in the context of that piece
- Worked better than a description
- First one (classic) you get a more literal description. This one shared the experience. More imagery coming from the second one.
- Pre-show notes for a series would work – so an audio introduction. I would like to know about the describer – what does the describer look like...

Extended

- My attention diverted because of the extended descriptions – they needed to be more immersive
- There were too many things being explained to me.
- No more than 2 in an episode this short, I’d say.
- And add sound effects to it – like you did for the radio drama
- The soundscape has to be meaningful and it wasn’t here.
- Mix of historical facts and context – I can see the benefit of it but has to be better treated
- And always an option as the it would make the programme so much longer

Film, drama – lose the thread of the story and film

RNIB20: The quality of the description.

RNIB21: Very clear music was atmospheric.

RNIB22:

1. Sounds from all directions
2. I was able to build a picture
3. Going under the gates – I think sound changed.

Radio

1. First voice was paced better – there was a lot to digest and because of the speed, it was very difficult to digest everything.
2. Although it was a more personal experience – there was no detachment, but it added that extra personal flair
3. If the speaking was slower then it would be smoother.

Extended

1. I thought it was really really helpful – especially if you want to go there. This is the kind of thing you want as an audio file or a CD. And when you are there – this track is triggered at the right point.
2. The speech was so clear – the female was building the picture and the man giving you the details so they have their roles cut out. I enjoyed the clarity. The two characters played very well off each other.
3. Not enough emotion in the description in the extended AD
4. I was filling in a lot of gaps because I couldn't visualise the extended description. Where is the person standing? There was no background sound so you join the dots in the main action but not the extended AD.

RNIB23: Liked the Radio best. Would have preferred the extended AD to have more atmosphere and less History to it.

RNIB24: Classic gave a better understanding of the video than Radio. Extended gives a better experience of whole episode.

RNIB25: Radio "brought you along with the describer". Extended could work if it's at the right point and in the right content. Classic describes what you're seeing Radio describes what you're feeling.

RNIB26:

1. Good AD- enjoyed it. Classic
2. There were sound effects that were not necessarily explained by then that's the challenge of AD. You can't explain everything.
3. Change the tonality – crystal clear voice vs muffled sound. Quality of sound differed a lot

Radio

1. Much more satisfying listen in terms of understanding the story. Got a lot more out of that than the classic.
2. It is doing something very different. It's not really audio description. This is a format of story-telling. It's not a bad thing- it's a different thing.
3. When the artist – director of the video knows what he is trying to convey. This puts me in the hands of the describer because it heavily interpreted by the describer. The scripting and intonation was so good that I was not independently trying to understand what is happening.
4. Film is designed to be different things to different people- if you are watching a multi layered piece then you would end potentially faired to someone's interpretation.
5. Detract from the original piece

Extended

6. I was on a roller coaster – no time to breathe. It was quite intense
7. Enjoyed this one – more for the details and noticed some instances where sounds were apparent to me than the other two
8. I was able to immerse myself more than the other two maybe it was because of the details
9. Soundscape improved my perception of the scene

10. Extended descriptions – very useful as it brings the story to life -gives me exactly what I want.

RNIB27: Classic description
The AD fit the piece really well. I could visualise. AI was just about sufficient.
The lady was quite descriptive and the two voices worked well together.

Extended
Makes it more interactive
It's optional as well
Documentaries – it's ideal but I can see it working with dramas especially the slower pace.
For example Poirot – give an extended description of what Poirot is looking at
But it needs to have background soundtrack for continuity

Radio drama
It was quite nice to have two presenters – felt more like he was walking with her. And then
you are exploring with them.
It feels like you are travelling description.
Nice rounded experience.

RNIB28: Radio set the scene better. Extra AD (extended) on entering the building set the scene and helped you imagine it more.

RNIB29: Radio felt more real. Felt like the environment not like someone was just talking to me. Extended, liked that I was given more information.

RNIB30: I ranked them based on the type of description I preferred for the clips.

3. How could AD be improved in this medium?

RNIB1: See below in comments.

RNIB2: Make it even more emotive. Like the AD on Netflix. Add more emotion to it.

RNIB3: Hard to understand the describer at times. He sounded distant.

RNIB4: See comments below.

RNIB5: You need to think all the different aspects - tone of the describer, accent, language and most importantly in VR, sound. Like you'd done for Pearl. I like the privilege of sound. Why wasn't that done for these clips? Privilege of sound with different scripts but that is a must!

RNIB6: See above.

RNIB7: Better sound quality and mixing.

RNIB8: See above.

RNIB9: See above.

RNIB10: See above.

RNIB11: More directional/positional content, better quality recording on radio.

RNIB12: Just headphones with bone conduction or ambient pass-through would be better.

RNIB13: See above.

RNIB14: See above.

RNIB16: Reduced background sound to be able to concentrate on AD. Want more colours and detail. Helps to imagine the scene better.

RNIB16: See above.

RNIB17: See above.

RNIB18: See above.

RNIB19: See above.

RNIB20: Instead of tone in Extended speech giving a brief idea of what the Extended Description entails eg "Layout of city"

RNIB21: Nothing.

RNIB23: More info about atmospheric bits rather than history etc.

RNIB24: More frequent AD utterances rather than chunks which break up the content.

RNIB25: Didn't like the "Hi there" in extended AD. Broke the flow.

RNIB26: See above.

RNIB27: See above.

RNIB28: More sound effects and less music. Ambient sounds set the scene more. Maybe still music for intro and outro.

RNIB29: Music was a bit loud at times.

RNIB30: I don't know. I think it's on the right track so far.

4. Other comments:

RNIB4: Enhanced: I would not never start-stop- start-stop as it breaks the flow. Immersion is important. Be there in my head.

RNIB6: See above.

RNIB8: See above.

RNIB10: See above.

RNIB12: Would perhaps like the video presented on a TV screen with navigation controls instead.

RNIB13: See above.

RNIB14: See above.

RNIB15: Liked the background music which gave a feeling of being there.

RNIB16: I really liked the audio introduction. It helps me visualise the scene better.

RNIB28: Liked descriptions of the people "kissing the star" and "taking their shoes off". Helped to picture the scene.

RNIB29: Real fan of audio description and really pleased to have it.

RNIB30: None.

Summary:

Classic mode:

- 11 participants chose the classic mode as their preferred track.
- 9 participants chose this as their second most preferred option
- 11 participants rated this as the least liked option out of the three modes presented to them during the test

It was worth noting that most participants who rated this mode as their most preferred option commented that how much it resembled the service on TV and this was how audio description was meant to sound.

"Classic - this was my favourite. It was the standard description like it's supposed to sound."

"Classic description - Absolutely fine. No surprises. Most practical one to produce. It's one we listen to on TV."

"Pair of cozy slippers - I'm so used to it."

"Classic paints a much better picture of the surroundings. Helps me visualise. This is more immersive. Tells me a lot more about other people are seeing - what's in front of the camera."

However, other participants, mostly occasional viewers of TV programmes and therefore, occasional users of audio description felt that this mode lacked the feel of the original content which affected their enjoyment and immersion.

"Classic, I hated it. Did not give me any information at all. It sounds as it has been added just to fill up the gap in narration."

"Very old school. Like on the TV. Just sit and watch something made specially for blind people. It's not great. The describer should not talk over the sound effects like the harp."

Feedback on the radio drama mode:

- 13 participants chose this as their preferred track.
- 14 participants chose this as their second most preferred option

- 4 participants rated this as the least liked option out of the three modes presented to them during the test

Participants who chose this as their most preferred option commented that the experience of listening to this track was much more satisfying as they got a lot more out of it than the classic mode particularly when it came to perceiving the feel of the content. It was interesting to note, in contrast to the classic version, a fair majority of the participants who chose this as their preferred option tended to be occasional viewers of TV programmes and therefore audio description. Instead audio content such as radio dramas, talking books and PODCASTS was their choice of media.

“I didn't like the voice or the recording, but the concept is perfect. I love listening to talking books and this is what it was like - talking book. Narrating a chapter to me.”

“Felt like I was listening to an audio book - it was good because I understood more here but this wouldn't work in a film or a drama. In classic, you get a more literal description. This one is for shared experience. More imagery coming from the second one.”

“I'm used to being AD being more impartial so I was confused – is it audio description? It was almost like the presenter and the describer were working together. So, there was no distinction. For example – my family will use AD because they know I need it. The last one will incorporate the two – they as sighted people will accept because it was part of the documentary. The intonation made me feel that it was the presenter and not the describer. That's the effect they will get as well. It is hard to pick-up where the AD ends and the commentary starts. This might be the answer if I'm watching content with a group of sighted people. I used to it being a side passage and not being integrated into the story.”

However, not all participants found this mode enjoyable or even as useful as the standard description offered in the classic version. They felt it relied heavily on the interpretation of the describer which influenced how they felt about the content.

“It is doing something very different. It's not really audio description. This is a format of storytelling. It's not a bad thing- it's a different thing. The artist – director of the video knows what he is trying to convey but this puts me in the hands of the describer because it is heavily interpreted by the describer. The scripting and intonation were so good that I was not independently trying to understand what was happening. Film is designed to be different things to different people.”

Feedback on the extended AD mode:

- 9 participants chose the extended mode as their preferred track.
- 10 participants chose this as their second most preferred option
- 12 participants rated this as the least liked option of the three modes presented to them during the test

Unlike the other two modes, in the extended description test, it was up to the viewer whether to trigger the extended descriptions beyond the first instance. In order to trigger, the viewer would need to tap the mousepad twice after hearing a short beep that would indicate the presence of extended description track. Once triggered, the main video would pause for the duration for the extended description and then continue once it had ended. The duration of tracks varied between 20 – 45 seconds and gave additional information on those aspects of the video that were not crucial for understanding of the story but gave details to build further familiarity with different aspects of the content. For example: the first instance of this mode in the first episode described the main anchor, her attire and the general look- feel of the content. In their feedback, whilst some viewers agreed that it added that depth to the experience, it wasn't a viable option for TV viewing.

“My attention diverted because of the extended descriptions – they needed to be more immersive - There were too many things being explained to me. - No more than 2 in an episode this short, I’d say. - And add sound effects to it – like you did for the radio drama - The soundscape has to be meaningful and it wasn’t here. - Mix of historical facts and context – I can see the benefit of it but has to be better treated - And always an option as the it would make the programme so much longer.”

“Extended I found it disconcerting. I was given all the information – then the information did not correlate to the action. It was just extra information. I found that it made me work hard. When you watch TV – you don’t want to work. AD enhances the movie – you don’t expect it to make you work. I wasn’t sure what to do with all that extra information.”

“I like the extended descriptions and the extra bits of info there. I would like these in films. What do the characters look like- what are they wearing. What's happening in the scene around them.”

Most participants felt that whilst extended description added to the overall feel of the content, it would probably not work for the content they watched on TV. Among others, reasons cited were that they would find it hard to sustain interest in the content with the additional details and affecting the overall enjoyment of the programme. Gaming, live tours in museums and heritage sites were given as examples of where this presentation mode might work well. However, not all agreed.

“Makes it more interactive. It’s optional as well. For documentaries – it’s ideal but I can see it working with dramas too especially the ones with the slower pace. For example, Poirot – give an extended description of what Poirot is looking at but it needs to have background soundtrack for continuity.”

5. TEST 3: AST PRESENTATION MODES

1. Which type of audio subtitles do you prefer for 360° videos?

AST: 8

AST-AD: 23

2. Explain in your own words why you prefer the option chosen in the first question.

RNIB 1: First one is too abrupt. It's almost as if sentences have been left incomplete.

RNIB2: AST for the libretto and the AD for description of the screenplay. Different voices for the two though like the Passion of the Christ. Mel Gibson film. Different voice for both and it worked really well.

RNIB3: There was not enough AD. AST were fine but you need to know what is happening on the screen too. the screen play is important.

RNIB4: I don't want description while the singing is on. I just want a translation but the voice needs to be somewhat softer for Romeo and Juliet.

RNIB5: I didn't like either of the two but since chose this as there were only 2 options in the question above. You should add - none to the alternatives above. Audio mixing was not good and the content is not good for the purpose. There is singing all throughout.

RNIB6: AD - I like when description tells me what is happening on the screen when the action is taking place. But this AD wasn't helpful because it anticipated a lot of the action. AST - they're not singing in English so I need subtitles otherwise I wouldn't know what they're saying. I can enjoy the singing later once I know the lyrics.

RNIB7: It should be like the radio mode - make it into a talking book - explain what's on the screen and tell me the dialogues so the piece would make sense. I can't waste my time on things that I don't understand.

- RNIB8:** As long as I have an audio introduction and then audio subtitles, why should I need AD? AI gives me the detail on the sets, costumes, characters etc. AST translates the dialogues. If AD is added, there is just too much talking!
- RNIB9:** It sounded better - AD did not tell me anything new. But then I know the play well do maybe that's why I didn't feel the need for extra description.
- RNIB10:** I understood more.
- RNIB11:** Preferred the audio mix of AST-AD version.
- RNIB12:** More description, better idea of who was singing rather than just what they were saying. Not too intrusive. Still get to hear the music.
- RNIB13:** I prefer detailed descriptions.
- RNIB14:** I can see a little bit so if I sit close enough - I don't need the description.
- RNIB15:** Wants to know what the actors are saying.
- RNIB16:** Would actually want both so I can listen to the audio description and know what's happening then go back and listen to the AST to know what's being said. If I could only have one then I could read the libretto before hand.
- RNIB16:** I am blind so I need description to tell me what's happening on the screen.
- RNIB17:** I am sighted in one eye though I am registered blind. But if I sit close enough to the screen, it works. So in the VR glasses - the experience is accessible but not clear enough. Therefore not enjoyable. I think the combination of AD and AST made the screenplay clearer for me - I didn't have to focus too much.
- RNIB18:** I can see quite a bit especially when I sit close to the screen so AD just gets in the way of me enjoying the opera.
- RNIB19:** I didn't like either but none was not an option.
- RNIB20:** More free flowing. AD shouldn't get in the way of the enjoyment.
- RNIB21:** Liked the explanation of the scene.
- RNIB22:** It just sounded better to me - more balanced.
- RNIB23:** Could mainly understand because of the sound effects. If that hadn't been clear then may have preferred the other one.
- RNIB24:** Felt more present. More description of what was going on.
- RNIB25:** Understand why what's happening more than what's happening. Although speech walked the listener through which meant the tension couldn't build. Lose the emotional effect from the opera music.
- RNIB27:** It interprets the dialogues so AST is useful but I wished AI was more useful. There was hardly any info in AI. AI should be more detailed.
- RNIB28:** You could hear more of the drama that was going on in the background.
- RNIB29:** Needed the French translated.
- RNIB30:** To me this version felt like it helped me understand what was happening in the clip more than the other version.

3. What system would you prefer?

Audio subtitles with no subtitles on screen: 14

Audio subtitles with subtitles on screen that can be enlarged: 4

I would like to select when I want subtitles on screen and when not: 13

4. How could audio subtitles be improved in this medium?

- RNIB1:** Add even more audio description especially if there is a lot happening on the screen as in this clip. But I also want to listen to the music. Maybe try enhanced description here. I can listen to the music and also get the description.
- RNIB2:** If they kept up with what was being said because not everything was AST'ed in this clip. The clip with only AD was partially accessible at best.
- RNIB3:** Add different voices - like in dubbing.
- RNIB4:** Operas don't need any access features. It's the music you come to enjoy. It's not about the story. You can read the story in advance. Audio introduction should be sufficient.
- RNIB6:** Better sound quality!
- RNIB7:** Better sound quality.

RNIB8: Add a text version for on-screen.

RNIB9: Use a clearer voice.

RNIB10: The quality of AD and subtitles wasn't great and why wasn't a drama chosen for this test!

RNIB11: Cutting out bass rather than full dipping could allow background audio to be heard, brain concentrates on bass notes so ensuring AD has bass helps user focus on it.

RNIB12: Better spatial separation of audio subtitles to communicate where the speaker is. More dipping when the audio subtitles come on.

RNIB13: I don't know.

RNIB14: Change the voices for each character. Female voice for female characters. Important for diversity and inclusion as well.

RNIB15: Needs a way to identify which actor is speaking.

RNIB16: Different voices for characters, more emotive voices. It should be treated as dubbing and not as AD.

RNIB17: Human voice please - no synthetic voice unless they start to sound human and have the right inflection!

RNIB18: Trying matching the pace and vigor of the content - the style of delivery.

RNIB20: Nothing.

RNIB21: Volume of the speech against the music. Sometimes couldn't hear speech so well.

RNIB22: Use human voice.

RNIB23: In Opera - Dialogue translation with very brief AD, "They fight", "Tybalt dies".

RNIB24: Don't know.

RNIB25: Need to select the pacing for the genre. Dramatic vs. constant.

RNIB26: Make them sound more human and authentic.

RNIB28: Female voice for female singer or have the dialogue more acted out. Quite liked the summarising.

RNIB29: Nothing needed improving.

RNIB30: Perhaps users can pick where they want them placed on the screen and it stays in that preferred place automatically.

5. In what excerpt did you feel more present?

Only AST: 8

AST and AD: 11

I did not feel present in any of them: 9

I felt equally present in both: 3

6. Other comments:

RNIB3: I would like to try this on a drama. Musicals are tough to describe any way and this is opera! I tried to follow the libretto in only AST but that didn't tell me enough about the characters' actions.

RNIB11: AD audio needs to match quality of main audio including frequency range.

RNIB15: Needs plenty of clarity. Needs to be easy to understand.

RNIB25: The ability to be able to skip back in case you miss something would be good. Not sure how to know how far back to go.

RNIB28: Clear who was speaking and gave a good sense of the scene.

RNIB30: No.

Summary:

Preference: audio subtitles or combination of audio subtitles and audio description

Viewers were first asked which of the two modes they preferred: only audio subtitles or a combination of audio subtitles and audio description.

75% of the participants stated that they preferred a combination of the two with only 25% preferring audio subtitles on their own.

“I am sighted in one eye though I am registered blind. But if I sit close enough to the screen, it works. So in the VR glasses - the experience is accessible but not clear enough. Therefore not enjoyable. I think the combination of AD and AST made the screenplay clearer for me - I didn't have to focus too much.”

Presence in the immersive environment:

When asked in which mode of the two, did they feel more present:

- About 34% of the participants said they preferred a combination of audio description and audio subtitles.
- About 28% percent said they did not feel present in either of the two formats
- 25% percent said they preferred only audio subtitles
- 12.5% percent said they liked the two modes equally.

There was a clear preference for both audio description and audio subtitles to be provided but some participants offered other potential solutions that had not been explored in this test. Participants with greater interest in opera and musical content in general had significantly different feedback to participants familiar with the content of the clips used.

“Add even more audio description especially if there is a lot happening on the screen as in this clip. But I also want to listen to the music. Maybe try enhanced description here. I can listen to the music and also get the description.”

“Operas don't need any access features. It's the music you come to enjoy. It's not about the story. You can read the story in advance. Audio introduction should be enough.”

“It should be like the radio mode - make it into a talking book - explain what's on the screen and tell me the dialogues so the piece would make sense. I can't waste my time on things that I don't understand.”

Format of subtitles:

On the subtitles specifically, when asked if they would want subtitles in audio only or with on-screen subtitles in text:

- About 43% said they would not want subtitles on-screen
- Another 43% also stated that they would want the option to select whether to have on-screen subtitles in text
- 12.5% said they would want on-screen subtitles that could be enlarged

The preference for subtitles in audio or text was largely dependent on the type and level of sight loss. More significant loss meant audio was the preferred format.

Final conclusions:

Most participants reiterated the need for an immersive soundscape for greater immersion regardless of whether the content was provided with audio description only or a combination of both audio description and audio subtitles.

Although all the three modes for audio description and the two for audio subtitles delivered an experience consistent with the general expectations of using access features for most end users, none were reported as fully immersive. As 360-degree format was described as a gamified – somewhat gimmicky experience, participants expected the description to be appropriately striking for that experience.

Among other aspects, participants agreed that an immersive soundscape would also impact orientation which is a crucial part of ‘involvement’, knowing where the action is happening. Traditional 360 experiences for sighted audiences rely heavily on viewers responding to sounds as it generates higher level of immersion as one if involved in the video. Therefore, the same rules apply to people with sight loss which may be achieved by spatial audio.

In audio description, the preference for classic, radio or extended description was somewhat linked to the type of content they watched. Viewers with greater interest in documentaries or audio content in general tended to the radio drama mode or even the extended description. However, regular drama or film viewers leaned towards the familiar classic mode for audio description.

It is evident from the feedback gathered during this pilot that the preference for specific format depends on the level of sight loss, the type of sight condition, genre of content and other creative elements such as type voice, intonation, delivery etc.

Lastly, participants with significant sight loss repeated their desire to enjoy these experiences without HMD as they found them unnecessary and isolating.

ANNEX 31. CROSS-NATIONAL PILOT REPORT (UAB)

Cross-national pilot on player interface, AD presentation modes and AST presentation modes: report

1. General information

- **Partner responsible:** UAB
- **Place and date:** January-February 2020, Barcelona
- **Access services discussed:** AD and AST
- **Research tool:** online questionnaires (Google Form)
- **Methodology:**
https://docs.google.com/document/d/1d4_1cmErhTJs_xvJXq5s5ZMCpEHecWijpacd_sFUMxA/edit

2. Demographic questionnaire:

- Number of end users: 31
- Link to responses:
<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1NjhnPdF-h8zYWR3gbtYY1WDPe0hMh-iKT3Ivll0lmc4/edit>
- Demographics for users:
 1. Sex: “female” (10), “male” (20), “other”, “I prefer not to reply” (1)
 2. Age: 22, 24, 27, 29, 30, 31 (2), 34, 35, 43, 44 (2), 47, 48 (2), 49, 52, 53 (2), 54, 57, 59, 62 (3), 64, 65, 66, 67, 70, 78
 3. Main language: Catalan (7), Catalan/Spanish (7), Castellano (11), Italian (1), Espanyol (4), Bulgaria, Espanyol, Ruso, Ingles, Catala (1).
 4. Please indicate your level of studies: “no studies” (0), “primary education” (2), “secondary education” (2), “further education” (7), “university” (20).
 5. I define myself as...: “blind person” (13), “partially-sighted person” (18), “other” (0).
 6. Age at which you started losing your sight: “from birth” (10), “0-4” (2), “5-12” (5), “13-20” (4), “21-40” (2), “41-60” (5), “more than 60” (3).
 7. What devices do you use on a daily basis? Multiple replies are possible: “TV” (21), “PC” (12), “Laptop” (14), “Mobile phone” (31), “Tablet” (9), “Head Mounted Display (HMD)” (1), “other”: “Braille (1)”, “radio (3)”, “subtest lupa television” (1), “lupa manual (1)”, “grabadora digital (1)”, “jaws, grabadora, calculadora” (1), “radio, libros electrónicos (1)”.
 8. How often do you watch virtual reality content (for instance, 360° videos)?

	Never	Occasionally	At least once a month	At least once a week	Every day
In smartphone	28 (90.32%)	2 (6.45%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (3.23%)
On a tablet	30 (96.77%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (3.23%)
On a PC	30 (96.77%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (3.23%)
In smartphone plugged to HMD	29 (93.55%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	2 (6.45%)
In dedicated HMD (ie. Vive, Oculus)	28 (90.32%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	3 (9.68%)

9. If you have never used virtual reality content such as 360° videos or only occasionally, please indicate why. Multiple answers are possible. “Because I am not interested” (3), “Because it is not accessible” (5), “Because I have not had the chance to use it” (21), “Other reasons”: “No applicable” (1), “No ho he trobat necessary” (1), “Después de la

perdida de vision, no puedo ver imagen”, “Prefiero hacer otras cosas” (1), “He vist contingut ocasionalment” (1), “N'he vist” (1).

10. Please state your level of agreement with the following statement: “I am interested in virtual reality content (such as 360° videos).” “I strongly agree” (12), “I agree” (11), “Neither agree nor disagree” (7), “Disagree”, “Strongly disagree” (1).
11. Do you own any device to access virtual reality content? “Yes” (2), “No” (29), “I don’t know or I don’t want to reply” (0).
12. If you replied “yes” to the previous question, please specify which device(s): “PS4” (1), “Play Station VR” (1).
13. Do you like watching the following types of content on television or online?

	I like it very much	I like it	Neither like it nor dislike it	I don’t like it	I don’t like it at all
News	8 (25.81%)	14 (45.16%)	4 (12.9%)	3 (9.68%)	2 (6.45%)
Fiction (series, films)	8 (25.81%)	10 (32.26%)	7 (22.58%)	4 (12.9%)	2 (6.45%)
Talk shows	6 (19.35%)	9 (29.03%)	6 (19.35%)	7 (22.58%)	3 (9.68%)
Documentaries	12 (31.71%)	9 (29.03%)	9 (29.03%)	0 (0%)	1 (3.23%)
Sports	8 (25.81%)	6 (19.35%)	3 (9.68%)	3 (9.68%)	11 (35.48%)
Cartoons	1 (3.23%)	4 (12.9%)	11 (35.48%)	8 (25.81%)	7 (22.58%)

14. How many hours a day do you watch audio described content? “None” (14), “Less than one hour” (10), “1-2 hours” (2), “2-3 hours” (1), “3-4 hours” (3), “4 hours and more” (1).
15. What do you use to access online content? “Magnifier (for example, ZoomText)” (2), “Screen reader (for example, JAWS, VoiceOver, TalkBack)” (14), “Both” (8), “None” (8).

Summary:

31 participants took part in the test, with ages ranging between 22-78 years. Their main languages were Catalan (7), Catalan/Spanish (7), Spanish (15), and Bulgarian/ Spanish/Russian, English and Catalan (1). Most participants had university (20) or further education (7). 18 participants defined themselves as partially-sighted persons and 13 participants as blind persons. Participants taking part in the study reported starting losing sight from birth (10), between 0-4 years old (2), between 5-12 years old (5), between 13-20 years old (4), between 21-40 years old (2), 41-60 years old (5), more than 60 years old (3). When asked which technologies participants use on a daily basis, all participants reported using mobile phones (31), followed by television (21), laptop (14), PC (12) and tablet (9), which suggests that users are frequent users of technological devices. As far as immersive technologies are concerned, only one participant reported using head-mounted display on a daily basis, and most of the participants never watch VR reality content on smartphones (28), on a tablet (30), on a PC (30), in a smartphone plugged to HMD (29) or in HMD (28). Similarly, only 2 participants reported having a device to access VR content (PS4 and Play Station VR). As few as 3 participants reported watching immersive content occasionally (1) or every day (1) in a smartphone, on a tablet (every day – 1), on a PC (every day – 1), in a smartphone plugged to HMD (every day – 2) or in HMD (every day – 3). The most frequent reason behind not watching such content was not having had the chance to use it (21), followed by lack of accessibility (5) or interest (3). Regarding the level of interest in immersive content, most of participants were strongly interested (12) or interested (11), followed by a neutral attitude (“neither agree nor disagree” – 7), and only one participant chose option “strongly disagree”. The following question asked participants about their preferred type of content on television or online. Participants were also asked about how many hours a day they watch audio described content. In this question, 14 participants chose the option “none”, 10 participants “less than one hour”, 2 “1-2 hours”, 1 “2-3 hours”, 3 “3-4 hours” and 1 “4 hours or more”. In the last question, which asked about the devices that participants use to access

online content, most of participants reported using screen readers (14), two participants reported using magnifiers, 8 participants chose option “both” and 8 “none”.

3. Results (test 1): interface interaction

3.1. System Usability Scale (SUS) results for blind users testing voice interaction:

Link to the results from the post-questionnaire:

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1ORfGwMB7g_IdO2OA2QdhiUJgZgMPxmTjpViGU9UKIU/edit#gid=1464835481

3.1.1. SUS scores (question by question)

1 – strongly disagree

5 – strongly agree

Please indicate the number of replies that you have received for each rating:

SUS statements	1	2	3	4	5
1. I think that I would like to use this system frequently	0 (0%)	2 (10.53%)	4 (21.1%)	3 (15.79%)	10 (52.63%)
2. I found the system unnecessarily complex	10 (52.63%)	4 (21.1%)	3 (15.79%)	2 (10.53%)	0 (0%)
3. I thought the system was easy to use	0 (0%)	1 (5.26%)	2 (10.53%)	2 (10.53%)	14 (73.7%)
4. I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system	7 (36.84%)	6 (31.6%)	2 (10.53%)	4 (21.1%)	0 (0%)
5. I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	0 (0%)	2 (10.53%)	3 (15.79%)	5 (26.31%)	9 (47.4%)
6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	7 (36.84%)	3 (15.79%)	5 (26.31%)	2 (10.53%)	2 (10.53%)
7. I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly	0 (0%)	2 (10.53%)	2 (10.53%)	5 (26.31%)	10 (52.63%)
8. I found the system very cumbersome to use	11 (57.9%)	5 (26.31%)	2 (10.53%)	1 (5.26%)	0 (0%)
9. I felt very confident using the system	0 (0%)	3 (15.79%)	1 (5.26%)	9 (47.4%)	6 (31.6%)
10. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system	8 (42.11%)	7 (36.84%)	2 (10.53%)	2 (10.53%)	0 (0%)

3.1.2. System Usability Scale (SUS) results:

The SUS average score is **77.37**.

The graph below shows how the SUS scores associate with the percentile ranks and letter grades¹¹ and the red line specifies where the ImAc AD editor is at this moment.

¹¹ Sauro, J. 2011. Measuring usability with the System Usability Scale (SUS). Retrieved from <http://www.measuringu.com/sus.php>

The letter grade is B+, and the obtained score corresponds to the percentile rank: 80-84%¹².

The excel spreadsheet with scores calculations can be consulted here:

https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1h-aAWG1IA4S_NtiAxwqR6HbRHyuMmNxe

3.2. System Usability Scale (SUS) results for partially sighted users testing the menu interaction:

Link to the results from the post-questionnaire:

https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1ORfG1wMB7g_IdO2OA2QdhiUJgZgMPxmTjpViGU9UKIU/edit#gid=1464835481

3.1.3. SUS scores (question by question)

1 – strongly disagree

5 – strongly agree

Please indicate the number of replies that you have received for each rating:

SUS statements	1	2	3	4	5
1. I think that I would like to use this system frequently	0 (0%)	2 (22.22%)	0 (0%)	2 (22.22%)	5 (55.56%)
2. I found the system unnecessarily complex	5 (55.56%)	4 (44.44%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
3. I thought the system was easy to use	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	5 (55.56%)	4 (44.44%)
4. I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system	7 (77.78%)	2 (22.22%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
5. I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	3 (33.33%)	6 (66.67%)
6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	5 (55.56%)	2 (22.22%)	0 (0%)	1 (11.11%)	1 (11.11%)
7. I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (11.11%)	3 (33.33%)	5 (55.56%)
8. I found the system very cumbersome to use	7 (77.78%)	1 (11.11%)	0 (0%)	1 (11.11%)	0 (0%)
9. I felt very confident using the system	1 (11.11%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	3 (33.33%)	5 (55.56%)
10. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system	7 (77.78%)	2 (22.22%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)

3.1.4. System Usability Scale (SUS) results:

The SUS average score is **86.39**.

¹² Sauro, J. & Lewis, J. R. 2016. *Quantifying the user experience: Practical statistics for user research*. Amsterdam: Morgan Kaufmann, p. 203-204.

The graph below shows how the SUS scores associate with the percentile ranks and letter grades and the red line specifies where the ImAc AD editor is at this moment.

The letter grade is A+, and the obtained score corresponds to the percentile rank: 96-100%.

The excel spreadsheet with scores calculations can be consulted here:

https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1h-aAWG1IA4S_NtiAxwqR6HbRHuMmNxe

3.2. Preference questions

3.2.1. Preference questions for blind users

1. What do you like the most about the menu interaction?

UAB01: T'entén molt bé i les ordres són fàcils. [It is responsive and the commands are easy]

UAB2: La possibilitat d'habilitar i desactivar les audiodescripcions. [The possibility to activate/desactivate AD]

UAB3: És molt còmode. [It's very comfortable]

UAB4: Molt còmode. [Very comfortable]

UAB5: Pots fer-la anar amb la veu. [You can interact by voice]

UAB6: Còmode, fàcil, funcional. [Comfortable, easy, functional]

UAB8: És fàcil. [It's easy]

UAB9: Poder fer servir tecnologia amb la veu. [You can interact with this technology by voice]

UAB10: Per mi és familiar perquè faig servir Google Home. [I am used to it because I use Google Home]

UAB12: La interacció. [the interaction]

UAB13: Facilitat [easiness of use]

UAB14: La facilitat en la interacció, la rapidesa en la resposta. [easiness of interaction, responsiveness]

UAB15: Pots controlar-ho tot a voluntat. [you can control evething at will]

UAB17: Poder dirle avança o retrocede, o sube el volumen o baja el volumen. [I can ask (Alexa) to move forward or go back, adjust volume up or down]

UAB19: Que tienes las manos libres y no tienes que utilizar las manos para activarlo. [That you have free hands and you do not need to use your hands to interact]

UAB24: Que puedes interactuar por voz que es humanizada, no es robotica. [You can interact with the voice that is human-like, not robotic]

UAB27: Es muy útil, muy práctico porque a través del reproductor y Alexa puedo reproducir los vídeos muy rápidamente. [It is very useful, very practical because by means of the player and Alexa I can play the videos very fast]

UAB28: La rapidez de la respuestas de Alexa. [The speed of Alexa's responses]

UAB30: Me gusta que puedo manejar las vídeos por voz. [I like that I can interact with the videos by voice]

2. What do you like less?

UAB01: Que sigui tan sensible. [It is very sensitive]

UAB2: L'extensió de la frase per donar una ordre. / No és natural. [The opening phrase before giving the command. It's not natural]

UAB5: No m'ha fet cas.

- UAB6:** Si falla Internet, pot no connectar-se bé. [If there is a problem with a connection to the internet, it may not connect well]
- UAB8:** Necessitaria una mica de suport tècnic. No sempre m'entenia. [I would need some technical support. The device not always did understand me]
- UAB9:** Cal parlar amb instruccions molt concretes. [You need to use very specific commands]
- UAB12:** Nada. [Nothing]
- UAB13:** palabras clave, los comandos que hay que decir. [Key words, the commands that need to be said]
- UAB14:** Veu robòtica. [Robotic voice]
- UAB15:** Quan actives una vegada es queda com esperant uns segons l'ordre següent. M'agradaria més que no es quedés esperant ordres: que executi l'ordre i no escolti. [When you activate it one times, it waits some seconds for the next commands. I would like more that it does not wait for the commands: that it follows an order and does not listen more]
- UAB17:** Que a veces se confunde, no es 100% eficaz. [Sometimes it makes mistakes, it is not 100% effective]
- UAB19:** Que tienes que hacer una secuencia muy concreta de palabras para poder activar el comando, me parece muy larga. [You need to say a very concrete sequence of words to activate a command, it seems very long to me]
- UAB24:** La falta de respuesta. [The lack of response]
- UAB30:** A veces no da las respuestas correctas. [Sometimes it does not give correct replies]

3. What do you think could be improved and how?

- UAB01:** Que no fos tan sensible (p. ex. que sabés qui està donant les ordres en un moment donat). [That it is less sensible (ex. that you know who is giving commands in a given moment)]
- UAB2:** Fer les frases més curtes. [condense the phrases]
- UAB5:** Que fos més fàcil la comunicació: frases curtes / sense verb (p. ex: alexa, 20 segundos / alexa, audiodescripció) [Easier interaction: short phrases / without verb (ex. Alexa, 20 seconds / Alexa, audio description)]
- UAB6:** Connexió. [Connection]
- UAB9:** Més varietat d'estructures. / Per exemple, evitar verb "dile". [more variety of structures / For example, to avoid verb 'dile'.
- UAB10:** Que les ordres no fossin tan llargues i amb tants passos (ex. portal ImAc). [That the orders were not so long and with so many steps (eg. ImAc portal).]
- UAB12:** Nada, está bien. [Nothing, is ok]
- UAB13:** Nada. [nothing]
- UAB14:** Sintetitzador de veu, és molt màquina. [Voice synthesizer, it's very machine-like.]
- UAB15:** El que he comentat a 2. El so d'activació també caldria implementar-lo. [What I commented on in the second question. The sound of activation should also be implemented]
- UAB17:** No mejoraría nada, solo que no se equivoque, que sea más eficaz. [I would not improve nothing, only that it makes less mistakes and is more effective]
- UAB19:** Acortaría las órdenes que hay que darle. [I would condense the commands that you need to give]
- UAB27:** Cuando más cortas son las órdenes, mejor. [The shorter the orders, the better]
- UAB30:** Hacer las órdenes más breves. [Make the commands shorter]

4. Other comments:

- UAB2:** Com més varietat de frases pugui fer servir l'usuari, més fàcil serà la interacció. [The more variety of phrases the user can use, the easier the interaction will be]
- UAB5:** Considero que és un sistema súper interessant. Per a persones amb baixa visió, facilita molt les coses. [I find it this system super interesting. For people with low vision, it makes things a lot easier]
- UAB12:** Para menú visual, mejor una flecha grande y blanca. Contraste rojo sobre negro no veo. [For a visual menu, I would prefer a larger and white pointer. I cannot see this contrast (red over black)]

UAB13: Nada. [Nothing]

UAB15: Em sembla molt interessant la integració amb Alexa. Soc usuari d'assistents virtuals. [Interaction with Alexa seems very interesting. I am a user of virtual assistants]

UAB17: Nada. [Nothing]

UAB19: Haciendo más flexible las órdenes, poder utilizar sinónimos, conjugaciones parecidas, etc. [By making commands more flexible, being able to use synonyms, similar conjugations etc.]

UAB21: Sin comentarios. [No comments]

Summary:

19 participants tested menu interaction using voice interaction (Amazon Echo Dot).

In the first question, which asked about what participants like the most about the interaction with the menu, participants' responses show that the interaction was deemed: "practical"(UAB27), "easy" (UAB6, 8, 13, 14), "comfortable" (UAB3, 4, 6), "useful" (UAB27) or "functional" (UAB6). Participants appreciated that they can interact by voice with the menu, without the need to use sight (UAB5, 9, 15, 19, 25, 30) and responsiveness of the device (UAB14, 28). One participant commented positively on the voice of Alexa which sounds natural and not robot-like (UAB24).

The second and third questions asked about what participants liked less and how the interaction with the menu can be improved. In these two questions, the comments indicate that participants would prefer shorter commands (UAB2, 5, 9, 10, 13, 19), and especially the following comments provide valuable feedback:

Que fos més fàcil la comunicació: frases curtes / sense verb (p. ex: alexa, 20 segundos / alexa, audiodescripció) [Easier interaction: short phrases / without verb (ex. Alexa, 20 seconds / Alexa, audio description)] (UAB5)

Més varietat d'estructures. / Per exemple, evitar verb "dile". [More variety of structures / For example, to avoid verb 'dile'.] (UAB9)

Que les ordres no fossin tan llargues i amb tants passos (ex. portal ImAc). [That the orders were not so long and with so many steps (eg. ImAc portal).] (UAB10)

Acortaría las órdenes que hay que darle. [I would condense the commands that you need to give] (UAB19)

Cuando más cortas son las comandas, mejor. [The shorter the orders, the better] (UAB27)

Hacer las comandas más breves. [Make the commands shorter] (UAB30)

3.2.1. Preference questions for partially sighted users

1. What do you like the most about the menu interaction?

UAB7: Los contrastes de colores y el tamaño del puntero. [Contrasts of colours and size of the pointer]

UAB11: Possibilitat de veure-ho tot molt bé. Veure totes les opcions disponibles dintre del reproductor de vídeo. [Ability to see everything very well. See all options available within the video player]

UAB16: I am not very familiar with virtual reality systems, as a user, so it seems normal. [I am not very familiar with virtual reality systems, as a user, so it seems normal]

UAB20: En grande y fácil de utilizar, no hay ningún problema. Todo funciona muy bien, también se puede hacer mas pequeño. [It is large and easy to use, and there is no problem (with using the menu). Everything works very well, and (the menu) can also be made smaller]

UAB21: Está bien con esta configuración. [This configuration is fine]

UAB25: Que puedes adaptar a lo que necesitas. Que puedes decidir en cuanto quieres ver y como. [You can adapt it to what you need. That you can decide how much you want and how]

UAB26: El contraste me ha ayudado a distinguir las diferentes opciones. [The contrast helped me to distinguish between the different options]

UAB29: Que lo puedes hacer funcionar como si fuera un video de los de antes. Que es muy práctico. [That you can make it work as if it was a standard video. Which is very practical]

UAB31: Es muy intuitivo y fácil de utilizar. Me gusta que el menú se puede mover. [It is very intuitive and easy to use. I like that the menu can move]

2. What do you like less?

UAB7: Cansa els ulls. Potser altres tons sense brillantor que també facin contrast ajudarien. [It tires the eyes. Maybe different tones without shine that have contrast would help]

UAB11: Abaixar el cap per haver de veure algunes coses del menú. [Lowering your head to see some of the items in the menú]

UAB16: Once selected English as the main language, and then changed some other settings, the system automatically switches back to Catalan.

UAB21: Nada. [Nothing]

UAB25: La sensibilidad del controller. Me gustaría por ejemplo pulsar dos veces para asegurarme que quiero la opción elegida. Cuando acerco el puntero sobre play, me gustaría tener la voz que dice a voz alto play. Me gustaría seleccionar el color y tamaño de puntero. [Sensibility of the controller. I would like for example to click the controller two times to ensure myself that I want the selected option. When I move the pointer over play, I would like to have the voice that says aloud play. I would like to select the color and size of the pointer]

UAB31: Al principio me costaba encontrar el menú después de mirar abajo. Es un poco lento y me gustaría mirar menos tiempo abajo. [At first, I had troubles to find the menu to look down. It is a bit slow and I would like to look less time down]

3. What do you think could be improved and how?

UAB7: Pantalla més gran; la mida de la lletra és petita: jo la llegia, però mola gent no podrà. +/- per apuntar i que canviï mida de la lletra. O poder decidir centrar el text i ampliar. [Larger screen; the font size is small: I can read it, but many people cannot. +/- to point and change the font size or to decide to center the text and enlarge it]

UAB11: El reproductor està molt bé, però accedir al reproductor costa, no és el millor. Quan surts del menú, perds tota l'ampliació que tenies. [The player is fine, but the accessing the player is difficult, it is not the best. When you leave the menu, you loose all enlargement that you had]

UAB20: Está muy bien. [It is fine]

UAB21: Calidad imagen. [Image quality]

UAB25: Me gustaría que los botones estén más separados. Sería más fácil seleccionar lo que quiero. [I would like to have the buttons more separated from each other. I would be easier to select what I want]

UAB26: Es muy adecuado. [It is very appropriate]

UAB29: Me gustaría que el menú accesible fuera un poco más grande. [I would like the accessible menu to be larger]

UAB31: Podría haber en configuración un botón con las mejoras en el puntero como por ejemplo inversión de colores o el círculo alrededor o una cruz para ayudar a localizar el puntero. En respecto a la inversión de colores, me refiero a que si el fondo es claro, el puntero se vea oscuro e si el fondo es oscuro, el puntero se vea claro. [There could be in configuration a button to adjust the pointer, for example to invert the colours or to have a circle or a cross around it to help localize the pointer. Regarding the inversion of colours, if the background is light, the pointer should be dark and if the background is dark, the pointer should be light]

4. Other comments:

UAB7: Perquè cansen, són per fer-los servir poca estona. Recomanacions de descans visual. [Because they are tiring, they are constructed to use them for a short time. Taking breaks is recommended]

UAB21: Sin comentarios. [No comments]

UAB25: ¡Que sigas investigando! [Keep investigating!]

UAB27: Conozco la integración por voz y la utilizo (Google Asistente). Me ayuda mucho! [I know voice interaction and I use it (Google Assistant). It helps me a lot!]

UAB29: Que se pudiera ajustar la visión de cada ojo independientemente. [That it would be possible to adjust each eye independently]

Summary:

9 participants tested menu interaction with accessible menu.

As far as the first question is concerned, participants deemed the interaction in their comments “practical” (UAB29), “intuitive” (UAB31) and “easy to use” (UAB29, 31). Participants especially appreciated the possibility to adjust the menu to their needs (UAB11, 20, 25), contrast (UAB7, 26) and the fact that the menu can move according to user’s head position (UAB31).

One partially-sighted participant (UAB19) did not finish the test with accessible menu because of weak contrast between the pointer (yellow) and the video (Holy Land 4 takes place during daytime at the desert and seaside which are in light colours). In the questions 2 and 3, two other participants provided comments on the colour of the pointer:

(...) Me gustaría seleccionar el color y tamaño de puntero. [I would like to select the color and size of the pointer] (UAB25)

Podría haber en configuración un botón con las mejoras en el puntero como por ejemplo inversión de colores o el círculo alrededor o una cruz para ayudar a localizar el puntero. En respecto a la inversión de colores, me refiero a que si el fondo es claro, el puntero se vea oscuro e si el fondo es oscuro, el puntero se vea claro. [There could be in configuration a button to adjust the pointer, for example to invert the colours or to have a circle or a cross around it to help localize the pointer. Regarding the inversion of colours, if the background is light, the pointer should be dark and if the background is dark, the pointer should be light] (UAB31)

Another relevant comment in the question 3 suggests that more separation between the buttons could facilitate the interaction with accessible menu for persons with sight loss:

Me gustaría que los botones sean más separados. Sería más fácil seleccionar lo que quiero. [I would like to have the buttons more separated from each other. I would be easier to select what I want] (UAB25)

4. TEST 2: AD PRESENTATION MODES

4.1. Results of the IPQ questionnaires

4.1.1. AD-C mode: 30 replies.

IPQ questions	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1. In the computer generated world I had a sense of "being there".	4 (13.33%)	1 (3.33%)	3 (10%)	2 (6.67%)	7 (23.33%)	7 (23.33%)	6 (20%)
2. Somehow I felt that the virtual world surrounded me.	5 (16.67%)	2 (6.67%)	2 (6.67%)	1 (3.33%)	7 (23.33%)	6 (20%)	7 (23.33%)
3. I felt like I was just perceiving pictures.	19 (63.33%)	2 (6.67%)	3 (10%)	3 (10%)	3 (10%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
4. I did not feel present in the virtual space.	6 (20%)	2 (6.67%)	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)	10 (33.33%)	4 (13.33%)	7 (23.33%)
5. I had a sense of acting in the virtual space, rather than operating something from outside.	7 (23.33%)	1 (3.33%)	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)	10 (33.33%)	5 (16.67%)	6 (20%)
6. I felt present in the virtual space.	7 (23.33%)	1 (3.33%)	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)	9 (30%)	8 (26.67%)	4 (13.33%)
7. How aware were you of the real world surrounding while navigating in the virtual world? (i.e. sounds, room temperature, other people, etc.)?	4 (13.33%)	1 (3.33%)	3 (10%)	3 (10%)	4 (13.33%)	8 (26.67%)	7 (23.33%)

IPQ questions	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
8. I was not aware of my real environment.	2 (6.67%)	3 (10%)	2 (6.67%)	2 (6.67%)	3 (10%)	9 (30%)	9 (30%)
9. I still paid attention to the real environment.	14 (46.67%)	9 (30%)	2 (6.67%)	3 (10%)	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)	1 (3.33%)
10. I was completely captivated by the virtual world.	4 (13.33%)	2 (6.67%)	1 (3.33%)	1 (3.33%)	5 (16.67%)	8 (26.67%)	9 (30%)
11. How real did the virtual world seem to you?	4 (13.33%)	6 (20%)	9 (30%)	2 (6.67%)	2 (6.67%)	2 (6.67%)	5 (16.67%)
12. How much did your experience in the virtual environment seem consistent with your real world experience ?	7 (23.33%)	2 (6.67%)	2 (6.67%)	1 (3.33%)	11 (36.67%)	4 (13.33%)	3 (10%)
13. How real did the virtual world seem to you?	6 (20%)	2 (6.67%)	3 (10%)	3 (10%)	9 (30%)	3 (10%)	4 (13.33%)
14. The virtual world seemed more realistic than the real world.	18 (60%)	3 (10%)	2 (6.67%)	4 (13.33%)	2 (6.67%)	0 (0%)	1 (3.33%)

4.1.2. AD-R mode: 30 replies.

IPQ questions	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1. In the computer generated world I had a sense of "being there".	4 (13.33%)	1 (3.33%)	1 (3.33%)	5 (16.67%)	7 (23.23%)	7 (23.23%)	5 (16.67%)
2. Somehow I felt that the virtual world surrounded me.	4 (13.33%)	2 (6.67%)	0 (0%)	6 (20%)	4 (13.33%)	8 (26.67%)	6 (20%)
3. I felt like I was just perceiving pictures.	18 (60%)	6 (20%)	0 (0%)	4 (13.33%)	0 (0%)	1 (3.33%)	1 (3.33%)
4. I did not feel present in the virtual space.	5 (16.67%)	1 (3.33%)	1 (3.33%)	3 (10%)	12 (40%)	5 (16.67%)	3 (10%)
5. I had a sense of acting in the virtual space, rather than operating something from outside.	6 (20%)	2 (6.67%)	0 (0%)	6 (20%)	9 (30%)	2 (6.67%)	5 (16.67%)
6. I felt present in the virtual space.	6 (20%)	0 (0%)	3 (10%)	5 (16.67%)	7 (23.23%)	4 (13.33%)	5 (16.67%)
7. How aware were you of the real world surrounding while navigating in the virtual world? (i.e. sounds, room temperature, other people, etc.)?	2 (6.67%)	2 (6.67%)	3 (10%)	5 (16.67%)	1 (3.33%)	6 (20%)	11 (36.67%)
8. I was not aware of my real environment.	4 (13.33%)	0 (0%)	2 (6.67%)	4 (13.33%)	2 (6.67%)	7 (23.23%)	11 (36.67%)
9. I still paid attention to the real environment.	15 (50%)	6 (20%)	1 (3.33%)	5 (16.67%)	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)	2 (6.67%)
10. I was completely captivated by the virtual world.	3 (10%)	1 (3.33%)	0 (0%)	2 (6.67%)	9 (30%)	7 (23.23%)	8
11. How real did the virtual world seem to you?	5 (16.67%)	7 (23.23%)	8 (26.67%)	4 (13.33%)	1 (3.33%)	2 (6.67%)	3 (10%)
12. How much did your experience in the virtual environment seem consistent with your real world experience ?	5 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	2 (6.67%)	8 (26.67%)	8 (26.67%)	4 (13.33%)	3 (10%)
13. How real did the virtual world seem to you?	7 (23.23%)	0 (0%)	4 (13.33%)	8 (26.67%)	6 (20%)	1 (3.33%)	4 (13.33%)
14. The virtual world seemed more realistic than the real world.	16 (53.33%)	4 (13.33%)	2 (6.67%)	4 (13.33%)	2 (6.67%)	1 (3.33%)	1 (3.33%)

4.1.3. AD-E mode: 30 replies.

IPQ questions	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1. In the computer generated world I had a sense of "being there".	4 (13.33%)	0 (0%)	3 (10%)	5 (16.67%)	5 (16.67%)	7 (23.23%)	6 (20%)
2. Somehow I felt that the virtual world surrounded me.	3 (10%)	2 (6.67%)	3 (10%)	4 (13.33%)	6 (20%)	6 (20%)	6 (20%)
3. I felt like I was just perceiving pictures.	18	3 (10%)	2 (6.67%)	3 (10%)	2 (6.67%)	1 (3.33%)	1 (3.33%)
4. I did not feel present in the virtual space.	4 (13.33%)	0 (0%)	4 (13.33%)	5 (16.67%)	7 (23.23%)	4 (13.33%)	6 (20%)
5. I had a sense of acting in the virtual space, rather than operating something from outside.	5 (16.67%)	1 (3.33%)	2 (6.67%)	3 (10%)	9 (30%)	4 (13.33%)	6 (20%)
6. I felt present in the virtual space.	5 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	3 (10%)	3 (10%)	8 (26.67%)	5 (16.67%)	6 (20%)
7. How aware were you of the real world surrounding while navigating in the virtual world? (i.e. sounds, room temperature, other people, etc.)?	2 (6.67%)	3 (10%)	3 (10%)	2 (6.67%)	5 (16.67%)	6 (20%)	9 (30%)
8. I was not aware of my real environment.	4 (13.33%)	2 (6.67%)	3 (10%)	2 (6.67%)	4 (13.33%)	6 (20%)	9 (30%)
9. I still paid attention to the real environment.	15 (50%)	4 (13.33%)	3 (10%)	3 (10%)	2 (6.67%)	1 (3.33%)	2 (6.67%)
10. I was completely captivated by the virtual world.	3 (10%)	1 (3.33%)	2 (6.67%)	3 (10%)	5 (16.67%)	6 (20%)	10 (33.33%)
11. How real did the virtual world seem to you?	7 (23.23%)	3 (10%)	10 (33.33%)	5 (16.67%)	0 (0%)	2 (6.67%)	3 (10%)
12. How much did your experience in the virtual environment seem consistent with your real world experience ?	6 (20%)	2 (6.67%)	2 (6.67%)	6 (20%)	4 (13.33%)	4 (13.33%)	6 (20%)
13. How real did the virtual world seem to you?	7 (23.33%)	1 (3.33%)	4 (13.33%)	5 (16.67%)	3 (10%)	4 (13.33%)	6 (20%)
14. The virtual world seemed more realistic than the real world.	17 (56.67%)	1 (3.33%)	2 (6.67%)	4 (13.33%)	4 (13.33%)	1 (3.33%)	1 (3.33%)

Summary:

A paired samples t-test has been used in order to compare the scores on each subscale across the different types of AD. None of these comparisons gave a statistically significant difference (all $p > .05$).

	General presence	Spatial presence	Involvement	Experienced realism
Radio Drama	4.70	4.5533	5.0417	3.5417
Extended AD	4.73	4.6400	4.8583	3.6333
Classic AD	4.73	4.6200	4.9750	3.4000

Table 1. Mean scores for all participants (N=30) in each subscale across AD type.

Table 2 presents the results obtained by each user type (Blind/Partially sighted) in each IPQ subscale, with the p value of each comparison. Coloured rows show significant differences.

		General presence	Spatial presence	Involvement	Experienced realism
Radio Drama	Blind	3.83	3.9167	4.8750	3.1458
	Partially sighted	5.28	4.9778	5.1528	3.8056
	<i>p</i> =	0.040	0.087	0.640	0.280
Extended AD	Blind	3.83	4.0333	4.5208	3.3750
	Partially sighted	5.33	5.0444	5.0833	3.8056
	<i>p</i> =	0.036	0.087	0.313	0.529
Classic AD	Blind	3.50	3.5500	4.6667	2.7292
	Partially sighted	5.56	5.3333	5.1806	3.8472
	<i>p</i> =	0.004	0.004	0.332	0.075

Table 2 IPQ results from persons with sight loss

A one-way ANOVA comparing the results of Blind vs partially-sighted users shows that there are significant differences in General Presence across all types of AD. Scores are higher for partially sighted users.

In addition, for Classic AD, scores for spatial presence are also significantly higher for partially-sighted users. There is also a trend to significance for Radio Drama and Extended AD ($p=.087$).

4.2. Results of the AD post-questionnaire

1. Which AD type do you prefer in 360°? Rank the AD modes according to your preferences: 1- preferred mode, 2- second preferred mode, 3 - the least preferred mode.

AD-C: 10 – the preferred mode, 10 – second preferred mode, 11 – the least preferred mode.

AD-R: 8 – the preferred mode, 11 – second preferred mode, 12 – the least preferred mode.

AD-E: 13 – the preferred mode, 10 – second preferred mode, 8 – the least preferred mode.

2. Please explain why you ranked the AD modes in this way.

UAB01: La primera m'ha semblat més completa, la tercera m'ha semblat menys completa, però amb l'opció d'informació addicional, i la segona m'ha semblat menys completa. [The first one seemed the most complete, the third one seemed to me less complete but it had additional information and the second one also seemed less complete]

UAB2: Condicionat perquè a l'AD-E m'ha agradat poder interactuar amb el contingut i decidir que jo volia una AD més extensa. L'AD-C és la que millor m'ha permès imaginar allò que no arribava a distingir. L'AD-R m'ha causat confusió si l'AD eren AST d'algú que parlava. [It depends because in AD-E, I liked the possibility to interact with the content and decide that I wanted a more extended AD. AD-C is that one that helped me the most to imagine what I could not see. I was confused by AD-R because I was not sure if the AD were AST of someone who talked.]

UAB3: Porque la AD-E era muy cansada. Quitaría la adicional. [Because AD-E was very tiring. I would remove the additional one]

- UAB4:** M'ha agradat poder tenir l'oportunitat d'ampliar informació. [I liked the possibility to have extended information]
- UAB5:** Totes m'han agradat molt, però l'explicació de la tercera m'ha aportat molta informació nova. / A l'AD-E m'agrada tenir l'opció d'ampliar la informació. [I liked all the types very much, but the explication in the third one gave me much new information. In AD-E I like having the option to extend the information]
- UAB6:** No he notat diferències entre AD-R i AD-E. M'han agradat els detalls de l'AD-C. [I have not noticed the differences between AD-R and AD-E. I liked the details in AD-C]
- UAB7:** AD-C m'ha sorprès molt. AD-E m'ha agradat molt i tenia més contingut amb perspectiva. AD-R m'ha semblat la més plana i hi havia elements que es descriuen abans de ser a la pantalla (5-6 segons). [AD-C suprised me a lot. In AD-E I liked very much that it had more content with a perspective. AD-R seemed the most flat and there were elements which are being described before appearing in the video (5-6 seconds)].
- UAB8:** Com que encara hi veig una mica, l'AD-C amb els detalls que donava em distreien de la imatge.
El vídeo que anava amb AD-R era molt impressionant visualment.
AD-E m'han agradat les explicacions. [As I can see a bit, AD-C with the details it was giving was distracting me from the image. The video with AD-R impressed me visually. I liked the explications in AD-E]
- UAB9:** No sempre atenia a l'AD. Cap de les tres era molesta. La resposta respon més al contingut dels vídeos. [I was not aware of AD. None of the three annoyed me. My reply refers more to the content of the videos]
- UAB10:** AD-E porque podía ampliar la información. [AD-E because I could broden the information]
- UAB11:** AD-E a vegades estàs més pendent de la campana que del que diuen. La part bona és que dona més informació.
Les altres dues les he trobades molt semblants, tot i que notava que deien coses diferents. [In AD-E sometimes you are paying more attention to the bell sound than to what they say. The good part is that it gives more information. I found the other two very similar, although I noticed that they are saying different things]
- UAB12:** EL segundo porque tenía la experiencia del primero y el tercero no me ha convencido el cambio de descripción, no le he encontrado significado, no lo he entendido qué sentido tenía el cambio de descripción. [The second one because I had the experience of the first one and in the third one the change of description did not convince me, I did not find it significative, I did not understand why the description was changed]
- UAB13:** Porque el último da más información de audio. [The last one gives more sound information]
- UAB14:** En AD-C me han gustado mucho las explicaciones, teniendo en cuenta que no hay más input que el oído. AD-E por la posibilidad de ampliar. [In AD-C, I really liked the explications, keeping in mind that there is no more input than sound. AD-E for the possibility of having extended information]
- UAB15:** AD-E me ha parecido más inmersiva, como si estaba más enfocada a ponerte dentro. La AD-R me parece una participación desde fuera, muy narrativa. [AD-E seemed to me more immersive, as if it was more focused to place you inside. AD-R seems to me like participating from outside, it is very narrative]
- UAB16:** Més coherent amb la narració, menys invasiu. [More coherent with the narration, less invasive]
- UAB17:** Porque en el vídeo 3 la AD era muy detallada, te daba detalles de todo tipo, desde las construcciones de los muros, te habla un poco de historia, nos explicaba donde pasaron la noche José y María, los detalles de cuándo fue construido, los colores, etc. Te daba detalles específicos que son interesantes de saber a la hora de ver vídeos como este. Por eso me gusta más esta opción, porque me da más información. La AD opcional está bien, pero no sé si la

gente que puede ver sabría ver. Creo que los detalles que da la AD opcional son detalles que deberían explicarse en el propio vídeo o no explicarlo, pero no dar información que no está ya en el vídeo. Daba detalles que considero que la AD no debería de dar, sino el vídeo en sí. [Because in the third video audio description was very detailed, it gave you details of all types, from the construction of walls, it talks a bit about the history, it explains us where Joseph and Maria spent the night, the details about when something was constructed, the colours, etc. It gave you details which are interesting when watching such a video. Because of this I like more this option because it gives me more information. The optional AD is fine, but I am not sure if sighted persons can see what it explains. I think that the details explained in the optional AD are the details that should be explained in the video itself or not be explained at all, not to give the information that is not yet in the video. It gave details that I think that it should not give, but they should be included in the video instead]

UAB18: AD-E da un poco más detalles, sería interesante para mí tener la posibilidad de activar más audiodescripciones extendidas de diferentes puntos del video. Es como escuchar un audio libro como cualquier documental que puedo ver en la televisión (AD-R). A nivel de audiodescripción se queda más pobre. La segunda (AD-C) da más información visual, las detalles buenos para imaginar. [AD-E gives a little more details, it would be interesting for me to have the possibility to activate more extended descriptions of different points of the video. AD-R is like listening to an audiobook, like any documentary that I can watch on TV. At AD level, it is poorer. The second (AD-C) gives more visual information and its details allow to imagine (the scene)].

UAB19: El dos me ha gustado porque escuchaba los sonidos del entorno, de la situación del documental a un volumen y una forma que em parecía muy realista y parecía que estaba en la situación del vídeo (AD-R). En el tercero, el sonido de la AD y los comentarios de la chica eran muy envolventes, pero prácticamente no oía los sonidos del entorno, por lo tanto para mí era como ver un documental (AD-E). Y el último (AD-C) era como ver directamente un documental, porque no se escuchaban los sonidos del vídeo. [I liked the second one because I heard ambient sounds, of the situation presented in the documentary in a volume and in a form that seemed very realistic and it seemed to me that I am in the situation presented in the documentary (AD-R). In the third one, the sound of AD and the comments of the girl were very immersive, but I could practically not hear any ambient sounds, and because of this for me it was like watching a documentary (AD-E). And the last one (AD-C) was like seeing directing a documentary because the sounds of the video were not hearable].

UAB20: Me han gustado las tres, me han parecido que eran parecidas y que estaban bien. [I like three of them, they seemed similar to me and that they were fine]

UAB21: No me ha gustado que pare el video para escuchar la descripción. [I did not like to stop the video to listen to the description]

UAB22: AD-E Me he sentido más atrapada en el mundo virtual, con más información y mejor calidad de información que provocaba que m'abstraía del mundo real. [I was feeling more present in the virtual world in AD-E, as it had more information and a better quality of information that made me less conscious of the real world.]

AD-C no estaba mal, tenía información valiosa.

AD-R era como un documental visto en la televisión, me faltaba AD extendida. [AD-C was not bad, it had important information. AD-R was like a documentary watched on TV, I was missing extended AD]

UAB23: AD-E me gusto más este vídeo porque puedo hacer clic de manera opcional. A veces uno necesita mas información y a veces no. Cuando el video tiene mucha descripción, se recarga de información, y esto no me gusta.

AD-R Me gusto mucho este vídeo porque lleva palabras como 'fantástico', era menos plano y más emotivo. Me gusta cuando hay mas emoción. [AD-E I liked more this video because I can

make a click optionally. Sometimes one needs more information and sometimes no. When a video has much description, it is filled with information and I don't like that]

UAB24: AD-E da la opción de información adicional y por eso he elegido este episodio. La audiodescripción extendida me da detalles que faltan en audiodescripción normal. [AD-E gives an option of additional information and because of this I chose this episode. The extended AD gives more details that are missing in a standard AD]

UAB25: Todos me han gustado igualmente. AD-R me ha gustado mucho porque podía imaginar todo muy bien, AD-C me ha gustaba también. Las personas ciegas necesitaran más información pero para mí era suficiente. AD-E me ha gustado mucho porque daba información adicional después de hacer un clic. [I liked them all equally. I liked AD-R a lot because I was able to imagine everything very well, and I also liked AD-C. Blind persons will need more information but for me it was sufficient. I liked AD-E a lot because it was giving me additional information after a click]

UAB26: AD-E me ha gustado mucho poder escuchar más información cuando suena la campana. AD-C y AD-R dos estaban bien. [In AD-E, I liked a lot the possibility to listen to more information after the bell]

UAB27: AD-R me gusta mucho porque con los sonidos ambientales el vídeo me parece más real. AD-E la veo como más completa de los tres. [I like AD-R a lot because the video seems very real with ambient sounds]

UAB28: AD-E me sentía mas informado, me sentía más que estaba ahí por las explicaciones que daban.

AD-R no era tan completa. La tercera (AD-C) era parecida al segundo. [In AD-E, I was feeling more informed, I was feeling more like I was being there because of the explanations it gave. AD-R was not so complete. The third one (AD-C) was similar to the second one]

UAB29: Lo he ordenado de esta manera porque el segundo video (AD-E) tiene más información que no es visual pero auditiva. En una escena hombres y mujeres están separados por una valla. Esto te lo dice la audiodescripción extendida. Detalles como este se pueden dejar de ver sin la audiodescripción. AD-C he ordenado en segundo lugar porque tenía AD pero no me parece tan buena como AD-E, no tan completa. Y en el tercer video (AD-R) no se nota audio descripción. Se nota solo la narración de una voz femenina y masculina. Además, en este tercer video hay espacios en blanco, sin voz. [I ordered the videos in this way because the second video has more information which is not visual but auditory. In the scene, men and women are separated by a wall. This is what extended AD says. Such details can escape you without AD. I ordered AD-C in the second place because it had AD but it does not seem as good as AD-E, not so complete. And the third video (AD-R), AD is not noticeable. Only the narration for a female and male voice is noticeable. Moreover, in this last video, there are blank spaces, without any voice]

UAB31: En el segundo vídeo la AD era mas corta y el estilo no me gustaba tanto (AD-R). En el tercero, hay AD adicional y es muy interesante (AD-E) el hecho de poder parar el video que permite profundizar la descripción del espacio o de la situación. AD-C AD esta mas integrada que en el segundo vídeo y da bastante detalles para entender todo. [In the second video, AD was shorter and I did not like that much its style (AD-R). In the third one (AD-E), there is additional AD and the possibility to stop the video is very interesting because it allows to deepen the description of the space and the situation. AD-C is more integrated than the second video and it gives enough details to understand everything]

3. How could AD be improved in this medium?

UAB1: L'AD perfecta seria que quan miressis un lloc et descrivís allò, o com a mínim que et situés en l'espai, perquè a vegades no trobava l'element que es descrivia (tècnica del rellotge, etc.). Que orienti cap a on són les coses. Ara no interactua amb el teu moviment. [A perfect AD would be when you look in one place, a description of that place is provided, or as a minimum that you are situated in the space because sometimes I could not find the described element (clock

technique, etc.) It could guide towards where the things are. Now it does not interact with your movement]

UAB2: Possibilitat d'interactuar i tenir ADs segons demanda (com a l'AD-E) seria una bona via. [A possibility to interact and have optional ADs (like AD-E) would be a good solution]

UAB3: Un documental amb explicacions, potser no caldria AD per a una persona amb baixa visió. // En un vídeo sense explicacions, caldria que fossin molt breus. [A documentary with explanations, maybe AD for a partially-sighted person is not necessary. // In a video without explanations, they could be shorter]

UAB4: No ho sé. [I don't know]

UAB5: M'agradaria poder fer preguntes, tant de contingut (p. ex.: per què homes i dones separats al mur?) com sobre on mires. [I would like to make questions about the content that you are watching (ex. why men and women are separated by a wall?)]

UAB6: M'agradaria notar el so espacial per sentir que m'envolta. Aquestes opcions són com qualsevol audioguia. [I would like to notice spatial sound to feel immersed. These options are like in any audioguide]

UAB7: Falta concreció en els detalls, sobretot per a gent que no hi veu gens: p. ex. colors. Localitzar les persones i els objectes (elements a esquerra i dreta). Alguns sons no són identificables. Al Cap. 1 s'explicava molt bé el que hi havia a les botiges; al Cap. 3, els falafels... [The details are missing, especially for people who are not seeing anything: ex. colours. Localizing persons and objects (elements to the left and to the right). Some of the sounds are not identifiable. In 1 ep. it was well-explained about the shops, in the ep. 3 falafels...]

UAB8: No ho sé. [I don't know]

UAB9: No ho sé, m'ha agradat. Són veus agradables i tranquil·les i a bon ritme. [I don't know, I liked it. The voices are pleasant, calm and at good pace]

UAB10: M'ha agradat. No he tingut sensació d'immersió per la part visual, però la descripció era bona. [I liked it. I did not have the sensation of immersion for visual part, but the description was fine]

UAB11: Que la màquina sàpiga si mires a la dreta o a l'esquerra. Per a les coses importants (p. ex. obres arquitectòniques), que t'orientessin sobre cap a on mirar. [That the machine knows if you are looking to the right or to the left. Regarding important things (ex. architectural works) that it orients you towards where you should look.]

UAB12: Siendo un poco más descriptivo en cuanto arriba, abajo, izquierda y derecha. Es decir, que el audiodescriptor te diga donde tienes que mirar. Por ejemplo, a la izquierda tienes la puerta de entrada al sepulcro. [Being more descriptive regarding (the directions): up, down, left, right. Audio describer should tell you where to look]

UAB13: Nada. [Nothing]

UAB14: AD-C me gusta. [I like AD-C]

UAB15: No lo sé. En una de ellas se parecen demasiado la voz que narra el documental y la que audiodescribe. Sería mejor que se distinguieran bien. [I don't know. In one of them the narrator's and audiodescriber's voice are too similar. It would be better that they are more distinctive.]

UAB17: Está bien. Me ha gustado mucho en el segundo vídeo pudieras pulsar el botón y parar el vídeo y que te diera información adicional (pero no la información que se daba en este vídeo). Que fuera como el tercer vídeo pero opcional. [It's fine. I liked a lot that in the second video you can click the button, stop the video and be provided with additional information (but not the information that was provided in this video). That it is like in the third video, but optional]

UAB18: Cuando más detalles hay, recibo más información. Se podría mejorar teniendo más audio descripciones extendidas. [The more details there are, the more information you receive. It could be improved by adding more extended descriptions]

- UAB19:** La AD está bien. Aunque era muy documental. Quizás explicarlo de manera más natural, no tan estructurado. Como por ejemplo si me lo estuviera explicando alguien que estuviera ahí conmigo, de manera más natural, más espontáneo. No tan guionizado. [AD is fine although it is very documentary-like. Maybe by explaining it in a more natural way, not so structured. Like for example someone who would be there with me explained it, in a more natural, more spontaneous way]
- UAB20:** Está bien como está. [It is fine]
- UAB21:** Simultánea (sonido y video al mismo tiempo). [Simultaneous (sound and video at the same time)]
- UAB22:** Con sonidos de entorno (viento, cascada, lluvia, pajaros, ruidos de las plantas, hojas, personas). [With ambient sounds (wind, waterfall, rains, birds, sounds of the plants, leaves, people)]
- UAB23:** Añadiendo audiodescripciones extendidas porque es mejor tener opciones, y cuando es más interactivo. [By adding extended audio descriptions because it is better to have options and when it is interactive]
- UAB24:** La audiodescripción extendida: el fondo de audiodescripción extendida debe traer el mismo fondo de la narración para que no se escucha como una interrupción. Me gustaría que la audiodescripción extendida estuviera más integrada al video. Se nota muy la interrupción, la audiodescripción extendida aparece de manera muy abrupta. Me gustaría que la audiodescripción comience con música del fondo, después haya voz de audiodescripción y termine con la misma música del video. [Extended AD: the background of extended audio description needs to convey the same background as the narration so that (upon activating) there is no interruption. I would like extended AD to be more integrated in the video. The interruption is very noticeable, extended AD starts abruptly. I would like extended AD to start with background music, then to have a description, and to finish with the same background music]
- UAB25:** Cuando audiodescripción me decía 'la puerta', necesitaría una flecha, una luz o algo que indique a donde está la puerta. También me gustaría información verbal como: a la izquierda, a la derecha, arriba. En la narración de AD me gustaría tener la información meteorológica, poner la temperatura y también la información sobre las texturas para sentirme más inmersa. [When audio description was telling me 'door', I would need an arrow, a light or something that indicates where is the door. I would also like a verbal information like: to the left, to the right, up. In the AD narration, I would like to have the meteorological information, information about the temperature and about the textures to feel more immersed]
- UAB26:** Me gustaría que todos los videos tuvieran estos comentarios adicionales. [I would like that all the videos had additional comments]
- UAB27:** Me gustaría que los sonidos ambientales y los efectos de sonido estén mas en la primera línea que las explicaciones. Me gustaría tener audiodescripción más en fondo y los efectos de sonido más destacados para sentir que el mundo presentado es real. Las explicaciones eran rápidas con entonación fuerte y esta manera de explicar es un poco tensa. Me gustaría que fuera más natural, relajada. [I would like that the ambient sounds and the sound effects are more in the first line than the explanations. I would like to have audio description more in the background and the sound effects more underlined to feel that the presented world is real. The explanations were fast with strong intonation and this way of explaining is a bit tense. I would like it to be more natural, relaxed]
- UAB28:** Cuando más detalles me dan, mejor. Me gusta lo más detallado posible. [The more details, the better. I like as many details as possible]
- UAB29:** Intentar audiodescribir los espacios en blanco y poner audiodescripción extendida. [Try to audio describe blank spaces and add extended AD]
- UAB31:** La campana (AD extendida) es un buen invento porque pudiendo parar el video tienes la sensación de no perder tanta información porque en el video de 360 grados no se puede ver

todo y no se puede abarcar. AD se podría mejorar en este medio añadiendo campanas, sobre todo en los documentales. [The bell (extended AD) is a good idea because by pausing the video, you have the impression of not losing so much information because in the video with 360 degrees one cannot see everything. AD could be improved in this media format by adding bells, especially in the documentaries]

4. Other comments:

UAB01: M'ha agradat en general: he flipat amb la informació que donava. [I liked it in general: I was content with the information it gave]

UAB2: Resulta difícil saber quan mires cap a la imatge que s'audiodescriu. Sovint no saps què tens davant. Amb una petita AD les imatges que no s'entenen cobren sentit. / O bé que s'indiqués cap a on mirar. [It is difficult to know when you look at the image that is being described. Often you do not know what lies ahead. With some AD you can understand images. / Or to indicate where to look]

UAB3: No sento que l'àudio m'envolti.

NS/NC per a les dues últimes del qüestionari AD-R. [I did not feel that the sound surrounds me. No answer for the two last questions in the AD-R questionnaire]

UAB4: El tipus de producte influeix molt en el so i en la immersió. Aquí el so no envolta (se sent com en una pel·lícula normal). No tinc una preferència clara entre C i R [The type of product influence a lot a sound and immersion. Here the sound is not surrounding you (one feels like in a normal film) I don't have a clear preference between C and R]

UAB5: Em sembla al·lucinant. És una experiència molt agradable. [I find it amazing. It is a very pleasant experience]

UAB6: No m'agrada l'enquesta (preguntes massa rígides). És totalment diferent del que necessita un cec total i una persona amb baixa visió: els qüestionaris haurien de ser diferents. [I don't like the questionnaire (the questions are too rigid). The needs of a totally blind person are different from the needs of partially-sighted persons: the questionnaires should be different]

UAB8: El contingut de cada vídeo influeix en les percepcions. [The content of every video influences the perception]

UAB10: La participant no tenia un nivell de català gaire alt: diu que ha entès gran part del vídeo, però ha demanat què volien dir paraules bàsiques com "seva" o "botiga". [The participant did not have a very high level of Catalan: (s)he said that (s)he understands a great part of the video, but asked what such basic words as "seva" or "botiga" mean]

UAB12: This participant is interested in stopping the video and to have audio descriptions when the video is stopped. Ampliación del campo visual. No le he prestado tanta atención a la audiodescripción, me ha llamado la atención del aumento del campo visual. Y eso me ha impactado y me he entrenado en ver hacia arriba, hacia abajo. Y no le he prestado tanta atención a la audio descripción porque he visto las imágenes. Lo más positivo es que me ha aumentado el campo visual, que normalmente lo tengo muy limitado. [Extension of the visual field. I have not paid much attention to audio description, the increase in the visual field has drawn my attention. And that has made an impression on me and I have trained myself to look up, down. And I haven't paid much attention to audio description because I've seen the pictures. The positive thing is that my visual field has increased, which I usually have very limited.]

UAB13: El hecho de no ver hace que el mundo virtual pierda sentido. [The fact of not seeing makes that the virtual world loses its sense]

UAB14: Para tener la sensación de estar en la esfera, necesitaría que la experiencia fuera multisensorial. [To feel the sensation of being inside the sphere, I would need the experience to be multisensory]

UAB15: AD-C ha sido como ver la televisión. [AD-C was like watching a TV]

UAB17: Nada. [Nothing]

UAB19: EL sonido del documental no era envolvente, era como ver un documental normal de la televisión. Me gustaría que el sonido fuera cuadrofónico, envolvente, para ser más inmersivo. [The sound of the documentary was not surround, it was like seeing a normal documentary in a TV. I would like the sound to be more quadrophonic, surround, to be more immersed]

UAB20: El sonido de la AD extendida de la campana no llama lo suficientemente la atención y no me he dado cuenta. Mejor un sonido que se escuche más o ponerlo en la audiointroducción. [The sound of the bell in the extended AD is not distinctive enough and I overlooked it. A sound that is more hearable would be better or otherwise (the bell sound) should be included in the audio introduction.

UAB21: Me gusta mas el 3d (AD-R) en el que se integra sonido e imagen si producir desfases en el tiempo [I would like that in the third one (AD-R) the sound and image are integrated so that there are no time lags]

UAB22: Fue muy bonito experimentarlo. [It was very nice to experience it]

UAB25: Me gustaría ajustar el volumen de AD. El sonido de campana debería ser más distinto. Me gustaría parar AD-E cuando quiero. [I would like to adjust the AD volume. The bell sound should be more distinctive. I would like to stop AD-E at will]

UAB26: AD-R me ha costado introducirme a historia porque era el video inicial y no era acostumbrado a esta tecnología. [It was difficult for me to introduce myself to the story in AD-R because it was an initial video and I was not accustomed to this technology]

UAB27: El sonido de AD era demasiado saliente (AD-R). [The sound of AD was too audible (AD-R)]

UAB31: Traducción del video y la AD están bien integradas. [The translation of the video and AD are well-integrated]

Summary:

Classic AD was the preferred option for 10 participants. Some users expressed the reasons behind their choice. UAB 1 found the visual information in this AD type more complete, and UAB 2 and 31 said that this AD type allowed them to imagine the sphere better. Four users (UAB2, 18, 29 31) said that the level of visual details in AD-R is not sufficient and two other users (UAB2 and 29) commented that the scripting style of AD-R does not resemble AD, but it is more like a separate narration. UAB15 said that listening to AD-C was like listening AD in standard TV (and for this content another type of scripting is better) - this person assessed better the script in AD-R.

Three users (UAB9, 20 and 25) did not notice the differences between scripts, and they liked equally each of them.

Two users (UAB17, 27) commented positively on ambient sounds in AD-R which made the experience more realistic and one participant (UAB23) commented positively on the emotive language in this type of AD.

17 participants commented positively on AD-E, the reasons being the possibility to interact with the content (UAB2) or the possibility to listen more at will (UAB4, 5, 10, 11, 13, 14, 23, 26, 31), gives more details (UAB18, 24, 27, 28, 29), allows to feel more immersed in the video (UAB22, 28).

UAB17 said that extended AD should include audio description, but not titbits (such information should be provided only in the video).

The improvements in audio description that participants proposed include:

- a) being oriented towards the described places, characters and objects (UAB1, UAB7, 11, 12, 25)
- b) having extended ADs (UAB2, 17, 18, 23, 26, 29, 31)
- c) having spatial sound (UAB6, UAB19 - other comments)

d) having ambient sounds (UAB22, 27)

e) to feel more present in the content, one participant suggested to integrate an information about the weather, temperature or textures in the script of AD (UAB25).

One participant (UAB24) suggested how extended AD can be improved. This participant would like extended AD to be more integrated with the video, so that the main video is not cut so abruptly. To this end, participant suggested that extended AD could start and end with ambient sounds/music present in the main video.

La audiodescripción extendida: el fondo de audiodescripción extendida debe traer el mismo fondo de la narración para que no se escucha como una interrupción. Me gustaría que audiodescripción extendida fuera mas integrada al video. Se nota muy la interrupción, la audiodescripción extendida aparece de manera muy abrupta. Me gustaría que la audiodescripción comenzara con música del fondo, después hubiera la voz de la audiodescripción y terminara con la misma música del video. [Extended AD: the background of extended audio description should convey the same background as the narration so that there is no interruption (upon activating extended AD). I would like extended AD to be more integrated in the video. The interruption is very noticeable, extended AD starts abruptly. I would like extended AD to start with background music, then to have a description, and to finish with the same background music] (UAB24)

Regarding the integration of ambient sounds and being present in the content, one comment seems particularly relevant:

Me gustaría que los sonidos ambientales y los efectos de sonido estuvieran más en la primera línea que las explicaciones. Me gustaría tener audi descripción más en fondo y los efectos de sonido más destacados para sentir que el mundo presentado es real. Las explicaciones eran rápidas con entonación fuerte y esta manera de explicar es un poco tensa. Me gustaría que fuera más natural, relajada. [I would like that the ambient sounds and the sound effects are more in the first line than the explanations. I would like to have audio description more in the background and the sound effects more underlined to feel that the presented world is real. The explanations were fast with strong intonation and this way of explaining is a bit tense. I would like it to be more natural, relaxed] (UAB27)

2 participants (UAB20, 25) commented on the 'bell' sound signaling extended AD. Those participants said that this sound is not distinctive enough and proposed to change it, or to introduce it first in audio introduction, so that users know which sound to expect.

One participant (UAB25) would like to have a possibility to adjust the sound of AD. That option could also be integrated in voice interaction with a player by Amazon Echo Dot (researcher's comment).

The additional comments of 5 participants (UAB3, 4, 13, 14, 19, 4 - partially sighted, 1 - blind) suggest that those participants would need to have more senses involved to feel more present in the storyworld.

5. TEST 3: AST PRESENTATION MODES

1. Which type of audio subtitles do you prefer for 360° videos?

AST: 16

AST-AD: 13

2. Explain in your own words why you prefer the option chosen in the first question.

UAB01: Porque entiendo más cuándo interactúa cada uno de los personajes. [Because I understand more when each of the characters interact]

UAB2: Porque me permite seguir el diálogo del texto cantado y da mucha información. [Because it allows me to follow the text of the songs and gives a lot of information]

UAB3: En realidad, me han gustado los dos. Los dos eran fáciles de seguir. [In reality, I liked two of them. They were both easy to follow]

- UAB4:** Más teatralizada. [More theatrical]
- UAB5:** No he notado diferencia. Las dos. [I did not notice the difference. The two]
- UAB6:** Sigue más el libreto. AST-AD permite oír más la música, AST la trama. (?) [It follows more the libretto. AST-AD allows to listen more to the music and AD to the plot]
- UAB7:** Me gusta más con la AD, porque me entera más, pero no va sincronizado con la escena. Narran con antelación. [I like more the one with AD because I understand more, but it is not synchronized with the scene. They narrate in advance]
- UAB8:** No he notado mucho las diferencias. No tengo preferencias. [I did not notice many differences. I don't have preferences]
- UAB9:** Me han gustado los dos. Me habría gustado el AST-AD si se distinguieran las voces entre AD y AST. [I liked the two. I would like the AST-AD if there were different voices for AD and AST.]
- UAB10:** Más descriptivo en cuanto a la escena (AST). [More descriptive regarding the scene (AST)]
- UAB11:** AST-AD te cuenta la acción, en vez de lo que decían cantando. [AST-AD tells you the action instead of what they are singing]
- UAB12:** Porque le da algo más de importancia a la música que a la narración y si quieres la historia te coges el libro y lo lees. Es mejor disfrutar de la música. [Because it gives more importance to the music than to narration and if you want the story, you can take the book (the libretto) and you can read it. It is better to appreciate the music]
- UAB13:** Los de antes lo que hacía era traducir la canción, mientras que los otros describían lo que pasaba. Cuando estoy oyendo ópera me gusta solo saber lo que cantan. [The previous one translated the song while the other ones explained what was happening. When I am listening to the opera, I like only to know what they are singing about]
- UAB14:** Porque entendía mejor la trama y sentía más la inmersión. [Because I understood better the plot and felt more immersed]
- UAB15:** Decía textualmente lo que ocurría, el otro era interpretativo. Alguien más fan de la ópera querrá escuchar más la ópera, yo prefiero saber de qué se trata... Es muy subjetivo. [It was saying what was happening, the other one was interpretative. Someone who is an opera fan will prefer to listen more to the opera and I prefer more to know what it is about. It is very subjective]
- UAB16:** The AST-AD mix distracts, it takes more time - or at least it feels like that, thus there is less time left to enjoy the original soundtrack.
- UAB17:** Era todo un poco más ordenado que en el segundo, primero te explicaba lo que iba a suceder, lo que se iba a ver digamos. Y luego durante la escena se iba explicando los subtítulos. Más o menos podías seguir la trama. En cambio en el segundo te lo explica todo antes de empezar, te mezcla imágenes con subtítulos, hay veces que no te lee los subtítulos y es más complicado de seguir. [Everything was a bit more ordered than in the second one, the first one explained you what was going to happen, what you were going to see. And then during the scene it was explaining the subtitles. More or less you could follow the plot. The second one explained you everything before the start, mixed the images with subtitles, there are times when the subtitles are not read aloud and it is more difficult to follow]
- UAB19:** En la primera iba diciendo a tiempo real lo que se decía durante la ópera. Y en la segunda a pesar de que mezclaba audiosubtitulación con AD había momentos que no había ni una cosa ni una otra, con lo cual tampoco sabía cómo interpretar los comentarios, no sabía si se referían a un tramo anterior o posterior, etc. Estaba un poco desorientado con las explicaciones de la AD. [The first one was telling you in real time what was being said during the opera. And in the second one, although the audiosubtitles were mixed with AD, there were moments when there were none. Because of this, I did not know how to interpret the commentaries, if they are referring to the plot before or later. I was a bit disorientated with AD explanations]

- UAB20:** Porque me daba más información sobre lo que estaba ocurriendo. [Because it gave me more information about what was happening]
- UAB21:** no me ha gustado ninguna. Pero, la segunda parece ser que interfiere menos en la escena. mejor una simple aclaracion del entorno. [I did not like any of them. But, the second one seems to interfere less with the scene. The simple explanation of the surroundings is better]
- UAB22:** La accion me atrapo mas, la senti como mas real. [The action caught me more, it felt more real]
- UAB24:** AST me gusta mas porque van describiendo, van narrando lo que estoy viendo, la escena al mismo tiempo. AST-AD no fue muy descriptivo. [I like AST more because it describes, narrates what I am seeing, the scene, at the same time. AST-AD was not very descriptive]
- UAB25:** AST-AD tiene más detalles, más información, más interpretación. Me he sentido más presente, más situada en este video. AST es más superficial. A nivel visual me gusta más AST-AD. [AST-AD has more details, more information, more interpretation. I was feeling more present, more situated in this video. AST is more superficial. At the visual level, I prefer more AST-AD]
- UAB26:** AST-AD me ha gustado más porque había interpretación de los diálogos también que audiodescripción que explica el contexto y cotexto. [I like more AST-AD because there was an interpretation of the dialogues as well as audio description that explains the context and cotext]
- UAB27:** En la primera (AST) no me senti como viendo opera pero como alguien me está leyendo la historia de la ópera. Las canciones son muy cortadas por la audiodescripción. AST-AD me gusto más porque da más oportunidad de sentirte en la opera. [In the first one (AST), I was not feeling like I was watching opera but as if someone reads me the story of the opera. The songs are often cut by the audio description. I liked AST-AD more because it gives you more opportunity to feel in the opera]
- UAB28:** AST-AD las explicaciones eran más distanciadas en el primer video, más calmadas, más suaves. AST En el segundo las explicaciones eran más cortos pero más seguidos, no era tiempo para escuchar el fondo y la música. [(AST-AD) the explanations were more separated in the first video, calmer, softer. In the second one (AST), the explanations were shorter but constant, there was no time to listen to the background and the music]
- UAB29:** AST-AD me ha gustado más porque la audiodescripción es más concentrada y deja escuchar más el sonido original. AST - la narración es tan seguida que no te deje escuchar ni la música ni el sonido original. [I liked more AST-AD because the audio description is more concentrated and it allows you to listen more the original sound. In AST, the narration is so frequent that it does not allow you to listen neither to the music nor to the original sound]
- UAB30:** No he notado diferencias entre la narracion, pero prefiero AST-AD porque este video es mas relajado y en el segundo hay mas violencia (AST). [I did not notice the differences between the narrations, but I prefer AST-AD because this video is more relaxed and in the second one there is more violence (AST)]
- UAB31:** El segundo (AST-AD) permite no perder la parte más dramática de la opera aunque pierda la literalidad de las parabras y la audiosubtitulacion no es invasiva. (AST) El primero nos permite captar todas las frases en el momento que las dicen pero pierdas la pasión, la emoción de la ópera. En el primer video, no pierdes el contexto original en la escena porque hay audiosubtítulos al mismo tiempo pero pierdes la emoción. [The second one (AST-AD) allows you not to miss the more dramatic part of the opera although you miss the literality of the words and the audio subtitles are not invasive. (AST) The first one allows us to listen to all phrases in the moment in which they are said, but you miss the passion, the emotion of the opera. In the first video, you don't miss the original context of the scene because there are audiosubtitles, but at the same time you miss the emotion]

3. What system would you prefer?

Audio subtitles with no subtitles on screen: 13 (6 – partially-sighted and

7 blind)

Audio subtitles with subtitles on screen that can be enlarged: 0

I would like to select when I want subtitles on screen and when not: 16 (12 – partially sighted, 4 – blind)

4. How could audio subtitles be improved in this medium?

UAB1: No lo sé. [I don't know]

UAB2: Los AST se anticipaban al pasaje cantado de forma que permitía entender lo que decía el cantante, y me ha gustado (en AST solo). [The AST were present only when there were songs in the form that allowed me to understand what the singer was saying, and I liked this (AST only)]

UAB3: NS/NC La voz es clara y se entiende. [The voice is clear and understandable]

UAB4: Inlús me invitó a una película audiosubtitulada sobre integración de personas con discapacidad cognitiva y me gustó más la metodología. [I was invited to see an audiosubtitled film about the integration of persons with cognitive disabilities and I liked more the methodology]

UAB5: No lo sé, ya está muy bien descrita. [I don't know, it is very well described]

UAB6: Me gustaría un sonido más sofisticado. Que fuera integrativa y sirviera para perfiles distintos. [I would like a more sophisticated sound. That it is integrative and serves various profiles]

UAB7: Sería mejor cada frase en el momento en que sucede. [It would be better to have each phrase in the moment when it is said]

UAB8: No lo sé. [I don't know]

UAB9: Yo esperaba que la voz del audiodescriptor fuera distinta de la voz del audiosubtitulador. [I was expecting that the voice of the audio describer would be different from the voice of audiosubtitler]

UAB10: A veces no entendía qué personaje entraba o salía. [Sometimes I did not understand if the character was entering or leaving the scene]

UAB11: No lo sé. [I don't know]

UAB12: Está bien, el segundo me ha gustado más. [It's fine, I liked the second one more]

UAB13: El sonido tiene que ir por un auricular y el original, porque si no se pisan y no oyes nada. [the sound (od AST) should come from one headphone piece, and the original for the other one. If not, they mix and you don't hear anything]

UAB14: No lo sé. [I don't know]

UAB15: En la versión AST, se quitaba protagonismo a la música. Quizás le subiría el volumen a la música para no anularla. [In the AST versión, the priority was given to the music. Perhaps the volume of the music could be turned up]

UAB16: make the AST track adjustable by the user and independent from the original soundtrack.

UAB17: Cuando estaba viendo el primero vídeo, al principio del vídeo la voz que iba haciendo la audiodescripción se solapaba con el cantante y no se escuchaba. Creo que no mejoraría nada de todos modos, siguiendo el ejemplo del primer vídeo. [When I saw the first video, at the beginning of this video, a voice of an audio describer was overlapping with the one of the singer and it was not hearable. I think that I would not improve anything, following the example of the first video]

UAB19: Yo añadiría algunos comentarios de AD a los AST como hacía el segundo pero a lo mejor en los momento que no hay diálogo para no cortar la AST y no perder partes de la escena por no tener la AD, partes que no se podrían deducir por el diálogo. [I would add some AD commentaries in AST (clip), as it was done in the second, but maybe at the moment when

there is not dialogue not to cut the AST and not to miss parts of the scene by not having AD, parts that cannot be guessed from the dialogue only]

UAB20: Está bien. [It's fine]

UAB21: Reduciendo el tiempo. Reducir el detalle a una mera definición del espacio, colocación de los personajes, luz y decorado. Quiero escuchar más la música [By reducing the time. Reducing the details to the simple definition of the space, location of the characters, light and decoration. I want to listen more to the music]

UAB22: Poniendo más detalles sobre ropa, personajes, entorno, color. [By adding more details about the clothes, the characters, surroundings, colours]

UAB24: Aquí hay solo una voz para dos o diferentes personajes. Me gustaría tener tantas voces tantos personajes, también voces femeninas y masculinas (que los tonos de voces sean completamente distintos). Me gust aría identificar los personajes. [There is just one voice for two or more characters. I would like to have as many voices as charactes, also female and male voices (so that the tones are completely distinctive). I would like to identify the characters.

UAB25: Me gustaría tener audiodescripción extendida en estos vídeo también para tener más informacion sobre por ejemplo las espadas y los vestidos o bolsos. Me gustaría intercambiar las voces dentro de los AST: las voces femeninas cuando hay personajes femeninas y masculinas cuando hay personajes masculinas sería una buena forma de mejorar AST. [I would like to have extended AD in these videos also to have more information about, for example, the swords, the clothes or bags. I would like to interchange the voices within AST: the female voices when there are female characters and masculine voiced when there are male characters would be a good way to improve AST]

UAB26: Preparando los audiosubtítulos como en el primer vídeo (AST-AD). [By preparing the AST like in the first video (AST-AD)]

UAB27: Los AST deberían leerse más suavemente, en segundo plane. No deberían destacar para escuchar la música de la ópera y sentirse presente en la obra. Me gustaría que los AST vinieran de detrás como un complemento, un comentario adicional. [The AST should be read more softly, in the second line. They shouldn't be so salient in order to listen to the opera music and feel present in the work. I would like AST to come from behind like an additional comment]

UAB28: Me gustaría una voz no tan sonora porque interrumpe mucho la música y el canto que está detrás. Me gustaría el tono de voz un poco más bajo y suave. [I would like the voice not to be so salient because it interrupts a lot the music and singing which is behind. I would like the tone of the voice to be a bit lower and softer]

UAB29: En el segundo vídeo (AST-AD) no hay nada que mejorar. [In the second video (AST-AD), there is nothing to improve]

UAB30: No tengo sugerencias. [I don't have any suggestions]

UAB31: En el primero vídeo (AST) cuando hay literalidad, me gustaría que no fuera tan sintético, me gustaría que se leyera con más emoción. Me gustaría poner algunas campanas (AD extendida) para escribir la sala, detalles arquitectónicos y dentro de la escena los vestidos y los decorados. [In the first video (AST) when there is literalness, I would like that it is not so much synthetic, but read out more emotionally. I would like to add some bells (extended AD) to describe the interior, architectural details and the clothes and decorations within the scene]

5. In what excerpt did you feel more present?

Only AST: 19

AST and AD: 8

I did not feel present in any of them: 2

I felt equally present in both: 9

6. Other comments:

UAB3: Yo no puedo leer los subtítulos (me lío). [I cannot read the subtitles]

UAB4: Me gusta más la versión teatralizada. [I prefer more the theatrical versión]

UAB5: Contenido alucinante. [Amazing content]

UAB6: ¿No está grabado en sonido envolvente? [Isn't it recorded with spatial sound?]

UAB7: El contenido afecta a la sensación de presencia: en un concierto (con escenario fijo) sueles mirar hacia delante, en una sola dirección. [The content has an influence over the sensation of presence: in a concert (with the scene in a place) you want to look in front of you, only in one direction]

UAB8: Mucha menos sensación de presencia que en los vídeos de Holy Land. [The feeling of presence was much weaker than in Holy Land videos]

UAB10: Las gafas aprietan en la cara, son incómodas. [The glasses press on the forehead, there are uncomfortable]

UAB11: Aprovecho para decir que en los vídeos de Holy Land notaba destellos (suaves). [I take this opportunity to say that in the videos of Holy Land I noticed flashes (soft).]

UAB12: Me gusta más el AST-AD porque me deja escuchar la música. [I prefer more AST-AD because it allows me to listen to the music]

UAB25: Los subtítulos escritos deberían ser al fondo negro y con letra blanca para mejorar el contraste. [The written subtitles should be in the black background and in white font to improve the contrast]

UAB31: En 3 pregunta, me gustaría seleccionar cuándo quiero subtítulos escritos en pantalla o no y que se pueden ampliar. [In the 3 question, I would like to select when I want written subtitles on the screen and when not, and I would also like to have the possibility to enlarge them]

Summary:

Participants who chose the AST option in the first question, put forward the following reasons behind their choice:

- a) this type of narration allows users to follow dialogues in real time (UAB1, 2, 10, 13, 14, 15, 17, 19, 22).
- b) it follows more the libretto (UAB6) or allow users to listen only to the original dialogues, without additional interpretation (UAB6).

Some participants felt distracted when listening to AST-AD (UAB16, 17, 19), as the audio subtitles were not synchronized with the dialogues in real time. UAB9 would like to have different voices for AST and AD.

Participants who chose the AST-AD option in the first question, put forward the following reasons behind their choice:

- a) it gives more time to listen to music (UAB12, 29) and feel immersed in the original content (UAB27, 31). Some of participants who preferred AST-AD option liked that the narration is provided in larger chunks and disliked that in AST option, the video clip is 'cut' by frequent audio subtitles. (UAB27, 28, 29)
- b) it had more details, more information, more interpretation (UAB20, 25, 26).

Some of participants preferred two options equally (UAB3, 5, 9).

Regarding possible improvements, participants proposed some solutions:

- a) To make the AST track adjustable by the user and independent from original soundtrack (UAB16).
- b) To have extended audio description in the videos with audio subtitles to listen more about the clothes and other details. (UAB25, 31)
- c) To have different voices for different characters. (UAB24, 26)
- d) To have AST read with another intonation. (UAB27, 28, 31)

Regarding subjective feeling of being present in the content, 19 participants felt more present in the video with only AST, 8 participants in the video with AST-AD, 9 felt equally present in both and 2 did not feel present in any of them.

13 participants prefer subtitles with no subtitles on screen (6 – partially-sighted and

7 blind) and 16 participants would like to select when they want subtitles on screen and when not (12 – partially sighted, 4 – blind).

ANNEX 32. METHODOLOGY FOR INTERMEDIATE/PRE-PILOT 2

SUBTITLING ACTIONS (UAB)

This annex includes the methodology for both the pre-test and the main test. Some changes were made to the main test methodology.

Methodology for subtitle experiment: pre-test

1. What will be tested? (summary)

The purpose of the experiment is to gather users' feedback (immersion, preferences and usability) about two different presentation modes for subtitles in cinematic virtual reality:

- 1) Part 1 - Position/Behaviour:
 - a) Fixed positioned: subtitles in three different fixed positions, evenly spaced each 120°.
 - b) Always visible: always displayed in front of the viewer, following viewer's head movements.
- 2) Part 2 - Speaker location identification (will be displayed in always visible mode):
 - a) Arrow
 - b) Auto-positioning view

2. Method

A within-subject design will be used to test the different presentation modes. Each participant will see 4 clips. Each clip will be randomly presented with a different variable (fixed positioned, always visible, arrow and auto-positioning). Participants will then be asked to reply to different questionnaires on presence (immersion), preferences and usability. The procedure will be explained in detail below.

Stimuli

Four clips have been chosen to test the different presentation modes. The participants will be shown the clips directly with an HMD (Oculus GO), so they won't need to navigate through the ImAc Player. Therefore, a 6-second black screen with the text "The test is about to start for XXX" should be included.

- *Holy Land Series*
 - Episode 4 - 04:13
 - Episode 5 - 04:58
 - Test: Part 1 - Position/Behaviour
 - Creator: RYOT
 - Description: documentary, travel, Jerusalem.
 - Genre: documentary.
 - Original language: English
 - Duration: around 4/5 minutes per clip
 - Features: voice-off most of the time. Different locations, landscapes. The presence of the hostess in some shots is not relevant for the narrative of the video.
 - Link: <http://84.88.32.46/UAB-test/>
 - Access services needed:
 - SPA SDH - fixed positioned
 - SPA SDH - always visible

In this case, the only SDH specific characteristics are:

- 1) Indicate when the music is sounding (some instances: * Middle Eastern music *)
 - 2) Indicate the narrator with the tag Narrator (italics are not available at this moment)
- An American Classic: Guelaguetza
 - Test: Part 2 - Speaker location
 - Description: documentary, food, cooking, United States, immigration.
 - Genre: documentary
 - Original language: English

- Duration: 07:58 (to be split in two parts)
 - Part 1 - From 00:00 to 03:46
 - Part 2 - From 03:46 to 07:16 (credits start)
 - Features: some parts are voice-off, some parts are narrated by a person on the screen (mainly the owners of the restaurant). This should elicit the viewers to look for the speaker in different scenes.
 - Link: <http://84.88.32.46/UAB-test/>
 - Access services needed:
 - SPA SDH - arrow
 - SPA SDH - auto-positioning
- Speaker identification: colours (according to UNE norm)

IDENTIFICATION CODES FOR THE STIMULI

- A1: *Holy Land 1* - fixed positioned
- A2: *Holy Land 1* - always visible
- B1: *Holy Land 2* - fixed positioned
- B2: *Holy Land 2* - always visible
- C1: Guelaguetza 1 - arrow
- C2: Guelaguetza 1 - auto-positioning
- D1: Guelaguetza 2 - arrow
- D2: Guelaguetza 2 - auto-positioning

The four clips and four conditions are counterbalanced using a Latin square, according to the table below. Each participant will see four clips, each with a different condition. The clip for the speaker location conditions (Guelaguetza) is always shown in chronological order (1-2), otherwise the participants would miss parts of the narrative.

LATIN SQUARE FOR ALL PARTICIPANTS

Each participant will follow a different order to avoid the order of presentation affecting the results.

Participant	Behaviour	Behaviour	Speaker location	Speaker location
PPilot01	A1	B2	C1	D2
PPilot02	A2	B1	C2	D1
PPilot03	B1	A2	C1	D2
PPilot04	B2	A1	C2	D1
PPilot05	A1	B2	C1	D2
PPilot06	A2	B1	C2	D1
PPilot07	B1	A2	C1	D2
PPilot08	B2	A1	C2	D1

Procedure

PLANNING

Introduction: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Welcome participants- Explain project and aim of the test- Consent forms and demographic questionnaires- Clip for acclimatation	20 min
Part 1 - Position: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Clip 1- IPQ questionnaire- Clip 2- IPQ questionnaire- Preference questionnaire	25 min
Part 2 - Speaker location <ul style="list-style-type: none">- Clip 1- IPQ questionnaire- Clip 2- IPQ questionnaire- Preference questionnaire	25 min
Farewell and thanks	5 min
Buffer time	5 min
Total	85 min

Procedure

- **Experimental protocol:** users will be asked to watch different stimuli, and then report on the usability, preferences and immersion through digital questionnaires with closed and open questions.
- **Research tools:** digital questionnaires (Google Forms). The questionnaires will be digital in order to facilitate data processing.
- **Measures:** presence (immersion), preferences and usability.
- **Participants:** hearing and hearing-impaired participants. Participants will be representative of the actual sample to test all possibilities, that is:
 - 1 young adult, hearing impaired, allegedly technologically-able (because of the age, we assume). If possible, include 2 young adults (one for each group specified before).
 - 1 young adult, non-hearing impaired, allegedly technologically-able (because of the age, we assume). If possible, include 2 young adults (one for each group specified before).
 - 1 adult, hearing impaired, allegedly non-technologically-able (because of the age, we assume). If possible, include 2 adults (one for each group specified before).
 - 1 adult, non-hearing impaired, allegedly non-technologically-able (because of the age, we assume). If possible, include 2 adults (one for each group specified before).
- **Duration:** approx. 85 minutes.
- **Language of the test:** Spanish.
- **Materials:** HMD, laptop and clips.
- **Facilitators:** one facilitator will be needed. The facilitator will be the leader (welcoming participants, explaining the project, explaining the test) and will assist the sessions (by

providing the digital questionnaires and helping to fill them in, providing technical assistance with the different devices, etc.).

- All materials and ethical forms must be ready before the test.

INTRODUCTION (20 min)

<u>What?</u>	<u>How long?</u>
<p>Welcome the participants, who will individually attend the test. Please assign a participant code when they arrive, so that they can enter that code in each online questionnaire.</p>	1 min
<p>Explain the project (if unknown to the participant), the aim of the test and the procedure.</p>	5 min
<p>Provide the participant with the consent form for ethical clearance. The last version can be found here: https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1X5Nj9KxkpFVwvEuKfK6XVgz0VFUSzUOS</p>	3 min
<p>Provide the participant with the digital demographic questionnaire to be filled in (access to a computer/laptop will be needed):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ES: https://drive.google.com/open?id=1r1Ez_uBQ1Y5lfUVYqKTO5Dy2Y8sZ2PegooxST_Xn4po https://goo.gl/forms/bhaSlaCm3PuhtTWE3 	6 min
<p>A clip for acclimatation to the HMD and the virtual reality experience will be shown to the participants. A clip from The New York Times app will be used.</p>	5 min

In the following sections, the different parts of the test will be explained, including tasks and measures.

PART 1 - Position (25 minutes)

- **Measures:**
 - Immersion: IPQ questionnaire
 - Preferences and usability: closed and open questions
- **Materials:**
 - Devices: the test will be performed with an HMD (Oculus Go).
 - Player:
 - Link to the player: <http://84.88.32.46/UAB-test/>
 - Stimuli: Two comparable clips (A, B) with 2 conditions (1, 2) for each presentation mode tested, so that participants can watch both conditions in different but comparable clips to avoid a learning effect. Stimuli explained above.
- **Room**: make sure the atmosphere is comfortable for the participants, with an adequate room arrangement.

Previous to task

The facilitator will explain the aim of this part: testing two different presentation modes to visualise the subtitles. There will be two presentation modes: subtitles in three different fixed positions and subtitles that follow head immediately. After watching the clips, they will be asked to answer a set of questions.

Procedure

- 1) The participants will be asked to watch the two randomised clips. The order is specified in the Latin Square provided above.
- 2) The participant will have to watch 2 clips (A, B) with the randomised variables: 1) fixed positioned and 2) always visible. After watching **each clip**, participants will have to reply to the IPQ (presence) questionnaire to gather feedback about immersion.

IPQ version in English to be translated into Spanish (no official version available):
https://drive.google.com/open?id=1c_10TqnXTaZnev0BNDM64dqRit2HkNR-tRiPhC23t9g

a) Always visible:

i) *Holy* *Land* 4:
https://drive.google.com/open?id=1c_10TqnXTaZnev0BNDM64dqRit2HkNR-tRiPhC23t9g

<https://goo.gl/forms/xTb0U2HTcFOV6TT23>

ii) *Holy* *Land* 5:
<https://drive.google.com/open?id=1j9oKSrtmHedAAsgfjdWO0EODnjdakw1e2zTdQgN0LnQ>

<https://goo.gl/forms/But6HUrkyDx34Oqr1>

b) Fixed positioned:

i) *Holy* *Land* 4:
<https://drive.google.com/open?id=1QhfulnrKyZfVjD04atlwisfOSAACElKhwl60Q4e04al>

<https://goo.gl/forms/7en8G5oAkl5bqDKE2>

ii) *Holy* *Land* 5:
https://drive.google.com/open?id=1as6mNjzr25OzV4GINO3AUMaJnn61luvHCy_YQ5YJtQA

<https://goo.gl/forms/vlSfa6kQgY62zt362>

- 3) After watching **the two clips**, the participants will be asked to provide feedback about preferences and usability:

a) LINK TO POST-QUESTIONNAIRE: https://drive.google.com/open?id=1-X8o48QLWHH76h2eKldhfjDPBks6U_IYqViJk3Y3FQ

PART 2 - Speaker location (25 minutes)

- **Measures:**
 - Immersion: IPQ questionnaire
 - Preferences and usability: close and open questions
- **Materials:**
 - Device: the test will be performed with an HMD.
 - Player:
 - Link to the player: <http://84.88.32.46/UAB-test/>
 - Stimuli: Two comparable clips (C, D) with 2 conditions (1, 2) for each presentation mode tested, so that participants can watch both conditions in different but comparable clips to avoid a learning effect. Stimuli explained above.
- **Room**: make sure the atmosphere is comfortable for the participants, with an adequate room arrangement

Introduction

The facilitator will explain the aim of this part: testing two different presentation modes to guide the user to the speaker. There will be two presentation modes: an arrow integrated in the subtitle that will indicate where to look for the speaker and an automatic view that will take the viewer directly to the speaker. After watching the clips, they will be asked to answer a set of questions.

Procedure

- 1) The participants will be asked to watch the two randomised clips. The order is specified in the Latin Square provided above.
- 2) The participant will have to watch 2 clips (C, D) with the randomised variables 1) arrow and 2) auto-positioning. After watching **each clip**, participants will have to reply to the IPQ (presence) questionnaire to gather feedback about immersion.
 - a) Arrow:
 - i) Guelaguetza 1:
https://drive.google.com/open?id=1nGYZb36ZlgyQ8IRuVjFhhUMn9x-RYeTlCT_3ynUbU_g
<https://goo.gl/forms/mN1uK6o4qnRllsr12>
 - ii) Guelaguetza 2:
https://drive.google.com/open?id=1nO7b9rCVXI3Phx5i_HZ1_S_ApFp_rCGzdamDQCICoc
<https://goo.gl/forms/1hQ1DIXfNtIKGa2U2>
 - b) Auto-positioning:
 - i) Guelaguetza 1:
https://drive.google.com/open?id=1LnXS73GS_1cfdk_dFypJMz3yiy31Y7aKpgwTaUEl2c8
<https://goo.gl/forms/KOUBqHGQKNxmkJiB2>
 - ii) Guelaguetza 2:
<https://drive.google.com/open?id=1jKg3xZhLPp7YXLH7BEPdnbCTXiMeldRpXP4byhnSyiM>
<https://goo.gl/forms/WXBDqj3R9ps34d0E3>
- 3) After watching **the two clips**, the participants will be asked to provide feedback about preferences and usability:
 - a) LINK TO POST-QUESTIONNAIRE: <https://goo.gl/forms/CHDH3aGCiEOkxPEU2>

FAREWELL AND THANKS to participants (1 min)

3. Questionnaires

Questionnaires will be provided to the participants using online forms, but is included below for reference.

Demographic questionnaire – Version 2 (Annex 46)

IPQ (Immersion) (Annex 44)

Post-questionnaire - Preferences (Position/Behaviour)

1. When reading subtitles in a 360° video, what system do you prefer?
 - a) Always visible
 - b) Fixed positioned
2. Please, explain why you prefer the above indicated option.
3. What do you think could be improved when placing the subtitles in the 360° videos, and how?
- 4a. How easy was it to find the always visible subtitles?
 - 1- Very difficult
 - 7- Very easy

- 4b. How easy was it to read the always visible subtitles?
1- Very difficult
7- Very easy
- 5a. How easy was it to find the fixed positioned subtitles?
1- Very difficult
7- Very easy
- 5b. How easy was it to read the fixed positioned subtitles?
1- Very difficult
7- Very easy
6. Did you find that the always visible subtitles were blocking important parts of the image?
a) Yes
b) No
7. Did you find that the fixed positioned subtitles were blocking important parts of the image?
a) Yes
b) No
8. Other comments.

Postcuestionario - Preferencias (Posición/Comportamiento)

1. ¿Qué sistema prefieres para leer los subtítulos en vídeos de 360º?
a) Subtítulos siempre visibles
b) Subtítulos colocados en posiciones fijas
2. Explica con tus propias palabras por qué prefieres la opción seleccionada en la pregunta anterior.
3. ¿Qué crees que se podría mejorar al colocar los subtítulos en vídeos de 360º y cómo lo mejorarías?
- 4a. ¿Te ha parecido fácil encontrar los subtítulos siempre visibles?
1- Muy difícil
7- Muy fácil
- 4b. ¿Te ha parecido fácil leer los subtítulos siempre visibles?
1- Muy difícil
7- Muy fácil
- 5a. ¿Te ha parecido fácil encontrar los subtítulos colocados en posiciones fijas?
1- Muy difícil
7- Muy fácil
- 5b. ¿Te ha parecido fácil leer los subtítulos colocados en posiciones fijas?
1- Muy difícil
7- Muy fácil
6. ¿Crees que los subtítulos siempre visibles obstruyen partes importantes de la imagen?
a) Sí
b) No
7. ¿Crees que los subtítulos colocados en posiciones fijas obstruyen partes importantes de la imagen?
a) Sí
b) No
8. Otros comentarios.

Post-questionnaire - Preferences (Speaker location)

1. When directions need to be indicated, what system do you prefer?
 - a) Arrow
 - b) Auto-positioning
2. Please, explain why you have chosen the above indicated option.
3. What do you think could be improved when indicating where the speakers are in 360º videos, and how?
4. How easy was it to find the speaker with the arrow system?
 - 1- Very difficult
 - 7- Very easy
5. How easy was it to find the speaker with the auto-positioning system?
 - 1- Very difficult
 - 7- Very easy
6. Did you find that the arrow distracted you from the action in the video?
 - a) Yes
 - b) No
7. Did you find that auto-positioning distracted you from the action in the video?
 - a) Yes
 - b) No
8. Other comments.

Postcuestionarios - Preferencias (Localización del hablante)

1. ¿Qué sistema prefieres para que te indiquen la localización del personaje que habla?
 - a) Flechas
 - b) Posicionamiento automático
2. Explica con tus propias palabras por qué prefieres la opción seleccionada en la pregunta anterior.
3. ¿Qué crees que se podría mejorar al indicar dónde está el personaje que habla en vídeos de 360º y cómo lo mejorarías?
4. ¿Te ha parecido fácil encontrar a la persona que habla con las flechas?
 - 1- Muy difícil
 - 7- Muy fácil
5. ¿Te ha parecido fácil encontrar a la persona que habla con el sistema de posicionamiento automático?
 - 1- Muy difícil
 - 7- Muy fácil
6. ¿Te ha parecido que las flechas te distraían de lo que estaba ocurriendo en el vídeo?
 - a) Sí
 - b) No
7. ¿Te ha parecido que el sistema de posicionamiento automático te distraía de lo que estaba ocurriendo en el vídeo?
 - a) Sí
 - b) No
8. Otros comentarios.

Main test

Methodology for subtitle experiment - Version 3

1. What will be tested? (summary)

The purpose of the experiment is to gather users' feedback (immersion, preferences and usability) about two different presentation modes for subtitles in cinematic virtual reality:

- 1) Part 1 - Position/Behaviour:
 - a) Fixed positioned: subtitles in three different fixed positions, evenly spaced each 120°.
 - b) Always visible: always displayed in front of the viewer, following viewer's head movements.
- 2) Part 2 - Speaker location identification (will be displayed in always visible mode):
 - a) Arrow (improved version)
 - b) Radar (improved version)

An analysis tool for tracking head movements (CVR Analyze, by Rothe et al.) will also be included in the experiments. We will later analyse the head movements (not eye movements, since no eye-tracking equipment is available for the test) to see if we can identify a movement pattern that could be linked to each specific variable.

2. Method

A within-subject design will be used to test the different presentation modes. Each participant will see 4 clips. Each clip will be randomly presented with a different variable (fixed positioned, always visible, arrow and radar). Participants will then be asked to reply to different questionnaires on presence (immersion), preferences and usability. The procedure will be explained in detail below.

Stimuli

Four clips have been chosen to test the different presentation modes. The participants will be shown the clips directly with an HMD (Samsung Gear VR with Samsung Galaxy S7), so they won't need to navigate through the ImAc Player. Therefore, a 6-second black screen with the text "The test is about to start for XXX" will be included. The stimuli will be shown without audio.

The reason to do the test without sound is that the emphasis of the test is accessibility, usability and immersion. First of all, we need to know if the subtitles actually help the viewers (hearing or deaf) to follow the story and navigate in the virtual world in an accessible and usable way. For example, we are testing different rendering modes that will imply different levels of freedom for the viewers and also different guiding to speaker mechanisms that can be more intuitive or usable for the viewers. Secondly, we need to determine if any of these implementations have an impact on immersion. If sound is used, we cannot control if the results regarding immersion for the hearing group are due to the sound or the implementation of subtitles. Also, sound can give some clues that would make the subtitling guiding mechanisms less relevant and then the results on preferences can be also less accurate. The ecological validity is here sacrificed in the hearing group in favour of controlling the external factors that can impact on the main research questions of this test: 1) which options are preferred because they are more accessible and usable?, and 2) which options lead to a more immersive experience?

- *Holy Land Series*
 - Episode 4
 - Episode 5
 - Test: Part 1 - Position/Behaviour
 - Creator: RYOT
 - Description: documentary, travel, Jerusalem.
 - Genre: documentary.
 - Original language: English
 - Duration: around 4/5 minutes per clip
 - Episode 4 - 04:13
 - Episode 5 - 04:58

- Features: voice-off most of the time. Different locations, landscapes. The presence of the hostess in some shots is not relevant for the narrative of the video.
- Link: <http://84.88.32.46/UAB-test4/>
- Access services needed:
 - SPA SDH - fixed positioned
 - SPA SDH - always visible

In this case, the only SDH specific characteristics are:

- 1) Indicate when the music is sounding (some instances: * Middle Eastern music *)
- 2) Indicate the narrator with the tag Narrator at the beginning.

Subtitles:

- Font type: Roboto
- Font size:
- Background box: no, better outlined text
- I, Philip
 - Test: Part 2 - Speaker location
 - Description: 23 years after Philip K. Dick's death, in 2005, David Hanson, a young engineer in robotics, revealed his first android with human form, "Phil". "I, Philip" immerses you in the memories of what could be the last love affair of the writer. But aren't these memories the fruit of the imagination of an android which learned, little by little, how to become a human?
 - Genre: sci-fi, drama
 - Original language: English
 - Duration: 12:26 (until the credits), to be split in two clips
 - Features: different speakers in different locations, narrator voice, first-person experience (the viewer sees the story through the eyes of Philip).
 - Link: <http://84.88.32.46/UAB-test4/>
 - Access services needed:
 - SPA SDH - arrow
 - SPA SDH - radar

Subtitles:

- Font type: Roboto
- Font size:
- Background box: no, better outlined text
- Speaker identification: colours (according to UNE norm)
- Off-speaker: italics, following UNE Standard.

IDENTIFICATION CODES FOR THE STIMULI

- A1: *Holy Land 1* - fixed positioned
- A2: *Holy Land 1* - always visible
- B1: *Holy Land 2* - fixed positioned
- B2: *Holy Land 2* - always visible
- C1: I, Philip 1 - arrow
- C2: I, Philip 1 - radar
- D1: I, Philip 2 - arrow
- D2: I, Philip 2 - radar

The four clips and four conditions are randomised using a Latin square, according to the table below. Each participant will see four clips, each with a different condition. The clip for the speaker location conditions (I, Philip) is always shown in chronological order (1-2), otherwise the participants would miss parts of the narrative.

LATIN SQUARE FOR ALL PARTICIPANTS

Each participant will follow a different order to avoid the order of presentation affecting the results.

Participant - Hearing	Participant - HoH	Behaviour	Behaviour	Speaker location	Speaker location
PH01	PHOH01	A1	B2	C1	D2
PH02	PHOH02	A2	B1	C2	D1
PH03	PHOH03	B1	A2	C1	D2
PH04	PHOH04	B2	A1	C2	D1
PH05	PHOH05	A1	B2	C1	D2
PH06	PHOH06	A2	B1	C2	D1
PH07	PHOH07	B1	A2	C1	D2
PH08	PHOH08	B2	A1	C2	D1
PH09	PHOH09	A1	B2	C1	D2
PH10	PHOH10	A2	B1	C2	D1
PH11	PHOH11	B1	A2	C1	D2
PH12	PHOH12	B2	A1	C2	D1
PH13	PHOH13	A1	B2	C1	D2
PH14	PHOH14	A2	B1	C2	D1
PH15	PHOH15	B1	A2	C1	D2
PH16	PHOH16	B2	A1	C2	D1
PH17	PHOH17	A1	B2	C1	D2
PH18	PHOH18	A2	B1	C2	D1
PH19	PHOH19	B1	A2	C1	D2
PH20	PHOH20	B2	A1	C2	D1

Procedure

PLANNING

<p>Introduction:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Welcome participants - Explain project and aim of the test - Consent forms and demographic questionnaires - Clip for acclimatation 	15 min
--	--------

Part 1 - Position: - Clip 1 - IPQ questionnaire - Clip 2 - IPQ questionnaire - Preference questionnaire	25 min
Part 2 - Speaker location - Clip 1 - IPQ questionnaire - Clip 2 - IPQ questionnaire - Preference questionnaire	25 min
Farewell and thanks	5 min
Buffer time	5 min
Total	80 min

Procedure

- **Experimental protocol:** users will be asked to watch different stimuli, and then report on the usability, preferences and immersion through digital questionnaires with closed and open questions.
- **Research tools:** digital questionnaires (Google Forms). The questionnaires will be digital in order to facilitate data processing.
- **Measures:** presence (immersion), preferences and usability.
- **Participants:** 20 hearing participants + 20 deaf/hard-of-hearing participants. Recruitment criteria:
 - Age: the age range should be balanced including:
 - Young adults 1: from 18 to 28
 - Young adults 2: from 29 to 39
 - Adults 1: from 40 to 50
 - Adults 2: from 51 to 61
 - Hearing capacity: the hearing capacity of participants should be balanced including:
 - 20 hearing participants
 - 20 hard-of-hearing participants: oralists, sign language speakers as their first language are excluded.
- **Duration:** approx. 80 minutes.
- **Language of the test:** Spanish.
- **Materials:** HMD, laptop and clips.
- **Facilitators:** one facilitator will be needed. The facilitator will be the leader (welcoming participants, explaining the project, explaining the test) and will assist the sessions (by providing the digital questionnaires and helping filling them in, providing technical assistance with the different devices, etc.).
- **Testing the methodology:** the experimental protocol below will be tested with 4/6 participants before the actual experiment. If the methodology needs to be improved based on this previous test, it will be updated accordingly (**and it was, this is version 3**).
 - Participants will be representative of the actual sample to test all possibilities, that is:
 - 1 young adult, hearing impaired, allegedly technologically-able (because of the age, we assume). If possible, include 2 young adults (one for each group specified before).
 - 1 young adult, non-hearing impaired, allegedly technologically-able (because of the age, we assume). If possible, include 2 young adults (one for each group specified before).

- 1 adult, hearing impaired, allegedly non-technologically-able (because of the age, we assume). If possible, include 2 adults (one for each group specified before).
- 1 adult, non-hearing impaired, allegedly non-technologically-able (because of the age, we assume). If possible, include 2 adults (one for each group specified before).

A first pilot was carried out:

First pilot: 2 deaf users + 6 hearing users.

Now, after preliminary feedback and modifications, a second pilot with less users will be carried out.

Also, questionnaires have been reviewed by a professional educational psychologist (psicopedagoga) specialized in teaching oral language to deaf people. She has provided valuable feedback about the wording of the questionnaires. She has provided suggestions to simplify questions and make them more accessible to hard-of-hearing users.

All changes will be tested in the second pilot.

Second pilot: 1 deaf user + 2 hearing users.

NOTE: A pilot will be done to test this final methodology with 2 hearing participants and 1 deaf participant. If changes need to be implemented, a VERSION 3 will be created (**and it was, this is version 3**).

Participant Pilot	Behaviour	Behaviour	Speaker location	Speaker location
PHPilot01	A1	B2	C1	D2
PHPilot02	A2	B1	C2	D1
PHOHPilot03	B1	A2	C1	D2

- All materials and ethical forms must be ready before the test.

INTRODUCTION (20 min)

<u>What?</u>	<u>How long?</u>
<p>Welcome the participants, who will individually attend the test.</p> <p>Please assign a participant code when they arrive, so that they can enter that code in each online questionnaire.</p>	1 min
<p>Explain the project (if unknown to the participant), the aim of the test and the procedure.</p>	5 min
<p>Provide the participant with the consent form for ethical clearance. The last version can be found here: https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1X5Nj9KxkpFVwvEuKfk6XVgz0VFUSzUOS</p>	3 min

<p>Provide the participant with the digital demographic questionnaire to be filled in (access to a computer/laptop will be needed):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ES: https://drive.google.com/open?id=1r1Ez_uBQ1Y5IfUVYqKTO5Dy2Y8sZ2PegooxST_Xn4po <p>https://goo.gl/forms/bhaSlaCm3PuhtTWE3</p>	6 min
<p>A clip for acclimatation to the HMD and the virtual reality experience will be shown to the participants. A clip from The New York Times app will be used.</p>	5 min

In the following sections, the different parts of the test will be explained, including tasks and measures.

PART 1 - Position (25 minutes)

- **Measures:**
 - Immersion: IPQ questionnaire
 - Preferences and usability: closed and open questions
- **Materials:**
 - Devices: the test will be performed with an HMD (Samsung Gear VR).
 - Player:
 - Link to the player: <http://84.88.32.46/UAB-test4/>
 - Stimuli: Two comparable clips (A, B) with 2 conditions (1, 2) for each presentation mode tested, so that participants can watch both conditions in different but comparable clips to avoid a learning effect. Stimuli explained above.
- **Room:** make sure the atmosphere is comfortable for the participants, with an adequate room arrangement.

Previous to task

The facilitator will explain the aim of this part: testing two different presentation modes to visualise the subtitles. There will be two presentation modes: subtitles in three different fixed positions and subtitles that follow head immediately. After watching the clips, they will be asked to answer a set of questions.

Procedure

- 1) The participants will be asked to watch the two randomised clips. The order is specified in the Latin Square provided above.
- 2) The participant will have to watch 2 clips (A, B) with the randomised variables: 1) fixed positioned and 2) always visible. After watching **each clip**, participants will have to reply to the IPQ (presence) questionnaire to gather feedback about immersion. IPQ version in English to be translated into Spanish (no official version available): https://drive.google.com/open?id=1c_10TqnXTaZnev0BNDM64dqRit2HkNR-tRiPhC23t9g
 - a) Always visible:
 - i) *Holy* *Land* 1:
https://drive.google.com/open?id=1c_10TqnXTaZnev0BNDM64dqRit2HkNR-tRiPhC23t9g
 - ii) *Holy* *Land* 2:
<https://drive.google.com/open?id=1j9oKSrtmHedAAsgfjdWO0EODnjdakw1e2zTdQgN0LnQ>
 - b) Fixed positioned:
 - i) *Holy Land 1:*
<https://drive.google.com/open?id=1QhfulnrKyZfVjD04atlwisfosAACELKhw160Q4e04al>

ii) *Holy Land 2*:

https://drive.google.com/open?id=1as6mNjzr25OzV4GINO3AUMaJnn61IuvHCy_YQ5YJtQA

- 3) After watching **the two clips**, the participants will be asked to provide feedback on their experience:
- a) LINK TO POST-QUESTIONNAIRE: https://drive.google.com/open?id=1-X8o48QLWHH76h2eK_IdhfjDPBks6U_IYqViJk3Y3FQ

PART 2 - Speaker location (25 minutes)

- **Measures:**
 - Immersion: IPQ questionnaire
 - Preferences and usability: close and open questions
- **Materials:**
 - Device: the test will be performed with an HMD.
 - Player:
 - Link to the player: <http://84.88.32.46/UAB-test4/>
 - Stimuli: Two comparable clips (C, D) with 2 conditions (1, 2) for each presentation mode tested, so that participants can watch both conditions in different but comparable clips to avoid a learning effect. Stimuli explained above.
- **Room**: make sure the atmosphere is comfortable for the participants, with an adequate room arrangement

Introduction

The facilitator will explain the aim of this part: testing two different presentation modes to guide the user to the speaker. There will be two presentation modes: an arrow integrated in the subtitle that will indicate where to look for the speaker and a radar that will also indicate where the speakers are located. After watching the clips, they will be asked to answer a set of questions.

Procedure

- 1) The participants will be asked to watch the two randomised clips. The order is specified in the Latin Square provided above.
- 2) The participant will have to watch 2 clips (C, D) with the randomised variables 1) arrow and 2) radar. After watching **each clip**, participants will have to the IPQ (presence) questionnaire to gather feedback about immersion.
 - a) Arrow:
 - i) I, Philip 1:
https://drive.google.com/open?id=1nGYZb36ZlgyQ8IRuVjFhhUMn9x-RYeTlct_3ynUbU_g
<https://goo.gl/forms/mN1uK6o4qnRllsr12>
 - ii) I, Philip 2:
https://drive.google.com/open?id=1nO7b9rCVXl3Phx5i_HZ1_S_ApFp_rCGzd_amDQCICoc
<https://goo.gl/forms/1hQ1DIXfNtIKGa2U2>
 - b) Radar:
 - i) I, Philip 1:
https://drive.google.com/open?id=1LnXS73GS_1cfdk_dFypJMz3yiy31Y7aKpgwTaUEl2c8
<https://goo.gl/forms/KOUBqHGQKNxmkJiB2>
 - ii) I, Philip 2:
<https://drive.google.com/open?id=1jKg3xZhLPP7YXLH7BEPdnbCTXiMeldRpXP4byhnSyiM>
<https://goo.gl/forms/WXBDqj3R9ps34d0E3>
- 3) After watching **the two clips**, the participants will be asked to provide feedback:

- a) LINK TO POST-QUESTIONNAIRE:
<https://drive.google.com/open?id=1m6KWWI1GBke8Yk9WPavnRHSVeee0k3uNGCCxr-M-Bk8>
<https://goo.gl/forms/CHDH3aGCiEOkxPEU2>

FAREWELL AND THANKS to participants (1 min)

3. Questionnaires

Questionnaires will be provided to the participants using online forms.

ANNEX 33. SUBTITLING INTERMEDIATE/PRE-PILOT 2 ACTIONS REPORTS (UAB)

The reports for both the pre-test and the main tests are included here.

Prepilot action

1. General information

- Partner responsible: UAB
- Place and date: 22nd to 28th November, 2018.
- Access service(s) discussed: subtitling.

2. Demographic questionnaire

- Number of end users: 8
- Demographics for users.
 1. Sex: female (3), male (5).
 2. Age: 26, 27 (2), 29 (2), 34, 54, 59.
 3. Main language: Spanish (5), Valencian (2), Catalan (1).
 4. Please indicate your level of studies: university (5), further education (2), primary education (1).
 5. I define myself as...: hearing person (6), deaf person (1), hearing impaired person (1).
 6. Age in which your disability began: n/a (6), from birth (1), 13-20 (1).
 7. What devices do you use on a daily basis? Multiple replies are possible: Mobile phone (8), TV (6), Laptop (5), PC (3), Tablet (1), Head Mounted Display (HMD) (1), game console (1).
 8. How often do you watch virtual reality content (for instance, 360° videos)?

	Never	Occasionally	At least once a month	At least once a week	Every day
In smartphone	6	2	0	0	0
On a tablet	8	0	0	0	0
On a PC	8	0	0	0	0
In smartphone plugged to HMD	7	1	0	0	0
In HMD	6	0	1	1	0

9. If you have never used virtual reality content such as 360° videos or only occasionally, please indicate why. Multiple answers are possible. Because I am not interested (2), Because I have not had the chance to use it. (4), Other reasons (3) [I did use virtual reality content before (2) and Because of lack of contents (1)].
10. Please state your level of agreement with the following statement: "I am interested in virtual reality content (such as 360° videos)." I strongly agree (3), I agree (2), Neither agree nor disagree (3), Disagree (0), Strongly disagree (0).
11. Do you own any device to access virtual reality content? Yes (3), No (5), I don't know or I don't want to reply (0).
12. If you replied "yes" to the previous question, please specify which device(s): Cardboard (2), PlayStation VR (2)
13. Do you like watching the following types of content on television or online?

	I like it very much	I like it	Neither like it nor dislike it	I don't like it	I don't like it at all
News	2	3	3	0	0
Fiction (series, films)	6	2	0	0	0
Talk shows	1	5	1	0	1
Documentaries	3	2	3	0	0

	I like it very much	I like it	Neither like it nor dislike it	I don't like it	I don't like it at all
Sports	0	3	1	2	2
Cartoons	0	4	1	1	2

14. When subtitling is available, do you activate it for the following type of content?

	Always	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
News	2	1	0	5
Fiction (series, films)	4	1	0	3
Talk shows	3	0	1	4
Documentaries	3	1	1	3
Sports	1	0	1	6
Cartoons	3	2	0	3

15. If it is available and you do not activate it, please select the reasons why. Because I don't need them (3), Because the interface is not accessible. (0), Because I don't want subtitling in all the content, only in certain types of content. (1), I always activate the subtitles (3), Others (1) [It depends on the language of the content and with whom I am watching it].
16. How many hours a day do you watch subtitled content? None (2), Less than 1 hour (1), 1-2 hours (4), 2-3 hours (0), 3-4 hours (0), 4 hours or more (1).
17. What do you use subtitles for? They help me understand (4), They are my only way to have access to the dialogue (1), I use them for language learning (1), I never use subtitles (2).

Summary: 5 male and 3 female users aged between 26 and 59 took part in the tests. 5 users indicated Spanish as mother tongue, 2 indicated Valencian and 1 indicated Catalan. 5 users had university studies, 2 had further education and 1 had primary education. 6 testers defined themselves as hearing, 1 as hearing-impaired and 1 as deaf. For one user the disability was from birth and for another user it began 13-20 years old.

The technical devices that were most often used on a daily basis were mobile phone (8), TV (6), laptop (5), PC (3), tablet (1), Head Mounted Display (HMD) (1), game console (1). Two users did watch VR content before and 6 of the users had never watched VR content before. The reasons for not having watched VR content before were: because they were not interested (2), because they had not had the chance to use it (4) or because of lack of contents (1). When directly asked if they were interested in VR content, some users (3) were strongly interested in VR content, some of them (3) were interested and some of them (2) were indifferent. Three participants owned a device to access VR content (Cardboard and PlayStation VR).

In terms of content preferences, the majority of the testers liked news, fiction, talk shows and documentaries, while some also liked sports, and cartoons. Users activated subtitles depending on their needs and the content. Three of them stated that they don't need subtitles, two of them stated that depending on the content (or language or company) and three of them stated that they always activate subtitles. Regarding how many hours a day they watch subtitled content, two participants indicated non, four participants 1-2 hours, and one participant indicated 4 hours or more.

When asked why they used subtitles, four indicated that they helped them understand, one participant indicated that they are my only way to have access to the dialogue; another participant said that they use them for language learning and two participants stated that they never use subtitles.

6. PART 1 - BEHAVIOUR

a) IPQ – Always visible (*Holy Land*)

Please indicate the number of replies that you have received for each rating.

IPQ Question	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8
Q1-PRES: In the computer generated world I had a sense of "being there". <i>1 not at all—7 very much</i>	2	6	3	3	6	5	6	7
Q2-SPA: Somehow I felt that the virtual world surrounded me. <i>1 fully disagree—7 fully agree</i>	3	5	4	4	6	5	6	7
Q3-SPA: I felt like I was just perceiving pictures. <i>1 fully disagree—7 fully agree</i>	3	2	2	3	2	6	2	1
Q4-SPA: I did not feel present in the virtual space. <i>1 did not feel—7 felt present</i>	2	6	2	3	6	2	6	6
Q5-SPA: I had a sense of acting in the virtual space, rather than operating something from outside. <i>1 fully disagree—7 fully agree</i>	1	6	2	5	6	5	7	7
Q6-SPA: I felt present in the virtual space. <i>1 fully disagree—7 fully agree</i>	2	6	2	5	6	3	6	7
Q7-INV: How aware were you of the real world surrounding while navigating in the virtual world? (i.e. sounds, room temperature, other people, etc.)? <i>1 extremely aware-moderately aware-7 not aware at all</i>	6	5	5	4	7	7	7	7
Q8-INV: I was not aware of my real environment. <i>1 fully disagree—7 fully agree</i>	6	5	5	4	7	7	7	6
Q9-INV: I still paid attention to the real environment. <i>1 fully disagree—7 fully agree</i>	6	6	2	6	7	7	7	6
Q10-INV: I was completely captivated by the virtual world. <i>1 fully disagree—7 fully agree</i>	2	7	4	6	6	6	7	7
Q11-REAL: How real did the virtual world seem to you? <i>1 completely real—7 not real at all</i>	1	6	4	5	3	4	6	6
Q12-REAL: How much did your experience in the virtual environment seem consistent with your real world experience ? <i>1 not consistent-moderately consistent-7 very consistent</i>	1	4	3	2	2	2	3	4

IPQ Question	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8
Q13-REAL: How real did the virtual world seem to you? <i>1 about as real as an imagined world—7 indistinguishable from the real world</i>	1	5	3	3	2	3	3	5
Q14-REAL: The virtual world seemed more realistic than the real world. <i>1 fully disagree—7 fully agree</i>	1	4	2	1	2	1	1	2

b) IPQ – Fixed positioned (Holy Land)

Please indicate the number of replies that you have received for each rating.

IPQ Question	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8
Q1-PRES: In the computer generated world I had a sense of "being there". <i>1 not at all—7 very much</i>	2	6	3	3	6	5	6	4
Q2-SPA: Somehow I felt that the virtual world surrounded me. <i>1 fully disagree—7 fully agree</i>	2	5	4	3	6	5	6	5
Q3-SPA: I felt like I was just perceiving pictures. <i>1 fully disagree—7 fully agree</i>	3	3	2	3	3	6	2	3
Q4-SPA: I did not feel present in the virtual space. <i>1 did not feel—7 felt present</i>	1	6	5	2	6	5	1	5
Q5-SPA: I had a sense of acting in the virtual space, rather than operating something from outside. <i>1 fully disagree—7 fully agree</i>	3	6	4	3	6	5	2	4
Q6-SPA: I felt present in the virtual space. <i>1 fully disagree—7 fully agree</i>	2	6	3	3	6	2	6	4
Q7-INV: How aware were you of the real world surrounding while navigating in the virtual world? (i.e. sounds, room temperature, other people, etc.)? <i>1 extremely aware-moderately aware-7 not aware at all</i>	6	3	4	4	7	2	3	5
Q8-INV: I was not aware of my real environment. <i>1 fully disagree—7 fully agree</i>	6	4	4	4	7	6	3	6
Q9-INV: I still paid attention to the real environment. <i>1 fully disagree—7 fully agree</i>	6	4	5	6	7	2	7	6
Q10-INV: I was completely captivated by the virtual world. <i>1 fully disagree—7 fully agree</i>	1	5	5	2	6	5	7	5
Q11-REAL: How real did the virtual world seem to you? <i>1 completely real—7 not real at all</i>	1	6	5	3	5	3	5	5
Q12-REAL: How much did your experience in the virtual environment seem consistent with your real world experience ? <i>1 not consistent-moderately consistent-7 very consistent</i>	1	4	3	2	4	1	3	4

IPQ Question	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8
Q13-REAL: How real did the virtual world seem to you? <i>1 about as real as an imagined world—7 indistinguishable from the real world</i>	1	5	3	2	4	3	5	5
Q14-REAL: The virtual world seemed more realistic than the real world. <i>1 fully disagree—7 fully agree</i>	1	4	3	1	2	2	1	2

c) Preferences & Usability (always vs fixed)

1. What system do you prefer to read subtitles in 360° videos?

a) Always visible	b) Fixed positioned
8	0

2. Please, explain why you prefer the above indicated option.

- PPilot02: It is much easier to be reading and seeing the landscapes or images with this mode, you concentrate more within the virtual world, you are more within the virtual world. You can move up and down without any problem to continue reading the subtitles.
- PPilot03: Because the subtitle follows me, I don't have to be looking for it, I always have it in front of me. And I see it right away. The other option (fixed positioned) it is not like that, the other option you have to be looking for it, you miss it. With the always visible, the subtitle is more accessible.
- PPilot01: Because you have to go looking for those that are in a fixed position and it already forces you to disconnect from the image.
- PPilot04: The subtitles in fixed positions didn't allow me to look around as freely as in the first video. I can't look too far up without seeing them. I also felt that in the video with subtitles in fixed positions I tended to put myself in one of the three fixed positions in order to be able to see the text always centred.
- PPilot05: Because you don't miss any information. The other subtitles make you turn your head quickly to find them and you may miss things.
- PPilot06: Sometimes the focus of attention distanced itself from where the subtitles are, being annoying and ignoring the subtitles.
- PPilot07: This way I can observe the environment of the virtual world at the same time that I can read the subtitles and not miss what is said (the text).
- PPilot08: With always visible subtitles I have been able to pay more attention to the virtual world.

3. What do you think could be improved, and how?

- PPilot02: The selected option is OK (always visible). The subtitles always visible are a little crooked, could be improved.
- PPilot03: I would need to put the subtitle in a way that I can see it but it doesn't cover the image. The subtitle should be lower, so that you can see the image. You can't focus on the subtitle and the image at the same time. I only pay attention to the subtitle.
- PPilot01: There's no need for always visible subtitles to be tilted when our head is tilted because it's quite unnatural and makes them more eye-catching.
- PPilot04: The best subtitles are always visible, but I felt that they were in an uncomfortable position, not very centered. I found myself on several occasions lowering my head to be able to read them, only to discover that the subtitles were also lowering.
- PPilot05: Let the subtitles always stay down even if you change the viewing angle of your head. That is to say, I started the video erect and the subtitles were well down in the field of vision. When I relaxed or leaned back, the subtitles covered the image or were half in the middle of the girl's face. Always visible subtitles have lag and don't read well (flickering).

- PPilot06: Be able to change the depth, font size and Y-axis (height). The subtitles should always be horizontal, just like the image and not tilt with the movement of the head.
- PPilot07: I would not improve anything.
- PPilot08: Could be improved, smaller and with more resolution (to avoid excessive displacements of the eyes), with translucent background behind ... to avoid dizziness.

4. Did you find it easy to find the always visible subtitles?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7- very easy
0	0	0	0	1	1	6

5. Did you find it easy to find the fixed positioned subtitles?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7- very easy
0	3	2	2	1	0	0

6. Did you find it easy to read the always visible subtitles?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7- very easy
0	2	1	0	1	3	1

7. Did you find it easy to read the fixed positioned subtitles?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7- very easy
0	2	1	0	2	2	7

8. Do you think always visible subtitles obstruct important parts of the image?

Yes (3)

No (5)

9. Do you think fixed positioned subtitles obstruct important parts of the image?

Yes (1)

No (7)

10. Other comments:

- PPilot02: When you turn quickly, the image becomes a bit black.
- PPilot03: There are images that I would like to see totally clear, if the subtitles were lower, you could see the image better.
- PPilot01: The subtitles of the second video were blurred, so you had to be more attentive to the reading. The yellow dot (the pointer) draws too much attention. When you turn your head, sometimes you see everything black and you have to wait for the image to load.
- PPilot04:
 - 1- Most of the elements that have caused the immersion to be lost are not due to the subtitles, but to the production of the video. I consider that low resolution, lack of depth (the video was 360°, but not in 3D), inconsistency in size scales from one shot to another, voice-over (reminding that you are watching a documentary and not a virtual world), slow buffering, etc. are more detrimental to the sensation of immersion than subtitles.
 - 2- The subtitles in fixed positions are more uncomfortable to read than the always visible ones, but I understand that some people can experience dizziness with the

always visible ones. Perhaps the best solution is to allow the user to configure the subtitles and choose which option is more comfortable.

- PPilot05: -
- PPilot06: -
- PPilot07: The quality of the video wasn't good enough to feel like you're totally in that place.
- PPilot08: -

7. PART 2 – GUIDING TO SPEAKER

a) IPQ – Arrow (American Guelaguetza)

Please indicate the number of replies that you have received for each rating.

IPQ Question	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8
Q1-PRES: In the computer generated world I had a sense of "being there". <i>1 not at all—7 very much</i>	2	5	2	3	5	5	6	7
Q2-SPA: Somehow I felt that the virtual world surrounded me. <i>1 fully disagree—7 fully agree</i>	3	6	2	3	5	5	5	6
Q3-SPA: I felt like I was just perceiving pictures. <i>1 fully disagree—7 fully agree</i>	2	2	3	2	5	4	2	1
Q4-SPA: I did not feel present in the virtual space. <i>1 did not feel—7 felt present</i>	2	5	2	3	4	2	6	7
Q5-SPA: I had a sense of acting in the virtual space, rather than operating something from outside. <i>1 fully disagree—7 fully agree</i>	3	5	2	3	4	4	6	2
Q6-SPA: I felt present in the virtual space. <i>1 fully disagree—7 fully agree</i>	3	6	2	3	5	1	6	6
Q7-INV: How aware were you of the real world surrounding while navigating in the virtual world? (i.e. sounds, room temperature, other people, etc.)? <i>1 extremely aware-moderately aware-7 not aware at all</i>	6	5	4	6	6	3	7	7
Q8-INV: I was not aware of my real environment. <i>1 fully disagree—7 fully agree</i>	6	4	4	6	6	6	7	7
Q9-INV: I still paid attention to the real environment. <i>1 fully disagree—7 fully agree</i>	7	5	5	6	7	4	7	7
Q10-INV: I was completely captivated by the virtual world. <i>1 fully disagree—7 fully agree</i>	2	6	4	6	5	4	5	7
Q11-REAL: How real did the virtual world seem to you? <i>1 completely real—7 not real at all</i>	2	4	3	3	3	3	6	6

IPQ Question	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8
Q12-REAL: How much did your experience in the virtual environment seem consistent with your real world experience? <i>1 not consistent-moderately consistent-7 very consistent</i>	1	3	2	2	2	3	2	6
Q13-REAL: How real did the virtual world seem to you? <i>1 about as real as an imagined world—7 indistinguishable from the real world</i>	1	4	2	2	2	3	5	5
Q14-REAL: The virtual world seemed more realistic than the real world. <i>1 fully disagree—7 fully agree</i>	1	3	2	1	1	2	1	5

b) IPQ – Auto-positioning (American Guelaguetza)

Please indicate the number of replies that you have received for each rating.

IPQ Question	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8
Q1-PRES: In the computer generated world I had a sense of "being there". <i>1 not at all—7 very much</i>	1	5	2	3	5	4	5	6
Q2-SPA: Somehow I felt that the virtual world surrounded me. <i>1 fully disagree—7 fully agree</i>	2	6	2	3	5	5	6	6
Q3-SPA: I felt like I was just perceiving pictures. <i>1 fully disagree—7 fully agree</i>	2	2	2	2	4	4	2	3
Q4-SPA: I did not feel present in the virtual space. <i>1 did not feel—7 felt present</i>	1	5	2	3	4	4	5	5
Q5-SPA: I had a sense of acting in the virtual space, rather than operating something from outside. <i>1 fully disagree—7 fully agree</i>	3	5	2	2	5	3	6	4
Q6-SPA: I felt present in the virtual space. <i>1 fully disagree—7 fully agree</i>	3	5	2	2	5	5	6	5
Q7-INV: How aware were you of the real world surrounding while navigating in the virtual world? (i.e. sounds, room temperature, other people, etc.)? <i>1 extremely aware-moderately aware-7 not aware at all</i>	6	4	4	4	6	7	7	6
Q8-INV: I was not aware of my real environment. <i>1 fully disagree—7 fully agree</i>	6	3	4	4	6	6	7	7
Q9-INV: I still paid attention to the real environment. <i>1 fully disagree—7 fully agree</i>	6	6	4	7	7	7	7	6
Q10-INV: I was completely captivated by the virtual world. <i>1 fully disagree—7 fully agree</i>	1	5	5	6	5	5	7	7
Q11-REAL: How real did the virtual world seem to you? <i>1 completely real—7 not real at all</i>	1	5	4	2	2	4	5	6

IPQ Question	P1	P2	P3	P4	P5	P6	P7	P8
Q12-REAL: How much did your experience in the virtual environment seem consistent with your real world experience ? <i>1 not consistent-moderately consistent-7 very consistent</i>	2	4	3	2	2	4	2	5
Q13-REAL: How real did the virtual world seem to you? <i>1 about as real as an imagined world—7 indistinguishable from the real world</i>	1	4	3	2	2	2	4	5
Q14-REAL: The virtual world seemed more realistic than the real world. <i>1 fully disagree—7 fully agree</i>	1	3	4	1	1	2	1	4

c) Preferences & Usability (arrow vs auto-positioning)

1. Which system do you prefer to indicate the location of the character speaking?

a) Arrow	b) Auto-positioning
7	1

2. Please, explain why you prefer the above indicated option.

- PPilot02: Because arrows are more intuitive than automatic positioning. Automatic positioning is confusing.
- PPilot03: With the arrows you have to look for the speaker and with auto-positioning is more comfortable, because you are already directly where the speaker is.
- PPilot01: Because I couldn't try the second option, it didn't work, so I can't compare. Also, in some moments of the video with automatic positioning the subtitles have stopped following me.
- PPilot04: I think it's harmful to move the camera independently from the natural movement of the viewer's head. One of the most frequent causes of dizziness caused by virtual reality is the feeling that the "world" moves on its own without the viewer moving his head.
- PPilot05: Autopositioning does not work.
- PPilot06: I can't fully answer this question because the automatic positioning system didn't work properly and was disorienting. It would be necessary to add a system that warns you that you are going to move, so that you know that it is going to start moving. The added value is recognized if you are in a chair where you cannot move.
- PPilot07: Because I don't like automatic positioning.
- PPilot08: Because with arrows it is more natural, with the automatic positioning you get very dizzy and it gives the feeling that there is no freedom to observe what you want.

3. What do you think could be improved, and how?

- PPilot02: I think automatic positioning doesn't work well, because it doesn't locate the person speaking. And in the case of arrows, it would be missing to indicate more quickly when the person speaking no longer appears in the field of vision. You have to be at a long distance for the arrow to appear, if it was at 30° it wouldn't come out, only if it was at 60°. I didn't see the speaker and the arrow didn't come out. You have to reduce the degrees to see the arrow. As soon as the speaker is not in the field of view, the arrow needs to show up, so you know where to turn.
- PPilot03: Autopositioning is fine.
- PPilot01: The arrows indicate it well, I wouldn't change that.
- PPilot04: The indication can be more precise if you also indicate where the interlocutor is on the vertical axis, not just the horizontal one.
- PPilot05: I liked that when there's an omniscient narrator, the subtitles follow you. The arrows are fine.

- PPilot06: the aesthetics of the arrows could be improved, giving a bit of transparency to be less invasive and more integrated into the overall image. The pointer of the controller has to be removed, or that it disappears after a while. Also add to the arrows "up and down" (if I look up, tell me that the speaker is below)
- PPilot07: Nothing.
- PPilot08: It could be improved, to point not only horizontally, but also vertically.

4. Did you find it easy to find the person who speaks with the arrows?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7- very easy
0	0	0	2	1	3	2

5. Did you find it easy to find the person who speaks with the autopoositioning?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7- very easy
3	0	1	0	0	1	3

6. Did the arrows seem to distract you from what was happening in the video?

Yes (1)

No (7)

7. Did the autopoositioning seem to distract you from what was happening in the video?

Yes (5)

No (3)

8. Other comments:

- PPilot02: The video quality is bad, it doesn't look good.
- PPilot03: When you're looking at something like that in virtual reality, the convenience of seeing everything at the same time is the best. It's more comfortable.
- PPilot01: In all the tests I come to the same conclusion: the quality of the image is decisive because in no case have I felt immersed in the virtual world.
- PPilot04: I think subtitles should be as unobtrusive as possible. In this sense, all subtitles anchored in one position (e.g. under the speaking character) limit the viewer's freedom to watch the video 360°. It might be the case that I want to look at another part of the scene, but I want to continue reading the subtitles. In addition, a deaf person may have the added difficulty of not knowing when someone is talking and may well be looking away for a while before discovering that an important dialogue is taking place behind his or her back.
- PPilot05: It seems to me that automatic positioning is distracting because I was waiting for it and it has never appeared.
- PPilot06: The automatic positioning was very abrupt and made me dizzy.
- PPilot07: The quality of the images is not so good as to feel that you are completely inside the virtual world.
- PPilot08: -

8. Conclusions

Always visible vs fixed positioned every 120°

All participants preferred the always visible subtitle rendering mode. According to the participants, the main reasons for having chosen this option is that with the always visible subtitles they had more freedom to look around without missing the subtitle content and the video scenes.

When asked about how easy it was to find the always visible subtitles based on a 7-point Likert scale (7 being the easiest and 1 being the most difficult), six participants (75%) replied 7, one (12.5%) replied 6, and one (12.5%) replied 5. When asked the same question about fixed positioned subtitles, three participants (37.5%) replied 2, two (25%) replied 3, two (25%) replied 4, and one (12.5%) replied 5. Then, according to these results, always visible subtitles (mean=5.78) were considered easier to find than fixed positioned subtitles (mean=3.12). This difference is statistically significant ($Z=-2.555$, $p=.011$, ties=0).

When asked about how easy it was to read always visible subtitles based on a 7-point Likert scale (7 being the easiest and 1 being the most difficult), three participants (37.5%) replied 6, two (25%) replied 2, one (12.5%) replied 7, one (12.5%) replied 5, and one (12.5%) replied 3. When asked the same question about fixed positioned subtitles (7 being the easiest and 1 being the most difficult), two (25%) replied 6, two (25%) replied 5, two (25%) replied 2, one (12.5%) replied 7, and one (12.5%) replied 3. Therefore, according to these results, always visible subtitles (mean=4.62) were considered slightly easier to read than fixed positioned subtitles (mean=4.5). However, this difference is not statistically significant ($Z=-.086$, $p=.031$, ties=1). When participants were asked whether subtitles were obstructing important parts of the image, five participants (62.5%) replied “no” and three (37.5%) replied “yes” for always visible subtitles, and seven participants (87.5%) replied “no” and one (12.5%) replied “yes” for fixed positioned subtitles.

The comparison of results from IPQ between the always visible and fixed positioned are as follows. For the presence scale, the test indicated that the difference between results is not statistically significant ($Z=-1.000$, $p=.317$, ties=7). For the spatial presence scale, the test indicated that the difference between results is not statistically significant ($Z=-.594$, $p=.553$, ties=1). For the realness scale, the test indicated that the difference between results is not statistically significant ($Z=-.318$, $p=.750$, ties=2). However, for the involvement scale, the test reported that the difference between results is statistically significant ($Z=-2.032$, $p=.042$, ties=1). This means that the fixed positioned subtitles had a negative impact on the involvement of participants. According to their comments in the open questions, this could be because they felt less free to explore the 360° scene and claimed to have missed parts of the subtitles content. Moreover, as reported above, participants found more difficult to find subtitles in this mode. Therefore, this extra effort could have caused a negative impact on involvement.

Arrow vs auto-positioning

Seven participants (87.5%) preferred the arrows over the auto-positioning method. Participants who favored the arrows argued that this guiding method is more intuitive and comfortable. Three participants suggested that the arrow guiding mechanism should also include indications for the vertical axis (up, down), not only for the horizontal one (left, right). The participant who preferred the auto-positioning considered that it was more comfortable, because there was no need to move or look for the speaker. One participant also argued that she would like to have a focus assistance technique not only for speakers, but also for the main action in the videos. For example, if a specific event is happening in a part of the video (even if no one is speaking), she considered that it would be useful to have an indicator to avoid getting lost.

When asked about how easy it was to find the speaker with the arrow guiding method, based on a 7-point Likert scale (7 being the easiest and 1 being the most difficult), three participants (37.5%) replied 6, two (25%) replied 7, two (25%) replied 4 and one (12.5%) replied 5. When asked the same question about the auto-positioning (7 being the easiest and 1 being the most difficult), three participants (37.5%) replied 7, three (37.5%) replied 1, one (12.5%) replied 6 and one (12.5%) replied 3. The different results in the latter could be because some participants reported feeling dizzy and disoriented with the auto-positioning system and others did not have the same experience. According to the results, arrows (mean=5.62) were considered more effective to find the speaker than auto-positioning (mean=4.12). However, the difference is not statistically significant ($Z=-1.476$, $p=.140$, ties=2). When asked whether the guiding methods distracted participants from the story, seven participants (87.5%) replied “no” and one (12.5%) replied “yes” for the arrows, and five participants (62.5%) replied “yes” and three (37.5%) replied “no” for the auto-positioning.

The comparison of results from IPQ between arrow and auto-positioning methods are as follows. For the spatial presence scale, the test indicated that the difference between results is not statistically significant ($Z=-.531$, $p=.595$, ties=2). For the involvement scale, the test indicated that the difference

between results is not statistically significant ($Z=-.431$, $p=.666$, ties=2). For the realness scale, the test indicated that the difference between results is not statistically significant ($Z=.000$, $p=1.000$, ties=1). However, for the presence scale, the test reported that the difference between results is statistically significant ($Z=-2.000$, $p=.046$, ties=4). This means that the auto-positioning method had a negative impact on the presence in the virtual world. According to comments in the open questions, some participants stated that auto-positioning caused dizziness, and had an impact on immersion, and resulted in confusion for some users.

Main test

1. General information

- Partner responsible: UAB
- Place and date: 13th March to 24th April 2019.
- Access service(s) discussed: *subtitling*.

2. Demographic questionnaire

- Number of end users: 40 (20 hard of hearing + 20 hearing)
- Demographics for users.
 1. Sex: female (26), male (14).
 2. Age: 18, 21 (2), 23 (2), 24 (2), 25, 26, 28, 29 (3), 30, 32, 33, 34, 35, 37 (4), 38, 43 (2), 44, 45 (2), 52, 53, 54 (2), 56, 58, 59 (2), 63, 65, 69, 70. (sd=14.8, mean=37.4, median=37)
 3. Main language: Spanish (31), Valencian (8), Catalan (3).
 4. Please indicate your level of studies: university (15), further education (10), secondary education (8), primary education (7).
 5. I define myself as...: hearing person (27), deaf person (7), hearing impaired person (6).
 6. Age in which your disability began: n/a (20), from birth (2), 0-4 (1), 5-12 (5), 13-20 (5), 21-40 (5), 41-60 (2).
 7. What devices do you use on a daily basis? Multiple replies are possible: mobile phone (38), TV (31), laptop (20), PC (13), tablet (11), game console (4), radio (1).
 8. How often do you watch virtual reality content (for instance, 360° videos)?

	Never	Occasionally	At least once a month	At least once a week	Every day
In smartphone	33	5	2	0	0
On a tablet	37	2	1	0	0
On a PC	33	7	0	0	0
In smartphone plugged to HMD	35	5	0	0	0
In HMD	35	2	2	1	0

9. If you have never used virtual reality content such as 360° videos or only occasionally, please indicate why. Multiple answers are possible. Because I am not interested (3), Because I have not had the chance to use it. (23), Because it is not accessible. (3), I did use virtual reality content before (10), Other reasons (4) [I don't have virtual reality glasses (1), I am not sure how to access virtual reality contents (1), I didn't know these contents existed (1) and I have an issue with my sight (1)].
10. Please state your level of agreement with the following statement: "I am interested in virtual reality content (such as 360° videos)." I strongly agree (14), I agree (14), Neither agree nor disagree (11), Disagree (1), Strongly disagree (0).
11. Do you own any device to access virtual reality content? Yes (5), No (35), I don't know, or I don't want to reply (0).
12. If you replied "yes" to the previous question, please specify which device(s): Plastic VR Headsets for smartphone (2), PlayStation VR (3)
13. Do you like watching the following types of content on television or online?

	I like it very much	I like it	Neither like it nor dislike it	I don't like it	I don't like it at all
News	12	17	9	2	0
Fiction (series, films)	25	11	4	0	0
Talk shows	1	13	12	4	10
Documentaries	18	15	5	1	1
Sports	8	9	11	6	6
Cartoons	4	14	13	0	9

14. When subtitling is available, do you activate it for the following type of content?

	Always	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
News	7	4	4	25
Fiction (series, films)	11	11	4	14
Talk shows	6	1	1	32
Documentaries	7	9	4	20
Sports	5	1	1	33
Cartoons	8	5	5	22

15. If it is available and you do not activate it, please select the reasons why. Because I don't need them (13), Because the interface is not accessible. (0), Because I don't want subtitling in all the content, only in certain types of content. (15), I always activate the subtitles (5), Others (6) [I don't use subtitles when they are bad quality (bad translation, wrong synchronization, etc.) (1), I don't use them because it is difficult to follow the images and the subtitles at the same time (1), Because they distract me (1), Because the subtitles do not correspond exactly to what is said in the dialogues or because they have not been properly translated (1), Because they are too fast for me to read (1), Because I don't know how to activate the subtitles (1), I only use subtitles when I don't have my earphones (1)].
16. How many hours a day do you watch subtitled content? None (13), Less than 1 hour (11), 1-2 hours (7), 2-3 hours (8), 3-4 hours (0), 4 hours or more (1).
17. What do you use subtitles for? They help me understand (22), They are my only way to have access to the dialogue (3), I use them for language learning (11), I never use subtitles (11), Other (2) [I use them when my baby is asleep (1), I don't use them because it is too difficult to follow the images and the subtitles at the same time (1)].

Summary: 14 male and 26 female users aged between 18 and 70 took part in the tests (sd=14.8, mean=37.4, median=37). 31 users indicated Spanish as main language, 8 indicated Valencian and 3 indicated Catalan. 15 users had university studies, 10 had further education, 8 had secondary education and 7 had primary education. 27 testers defined themselves as hearing, 6 as hearing-impaired and 7 as

deaf (although 20 were identified as hard-of-hearing and 20 as hearing [which can be confirmed by the replies of the following question “Age in which your disability began”, which 20 hard-of-hearing users replied accordingly], but this question was subjective; some people with hearing aids considered themselves as hearing). For 2 users the disability started from birth, for 1 user it began from 0 to 4 years old, for 5 users from 5 to 12 years old, for 5 users from 13 to 20 years old, for 5 users from 21 to 40 years old and for 2 users from 41 to 60 years old.

The technical devices that were most often used on a daily basis were mobile phone (38), TV (31), laptop (20), PC (13), tablet (11), game console (4) and radio (1). Most users (33) had never watched VR content before. And some of them have watched it occasionally, only one of them reported to watch VR content once a week. The reasons behind this behaviour were: because they are not interested (3), because they have not had the chance to use it (23), because it is not accessible (3) or other reasons (4). 10 participants did use virtual reality content before.

When directly asked if they were interested in VR content, some users (14) were strongly interested in VR content, some of them (14) were interested, some of them (11) were indifferent and one of them was not interested. Five participants owned a device to access VR content (Plastic VR Headsets for smartphone and PlayStation VR).

In terms of content preferences, the majority of the testers liked news (29), fiction (36), and documentaries (33), while some also liked talk shows (14), sports (17) and cartoons (18). Users activated subtitles depending on their needs and the content. 13 of them stated that they don't need subtitles, 15 of them stated that depending on the content and 5 of them stated that they always activate subtitles. Regarding how many hours a day they watch subtitled content, 13 participants indicated none, 11 participants indicated less than 1 hour, 7 participants replied 1-2 hours, 8 participants replied 2-3 hours, and one participant indicated 4 hours or more.

When asked why they used subtitles, 22 indicated that they helped them understand, 3 participants indicated that they are their only way to have access to the dialogue, 11 participants said that they use them for language learning and 11 participants stated that they never use subtitles.

9. PART 1 - BEHAVIOUR

d) IPQ – Always visible (*Holy Land*)¹³

¹³ Q1-PRES: In the computer generated world I had a sense of "being there".

1 not at all—7 very much

Q2-SPA: Somehow I felt that the virtual world surrounded me.

1 fully disagree—7 fully agree

Q3-SPA: I felt like I was just perceiving pictures.

1 fully disagree—7 fully agree

Q4-SPA: I did not feel present in the virtual space.

1 did not feel—7 felt present

Q5-SPA: I had a sense of acting in the virtual space, rather than operating something from outside.

1 fully disagree—7 fully agree

Q6-SPA: I felt present in the virtual space.

1 fully disagree—7 fully agree

Q7-INV: How aware were you of the real world surrounding while navigating in the virtual world? (i.e. sounds, room temperature, other people, etc.)?

1 extremely aware-moderately aware-7 not aware at all

Q8-INV: I was not aware of my real environment.

1 fully disagree—7 fully agree

Q9-INV: I still paid attention to the real environment.

1 fully disagree—7 fully agree

Q10-INV: I was completely captivated by the virtual world.

1 fully disagree—7 fully agree

Q11-REAL: How real did the virtual world seem to you?

1 completely real—7 not real at all

Q12-REAL: How much did your experience in the virtual environment seem consistent with your real world experience ?

1 not consistent-moderately consistent-7 very consistent

Participant code	Q1-PRES	Q2-SPA	Q3-SPA	Q4-SPA	Q5-SPA	Q6-SPA	Q7-INV	Q8-INV	Q9-INV	Q10-INV	Q11-REAL	Q12-REAL	Q13-REAL	Q14-REAL
PHOH01	6	5	1	4	4	5	1	1	7	5	3	4	1	1
PHOH04	6	7	1	7	7	7	2	2	1	6	1	6	1	4
PHOH05	2	2	7	2	2	2	7	7	1	2	7	1	2	1
PHOH08	6	5	4	6	6	6	1	1	1	5	3	4	3	4
PHOH09	5	5	2	5	5	5	5	5	6	6	3	3	5	3
PHOH12	5	5	2	2	3	2	3	3	1	3	4	2	2	2
PH01	7	7	2	6	6	6	4	6	2	6	2	6	6	4
PH04	4	5	3	2	2	2	2	2	3	3	4	3	3	2
PH05	5	6	1	5	2	2	5	6	1	5	1	5	5	3
PH08	7	7	1	7	7	7	6	6	1	7	2	6	4	4
PH12	6	6	1	7	5	6	1	1	6	6	2	5	5	1
PH13	6	6	2	6	6	6	2	1	6	6	2	5	4	4
PHOH13	7	7	1	7	7	7	7	7	1	7	2	4	4	1
PHOH16	4	2	1	1	6	1	7	7	1	7	1	6	7	1
PHOH17	7	7	1	7	7	7	7	7	1	7	1	6	7	1
PHOH20	6	6	2	7	6	6	4	4	6	6	2	5	4	1
PHOH02	7	7	3	7	7	7	7	7	1	7	1	7	7	7
PHOH03	4	4	4	3	4	3	4	3	3	4	3	4	3	3
PHOH06	7	7	1	7	7	7	6	6	1	7	1	6	7	5
PHOH07	5	6	1	5	5	5	4	4	6	6	4	1	2	1
PHOH10	7	7	7	7	7	7	4	1	1	4	1	7	7	1

Q13-REAL: How real did the virtual world seem to you?
1 about as real as an imagined world—7 indistinguishable from the real world
Q14-REAL: The virtual world seemed more realistic than the real world.
1 fully disagree—7 fully agree

Participant code	Q1-PRES	Q2-SPA	Q3-SPA	Q4-SPA	Q5-SPA	Q6-SPA	Q7-INV	Q8-INV	Q9-INV	Q10-INV	Q11-REAL	Q12-REAL	Q13-REAL	Q14-REAL
PHOH11	5	3	6	3	2	3	1	1	1	7	5	1	2	2
PH02	6	6	2	6	6	6	5	4	6	2	4	5	2	2
PH03	6	6	1	5	6	6	3	3	5	5	2	3	5	2
PH06	5	6	1	5	4	6	6	6	2	6	4	1	2	1
PH07	7	6	1	6	6	6	7	7	1	7	1	6	6	4
PH10	6	6	3	2	7	7	4	4	1	7	1	5	5	3
PH11	5	6	1	5	5	5	4	4	5	4	4	2	4	1
PH14	6	6	2	5	6	6	6	6	2	6	2	4	4	3
PHOH14	6	7	1	7	7	7	7	7	1	7	1	7	7	5
PHOH15	7	7	1	7	7	7	7	7	1	7	1	7	7	4
PH15	6	7	1	6	6	6	6	6	2	6	6	4	4	2
PHOH18	7	7	1	7	6	7	7	7	1	7	1	4	4	3
PHOH19	7	7	1	7	7	7	1	1	7	7	4	4	2	1
PH16	7	7	2	4	4	5	7	7	2	6	2	3	4	2
PH17	6	6	2	7	6	6	5	6	2	6	2	5	4	2
PH20	5	6	2	3	3	5	3	3	5	4	3	5	5	2
PH21	5	5	2	5	5	5	4	4	4	5	2	5	2	5
PH18	2	5	6	3	3	3	5	6	2	4	5	2	3	1
PH19	5	5	2	5	2	4	3	2	2	5	3	2	2	1

e) IPQ – Fixed positioned (*Holy Land*)

Participant code	Q1-PRES	Q2-SPA	Q3-SPA	Q4-SPA	Q5-SPA	Q6-SPA	Q7-INV	Q8-INV	Q9-INV	Q10-INV	Q11-REAL	Q12-REAL	Q13-REAL	Q14-REAL
PHOH01	5	7	5	6	6	6	1	1	7	7	3	4	2	1

Participant code	Q1-PRES	Q2-SPA	Q3-SPA	Q4-SPA	Q5-SPA	Q6-SPA	Q7-INV	Q8-INV	Q9-INV	Q10-INV	Q11-REAL	Q12-REAL	Q13-REAL	Q14-REAL
PHOH04	7	7	1	7	7	7	7	7	1	7	1	7	1	4
PHOH05	7	7	4	5	6	6	7	7	1	6	1	6	7	5
PHOH08	2	3	7	2	3	4	1	1	4	4	4	5	5	3
PHOH09	5	5	2	2	5	6	5	5	6	6	1	2	2	5
PHOH12	2	3	2	3	3	3	5	6	3	2	3	1	2	2
PH01	5	5	2	6	6	5	5	2	2	6	1	6	5	3
PH04	4	4	3	4	3	3	4	4	4	4	5	4	3	2
PH05	6	5	1	5	2	2	6	6	1	6	2	5	5	3
PH08	4	3	5	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	5	4	3	2
PH12	5	3	1	2	1	1	1	1	6	4	5	4	4	1
PH13	4	6	1	6	4	5	5	2	5	5	2	4	4	5
PHOH13	7	7	5	4	5	5	5	5	1	7	2	5	5	1
PHOH16	2	2	1	1	7	7	7	7	1	7	1	7	7	5
PHOH17	7	7	1	7	7	7	7	7	1	7	1	6	7	1
PHOH20	6	6	2	6	4	4	4	4	4	6	5	2	4	1
PHOH02	7	7	3	7	7	7	7	7	1	7	1	7	7	7
PHOH03	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	3	6	4	3	4	3	3
PHOH06	7	7	1	7	7	7	7	7	1	7	1	6	7	5
PHOH07	5	4	1	6	4	6	3	3	4	5	3	1	5	1
PHOH10	7	7	1	7	7	7	1	1	7	1	1	7	7	1
PHOH11	5	7	3	3	6	6	3	3	4	5	4	2	4	3
PH02	6	6	4	5	6	6	3	4	6	5	4	5	4	3
PH03	7	7	1	7	7	7	3	3	5	6	1	6	5	2
PH06	5	5	2	3	3	3	6	6	3	5	5	2	2	1
PH07	6	7	1	5	5	5	7	7	1	7	2	5	7	4

Participant code	Q1-PRES	Q2-SPA	Q3-SPA	Q4-SPA	Q5-SPA	Q6-SPA	Q7-INV	Q8-INV	Q9-INV	Q10-INV	Q11-REAL	Q12-REAL	Q13-REAL	Q14-REAL
PH10	4	5	4	5	5	4	6	7	2	6	3	4	4	3
PH11	3	4	2	3	3	2	1	1	5	3	5	1	2	1
PH14	5	5	2	5	5	5	3	4	2	5	5	4	4	4
PHOH14	5	7	1	6	6	6	7	7	1	6	1	6	6	5
PHOH15	6	7	1	7	7	7	7	7	1	7	1	7	7	4
PH15	4	5	1	4	4	4	7	4	5	3	4	3	4	2
PHOH18	2	2	2	3	3	5	7	7	1	7	3	4	5	4
PHOH19	7	7	1	7	7	7	1	1	7	7	1	1	4	1
PH16	2	6	6	2	2	3	4	4	2	3	4	2	3	2
PH17	6	6	2	6	6	6	5	5	3	4	2	5	3	1
PH20	3	3	3	4	3	3	3	3	5	3	4	5	5	3
PH21	7	6	3	6	6	6	6	6	2	6	1	5	2	6
PH18	2	2	4	2	1	2	6	5	6	2	4	3	2	1
PH19	5	6	2	5	4	5	2	2	3	6	3	2	2	1

f) Preferences & Usability (always vs fixed)

1. What system do you prefer to read subtitles in 360° videos?

a) Always visible	b) Fixed positioned
33	7

2. Please, explain why you prefer the above-indicated option.

- PHOH01 (always visible) When watching the video, it is preferable to have the always visible subtitles because of the movement, to be able to look at all parts of the video.
- PHOH02 (always visible) Because I could read the subtitles while I moved, and I didn't get lost like with the others [fixed positioned].
- PHOH03 (fixed positioned) Because of the ease of viewing the content.
- PHOH04 (always visible) In the first video even if I moved I didn't have to look for the subtitle.
- PHOH05 (fixed positioned) Because the other subtitles [always visible] I couldn't read them well, I had to stop and look down to read them.
- PHOH06 (always visible) Actually I think that the two options seemed almost the same and both were good. Because I have enough time to read what it says in the fixed positioned subtitles and then see the images as well.
- PHOH07 (always visible) You can see the whole environment and read the subtitles at the same time.

- PHOH08 (always visible) Because you could visualize them in any degree in which you turned or moved your head.
- PHOH09 (always visible) I liked the always visible subtitles. You don't miss the images at all.
- PHOH10 (always visible) I prefer that option more because when you move gives you more freedom to act.
- PHOH11 (fixed positioned) Because you see the subtitle and you read it. The other [always visible] you don't have enough time to read it because it moves a lot.
- PHOH12 (always visible) It is much more comfortable that they are always visible.
- PH01 (always visible) They are much easier to follow, you don't have to look for them and miss interesting parts of video.
- PH02 (always visible) I find it easier to observe the video environment with this type of subtitles.
- PH03 (always visible) I find them easier to read and you can pay attention to what happens in the video and read at the same time.
- PH04 (always visible) Because you pay more attention to what you're seeing; if you want to turn around, the subtitles follow you. With the fixed positioned subtitles, you have to turn your neck a lot to read the subtitle that is placed farthest from you.
- PH05 (always visible) Because you don't miss any visual information when searching for subtitles.
- PH06 (always visible) Because with the always visible subtitles I have time to read the subtitle and see the landscape at the same time. I have plenty of time to see the images. With the ones placed in three fixed positions, I have to look for them and I didn't have time to see the landscapes.
- PH07 (always visible) Because I have more time to read it and I can enjoy the images.
- PH08 (always visible) The video was smoother, and the images were continuous, and I didn't have to stop to read. I had more freedom of movement.
- PH10 (always visible) Because I don't miss any detail of the image and at the same time I can read the subtitles well.
- PH11 (always visible) The always visible subtitles do not distract me that much because I don't have to be searching for the subtitles.
- PH12 (always visible) Because always visible subtitles give you more freedom to explore the virtual world. With the other option, it feels like you may miss part of the subtitles.
- PH13 (always visible) Because the subtitles are more integrated in the video.
- PH14 (always visible) Because these are more comfortable to read and follow the images of the video.
- PHOH13 (always visible) Since the subtitles are following the images, they help to understand the images better.
- PHOH14 (always visible) They make me carefree and have more field of vision and make the immersion experience more effective.
- PHOH15 (fixed positioned) Because it is more comfortable to read them.
- PH15 (always visible) Because they allowed me to see more of the full image and move around the video.
- PHOH16 (always visible) Because it allows me to look and read.
- PHOH17 (fixed positioned) Because with the fixed positioned subtitles I didn't notice the difference of being in one place or another and it seemed that where I looked they were always there, and I could read them well. And the ones that move I had to stop to read them because otherwise I would get dizzy.
- PHOH18 (always visible) Because with the subtitles placed in three fixed positions there is too much distance between them, so it doesn't give enough time to observe the whole scenario with calm without missing the subtitles, since you want to be able to read at the same time that you observe the scenario.
- PHOH19 (always visible) Because I can see the image simultaneously.
- PHOH20 (always visible) The subtitles are easier to read, because they are always in front of you.

- PH16 (always visible) Because the subtitles let me enjoy the content while I read.
 - PH17 (always visible) With these subtitles, you make sure no details are missed, neither subtitles nor images. You can look wherever you want and whenever you want, and you do not miss information.
 - PH18 (always visible) With fixed positioned subtitles, I feel like I'm just looking in one of the three directions that they can be read. Less freedom to move through virtual space.
 - PH19 (fixed positioned) It is easier to get used to the three positions, you also avoid the "dizziness".
 - PH20 (always visible) The always visible subtitles allow you to explore more of the video itself. With the subtitles placed in three fixed positions, I had to find where they were, so I could follow the content of the video, which limited the experience.
 - PH21 (fixed positioned) The subtitles in movement caused me a slight dizziness and, in some moments, became the most relevant part of the scene. The downside of having them in fixed positions is that sometimes reference is made to an element that is not in the field of vision, but that also invites to take more advantage of the virtual reality experience and move more through the virtual space.
3. What do you think could be improved, and how?
- PHOH01 (always visible) The subtitles should not move so much in order to read them more comfortably.
 - PHOH02 (always visible) Nothing.
 - PHOH03 (fixed positioned) I would improve the contrast of the subtitles.
 - PHOH04 (always visible) Nothing.
 - PHOH05 (fixed positioned) Like in the first video. [The first video was the one with fixed positioned subtitles]
 - PHOH06 (always visible) The subtitles and the image need to be clearer, they should be seen in a clearer way and less blurred (a little bit).
 - PHOH07 (always visible) That when you move the subtitles do not move irregularly and you do not have to stop to read.
 - PHOH08 (always visible) Of course and I would recommend it. I think they should be placed close to the area or the element to which the subtitle (in this case the monument) refers, in order to identify the monument or object and see at the same time that the subtitles are read.
 - PHOH09 (always visible) All good.
 - PHOH10 (always visible) Improve the distortion of the subtitles.
 - PHOH11 (fixed positioned) It is fine.
 - PHOH12 (always visible) Yes.
 - PH01 (always visible) They are fine.
 - PH02 (always visible) Nothing.
 - PH03 (always visible) Nothing.
 - PH04 (always visible) I would put the subtitles in a place that would not disturb the image, for example, I would put them in the sky so that you can see the whole image.
 - PH05 (always visible) Nothing.
 - PH06 (always visible) They're fine.
 - PH07 (always visible) They're fine.
 - PH08 (always visible) That the subtitles are not so centred, but a little more at the bottom of the video.
 - PH10 (always visible) All good.
 - PH11 (always visible) Subtitles always visible are fine.
 - PH12 (always visible) In the always visible subtitles, instead of being so centred on the screen, I'd like it better if they were a little lower.
 - PH13 (always visible) No.
 - PH14 (always visible) In some parts of the video, the subtitles were too fast and not very spaced, and I didn't have time to read and understand.

- PHOH13 (always visible) Sometimes subtitles went too fast, they could be a bit slower. The images of people sometimes look too close to me and that is to some extent unpleasant because it does not help you to perceive the environment in which you are.
- PHOH14 (always visible) I do not know how to improve it.
- PHOH15 (fixed positioned) The subtitle on the right is far behind.
- PH15 (always visible) Investigating the reactions and impressions of the "spectators".
- PHOH16 (always visible) It is fine
- PHOH17 (fixed positioned) They were fine.
- PHOH18 (always visible) The one that I have chosen (always visible) seems to me quite comfortable and I would not know how to improve it because they are already quite well. For the ones placed in three fixed positions, I would say to shorten the distance between the 3 subtitles and that thus one can see everything without losing any subtitle.
- PHOH19 (always visible) Yes. I think if the letters weren't so striking in color, I'd see the images better.
- PHOH20 (always visible) Place the subtitles lower, so that it does not remove the sensation of reality.
- PH16 (always visible) A better rendering of subtitles (load faster).
- PH17 (always visible) Try not to cover too much the main image.
- PH18 (always visible) Option to configure the subtitles always visible (size, color, distance from the center of the screen...)
- PH19 (fixed positioned) Despite the movement, they could be a little more static or be clearer compared to the others. I should not focus so much on them as on the image.
- PH20 (always visible) When I moved to explore the video, there were times, especially in the most abrupt movements, that the subtitles shook a little. That made reading a little more difficult.
- PH21 (fixed positioned) Indication of where to look if they are fixed. If they are in movement, less spaced between lines so that they do not occupy so much screen.

4. Did you find it easy to find the always visible subtitles?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7- very easy
1	0	3	2	1	1	32

5. Did you find it easy to find the fixed positioned subtitles?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7- very easy
1	5	6	13	7	2	6

6. Did you find it easy to read the always visible subtitles?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7- very easy
2	4	0	0	6	7	21

7. Did you find it easy to read the fixed positioned subtitles?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7- very easy
1	6	5	6	3	9	10

8. Do you think always visible subtitles obstruct important parts of the image?

1- yes very much	2	3	4	5	6	7- not at all

2	4	0	4	4	8	18
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9. Do you think fixed positioned subtitles obstruct important parts of the image?

1- yes very much	2	3	4	5	6	7- not at all
0	0	2	6	5	9	18

10. Do you think that always visible subtitles distract you from the video?

1- yes very much	2	3	4	5	6	7- not at all
4	2	1	2	4	12	15

11. Do you think that fixed positioned subtitles distract you from the video?

1- yes very much	2	3	4	5	6	7- not at all
8	9	5	2	4	2	10

10. Other comments:

- PHOH01 (always visible) No.
- PHOH02 (always visible) No.
- PHOH03 (fixed positioned) No.
- PHOH04 (always visible) No.
- PHOH05 (fixed positioned) Comment from the researcher: the participant has a vision problem and does not just see the always visible. She said that she didn't like the three positions, but because she couldn't read the always visible ones well, she preferred the others.
- PHOH06 (always visible) Comment: it is necessary that the video and subtitles are seen with more resolution.
- PHOH07 (always visible) No.
- PHOH08 (always visible) Remember that people who watch videos with subtitles are used to divide their attention at the same time in two parts, one in the video or what you want to show, and another in the reading of the subtitles, so it would be advisable and facilitate the vision to be placed near the monument you want to highlight and visualize with really legible colors, since white in some very clear landscapes could not be read correctly.
- PHOH09 (always visible) No.
- PHOH10 (always visible) No.
- PHOH11 (fixed positioned) Research comment: participant has a mild cognitive disability.
- PHOH12 (always visible) No.
- PH01 (always visible) No.
- PH02 (always visible) No.
- PH03 (always visible) In the two videos, just before the subtitles appeared, the image was stopped for a second or less and has gone like this all the time each time a subtitle was going to appear.
- PH04 (always visible) No.
- PH05 (always visible) No.
- PH06 (always visible) It would be good to do the test with a swivel chair or standing to be able to see the whole video.
- PH07 (always visible) No.
- PH08 (always visible) No.
- PH10 (always visible) The video with the subtitles placed in three fixed positions took longer to load when turning the head.
- PH11 (always visible) No.

- PH12 (always visible) No.
- PH13 (always visible) No.
- PH14 (always visible) No.
- PHOH13 (always visible) The first video was not appropriate for this type of tests because it was politicized.
- PHOH14 (always visible) Perhaps there could be an option to reduce the size of the letters in certain videos of landscapes, trips, etc.
- PHOH15 (fixed positioned) No.
- PH15 (always visible) No.
- PHOH16 (always visible) No.
- PHOH17 (fixed positioned) No.
- PHOH18 (always visible) No.
- PHOH19 (always visible) No.
- PHOH20 (always visible) Leave the always visible subtitles fixed [in the field of view, not moving] so as not to feel dizzy, as in any documentary or film.
- PH16 (always visible) I prefer the always visible ones because the fixed ones make you miss a lot of information.
- PH17 (always visible) No.
- PH18 (always visible) No.
- PH19 (fixed positioned) When moving the subtitles always visible you have a feeling of dizziness.
- PH20 (always visible) No.
- PH21 (always visible) No.

11. PART 2 – GUIDING TO SPEAKER

d) IPQ – Arrow (I, Philip)¹⁴

¹⁴ Q1-PRES: In the computer generated world I had a sense of "being there".

1 not at all—7 very much

Q2-SPA: Somehow I felt that the virtual world surrounded me.

1 fully disagree—7 fully agree

Q3-SPA: I felt like I was just perceiving pictures.

1 fully disagree—7 fully agree

Q4-SPA: I did not feel present in the virtual space.

1 did not feel—7 felt present

Q5-SPA: I had a sense of acting in the virtual space, rather than operating something from outside.

1 fully disagree—7 fully agree

Q6-SPA: I felt present in the virtual space.

1 fully disagree—7 fully agree

Q7-INV: How aware were you of the real world surrounding while navigating in the virtual world? (i.e. sounds, room temperature, other people, etc.)?

1 extremely aware-moderately aware-7 not aware at all

Q8-INV: I was not aware of my real environment.

1 fully disagree—7 fully agree

Q9-INV: I still paid attention to the real environment.

1 fully disagree—7 fully agree

Q10-INV: I was completely captivated by the virtual world.

1 fully disagree—7 fully agree

Q11-REAL: How real did the virtual world seem to you?

1 completely real—7 not real at all

Q12-REAL: How much did your experience in the virtual environment seem consistent with your real world experience ?

1 not consistent-moderately consistent-7 very consistent

Q13-REAL: How real did the virtual world seem to you?

1 about as real as an imagined world—7 indistinguishable from the real world

Q14-REAL: The virtual world seemed more realistic than the real world.

1 fully disagree—7 fully agree

Participant code	Q1-PRES	Q2-SPA	Q3-SPA	Q4-SPA	Q5-SPA	Q6-SPA	Q7-INV	Q8-INV	Q9-INV	Q10-INV	Q11-REAL	Q12-REAL	Q13-REAL	Q14-REAL
PHOH01	4	6	1	6	4	5	1	1	7	4	4	1	3	1
PHOH03	4	5	3	4	5	4	5	5	5	4	5	4	4	3
PHOH05	7	7	1	7	7	7	7	7	1	7	1	7	7	5
PHOH07	6	6	1	6	5	5	4	4	3	6	5	1	2	1
PHOH09	5	5	3	5	5	5	5	4	5	5	2	3	5	5
PHOH11	5	6	1	4	3	4	7	7	1	6	3	1	4	1
PH01	7	7	1	6	7	6	5	5	2	6	2	6	6	5
PH03	7	7	1	7	7	7	6	6	2	6	1	5	5	3
PH05	5	5	2	4	3	4	6	6	2	5	2	4	5	3
PH07	5	3	1	5	5	5	7	7	1	7	1	6	7	4
PH11	5	5	2	5	2	5	5	5	6	4	4	2	3	1
PH13	4	4	2	5	4	4	2	2	2	5	3	4	4	3
PHOH13	7	7	1	7	7	7	7	7	1	7	3	4	4	1
PHOH15	7	7	1	7	7	7	7	7	1	7	1	7	7	4
PH15	6	7	1	6	6	6	7	7	1	7	2	5	6	2
PHOH17	7	7	1	6	7	7	6	6	6	7	1	5	7	1
PHOH19	7	7	1	7	7	7	5	1	6	7	4	2	2	1
PHOH02	7	7	2	1	7	2	1	1	7	2	1	7	7	7
PHOH04	7	7	1	7	7	7	7	7	1	7	1	4	1	4
PHOH06	7	7	1	7	7	7	7	7	1	7	1	7	7	5
PHOH08	4	3	4	3	4	4	1	1	4	4	4	4	3	3
PHOH10	7	7	1	7	7	7	1	1	1	7	1	7	7	1
PHOH12	3	3	4	4	3	3	3	3	5	3	3	3	5	3
PH02	6	6	2	6	6	6	2	2	4	6	3	5	4	3
PH04	4	4	3	5	5	5	6	6	2	6	4	4	4	1
PH06	5	5	1	4	6	6	6	6	2	6	4	2	2	1
PH08	6	5	3	6	6	6	4	4	2	6	2	6	5	6
PH10	6	6	3	6	3	6	6	6	1	7	2	6	5	4
PH12	5	5	1	5	6	6	1	1	2	4	5	3	5	1
PH14	6	6	2	6	5	5	7	7	2	6	2	4	4	3
PHOH14	7	7	1	7	7	7	7	7	1	7	1	7	6	4
PHOH16	1	1	1	1	5	1	7	7	1	7	7	1	1	1
PHOH18	7	7	1	6	7	7	7	7	1	7	2	3	5	3

Participant code	Q1-PRES	Q2-SPA	Q3-SPA	Q4-SPA	Q5-SPA	Q6-SPA	Q7-INV	Q8-INV	Q9-INV	Q10-INV	Q11-REAL	Q12-REAL	Q13-REAL	Q14-REAL
PHOH20	4	4	2	4	4	4	2	2	6	4	4	2	2	1
PH16	5	5	3	4	3	4	3	3	5	4	3	4	4	2
PH18	7	6	4	6	2	5	6	2	1	6	3	2	3	1
PH20	6	6	2	6	6	6	3	3	5	6	3	5	5	3
PH17	6	6	2	6	6	6	5	6	2	6	3	5	5	2
PH19	6	6	2	5	3	5	5	4	2	6	3	2	3	1
PH21	4	4	1	4	4	4	5	5	2	5	4	4	4	3

e) IPQ – Radar (I, Philip)

Participant code	Q1-PRES	Q2-SPA	Q3-SPA	Q4-SPA	Q5-SPA	Q6-SPA	Q7-INV	Q8-INV	Q9-INV	Q10-INV	Q11-REAL	Q12-REAL	Q13-REAL	Q14-REAL
PHOH01	6	4	1	5	4	5	1	1	7	4	4	1	7	4
PHOH03	4	4	3	4	4	4	4	4	5	4	4	5	4	4
PHOH05	7	7	1	7	7	7	7	7	1	7	1	7	7	4
PHOH07	6	6	1	6	6	6	4	4	4	6	4	2	2	1
PHOH09	4	4	4	5	5	5	5	2	6	5	2	3	3	5
PHOH11	7	7	1	6	6	7	7	7	1	7	3	1	4	1
PH01	7	6	2	6	6	6	2	2	2	7	2	6	6	6
PH03	6	6	1	6	6	6	6	6	3	6	1	2	6	2
PH05	6	4	2	5	3	5	6	6	2	6	2	6	5	3
PH07	4	6	1	4	4	4	7	7	1	6	1	4	4	4
PH11	5	6	2	5	5	5	4	4	5	4	4	2	4	1
PH13	2	3	4	2	3	3	3	4	3	3	5	2	3	2
PHOH13	7	7	2	7	7	7	7	7	1	7	4	4	4	1
PHOH15	7	7	1	7	7	7	7	7	1	7	1	7	7	4
PH15	3	3	3	2	6	3	5	5	2	4	4	2	3	1
PHOH17	6	7	1	7	6	7	6	6	1	7	1	6	7	1
PHOH19	7	7	1	7	7	7	4	1	7	7	4	2	2	1
PHOH02	5	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	7	2	1	7	7	7
PHOH04	7	7	1	7	7	7	7	7	1	7	1	1	1	5
PHOH06	7	7	1	7	7	7	7	7	1	7	1	6	7	5
PHOH08	3	3	5	5	4	4	2	3	4	4	5	4	4	4

Participant code	Q1-PRES	Q2-SPA	Q3-SPA	Q4-SPA	Q5-SPA	Q6-SPA	Q7-INV	Q8-INV	Q9-INV	Q10-INV	Q11-REAL	Q12-REAL	Q13-REAL	Q14-REAL
PHOH10	7	7	1	7	7	7	1	1	1	7	1	7	7	1
PHOH12	3	4	2	3	3	4	3	3	3	3	3	2	2	2
PH02	5	5	1	6	6	6	2	2	5	4	3	5	5	4
PH04	2	2	3	2	2	2	5	5	4	3	5	2	2	1
PH06	6	6	1	6	6	6	7	7	2	7	2	4	4	2
PH08	7	6	1	6	6	6	6	6	2	6	2	7	5	3
PH10	6	6	3	6	4	5	2	3	1	7	3	4	5	3
PH12	5	3	1	3	5	5	1	1	5	2	4	2	7	1
PH14	6	6	2	6	6	6	3	2	2	6	3	4	5	4
PHOH14	6	6	1	6	4	4	7	7	1	4	3	7	4	4
PHOH16	1	1	1	5	5	1	7	7	1	7	7	1	1	1
PHOH18	5	7	1	6	6	6	7	7	1	7	3	3	6	4
PHOH20	4	3	1	3	4	3	3	2	6	2	4	2	2	1
PH16	5	5	2	5	6	6	3	3	4	2	5	3	5	1
PH18	6	5	4	5	5	5	6	6	2	7	3	3	4	1
PH20	6	6	2	6	6	6	3	3	5	6	2	5	5	3
PH17	6	6	2	6	6	6	5	5	3	6	3	5	3	2
PH19	5	5	2	6	2	4	3	3	2	5	6	2	2	1
PH21	4	5	2	4	4	4	3	3	4	4	5	4	4	2

f) Preferences & Usability (arrow vs auto-positioning)

1. Which system do you prefer to indicate the location of the character speaking?

a) Arrow	b) Radar
33	7

2. Please, explain why you prefer the above indicated option.

- PHOH01 (arrows) Because it is more direct.
- PHOH02 (arrows) Because arrows told me more directly where the person was and with the radar I had to find out.
- PHOH03 (arrows) I choose arrows for the ease of understanding conversation.
- PHOH04 (radar) Because it indicated to me where the person was, with the arrows I needed to look for the person.
- PHOH05 (arrows) With the color identification is enough. The arrows I did not see them, I realized because it was changing color.
- PHOH06 (radar) I prefer no guiding mechanism, I don't need it.
- PHOH07 (radar) I liked it more because it gives more spatial information.
- PHOH08 (radar) Because the subtitles appeared in the person speaking.
- PHOH09 (arrows) It is easier to identify the person speaking.
- PHOH10 (arrows) Because it is more intuitive.

- PHOH11 (radar) Because it better indicates where the person is and gives you more information.
- PHOH12 (arrows) It is easier to orient yourself to know where the speaker is.
- PH01 (arrows) It is less invasive.
- PH02 (arrows) I liked the arrows more but if the radar were centred in the field of vision I would also like it.
- PH03 (arrows) The arrows are more intuitive and comfortable to see, with the radar you deviate too much attention and is not very comfortable to watch.
- PH04 (arrows) Because with the arrows it is easier, more intuitive. Radar is hard to understand.
- PH05 (arrows) I have not seen the arrows, only the colors, enough. The radar has made me miss video information.
- PH06 (arrows) Because I don't have to look so carefully at the radar and the arrows directly tell you where to look.
- PH07 (arrows) Because you notice the arrows more, the radar goes more unnoticed. The arrows attract more attention because of the colors and the radar has neutral colors and you pay less attention to it.
- PH08 (arrows) Because it is easier to recognize than the radar, better indicated.
- PH10 (arrows) Both seem like good options to me.
- PH11 (arrows) The radar is clearer, but it takes a little while to understand it.
- PH12 (arrows) The system of arrows seems to me more intuitive.
- PH13 (arrows) Because it's easier to follow them without thinking.
- PH14 (arrows) Because it helps me see the person who is talking, and it seems more real. I haven't understood how the radar works, so it hasn't worked for me.
- PHOH13 (arrows) I haven't noticed the arrows, but I don't need any indication because you can see where the speakers are.
- PHOH14 (arrows) It is more intuitive and especially in dialogues of several people the different colors is what helps the most.
- PHOH15 (arrows) Because it's easier to follow.
- PH15 (arrows) With the arrows, maybe because of the video, I had the feeling that I didn't need them too much. In fact, there were times when I didn't see them because I was looking at the right place. Radar took me out of the story (broke immersion). I found it unintuitive and difficult to follow. Also, when the background of the image is white, it disappears from the image and is difficult to follow.
- PHOH16 (radar) Because it called my attention and made me focus on the person who was speaking.
- PHOH17 (arrows) I didn't get to see the arrows or realize them, but I didn't need them because I could see who was talking. I didn't like the radar because I could not see it properly in my field of view.
- PHOH18 (arrows) Because it is much more comfortable since it appears at the end of each subtitle, also with the radar you could not focus on the image well because it was very far from the scene and distracted you from what was happening.
- PHOH19 (arrows) With the radar I lost vision.
- PHOH20 (arrows) Because it is more visible and easier to understand.
- PH16 (arrows) Because it is more intuitive, and the radar took me longer to understand.
- PH17 (arrows) It indicates in a simple way where to look to follow the dialogue without disturbing the subtitles and without missing anything of the story or the images. The radar seemed to me almost impossible to understand.
- PH18 (arrows) The system is less precise, but more comfortable.
- PH19 (arrows) Because of the action of the images it is often understood where you have to look. Arrows can be useful at times, but continuous radar seems unnecessary to me.
- PH20 (radar) I find more precise and gives more information than the arrow. It also indicates who is speaking even though you are looking at that person. It also reminds me of other systems I'm used to that are used in video games.

- PH21 (arrows) I found it hard to understand how the radar worked; the arrows were clearer and more intuitive.

3. What do you think could be improved, and how?

- PHOH01 (arrows) It's fine.
- PHOH02 (arrows) Nothing.
- PHOH03 (arrows) I really liked the arrows.
- PHOH04 (radar) Nothing.
- PHOH05 (arrows) Nothing.
- PHOH06 (radar) I would prefer that nothing appears.
- PHOH07 (radar) I would place the radar in the center and down, not on a side.
- PHOH08 (radar) First, place them in an area that is easily visible without having to split the character in two or just see the forehead because it covers the rest of the face.
- PHOH09 (arrows) It's fine.
- PHOH10 (arrows) Nothing.
- PHOH11 (radar) It's fine.
- PHOH12 (arrows) Nothing.
- PH01 (arrows) Nothing.
- PH02 (arrows) Nothing.
- PH03 (arrows) Nothing.
- PH04 (arrows) It would be good to mark the person speaking with a dot or something visual to make it clearer who is speaking.
- PH05 (arrows) The colors have worked very well, in fact I did not need to see the arrows. The more stimuli you have to pay attention to, the more complicated.
- PH06 (arrows) It's fine.
- PH07 (arrows) It's fine.
- PH08 (arrows) It's fine.
- PH10 (arrows) All right.
- PH11 (arrows) Both the radar and the arrows are pretty effective as they are.
- PH12 (arrows) In the system of arrows, according to the distance at which the speaker is, there could be more or less arrows, that is, if it is very far 3 arrows, if it is close, 1 arrow.
- PH13 (arrows) Nothing.
- PH14 (arrows) All right.
- PHOH13 (arrows) Subtitles should be slower to make reading easier.
- PHOH14 (arrows) I don't know
- PHOH15 (arrows) It was fine.
- PH15 (arrows) Maybe keep the arrow a little longer on screen.
- PHOH16 (radar) It's fine.
- PHOH17 (arrows) It's fine.
- PHOH18 (arrows) I would place the arrows at the top of the subtitle because it gives you time to turn and look at the person speaking, because being at the end of the subtitle you don't realize who is speaking until you read the entire subtitle and you can finally see the arrows.
- PHOH19 (arrows) The arrows are fine.
- PHOH20 (arrows) Place the subtitles lower to avoid covering the image.
- PH16 (arrows) I would make arrows more visible.
- PH17 (arrows) It's fine.
- PH18 (arrows) That the arrows are not limited to a single dimension, that also indicate the position of the speaker as it is up or down.
- PH19 (arrows) Arrows seem like a good choice to me.
- PH20 (radar) I think that, although I liked the radar more, it is more complex and difficult to understand, so a brief explanation or introduction would be nice.
- PH21 (arrows) With the arrows, only characters were indicated on both sides, not up and down, that is, if for example you raised your eyes, it was not indicated that the person spoke from below.

4. Did you find it easy to find the person who speaks with the arrows?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7- very easy
0	1	1	3	4	9	22

5. Did you find it easy to find the person who speaks with the radar?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7- very easy
6	8	6	7	1	1	11

6. Did the arrows seem to distract you from what was happening in the video?

1- yes very much	2	3	4	5	6	7- not at all
0	0	2	1	1	10	26

7. Did the radar seem to distract you from what was happening in the video?

1- yes very much	2	3	4	5	6	7- not at all
9	8	3	4	3	0	13

8. Other comments:

- PHOH01 (arrows) No.
- PHOH02 (arrows) No.
- PHOH03 (arrows) No.
- PHOH04 (radar) No.
- PHOH05 (arrows) Comment from the researcher: the participant does not see the arrows and does not see the radar, she is guided by the colors.
- PHOH06 (radar) Comment: both the video and the subtitles need to be seen with more resolution.
- PHOH07 (radar) No.
- PHOH08 (radar) When you want to watch virtual reality content, you supposedly choose it because you expect to be able to appreciate the whole environment without missing any detail. In a part of the video, while the interview with the journalist and the creators of the robot was taking place and when they were doing the conference with the university students, when a person spoke, I had to turn my head from one side to the other in order to be able to identify the character who spoke, losing sight of the rest of the characters. This is something that made a little dizzy and it would be preferable to be able to visualize everything in the same shot, without losing contact with the rest of the characters.
- PHOH09 (arrows) No.
- PHOH10 (arrows) No.
- PHOH11 (radar) Research Comment: Participant has a mild cognitive disability.
- PHOH12 (arrows) No.
- PH01 (arrows) The radar requires more time of adaptation [learning] than the arrows.
- PH02 (arrows) No.
- PH03 (arrows) They are fine.
- PH04 (arrows) The first part of the video has not been very interesting to me, the second part a little more.
- PH05 (arrows) No.
- PH06 (arrows) I really didn't need the directions because you could see who was talking easily in the video.
- PH07 (arrows) No.
- PH08 (arrows) No.
- PH10 (arrows) No.
- PH11 (arrows) No.

- PH12 (arrows) No.
- PH13 (arrows) No.
- PH14 (arrows) No.
- PHOH13 (arrows) Images of people are too big and too close, we should improve the scale, make it more realistic.
- PHOH14 (arrows) With the radar, I was paying attention to the radar and trying to figure out how it worked. It has been difficult for me to understand it.
- PHOH15 (arrows) No.
- PH15 (arrows) No.
- PHOH16 (radar) Nothing.
- PHOH17 (arrows) No.
- PHOH18 (arrows) No.
- PHOH19 (arrows) Paying attention to subtitle and the radar at the same time is too much.
- PHOH20 (arrows) No.
- PH16 (arrows) The radar is not very intuitive, once you get it you can get a little bit into the story but until then you've lost a lot of content figuring out what the radar is and how to understand it. The arrows seem to me to be more appropriate although I think it depends on what kind of person I wouldn't find them at first.
- PH17 (arrows) No.
- PH18 (arrows) No.
- PH19 (arrows) For me there is no doubt: arrows disrupt less.
- PH20 (radar) No.
- PH21 (arrows) No.

Conclusions

Always visible vs fixed positioned

33 participants preferred the always visible subtitles and 7 participants preferred the fixed positioned subtitles. According to the participants, the main reasons for having chosen this option is that with the always visible subtitles they had more freedom to look around without missing the subtitle content and the video scenes and in a more comfortable way. The reasons of the users who chose the fixed positioned subtitles are because they can be read better than the always visible subtitles and they avoided the dizziness effect. Some users suggested to make the “always visible” more static, because the movement sometimes is distracting and hinders readability. It would be great to come with a technical solution to improve that.

When asked about **how easy it was to find the always visible subtitles** based on a 7-point Likert scale (7 being the easiest and 1 being the most difficult), 32 participants (80%) replied 7, one (2.5%) replied 6, one (2.5%) replied 5, two (5%) replied 4, 3 (7.5%) replied 3 and one (2.5%) replied 1. When asked the same question **about fixed positioned subtitles**, six participants (15%) replied 7, two (5%) replied 6, seven (17.5%) replied 5, 13 (32,5%) replied 4, six (15%) replied 3, five (12.5%) replied 2 and one (2.5%) replied 1. Then, according to these results, **always visible subtitles** (mean=6.01) **were considered easier to find than fixed positioned subtitles** (mean=3.92). This difference is **statistically significant** ($Z=-3.986$, $p=.000$, ties=5).

When asked about **how easy it was to read always visible subtitles** based on a 7-point Likert scale (7 being the easiest and 1 being the most difficult), 21 participants (52.5%) replied 7, seven participants (17.5%) replied 6, six participants (15%) replied 5, four participants (10%) replied 2 and two (5%) participants replied 1. When asked the same question **about fixed positioned subtitles** (7 being the easiest and 1 being the most difficult), ten (25%) replied 7, nine (22.5%) replied 6, three (7.5%) replied 5, six (15%) replied 4, five (12.5%) replied 3, six (15%) replied 2, and one (2.5%) replied 1. Therefore, according to these results, **always visible subtitles** (mean=5.19) **were considered easier to read than fixed positioned subtitles** (mean=4.30). This difference is **statistically significant** ($Z=-1.919$, $p=.055$, ties=9) (even if the threshold is set at .05, the result can be considered statistically relevant but with a slightly higher margin of error).

When participants were asked whether **always visible subtitles were obstructing important parts of the image** based on a 7-point Likert scale (7 being not at all and 1 being yes very much), 18 participants (45%) replied 7, eight participants (20%) replied 6, four participants (10%) replied 5, four participants (10%) replied 4, four (10%) participants replied 2 and two participants (5%) replied 1. When asked the same question **about fixed positioned subtitles** (7 being the easiest and 1 being the most difficult), 18 participants (45%) replied 7, nine participants (22.5%) replied 6, five participants (12.5%) replied 5, six participants (15%) replied 4 and two (5%) participants replied 3. Therefore, according to these results, **fixed positioned subtitles** (mean=5.71) **were considered slightly less obstructive than always visible subtitles** (mean=4.97). This difference is **not statistically significant** ($Z=-1,123$, $p=.261$, ties=23)

When participants were asked whether **subtitles were distracting them from what was happening in the video**, based on a 7-point Likert scale (7 being not at all and 1 being yes very much), 15 participants (37.5%) replied 7, 12 participants (30%) replied 6, four participants (10%) replied 5, two participants (5%) replied 4, one participant (2.5%) replied 3, two participants (5%) replied 2 and four participants (10%) replied 1. When asked the same question **about fixed positioned subtitles** (7 being not at all and 1 being yes very much), ten (25%) replied 7, two participants (5%) replied 6, four participants (10%) replied 5, two participants (5%) replied 4, five participants (12.5%) replied 3, nine participants (22.5%) replied 2 and eight participants (20%) replied 1. Therefore, according to these results, **always visible subtitles** (mean=4.76) **were considered less distracting than fixed positioned subtitles** (mean=3.00). This difference is **statistically significant** ($Z=-2,696$, $p=.007$, ties=13).

The **comparison of results from IPQ between the always visible and fixed positioned** are as follows. For the spatial scale, the test indicated that the difference between results is not statistically significant ($Z=-1.791$, $p=.073$, ties=7). For the involvement scale, the test reported that the difference between results is not statistically significant ($Z=-1.229$, $p=.219$, ties=8). For the realness scale, the test indicated that the difference between results is not statistically significant ($Z=-.064$, $p=.949$, ties=14). However, for the **presence scale**, the test indicated that the difference between results is **statistically significant** ($Z=-2.694$, $p=.007$, ties=17). This means that the **fixed positioned subtitles had a negative impact on the presence** of participants. According to their comments in the open questions, this could be because they felt less free to explore the 360° scene and claimed to have missed parts of the subtitles content. Moreover, as reported above, participants found more difficult to find and read subtitles in this mode, and also considered them more distracting. Therefore, this extra effort could have caused a negative impact on presence.

Arrow vs radar

33 participants preferred arrows and **7 participants preferred the radar** as guiding methods. Participants who favored the arrows argued that this guiding method is more intuitive, direct, comfortable, less invasive and distracting. Also, many participants did not understand how the radar worked. Participants who preferred the radar argued that it gives more accurate and spatial information. A participant suggested that a short explanation about how the radar works before using it could improve the user reception of this mechanism. Also, a couple of participants suggested to move the radar to the center (maybe right below the subtitle) instead of being on the right side in order to improve usability. Some participants (4) stated that they would prefer no guiding mechanisms and that with the color identification was enough.

When asked about **how easy it was to find the speaker with the arrow guiding method**, based on a 7-point Likert scale (7 being the easiest and 1 being the most difficult), 22 participants (55%) replied 7, nine participants (22,5%) replied 6, four (10%) replied 5, three participants (7.5%) replied 4, one (2.5%) replied 3 and one (2.5%) replied 2. When asked **the same question about the radar** (7 being the easiest and 1 being the most difficult), 11 participants (27.5%) replied 7, one (2.5%) replied 6, one (2.5%) replied 6, one participant (2.5%) replied 4, seven participants (17.5%) replied 4, six participants (15%) replied 3, eight participants (20%) replied 2 and six participants (15%) replied 1. According to the results, **arrows** (mean=5.95) **were considered easier to find the speaker than the radar** (mean=3.20). The difference is **statistically significant** ($Z=-4.166$, $p=.000$, ties=10).

When asked **whether the arrows methods distracted participants from what was happening in the video**, based on a 7-point Likert scale (7 being not at all and 1 being yes very much), 26 participants (65%) replied 7, 10 participants (25%) replied 6, one participant (2.5%) replied 5, one participant (2.5%)

replied 4, and two participants (5%) replied 3. When asked **the same question about the radar** (7 being not at all and 1 being yes very much), 13 participants (32.5%) replied 7, three participants (7.5%) replied 5, four participants (10%) replied 4, three participants (7.5%) replied 3, eight participants (20%) replied 2 and nine participants (22.5%) replied 1. According to the results, **arrows** (mean=6.31) **were considered less distracting than the radar** (mean=3.04). The difference is statistically significant ($Z=4.125$, $p=.000$, ties=12).

The comparison of results from **IPQ between arrow and radar methods** are as follows. For the presence scale, the test indicated that the difference between results is not statistically significant ($Z= -1.852$, $p=.064$, ties=21). For the spatial scale, the test indicated that the difference between results is not statistically significant ($Z=-1.000$, $p=.317$, ties=13). For the realness scale, the test indicated that the difference between results is not statistically significant ($Z=-1.430$, $p=.153$, ties=7). However, for the involvement scale, the test indicated that the difference between the results is statistically significant ($Z=-2.138$, $p=.033$, ties=12). This means that the **radar had a negative impact on the involvement of participants**. According to their comments in the open questions, this could be because some participants did not understand how the radar worked and the arrow was considered more intuitive and direct.

ANNEX 34. METHODOLOGY FOR EASY-TO-READ PRE-PILOT 2 ACTIONS (UAB) (I)

What will be tested? (summary)

The purpose of the experiment is to gather users' feedback on different presentation modes for E2R in cinematic virtual reality. The test will have two main tasks:

a) **Task 1.** Display of subtitles in Easy to Read and SDH to measure immersion and preferences. Opera content.

1. When?

- Spanish Pilot: from 15st March to 1st June.

2. Who?

- Spanish pilot: UAB

3. Stimuli

- Opera Romeo and Juliet
 - Test: Task 1.
 - Description: musical.
 - Genre: musical
 - Original language: French.
 - Duration: 4min15seg
 - Link to player:
 - <http://84.88.32.46/UAB-test5b/>
 - Access services needed:
 - SP E2R with arrows (as guiding mechanisms)
 - SP SDH with arrows (as guiding mechanisms)

IDENTIFICATION CODES FOR THE STIMULI

The letters refer to the subtitles and the numbers to the variables:

360º video: Opera 1. Subtitles in Spanish: SDH + easy-to-read

- A1 (4min15sec) . Opera Part 1 - SDH Subtitles.
- B1 (4min15sec). Opera Part 2 - Easy-to-Read Subtitles.
- B2 (4min15sec). Opera Part 1 - Easy-to-Read Subtitles.
- A2 (4min15sec). Opera Part 2 - SDH Subtitles

[NOTE 1]: Counter-balance conditions:

Even participants: watch video A1 & B1 (only one time)

Odd participants: watch video A2 & B2 (only one time)

[NOTE 2] Variable SDH vs E2R (both types of subtitles have been validated in E2R)

[NOTA 3] Font selection ROBOTO

4. Methodology: overview

- **Aim:** gather data from users about their experience with different presentation modes, replying to questions regarding immersion and preferences.
- **Experimental protocol:** users will be asked to watch different stimuli, and then report on the preferences and immersion through digital questionnaires with closed and open questions.
- **Research tools:** digital questionnaires (Google Forms). The questionnaires will be digital in order to facilitate data processing. The questionnaires will be translated into Spanish. IPQ translations will be provided by UAB. They are available under the sub-folder SURVEYS.
- **Measures:** preferences and presence (immersion).
- **Participants:** Recruitment will be done via associations/organisation and/or at partners' discretion.
 - 8 participants in total. 2 participants with hearing loss.
- **Duration:** approx. 45 minutes.

- **Language of the test:** Spanish.
- **Materials:** HMD, computer and clips.
- **Facilitators:** two facilitators will be needed. One facilitator will be the leader (welcoming participants, explaining the project, explaining the test) and another facilitator will assist the sessions (by providing the digital questionnaires and helping filling them in, providing technical assistance with the different devices, etc.).
- **Test accessibility:** adequate measures must be taken by tests organisers (UAB) so that communication with persons with hearing loss is fluent.
- **Reporting:** results will be included in a report created by each partner. This will be done exporting data from the Google Form. A template will be provided. All feedback must be translated into English by the partners responsible for the pilots (UAB).
- **Testing the methodology:** the methodology will be tested prior to the test.
- Please make sure that you have all materials and ethical forms ready before the test.

5. Methodology: experimental protocol

PLANNING

Introduction	15 min
Task 1	20 min
Farewell and thanks	5 min
Buffer time	5 min
Total	45 min

WORKFLOW

LATIN SQUARE FOR ALL PARTICIPANTS (if more than 10, repeat from the beginning).

Each participant will follow a different order to avoid the order of presentation affecting the results.

Participant	TASK 1	TASK 1
UAB1	A2	B2
UAB2	A1	B1
UAB3	A2	B2
UAB4	A1	B1
UAB5	A2	B2
UAB6	A1	B1
UAB7	A2	B2
UAB8	A1	B1

INTRODUCTION (15 min)

<u>Who?</u>	<u>What?</u>	<u>How long?</u>
Lead facilitator	Welcome the participants, who will individually attend the test. Please assign a participant code when they arrive, so that they can enter that code in each online questionnaire.	1 min
Lead facilitator	Explain the project (if unknown to the participant), the aim of the test and the procedure .	5 min
Assistant facilitator	Provide the participant with the consent form for ethical clearance. You can find the last version here: https://docs.google.com/document/d/1JwH-IF61UFHwaQpKfejQC7p0A35zTvCg2Zcbfrc3kf4/edit Provide signed original consent forms to UAB (next meeting or send by snail mail).	3 min

Assistant facilitator	Provide the participant with the digital demographic questionnaire to be filled in (access to a computer/laptop will be needed): SP: https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSev8s6YPEvggEQbMP65pGobRyZr640Eisq_Ov_QFnJakdCFVg/viewform	6 min
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In the following sections, the different parts of the test will be explained, including tasks and measures.

TASK 1 (20 min)

- **Measures:** immersion and preferences
- **Participants:** 8
- **Materials:**
 - **Devices:** the test will be performed with an HMD.
 - **Player:**
 - Link to the player: <http://84.88.32.46/UAB-test5b/>
 - **Stimuli:** Two comparable clips (A, B) with 2 conditions (1, 2) for each presentation mode tested, so that participants can watch both conditions in different but comparable clips to avoid a learning effect.
 - Opera:
 - 2 comparable clips, 4min15sec each.
- **Room:** make sure the atmosphere is comfortable for the participants, with an adequate room arrangement.

Previous to task (5 min) The lead facilitator will explain the aim of this part: testing two different SDH and Easy to Read modes. The participants will be asked to watch the two randomised clips.

After watching **the two clips**, participants will have to reply to the IPQ (presence) questionnaire to gather feedback about immersion.

Answer a set of questions.

- a) SDH - Opera: <https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1JAnzKahTVD7neVfCQ-4oIcPgWZu0cwFIjff377bE-DM/edit>
- b) E2R - Opera: https://docs.google.com/forms/d/12vkD_qvQWacOM4OMgKjBKqz7mpluP47EtojkDQfDciU/edit

The order of presentation of the stimuli will be balanced across participants. See Latin square protocol in which the presentation mode is tested with two conditions (SDH and E2R).

In order to measure also **preferences** participants will be asked to answer a set of questions:

1. What system do you prefer for subtitles?
 - a) Deaf and Hard of Hearing
 - b) Easy to Read
2. Please, explain why you prefer the above indicated option.
3. Please explain why you did not choose the other option in question 1).
4. What do you think could be improved, and how?
5. How easy was it to **read** the subtitles in SDH mode?
 - 1- Very difficult
 - 7- Very easy
6. How easy was it to **read** the subtitles in E2R mode?
 - 1- Very difficult
 - 7- Very easy

7. How easy was it to **understand** the subtitles in SDH mode?
 - 1- Very difficult
 - 7- Very easy
8. How easy was it to **understand** the subtitles in E2R mode?
 - 1- Very difficult
 - 7- Very easy
9. Do you think you will be able to enjoy 360° videos with this type of subtitles? Explain your answer.

FAREWELL AND THANKS to participants (5 min)

REPORTING (after the tests)

Upload your report one week after the tests under Google Drive under **IMAC_SHARED_FOLDER/ WP5/ T5.1./ 2 PRE PILOT ACTIONS - 2019 / END USER – E2R / PARTNER REPORTS.**

It must follow the template available in the same folder:

6. Questionnaires

Questionnaires will be provided to the participants using online forms, but is included below for reference.

Demographic questionnaire for home users – Version 1 (Annex 46)

IPQ (Immersion) (Annex 44)

ANNEX 35. EASY-TO-READ PRE-PILOT 2 ACTIONS REPORT (UAB) (I)

1. General information

- Partner responsible: UAB
- Place and date: May 2019
- Access service(s) discussed: *Preferences and presence between SDH and E2R subtitling.*

2. Demographic questionnaire

- Number of end users: 8
- Demographics for users.
 - Sex:
 - “female” 5
 - “male” 3
 - “other”, “I prefer not to reply”
 - Age: 50-79
 - Main language: Catalan-Spanish
 - Please indicate your level of studies:
 - “no studies”
 - “primary education”
 - “secondary education” 2
 - “further education” 3
 - “university” 3
 - I define myself as...:
 - “deaf person”,
 - “hearing impaired person” 2
 - “deaf-blind person”,
 - “other” = Not apply 6
 - Age in which your disability began:
 - “from birth”,
 - “0-4”,
 - “5-12”,
 - “13-20”,
 - “21-40”,
 - “41-60”,
 - “more than 60” 2
 - What devices do you use on a daily basis? Multiple replies are possible: “TV” 8
 - “PC” 3
 - “Laptop” 3
 - “Mobile phone” 8
 - “Tablet” 4
 - “Head Mounted Display (HMD)”
 - “other”. 1 (radio)
 - How often do you watch virtual reality content (for instance, 360º videos)?

	Never	Occasionally	At least once a month	At least once a week	Every day
In smartphone	7	1			
On a tablet	8				
On a PC	7	1			
In smartphone plugged to HMD	7	1			
In HMD	8				

9. If you have never used virtual reality content such as 360° videos or only occasionally, please indicate why. Multiple answers are possible. "Because I am not interested." 1
"Because it is not accessible."
"Because I have not had the chance to use it." 7
"Other reasons."
10. Please state your level of agreement with the following statement:
"I am interested in virtual reality content (such as 360° videos)."
"I strongly agree" 3
"I agree" 3
"Neither agree nor disagree" 2
"Disagree"
"Strongly disagree"
11. Do you own any device to access virtual reality content?
"Yes"
"No" 8
"I don't know or I don't want to reply".
12. If you replied "yes" to the previous question, please specify which device(s).
13. Do you like watching the following types of content on television or online?

	I like it very much	I like it	Neither like it nor dislike it	I don't like it	I don't like it at all
News	5	3			
Fiction (series, films)	2	2	2	1	1
Talk shows	3	4			1
Documentaries	5	3			
Sports	1	4	2	1	
Cartoons		2		3	3

14. When subtitling is available, do you activate it for the following type of content?

	Always	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
News		1	1	6
Fiction (series, films)	1		3	4
Talk shows		1		7
Documentaries	1	2		5
Sports			2	6
Cartoons				7

15. If it is available and you do not activate it, please select the reasons why. "Because the interface is not accessible."
"Because I don't want subtitling in all the content, only in certain types of content." 8
"Other"
16. How many hours a day do you watch subtitled content?
"None" 4
"Less than 1 hour" 2
"1-2 hours" 2
"2-3 hours"
"3-4 hours"
"4 hours or more"
17. What do you use subtitles for?
"They help me understand" 4
"They are my only way to have access to the dialogue"

"I use them for language learning" 1
 "Other". 3

3. PART 2

TASK 1

a) IPQ – SDH (Opera)

IPQ Question	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
In the computer generated world I had a sense of "being there".			1			6	1
Somehow I felt that the virtual world surrounded me.			1		1	4	2
I felt like I was just perceiving pictures.		7				1	
I did not feel present in the virtual space.			1		1	5	1
I had a sense of acting in the virtual space, rather than operating something from outside.					2	5	1
I felt present in the virtual space.			1		1	4	2
How aware were you of the real world surrounding while navigating in the virtual world? (i.e. sounds, room temperature, other people, etc.)?		1	1			5	1
I was not aware of my real environment.		2			1	4	1
I still paid attention to the real environment.	2	4			1	1	
I was completely captivated by the virtual world.	1				1	5	1
How real did the virtual world seem to you?	1	5				1	1
How much did your experience in the virtual environment seem consistent with your real world experience ?	1				1	5	1
How real did the virtual world seem to you?	1	1	1		1	3	1
The virtual world seemed more realistic than the real world.	1	3	3			1	

b) IPQ – E2R (Opera)

IPQ Question	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
In the computer generated world I had a sense of "being there".				1		6	1
Somehow I felt that the virtual world surrounded me.				1	1	3	3
I felt like I was just perceiving pictures.	3	3	1			1	
I did not feel present in the virtual space.				1	1	5	1
I had a sense of acting in the virtual space, rather than operating something from outside.			1		1	4	2
I felt present in the virtual space.			1		1	4	2
How aware were you of the real world surrounding while navigating in the virtual world? (i.e. sounds, room temperature, other people, etc.)?		2			1	4	1
I was not aware of my real environment.		1			2	3	2
I still paid attention to the real environment.	3	2	1	1	1		
I was completely captivated by the virtual world.			1	1	1	5	
How real did the virtual world seem to you?	3	2	2			1	
How much did your experience in the virtual environment seem consistent with your real world experience ?		1	1		2	3	1
How real did the virtual world seem to you?	1	1	1		2	2	1
The virtual world seemed more realistic than the real world.		2	2	2	1	1	

We used a Wilcoxon Signed Ranks test to compare the ratings for both subtitle types and found no differences in any IPQ scale (General Presence $Z=-.184$, $p=.854$, ties=4; Spatial Presence $Z=-.639$, $p=.523$, ties=0; Involvement $Z=-.431$, $p=.666$, ties=2; Experienced realism $Z=-1.222$, $p=.222$, ties=0).

Group	General Presence	Spatial Presence	Involvement	Experienced Realism
SDH	5	5	4.63	4
E2R	5	5	4.88	3.88

c) Preferences (SDH vs E2R)

1. What system do you prefer for subtitles?

a) SDH	b) E2R
3	5

2. Please, explain why you prefer the above indicated option.

E2R

- UAB1: They were shorter and easier to read
- UAB2: They were easier to read
- UAB3: Because you can get more into the story and not be so aware of the text
- UAB4: Because it was easier to read the subtitles and so I could enjoy the performance better
- UAB8: Although apparently I have not noticed the difference they were easier to read

SDH

- UAB5: They were more defined and clearer
- UAB7: They were in the second video and I was more used to reading the subtitles
- UAB6: The language was more appropriate

3. Please explain why you did not choose the other option in question 1).

Participants that choose E2R as preferred option answered:

- UAB1: I also liked them but less
- UAB 2: They were more dense
- UAB 3: Because you have to be so aware of the text that you lose part of the plot
- UAB5: Because they were more difficult to read
- UAB 8: Because they were longer

Participants that choose SDH as preferred option answered:

- UAB 4: Possibly because I already get used to subtitles and they were easier for me.
- UAB 6: Because the text content seemed silly to me.
- UAB 7: It has been easier for me to read the SDH subtitles because I am used to glasses and to be more for the text than for the environment.

4. What do you think could be improved, and how?

Regarding SDH

- UAB1: They should be shorter
- UAB2: They should be made in easy to read
- UAB 3: Text should be reduced as much as possible
- UAB 5: Adopt the visibility and readability of the E2R option
- UAB 8: I don't know

Regarding E2R

- UAB 4: Nothing
- UAB 6: Use a more accurate language
- UAB 7: They were quite good

5. How easy was it to **read** the subtitles for Deaf and Hard of Hearing?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5- very easy
	1	2	3	2

6. How easy was it to **read** the subtitles in Easy to Read?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5- very easy
	1		1	6

7. How easy was it to **understand** subtitles for Deaf and Hard of Hearing?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5- very easy
	1	2	3	2

8. How easy was it to **understand** the subtitles in Easy to Read?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5- very easy
	1			7

9. Do you think you will be able to enjoy 360° videos with this type of subtitles? Explain your answer.

- UAB 1: Yes, because it is easy to read and you can understand everything
- UAB 2: Yes, because the size of the font it is easy to read
- UAB 3: Yes, because Easy to read subtitles are not as invasive as SDH and you can spend more time enjoying the stage performance
- UAB 4: Yes, because the eye becomes easily used to subtitles in the Easy to read format
- UAB 5: Yes, because they help you to understand the plot of the performance
- UAB 6: No, because I am reluctant to virtual worlds
- UAB 7: Yes, perfectly
- UAB 8: Yes, because subtitles are a good method to understand the plot of the audiovisual content.

4. Conclusions

Users seemed to welcome E2R subtitles overall because they are easy to read and “you can understand everything”, because they are not as invasive as SDH and because the “eye becomes easily used to subtitles in the E2R format”. Complaints referred to virtual worlds (“I am reluctant to virtual worlds”), not the actual implementation of the subtitles.

ANNEX 36. METHODOLOGY FOR EASY-TO-READ PRE-PILOT 2 ACTIONS (UAB) (II)

What will be tested? (summary)

The purpose of the experiment is to gather users' feedback on different presentation modes for E2R in cinematic virtual reality.

Who?

- Spanish pilot: UAB

Stimuli

- **Devices:** the test will be performed with an HMD.
- **Player:** Link to the player: <http://84.88.32.46/UAB-test5b/>
- Opera Romeo and Juliet
 - Description: musical.
 - Genre: musical
 - Original language: French.
 - Duration: 4min15seg
 - Access services needed:
 - SP E2R with arrows (as guiding mechanisms)
 - SP SDH with arrows (as guiding mechanisms)
 - Two comparable clips (A, B) with 2 conditions (1, 2) for each presentation mode tested, so that participants can watch both conditions in different but comparable clips to avoid a learning effect.

IDENTIFICATION CODES FOR THE STIMULI

The letters refer to the subtitles and the numbers to the variables:

360º video: Opera 1. Subtitles in Spanish: SDH + easy-to-read

- A1 (4min15sec) . Opera Part 1 - SDH Subtitles.
- B1 (4min15sec). Opera Part 2 - Easy-to-Read Subtitles.
- B2 (4min15sec). Opera Part 1 - Easy-to-Read Subtitles.
- A2 (4min15sec). Opera Part 2 - SDH Subtitles

[NOTE 1]: Counter-balance conditions:

Even participants: watch video A1 & B1 (only one time)

Odd participants: watch video A2 & B2 (only one time)

[NOTE 2] Variable SDH vs E2R (both types of subtitles have been validated in E2R)

[NOTE 3] Font selection ROBOTO

Methodology: overview

- **Aim:** gather data from users about their experience with different presentation modes, replying to questions regarding immersion and preferences.
- **Experimental protocol:** users will be asked to watch different stimuli, and then report on the preferences and immersion through digital questionnaires with closed and open questions.
- **Research tools:** digital questionnaires (Google Forms). The questionnaires will be digital in order to facilitate data processing. The questionnaires will be translated into Spanish. IPQ translations will be provided by UAB. They are available under the sub-folder SURVEYS.
- **Measures:** preferences and presence (immersion).
- **Participants:** Recruitment will be done via associations/organisation and/or at partners' discretion. Aim: 40 participants.
- **Duration:** approx. 30 minutes.
- **Language of the test:** Spanish.
- **Materials:** HMD, computer and clips.
- **Facilitators:** A single facilitator will be needed. One facilitator will be the leader (welcoming participants, explaining the project, explaining the test) and another facilitator will assist the

sessions (by providing the digital questionnaires and helping filling them in, providing technical assistance with the different devices, etc.).

- **Test accessibility:** adequate measures must be taken by tests organisers (UAB) so that communication with persons with hearing loss is fluent.
- **Reporting:** results will be included in a report created by each partner. This will be done exporting data from the Google Form. A template will be provided. All feedback must be translated into English by the partners responsible for the pilots (UAB).
- **Testing the methodology:** the methodology will be tested prior to the test.
- Please make sure that you have all materials and ethical forms ready before the test.

Methodology: experimental protocol

PLANNING

Introduction	15 min
Task 1	20 min
Farewell and thanks	5 min
Buffer time	5 min
Total	45 min

WORKFLOW

LATIN SQUARE FOR ALL PARTICIPANTS (if more than 10, repeat from the beginning).

Each participant will follow a different order to avoid the order of presentation affecting the results.

Participant	TASK 1	TASK 1
UAB1	A2	B2
UAB2	A1	B1
UAB3	A2	B2
UAB4	A1	B1
UAB5	A2	B2
UAB6	A1	B1
UAB7	A2	B2
UAB8	A1	B1

INTRODUCTION (15 min)

<u>Who?</u>	<u>What?</u>	<u>How long?</u>
Lead facilitator	Welcome the participants, who will individually attend the test. Please assign a participant code when they arrive, so that they can enter that code in each online questionnaire.	1 min
Lead facilitator	Explain the project (if unknown to the participant), the aim of the test and the procedure .	5 min
Assistant facilitator	Provide the participant with the consent form for ethical clearance. You can find the last version here: https://docs.google.com/document/d/1JwH-IF61UFHwaQpKfejQC7p0A35zTvCg2Zcbfrc3kf4/edit Provide signed original consent forms to UAB (next meeting or send by snail mail).	3 min
Assistant facilitator	Provide the participant with the digital demographic questionnaire to be filled in (access to a computer/laptop will be needed): SP: https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSev8s6YPEvggEQbMP65pGobRyZr640Eisq_Ov_QFnJakdCFVg/viewform	6 min

Previous to task (5 min) The lead facilitator will explain the aim of this part: testing two different SDH and Easy to Read modes. The participants will be asked to watch the two randomised clips.

After watching **the two clips**, participants will have to reply to the IPQ (presence) questionnaire to gather feedback about immersion.

Answer a set of questions.

- c) SDH - Opera: <https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1JAnzKahTVD7neVfCQ-4oIcPgWZu0cwFijff377bE-DM/edit>
- d) E2R - Opera: https://docs.google.com/forms/d/12vkD_qvQWacOM4OMgKjBKqz7mpluP47EtojkDQfDciU/edit

The order of presentation of the stimuli will be balanced across participants. See Latin square protocol in which the presentation mode is tested with two conditions (SDH and E2R).

In order to measure also **preferences** participants will be asked to answer a set of questions:

1. What system do you prefer for subtitles?
 - a) Deaf and Hard of Hearing
 - b) Easy to Read
2. Please, explain why you prefer the above indicated option.
3. Please explain why you did not choose the other option in question 1).
4. What do you think could be improved, and how?
5. How easy was it to **read** the subtitles in SDH mode?
 - 1- Very difficult
 - 7- Very easy
6. How easy was it to **read** the subtitles in E2R mode?
 - 1- Very difficult
 - 7- Very easy
7. How easy was it to **understand** the subtitles in SDH mode?
 - 1- Very difficult
 - 7- Very easy
8. How easy was it to **understand** the subtitles in E2R mode?
 - 1- Very difficult
 - 7- Very easy
9. Do you think you will be able to enjoy 360° videos with this type of subtitles? Explain your answer.

FAREWELL AND THANKS to participants (5 min)

REPORTING (after the tests)

Upload your report one week after the tests under Google Drive under **IMAC_SHARED_FOLDER/ WP5/ T5.1./ 2 PRE PILOT ACTIONS - 2019 / END USER – E2R / PARTNER REPORTS.**

It must follow the template available in the same folder.

7. Questionnaires

Questionnaires will be provided to the participants using online forms, but is included below for reference.

Demographic questionnaire for home users – Version 1 (Annex 46)

IPQ (Immersion) (Annex 44)

ANNEX 37. EASY-TO-READ PRE-PILOT 2 ACTIONS REPORT (UAB) (II)

1. General information

- Partner responsible: UAB
- Place and date: October 2019
- Access service(s) discussed: *Preferences and presence between SDH and E2R subtitling.*

2. Demographic questionnaire

- Number of end users: 36
 - Demographics for users.
1. Sex:
 - “female” 19 (52.8%)
 - “male” 17 (47.2%)
 - “other”, “I prefer not to reply”
 2. Age: 62-79
 3. Main language: Catalan-Spanish
 4. Please indicate your level of studies:
 - “no studies” 2 (5.6%)
 - “primary education” 10 (27.8%)
 - “secondary education” 7 (19.4%)
 - “further education” 8 (22.2%)
 - “university” 9 (25%)
 5. I define myself as...:
 - “deaf person”,
 - “hearing impaired person” 11 (30.6%)
 - “visually impaired person” 11 (30.6%)
 - “cognitively impaired person” 1 (2.8%)
 - “motoric impaired person”
 - “other” = 13 (36%) reported not to have any type of impairment but some type of sensory decline.
 6. Age in which your disability began:
 - “from birth”,
 - “0-4”, 1
 - “5-12”,
 - “13-20”,
 - “21-40”,
 - “41-60”, 11
 - “more than 60” 11
 7. What devices do you use on a daily basis? Multiple replies are possible: “TV” 34 (94,4%)
 - “PC” 12 (33.3%)
 - “Laptop” 16 (44.4%)
 - “Mobile phone” 35 (97.2%)
 - “Tablet” 16 (44.4%)
 - “Head Mounted Display (HMD)”
 - “other”. 1 (2.8%) (radio)

8. How often do you watch virtual reality content (for instance, 360° videos)?

	Never	Occasionally	At least once a month	At least once a week	Every day
In smartphone	36				
On a tablet	36				
On a PC	36				
In smartphone plugged to HMD	36				
In HMD	29	7			

9. If you have never used virtual reality content such as 360° videos or only occasionally, please indicate why. Multiple answers are possible. "Because I am not interested." 3 (8.3%)

"Because it is not accessible."

"Because I have not had the chance to use it." 29 (80.6%)

"Other reasons." 4 (11.1%)

10. Please state your level of agreement with the following statement:

"I am interested in virtual reality content (such as 360° videos)."

"I strongly agree" 3 (8.3%)

"I agree" 19 (52.8%)

"Neither agree nor disagree" 12 (33.3%)

"Disagree" 2 (5.6%)

"Strongly disagree"

11. Do you own any device to access virtual reality content?

"Yes"

"No" 36 (100%)

"I don't know or I don't want to reply".

12. If you replied "yes" to the previous question, please specify which device(s).

13. Do you like watching the following types of content on television or online?

	I like it very much	I like it	Neither like it nor dislike it	I don't like it	I don't like it at all
News	7	23	2	2	2
Fiction (series, films)	9	22	3	1	1
Talk shows	7	23	2	1	3
Documentaries	18	14	2	1	1
Sports	7	8	5	11	5
Cartoons	2	12	7	11	4

14. When subtitling is available, do you activate it for the following type of content?

	Always	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
News			1	35
Fiction (series, films)	2	11	3	20
Talk shows		1		35
Documentaries	1	6	2	27
Sports		1		35
Cartoons			2	34

15. If it is available and you do not activate it, please select the reasons why. "Because the interface is not accessible."
 "Because I don't want subtitling in all the content, only in certain types of content." 15 (41.7%)
 "Other" 21 (58.3%) participants with the lower study levels reported that they did not activate the subtitles because their reading speed was too low to follow the subtitles and they feel frustrated with subtitles because they miss the visual content.
16. How many hours a week do you watch subtitled content?
 "None" 17 (47.2%)
 "Less than 1 hour" 10 (27.8%)
 "1-2 hours" 6 (16.7%)
 "2-3 hours" 3 (8.3%)
 "3-4 hours"
 "4 hours or more"
17. What do you use subtitles for?
 "They help me understand" 14 (38.9%)
 "They are my only way to have access to the dialogue"
 "I use them for language learning" 5 (13.8%)
 "Other". 17 (47.6%) reported not to use subtitles mainly because they do not like them. Within this group it must be mentioned that 5 (14%) participants, the ones with the lower study level, reported that they did not activate the subtitles because their reading speed was too low to follow the subtitles and they feel frustrated and with subtitles miss the visual content.

4. PART 2

TASK 1

d) IPQ – SDH (Opera)

IPQ Question	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
In the computer generated world I had a sense of "being there".				4	11	11	9
Somehow I felt that the virtual world surrounded me.			2	3	11	10	9
I felt like I was just perceiving pictures.	17	7	7	3			1
I did not feel present in the virtual space.			1	4	2	16	12
I had a sense of acting in the virtual space, rather than operating something from outside.			1	1	6	13	14
I felt present in the virtual space.	1			2	6	14	12
How aware were you of the real world surrounding while navigating in the virtual world? (i.e. sounds, room temperature, other people, etc.)?	2	3	1	2	9	11	7
I was not aware of my real environment.	4	1	1		8	14	7
I still paid attention to the real environment.	9	9	3	2	2	8	2
I was completely captivated by the virtual world.			1	3	4	12	15
How real did the virtual world seem to you?	11	7	5	3	7	1	1
How much did your experience in the virtual environment seem consistent with your real world experience ?	1	2	1	4	10	7	10
How real did the virtual world seem to you?		3	2	5	12	8	5
The virtual world seemed more realistic than the real world.	5	2	5	7	7	5	4

e) IPQ – E2R (Opera)

IPQ Question	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
In the computer generated world I had a sense of "being there".			1	3	9	14	9
Somehow I felt that the virtual world surrounded me.			3	1	9	14	9
I felt like I was just perceiving pictures.	19	11	3	2			1
I did not feel present in the virtual space.			3	2	4	14	13
I had a sense of acting in the virtual space, rather than operating something from outside.			4		7	12	13
I felt present in the virtual space.	1		2	1	8	13	11
How aware were you of the real world surrounding while navigating in the virtual world? (i.e. sounds, room temperature, other people, etc.)?	1	1	1	5	7	10	11
I was not aware of my real environment.	1	1	1	2	7	14	10
I still paid attention to the real environment.	11	7	2		5	10	1
I was completely captivated by the virtual world.			2	1	4	15	14
How real did the virtual world seem to you?	11	11	4	3	5	1	1
How much did your experience in the virtual environment seem consistent with your real world experience ?	3		1	5	9	11	7
How real did the virtual world seem to you?	5	1	2	6	9	8	5
The virtual world seemed more realistic than the real world.	2	1	4	9	9	6	5

Group	General Presence	Spatial Presence	Involvement	Experienced Realism
SDH	4.71	4.91	4.26	3.90
E2R	4.74	4.87	4.41	3.90

Planned comparisons (T-test) show that the results of four scales of Presence (General presence, Spatial Presence, Involvement and Experienced Realism) are not different if participants have seen E2R subtitles or SDH subtitles: General Presence $t(34)=.138$, $p=.891$; Spatial Presence $t(34)=-.361$, $p=.720$; Involvement $t(34)=-.803$, $p=.428$; Experienced realism $t(34)=.000$, $p=1$.

f) Preferences (SDH vs E2R)

1. What system do you prefer for subtitles?

a) SDH	b) E2R	c) Both
19 (52.78%)	16 (44.44%)	1 (2.7%)

2. Please, explain why you prefer the above indicated option.

UAB1	E2R because it reflects the real life
UAB2	E2R because there was more dialogue
UAB3	SDH, because in E2R there was more action and colors were more aggressive
UAB4	I prefer SDH but I understood both perfectly
UAB5	E2R because I do not need the language of the deaf impaired audiences
UAB6	I prefer E2R but both options were good for me
UAB7	SDH because there was more coherence between audio and the subtitles. I understand French
UAB8	I prefer E2R but both options were ok for me. The second E2R you are more used to the subtitles. For the first SDH the scene was more aggressive and I like it more
UAB9	E2R I understood it better
UAB10	SDH It seemed to me more real
UAB11	E2R. In SDH the script was more real but to me E2R was easier to read
UAB12	E2R was more clear
UAB13	SDH I read it better
UAB14	E2R because it was easier but I understood both very well.
UAB15	E2R were shorter but both were clear and readable
UAB16	E2R was easier I was confused with the change of colors
UAB17	SDH was more pleasant also because of the type action in the scene

UAB18	SDH the colors and the size of the letter caught better my attention
UAB19	E2R the expressions were shorter
UAB20	SDH because even if I don't some people need extralinguistic information
UAB21	E2R the subtitles were shorter and I understood them better
UAB22	SDH the font was easier to read for me and the color contrast was better
UAB23	E2R the scene was more active and there were no words in another language
UAB24	SDH it was easier to read for me. In this video I put the glasses on and it was perfect
UAB25	E2R because the text was shorter and easier to understand
UAB26	E2R was easier and it seemed more complete to me
UAB27	SDH because there was more color variation and more actors. I had to concentrate more
UAB28	BOTH I regret that the image could have been better but I liked both subtitle types
UAB29	SDH I liked more because of the scene
UAB30	SDH I had the impression that the letters were bigger
UAB31	SDH I found it more real (accurate) they helped me to have a better immersive experience
UAB32	E2R they were easier to read more simplified and clear
UAB33	SDH because were the first subtitles and I recalled when I was at the Liceu enjoying this opera.
UAB34	SDH because were the second subtitles and I was more used to read them than in the first
UAB35	E2R because I saw them more clear and I could read them better
UAB36	E2R because the colors were more clear

3. Please explain why you did not choose the other option in question 1).

UAB1	In the SDH I was still not immerse in the scene
UAB2	In the SDH the plot was not very large
UAB3	I liked more the E2R because of the scene but I could read SDH better
UAB4	I understood both perfectly

UAB5	Because it was easier to read with no extra information
UAB6	I liked both options
UAB7	To me it seemed that in the E2R there was a gap between the singing and the text because I understand French
UAB8	I liked both
UAB9	In the SDH there were words that I did not understand
UAB10	E2R did not seem me very real
UAB11	SDH was easier to read
UAB12	At the beginning SDH seemed that was not translated properly
UAB13	E2R for me was better maybe because I got used to it
UAB14	Both were very good
UAB15	Both options were clear and legible
UAB16	In SDH there were more colors and I got confused
UAB17	In E2R the content was more serious and I could not finish to read some sentences
UAB18	In E2R I did not understand the action
UAB19	In SDH the text was too large for the rhythm of the opera
UAB20	I actually like both in general it might depend on the content of the opera
UAB21	SDH were larger and I had no time to read them. The words were more difficult
UAB22	In E2R the color contrast was not that clear to me.
UAB23	In SDH there were words that I did not understand
UAB24	In E2R I did not had my glasses on so I could not read as good as the SDH
UAB25	Both were good but in SDH there were some words that I did not understand
UAB26	In SDH some information was missing
UAB27	In E2R there was not much action and the subtitles were mostly in the same color. I understood better E2R.
UAB28	I liked both
UAB29	In E2R I did not like the scene that much
UAB30	I also liked the E2R
UAB31	E2R seemed less real I had the feeling that requested more attention
UAB32	SDH were longer

UAB33	In E2R I had the feeling that the scene was slower. I also started to cough so I did not enjoyed that much
UAB34	I found both good
UAB35	SDH were less clear
UAB36	I preferred the colors in E2R

4. What do you think could be improved, and how?

UAB 1	Nothing
UAB 2	Nothing
UAB 3	In E2R the colours were too aggressive and I mixed up things. The font size was too large
UAB 4	Nothing
UAB 5	In both options the subtitle text should be more centred in the field of view
UAB 6	Nothing
UAB 7	I understand French and in E2R there were repetitions that differed from the original
UAB 8	Nothing
UAB 9	In SDH There were words that I did not understood
UAB 10	In SDH the subtitles were too fast
UAB 11	The second option, the font size seemed larger in the second clip (SDH)
UAB 12	The colours should be softer in both versions
UAB 13	The quality of the video should be better in both options
UAB 14	Font size and colour were good. Maybe softer colours would be easier to read.
UAB 15	The quality of the video should be better in both options.
UAB 16	The quality of the image. The quality of the subtitles is better than the image of the
UAB 17	Nothing
UAB 18	The quality of the video should be better in both options.
UAB 19	The subtitle should be shorter to allow longer reading times.
UAB 20	Sometimes the size of the text was too big. It would be great if you could adapt it.
UAB 21	Make SDH easier to understand
UAB 22	In both options the colour contrast should be softer.
UAB 23	Nothing
UAB 24	I don't know, I understood everything. The texts were short and I could read everything. Maybe some colours (yellow and green) were easier to read.

UAB 25	I like the colour differentiation for identifying the characters but colours should be
UAB 26	The E2R option should include all information as in the SDH option to understand the
UAB 27	Nothing. In both options the colours help a lot and the size of the font was very easy to read.
UAB 28	Nothing. In both options there should be more contents to compare
UAB 29	Nothing both options are very good.
UAB 30	Nothing both options are very good. But the size of the second option seemed larger.
UAB 31	Nothing. But I do not like the invasiveness of the subtitles
UAB 32	In both options some colours are difficult to read
UAB 33	The size of the font was perfect.
UAB 34	Nothing
UAB 35	I don't know
UAB 36	In both options, the stronger colours do not allow me to connect properly with the opera which is immersive and for me this is important.

5. How easy was it to **read** the subtitles for Deaf and Hard of Hearing?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5- very easy
	1 (2.8%)	6 (16.7%)	5 (13.9%)	24 (66.7%)

6. How easy was it to **read** the subtitles Easy to read?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5- very easy
		3 (8.3%)	9 (25%)	24 (66.7%)

7. How easy was it to **understand** subtitles for Deaf and Hard of Hearing?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5- very easy
		8 (22.2%)	5 (13.9%)	23 (63.9%)

8. How easy was it to **understand** Easy to read subtitles?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5- very easy
		1 (2.8%)	9 (25%)	26 (72.2%)

9. Do you think you will be able to enjoy 360° videos with this type of subtitles? Explain your answer.

UAB1	No because if you read you can't enjoy the play that is why I do not like the subtitles. I prefer to stay focus on the paly also because in this case I do not speak French
UAB2	I could enjoy it in other types of content. I do not like opera
UAB3	Yes perfectly. I speak French and I understood some things in French
UAB4	Yes perfectly. I had time to read the subtitles in both cases
UAB5	Yes but I would like the font smaller. It would be great if you could customize it

UAB6	Yes with this type of subtitles (font and size) and times yes.
UAB7	Yes specially when you hear an opera it helps you to follow the plot
UAB8	Yes perfectly.
UAB9	Yes because it entertains you
UAB10	Yes because you can read it properly, it is good explained and I love theater
UAB11	Yes because in the opera you do not understand the singing and the subtitles help you to understand
UAB12	Yes the subtitles help you to understand the opera when it is in a foreign language
UAB13	Yes bot types of subtitles are useful to help you understand content in another language
UAB14	Yes I like subtitles in general because they help you to understand the meaning
UAB15	Yes because you could read the subtitles very well. They had a good color-contrast and were very well segmented. I like them.
UAB16	Yes because the virtual reality is very real and the subtitling is not tiring
UAB17	Yes because it is the first time that I watch this type of content and it was very real and very easy to read.
UAB18	I don't know because it is hard for me to enjoy AV content with subtitles
UAB19	Yes because this format it allows you to watch and enjoy all type of AV content from inside and the subtitles give you access to the content
UAB20	Yes because if a person do not have much mobility and likes theater he/she can enjoy it.
UAB21	I never have time to read the subtitles. In a documentary, a musical play or a movie it would be perfect.
UAB22	Yes because it is easy when you combine reading and head movement. Here is easy because the subtitles join you when you move around
UAB23	Yes even if I do not favor subtitles. We should use subtitles from a very early stage
UAB24	Yes because it helps you to understand the content when it is in another language.
UAB25	Yes I would like to attend an opera with this type of subtitles (font and size)
UAB26	Yes the subtitles helped me to understand the plot of the opera. Without the subtitles I wouldn't have understood anything. It would have been like watching a football match
UAB27	Yes because with this type of devices you can listen and read without anybody bothering you. With this glasses you have full immersion. If you live with many people it is a good solution.
UAB28	Yes because it could be read easily. You had time to read and the content was synchronized with the image

UAB29	Yes because I like opera and if it is subtitled it is easier to follow it. The font size was perfect.
UAB30	Yes subtitles allowed me to understand the content
UAB31	Yes because if I do not understand the language of the play, the subtitles would help me to understand the plot. It is a matter of language.
UAB32	Yes it would be interesting in order to understand
UAB33	Yes it is another way to see things
UAB34	Yes because it is very real and it seems that you are inside and the subtitling helps you to understand
UAB35	Yes because if there is no subtitling you do not understand much
UAB36	Yes because I like the music and the subtitles help me to understand more the plot and the music.

4. Conclusions

The scope of this study was to test two different types of subtitles, namely SDH and E2R with a limited number of participants. A specific group profile, aged people - aged between 62-79 years old (19 female and 17 male) - was identified to clarify the willingness of this target group to use these technologies and the suitability of SDH or E2R subtitles.

The AV content was in French language and subtitles in both formats were displayed in Spanish. Only two participants reported to speak or understand French language. All participants were Spanish. 20 participants were bilingual with Spanish and Catalan as their mother tongues, and 16 participants only spoke Spanish. Regarding education level, 2 participants (5,6%) reported not having any type of studies, 10 participants (27,8%) had primary education, 7 participants (19,4%) secondary education, 8 participants (22,2%) professional studies and 9 participants (25%) a university degree.

None of the participants owned VR equipment and only seven participants were familiar with VR content. 29 participants (80.55%) reported not having had the opportunity to enjoy VR content. 3 participants (8.33%) were very interested in VR content, 12 (33.33%) were interested, 19 (50%) participants were neutral. Regarding the type of AV content, animations and sports were the least valued. On the other hand, documentaries and fiction were the most valued. 17 participants (47.22%) claimed that they never use subtitles, two participants (5.6%) claimed that they always use subtitles and 11 participants (30,55%) that they use them sometimes depending on the content and language of the AV content. Regarding the reasons to use subtitles, 5 participants (13.88%) said to learn languages and 14 (38.88%) said that they used them because subtitles helped them to understand. 17 participants (47.22%) reported not to use subtitles mainly because they do not like them. Within this group it must be mentioned that 5 participants (13.88%), the ones with the lower study levels, reported that they did not activate the subtitles because their reading speed was too low to follow the subtitles and they feel frustrated and with subtitles miss the visual content.

Almost half of participants reported not to have any type of impairment but some type of sensory decline. While only two participants used hearing aids, 22 participants (61.11%) reported mild hearing loss and/or visual decline, 11 participants (30.55%) reported to have it detected between 41 and 60 years old and 11 participants (30.55%) since they were 60 years old. Only one participant (2.77%) declared to have a cognitive decline.

The results obtained regarding preferences were that 19 (52.78%) out of 36 participants preferred E2R subtitles, 16 participants (44.44%) preferred SDH and 1 participant (2.7%) had no preference. The main reasons for choosing the E2R option according to the participants were that they are shorter and easier to read than SDH, and that in the SDH subtitles there were some words that they did not understand. When asked 'Why did they do not chose the other option?' the reasons were because SDH subtitles were more dense, longer and more difficult to read. Also, the exposure time ('6 second rule') should be reviewed because some participants reported not having the time to read the subtitles. On the other

hand, participants that chose the SDH option argued that SDH were more defined and clearer, and the language, more accurate.

When asked what could be improved, 9 participants (25%) reported that there was nothing to be improved and one participant (2.77%) did not know. In addition, three participants (8.33%) reported that the size of the font in both options was perfect and three participants (8.33%) reported that the quality of the image should be better. Most participants found the use of colours for character identification very helpful and the size of the font very easy to read. Regarding the colour, eight participants (22.22%) reported that some colours were difficult to read, especially for the stronger ones, which did not allow them to connect with the visuals. One participant (2.77%) mentioned that there should be more subtitled contents in E2R and SDH to compare, another participant (2.77%) did not like the invasiveness of the subtitles, another participant (2.77%) considered that the subtitle should be more centered in the field of view and a last one (2.77%) found the size of the text too big and users should be able to adapt it. For the SDH two participants (5.55%) reported that there were words that they did not understand and two participants (5.55%) reported that the reading times were too fast. For the E2R two participants (5.55%) reported that the subtitles were too fast and another two participants (5.55%) reported font size seemed larger than SDH.

Regarding the closed questions on readability and understandability of both subtitle options: For E2R, 24 participants (66.7%) reported that they were very easy to read, 9 participants (25%) stated that they were easy to read and 3 participants (8.3%) were neutral. For understandability of E2R subtitles, most participants, 26 (72.22%), answered that they were very easy to understand, 9 participants (25%) answered that they were easy to understand and only 1 participant (2.8%) was neutral. Regarding the results for the readability of SDH subtitles, they were slightly lower: 24 participants (66.7%) replied that SDH subtitles were very easy to read, 5 participants (13.9%) that they were easy to read, 6 participants (16.7%) were neutral and only 1 participant (2.8%) reported that they were difficult to read. For understandability of SDH, most participants (23=63.9%) answered that they were very easy to understand, 5 participants (13.9%) answered that they were easy to understand and 8 participants (22.2%) stayed neutral.

When comparing the feedback provided for the question, 'Do you think you will be able to enjoy 360° videos with this type of subtitles? Explain your answer', 34 participants (95.2%) agreed on a positive answer, arguing that subtitles in both cases helped them to understand the plot which was in French language. Only 2 participants (5.6%) reported that they do not like subtitles. Regarding the type and size of the font, almost all participants 35 (98%) reported that size and font were easy to read and the eye became easily adapted to subtitles in this format. Only one participant (2.8%) reported that it would be a great advantage if the size could be customized. In addition, 1 participant (2.8%) with primary studies reported not having had the time to read the subtitles.

To conclude, it should be highlighted that, the selected AV contents might have had an impact on preferences and presence results, that are not directly related to the different subtitle modes. It is important to mention that the second video with a more active scene was the most preferred by all participants. According to the feedback received by all participants, aged people are willing to use HMD-VR and have more positive attitudes towards HMD-VR after a first positive experience in immersive AV content.

ANNEX 38. METHODOLOGY FOR SIGN LANGUAGE PRE-PILOT 2 ACTIONS (RBB)

1. What will be tested? (summary)

The purpose of the experiment is to gather users' feedback on different presentation modes for Sign Language. The test will have three main tasks:

- a) **Task 1.** Display of signer video: *continuous* versus *non-continuous*. I, Philip. Immersion and preferences.
 - 1) currently we produced the sign language interpreter videos as one continuous video and if there is nothing to translate the interpreter just stands still and is visible.
 - 2) in the non-continuous mode, the user will only see the sign language interpreter video window when somebody is speaking (off-speaker or on-screen speaker).
- b) **Task 2.** Sign language + Subtitles versus Sign language only. Opera content.
- c) **Task 3.** Speaker representation: *textual* versus *emoticon*. I Phillip snippets. Only preferences.
 - 1) only with emojis representing the character who is speaking together with the arrow to guide the user - both will be displayed directly under the video window.
 - 2) only textual description of character together with arrow - both will be displayed directly under the video window.

1. When?

- German Pilot: from 1st April to 1st June.

2. Who?

- German pilot: RBB. CCMA will not perform this test.

3. Stimuli

- Opera Romeo and Juliet
 - Test: Task 2.
 - Description: musical.
 - Genre: musical
 - Original language: French.
 - Duration: around 8 minutes (to be splitted in two parts).
 - Link to player: <https://imac.gpac-licensing.com/pilot-test2/>
 - Access services needed:
 - GER Sign Language with arrow
 - GER Sign Language + Responsive subtitles with indicator arrow (limited space for SUB shorter than defined characters per line)
- I, Philip (RBB)
 - Test: Task 1 and Task 3
 - Description: 23 years after Philip K. Dick's death, in 2005, David Hanson, a young engineer in robotics, revealed his first android with human form, "Phil". "I, Philip" immerses you in the memories of what could be the last love affair of the writer. But aren't these memories the fruit of the imagination of an android which learned, little by little, how to become a human?
 - Genre: Sci-Fi, drama
 - Original language: English
 - Duration: 12:26 (until the credits), to be split in two clips for Task 1 and pre-selected snippets for Task 3 https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1f1P9_r9-97cDIBTeK4vhFxrrhym0evv9SVI8baMZDaY/edit
 - Link: <https://imac.gpac-licensing.com/pilot-test2/>
 - Access services needed:
 - GER Sign Language with arrow

IDENTIFICATION CODES FOR THE STIMULI

The letters refer to the videos and the numbers to the variables:

- A1: Opera part 1 – Sign language + Subtitles
- A2: Opera part 1 – Sign language only
- B1: Opera part 2 – Sign language + Subtitles
- B2: Opera part 2 – Sign language only
- C1: I, Philip part 1 – continuous
- C2: I, Philip part 1 – non-continuous
- D1: I, Philip part 2 – continuous
- D2: I, Philip part 2 – non-continuous
- E1: I, Philip snippet 1 – text
- E2: I, Philip snippet 1 – emoticon
- F1: I, Philip snippet 2 – text
- F2: I, Philip snippet 2 – emoticon

4. Methodology: overview

- **Aim:** gather data from users about their experience with different presentation modes, replying to questions regarding immersion and preferences.
- **Experimental protocol:** users will be asked to watch different stimuli, and then report on the preferences and immersion through digital questionnaires with closed and open questions.
- **Research tools:** digital questionnaires (Google Forms or internal tools). The questionnaires will be digital in order to facilitate data processing. The questionnaires will be translated into German by the responsible for the pilot (RBB). IPQ translations will be provided by UAB.
- **Measures:** preferences and presence (immersion).
- **Participants:** Recruitment will be done via associations/organisation and/or at partners' discretion.
 - 10 participants x task. Deaf participants who are Signers.
- **Duration:** approx. 90 minutes.
- **Language of the test:** German.
- **Materials:** HMD, computer and clips.
- **Facilitators:** two facilitators will be needed. One facilitator will be the leader (welcoming participants, explaining the project, explaining the test) and another facilitator will assist the sessions (by providing the digital questionnaires and helping filling them in, providing technical assistance with the different devices, etc.).
- **Test accessibility:** adequate measures must be taken by tests organisers (RBB) so that communication with signers is fluent and a translation into SL is available. A sign language interpreter may be required.
- **Reporting:** results will be included in a report created by each partner. This will be done exporting data from the Google Form or other formats. A template will be provided. All feedback must be translated into English by the partners responsible for the pilots (RBB).
- **Testing the methodology by RBB:** please make sure you test the experimental protocol below before the actual pilot action. If the methodology needs to be improved based on this previous test, let UAB know.
- Please make sure that you have all materials and ethical forms ready before the test.

5. Methodology: experimental protocol

PLANNING

Introduction	15 min
Task 1	25 min
Task 2	20 min
Task 3	20 min
Farewell and thanks	5 min
Buffer time	5 min
Total	90 min

WORKFLOW

LATIN SQUARE FOR ALL PARTICIPANTS (if more than 10, repeat from the beginning).

Each participant will follow a different order to avoid the order of presentation affecting the results.

Participant	TASK 1	TASK 1	TASK 2	TASK 2	TASK 3	TASK 3
RBB1	A1	B2	C1	D2	E1	F2
RBB2	A2	B1	C2	D1	E2	F1
RBB3	A1	B2	C1	D2	E1	F2
RBB4	A2	B1	C2	D1	E2	F1
RBB5	A1	B2	C1	D2	E1	F2
RBB6	A2	B1	C2	D1	E2	F1
RBB7	A1	B2	C1	D2	E1	F2
RBB8	A2	B1	C2	D1	E2	F1
RBB9	A1	B2	C1	D2	E1	F2
RBB10	A2	B1	C2	D1	E2	F1

INTRODUCTION (15 min)

Who?	What?	How long?
Lead facilitator	<p>Welcome the participants, who will individually attend the test.</p> <p>Please assign a participant code when they arrive, so that they can enter that code in each online questionnaire. Codes should be as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> For RBB: RRB1, RBB2, RBB3, RBB4, etc. 	1 min
Lead facilitator	<p>Explain the project (if unknown to the participant), the aim of the test and the procedure.</p>	5 min
Assistant facilitator	<p>Provide the participant with the consent form for ethical clearance. You can find the last version here: https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1X5Nj9KxkpFVvwEuKfK6XVgz0VFUSzUOS</p> <p>If compensation is provided, please use the version here:</p>	3 min

	https://drive.google.com/open?id=11k6zNWikjikTILn5tJjnXCiNFNrKeXFC Provide signed original consent forms to UAB (next meeting or send by snail mail).	
Assistant facilitator	Provide the participant with the digital demographic questionnaire to be filled in (access to a computer/laptop will be needed): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ENG: https://goo.gl/forms/j5ZDIx8RBcRGHCsc2 • GER: https://goo.gl/forms/PTVnDQ4F6J6JPqn12 	6 min

In the following sections, the different parts of the test will be explained, including tasks and measures.

TASK 1 (25 min)

- **Measures:** preferences and immersion
- **Participants:** 10
- **Materials:**
 - **Devices:** the test will be performed with an HMD.
 - **Player:**
 - Link to the player: <https://imac.gpac-licensing.com/pilot-test2/>
 - **Stimuli:** Two comparable clips (C, D) with 2 conditions (1, 2) for each presentation mode tested, so that participants can watch both conditions in different but comparable clips to avoid a learning effect.
 - I, Philip:
 - 2 comparable clips, 5/6 min each.
- **Room:** make sure the atmosphere is comfortable for the participants, with an adequate room arrangement.

Previous to task (5 min)

The lead facilitator will explain the aim of this part: testing two different SL presentation modes. There will be two presentation modes: continuous vs non-continuous. After watching the clips, they will be asked to answer a set of questions.

The order of presentation of the stimuli will be balanced across participants. A Latin square protocol in which the presentation mode is tested with two conditions (continuous and non-continuous).

Order of presentation (please repeat up to the number of agreed participants): Please follow the Latin Square provided above.

Task (20 min):

1. The participants will be asked to watch the two randomised clips. Please follow the order specified in the Latin Square provided above.
2. The participant will have to watch 2 clips (C, D) with the randomised variables (1) continuous and 2) non-continuous). After watching **each clip**, participants will have to reply to the IPQ (presence) questionnaire to gather feedback about immersion. Please don't share technicalities with participants, only tell them they will be asked to reply some questions in the following forms:
 - a. Continuous - I, Philip:
 - i. ENG: <https://goo.gl/forms/Gq12YIURebmLLV53>
 - ii. GER: <https://goo.gl/forms/v9HL2OJxZOlAYZSQ2>
 - b. Non-continuous - I, Philip:
 - i. ENG: <https://goo.gl/forms/dlolCl3vPi2k97Eu2>
 - ii. GER: <https://goo.gl/forms/fRnmONAnz90laOK53>

IMPORTANT: Please make sure that you provide the correct IPQ questionnaire to participants depending on the order in which they are visualising the clips.

3. After watching the two clips, the participants will be asked to provide feedback about preferences:

UAB's proposal:

1. What presentation mode do you prefer?
 - a) Continuous
 - b) Non-continuous
2. Please, explain why you prefer the above indicated option.
3. Please explain why you did not choose the other option in question 1).
4. What do you think could be improved, and how?
5. Other comments:

TASK 2 (20 min)

- **Measures:** preferences
- **Participants:** 10
- **Materials:**
 - **Devices:** the test will be performed with an HMD.
 - **Player:**
 - Link to the player: <https://imac.gpac-licensing.com/pilot-test2/>
 - **Stimuli:** Two comparable clips (A, B) with 2 conditions (1, 2) for each presentation mode tested, so that participants can watch both conditions in different but comparable clips to avoid a learning effect.
 - **Opera:**
 - 2 comparable clips, 5 min each.
- **Room:** make sure the atmosphere is comfortable for the participants, with an adequate room arrangement.

Previous to task (5 min)

The lead facilitator will explain the aim of this part: testing two different presentation modes. There will be two presentation modes: SL + SUB versus SL only. After watching the clips, they will be asked to answer a set of questions.

The order of presentation of the stimuli will be balanced across participants. A Latin square protocol in which the presentation mode is tested with two conditions (SL + SUB and SL only).

Order of presentation (please repeat up to the number of agreed participants): Please follow the Latin Square provided above.

Task (20 min):

1. The participants will be asked to watch the two randomised clips. Please follow the order specified in the Latin Square provided above.
2. The participant will have to watch 2 clips (A, B) with the randomised variables (1) SL + SUB and 2) SL only). After watching **the two clips**, the participants will be asked to provide feedback about preferences:

UAB's proposal:

1. What presentation mode do you prefer?
 - a) Sign language + subtitles
 - b) Sign language only
2. Please, explain why you prefer the above indicated option.
3. Please explain why you did not choose the other option in question 1).

4. What do you think could be improved, and how?
5. How easy was it to **understand** the video with Sign language + subtitles?
 - 1- Very difficult
 - 7- Very easy
6. How easy was it to **understand** the video with Sign language only?
 - 1- Very difficult
 - 7- Very easy
7. How easy was it to **“read”** all the information with Sign language + subtitles?
 - 1- Very difficult
 - 7- Very easy
8. How easy was it to **“read”** all the information with Sign language only?
 - 1- Very difficult
 - 7- Very easy
9. Please, indicate your level of agreement with this statement: “I think “read” sign language and subtitling simultaneously is overwhelming for me.”
 - 1- Strongly disagree
 - 7- Strongly agree
10. Other comments:

TASK 3 (20 min)

- **Measures:** preferences
- **Participants:** 10
- **Materials:**
 - **Devices:** the test will be performed with an HMD.
 - **Player:**
 - Link to the player: <https://imac.gpac-licensing.com/pilot-test2/>
 - **Stimuli:** Two comparable clips (E, F) with 2 conditions (1, 2) for each presentation mode tested, so that participants can watch both conditions in different but comparable clips to avoid a learning effect.
 - I, Philip snippets:
 - 2 comparable snippets.
- **Room:** make sure the atmosphere is comfortable for the participants, with an adequate room arrangement.

Previous to task (5 min)

The lead facilitator will explain the aim of this part: testing two different SL presentation modes. There will be two presentation modes for speaker representation: textual vs emoticon. After watching the clips, they will be asked to answer a set of questions.

The order of presentation of the stimuli will be balanced across participants. A Latin square protocol in which the presentation mode is tested with two conditions.

Order of presentation (please repeat up to the number of agreed participants): Please follow the Latin Square provided above.

Task (20 min):

1. The participants will be asked to watch the two randomised clips. Please follow the order specified in the Latin Square provided above.
2. The participant will have to watch 2 clips (E, F) with the randomised variables (1) textual and 2) emoticon). After watching **the two clips**, the participants will be asked to provide feedback about preferences:

UAB’s proposal:

1. What presentation mode do you prefer for speaker representation?
 - a) Textual

b) Emoji

2. Please, explain why you prefer the above indicated option.
3. Please explain why you did not choose the other option in question 1).
4. What do you think could be improved, and how?
5. How easy was it to **know** who was speaking with the textual representation?
 - 1- Very difficult
 - 7- Very easy
6. How easy was it to **know** who was speaking with the emoticon representation?
 - 1- Very difficult
 - 7- Very easy
7. Other comments:

FAREWELL AND THANKS to participants (1 min)

REPORTING (after the tests)

Upload your report one week after the tests under Google Drive under **IMAC_SHARED_FOLDER/ WP5/ T5.1./ 2 PRE PILOT ACTIONS - 2019 / END USER – SL / PARTNER REPORTS.**

It must follow the template available in the same folder.

6. Questionnaires

Questionnaires will be provided to the participants using online forms, but is included below for reference.

Demographic questionnaire for home users – Version 1 (Annex 46)

IPQ (Immersion) (Annex 44)

ANNEX 39. SIGN LANGUAGE PRE-PILOT 2 ACTIONS REPORT (RBB)

Report for sign language pre-pilot test 2

General information

- Partner responsible: RBB
- Place and date: 06.05.19 - 24.05.19
- Access service(s) discussed: *sign language*.
- Demographic questionnaire
- Number of end users: 10

Demographics for users

1.	Sex	4 6 0 0	male female other prefer not to reply
2.	Age	38, 18, 51, 42, 46, 29, 48, 18, 15, 43	
3.	Main language of the participants:	German sign language (8x), German (2x)	
4.	Level of studies	0 0 7 0 3	no studies primary education secondary education further education university
5.	I define myself as a..."	8 0 0 2	deaf person hearing impaired person deaf-blind person other: RBB4: deafened, switches between sign language and spoken language, RBB7: person which deafened very late
6.	Age in which your disability began	8 1 0 0 1 0 0	From birth 0-4 5-12 13-20 21-40 41-60 More than 60
7.	What technology do you use on a daily basis? You can select more than one.	5 2 9 10 6 1 1	TV PC Laptop Mobile Phone Tablet Head Mounted Display (HMD) Other: Playstation

8. How often do you watch virtual reality content (for instance, 360° videos)?

	Never	Occasionally	At least once a month	At least once a week	Every day
In smartphone	9	1			
On a tablet	9	1			
On a PC	10				
In smartphone plugged to HMD	10				
In HMD	8	2			

9.	If you have never used virtual reality content such as 360° videos or only occasionally, please indicate why. Multiple answers are possible.	0 3 6 2	Because I am not interested. Because it is not accessible. Because I have not had the chance to use it. Other reasons. RBB7: I wouldn't even recognize/find, RBB8: less VR content
10.	Please state your level of agreement with the following statement: "I am interested in virtual reality content (such as 360° videos)."	3 4 3 0 0	I strongly agree I agree Neither agree nor disagree Disagree Strongly disagree
11.	Do you own any device to access virtual reality content?	3 5 2	Yes No I don't know or I don't want to reply
12.	If you replied "yes" to the previous question, please specify which device(s).		RBB4: iPhone, iPad, RBB8: PlayStation VR, RBB9: Smartphone

13. Do you like watching the following types of content on television or online?

	I like it very much	I like it	Neither like it nor dislike it	I don't like it	I don't like it at all
News	3	4	1	2	0
Fiction (series, films)	8	2			
Talk shows	1	3	4	1	1
Documentaries	5	4	1		
Sports	3	3	2	1	1
Cartoons	4	2	3	1	

14. When subtitling is available, do you activate it for the following type of content?

	Always	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
News	10			
Fiction (series, films)	10			
Talk shows	9			1
Documentaries	10			
Sports	7	2		1
Cartoons	7	3		

15.	If it is available and you do not activate it, please select the reasons why.	4 0 6	Because the interface is not accessible. Because I don't want subtitling in all the content, only in certain types of content. Other: RBB1, RBB6, RBB7: I always use subtitles if available, RBB2: if there is enough facial expression no subtitles are needed – case for cartoon, RBB4: I don't watch anything without subtitles, RBB10: does not happen
16.	How many hours a day do you watch subtitled content?	0 0 5 1 3 1	None Less than 1 hour 1-2 hours 2-3 hours 3-4 hours 4 hours or more

11.	What do you use subtitles for?	6 3 0 1	They help me understand They are my only way to have access to the dialogue I use them for language learning Other: RBB8: all three possibilities, RBB7: would like to choose option and 1 and 2

Summary:

6 female and 4 male users aged between 15 and 51 took part in the tests. 2 users indicated German as mother tongue and 8 indicated German sign language. Most of the users had at least a secondary education or higher. 10 testers saw themselves as deaf and one of them indicated that he/she got deaf very late. Another person stated that he/she deafened and switches between sign language and spoken language. For almost all users, the impairment began at birth or below the age of 4, while for 1 user the impairment started between 21 and 40 years.

The technical device used most often on a daily basis was a smartphone (10 users), followed by laptop (9 users), tablet (6 users) and TV (5 users), while PC and HMD were least often used (both 3 users). Almost all of the users had never watched VR content before, mostly because they had not had the chance to (6 users) or it is not accessible (3 users). Two users indicated as further reasons that there is not much VR content available or they wouldn't be able to find it.

When directly asked if they were interested in VR content, most of the testers agreed while some were not sure. The majority of the users do not own a device to access VR content.

In terms of content preferences, the majority of the testers liked fiction, news and documentaries, while some also liked sports, talk shows and cartoons. Almost all of them used subtitles for all types of content and a smaller group indicated that they do not activate subtitles because the interface is not accessible. Only one tester who did not always use subtitles explained that he/she only uses ST for certain types of content as it is possible to read from the lips.

Most of the users consume subtitles between 1 and 4 hours and the majority of the testers use ST because they help them to understand or it is the only way to have access to the dialogue.

TASK 1 – continuous vs. non-continuous

IPQ – Continuous (I, Philip)

IPQ Question	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1. In the computer generated world I had a sense of "being there".				1	4	2	2
2. Somehow I felt that the virtual world surrounded me.				1	3	3	2
3. I felt like I was just perceiving pictures.	4	1	1	1			2
4. I did not feel present in the virtual space.	3	3	1			2	
5. I had a sense of acting in the virtual space, rather than operating something from outside.	2	2	1			3	1
6. I felt present in the virtual space.					1	4	4
7. How aware were you of the real world surrounding while navigating in the virtual world? (i.e. sounds, room temperature, other people, etc.)?	2		1	2	2	1	1
8. I was not aware of my real environment.		3		1	1	1	3
9. I still paid attention to the real environment.	3	2			1	2	1
10. I was completely captivated by the virtual world.					2	4	3
11. How real did the virtual world seem to you?	2		1	1	2	2	1
12. How much did your experience in the virtual environment seem consistent with your real world experience ?	2	3	2		2		
13. How real did the virtual world seem to you?		1	1		2	4	1
14.The virtual world seemed more realistic than the real world.	5	2	1	1			

IPQ – Non-continuous (I, Philip)

IPQ Question	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1. In the computer generated world I had a sense of "being there".			1		1	3	4
2. Somehow I felt that the virtual world surrounded me.			2	1	1	3	2
3. I felt like I was just perceiving pictures.	3	1	1	1	1		2
4. I did not feel present in the virtual space.	3	3	1		1	1	
5. I had a sense of acting in the virtual space, rather than operating something from Outside.	3	1	1			3	1
6. I felt present in the virtual space.		1		1	1	4	3
7. How aware were you of the real world surrounding while navigating in the virtual world? (i.e. sounds, room temperature, other people, etc.)?	2			3	1	2	1
8. I was not aware of my real environment.	1	1	4				3
9. I still paid attention to the real environment.	3	2	1			2	1
10. I was completely captivated by the virtual world.				1	1	4	3
11. How real did the virtual world seem to you?	2	1		3	2	1	
12. How much did your experience in the virtual environment seem consistent with your real world experience ?	3	2			2	1	1
13. How real did the virtual world seem to you?	1	1	1		3	1	2
14.The virtual world seemed more realistic than the real world.	4	3	1	1			

Concerning the presentation of continuous or non-continuous sign language interpreting, median scores for each subscale on the IPQ questionnaire are:

	General Presence	Spatial Presence	Involvement	Experienced Realism
Continuous	4	3.60	4.13	2.5
Non-Continuous	5	3.60	3.75	2.5

The comparison of each of the subscales of IPQ questionnaire with the Wilcoxon Signed Ranks test does not show any significant difference between the two conditions (General presence $Z=-.604$, $p= .546$, ties=3 ; Spatial presence $Z=-1.532$, $p=.125$, ties=3 ; Involvement $Z=-.341$, $p=.733$, ties=3; Experienced realism $Z= -.421$, $p= .674$, ties=2).

Preferences continuous vs. non-continuous

RBB1 is missing due to a technical error while saving the online questionnaire.

1. What presentation mode do you prefer?

a) Continuous	b) Non-continuous
3	6

2. Please, explain why you prefer the above indicated option.

RBB2: Non-continuous: it is easier to concentrate on the video

RBB3: Non-continuous: concentration on video

RBB4: Non-continuous: free view on everything, if there are no noises and dialogues

RBB5: Non-continuous: I can see if something is being said or not.

RBB6: Continuous: better overview. This option is more like the real-world situation with a real SL interpreter

RBB7: Non-continuous: Focusing on the video is more relaxed. I am informed that there is no dialogue.

RBB8: Continuous: Security that the interpreter is there

RBB9: Continuous: always clear that everything is working

RBB10: Non-continuous: You focus too much on the interpreter when it's always visible.

3. Please explain why you did not choose the other option in question 1).

RBB2: more disturbing

RBB3: constantly obscures the film

RBB4: constant expectation that communication starts

RBB5: If it is constantly visible, I don't know when somebody starts speaking again

RBB6: I keep thinking there is a technical problem.

RBB7: The SL video obscures part of the main video, the eyes keep focusing on the SL video, the surrounding video is more in the background.

RBB8: it is like I don't hear nothing, loss of orientation

RBB9: unclear why the sign language interpreter appears and disappears

RBB10: You focus too much on the interpreter when it is always visible.

4. What do you think could be improved, and how?

RBB2: SL should slightly be more in the middle and less out-of-focus

RBB3: signer with the background removed

RBB4: Please position SL video more centrally so that you don't look to the right (below).

RBB5: SL video should be more in the middle

RBB6: Names of characters below SL video would be good. SL video larger and more in the middle would be good (as personalization option).

RBB7: SL video should be variable, tailored to the individual needs; arrows could have colour

RBB8: possibility to interact

RBB9: it should be possible to select subtitles and/or sign language interpreter, size of sign language interpreter should be adjustable

5. Other comments:

RBB3: differentiate between sound and dialogues

RBB7: Please implement soon 😊

RBB8: sign language interpreter should be more in the middle, is too far out

RBB9: position was too far outside, method to identify speaker should be selectable, quality of service is important

TASK 2

Preferences – Open questions - SL only vs. SL and ST

1. What presentation mode do you prefer?

a) Sign language + subtitles	b) Sign language only
6	4

2. Please, explain why you prefer the above indicated option.

RBB1: SL only: I can concentrate better

RBB2: SL only: SL is enough and I understand it better

RBB3: SL & ST: coloured ST gives me a better understanding of role changes

RBB4: SL & ST: Especially in this video I could better understand who was talking. Furthermore the ST were more in the middle of the viewing field

RBB5: SL only: It is too much. I prefer having either SL video or ST only.

RBB6: SL & ST: Because of the colour it was easier to understand who was speaking, I could follow the dialogue better. ST was directly below the viewing direction, which is better for the eyes.

RBB7: SL & ST: Since I got deaf at a high age, German is my mother tongue. Therefore I have to concentrate on the SL interpreter a bit more. I perceive ST more intuitively and understanding is more relaxed.

RBB8: SL & ST: music with subtitles is better, also personal identification with colours is easier

RBB9: SL & ST: I'm faster with subtitles.

RBB10: SL only: both services together are more disturbing

3. Please explain why you did not choose the other option in question 1).

RBB1: both together are too much

RBB2: don't need the subtitles

RBB3: Less possibilities regarding expression

RBB4: Because of the rather complicated language of the content (Opera) and because of the many people involved in speaking, the ST helped understanding on top of the SL video

RBB5: -

RBB6: Not enough information. I did not always understand who was being translated.

RBB7: German sign language is not my mother tongue

RBB8: sign language interpreter transfers more emotions

RBB9: The picture was blurred, so too much attention was paid to the interpreter.

RBB10: Two at a time bother me. I was distracted by the change of the colour of the subtitles.

4. What do you think could be improved, and how?

RBB1: SL should slightly be more in the middle

RBB2: SL should be less out-of-focus

RBB3: add information about background music and off-speaker information

RBB4: Fade out SL video together with ST (i.e. non-continuous) and move a little bit more to the middle of the viewing field. Show the change of speakers better/differently with the SL video. When older languages are used, the artistic realization of the SL interpretation could be even better.

RBB5: Transparent background of SL video.

RBB6: Maybe show the ST below the SL video (both in the middle). Semi-transparent box as background for ST not so good as contrast.

RBB7: Adapt the SL video to the needs of the user. Maybe dynamically adapt the SL video to the dialogue (change from left to right).

RBB8: subtitles a little bit larger

RBB9: Choice of a combination of both. With UT the SL video can go into corner. Otherwise not.

RBB10: choice to have only one service

5. How easy was it to understand the video with Sign language + subtitles?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7- very easy
	2			1	1	6

6. How easy was it to understand the video with Sign language only?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7- very easy
		1	3		3	3

7. How easy was it to “read” all the information with Sign language + subtitles?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7- very easy
	1		1	1	3	4

8. How easy was it to “read” all the information with Sign language only?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7- very easy
		1	1	2	4	2

9. Please, indicate your level of agreement with this statement: “I think “read” sign language and subtitling simultaneously is overwhelming for me.”

1- strongly disagree	2	3	4	5	6	7- strongly agree
2	2	1	1	1		3

10. Other comments:

RBB1: video quality of I,Philip and Opera was not so good, but I got used to it from the third video, challenge of use because many impressions

RBB3: I can understand the content also without sign language and only with coloured subtitles

RBB4: For me SL & ST together are ideal. Keep going with the research and development!

RBB7: Both services at once do not make sense in my eyes. Each user has his needs and should be able to choose one of both services.

RBB8: subtitles plus sign language interpreter plus video is too much, can't follow all

RBB9: I can only follow one service not both

RBB10: -

TASK 3

Preferences (emoji vs text)

1. What presentation mode do you prefer for speaker representation?

a) Textual	b) Emoji
7	3

2. Please, explain why you prefer the above indicated option.

RBB1: Text: clearer

RBB2: Text: Text is clearer and its colour helps to identify the speaker (additional note by interviewer: emojis are more for younger people – comment was made by an 18 year old tester)

RBB3: Text: I'm used to having coloured subtitles

RBB4: Emojis: The current speaker is very easy to find/recognize with the emojis

RBB5: Emojis: Easier to understand who is speaking

RBB6: text: Text was clearer.

RBB7: text: The text gives clear information.

RBB8: text: I'm used to it, and have additionally the colours

RBB9: text: clear identification of speaker

RBB10: Text: I know better who is speaking.

3. Please explain why you did not choose the other option in question 1).

RBB1: Emojis are more for children

RBB2: I need more time to understand the emojis

RBB3: Emojis are unknown to me, but they are trendsetting

RBB4: With the written text I expected ST and had to "think" in order to know who is who.

RBB5: The names change very quickly, this was not so apparent with the emojis. More comfortable for the eyes.

RBB6: Emojis did not fit the characters very well, weren't so accurate.

RBB7: Emojis are vague and unclear and leave room for interpretation. Interpretation needs time and at a certain point you lag behind in the film.

RBB8 is okay, but not unusual

RBB9: Emojis are not clear enough

RBB10: Emojis are confusing for me.

4. What do you think could be improved, and how?

RBB1: -

RBB2: -

RBB3: Emojis should be larger

RBB4: Nothing.

RBB5: -

RBB6: Maybe emojis and text could be combined.

RBB7: Leave away emojis 😊

RBB8: Emojis should be larger and above the sign language interpreter

RBB9: timing is very important

RBB10: -

5. How easy was it to know who was speaking with the textual representation?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7- very easy
				3	2	5

6. How easy was it to know who was speaking with the emoticon representation?

1- very difficult	2	3	4	5	6	7- very easy
	2		1	2	2	3

7. Other comments:

RBB1: The name Philip was misleading in the video example as the character's nickname is Phil – tester thought that it might be an additional character

RBB3: Emojis were not bad

RBB4: With emojis it was very very clear to identify the speaker, that's why I prefer them, especially when switching on the film halfway through.

RBB5: I pay more attention to SL video or ST, not so much to what is displayed below.

RBB6: Maybe the name of the person could be displayed at the position of the speaker. The arrow showed the direction of the speaker but when I turned and there were two speakers there, I didn't know who was speaking.

RBB8: colours make it easier to identify speaker, it was easier to grasp the emojis but they were nameless

RBB9: Timing with Emojis or text was wrong. Introduction of names is important.

RBB10: -

Conclusions

TASK 1 continuous vs. non-continuous sign language interpreter

A slight majority of the users preferred the non-continuous sign-language interpreter. The main reason for their choice was that it is easier to concentrate on the main content (360° video) and look around freely. Those users who preferred the continuous sign language interpreter expressed that they know for sure that the interpreter is there like it would be in a real-world situation and that there is no technical problem.

Consequently, we recommend giving the user the choice which presentation mode he or she prefers and offering both options as personalisation setting.

Improvements:

SL video should be positioned slightly more in the middle as it was too far outside. One user even proposed to have the SL video in general centrally in the field of view.

Arrow should be in the same colour as the subtitles to indicate different speakers

TASK 2 - SL only vs. SL and ST

The presentation of SL and ST together was in general accepted by the users although only 6 of 10 users stated this as a preference.

The users expressed that the advantages to have both services together were 1) the colour of the subtitles helped to identify the speaker and 2) especially in the Opera content the subtitles transported more information than the sign language interpretation.

We would like to give the user the choice to activate both services if they want to.

Improvements:

Sign language video should be slightly more in the middle

TASK 3 – speaker presentation textual vs. emojis

A clear majority of 7 users preferred the textual speaker presentation. The main reason was that the text enables a fast and easy identification of the speaker. Emojis give room for interpretation and the representation of the speaker was not accurate enough.

ANNEX 40. METHODOLOGY FOR SPANISH AND GERMAN PILOT 2

1. Shared methodological approach

Procedure

- Short introduction to the project and to the specific pilot action.
- Data privacy info and informed consent. Users need to explicitly accept it.
- Enable autoplay in your browser (short screencast).
- Free viewing, with no services activated. Objective data are tracked during this free viewing.
- Final questionnaire.

Objective data tracking

Using Google Analytics, i2Cat can gather data on:

Users:

- Random id
- Region and access time
- Type of device
- Browser
- New user or previous user

ImAc portal

- Options and settings used and the selected video, including timestamps for each action.

Videos (and including time-stamps for each selection)

- Duration of video playout
- Access services selected, and for how long
- Settings in the player menu used/enabled
- Playout controls used
- Viewing directions (latitude and longitude angles)
- Options and settings

QoS and QoE related metrics

- Device id and selected video
- The startup delay (delay since pressing play and actually watching the video)
- Throughput (effective bandwidth)
- Video quality selected in each iteration.
- Current playout buffer fullness level.
- Playout time evolution.
- Viewing direction (latitude and longitude angles).

Questionnaire: Feedback on 360° videos with subtitles and/or sign language

10. Age:
11. I define myself as...
 - a. A hearing person
 - b. A person with hearing loss
12. Have you watched 360 contents before? Yes/No.
13. How did you watch the 360 content? PC/HMD/tablet/mobile phone
14. Did you use the subtitles? Yes/No.
 - a. If yes, how much did you like...

- i. Arrow (menu under indicator) (****) / I did not use it.
 - ii. Radar (menu under indicator) (****) I did not use it.
 - iii. Size personalisation (****) I did not use it.
 - iv. Position personalisation (****) I did not use it.
 - v. Background personalisation (****) I did not use it
 - vi. Subtitle control with mouse/controller (****) I did not use it
- 15. (only for RBB pilot) Did you use Sign Language? Yes/No.
 - a. If yes, how much did you like...
 - i. Arrow (menu under indicator) (****) / I did not use it.
 - ii. Radar (menu under indicator) (****) I did not use it.
 - iii. Size personalisation (****) I did not use it.
 - iv. Position personalisation (****) I did not use it.
 - v. Display of subtitles and sign language together (****) / I did not use it.
 - vi. Name of speaker under SL video window (****) / I did not use it.
 - vii. SL interpreter only visible when someone is speaking (menu under Dynamic)(****) / I did not use it.
 - viii. The drag-and-drop functionality of the sign language interpreter (****) / I did not use it.
- 16. (only pilots for synchronisation in CS at CCMA) Did you like having the traditional content on a main screen and an immersive 360 content on your second device? Yes/No/I didn't use it.
- 17. How easy to use was the player? (very difficult**** very easy)
- 18. Would you recommend the player to your friends? Yes/No.
- 19. If you want, you can give us additional feedback here. (non-compulsory text field)

3.2. Content

German pilot

Content:

- **I, Philip**: ready with accessibility services, ST and SL .
- **360° Abendschau**: ready with accessibility services, ST and SL.

Spanish pilot

- **Making of TN'**: 360 and traditional productions with accessibility services (ST).
- **'Making Off FAQs'**: 360 and traditional productions with accessibility services (ST).
- **'Sant Jordi's Day'**: 360 and traditional productions ready with accessibility services (ST).
- **'Cuines'**: 360 and traditional productions with accessibility services (ST).
- **'Romeo and Juliet'**: 360 production and traditional productions with accessibility services (ST).
- **'Desconcert 1'**: 360 production with accessibility services (ST).
- **'Desconcert 2'**: 360 production with accessibility services (ST).

ANNEX 41. PILOT 2 REPORT (RBB)

1. General information

Status: 16.03.20

Partner responsible: Rundfunk Berlin-Brandenburg

Place and date: 17.02.20 – 17.03.20

Access service(s) discussed: *subtitling/SL*.

2. Questionnaire results

Total number of end users: 31

Age: mean of 41

	age	%
1	no answer	3.2
1	17	3.2
1	23	3.2
1	25	3.2
1	26	3.2
1	32	3.2
2	35	6.7
1	36	3.2
1	38	3.2
2	39	6.7
4	40	13.3
1	43	3.2
1	52	3.2
1	45	3.2
1	50	3.2
2	53	6.7
1	55	3.2
1	56	3.2
1	59	3.2
2	60	6.7
2	62	6.7
1	64	3.2

I define myself as...:	...a hearing person.	20 (65%)
	...a person with hearing loss.	11 (35%)
Have you watched 360 contents before?	Yes	21 (68%)
	No	10 (32%)
How did you watch the 360 content?	PC	24 (77%)
	HMD	4 (13%)
	tablet	3 (10%)
	mobile phone	5 (16%)

Did you use the subtitles? 25 x "Yes" (81%), 6 x "No" (19%)

If yes, did you like...

	1	2	3	4	5	total	I did not use it.
Arrow	1	0	2	7	7	17	8
Radar	1	1	3	8	4	17	8
Size personalisation	2	1	4	6	6	19	6
Position personalisation	1	2	3	4	11	21	4
Background personalisation	3	1	5	4	4	17	8
Move subtitles with mouse/controller	1	0	5	6	5	17	8

Did you use Sign Language? 17 x "Yes", 14 x "No"

If yes, how much did you like...

	1	2	3	4	5	total	I did not use it.
Arrow	1	0	0	4	6	11	6
Radar	2	0	0	5	3	10	7
Size personalisation	2	1	2	4	3	12	5
Position personalisation	2	0	2	2	8	14	3
Display of subtitles and SL together	1	1	2	3	6	13	4
Name of the speaker under SL video window	2	0	0	3	9	14	3
SL interpreter only visible when someone is speaking	2	0	3	2	4	11	6
The drag-and-drop functionality of the sign language interpreter	2	0	1	3	5	11	6

How easy to use was the player? (very difficult* * * * * very easy)

*	**	***	****	*****
Very difficult				Very easy
1	0	7	13	8

Would you recommend the player to your friends? 25 x "Yes", 6 x "No"

If you want, you can give us additional feedback here.

There was a technical problem with the crime scene content. It returns to a green background three times. I need to find the video image in the garage.

I'm not a technical skilled person. That's why I'm so happy to be able to participate here and support you. I was surprised how easy I got in here. For me, it must be as easy to use as possible and what you

are offering now already corresponds to my expectations. It is important for me that in the future all broadcasts are subtitled or signed in this way. Keep going!

Sometimes the sign language interpreter jumped to an unpredictable spot when I switched him on. This confused me a little.

On PC (unlike on smartphones) the film quality was not so good. Also, the movie started slowly, and the menu bar worked only conditionally. Sometimes you had to click several times to activate something. It's a pity that you can't move the subtitles and the sign language interpreter on the smartphone.

Subtitles with outline: The border is too narrow and poor contrast (color)

"...you have to practice; it is difficult to understand it the first time "

I tested with a pixel 3a and it was not possible to use the player with the cardboard

On the PC it is rather boring, because I have to "look around" with the mouse, but this was to be expected.

I found the video partly quite blurred. It was blurred at the beginning in the editorial department, then sharper at the House of Representatives and then again blurred in the control room.

I was not able to activate the subtitles.

In the Firefox browser of my VR glasses (Pico 2) the 360° video was distorted, so I switched to the browser on my PC.

I found subtitles fixed to the speaker unattractive, because so much of the speaker was overlaid.

Moving the sign language/subtitles was only possible to a limited extent, and the videos were paused or paused automatically during this time. /

Radar was for me a little more distracting than the arrow indicator. /

As far as possible, please display the indicators a little earlier in order to be able to react more adequately as a reader (especially for short sentences with frequent speaker changes).

If you watch the videos with subtitles, you sometimes have to search a bit until you 'find' the person who is talking (e.g. in the video of the crime scene in the underground car park). But maybe I didn't try all possibilities for this. All in all I like the project (as a hearing person) very much.

Conclusions

Subtitles

The personalization of the position (82% - based on all ratings) followed by arrow and radar (each 71% - based on all ratings) were rated very positive with 4 or 5 which leads to the conclusion that they are very important for the consumption.

Sign Language

It is noticeable that the functionality of the arrow as indicator leading to the speaker (91% - based on all ratings) and the name under the SL video (86% - based on all ratings) are rated very positive.

Overall satisfaction with player

Most of the users like the player and would recommend it to a friend. The respective users which answered that they wouldn't recommend it to a friend unfortunately did not give additional feedback in the open text field so that reasons cannot be identified.

ANNEX 42. PILOT 2 REPORT (CCMA)

1. General information

- Partner responsible: CCMA
- Place and date: Spain – February 2020
- Access service discussed: Subtitling

2. Questionnaire results

- Total number of end users: 44
Demographics for users (include absolute number and percentage, please)

1. Age:

15y,16y(x2),26,27y,30y(x2),31,32,33,34,35,36,40,42(x3),44,46y(x2),49y
(x2),50y,51y,53y,54y,55y(x2),56y,57y,58y(x2),59y(x3),60, 61,62,63,64,66,67, 84.

2. I define myself as:

“a hearing person” : 33 (75%)

“a person with hearing loss”: 11 (25%)

3. Have you watched 360 contents before?

Yes: 32 users (72.72%)

No: 12 users (27.27%)

4. How did you watch the 360 content?

PC: 25 users (56.81%)

HMD: 24 users (54.54%)

Tablet: 16 users (36.36%)

Smartphone: 18 users (40.9%)

5. Did you use the subtitles?

Yes: 30 users (68.18%)

No: 14 users (31.81%)

If yes, did you like...

i.

	1	2	3	4	5	I did not use it
Arrow	0	0	6 (20%)	10 (33.3%)	13 (43.3%)	1 (3.3%)
Radar	5 (16.7%)	6 (20%)	7 (23.3%)	4 (13.3%)	5 (16.7%)	3 (10%)
Size personalisation	0	1 (3.3%)	4 (13.3%)	15 (50%)	9 (30%)	1 (3.3%)
Position personalisation	0	3 (10%)	4 (13.3%)	13 (43.4%)	9 (30%)	1 (3.3%)
Background personalisation	0	1 (3.3%)	5 (16.7%)	13 (43.4%)	9 (30%)	2 (6.7%)
Move subtitles with mouse/controller	0	4 (13.3%)	7 (23.3%)	6 (20%)	11 (36.7%)	2 (6.7%)

6. Did you like having the traditional content on a main screen and an immersive 360 content on your second device?

Yes : 30 users (68.18%)
 No : 2 users (4.5%)
 I didn't use it : 12 users (27.27%)

7. How easy to use was the player? (very difficult* * * * * very easy)

*	**	***	****	*****
Very difficult				Very easy
1	1	11	19	12

8. Would you recommend the player to your friends?

Yes : 40 users (90.9%)
 No : 4 users (9.1%)

9. If you want, you can give us additional feedback here.

- A very good option that allows you to enjoy more.
- Motivating and pleasant experience, teleporting to distant realities, seeing again in more detail a content that you have already seen, and being able to see in a space so small as the screen of a Smartphone large spaces regardless of the direction you choose.
- HMD impact and are very useful in informative content.
- A new experience that is very useful for impaired people.
- A breakthrough so that everyone can enjoy accessible immersive content.

3. Conclusions

Majority of the comments from users about the ImAc experience are positive. The HMD is not much available at homes but a general opinion points that is a question of a short time because is an spectacular and very interesting experience. Accessibility in this type of contents is welcome.

a) Subtitles

- Subtitles should be with background or in bold presentation to make it easy to be read.
- The elder people find difficult to follow subtitle in two devices.
- Most preferred the subtitle in the lower position.

b) Sign Language

c) Companion screen

- CS Not for use only one person.
- When you look at a content for the first time it is not useful enough.
- It is quite difficult to follow ST in both devices.
- As a person with hearing loos , CS does not give you more help. Usually you only look at one device.
- It is easy to get lost in the content. You don't pay enough attention.
- Is interesting in a second play of the content.
- In CS you can choose different points of view just for curiosity.

d) Overall satisfaction with player

A very high percentage of users were satisfied with the player, although there were critical comments related to the lack of information on how to use it, and somehow difficulties in saving user preferences.

ANNEX 43. SUS QUESTIONNAIRE

Original English version

	Strongly disagree				Strongly agree
1. I think that I would like to use this system frequently	<input type="checkbox"/>				
	1	2	3	4	5
2. I found the system unnecessarily complex	<input type="checkbox"/>				
	1	2	3	4	5
3. I thought the system was easy to use	<input type="checkbox"/>				
	1	2	3	4	5
4. I think that I would need the support of a technical person to be able to use this system	<input type="checkbox"/>				
	1	2	3	4	5
5. I found the various functions in this system were well integrated	<input type="checkbox"/>				
	1	2	3	4	5
6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in this system	<input type="checkbox"/>				
	1	2	3	4	5
7. I would imagine that most people would learn to use this system very quickly	<input type="checkbox"/>				
	1	2	3	4	5
8. I found the system very cumbersome to use	<input type="checkbox"/>				
	1	2	3	4	5
9. I felt very confident using the system	<input type="checkbox"/>				
	1	2	3	4	5
10. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with this system	<input type="checkbox"/>				
	1	2	3	4	5

German version: Fragebogen zur System-Gebrauchstauglichkeit

Stimme überhaupt nicht zu – 1	2	3	4	Stimme voll zu – 5
-------------------------------	---	---	---	--------------------

1. Ich denke, dass ich das System gerne häufig benutzen würde.
2. Ich fand das System unnötig komplex.
3. Ich fand das System einfach zu benutzen.
4. Ich glaube, ich würde die Hilfe einer technisch versierten Person benötigen, um das System benutzen zu können.
5. Ich fand, die verschiedenen Funktionen in diesem System waren gut integriert.
6. Ich denke, das System enthielt zu viele Inkonsistenzen.
7. Ich kann mir vorstellen, dass die meisten Menschen den Umgang mit diesem System sehr schnell lernen.
8. Ich fand das System sehr umständlich zu nutzen.
9. Ich fühlte mich bei der Benutzung des Systems sehr sicher.
10. Ich musste eine Menge lernen, bevor ich anfangen konnte das System zu verwenden.

Catalan version

totalment en desacord – 1	2	3	4	totalment d'acord – 5
---------------------------	---	---	---	-----------------------

1. Crec que utilitzaria aquest sistema amb freqüència.
2. Penso que el sistema és massa complex.
3. Crec que el sistema és fàcil d'utilitzar.
4. Crec que em caldria suport tècnic per a poder utilitzar aquest sistema.
5. Penso que les diferents funcions d'aquest sistema estan ben integrades.
6. Penso que el sistema presenta massa inconsistències.
7. Crec que la majoria de gent aprendria a utilitzar el sistema molt ràpidament.
8. Penso que el sistema és incòmode d'utilitzar.
9. M'he sentit molt segur utilitzant el sistema.
10. He hagut d'aprendre moltes coses abans de fer-lo anar.

Spanish version

totalmente en desacuerdo – 1	2	3	4	totalmente de acuerdo – 5
------------------------------	---	---	---	---------------------------

1. Creo que me gustaría usar este sistema frecuentemente.
2. Me ha parecido innecesariamente complejo este sistema.
3. El sistema me ha parecido fácil de usar.
4. Creo que necesitaría la ayuda de una persona con conocimientos técnicos para usar este sistema.
5. Me ha parecido que las distintas funciones de este sistema están bien integradas.
6. Creo que el sistema es demasiado inconsistente.
7. Imagino que la mayoría de la gente aprendería a usar este sistema de forma muy rápida.
8. El sistema me ha parecido engorroso.
9. Tenía muy claro cómo usar este sistema todo el rato.
10. Tuve que adquirir muchos conocimientos antes de poder usar este sistema.

ANNEX 44. IPQ QUESTIONNAIRE

English IPQ Items

Source: <http://www.igroup.org/pq/ipq/download.php>

Number	PQ/II Nr. (internal)	IPQ item name	shortcut	loading on ...	English question	English anchors	Copyright (item source)
1	s62	G1	sense of being there	PRES	In the computer generated world I had a sense of "being there"	not at all--very much	Slater & Usoh (1994)
2	s44	SP1	sense of VE behind	SP	Somehow I felt that the virtual world surrounded me.	fully disagree--fully agree	IPQ
3	s30	SP2	only pictures	SP	I felt like I was just perceiving pictures.	fully disagree--fully agree	IPQ
4	s28	SP3	not sense of being in v. space	SP	I did not feel present in the virtual space.	did not feel--felt present	???
5	s31	SP4	sense of acting in VE	SP	I had a sense of acting in the virtual space, rather than operating something from outside.	fully disagree--fully agree	IPQ
6	s33	SP5	sense of being present in VE	SP	I felt present in the virtual space.	fully disagree--fully agree	IPQ
7	s64	INV1	awareness of real env.	INV	How aware were you of the real world surrounding while navigating in the virtual world? (i.e. sounds, room temperature, other people, etc.)?	extremely aware--moderately aware--not aware at all	Witmer & Singer (1994)

8	s37	INV2	not aware of real env.	INV	I was not aware of my real environment.	fully disagree-- fully agree	IPQ
9	s40	INV3	no attention to real env.	INV	I still paid attention to the real environment.	fully disagree-- fully agree	IPQ
10	s38	INV4	attention captivated by VE	INV	I was completely captivated by the virtual world.	fully disagree-- fully agree	IPQ
11	s48	REAL1	VE real (real/not real)	REAL	How real did the virtual world seem to you?	completely real--not real at all	Hendrix (1994)
12	s7	REAL2	experience similar to real env.	REAL	How much did your experience in the virtual environment seem consistent with your real world experience ?	not consistent-- moderately consistent-- very consistent	Witmer & Singer (1994)
13	s59	REAL3	VE real (imagined/real)	REAL	How real did the virtual world seem to you?	about as real as an imagined world-- indistinguishable from the real world	Carlin, Hoffman, & Weghorst (1997)
14	s47	REAL4	VE wirklich	REAL	The virtual world seemed more realistic than the real world.	fully disagree-- fully agree	IPQ

German IPQ Items

Number	IPQ item name	German question	German anchors
1	G1	In der computererzeugten Welt hatte ich den Eindruck, dort gewesen zu sein...	überhaupt nicht--sehr stark
2	SP1	Ich hatte das Gefühl, daß die virtuelle Umgebung hinter mir weitergeht.	trifft gar nicht zu- -trifft völlig zu
3	SP2	Ich hatte das Gefühl, nur Bilder zu sehen.	trifft gar nicht zu- -trifft völlig zu
4	SP3	Ich hatte nicht das Gefühl, in dem virtuellen Raum zu sein.	hatte nicht das Gefühl--hatte das Gefühl
5	SP4	Ich hatte das Gefühl, in dem virtuellen Raum zu handeln statt etwas von außen zu bedienen.	trifft gar nicht zu- -trifft völlig zu
6	SP5	Ich fühlte mich im virtuellen Raum anwesend.	trifft gar nicht zu- -trifft völlig zu
7	INV1	Wie bewußt war Ihnen die reale Welt, während Sie sich durch die virtuelle Welt bewegten (z.B. Geräusche, Raumtemperatur, andere Personen etc.)?	extrem bewußt-mittelmäßig bewußt-unbewußt
8	INV2	Meine reale Umgebung war mir nicht mehr bewußt.	trifft gar nicht zu- -trifft völlig zu
9	INV3	Ich achtete noch auf die reale Umgebung.	trifft gar nicht zu- -trifft völlig zu
10	INV4	Meine Aufmerksamkeit war von der virtuellen Welt völlig in Bann gezogen.	trifft gar nicht zu- -trifft völlig zu
11	REAL1	Wie real erschien Ihnen die virtuelle Umgebung?	vollkommen real-weder noch- gar nicht real
12	REAL2	Wie sehr glich Ihr Erleben der virtuellen Umgebung dem Erleben einer realen Umgebung?	überhaupt nicht-etwas- vollständig
13	REAL3	Wie real erschien Ihnen die virtuelle Welt?	wie eine vorgestellte Welt- - nicht zu unterscheiden von der realen Welt
14	REAL4	Die virtuelle Welt erschien mir wirklicher als die reale Welt.	trifft gar nicht zu- -trifft völlig zu

Catalan IPQ Items

Number	loading on ...	Catalan question	Catalan anchors
1	PRES	En el món generat per ordinador, he tingut la sensació de "trobar-m'hi a dins".	de cap manera--moltíssim
2	SP	He sentit que en certa manera el món virtual m'envoltava.	totalment en desacord--totalment d'acord
3	SP	He sentit com si només veiés fotografies	totalment en desacord--totalment d'acord
4	SP	No m'he sentit present en l'espai virtual.	no m'hi he sentit present--m'hi he sentit present
5	SP	He tingut la sensació d'estar dins l'espai virtual, en lloc de mirar-m'ho des de fora.	totalment en desacord--totalment d'acord
6	SP	M'he sentit present a l'espai virtual.	totalment en desacord--totalment d'acord
7	INV	Fins a quin punt eres conscient del món real que t'envoltava quan navegaves pel món virtual? (per exemple, sorolls, temperatura de la sala, altres persones, etc.)	molt conscient--moderadament conscient--gens conscient
8	INV	No era conscient de l'entorn real que m'envoltava.	totalment en desacord--totalment d'acord
9	INV	He continuat parant atenció al món real que m'envoltava.	totalment en desacord--totalment d'acord
10	INV	Estava totalment captivat pel món virtual.	totalment en desacord--totalment d'acord
11	REAL	Fins a quin punt t'ha semblat real, el món virtual?	totalment real--gens real
12	REAL	Fins a quin punt l'experiència en el món virtual t'ha semblat comparable a l'experiència en el món real?	gens - moderadament- molt
13	REAL	Fins a quin punt t'ha semblat real, el món virtual?	tan real com un món imaginat--impossible de distingir del món real
14	REAL	El món virtual m'ha semblat més realista que el món real.	totalment en desacord--totalment d'acord

Spanish IPQ items

Number	loading on ...	Spanish question	Spanish anchors
1	PRES	En el mundo virtual generado por ordenador, he tenido la sensación de “estar dentro”.	en absoluto--muchísimo
2	SP	En cierto modo, he sentido que el mundo virtual me rodeaba.	totalmente en desacuerdo-- totalmente de acuerdo
3	SP	He sentido como si viera fotografías.	totalmente en desacuerdo-- totalmente de acuerdo
4	SP	No me he sentido presente en el espacio virtual.	no me he sentido presente-- me he sentido presente
5	SP	He tenido la sensación de estar dentro del espacio virtual, en lugar de observarlo desde fuera.	totalmente en desacuerdo-- totalmente de acuerdo
6	SP	Me he sentido presente en el espacio virtual.	totalmente en desacuerdo-- totalmente de acuerdo
7	INV	¿Hasta qué punto eras consciente del mundo real que te rodeaba mientras navegabas por el mundo virtual (por ejemplo, sonidos, la temperatura de la habitación, otras personas, etc.)?	Muy consciente- moderadamente consciente- nada consciente
8	INV	No era consciente del entorno real que me rodeaba.	totalmente en desacuerdo-- totalmente de acuerdo
9	INV	He continuado prestando atención al mundo real que me rodeaba.	totalmente en desacuerdo-- totalmente de acuerdo
10	INV	Estaba totalmente cautivado/a por el mundo virtual.	totalmente en desacuerdo-- totalmente de acuerdo
11	REAL	¿Hasta qué punto te ha parecido real el mundo virtual?	Completamente real--nada real
12	REAL	¿Hasta qué punto la experiencia en el mundo virtual te ha parecido comparable a la experiencia en el mundo real?	Nada comparable- moderadamente-muy comparable
13	REAL	¿Hasta qué punto te ha parecido real el mundo virtual?	Tan real como un mundo imaginado--indistinguible del mundo real
14	REAL	El mundo virtual parecía más realista que el mundo real.	totalmente en desacuerdo-- totalmente de acuerdo

ANNEX 45. DEMOGRAPHIC QUESTIONNAIRE: PROFESSIONALS

(Where relevant) **0. This is the second ImAc (subtitle/AD) editor test. Did you take part in the first ImAc subtitle editor test?**

- a) Yes
- b) No

1. Sex

- a) Female
- b) Male
- c) Other
- d) I prefer not to reply

2. Age:

3. Main language:

4. Please, describe your current job

5. Have you ever subtitled/audio described/ sign language interpreted a 360° video? Yes / No

6. For how long have you been working in the field of subtitling/AD/SL?

7. How many hours of subtitling/AD/SL have you produced in your professional life?

- a) Less than 50 hours
- b) 51-150 hours
- c) 151-300 hours
- d) More than 300 hours

8. In what language or languages do you normally subtitle/AD/SL?

9. What software do you normally use?

10. Please indicate your level of studies.

- a) Primary education
- b) Secondary education
- c) Further education. Please specify _____
- d) University. Please specify _____

11. If you replied "Further education" or "University" in the previous question, please specify.

12. If you have received specific training on subtitling, please indicate it here.

13. What devices do you use on a daily basis? Multiple replies are possible.

- a) TV
- b) PC
- c) Laptop
- d) Mobile phone
- e) Tablet
- f) HMD
- g) Other: _____

14. How often do you watch virtual reality content (for instance, 360° videos)?

	Never	Occasionally	At least once a month	At least once a week	Every day
In smartphone					
On a tablet					
On a PC					
In smartphone plugged to HMD					
In HMD					

15. If you have never used virtual reality content such as 360° videos or only occasionally, please indicate why. Multiple answers are possible.

- a) Because I am not interested.
- b) Because it is not accessible.
- c) Because I have not had the chance to use it.
- d) Other reasons. Please explain: _____

16. Please state your level of agreement with the following statement: "I am interested in virtual reality content (such as 360° videos)."

- a) I strongly agree
- b) I agree
- c) Neither agree nor disagree
- d) Disagree
- e) Strongly disagree

17. Do you own any device to access virtual reality content?

- a) Yes (If yes, which one? _____)
- b) No
- c) I don't know or I don't want to reply

18. If you replied "yes" to the previous question, please specify which device(s).

ANNEX 46. DEMOGRAPHIC QUESTIONNAIRE: HOME USERS

VERSION 1 (only addressed to persons with disabilities)

ENGLISH

Please reply to these general questions about yourself.

Participant code:

1. Sex:

- a) Female
- b) Male
- c) Other
- d) I prefer not to reply

2. Age: _____

3. Main language: _____

4. Please indicate your level of studies.

- a) No studies
- b) Primary education
- c) Secondary education
- d) Further education
- e) University

5. I define myself as....

For ST and SL tests

- a) Deaf person
- b) Hearing impaired person
- c) Deaf-blind person
- d) Other: _____.

For AD tests

- a) Blind person
- b) Partially-sighted person
- c) Other: _____.

6. Age in which your disability began:

- a) From birth
- b) 0-4
- c) 5-12
- d) 13-20
- e) 21-40
- f) 41-60
- g) more than 60

7. What devices do you use on a daily basis? Multiple replies are possible.

- a) TV
- b) PC
- c) Laptop
- d) Mobile phone
- e) Tablet
- f) Head Mounted Display
- g) Other: _____

8. How often do you watch virtual reality content (for instance, 360° videos)?

	Never	Occasionally	At least once a month	At least once a week	Every day
In smartphone					
On a tablet					
On a PC					
In smartphone plugged to HMD					
In HMD					

9. If you have never used virtual reality content such as 360° videos or only occasionally, please indicate why. Multiple answers are possible.

- a) Because I am not interested.
- b) Because it is not accessible.
- c) Because I have not had the chance to use it.
- d) Other:_____.

10. Please state your level of agreement with the following statement: "I am interested in virtual reality content (such as 360° videos)."

- a) I strongly agree
- b) I agree
- c) Neither agree nor disagree
- d) Disagree
- e) Strongly disagree

11. Do you own any device to access virtual reality content?

- a) Yes
- b) No
- c) I don't know or I don't want to reply

12. If you replied "yes" to the previous question, please specify which device(s).

13. Do you like watching the following types of content on television or online?

	I like it very much	I like it	Neither like it nor dislike it	I don't like it	I don't like it at all
News					
Fiction (series, films)					
Talk shows					
Documentaries					
Sports					
Cartoons					

14. When subtitling/sign language is available, do you activate it for the following type of content?

	Always	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
News				
Fiction (series, films)				
Talk shows				
Documentaries				
Sports				
Cartoons				

15. If subtitling/sign language interpretation is available and you do not activate it, please select the reasons why

- a) Because the interface is not accessible.
- b) Because I don't want subtitling/sign language interpretation in all the content, only in certain types of content.
- c) Other: _____.

16. How many hours a day do you watch subtitled/audio described/sign language interpreted content?

- a) None
- b) Less than 1 hour
- c) 1-2 hours
- d) 2-3 hours
- e) 3-4 hours
- f) 4 hours or more

17. What do you use subtitles/sign language interpretation for?

- a) They help me understand
- b) They are my only way to have access to the dialogue
- c) I use them for language learning
- d) Other: _____

18. What do you use to access online content? (only for AD tests)

- a) Magnifier (for example, ZoomText)
- b) Screen reader (for example, JAWS, VoiceOver, TalkBack)
- c) Both
- d) None

SPANISH

Por favor, responde a las siguientes preguntas sobre ti.

Código de participante:

1. Sexo:

- a) Mujer
- b) Hombre
- c) Otro
- d) Prefiero no contestar

2. Edad: _____

3. Lengua materna: _____

4. Por favor, indica tu nivel de estudios.

- a) Sin estudios
- b) Educación primaria
- c) Educación secundaria
- d) Formación profesional
- e) Universidad

5. Me define como una persona...

For ST and SL tests

- a) Sorda
- b) Con pérdida auditiva
- c) Sordociega
- d) Otros: _____.

For AD tests

- a) Ciega
- b) Con baja visión
- c) Otro: _____.

6. Edad en la que empezaste a perder la vista (AD tests) / Edad en la que empezó tu pérdida auditiva (ST and SL tests):

- a) De nacimiento
- b) De 0 a 4 años
- c) De 5 a 12 años
- d) De 13 a 20 años
- e) De 21 a 40 años
- f) De 41 a 60 años
- g) Después de los 60

7. ¿Qué aparatos utilizas todos los días? Puedes seleccionar más de una respuesta.

- a) TV
- b) Ordenador de sobremesa
- c) Ordenador portátil
- d) Teléfono móvil
- e) Tablet
- f) Gafas de realidad virtual
- g) Otro: _____

8. ¿Cuántas veces ves contenidos de realidad virtual (por ejemplo, vídeos de 360º)?

	Nunca	Ocasionalmente	Al menos una vez al mes	Al menos una vez a la semana	Todos los días
En el teléfono móvil					
En la tablet					
En el ordenador					
En el teléfono móvil conectado a unas gafas de realidad virtual					
En unas gafas de realidad virtual (por ejemplo, Vive, Oculus)					

9. Si nunca has visto contenido en realidad virtual como vídeos de 360º o solo lo has hecho en alguna ocasión, indica el motivo. Puedes escoger más de una respuesta.

- a) Porque no me interesa.
- b) Porque no es accesible.
- c) Porque no he tenido la oportunidad de hacerlo.
- d) Otro: _____.

10. Por favor, indica tu nivel de acuerdo con la siguiente afirmación: “Me interesa el contenido de realidad virtual (como vídeos de 360º)”.

- a) Muy de acuerdo
- b) De acuerdo
- c) Ni de acuerdo ni en desacuerdo
- d) En desacuerdo
- e) Muy en desacuerdo

11. ¿Tienes algún dispositivo para acceder contenido de realidad virtual (por ejemplo, Google Cardboard, Samsung VR, Oculus Rift, PlayStation VR, etc.)?

- a) Sí
- b) No
- c) No lo sé o no quiero contestar

12. Si has respondido “sí” en la pregunta anterior, especifica qué dispositivo(s): _____.

13. ¿Qué tipo de contenidos te gusta ver en televisión o en línea?

	Me gusta mucho	Me gusta	Ni me gusta ni me disgusta	No me gusta	No me gusta nada
Noticias					
Ficción (series, películas)					
Programas de debate					
Documentales					
Deportes					
Dibujos animados					

14. Si hay subtítulos/interpretación en lengua de signos disponibles, ¿los activas para los siguientes contenidos?

	Siempre	A veces	Pocas veces	Nunca
Noticias				
Ficción (series, películas)				
Programas de debate				
Documentales				
Deportes				
Dibujos animados				

15. Si los subtítulos/interpretación en lengua de signos están disponibles y no los activas, ¿por qué no? Selecciona los motivos.

- a) Porque la interfaz no es accesible.
- b) Porque no quiero subtítulos/interpretación en lengua de signos en todos los contenidos, solo en ciertos tipos de contenido.
- e) Otro: _____.

16. ¿Cuántas horas al día pasas viendo contenido subtulado/audiodescrito/interpretado en lengua de signos?

- a) Ninguna
- b) Menos de una hora
- c) Entre 1 y 2 horas
- d) Entre 2 y 3 horas
- e) Entre 3 y 4 horas
- f) 4 horas o más

17. ¿Para qué utilizas los subtítulos/interpretación en lengua de signos?

- a) Me ayudan a entender
- b) Son mi única manera de acceder a los diálogos
- c) Los uso para aprender idiomas
- d) Otros: _____

18. ¿Qué usas para acceder al contenido en línea? (only for AD tests)

- a) Magnificador (por ejemplo, ZoomText)
- b) Lector de pantalla (por ejemplo, JAWS, VoiceOver, TalkBack)
- c) Los dos
- d) Ninguno

CATALAN

Respongui a aquestes preguntes generals sobre vostè.

Codi de participant:

1. Sexe:

- a) Dona
- b) Home
- c) Un altre
- d) Prefereixo no respondre

2. Edat: _____

3. Llengua principal: _____

4. Indiqui el seu nivel d'estudis.

- a) Sense estudis
- b) Educació primària
- c) Educació secundària
- d) Educació superior
- e) Universitat

5. Em defineixo com una persona...

For ST and SL tests

- a) Sorda
- b) Amb pèrdua d'audició
- c) Sordcega
- d) Altres: _____.

For AD tests

- a) Cega
- b) Amb baixa visió
- c) Altres: _____.

6. Edat en què vas començar a perdre la visió: (AD test) / Edat d'inici de la discapacitat: (ST and SL tests):

- a) De naixement
- b) 0-4 anys
- c) 5-12 anys
- d) 13-20 anys
- e) 21-40 anys
- f) 41-60 anys
- g) Més de 60 anys

7. Quins dispositius utilitza diàriament? Pot seleccionar més d'una opció.

- a) TV
- b) Ordinador de taula
- c) Ordinador portàtil
- d) Telèfon mòbil
- e) Tauleta
- f) Ulleres de realitat virtual
- g) Un altre: _____

8. Amb quina freqüència veu contingut de realitat virtual (per exemple, vídeos de 360º)?

	Mai	De tan ten tant	Almenys una vegada al mes	Almenys una vegada a la semana	Cada dia
En el telèfon mòbil					
En una tauleta					
En un ordinador de taula					
En el telèfon mòbil connectat a un dispositiu d'ulleres de realitat virtual					
Amb unes ulleres de realitat virtual					

9. Si mai no ha vist contingut de realitat virtual, com ara vídeos de 360º o només ocasionalment, indiqui per què. Pot seleccionar més d'una opció.

- a) Perquè no m'interessa.
- b) Perquè no és accessible.
- c) Perquè no he tingut l'oportunitat d'usarlo.
- d) Altres:_____.

10. Indiqui el seu nivell d'acord amb la següent declaració: "Tinc interès en contingut de realitat virtual (com ara vídeos de 360º)".

- a) Totalment d'acord
- b) D'acord
- c) Ni d'acord ni en desacord
- d) En desacord
- e) Totalment en desacord

11. Disposa d'algun dispositiu per accedir a contingut de realitat virtual?

- a) Sí
- b) No
- c) No sé o no vull respondre

12. Si ha respost "sí" a la pregunta anterior, especifiqui quin(s) dispositiu(s): _____.

13. Li agrada veure els següents tipus de contingut a la televisió o en línia?

	M'agrada molt	M'agrada	Ni m'agrada ni em desagrada	No m'agrada	No m'agrada gens
Notícies					
Ficció (sèries, pel·lícules)					
Programes de debat					
Documentals					
Esports					
Dibuixos animats					

14. Quan hi ha subtítols/interpretació en llengua de signes disponibles, els activa per al següent tipus de contingut?

	Sempre	De vegades	Rarament	Mai
Notícies				
Ficció (sèries, pel·lícules)				
Programes de debat				
Documentals				
Esports				
Dibuixos animats				

15. Si els subtítols/interpretació en llengua de signes estan disponibles i no els activa, seleccioni per quin motiu

- a) Perquè la interfície no és accessible.
- b) Perquè només vull subtítols/interpretació en llengua de signes en determinats tipus de contingut.
- c) Otro: _____.

16. Quantes hores al dia veu contingut subtitulat, audiodescrit, interpretat en llengua de signes?

- a) Cap
- b) Menys d'un hora
- c) 1-2 hores
- d) 2-3 hores
- e) 3-4 hores
- f) 4 hores o més

17. Per què utilitza els subtítols/interpretación en llengua de signes?

- a) M'ajuden a entendre
- b) Són la meua única manera de tenir accés al diàleg
- c) En faig ús per a l'aprenentatge d'idiomesç
- d) Otros: _____

18. Què fa servir per accedir als continguts en línia? (only for AD tests)

- a) Magnificador (per exemple, ZoomText)
- b) Lector de pantalla (per exemple, JAWS, VoiceOver, TalkBack)
- c) Tots dos
- d) Cap

GERMAN

Bitte beantworten Sie folgende Fragen zu Ihrer Person.

Teilnehmer Code:

1. Geschlecht:

- a) Weiblich
- b) Männlich
- c) Sonstiges
- d) Ich möchte nicht darauf antworten.

2. Alter: _____

3. Was ist Ihre Muttersprache? _____

4. Bitte geben Sie Ihren Bildungsgrad an.

- a) Keiner
- b) Grundschulbildung
- c) Weiterführende Schule
- d) Weiterbildung
- e) Universität

5. Ich sehe mich als...

- a) Gehörlose Person
- b) Schwerhörige Person
- c) Blinde und Gehörlose Person
- d) Other: _____.

6. Beginn des Hörverlustes:

- a) Von Geburt an
- b) im Alter von 0-4 Jahren
- c) im Alter von 5-12 Jahren
- d) im Alter von 13-20 Jahren
- e) im Alter von 21-40 Jahren
- f) im Alter von 41-60 Jahren
- g) im Alter von über 60 Jahren

7. Welche Geräte nutzen Sie täglich? Es kann mehr als eine ausgewählt werden.

- a) TV
- b) PC
- c) Laptop, Notebook
- d) Smartphone
- e) Tablet
- f) VR-Brille
- g) Other: _____

8. Wie oft schauen Sie Virtual Reality (VR) Inhalte (wie zum Beispiel, 360° Videos)?

	Niemals	Gelegentlich	Midestens einmal im Monat	Midestens einmal pro Woche	Jeden Tag
Mit dem Smartphone					
Auf einem Tablet					
Auf einem PC					
Mit dem Smartphone und einer VR-Brille					
Mit einer VR- Briller					

9. Falls Sie noch nie oder nur gelegentlich VR Inhalte angeschaut haben, sagen Sie bitte warum? Es kann mehr als eine ausgewählt werden.

- a) Weil ich nicht interessiert bin.
- b) Weil es nicht barrierefrei zugänglich ist.
- c) Weil ich noch keine Gelegenheit hatte, es zu benutzen.
- d) Other: _____.

10. Stimmen Sie folgender Aussage zu? "Ich interessiere mich für Virtual-Reality-Inhalte (z.B. 360°-Videos)."

- a) Ich stimme dem ausdrücklich zu
- b) Ich stimme zu
- c) Ich stimme weder zu noch widerspreche ich
- d) Ich bin nicht einverstanden
- e) Ich bin absolut nicht einverstanden

11. Haben Sie ein Gerät zu Hause mit dem Sie VR Inhalte anschauen können?

- a) Ja
- b) Nein
- c) Ich weiß nicht oder möchte nicht antworten

12. Fall Sie mit Ja geantwortet haben, sagen Sie bitte welches Gerät.

13. Schauen Sie folgende Inhalte auf dem Fernsehen oder Online?

	Ich mag es sehr	Ich mag es	Weder noch	Ich mag es nicht	Ich mag es überhaupt nicht
Nachrichten					
Serien, Filme					
Talk shows					
Dokumentarfilme					
Sport					
Zeichentrick					

14. Für welche Inhalte nutzen Sie Untertitel, wenn Sie verfügbar sind?

	Immer	Manchmal	Selten	Nie
Nachrichten				
Serien, Filme				
Talk shows				
Dokumentarfilme				
Sport				
Zeichentrick				

15. Warum nutzen Sie keine Untertitel, wenn Sie verfügbar sind. Nennen Sie uns Gründe dafür.

- a) Weil das Menü nicht barrierefrei ist.
- b) Weil ich Untertitel nicht in alle Inhalten möchte sondern nur in ausgewählten.
- c) Other: _____.

16. Wie viele Stunden am Tag schauen Sie Untertitelte Inhalte?

- a) Keine
- b) Weniger als eine Stunde
- c) 1-2 Stunden
- d) 2-3 Stunden
- e) 3-4 Stunden
- f) 4 Stunden oder mehr

17. Wofür benutzen Sie Untertitel?

- a) Sie helfen mit den Inhalt zu verstehen.
- b) Nur so kann ich dem Dialog folgen.
- c) Ich nutze Sie um eine andere Sprache zu lernen.
- d) Other: _____

VERSION 2 (addressed to persons with hearing loss and hearing people; only used for a test conducted in Spain, so only English and Spanish version are available)

Demographic questionnaire - ENG

Some questions about yourself

Please reply to these general questions about yourself.

Participant code:

1. Sex

- a) Female
- b) Male
- c) Other
- d) I prefer not to reply

2. Age: _____

3. Main language: _____

4. Please indicate your level of studies.

- a) No studies
- b) Primary education
- c) Secondary education
- d) Further education
- e) University

5. I define myself as....

- a) Person with hearing loss
- b) Hearing person
- c) Other: _____.

6. Age in which your disability began (if applicable):

- a) From birth
- b) 0-4
- c) 5-12
- d) 13-20
- e) 21-40
- f) 41-60
- g) more than 60
- h) Not applicable

7. What devices do you use on a daily basis? Multiple replies are possible.

- a) TV
- b) PC
- c) Laptop
- d) Mobile phone
- e) Tablet
- f) Head Mounted Display
- g) Game console
- h) Other: _____

8. How often do you watch virtual reality content (for instance, 360° videos)?

	Never	Occasionally	At least once a month	At least once a week	Every day
In smartphone					
On a tablet					
On a PC					
In smartphone plugged to HMD					
In HMD					

9. If you have never used virtual reality content such as 360° videos or only occasionally, please indicate why. Multiple answers are possible.

- a) Because I am not interested.
- b) Because it is not accessible.
- c) Because I have not had the chance to use it.
- d) Other:_____.

10. Please state your level of agreement with the following statement: "I am interested in virtual reality content (such as 360° videos)."

- a) I strongly agree
- b) I agree
- c) Neither agree nor disagree
- d) Disagree
- e) Strongly disagree

11. Do you own any device to access virtual reality content?

- a) Yes
- b) No
- c) I don't know or I don't want to reply

12. If you replied "yes" to the previous question, please specify which device(s).

13. Do you like watching the following types of content on television or online?

	I like it very much	I like it	Neither like it nor dislike it	I don't like it	I don't like it at all
News					
Fiction (series, films)					
Talk shows					
Documentaries					
Sports					
Cartoons					

14. When subtitling is available, do you activate it for the following type of content?

	Always	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
News				
Fiction (series, films)				
Talk shows				
Documentaries				
Sports				
Cartoons				

15. If it is available and you do not activate it, please select the reasons why

- a) Because the interface is not accessible.
- b) Because I don't want subtitling in all the content, only in certain types of content.
- c) Other:_____.

16. How many hours a day do you watch subtitled content?

- a) None
- b) Less than 1 hour
- c) 1-2 hours
- d) 2-3 hours
- e) 3-4 hours
- f) 4 hours or more

17. What do you use subtitles for?

- a) They help me understand
- b) They are my only way to have access to the dialogue
- c) I use them for language learning
- d) Other: _____

SPANISH

Algunas preguntas sobre ti

Por favor, responde a las siguientes preguntas sobre ti.

Código de participante:

1. Sexo:

- a) Mujer
- b) Hombre
- c) Otro
- d) Prefiero no contestar

2. Edad: _____

3. Lengua materna: _____

4. Por favor, indica tu nivel de estudios.

- a) Sin estudios
- b) Educación primaria
- c) Educacion secundaria
- d) Formación profesional
- e) Universidad

5. Me defino como...

- a) Persona con pérdida auditiva
- b) Persona oyente
- c) Otro: _____

6. Edad en la que empezó tu pérdida auditiva (si procede):

- a) De nacimiento
- b) De 0 a 4 años
- c) De 5 a 12 años
- d) De 13 a 20 años
- e) De 21 a 40 años
- f) De 41 a 60 años
- g) Después de los 60
- h) No procede

7. ¿Qué dispositivos utilizas a diario? Puedes seleccionar más de una respuesta.

- a) Televisión
- b) Ordenador de sobremesa
- c) Ordenador portátil
- d) Teléfono móvil
- e) Tablet
- f) Gafas de realidad virtual (tipo Oculus Rift/PlayStation VR o Google Cardboard/Samsung VR)
- g) Videoconsola
- h) Otros: _____

8. ¿Cada cuánto ves contenidos de realidad virtual (por ejemplo, vídeos de 360º)?

	Nunca	Ocasionalmente	Al menos una vez al mes	Al menos una vez a la semana	Todos los días
En el teléfono móvil					
En la tablet					
En el ordenador					
En el teléfono móvil conectado a unas gafas de realidad virtual (tipo Google Cardboard o Samsung VR)					
En unas gafas de realidad virtual (tipo Oculus Rift o PlayStation VR)					

9. Si nunca has visto contenido en realidad virtual como vídeos de 360º o solo lo has hecho en alguna ocasión, indica el motivo. Puedes escoger más de una respuesta.

- e) Porque no me interesa.
- f) Porque no es accesible.
- g) Porque no he tenido la oportunidad de hacerlo.
- h) Otro: _____.

10. Por favor, indica tu nivel de acuerdo con la siguiente afirmación: “Me interesa el contenido de realidad virtual (como vídeos de 360º)”.

- f) Muy de acuerdo
- g) De acuerdo
- h) Ni de acuerdo ni en desacuerdo
- i) En desacuerdo
- j) Muy en desacuerdo

11. ¿Tienes algún dispositivo para acceder contenido de realidad virtual (por ejemplo, Google Cardboard, Samsung VR, Oculus Rift, PlayStation VR, etc.)?

- a) Sí
- b) No
- c) No lo sé o no quiero contestar

12. Si has respondido “sí” en la pregunta anterior, especifica qué dispositivo(s): _____.

13. ¿Qué tipo de contenidos te gusta ver en televisión o en línea?

	Me gusta mucho	Me gusta	Ni me gusta ni me disgusta	No me gusta	No me gusta nada
Noticias					
Ficción (series, películas)					
Programas de debate					
Documentales					
Deportes					
Dibujos animados					

14. Si hay subtítulos disponibles, ¿los activas para los siguientes contenidos?

	Siempre	A veces	Pocas veces	Nunca
Noticias				
Ficción (series, películas)				
Programas de debate				
Documentales				
Deportes				
Dibujos animados				

15. Si los subtítulos están disponibles y no los activas, ¿por qué no? Selecciona los motivos.

- a) Porque la interfaz no es accesible.
- b) Porque no quiero subtítulos en todos los contenidos, solo en ciertos tipos de contenido.
- c) Porque no los necesito.
- d) Los activo siempre.
- e) Otro: _____.

16. ¿Cuántas horas al día pasas viendo contenido subtulado?

- a) Ninguna
- b) Menos de una hora
- c) Entre 1 y 2 horas
- d) Entre 2 y 3 horas
- e) Entre 3 y 4 horas
- f) 4 horas o más

17. ¿Para qué utilizas los subtítulos?

- a) Me ayudan a entender
- b) Son mi única manera de acceder a los diálogos
- c) Los uso para aprender idiomas
- d) No los uso nunca
- d) Otros: _____

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